

An Application of Analytic Network Process (ANP) to Assess Critical Risks of Bridge Projects in the Mekong Delta Region

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ABSTRACT

Risk management is one of the critical factors contributing to infrastructure project success. Risk assessment enables both practitioners and decision-makers to identify and analyze potential risks and quantify risk impacts on project performance in terms of time, cost, and quality. Even though many studies attempt to investigate the risk of construction projects with the consideration of technical, organizational, and legal aspects, only a few studies deeply focus on identifying the critical risks of bridge projects with the examination of climate change impact. The current study concentrates on analyzing risks in bridge construction projects in the Mekong Delta region which has been significantly affected by climate change. An intensive review of previous publications and technical project reports from 2010 to 2021 was conducted to identify the list of potential risks and interviews and discussions with engineers and managers involved in bridge projects were carried out to identify critical risks of bridge projects. Analytic Network Process (ANP) method was introduced to evaluate the impact of such risks on the performance of bridge project implementation. The initial results of this study provide a holistic picture of risk management for bridge projects with the consideration of climate change impact. The findings can help the involved parties including owners, contractors, and project managers to assess particular risks and scheme backup plans to mitigate project delays and cost overruns.

Keywords-risk assessment; risk management; bridge projects; Mekong Delta

I. INTRODUCTION

Risk is defined as a positive or negative deviation of a variable from its expected value and is commonly understood as a loss [1]. Due to potential risks, bridge construction projects often fail to achieve their time, quality, budget and operation goals [2]. Risk management plays a vital role in minimizing the negative consequences of unexpected events on the bridge project performance. However, risk management for bridge construction projects is a challenging process with the involvement of uncertainty factors from policy, society, economy, environment, finance, and technology [3]. Even though many studies have attempted to investigate the separate risks of bridge construction projects, only a few studies provide a holistic picture of risk management regarding bridge construction projects. Particularly very few scholars focus on

assessing the potential risks of bridge projects in the context of developing countries. Thus, a case study in Vietnam with the consideration of bridge projects in the Mekong Delta region is carefully examined in this paper. The selected case study, the Mekong Delta region, encompasses a large portion of southwestern Vietnam, with an area over 40,500km², which has a large number of ongoing bridge projects [4]. Bridge construction projects in this area play a vital role in connecting the Southern areas of Vietnam, and improving the agricultural trading capacity which directly contributes to the local economic growth [5]. Risk management for bridge projects in the Mekong Delta is considered monumental in ensuring the success of strategic connection goals of local governments. In practice, conventional studies on risk assessment in technical and organizational terms have been carried out, but there is a

lack of studies concentrating on potential risks caused by climate change. Therefore, in this paper, we aim to provide a holistic picture of risk management by considering potential risks caused by climate change. The Analytic Network Process (ANP) is a promising approach [6] that was selected to identify critical risk factors and assess the impacts of risk on project objectives including time, cost, quality, and operation.

II. RISK IDENTIFICATION

A. Literature Review

In this study, a mini scoping technique was applied for searching articles. The SCOPUS database was selected for searching with the use of the combination of keywords: Construction Projects AND Bridge projects AND Risk management OR Risk identification OR Risk assessment within a specific period from 2000 to 2020. The initial search resulted in 192 articles related to construction project risk management. Next, we focused on the risks of bridge projects to eliminate some articles and a shortlist of 52 articles was produced. Further, our research team carefully read the titles and abstracts and skimmed the whole content of the studies and finally, 28 of 52 publications were selected for analysis.

B. Documentation Review

The Mekong Delta region in Vietnam is one of the affected places by climate change [1]. The implementation of bridge projects in this region suffers from many difficulties and potentially contains significant risks in comparison with bridge construction conditions in other regions in Vietnam. In this study, we carefully examined the documentation of real bridge projects in the Mekong Delta region during the period from 2000 to 2020. As a result, 30 typical projects were selected to clarify practical risks which were used to compare to risks identified from the literature.

C. Risk Identification Results

Through the survey of literature review along with the project documentation review, a list of critical risk factors was identified and is presented in Table I. These risk factors were classified into the following groups: Political and legal risks, Social risks, Technical risks, Economic risks, Environmental risks, and Financial and Commercial risks.

III. APPLICATION OF ANALYTIC NETWORK PROCESS (ANP) TO ASSESS CRITICAL RISKS

A. Analytic Network Process Model

ANP is widely used for multi-criteria-decision-making [52]. ANP is a multi-criteria theory of measurement used to derive relative priority scales of absolute numbers from individual judgments that also belong to the fundamental scale of absolute numbers [53]. The judgments in the ANP model show the relative impact of one of two elements over the other in a pairwise comparison process on a third element in the system [53]. In ANP, pairwise comparisons of the elements in each level are conducted with respect to their relative importance towards their control criterion.

TABLE I. RISK FACTORS IN BRIDGE CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS IN THE MEKONG DELTA REGION

No	Code	Risks	References
I	PL	Political and legal risks	
	PL1	Changes in the state organization	[2-11]
	PL2	Political interference	[2-5, 12, 13]
	PL3	Legal procedures are complicated and unclear	[3, 9, 14-18]
	PL4	Changes in legal documents and regulations	[3, 8, 9, 16-18]
	PL5	Corruption of officials	[3, 17, 19, 20]
II	SO	Social risks	
	SO1	Difficulty in ground clearance	[6, 9, 15, 21-25]
	SO2	Compensation cost	[23-25]
	SO3	Opposition of the community	[6, 9, 15, 21, 22]
	SO4	Disputes in projects	[26-29]
	SO5	Security at the construction site	[26, 28, 29]
	SO6	Local resident consensus	[19, 30-33]
III	TE	Technical risks	
	TE1	Lack of management method	[29, 23]
	TE2	Errors in defining project scope	[4, 7, 14, 29, 35]
	TE3	Incomplete and inaccurate survey and experimental data	[4, 16, 36, 37]
	TE4	Inappropriate project approaches	[9, 10, 21, 37-39]
	TE5	Errors in design appraisal and estimation	[13, 40]
	TE6	Non-compliance with construction standards	[4, 7, 14, 29, 41]
	TE7	Changing design and technical plans	[4, 17, 18]
	TE8	Supply delays	[10, 37-39]
	TE9	Unsuitable construction organization	[8, 14, 21, 37]
	TE10	Machinery breakdown	[8, 14, 17, 22, 36, 39]
	TE11	Capacity of contractors, supervision consultants	[8, 10, 15, 37, 38, 42, 43]
IV	EC	Economic risks	
	EC1	Inflation	[3, 36]
	EC2	Interest rates change	[3, 4, 43, 44]
	EC3	Economic policy	[3, 4, 9, 10, 37, 44]
	EC4	Currency exchange rate changes	[3, 6, 22, 36]
	EC5	Economic depression	[3, 4, 9, 10, 37, 43, 44]
	EC6	Fuel/material prices change	[13, 45]
	EC7	Macroeconomics	[3, 4, 9, 10, 37, 43, 44]
	EC8	The market changes	[21, 39, 46]
V	EN	Environment risks	
	EN1	Unstable geology	[6, 9, 15, 21, 22, 47-49]
	EN2	Sea level rise	[10, 14, 21, 43, 50]
	EN3	Erosion	[10, 14, 21, 50]
	EN4	Changes in rainy season, rainfall	[2, 7, 10, 14, 21, 43, 50]
	EN5	Temperature change	[2, 7, 10, 14, 21, 43, 50]
	EN6	Saltwater intrusion	
	EN7	Storms	[6, 8, 50]
	EN8	Floods	[6, 8, 50]
VI	FC	Financial and Commercial risks	
	FC1	Project funding	[6, 22, 51]
	FC2	The ability to attract finance for the project	[6, 22, 51]
	FC3	Financial capacity of the contractor	[8, 14, 22]
	FC4	Weak financial management	[4, 16, 21, 46]
	FC5	Disrupted commercial activities	[14, 20, 24, 25, 30]
	FC6	Compensation for accidents	[2, 22]
	FC7	Weak contract management	[10, 14, 15, 21, 22]
	FC8	Weak cost management	[5, 18, 21, 50]
	FC9	Exceeded estimated cost	[5, 17, 18, 21, 20]

Once the pairwise comparisons are completed for the whole network, the vectors corresponding to the maximum eigenvalues of the constructed matrices are computed and a priority vector is obtained. The outcome of the comparison process is used in the development of the unweighted matrix, weighted matrix, and limit matrix. The super matrices' outcome of ANP is used to assess the priority of risk groups as in Figure 1. The goal of the ANP model in this study is to assess the priority of risks with the consideration of successful criteria of a bridge project. In the literature, there are common perspectives on success criteria for a construction project, as is clearly shown in Table II.

Fig. 1. The ANP model assesses the priority of risks.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF SUCCESS CRITERIA

No	Success criteria	Reference
1	Cost, Time, Performance, Satisfaction, Operation, Effectiveness	[54]
2	Cost, Time, Technical Requirements, Customer Satisfaction, Operation	[55]
3	Time Performance, Cost Performance, Quality Performance, Health, Safety and Environment (HSE), Client satisfaction	[56]
4	Cost, Time, Meeting the technical specifications, Customer satisfaction, Stakeholder satisfaction, Operation	[57]
5	Cost, Time, Quality, Scope, Customer satisfaction, Safety, Team satisfaction, Shareholder satisfaction	[58]

Conventionally, successful criteria for a construction project often include time, cost, and quality. However, the efficiency of operating bridge projects is a major concern. Thus, we decided to select 4 main successful criteria, i.e. quality, cost, time, and operation to assess the priority of risks to ensure comprehensive risk assessment. In addition, the alternatives in the ANP model are 6 main risk groups (Figure 1) consisting of Political and Legal risks (PL), Social risks (SO), Technical risks (TE), Economic risks (EC), Environmental risks (EN), and Financial and Commercial risks (FC).

B. Questionnaire Survey

The identification of risk factors obtained in the literature review and documentation review (Table I) was used to design

a questionnaire survey. The survey was then carried out to collect data from project stakeholders including project owners, project managers, contractors, sub-contractors and consultants who have been involved in the bridge construction projects in the Mekong Delta region. The respondents were asked to rate the impact level of critical risks on project cost, time, quality, and operation on the scale shown in Table III.

TABLE III. SCORE OF IMPORTANCE

Score	Importance	Score	Importance	Score	Importance
1	Extremely low importance	4	Moderately low importance	7	High importance
2	Very low importance	5	Moderate importance	8	Very high importance
3	Low importance	6	Moderately high importance	9	Extremely high importance

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Questionnaire Participants

A total of 170 survey questionnaires were sent to experts in the bridge construction field. Face-to-face and online modes were used to survey. We received 88 full responses, accounting for around 53% of the total number of target participants. Most respondents have more than 5-year experience, and particularly more than 32% of respondents have more than 10-year experience in the construction industry domain.

Fig. 2. Stakeholder percentages

Fig. 3. Expert experience percentages.

B. Impact Risk Level Rating by MSI (Mean Score of Importance) Results

Six main groups and 47 associated risk factors were assessed by experts through the questionnaire survey. The experts participating in the survey were asked to rate the importance of the risk prioritization with the consideration of four main project objectives: Quality cost, time, and operation. The final results are shown in Tables IV-XI.

TABLE IV. IMPORTANCE OF THE CRITERIA THROUGH MSI

Criteria	Min score	Max score	Average score	Ranking
Importance of quality	7	9	8.44	1
Importance of cost	6	9	7.64	3
Importance of time	6	9	7.57	4
Importance of operation	7	9	8.07	2

TABLE V. IMPORTANCE OF RISK GROUPS

Risk groups	Importance				Average score	Ranking
	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation		
PL	4.78	5.94	6.78	6.38	5.97	5
SO	4.17	5.50	6.50	6.22	5.59	6
TE	7.28	6.83	7.16	7.11	7.09	1
EC	5.84	6.78	6.17	6.61	6.35	3
EN	6.00	6.33	6.22	7.22	6.44	2
FC	5.72	6.83	6.17	6.11	6.20	4

TABLE VI. IMPORTANCE OF RISK FACTORS IN POLITICAL AND LEGAL GROUPS

Risk Factors	The importance for				Average score	Ranking
	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation		
PL1	5.11	5.44	5.33	4.72	5.15	5
PL2	5.28	5.72	5.33	5.44	5.44	4
PL3	5.78	7.17	7.00	6.33	6.57	1
PL4	6.06	6.94	6.78	6.27	6.51	2
PL5	6.11	6.78	5.94	5.77	6.15	3

TABLE VII. IMPORTANCE OF RISK FACTORS IN SOCIAL GROUP

Risk Factors	The importance for				Average score	Ranking
	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation		
SO1	6.00	7.89	7.83	6.77	7.12	1
SO2	5.67	7.50	7.39	6.77	6.83	2
SO3	5.39	6.28	6.83	6.22	6.18	3
SO4	4.94	5.89	6.94	6.05	5.96	5
SO5	4.83	5.56	5.78	5.83	5.50	6
SO6	4.94	6.83	6.39	6.50	6.17	4

TABLE VIII. IMPORTANCE OF RISK FACTORS IN TECHNICAL GROUP

Risk Factors	The importance for				Average score	Ranking
	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation		
TE1	5.67	6.22	6.00	7.00	6.22	8
TE2	7.39	6.50	6.67	7.11	6.92	5
TE3	6.89	6.33	6.33	7.05	6.65	7
TE4	7.56	6.39	6.72	7.27	6.99	4
TE5	7.78	6.56	6.56	7.27	7.04	3
TE6	6.83	6.28	6.89	6.72	6.68	6
TE7	6.00	6.11	6.28	5.77	6.04	9
TE8	7.22	6.39	6.50	6.50	6.65	7
TE9	6.39	5.67	5.72	5.94	5.93	10
TE10	7.50	7.44	7.33	7.00	7.32	1
TE11	7.17	7.17	7.11	6.94	7.10	2

TABLE IX. IMPORTANCE OF RISK FACTORS IN ECONOMIC GROUP

Risk Factors	The importance for				Average score	Ranking
	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation		
EC1	5.11	6.39	5.89	5.66	5.76	2
EC2	4.89	6.11	5.89	5.61	5.63	4
EC3	4.89	5.83	6.11	5.66	5.62	5
EC4	4.83	5.56	5.44	5.50	5.33	8
EC5	5.06	6.11	5.61	5.50	5.57	6
EC6	6.11	7.22	6.89	5.72	6.49	1
EC7	5.00	6.22	5.83	5.83	5.72	3
EC8	4.78	6.11	5.56	5.72	5.54	7

TABLE X. IMPORTANCE OF RISK FACTORS IN ENVIRONMENTAL GROUP

Risk Factors	The importance for				Average score	Ranking
	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation		
EN1	6.94	6.72	6.17	6.27	6.53	1
EN2	4.94	6.11	5.33	4.94	5.33	2
EN3	4.94	6.17	5.44	4.77	5.33	2
EN4	5.22	5.67	5.44	4.77	5.28	3
EN5	4.83	5.06	4.83	4.61	4.83	7
EN6	4.89	5.33	4.94	4.61	4.94	5
EN7	5.00	5.00	4.83	4.72	4.89	6
EN8	5.17	5.22	5.39	4.72	5.13	4

TABLE XI. IMPORTANCE OF RISK FACTORS IN FINANCIAL AND COMMERCIAL GROUPS

Risk Factors	The importance for				Average score	Ranking
	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation		
FC1	5.83	7.28	7.00	6.22	6.58	1
FC2	5.28	6.78	6.39	5.61	6.02	7
FC3	6.22	7.33	7.00	5.66	6.55	2
FC4	6.00	6.78	6.61	5.77	6.29	4
FC5	5.22	5.28	5.67	5.33	5.38	9
FC6	5.22	5.78	5.56	5.22	5.45	8
FC7	6.17	6.78	6.22	6.05	6.31	3
FC8	6.00	6.44	6.06	6.00	6.13	5
FC9	5.61	6.50	6.28	5.83	6.06	6

The presented survey results helped us to assess the importance level of the risks on specific groups. However, this approach does not accurately reflect the interaction of risks within the whole project. In order to clarify the impact among criteria and risks, the ANP model was applied to overcome obstacles.

C. Analytic Network Process Rating of the Impact Level of Risks

The purpose of applying the ANP model is to evaluate the priority of the risk groups and risk factors through the calculation of the Risk Priority Index (RPI). This is a method of ranking all risks while taking into account their importance to all considered criteria. Based on the survey results of experts, the MSI has been determined. In addition, along with the opinions of experts in the group discussion, a pairwise comparison matrix for each model will be established which is scored by a pairwise table [53].

1) Criteria Priority

To assess risk priority considering the main criteria, a sub model was established and is depicted in Figure 4.

TABLE XII. PAIRWISE TABLE

Level of importance	Pairwise comparison score
1: Equally important	1:1
2: Equally important to moderate	2:1, 3:2, 4:3, 5:4, 6:5, 7:6, 8:7, 9:8
3: Moderately important	3:1, 4:2, 5:3, 6:4, 7:5, 8:6, 9:7
4: Moderately important to slightly more important	4:1, 5:2, 6:3, 7:4, 8:5, 9:6
5: Slightly more important	5:1, 6:2, 7:3, 8:4, 9:5
6: Slightly important to very important	6:1, 7:2, 8:3, 9:4
7: Very important	7:1, 8:2, 9:3
8: Very important to extremely important	8:1, 9:2
9: Extremely important	9:1

Fig. 4. Sub model for assessing the priority of criteria.

Through the use of Super Decision software, the unweighted super matrix, the weighted super matrix, and the limit matrix of bridge project criteria were calculated and are presented in Tables XIII-XV.

TABLE XIII. UNWEIGHTED SUPER MATRIX CONSIDERING THE FOUR MAIN CRITERIA

Cluster	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation	Priority
Value	0.400	0.00	0.259	0.310	0.167
	0.200	0.310	0.412	0.000	0.333
	0.000	0.195	0.327	0.493	0.333
	0.400	0.493	0.00	0.195	0.167

TABLE XIV. WEIGHTED SUPER MATRIX CONSIDERING THE FOUR MAIN CRITERIA

Cluster	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation	Priority
Value	0.400	0.00	0.259	0.310	0.167
	0.200	0.310	0.412	0.000	0.333
	0.000	0.195	0.327	0.493	0.333
	0.400	0.493	0.00	0.195	0.167

TABLE XV. LIMIT MATRIX CONSIDERING THE FOUR MAIN CRITERIA

Cluster	Quality	Cost	Time	Operation	Priority
Value	0.243	0.243	0.243	0.243	0.243
	0.236	0.236	0.236	0.236	0.236
	0.252	0.252	0.252	0.252	0.252
	0.267	0.267	0.267	0.267	0.267

The Normalized Priority Value (NPV), Total Priority Value (TPV), and Ideal Priority Value (IPV) of criteria were calculated and can be seen in Table XVI.

TABLE XVI. CRITERIA PRIORITY

Criteria	TPV	NPV	IPV	Ranking (R)
Quality	0.333	0.333	1.000	1
Cost	0.167	0.167	0.500	2
Time	0.167	0.167	0.500	2
Operation	0.333	0.333	1.000	1

2) Risk Group Priority

The 6 risk groups of bridge construction projects are Political and legal risks (PL); Social risks (SO); Technical risks (TE); Economic risks (EC); Environmental risks (EN); Financial and Commercial risks (FC). The model in Figure 1 could be used to assess the priority of the risk groups. Through the use of Super Decision software, the unweighted super matrix, the weighted super matrix, and the limit matrix of the bridge project criteria were calculated and are shown in Tables XVII-XIX.

TABLE XVII. UNWEIGHTED SUPER MATRIX FOR RISK GROUPS

	NODES	EC	EN	FC	PL	SO	TE	Cost	Operation	Quality	Time
Alternatives	EC	0.000	0.206	0.183	0.252	0.219	0.186	0.222	0.166	0.176	0.100
	EN	0.201	0.000	0.252	0.100	0.136	0.312	0.111	0.223	0.176	0.200
	FC	0.180	0.162	0.000	0.190	0.252	0.121	0.222	0.125	0.176	0.100
	PL	0.222	0.182	0.177	0.000	0.205	0.190	0.111	0.152	0.097	0.200
	SO	0.171	0.249	0.186	0.271	0.000	0.191	0.111	0.111	0.060	0.200
	TE	0.226	0.200	0.201	0.186	0.187	0.000	0.222	0.223	0.315	0.200
Criteria	Cost	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Operation	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Quality	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Time	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

TABLE XVIII. WEIGHTED SUPER MATRIX FOR RISK GROUPS

	NODES	EC	EN	FC	PL	SO	TE	Cost	Operation	Quality	Time
Alternatives	EC	0.000	0.103	0.092	0.126	0.110	0.093	0.222	0.166	0.176	0.100
	EN	0.100	0.000	0.126	0.050	0.068	0.156	0.111	0.223	0.176	0.200
	FC	0.090	0.081	0.000	0.095	0.126	0.061	0.222	0.125	0.176	0.100
	PL	0.111	0.091	0.089	0.000	0.103	0.095	0.111	0.152	0.097	0.200
	SO	0.086	0.125	0.093	0.136	0.000	0.095	0.111	0.111	0.060	0.200
	TE	0.113	0.100	0.101	0.093	0.094	0.000	0.222	0.223	0.315	0.200
Criteria	Cost	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Operation	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Quality	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Time	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

TABLE XIX. LIMIT MATRIX FOR RISK GROUPS

	NODES	EC	EN	FC	PL	SO	TE	Cost	Operation	Quality	Time
Alternatives	EC	0.113	0.113	0.113	0.113	0.113	0.113	0.113	0.113	0.113	0.113
	EN	0.116	0.116	0.116	0.116	0.116	0.116	0.116	0.116	0.116	0.116
	FC	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102
	PL	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102	0.102
	SO	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.100
	TE	0.134	0.134	0.134	0.134	0.134	0.134	0.134	0.134	0.134	0.134
Criteria	Cost	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083
	Operation	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083
	Quality	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083
	Time	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083	0.083

The NPV, TPV, and IPV of risk groups were calculated and are shown in Table XX.

TABLE XX. PRIORITY OF RISK GROUPS

Risk Group	TPV	NPV	IPV	R
EC	0.16942	0.16942	0.845723	3
EN	0.174148	0.174148	0.869325	2
FC	0.152897	0.152897	0.763242	4
PL	0.152674	0.152674	0.76213	4
SO	0.150537	0.150537	0.751463	5
TE	0.200325	0.200325	1	1

V. DISCUSSION

A. Criteria Priority

Through the ANP, this study ranked the risk priority with the consideration of the main assessment criteria of a bridge construction project. Quality and Operation are the most important criteria with a priority value of 0.333 for both. In addition, Cost and Time had equal importance with a score of 0.167.

B. Risk Group Priority

The Technical risk group is the most critical in a bridge construction project in the Mekong Delta region. This group has significant impacts on the Quality, Cost, Time and Operation of projects. The results are similar with the ones of [9, 36, 37]. The results revealed that technical risk is always the first risk priority for construction project management.

The Environmental risk group ranks second among risk groups. This result can be explained by the geographic features of the Mekong Delta region which was significantly influenced by climate change in recent years.

The third-ranking group is the Economic risk. This group consists of 8 risk factors, in which "Fuel/material prices change" is assessed as the most important factor. In fact, the main material prices for bridge construction projects have increased dramatically over the years. For instance, the steel price went up around 40% in one year and the cement price jumped up by approximately 90.000VND (3.94\$) per ton compared to the price in 2020. Consequently, bridge projects suffered cost overrun, which this is the main cause leading to project delays.

Finally, while Political and legal risks and Financial and Commercial risks are ranked equally, the Social risk is considered as having less impact on the bridge construction

projects in the Mekong Delta region. This shows that the Vietnam government has provided a sustainable political environment and mainly facilitated consistent policy for construction industry development.

The findings of this study are in accordance with the results of recent studies [59-61] and provide insight for policy makers in establishing risk mitigation strategies for large-scale bridge projects.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we identified 47 potential risk factors with the focus on bridge construction projects in the Mekong Delta region. Such risk factors have been categorized into 6 main groups for assessment, including Political and legal (PL), Social (SO), Technical (TE), Economic (EC), Environmental (EN), and Financial and Commercial (FC). By reviewing the importance of the risk-given groups with the consideration of 4 main criteria (quality, cost, time, and operation) along with practical surveys to collect expert opinions, the priority of risk groups had been determined.

The TE group was ranked at the highest level (IPV = 1) which potentially has the most significant impact on the performance of bridge construction projects. The EN group was ranked at the second-highest level (IPV = 0.8693), which reflects the risk consequences of the climate change on the bridge projects carried out in the Mekong Delta region. In addition, the EC group was also ranked in the top three, which indicates that economic risks have potential influences on the project's success.

The results of this study can enhance project managers to have a backup plan which can mitigate potential risks in the implementation of bridge construction projects in the Mekong delta region. Moreover, the results of this study can be considered as a blueprint for bridge project risk management in the context of developing countries

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Effects of Crossover Operators on Genetic Algorithms for the Extraction of Solar Cell Parameters from Noisy Data

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the accuracy of solar cell modeling parameters extracted from noisy data using Genetic Algorithms (GAs). Three crossover operators (XOs) were examined, namely the Uniform (UXO), Arithmetic (AXO), and Blend (BXO) operators. The data used were an experimental benchmark cell and a simulated curve where noise levels (p) from 0 to 10% were added. For each XO, the analysis was carried out by running GAs 100 times and varying p and population size (N_{pop}). Simulation results showed that UXO and AXO suffered from premature convergence and failed to provide parameters with good precision even with very high N_{pop} , although they provided good fitting. In all analyzed cases, BXO outperformed UXO and AXO and the results showed that it can compete with the most efficient methods. For the benchmark curve, BXO reproduced the best RMSE found in the literature (0.7730062 mA) while providing the exact values of the parameters and a very low RMSE (1E-13) for the clean curve ($p=0$). For noisy curves, the errors of the extracted parameters were smaller than 10% for p lower than or equal to 6%. For higher values of p , the errors were smaller than 30%.

Keywords-solar cells; parameter extraction; genetic algorithms; crossover operators

I. INTRODUCTION

The current-voltage (I - V) characteristic of a Solar Cell (SC) is often predicted by the Single Diode Model (SDM) [1]:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_s \left[e^{(V+R_s I) / nV_{th}} - 1 \right] - G_p (V + R_s I) \quad (1)$$

where $V_{th} = kT/q$ is the thermal voltage, T is the temperature, k is the Boltzmann constant, and q is the elementary charge. The photocurrent I_{ph} , the reverse saturation current I_s , the ideality factor n , the series resistance R_s , and the parallel conductance G_p are SDM parameters that are commonly supposed constants independent of temperature and voltage. The non-linear nature of this equation makes the extraction of SDM parameters from I - V characteristics a very hard task. Since the '60s, many methods have been proposed [1-12]. Despite their huge number, none is wholly satisfactory and there is a need and a challenge to propose new methods. The proposed methods are either analytical or numerical [12-13]. The analytical methods, mainly published before 2000, often operate in specified regions of I - V curves and require prior knowledge of some

defined points, such as the short-circuit current I_{sc} , the open-circuit voltage V_{oc} , the current I_m , and the voltage V_m at the maximum power point [13]. The numerical methods are based on deterministic or Metaheuristic Optimization Algorithms (MOAs) that process over the whole curve and do not require any specified points. Deterministic algorithms are based on initial conditions, require curve derivatives, and do not guarantee a global solution. These drawbacks were overcome by MOAs [14], where evolutionary algorithms (EAs) constitute an important subclass. Hence, they are increasingly used in SC parameter estimation [1, 4]. Despite the huge number of proposed methods, only a few deal with the effects of noise levels on the extracted parameters [9-13, 15, 16]. This is an important issue, since noise is always present in the measured data and may vary with environmental conditions. Only [12] and [13], by proposing a least squares-based method and four metaheuristic-based methods, namely, the Self-Adaptive Differential Evolution algorithm (SADE), the Performance Guided JAYA algorithm (PGJAYA), the Self-Adaptive Teaching-Learning-based Optimization algorithm (SATLBO), and the Biogeography-based Heterogeneous Cuckoo Search

algorithm (BHCS), respectively, evaluated in-depth the effect of noise on the extracted parameters. These studies investigated the effect of noise levels from 0 to 10% on each method and parameter. In addition, in [13], the performance of the methods was analyzed by varying the population size.

This study investigated the effects of noise on the extracted parameters of SCs using GAs, compared 3 distinct crossover operators (XOs), and showed that the performance depends on the chosen XO. Experimental and synthetic noisy and noise-free curves were used. The study of the effects of XO on GAs applied to the extraction of SDM from noisy curves has not been considered before.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The SC parameter estimation problem is formulated as finding a vector $P=(I_{ph}, I_s, n, R_s, G_p)$ such that N synthetic data $(I_{s,i}, V_i)$, generated with the SDM (1), fit the experimental ones $(I_{e,i}, V_i)$. The problem is solved by minimizing an Objective Function (OF) that calculates the error between the experimental and synthetic data. This study used the Root Mean Square Estimation (RMSE) defined by (2) as OF, which is the most used in fitting problems [1-12]:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [I_{e,i} - I_{s,i}]^2} \tag{2}$$

III. GENETIC ALGORITHM TUNING

Since their introduction in [17], GAs have been increasingly studied, developed, and used in solving complex problems in science and engineering [18-19], machine learning [20], economics and finance [21], VLSI design [22], embedded system design [23], and others [24-25]. GAs are metaheuristic methods that mimic Darwin’s natural selection principles and genetics, that is, survival of the fittest [14, 26], and use selection, mutation, and crossover genetic-like operators. When using GAs, decisions have to be made on the stopping condition, the alphabet used, the population size, the genetic operators, and the corresponding probabilities to use. The program was set to stop when either it reached 20000 generations or all solutions in the population were in a prescribed standard deviation of 10^{-12} . Real coding (RCGA) was used to provide good resolution, where each chromosome was a P vector with the SDM parameters. The selection and mutation operators were set to the 'roulette wheel' and 'Gaussian', respectively, and the probabilities were fixed to $p_{cross}=0.9$ and $p_{mut}=0.01$ for the crossover and the mutation operators, respectively. The population size was taken as a variable in the range of [20, 20000]. Since GAs are considered to get their power from the XO [27-28], three widely used XOs were compared: the uniform, the arithmetic, and the blend operators [29-31].

A. Uniform Operator

The Uniform crossover operator (UXO) is inherited from binary coding and was historically the first one to be used [26]. When two chromosomes are crossed, each gene of the offspring randomly comes from the first or the second parent. When used with RCGA, UXO does not create new values of

genes other than those initially created. Only mutation can do this.

B. Arithmetic Operator

Given two parents x and y with genes x_i and y_i , respectively, and α_i in $[0, 1]$, the Arithmetic crossover operator (AXO) creates two offsprings z and w whose genes z_i and w_i are:

$$\begin{aligned} z_i &= \alpha_i x_i + (1 - \alpha_i) y_i \\ w_i &= \alpha_i y_i + (1 - \alpha_i) x_i \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where α_i are either uniform random numbers or constants in uniform and non-uniform AXO, respectively. AXO reduces the range of gene values in the population.

C. Blend Operator

Given $d_i=abs(x_i-y_i)$ and a fixed α , usually 0.5, the Blend crossover operator (BXO) creates an offspring U whose genes are uniform random numbers in the interval U_i given by [32]:

$$U_i = [min(x_i, y_i) - \alpha d_i, max(x_i, y_i) + \alpha d_i] \tag{4}$$

BXO enlarges the range of gene values in the population.

IV. COMPUTATIONAL PROCEDURE

The GAs were coded in C++ using the GALib library [33], and applied to the experimental and the synthetic versions of the most used benchmark $I-V$ curve [34]: a 57mm diameter crystalline silicon SC from RTC France, operating at 33°C and 1000W/m². The synthetic version was simulated with (1) in the voltage range of [0-0.6V] using the parameters of [13], shown in Table I, along with the restricted search intervals. Since the exact values are known, the convergence can be easily analyzed. To study the effect of noise on the extracted parameters, an artificial noise was added to the synthetic curve [9, 12-13, 15, 35]:

$$I_{noisy} = I_{syn} \times (1 + p \times rand) \tag{5}$$

where I_{noisy} is the noisy current, I_{syn} is the synthetic noise-free current, $rand$ is a random number between -1 and +1, and p is the noise level from 0 to 10%, to be added. For each XO considered, GAs were run by varying p and N_{pop} . To obtain a statistical evaluation, 100 GA runs were executed for each pair (p, N_{pop}) , and the best solution and related parameters (RMSE, P) were saved for each run. The parameter values corresponding to the best RMSE on the 100 runs were then selected as the solution. Two other important quantities, the absolute (Δ) and the relative error (Δ_B) between the exact and the best values, respectively, were also computed.

TABLE I. EXACT VALUES AND SEARCH INTERVALS OF THE PARAMETERS APPLIED TO GA

	I_{ph} (A)	I_s (μA)	n	R_s (Ω)	G_p (Ω ⁻¹)
Exact	0.7608	0.3223	1.4808	0.0367	0.0173
Low	0.0000	0.1000	1.0000	0.0001	0.0001
High	1.0000	1.0000	2.0000	1.0000	1.0000

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of applying GAs to the parameter extraction of the noise-free and noisy curves and the benchmark cell considering the three XOs.

A. Synthetic Curve

1) Noise-Free Curve

Figure 1 shows the RMSE obtained for the 3 considered XOs as a function of N_{pop} . According to [13], a good RMSE for this SC should be smaller than 9.86022×10^{-4} . As such, the fittings obtained by using BXO with all N_{pop} and UXO and AXO with N_{pop} of at least 150 and 100, respectively, are good. For UXO and AXO, the RMSE achieved was not less than 2×10^{-5} and 2×10^{-4} , respectively, while for BXO it steeply decreased to smaller values by several orders of magnitude: 5×10^{-4} , 2×10^{-5} , 2×10^{-8} , 1×10^{-13} , and 2×10^{-16} for $N_{pop}=20, 50, 100, 150,$ and $20000,$ respectively. Running GAs using BXO with $N_{pop}=50$ gives an equivalent performance to using UXO with $N_{pop}=20000$. For greater N_{pop} , BXO outperformed UXO and AXO. However, BXO converges very slowly, in more than 2000 iterations. On the other hand, UXO and AXO perform between 45 and 200 iterations until convergence is reached. The fast convergence to a non-optimal value and the slow decrease of the RMSE indicate that these XOs favor premature convergence. UXO does not create new genes other than those initially generated, and AXO does not explore the space outside the parents. The iterations quickly reach a state where there is no population diversity. Several techniques have been proposed to avoid premature convergence, but their study is beyond the scope of this work.

Fig. 1. RMSE of the noise-free curve as a function of population size (N_{pop}) for the three crossover operators.

a) The UXO Operator

Figure 2 shows the relative error Δ_B of the extracted parameters as a function of N_{pop} and the slow increase of precision (decrease of the error) as N_{pop} increases. I_{ph} is the parameter extracted with the highest precision, followed, in not less than one order of magnitude away, by $n, R_s, G_p,$ and I_s . With N_{pop} greater than 150, the errors were always smaller than 20%, and for 20000 they were smaller than 0.4%. This corresponds to the region where the RMSE was less than $1 \times 10^{-3}\%$. This increase is ascribed to the increase in the resolution of the initial population. Better performance can be achieved by increasing N_{pop} at the expense of huge memory space and execution time. Despite these results, a smaller

RMSE was expected since the exact parameter values were known and the noise-free data. It was expected to get all the Significant Digits (SDs) of the parameters given in Table I to generate the curve using (1). Such performance can be easily obtained with the Newton-Raphson method. Given the values and precision of each parameter, it can be easily shown that the errors must be smaller than $6.5 \times 10^{-3}\%, 1.5 \times 10^{-2}\%, 3.3 \times 10^{-3}\%, 0.14\%,$ and 0.29% for $I_{ph}, I_s, n, R_s,$ and $G_p,$ respectively, to extract all SDs of each parameter. So, each error must be smaller than $3.3 \times 10^{-3}\%$ to extract all SDs from the 5 parameters. This can be verified in Table II which shows the RMSE, the extracted parameters, and the errors obtained with $N_{pop}=100, 1000,$ and 20000 . A comparison of Tables I and II shows that for $N_{pop}=20000,$ the extracted parameters were close to the exact values. However, there is a lack of precision since, although all SDs of I_{ph} and R_s were found, there was a loss of two SDs for I_s and n and one for G_p . For more practical cases, i.e. $N_{pop}=100$ and $1000,$ all SDs were lost for I_s and 2 were lost for $I_{ph}, R_s,$ and G_p . For $n,$ 4 and 3 SDs were lost for N_{pop} values of 100 and 1000. Despite this lack of precision, a good fit was obtained and all RMSEs for N_{pop} greater than 150 were better than the value of 9.86022×10^{-4} found in [13].

TABLE II. RESULTS FOR NOISE-FREE CURVE USING UXO

N_{pop}	100		1000		20000	
Param	Value	$\Delta_B(\%)$	Value	$\Delta_B(\%)$	Value	$\Delta_B(\%)$
$I_{ph}(A)$	0.76156	9.99E-2	0.76102	2.87E-2	0.76082	2.75E-3
$I_s(\mu A)$	0.56704	75.94	0.26864	16.65	0.32390	0.4978
n	1.54066	4.043	1.46262	1.228	1.48131	3.47E-2
$R_s(\Omega)$	0.03419	7.011	0.03736	1.614	0.03673	8.29E-2
$G_p(\Omega^{-1})$	0.01839	6.190	0.01609	10.25	0.01738	0.3698
RMSE	1.193E-3		3.287E-4		2.154E-5	

Fig. 2. Errors of the extracted model parameters of the synthetic noise-free solar cell as a function of the population size for the UXO operator.

b) The AXO Operator

Figure 3 shows Δ_B as a function of N_{pop} . I_{ph} was extracted with the highest precision, followed by $n, R_s, G_p,$ and I_s at several orders of magnitude away. The precision increased very slowly with increasing N_{pop} and the errors were smaller than 50% only for N_{pop} greater than 500. Figure 1 shows that the RMSE was less than 1×10^{-3} for N_{pop} greater than 100. The effect of premature convergence was stronger and the precision of the extracted parameters was lower than in UXO. Table III shows the RMSE, the extracted parameters, and the errors obtained with $N_{pop}=100, 1000,$ and $20000,$ where there was a lack of precision, although all RMSEs were good. Although 3 SDs were found for $I_{ph},$ all SDs of I_s were lost, and only 1 was found for the other parameters.

Fig. 3. Errors of the extracted model parameters of the synthetic noise-free solar cell as a function of the population size for the AXO operator.

TABLE III. RESULTS FOR NOISE-FREE CURVE USING AXO

N_{pop}	100		1000		20000	
Param	Value	$\Delta_B(\%)$	Value	$\Delta_B(\%)$	Value	$\Delta_B(\%)$
$I_{ph}(A)$	0.76085	6.75E-3	0.76065	1.97E-2	0.76072	9.90E-3
$I_s(\mu A)$	0.54841	70.15	0.44515	38.12	0.42017	30.37
n	1.53643	3.7570	1.51404	2.2446	1.5081	1.845
$R_s(\Omega)$	0.03460	5.908	0.03531	3.959	0.03568	2.969
$G_p(\Omega^{-1})$	0.01433	17.27	0.01501	13.30	0.01553	10.33
RMSE	8.780E-4		5.766E-4		4.047E-5	

c) The BXO Operator

Figure 4 shows that the Δ_B of the extracted parameters using BXO was less than 1% for all considered N_{pop} . I_{ph} was the parameter extracted with the highest precision, as its corresponding error was always lower than $1 \times 10^{-3}\%$, and for N_{pop} greater than 400 it was 0% (it was set $1 \times 10^{-15}\%$ in Figure 4 for the sake of logarithmic scale). This parameter was followed, not less than one order of magnitude away, by n , R_s , G_p , and I_s . The increase of precision was very fast as N_{pop} increased from 20 to 400. The error of I_s decreased from 1% to $1 \times 10^{-11}\%$. When N_{pop} increased from 400 to 20000, the precision slowly increased and the error of I_s decreased from 1×10^{-11} to $1 \times 10^{-13}\%$. The errors obtained, less than 1%, show that for N_{pop} as low as 20, at least one SD was found for each parameter. For $N_{pop}=100$, the absolute errors were $1.31 \times 10^{-6}\%$, $1.88 \times 10^{-3}\%$, $5.92 \times 10^{-4}\%$, $2.39 \times 10^{-5}\%$, and $3.62 \times 10^{-5}\%$ for I_{ph} , I_s , n , R_s , and G_p , respectively. This is only a loss of two SDs in I_s and one in n . For N_{pop} greater than or equal to 150, all SDs of the parameters were exact in each GA execution.

TABLE IV. RESULTS FOR NOISE-FREE CURVE USING BXO

N_{pop}	150		1000		20000	
Error	Δ	$\Delta_B(\%)$	Δ	$\Delta_B(\%)$	Δ	$\Delta_B(\%)$
$I_{ph}(A)$	9.4E-15	1.2E-12	0.0000	0.0000	0.000	0.000
$I_s(\mu A)$	1.1E-11	3.55E-9	6.7E-11	2.1E-12	5.6E-12	1.7E-13
n	3.6E-12	2.4E-10	2.1E-11	1.4E-13	1.7E-12	1.2E-14
$R_s(\Omega)$	1.5E-13	4.1E-10	8.7E-13	2.4E-13	7.0E-14	1.9E-14
$G_p(\Omega^{-1})$	2.3E-13	1.38E-9	1.6E-12	9.3E-13	1.7E-13	1.0E-13
RMSE	1.418E-10		2.686E-15		2.695E-16	

Table IV shows the RMSE, Δ , and Δ_B of the extracted parameters for $N_{pop}=150, 1000,$ and 20000 . The maximum Δ ($1.14E-11$), was seven positions away from the last SD of I_s . Hence, increasing N_{pop} to over 150 did not improve the precision. Figure 1 shows that running GAs using BXO with

$N_{pop}=50$ gave equivalent RMSEs as using UXO with $N_{pop}=20000$. Figures 2-4 for these N_{pop} show that BXO had better precision, and outperformed UXO and AXO with $N_{pop}=150$.

Fig. 4. Errors of the extracted model parameters of the synthetic noise-free solar cell as a function of the population size for the BXO operator.

d) Comments

The precision of the SC parameters extracted by GAs from noise-free data was greatly affected by the XO used. As reported in [36], obtaining a good fit, a synonym for good RMSE, does not prove the validity of the model parameters. Parameter extraction can have many purposes. If the goal is a good fitting regardless of the parameter precision, GAs can be run several times either by using BXO with a very low N_{pop} , such as 20, or by using UXO or AXO with a low N_{pop} , such as 150, and pick the best solution. If the goal is good precision ($\Delta_B < 10\%$), GAs can be run several times using UXO with a high N_{pop} , such as 2000, and pick the best solution. If the goal is a high parameter precision ($\Delta_B < 1\%$), GAs can be run using UXO several times with a very high N_{pop} , such as 20000, and pick the best solution. For all purposes, GAs can be run only once using BXO with a relatively low N_{pop} , such as 150, and get very good fitting and parameter precision. AXO gives parameters with very low precision for all N_{pop} , and can only be used for good fitting.

2) Noisy Curve

A noise level p varying from 0.1 to 10% was added to the synthetic curve using (5). The parameters of the noisy curves were extracted by GAs using UXO, AXO, and BXO. For all cases, the solutions were picked as the best over 100 runs of GAs.

a) The UXO and AXO Operators

Figures 5 and 6 show the errors of the parameters extracted by the GAs with $N_{pop}=20000$ using UXO and AXO, respectively, as a function of noise levels. The errors were independent of noise levels for all N_{pop} values. For the two XOs, I_{ph} was the parameter extracted with the highest precision for all noise levels, with errors less than 1.2% and 0.5% for UXO and AXO, respectively. Although the errors were acceptable for R_s and n , with 14% and 7% for UXO and AXO, respectively, they reached very high values for G_p and I_s . The I_s and G_p values were 120% and 210% for UXO and 45% and

80% for AXO, respectively. Therefore, AXO performed better than UXO.

b) The BXO Operator

Figure 7 shows the results obtained with GA using BXO with $N_{pop}=250$ as a function of p , where the errors increased with p . All errors were lower than 10%, except for I_s which reached 30% for p more than 6%. The errors of I_{ph} , n , R_s , and G_p were always less than 0.1%, 2%, 2%, and 10%, respectively. For practical cases with p less than 5%, all errors were less than 10%. Thus, BXO outperformed AXO and UXO for noisy curves.

Fig. 5. Errors of the model parameters of the noisy synthetic solar cell as a function of the noise level for the UXO operator and $N_{pop}=20000$.

Fig. 6. Errors of the model parameters of the noisy synthetic solar cell as a function of the noise level for the AXO operator and $N_{pop}=20000$.

Fig. 7. Errors of the model parameters of the noisy synthetic solar cell as a function of the noise level for the BXO operator and $N_{pop}=250$.

c) Curve Fitting

Figures 8-10 show the noisy curves corresponding to $p=1, 2, 5,$ and 10% , along with the corresponding fitting curves by

UXO, AXO, and BXO. Comparing the curves with the synthetic curve ($p=0\%$) shows the good fit obtained by AXO and BXO. In the region $I_{sc}-I_m$, UXO gave a less good fit, which is acceptable only when considering that the curves are noisy.

Fig. 8. Noisy synthetic data and corresponding fitted curves with parameters extracted by using UXO with $N_{pop}=20000$.

Fig. 9. Noisy synthetic data and corresponding fitted curves with parameters extracted by using AXO with $N_{pop}=20000$.

Fig. 10. Noisy synthetic data and corresponding fitted curves with parameters extracted by using BXO with $N_{pop}=250$.

d) Comments

For the noise-free curve, the quality of fit and the precision of parameters extracted by GAs were highly affected by the used XO. While AXO and BXO give good fitting, only BXO gives good parameter precision. For UXO, neither the fitting nor the parameter precision is good.

B. Experimental Data

The GAs were applied to the parameter extraction of the most used SC in the literature [34]. Table V shows the optimal obtained results along with those of some recently published studies, namely Grouping-based Global Harmony Search

(GGHS) and Innovative Global Harmony Search (IGHS) [37], Self-Adaptive Differential Evolution (SADE), Performance Guided JAYA (PGJAYA), and Self-Adaptive Teaching-Learning-based Optimization (SATLBO) [13], and Differential Evolution with Dynamic Control Factors (DEDCE) [38]. Figure 11 shows the obtained fitting.

The results of UXO and AXO were obtained with $N_{pop}=20000$ and were very close to those of BXO. However, they were obtained only once in all GAs runs, and there is no guarantee that they will be reproduced in other runs. AXO gave better results than those of [13] and [37], but worse than BXO, due to the strong effect of premature convergence.

TABLE V. PARAMETERS EXTRACTED BY DIFFERENT METHODS

Work	$I_{ph}(A)$	$I_s(\mu A)$	n	$R_s(\Omega)$	$G_p(\Omega^{-1})$	RMSE ($\times 10^{-4}A$)
This work						
BXO	0.7608	0.3107	1.4773	0.0365	0.0189	7.73006
UXO	0.7606	0.3059	1.4757	0.0367	0.0181	7.87296
AXO	0.7606	0.4455	1.5143	0.0349	0.0157	9.65930
Previous works						
GGHS [37]	0.7609	0.3262	1.4822	0.0363	0.0188	9.9097
Fébbba [13] ^(a)	0.7068	0.3230	1.4812	0.0364	0.0537	9.8602
DEDCE [38]	0.7608	0.3107	1.4767	0.0365	0.0189	7.73006
IGHS [37]	0.7608	0.3435	1.4874	0.0361	0.0188	9.9306

a: DE, PGJAYA, and SATLBO [13]

Fig. 11. Experimental data and fitted curves for the RTC solar cell.

BXO gave the same RMSE, I_{ph} , I_s , R_s , and G_p as DEDCE which had the smallest RMSE (7.730062×10^{-4}) for this SC [38]. There is only a small difference of 0.04% in the value of n , 1.4773 for BXO against 1.4767 for DEDCE. The concordance seems perfect. It can also be noticed that the results shown in Table V for BXO were reproduced in each GA run for all N_{pop} greater than or equal to 150 (1100 executions). Differences were observed only beyond the 7th SD. Hence, BXO outperforms UXO and AXO and competes with the most efficient methods.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study analyzed the accuracy of the 5 SDM parameters of SCs using GAs by considering the effect of 3 XOs, namely the UXO, the AXO, and the BXO. Three datasets were used, an experimental benchmark cell and simulated curves with noise levels (p) of 0-10%. The analysis was performed by varying N_{pop} from 20 to 20000. For each triplet (XO, p , N_{pop}), 100 GA runs were conducted and the solution was picked as the result

of the best run. The simulation results showed that the performance of GAs varied significantly with the employed XO. When using UXO or AXO with very high N_{pop} (as high as 20000), GAs only produced good accuracy in the two following cases:

- with UXO for the noise-free curve
- with AXO for the benchmark cell, obtaining an RMSE of 7.87296×10^{-4} . As this result was obtained only once in more than 1400 runs, there is no guarantee that it can be reproduced.

For all other cases, the parameter accuracy is very low, explicitly:

- with UXO, for noisy data and the benchmark cell
- with UXO, for the noise-free curve with low and moderate N_{pop}
- with AXO, for noise-free and noisy data
- with AXO, for the benchmark cell with low and moderate N_{pop} .

This performance is a consequence of premature convergence, a well-known problem of EAs. As such, GAs with UXO or AXO are not appropriate for SC parameter extraction. On the other hand, GAs give very high accuracy when using BXO with a N_{pop} as small as 150, for all analyzed cases:

- For the noise-free curve, the parameter errors were smaller than $10^{-13}\%$
- For noisy data, the parameter errors were smaller than 10% for practical cases, i.e. for noise up to 5%, and smaller than 30% for p up to 10%
- For the benchmark data, GAs gave the same RMSE as DEDCE [38], which has provided the smallest RMSE for this SC equal to 7.730062×10^{-4} .

It is important to note that the above results were reproduced in each of the 100 GA runs for each N_{pop} and had the same quality as the 5 methods considered in [13]. These results demonstrate that for SC parameter extraction, GAs with BXO should be classified at the top of the most efficient EAs. Previous studies carried out on clean data, concluded that GAs give bad precision or/and are not appropriate for SCs parameter extraction [1-4, 6, 39, 40]. This study used clean and noisy data, showing that if such conclusions are correct for UXO or AXO, they are not correct for BXO. Therefore, this study recommends the use of GA with BXO for SC parameter extraction. This result has to be confirmed with other OFs, other experimental data, and other XOs. Future works on EAs must study the effects of varying the genetic operators on the extracted parameters.

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The Effect of Polypropylene Fibers on the Fracture Characteristics of Lightweight Aggregate Crumb Rubber Concrete Composites

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ABSTRACT

The increasing use of rubber tires and their low recycling ratio have made them a serious environmental problem. This work aims to develop and investigate enhanced lightweight aggregate crumb rubber concrete (PFLWACRC) composites regarding the fracture properties of concrete. Polypropylene (PP) fibers are commonly familiar with increased crack growth endurance of concrete. On the other hand, the reuse of waste rubber in concrete plays a major role in the mitigation of the effects of climate change. Various concrete mixtures were designed with conventional Portland cement and common lightweight coarse aggregates. The variables considered in this study are PP fibers in different percentages (0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6% volume fraction), and crumb rubber with various substitution proportions (0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% of fine aggregates). Cement with 450kg/m³ density with 10% silica fume was used. The fracture characteristics, which involve fracture toughness (KIC) and fracture energy generation (GF), of all concrete mixtures were evaluated by testing two types of samples, i.e. 54 notched concrete beams with dimensions of 10×10×52cm and 54 cylinders with diameter×height equal to 15×30cm. The results showed that the fracture toughness generation addresses the energy scattering limit of concrete mixtures. The findings showed that the existence of PP fibers increased the fracture energy and critical Crack Mouth Opening Displacement (CMOD_c). The PP fibers had a limited effect on the compressive strength and may even reduce it, but a remarkable enhancement of the energy absorption was observed.

Keywords-lightweight aggregates; silica fume; crack growth; polypropylene fibers; crumb rubber; fracture energy

I. INTRODUCTION

Fibers and waste rubber in Lightweight Aggregate Concrete (LWAC) are promising additive materials to control and improve its fracture behavior. The fracture properties of concrete altogether impact the underlying conduct of concrete constituents [1]. Authors in [2] examined the fresh properties of

exact Low-Strength Rubber Concrete (LSRC) and Controlled Low-Strength Rubber Lightweight aggregate Cement (CLSRC) with unused-tire rubbers in different substitution percentages, namely 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%. The percentage of substitution influences the unit weight and initial setting time. About 10% growth in the content of rubber fragments

diminishes the unit weight by about 70kg/m^3 . The compressive strength of CLSRC and CLSRLC declines even though the content of rubber substitution increments. Authors in [3] examined the mechanical properties and the penetrability of rubber treated plain pervious concrete. Three different sorts of rubber have been developed as a substitute for aggregates in the design of rubber-handled simple concrete combinations. In the analysis, four-detailed rubber substances by total aggregate volume were considered. The outcome showed that the utilization of rubber essentially exasperated the pervious concrete mechanical properties.

Generally, alternatives of common aggregates, including rubber grains, exhibit a critical increment in stiffness and ductility of concrete and a better damping limit. Authors in [4] examined the appropriateness of trash tire synthetic rubber in concrete as an alternative for river sand. Three water/cement ratios (0.40, 0.45, and 0.50) and 0–20% replacement of fine aggregates were used. In [5], tests were carried-out to evaluate characteristics such as compressive strength, flexural strength, abrasion resistance, microstructure, and water penetrability. It was found that a 50% replacement of aggregates with tire rubber might be used for regular fine aggregates without a significant decrease in strength. It was noticed that the replacement of mineral aggregates with tire-rubber particles showed a substantial decrease in ultimate compressive strength and modulus of elasticity. Due to this reduction in ultimate compressive strength, the maximum percentage of aggregate replacement with rubber should not be more than 25% [5]. In general, the crack generation in concrete containing waste rubber is smaller than that occurring in ordinary concrete. The mode of failure in tire-rubber concrete compared to that of plain concrete exhibits higher deformation. Future investigations are needed to address the energy retention of tire-rubber concrete under dynamic loads, and the toughness of tire-rubber cement under unfavorable enduring conditions. Authors in [6] proposed the replacement of aggregates with 20–40% crumb rubber. It was found that concrete mixtures with such substitutions showed beneficial and superior properties. Authors in [7] reported that the addition of crumb tire rubber in up to 5% volume fraction in a cement matrix does not yield a significant variation of concrete's maximum stress and elastic modulus. In terms of splitting tensile strength, Portland cement concrete specimens made with 25% of rubber fibers by total aggregate volume retained 20% of their splitting tensile strength after initial failure.

Cement and concrete were subjected to high-level warming in [8, 9]. It was discovered that the harm due to warming from 120 to 400°C enlarges crack energy by half. Authors in [10] examined the residual fracture energy of cement paste, mortar, and concrete subjected to high temperature and found that the thermal damage due to heating from 120 to 400°C increases the fracture energy by 50%. They reported that the post-cracking behavior of concrete specimens was unaffected by the partial substitution of fine aggregates with rubber particles having similar dimensions, whereas a good residual strength after cracking and significant energy absorption were observed for rubber concrete mixes obtained by adding coarse rubber chips in place of coarse aggregates.

Among non-metal fibers, the impact of polypropylene (PP) compositions on the assets of LWAC has been examined thoroughly. The test consequences of [11-16] demonstrated that, if PP fibers are utilized in combination with a LWAC blend, they may have a moderate impact on the enhancement of the compressive strength and may even decrease it. The impact of 3 kinds of fibers on the properties of expanded clay LWAC was explored. PP composition did not influence the compressive strength, while carbon composition and steel fibers had impact up to 1.0% and up to 1.5%, respectively. The PP fibers can likewise be utilized in LWAC to avoid weak actions. Authors in [17] used small PP fibers ($L = 1.3\text{cm}$ and $D = 0.0015\text{cm}$). They announced that PP fibers marginally improve the energy ingestion while steel fibers greatly affect the energy retention of concrete under pressure. The significance of the ductility of concrete constructions exposed to seismic loading is broadly recognized and configuration codes represent this limit. These perceptions accentuate the preferred position that PP fibers add to the pliability of pumice LWAC, which is viewed as weak. Subsequently, more productive and more efficient arrangements might be conceived by fusing pumice insubstantial aggregates with steel rods in mixtures [18-23]. The extent of this examination is unquestionably very restricted to give some exploratory information on the impact of PP fibers and scrap rubber on fracture properties (counting G_F and K_{IC}) of PP Fiber Lightweight Aggregate Crumb Rubber Concrete (PFLWACRC). An amount 10% silica fume has been utilized to upgrade the mechanical properties of this kind of concrete.

The impact of PP fibers on the properties of LWAC is examined in this paper. This investigation studied the crack generation of PFLWACRC. The impact of waste rubber on the crack growth of the PFLWACRC with different levels of PP fibers is presented. In PFLWACRC, PP fibers were utilized to improve the crack growth resistance of concrete, while the incorporation of waste rubber is eco-friendly and requires less energy.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

A. Concrete Ingredients

- Cement: Ordinary Portland concrete (Type I) was used in the current study. The density of cement was kept constant as 450kg/m^3 .
- Fine aggregates: Regular ordinary weight fine clean sand free from any contaminations was utilized. Specific gravity, water absorption, and fineness modulus of the soil were 2.3, 2.9%, and 2.2, respectively, according to ASTM C-33.
- Coarse aggregates: Normal lightweight aggregates (Pumic), obtained from southwestern Saudi Arabia, were utilized. Sieve analysis test for lightweight aggregates was conducted according to ASTM C 330. The properties of the Lightweight Aggregates (LWA) are given in Table I.
- PP fibers were added at 0.2%, 0.4 %, and 0.6%. The main properties of the fibers are shown in Table II.
- The crumb rubber utilized was obtained from used and worn-out vehicle tires. The particle diameter ranged

between 14 and 20 sieve size (0.85 - 1.40mm), as indicated by ASTM-E11-09, while the specific gravity was found to be 1.20, and the melting point was 200°C. Scrap rubber with different quantities (0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%) was utilized.

- Admixture: super-plasticizer with a solid substance of 40% and water reduction of 25% with a density of 1,210kg/m³ (ASTM C-494) was treated as intermixture to realize workable concrete mixtures (slump value of 120mm±25mm). Based on slump trails and tests, super plasticizer of 1.0% by weight of cement was used.
- Silica Fume (SF) was utilized in concrete mixes. It exhibited an explicit surface area of 19.7m²/gm and specific gravity of 2.27. As a partial replacement, the amount of SF used was 10% by total weight of cement.
- Water: potable water was used in all concrete specimens. The 0.45 water-cement ratio (w/c) was kept constant for all mixes.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF LWA

Property	Specification/Value
Color	grayish/black
Bulk density (kg/m ³) for coarse aggregates	780
Bulk specific gravity (SSD)	1.85
Oven dry specific gravity	1.66
L-A abrasion value	16.4
Water absorption	9.7%
Porosity	8.1%
N.M.S	14 mm

TABLE II. CHARACTERISTICS OF PP FIBERS

Property	Value
Tensile strength (Mpa)	450
Specific gravity	0.89
Elongation at peak (%)	18
young's modulus (GPA)	5
Length (mm)	60
Diameter (mm)	12

TABLE I. LWA DELIBERATE PROPERTIES

LWA type	Deliberate properties
LWA-FR0	LWA with 0% rubber at different levels of fiber content.
LWA-FR5	LWA with 5% rubber at different levels of fiber content.
LWA-FR10	LWA with 10% rubber at different levels of fiber content.
LWA-FR15	LWA with 15% rubber at different levels of fiber content.
LWA-FR20	LWA with 20% rubber at different levels of fiber content.
LWA-FR25	LWA with 25% rubber at different levels of fiber content.

The Lightweight Concrete (LWC) mixtures were divided into 6 groups based on the percentages of PP fiber replacement. Each group consisted of 9 150cm×30.0cm standard cylinders in conjunction, and 9 10cm×10cm×52cm notched beams. All tests were conducted after 28 days. Figure 1 shows the compressive strength vs the unit weight, and fiber percentage.

Fig. 1. Mix proportions by weight and compressive strength.

B. Flexural Tests

Three-point load setup was employed to address the rupture performance of PFLWACRC as per the proposal of RILEM Fracture System Commission (TC50-FMC) [18]. As demonstrated in Figure 2(a), the notched beams had effective length of 40.0cm and a notch at 30mm ($a_0/h = 0.3$) depth was located at the mid-span place. The test was conducted with a closed-loop electrohydraulic universal testing machine with a 1000kN capacity. Control specimens comprised of 3 cylinders with zero percentage of fibers and rubber. The properties (compressive strength and unit weight) of these specimens are almost the equivalent for LWA-FR0. A load cell of 50kN capacity with accuracy of 1N plus a 5.0cm Linear Variable

Differential Transducer (LVDT) with 0.001cm precision were utilized to determine the weight combined with refraction at the middle of length, exclusively. Conversely, Crack Mouth Opening Displacement (CMOD) with a 1.0cm cut on measurements and 0.0001cm precision was used. Steady movement rate of 0.005cm/min was applied up to failure. The testing procedure of the 3-point twisting system (Figure 2(b)) intended to minimize the influence of compressive flexible deformity at the loading points (the platform and actuator head). Two LVDTs were mounted on the two inverse countenances for all specimens to evaluate the rebound at the halfway of length. Specimen, instrumentations, and test set-up are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Flexural three-point load-bending test: (a) Notched beam, (b) setup, (c) photo sample.

C. Evaluation of the Fracture Force

The fracture force is characterized as the all-out force disseminated across a unit section of a broken ligament. It is acquired as of the work carried out (the section below the P-δ arch). The fracture force of the jagged planks comprises 4 sections [1], and is mathematically expressed as:

$$W = W_0 + W_1 + W_2 + W_3 \tag{1}$$

where W_0 is the work done by the external force P , which is recorded by the data acquisition system, W_1 is the work performed by the ego-weight of the planks before the

utilization of the outer force. It has a very small value, and can be neglected. W_2 and W_3 represent the extra work done for the duration of the packing cycle by the own substance of the planks. So, $W_2 = 0.5mg\delta_0$, and W_3 (the end part of the chart after δ_0), can't be estimated in the tests.

The computational derivation of the fracture energy is:

$$w_1 = \int_0^{\delta_0} p d\delta$$

In order to compute the extra work W_3 done by scaled weight, the plunging part of the deflection-load (δ - P) chart is misleadingly stretched out by curve fitting dependent upon the energy work technique [20, 21]:

$$p = \beta\delta^{-\lambda} \geq 0 \quad (\beta, \lambda > 0)$$

$$\ln p = \beta - \lambda \ln \delta \tag{2}$$

The dependability of the matching curves addressed by the consistency factor, R^2 , and the particular fitting boundaries (for example β, λ, R^2) were calculated. W_3 is determined by (2)-(3):

$$w_3 = \int_{\delta_0}^{\infty} \frac{\beta}{\delta^\lambda} d\delta = \frac{\beta}{(\lambda-1)\delta_0^{(\lambda-1)}} \tag{3}$$

The physical fracture force of all concrete mixtures shows an agreement with (4), where A_{lig} is the zone of tendon, specifically $A_{lig} = t(h-a_0)$.

$$G_f = \frac{w_0 + w_1 + w_2 + w_3}{A_{lig}} \tag{4}$$

The obtained outcome of the crack force of all concrete mixtures with different percentages of waste rubber and fibers is shown in Figure 3.

D. Evaluation of the Rupture Toughness

The rupture force (K_{IC}) of concrete reflects its capacity to avoid break down propagation and the capacity of resisting weak rupture in particular. The rupture durability of a concrete material is basically determined by (5) as per ASTM E399-74.

$$K_{IC} = \frac{P_{max} S}{t h^2} f\left(\frac{a}{h}\right) \tag{5}$$

where P_{max} is the vertical upper limit load, h, t and S are the elevation, thickness, and length of the samples, respectively, and $f\left(\frac{a}{h}\right)$ is the numerical shape element, which is computed by:

$$f\left(\frac{a}{h}\right) = 2.9 \left(\frac{a}{h}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 4.6 \left(\frac{a}{h}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} + 21.8 \left(\frac{a}{h}\right)^{\frac{5}{2}} - 37.6 \left(\frac{a}{h}\right)^{\frac{7}{2}} + 38.7 \left(\frac{a}{h}\right)^{\frac{9}{2}} \tag{6}$$

The contribution of PP fibers in concrete is that a bridging force is developed between the fibers and the cement paste, strengthening the material. The equation of ascertaining flexural rigidity suggested by ASTM refers to a simple material. The impact of flexural measure region on the fracture energy of PP fiber strengthened material is incorporated by the supplanting of the efficient fracture size (a_c), which is determined by $a_c = a_0 + \Delta a_c$. When the checking weight (P) arrives at its peak (P_{max}), the crack estuary hole movement goes its critical maximum value ($CMOD_c$), and the genuine length

of pre-break is created from the first value (a_0) to the critical crack length (a_c). Thus, as indicated by the direct asymptotic behavior of superposition, a_c is determined by a LFM equation (7) [19, 23]:

$$a_c = \frac{2}{\pi}(h + h_0) \arctan \sqrt{\frac{tE(\text{CMOD}_c)}{32.6p_{max}} - 0.1135} - h_0 \quad (7)$$

where h_0 is the width of the hardened layer employed to adjust fastening on instruments on the crack lip, (CMOD_c) is the

significant amount of the crack lip hole movement, and E is the modulus of elasticity, calculated by:

$$E = \frac{1}{tc_i} \left[3.70 + 32.60 \tan^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \frac{a_0 + h_0}{h + h_0} \right) \right] \quad (8)$$

where $c_i = \frac{(\text{CMOD}_i)}{p_i}$ is a preliminary quantity defined at an capricious position, (P , CMOD) on the gradient phase of P - CMOD curves. The estimated calculations of the fracture force (K_{IC}) of all mixtures are reviewed in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Computed and experimental results.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The densities of hardened concrete tested at 28 days are shown in Figure 1. It is observed that the PP fibers bring an

unimportant impact on concrete samples. However, the solid thickness is predominantly influenced by the presence of morsel elastic. The solid thickness of the reference sample was 1870kg/m³, the density of concrete comprised of 5%, 10%,

15%, 20%, and 25% waste rubber was 1815, 1785, 1743, 1711, and 1681 kg/m³, respectively. The specimens made up by 0.2%, 0.4%, and 0.6% PP fibers, almost had similar values. Considering the minimal specific gravity of rubber particles, the unit weight of the mixtures with rubber was reduced as the percentage of rubber increased [4, 17].

Based on the compressive strength results recorded in this study, a slight decrease in the compressive strength was observed as the PP fiber percentage increased. From Figure 1, it may be stated that the expansion of PP fibers up to 0.2% of concrete volume appears to have an insignificant impact on the compressive strength of concrete. Yet, adding more PP fibers, up to 0.6%, caused a reduction in compressive strength by about 10%.

The impact of the substitution of fine aggregates with scrap rubber at the compressive force is shown in Figure 1. It is obvious that there is degradation in compressive strength depending on the percentage of waste rubber used, around 15% for 10% of rubber used. The use of SF decreased the degradation in compressive strength [10]. The concrete samples containing rubber showed post failure pressure loads and experienced a large displacement before failure. The samples cracked and withstood a portion of the ultimate load. The large noticed displacement and deformation are certainly related to the fact that the rubber aggregates can withstand huge distortions. It is well known that rubber materials exhibit a low elastic modulus which leads to a deferral in extending the crack and forestalling calamitous failure, which is generally experienced in plain concrete specimens.

The fracture properties of PFLWACRC beams with various replacement percentages of waste rubber and PP fibers were assessed by three-point loading tests. The obtained weight break cheek hole relocation (P -CMOD) relationship is shown in Figure 3. Furthermore, the impact of PP fibers and rubber in fracture force and toughness is shown in Figures 4 and 5. Established on the (δ - P) and P -CMOD behavior, the crack force (G_f) and fracture stiffness durability (K_{IC}) of concrete for all mixtures was determined and is shown in Figure 3. It should be noted that each incentive in Figure 3 was the average of 3 samples in each group.

Obviously, the aim of inserting fibers and rubber to LWA is to enhance fracture behavior. The impacts of fibers and waste rubber on the deflection-weight (δ - P) and load crack mouth opening displacement (P -CMOD) behaviors are plotted in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. Generally speaking, PP fibers marginally improve the energy retention and durability of the material under flexible loads. Overall, PP fibers have a minimal impact on the ductility of LWC at 0.2% volume. For example, the presence of PP fibers expanded the absolute fracture energy and fracture energy of concrete as shown in Figure 5. On the other side, the addition of 0.2% PP increased somewhat the total energy. Figure 4 illustrates the correlation of load refraction behavior for 3 distinctive fiber sizes. Figure 4 demonstrates that the beams along with greater volumes of fiber content (specifically 0.6% by volume) demonstrate a superior resistance particularly beyond large deflections. Concrete mixtures containing 0.4% and 0.6% of PP fibers show more ductility than those with 0.2% PP fibers (Figure 4 (b)-(c)).

It appears that PP fiber volume fraction equal to 0.2% is inconsequential. In this manner, it is proposed that adding 0.4% PP fibers in mixtures improves the flexural properties of LWC. It is seen that the refraction associated to extreme weight increases with the increase of fiber size. This is recognized as the impact of fibers bridging and catching cracking. Figure 4 additionally displays the liner flexible segment of the curvature prior to the propagation of micro cracks in the matrix when using PP fibers. Due to lacking stiffness, it was difficult to gauge the dropping part of LWC. Figure 5 depicts the CMOD relations for 3 distinctive fiber volume substances. It should be noted that, at similar loads after cracking, the beam with larger volume of fibers exhibits substantially more CMOD values.

Fig. 4. Load-deflection curves of all mixes containing (a) 0.2% and (b) 0.4% PP.

Fig. 5. Load - CMOD Curves of all mixes containing (a) 0.2% and (b) 0.4% PP.

A. Fracture Energy

The values of the fracture force of the concrete mixtures are displayed in Figure 3. The impacts of fibers and rubber on the rupture vitality and fracture energy of material mixtures are shown in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. It is obvious that the addition of rubber effectively affects the rupture vitality of material mixtures up to 10%. This outcome demonstrates that fitting rubber waste improves the energy ingestion limit of the concrete. However, too much rubber may negatively affect the energy retention limit. Accordingly, to viably improve the energy assimilation limit of concrete mixes, a fitting measure of rubber ought to be chosen. This result is in accordance with [17, 24]. On the other hand, the fracture properties can be improved with the addition of PP fibers, particularly fracture energy (Figures 3-4). The fracture energy of the concrete mixtures increases by more than 3.0 by expanding the fiber content from 0.2% to 0.6%. The fibers delay the crack spread and do not go to rapid failure, which causes an expansion in the weight carrying capability of beams [25].

B. Rupture Durability

The impact of adding rubber fibers on the durability of the mixtures is shown in Figure 5. It can be noticed from Figure 5 that the rupture force of the mixtures clearly changes with increasing fiber content. With the addition of rubber, the impact of fiber content on the rupture force of the material mixtures is predictable. The rupture force originally increased when up to 15% rubber substance was used and it decreased with further increment of elastic substance until 25%, with the fracture energy being the smallest at 0.2% fiber content. At 0.2% PP fiber, the fracture energy increased by about 80% and 88% when rubber was added by 10% and 15%, respectively. This increase diminished to 56% at 25% rubber substitution. A similar pattern was noticed to the 0.4% and 0.6% PP fiber concrete mixes.

Fig. 6. Effects on fracture energy combined with elastic substance on the fiber.

As shown in Figures 6 and 7, the elevated addition of fibers and rubber may prompt a large increase of the rupture stiffness, maybe because the material power relies on the intensity of the substance and the aggregates are improved by the presence of fibers [18]. For concrete mixtures arranged with various replacement percentages of fiber and rubber, the distinction in

the highest pressure and rupture force may be identified with the force of the interfacial connection. Through vibrations, the water within the material is allowed to go to the LWA due to their extreme-water retention limit, making a moderately superior w/c incentive. Accordingly, a more grounded bond may be framed between the cement paste and LWA, particularly when SF is added to the concrete blend. The above outcome showed that adding rubber improves the protection of concrete mixtures from brittle fracture. However, adding too much rubber may negatively affect that protection. It very well may be inferred that the ideal estimations of rubber to upgrade the fracture properties lie between 10% and 15%, while the PP fibers should not be under 0.4% volume fraction.

Fig. 7. Effect of fiber and rubber on rupture stiffness.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In the current study, the impact of the addition of PP fibers and rubber waste in concrete mixtures on the fracture toughness and fracture energy of LWC were addressed. The progression of 3-point load on 10cm×10cm×52cm beams was examined. Based on the experimental results and the derived calculations, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The addition of PP fibers has irrelevant impact on the density of concrete samples. The concrete density is predominantly influenced by the use of scrap rubber. A serious dilapidation of compressive strength was observed for all concrete mixtures by expanding the rubber substance addition to more than 15%.
- PP fiber addition prompts a critical expansion in the fracture toughness. For addition of the rubber substance from 5% to 10%, the fracture toughness originally increased, whereas the addition up to 25% diminished the increment of fracture toughness.
- PP fibers have no recognizable impact on the hardened properties of concrete at replacement level below 0.2%. The addition of 0.4% PP fibers in concrete affects the compressive behavior. Nonetheless, 0.4% PP fibers increased slightly both fracture toughness and fracture energy. The impact of PP is undeniable in the concrete mixtures. The proposed dose of PP fibers to be utilized in lightweight concrete in order to avoid brittle failure is up to 0.4%.

- Suitable waste rubber level improves the concrete brittleness behavior, however, an excessive amount of rubber may negatively affect this protection. The ideal addition of rubber content to improve the crack behavior varies between 10% and 15%, while PP fiber addition up to 0.4% volume fraction was acknowledged.

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Impact of Leachate Recirculation on the Stabilization of Municipal Solid Waste in Anaerobic Bioreactors of Different Compositions

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the current study is to determine the impacts of leachate recirculation on the degradation of three compositions of municipal solid waste in anaerobic bioreactors. The study was completed by using six columns with equal volume (0.042m³) containing different densities and compositions of solid waste, in order to follow waste degradation over a limited time. Three compositions of waste were studied: simulated fresh waste of standard composition, simulated fresh waste of fermentable composition, and actual aged waste. Measurements of the significant parameters including pH, leachate conductivity, Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), and waste settlement, were carried out. The quantity of oxidized organic matter was increased by the leachate recirculation, and the degradation period was reduced by using leachate recirculation. After 300, 150, and 480 days, waste stabilization seemed to be reached for fresh, aged, and fermentable waste, whereas the organic content decreased to 650, 480, and 4000mg COD/L, respectively.

Keywords-solid waste stabilization; leachate recirculation; bioreactor; chemical oxygen demand

I. INTRODUCTION

The quantity of domestic waste has increased along with population density [1]. Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) generation increases gradually as the commercial and industrial activities extend [2]. The percentages of green and food waste in MSW for middle- and low-income countries are very high [3], whereas landfilling is the most common option of waste disposal. However, during the landfilling process, the high organics amount in MSW often leads to leachate generation [4, 5]. Appropriate landfill management is required globally, especially in developing countries. Early landfill site stabilization and environmental pollution reduction caused by leachates are commonly recognized as important issues. In most developing countries, landfill leachates are treated in stabilization ponds [6], or are collected for further treatment [7]. The leachates are generated either from external water or from within the waste mass [8]. Overflow of untreated leachates or leakage into the environment is a problem because large amounts of landfill leachates are produced by landfill sites with high seasonal rainfalls. Recirculation of leachates in landfills is an attractive technology that can reduce the amount of leachates and limit the decomposition of pollutants in

landfills [9, 10]. Leachate recycling is a proven on-site leachate treatment method. It has been shown that leachate recirculation improves biogas production and final leachate quality and reduces waste stabilization time [11]. Bioreactor landfills are designed to address the shortcomings of conventional landfills and reduce long stabilization times [12]. Bioreactor landfills are categorized as aerobic, anaerobic, semi-aerobic, and hybrid, depending on their operational characteristics [13].

Many researchers had applied such or similar techniques to show the impact of leachate recirculation on the stabilization of MSW. Authors in [14] used untreated leachates for liquid recycling and added water to investigate the effect on the anaerobic digestion of food waste. They combined batch analysis of mesophilic Biochemical Methane Potential (BMP) with a cyclical water reuse operation. Cyclic BMP assays showed that using an appropriate proportion of recycled leachates along with fresh water can stimulate the methanogenic activity and promote biogas production. Authors in [15] studied the impact of different leachate recirculation strategies on the discontinuous anaerobic digestion of solid organic waste. Many leachate recirculation strategies have been used in digestion systems of batch solid-phase in laboratory-

scales experiments. Comparative studies with intermittent and continuous return of exudate showed no improvement of continuous flow. Authors in [16] used landfill leachates and gases to predict the moisture distribution and the water and gas pores of typical bioreactor landfills as the leachate recirculation or injection system. The effects of the unsaturated hydraulic conductivity and the anisotropic nature and heterogeneity of MSW, the geometry of vertical wells on pore water, moisture distribution, and gas pressure were tested. The unsaturated hydraulic properties of MSW have significant impact on the wetted area and pore water pressure during the initial stage of leachate injection and subsequent gravity drainage. Authors in [17] investigated the combination of a vertical well and a spray recirculation system simultaneously, and stated the impact of their synchronized application on landfill leachates. Authors in [18] investigated the impact of aeration on leachate recycling and waste decomposition rates using leachate quality and quantity. This study investigated the stabilization of MSW in different bioreactor landfills (anaerobic, semi-aerobic, aerobic, and recirculating anaerobic leachate landfills) in terms of leachate characteristics. The results noted that leachate recycling appeared to be a good solution to deliver in-situ treatment and minimize time of leachate stabilization when an aerobic landfill is not applicable. Authors in [19] investigated the effect of a semi-aerobic bioreactor landfill and the co-treatment of leachate recirculation and pre-aeration on landfill stabilization. The results proved high removal rates for COD and ammonia nitrogen, reaching 97% and 88%, respectively. The current research mainly addresses the determination of the effects of leachate recirculation on solid waste stabilization and settlement at different degradation stages and for different compositions (fresh, aged, and fermentable MSW) collected from different locations in Baghdad, Iraq to eliminate the risk of waste contamination in the long term.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

A. Waste Samples

The physical compositions of the MSW samples adopted in this study were manually adjusted to simulate the typical MSW compositions in Baghdad based on the average of 12 samples (Table I).

TABLE I. WASTE SAMPLE INGREDIENTS AND COLLECTION POINTS

District	Type and weight of waste (kg)					
	Organic	Plastic	Paper	Metal	Glass	Other
1 Al-Shaab	41	21	17	5	6	10
2 Al-Ghadeer	43	21	16	4	5	11
3 New Baghdad	42	22	17	4	6	8
4 Al-Sader1	44	19	16	4	4	13
5 Al-Sader2	43	20	17	4	5	11
6 Al-Adhamya	39	21	19	6	7	8
7 Al-Karada	39	21	20	5	6	9
8 Al-Rasafa	39	22	20	5	6	8
Average	41.25	20.875	17.75	4.625	5.625	9.75

B. Experimental Work

The experiment was conducted using 6 plastic columns of 750mm height and 300mm diameter, named C1-C6 (Figures 1-2). Each column has a cover and two perforated plastic plates,

the first plate at a height of 5cm from the base of the reactor to ensure that the waste does not fall to the bottom during the decomposition process and thus clog the leachate collection valve, and the second plate at a distance of 5cm from the top of the reactor to distribute the recycled leachate and water simulating local seasonal rainfall rate. Finally, an external meter containing two sensors was inserted inside the columns to measure pH and moisture content during the bioreaction processes. Moisture content was maintained within the range of 40 to 60% by weight in order to prevent oxygen deficit due to void saturation from occurring. Table II shows the composition of MSW compacted in each column: fresh waste generated from households without sorting, waste that have been buried for several years from an aged sanitary landfill site, and fermentable only organic waste, which are represented by food waste, tree leaves, and garden waste.

Fig. 1. Sketch of the anaerobic bioreactor. 1-Gas valve, 2-upper storage container for leachate recirculation, 3-upper perforated plate, 4-thermometer, 5-anaerobic biodegradation tank, 6-lower perforated plate, 7-leachate collection container, 8-extra leachate container, 9-pump, 10-pH and moisture content meter, 11-cover for waste feeding.

Fig. 2. Six bioreactor columns.

TABLE II. SOLID WASTE CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO COLUMNS

Column's code	C6	C5	C4	C3	C2	C1
Waste type	Fermentable	Fermentable	Aged	Aged	Fresh	Fresh
Waste mass (kg)	25	25	30	30	15	15
Waste height (m)	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6
Waste volume (m ³)	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.042
Waste density (kg/m ³)	595.24	595.24	714.29	714.29	357.14	357.14
Precipitation (L/week)	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6
Leachate recirculation (flowrate) (L/day)	0.03	0	0.1	0	0.06	0

C. Analysis Methods

Leachate samples were analyzed for pH, Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), and Electrical Conductivity (EC) on a monthly basis. All the parameters were measured according to standard methods [20].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. pH Value

The pH changes in the bioreactor leachates are depicted in Figure 3. The waste in reactors 1, 2, 5, 6 went through aerobic decomposition and produced a greater initial CO₂ concentration due to the tiny amount of air in the voids of the fresh waste after loading. As a result, the pH values decreased over the first 100 days. Leachate recharge has the ability to speed up the hydrolysis of organic matter [12, 21], and acidogens, which are rapidly growing bacteria, have the ability to quickly transform soluble organic waste into volatile fatty acids [22]. The pH levels of the 6 reactors gradually rose to above 8 after 100 days. The relatively lower pH level in the reactors over a longer period of time suggests that acidogenic and hydrolytic bacteria were predominant and that the accumulation of their degradation products, including small molecular organic acids and simple soluble organic matter, delayed the methanogenesis phase. Acidity is the primary inhibitor of methanogenesis under anaerobic conditions. A pH range of 6.5 to 8.0 is optimal for methanogenic bacteria, while a pH range of 5.5 to 6.5 promotes the hydrolysis and acidolysis processes [23]. After this period, the pH of all the reactors rapidly increased and then was maintained at steady state levels.

B. Electrical Conductivity Monitoring

EC in the leachates varied for the 3 types of MSW. High values of EC indicate the presence of high dissolved inorganic materials in samples, yet conductivity values tended to decrease after the 90th day, as shown in Figure 4. It should be noted that fermentable solid waste leachates have a higher EC value. This result is in accordance with the findings of [24], where it is reported that average EC declines with increasing landfill age. The loss of some easily mobilized ions, such as sulphate, metals, and chloride, among others are possible causes of the experiment's decreased EC. These factors would tend to remove the ionic strength from the solution.

Fig. 3. pH profile of (a) fresh, (b) aged, and (c) fermentable waste.

C. Removal of Organic Content

The primary indication of the impact of contaminants in bioreactors is COD. All of the bioreactors' COD patterns were virtually comparable, and the COD concentration increased significantly throughout the first 100 days (Figure 5). One possible reason for this could be that the generated leachates were produced in an unusually tiny amount, making it impossible for the COD to accurately reflect the concentration of organic matter in the waste leachates. Afterwards, as leachates were recirculated, hydraulic loading was increased accordingly providing additional nutrients and sufficient moisture to accelerate the rates of biodegradation [25]. Moreover, food waste is a component that degrades quickly [26]. Because there were not enough microbes to completely break down all the soluble organic waste, the concentration of COD was likely higher [27]. In recirculation reactors, COD concentrations rose quickly to maximum levels for both fresh and aged waste after around 90 days of operation, whereas this was accomplished after 120 days for fermentable waste. These findings demonstrate that leachates might leak more organics if the amount of leachate recirculation is increased within a specific range. The COD concentrations in all the reactors rapidly dropped when the bacteria gradually adjusted to the

conditions in the reactor. These results are marginally better than those found in [28], despite the fact that their work involved more frequent leachate recirculation and utilized significantly more biodegradable materials.

Fig. 4. Profile of electrical conductivity.

D. Settlement of Solid Waste in Columns

One important criterion that makes anaerobic bioreactor landfills identifiable is the settlement of MSW, is settlement [29]. Following the end of the operation time, all bioreactors had a large settlement, as indicated in Table III, primarily as a result of the waste's gravity-induced settling. The anaerobic treatment showed a higher degree of settlement, indicating that the voids accelerated the rate and amount of subsidence. In [30] and over a 400-day testing period, the settlement in aerobic, anaerobic, and dry anaerobic reactors was 32%, 20%, and 7%, respectively, which are lower than the values acquired during the current study. This may be due to the biological decomposition of organic materials, which is influenced by humidity and the amount of organic material in the waste and partially determines the degree of settlement [31, 32]. The low aeration rates for the anaerobic reactors in this experiment could lead to high moisture content in waste, which has a visible effect on the biodegradation of organic matter. Moisture content is also essential for microbial activity.

Fig. 5. Profile of organic content removal

TABLE III. WASTE SETTLEMENT INFORMATION

Code	C6	C5	C4	C3	C2	C1
Total height (cm)	60	60	60	60	60	60
Original volume (cm ³)	42412	42412	42412	42412	42412	42412
Final height (cm)	5	17	44	45	29	34
Final height (%)	8.33	28.3	73.3	75	48.3	56.6
Remaining volume (cm ³)	3534	12017	31102	31809	20499	24033
Removed height %	91.67	71.7	26.7	25	51.7	43.4
Removal ratio difference	6C&5C		C3&C4		C1&C2	
Percentage%	20%		1.7%		8.3%	

IV. CONCLUSION

The usage of different solid waste columns allowed characterizing the main stages of waste decomposition in a limited period of time and highlighting the main disadvantages and advantages of leachates recycling for waste decomposition. Waste composition and degradation rate have a significant

impact on the duration of the degradation process. Recirculating the leachate can reduce the time it takes fresh and old waste columns to reach the methanogenic stage.

Recirculation appeared to limit the risk of waste contamination in the long run. The amount of oxidizable substances co-released into the leachates was even more significant for columns in circulation. The quality of the recycled leachates and the quality of the leachates released from the waste appeared to be similar. After 450 days of recirculation, injecting the still-contaminated leachates appeared to mask contamination that could still be released by the waste.

This study has shown interest in the application of leachate recirculation due to advantages such as the shortening of the deterioration period. The quality of the recirculating leachates and the type of waste (composition and degradation state) are the parameters that determine the impact of recirculation on emissions. The waste settlements increased the leachate recirculation up to 20, 1.7 and 8.3% for fresh, aged, and fermentable waste, respectively.

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Analyzing the Effects of MBPSS on the Transit Stability and High-Level Integration of Wind Farms during Fault Conditions

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ABSTRACT

As the demand for renewable energy continues to increase, wind power has emerged as a prominent source of clean energy. However, incorporating wind energy into the power generation system at a high level can significantly impact the dynamic performance of the power system, resulting in increased uncertainties during operation. This study investigated the effectiveness of the Multi-Band Power System Stabilizer (MBPSS), a new power system stabilizer, in suppressing dynamic oscillations in a multi-machine power system connected to a wind farm. This research focused on analyzing the transient stability of a nine-bus network, commonly known as the Western System Coordinating Council (WSCC), integrated with a Doubly Fed Induction Generator (DFIG) using MATLAB/Simulink. The study evaluated the dynamic performance of the proposed system under fault conditions, including Line-to-Line-to-Line-to-Ground (LLLG) faults. Simulation results showed that MBPSS effectively dampened oscillations and improved the stability of the power system, even in the presence of severe faults and high-level integration of wind farms.

Keywords-wind farm; DFIG; MBPSS; LLLG fault; multimachine power system; transit stability

I. INTRODUCTION

Wind is a highly promising source of renewable energy, thanks to its environmental-friendly characteristics and widespread availability [1]. However, the current rate of integration of wind energy into the electricity grid remains relatively low. The large-scale integration of wind power sources presents potential technical challenges due to their intermittent nature, which must be carefully examined and addressed as part of the development of a sustainable energy system for the future [2-4].

The 9-bus system has been extensively used in power system analyses. In [5], a probabilistic load flow analysis was presented for the 9-bus WSCC system, using a stochastic

approach to validate the effectiveness of probabilistic analysis techniques to gain a more comprehensive understanding of power systems compared to deterministic analysis. The transient stability analysis of the IEEE-9 bus system under multiple contingencies was investigated in [6]. This study compared and employed both the Euler and Runge methods to examine changes in the frequency and rotor angle of the system under various fault conditions. The simulation results showed that the Runge method had a faster response. In [7], transient stability analysis was conducted on the IEEE 9-bus system, taking into account the integration of DFIG- and SCIG-based wind turbines. The simulation results showed that the DFIG-based wind turbine had a lower peak value of relative power angle than the SCIG-based one, but the results for settling time

were reversed. In [8], the transient stability assessment of an IEEE 9-Bus system integrated with a wind farm was investigated to evaluate its stability with DFIG integration.

Two techniques are used to improve oscillation damping and ensure system stability: Power System Stabilizers (PSSs) and FACTS systems have effects extensively documented [9-11]. However, while PSS is effective in damping local modes, it may not sufficiently address inter-zonal modes. Hence, various design approaches have been proposed to enhance PSS efficiency in damping diverse oscillation modes, such as the optimization of performance criteria to achieve optimal control [12], the use of neural networks in smart stabilizers [13], robust control [14], and fuzzy logic [15]. In summary, these controllers have been proven effective in addressing stability issues. This motivates the proposal of a novel power system stabilizer that integrates wind power generation for multi-machine systems. The implementation of MBPSS can significantly improve the primary frequency response of a power system. This is exemplified by the use of MBPSS at Hydro-Quebec (HQ) for several years [16]. Several studies, such as [17-19], highlighted the favorable effects of certain techniques on power systems. These techniques were shown to improve frequency response, global and electromechanical mode damping, and voltage stability. The improvements in the HQ transmission system can be attributed, at least in part, to its unique characteristics. HQ is isolated from the rest of the Eastern Interconnection and is characterized by a long radial structure, with power flow patterns established predominantly in the north-to-south direction.

This study investigated the integration of a wind farm that utilized DFIG as variable speed generators directly connected to the grid into a 9-bus network at a high level. The primary objective was to analyze the impact of wind farm integration on the transient stability of the power system, focusing on evaluating the effects of the MBPSS stabilizer. The evaluation of the system's transient state was based on analyzing the power angles, angular speeds, and frequencies of the synchronous generators. Additionally, fault scenarios, such as the LLLG fault, were considered to assess the system's dynamic performance. The main contributions of the current paper are:

- This study explored the effectiveness of an MBPSS that featured a three-frequency band structure (i.e. low-, intermediate-, and high-frequencies) for analyzing the system's transient stability.
- High-level integration of the wind farm was taken into account to improve the robustness of the MBPSS.
- The suggested system was exposed to high-level perturbation scenarios, including the LLLG fault, and the robustness of the controller was demonstrated to facilitate swift system recovery from these faults.

II. WIND FARM MODEL

A. Wind Speed Model

Accurate modeling of wind turbines is highly dependent on the wind speed model. While wind is often viewed as a random

phenomenon, its variability can be modeled using various approaches [20]. One way to represent the wind speed is to decompose it into a sum of harmonics, as demonstrated by [21]:

$$V_p(t) = 10 + 0.55[\sin(0.0393t) - 0.875 \sin(0.1178t) + 0.75 \sin(0.1963t) - 0.625 \sin(0.3927t) + 0.5 \sin(1.178t) + 0.25 \sin(1.9634t) + 0.125 \sin(3.9269t)] \quad (1)$$

B. Wind Turbine Model

A wind turbine aims to utilize wind energy and convert it into torque that rotates the rotor blades. The amount of wind energy converted into mechanical energy by the rotor is determined by three factors: density of the air, swept area of the rotor, and wind speed. Air density and wind speed are unique to each location and are considered climatic parameters [22]. The mathematical expression for the mechanical power output of a wind turbine is given by [23]:

$$P_m = C_p(\lambda, \beta) \frac{\rho A}{2} V_\omega^3 \quad (2)$$

The mechanical power harvested by the wind turbine and transferred to the rotor is represented by P_m (W). The turbine power coefficient is denoted by C_p , while ρ (kg/m^3) represents the density of the air, A (m^2) indicates the area swept by the rotor, V_ω (m/s) represents the wind speed, λ stands for the speed ratio, and β ($^\circ$) is the blade angle of inclination. Each wind turbine has its distinct power coefficient characteristics. As an example, the power coefficient for a 1.5MW wind turbine can be estimated through measurements and be approximated using [24]:

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta) = 0.5176 \left(\frac{116}{\lambda_i} - 0.4\beta - 5 \right) e^{-21/\lambda_i} + 0.0068 \lambda \quad (3)$$

The value of the λ_i parameter is determined by:

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i} = \frac{1}{\lambda + 0.08\beta} - \frac{0.035}{\beta^3 + 1} \quad (4)$$

C. DFIG Model

The utilization of dynamic modeling for the DFIG in the rotating d - q reference frame yields the following equations [23-25]:

$$\begin{cases} v_{ds} = R_s i_{ds} - \omega_s \psi_{qs} + \frac{d\psi_{ds}}{dt} \\ v_{qs} = R_s i_{qs} + \omega_s \psi_{ds} + \frac{d\psi_{qs}}{dt} \\ v_{dr} = R_r i_{dr} - (\omega_s - \omega_r) \psi_{qr} + \frac{d\psi_{dr}}{dt} \\ v_{qr} = R_r i_{qr} + (\omega_s - \omega_r) \psi_{dr} + \frac{d\psi_{qr}}{dt} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} \psi_{ds} = L_s i_{ds} + L_m i_{dr} \\ \psi_{qs} = L_s i_{qs} + L_m i_{qr} \\ \psi_{dr} = L_r i_{dr} + L_m i_{ds} \\ \psi_{qr} = L_r i_{qr} + L_m i_{qs} \end{cases}$$

The variables u_{ds} , u_{qs} , u_{dr} , and u_{qr} denote the d - q axis stator and rotor voltages, while i_{ds} , i_{qs} , i_{dr} , and i_{qr} represent the stator and rotor currents on the same axis. Additionally, ψ_{ds} , ψ_{qs} , ψ_{dr} , and ψ_{qr} indicate the stator and rotor flux components on the d - q axis. The stator and rotor resistances per phase are denoted by R_s and R_r . The stator and rotor inductances are represented by L_s and L_r , respectively, and L_m denotes the magnetizing inductance.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Synchronous Generator Model

The equations governing the two-axis models of the i -th synchronous machine in a multiple-machine network are [26]:

$$\begin{cases} T'_{d0}\dot{E}'_q = -E'_q - \left(\frac{X_d - X'_d}{T'_{d0}} - \frac{T'_{d0} X''_d}{T'_{d0} X'_d} (X_d - X'_d) \right) i_d + E_{fd} \\ T''_{d0}\dot{E}''_q = -E''_q + E'_q - \left(\frac{X'_d - X''_d}{T''_{d0}} + \frac{T''_{d0} X''_d}{T'_{d0} X'_d} (X_d - X'_d) \right) i_d + E_{fd} \\ T'_{q0}\dot{E}'_d = -E'_d - \left(X_q - X'_q - \frac{T'_{q0} X''_q}{T'_{q0} X'_q} (X_q - X'_q) \right) i_q \\ T''_{q0}\dot{E}''_d = -E''_d + E'_d - \left(X_q - X'_q + \frac{T''_{q0} X''_q}{T'_{q0} X'_q} (X_q - X'_q) \right) i_q \\ \dot{\delta} = \Omega_b(\omega - 1) \\ M\dot{\omega} = (P_m - P_e - D(\omega - 1)) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The equation includes multiple terms. $E'_{d,q}$ and $E''_{d,q}$ indicate the machine's transient and subtransient voltages along the d - q axis per unit (pu), E_{fd} represents the machine's excitation voltage (pu), $i_{d,q}$ signifies the current on the d - q axis (pu), $X_{d,q}$, $X'_{d,q}$, and $X''_{d,q}$, represent the synchronous, transient, and subtransient reactances along the d - q axis (pu), $T'_{d0,q0}$ and $T''_{d0,q0}$ express the machine's transient and subtransient time constants along the d - q axis (s), δ denotes the machine's rotor angle (rad), Ω_b represents the machine's synchronous base speed (rad/s), ω signifies the machine's rotor speed (pu), M refers to the machine's inertia coefficient (pu.s²/rad), D stands for the machine's damping coefficient (pu.s/rad), P_m indicates the mechanical power applied to the machine shaft (pu), and P_e denotes the electrical power generated by the machine (pu).

B. MBPSS model

The Hydro-Québec-developed MB-PSS [27-28] differs from traditional stabilizers that usually use a series of stacked filters (high-pass and phase-lead-lag). Instead, the MB-PSS consists of three separate stages that work autonomously at low, medium, and high frequencies, making it more robust in different circumstances. The process of selecting the optimum values for Multi-Band Power System Stabilizer (MBPSS) parameters involves a combination of theoretical analysis, simulation studies, and field testing. By utilizing the Genetic Algorithm as an optimization technique, the optimal MBPSS parameters can be ascertained [29]. Based on the simulation studies, the MBPSS parameters are tuned to optimize the controller's performance. The tuning process involves adjusting the gain and time constants of the controller's different bands to achieve the desired damping ratio and bandwidth. The simplified structure comprises three gains K_L , K_I , and K_H ,

which are categorized as low, intermediate, and high, and three frequencies F_L , F_I , and F_H that correspond to low, intermediate, and high frequencies measured in Hz.

IV. RESULTS AND SIMULATION

A. 9-Bus Network

A 9-bus test system was employed for all simulations, as shown in Figure 1. The system consists of three voltage levels, namely 16.5, 18, and 13.8KV, and includes three generators with a 567.5MVA total power output, six transmission lines, and three load nodes with 315MW combined consumption. The generator parameters are specified in the Appendix.

Fig. 1. Nine bus network.

Fig. 2. Nine-bus network with a wind farm.

B. Modified Nine-Bus Network

Multiple strategies can improve the effectiveness of the electrical grid across various stages of the power supply chain, including power generation, transmission, and distribution [30-

32]. Various tests were conducted to determine the optimal wind turbine integration rate and the results showed that bus 7 was the best location for the wind farm. As a result, this location was selected to install a farm consisting of 74 turbines, each generating 1.5MW, for a total capacity of 111MW. The turbine parameters are shown in the Appendix. Figure 2 shows an updated illustration of the grid structure.

C. Applying a Fault in the Proposed System

At time $t=1s$, there was a fault with a duration of 0.1s on the transmission line between nodes 5 and 7. The fault was located in the middle of the line and was classified as an LLLG fault. The modified 9-node WSCC network simulation model was implemented using MATLAB/Simulink. A random wind profile was used to simulate realistic wind conditions, with wind speeds fluctuating between 8 and 14m/s for 10s. Figure 3 shows this time-varying profile which was the basis of the case study.

Fig. 3. Wind speed profile.

As mentioned above, the presence of a defect combined with a high level of wind energy integration (35%) results in changes to the power angle and angular speed differences of generators 2 and 3, as well as the frequency at each synchronous generator. To visualize these changes, the Figures below show the evolution of these parameters for two scenarios: (1) without MBPSS, and (2) with MBPSS. The simulation results show that the implementation of MB-PSS in a high wind power integration scenario results in reduced overshoot and faster convergence to the stable equilibrium point, compared to the system without MBPSS. Table I shows a comparison of the damping duration periods for the two scenarios.

TABLE I. DURATION OF DAMPING

Command	Duration of damping
Without MBPSS	>10s
With MBPSS	3s

These data highlight the effectiveness of MBPSS in significantly reducing the damping period of the system. Figures 4 and 5 depict the power angle differences of generators 2 and 3. The power angles δ_{21} and δ_{31} undergo an increase to approximately 58.22° and 33.07° , respectively, followed by subsequent declines to 38.34° and 31.07° for generators 2 and 3. It can be noted that the inclusion of MBPSS results in a reduction of power angle, compared to the system

without it, indicates system stability without any oscillations. The effectiveness of MBPSS in damping oscillations across all frequency ranges is demonstrated in Figures 6 and 7. Specifically, when subjected to an LLLG fault and a 35% wind turbine integration, the system with MBPSS outperforms the one without it. This can be attributed to its multi-stage structure and the presence of three distinct bands, which enable it to efficiently mitigate low-, intermediate-, and high-frequency oscillations.

Fig. 4. Power angle variation δ_{21} .

Fig. 5. Power angle variation δ_{31} .

Fig. 6. Angular speed variation ω_{21} .

Figures 8-10 illustrate a significant increase in generator frequencies leading to system instability before the implementation of the MBPSS power regulator. Implementing MB-PSS, the generator frequencies were stabilized and consistently maintained the nominal frequency of 50Hz. Following a severe disturbance (LLLG fault), the simulation results for a 35 % wind turbine integration scenario with the MBPSS regulator indicate a faster response time and shorter stabilization period, compared to the same scenario without it.

Fig. 7. Angular speed variation ω_{31} .

Fig. 8. Frequency profile generator 1.

Fig. 9. Frequency profile generator 2.

Fig. 10. Frequency profile generator 3.

V. CONCLUSION

This study extensively investigated the modeling and simulation of a high-level wind farm system connected to an electrical network. Dynamic simulations were conducted on a 9-bus multi-machine network that included a wind farm to evaluate the effectiveness and robustness of the MBPSS stabilizer. A wind farm with a capacity of 111MW was installed at bus 7. Using MATLAB/Simulink, this study

analyzed the impact of MBPSS on the transient stability of the power system under failure scenarios, including LLLG faults, and high-level integration of the wind farm. The simulation results indicate a direct correlation between wind farm capacity and power system transient stability. Integrating wind generation at higher levels led to an increase in transient instability. Moreover, the MBPSS was highly effective in enhancing power system stability during high-level integration of wind energy and severe faults and provided adequate damping to all oscillation modes as it consisted of multiple stages with three distinct frequency bands, enabling it to effectively dampen low-, intermediate-, and high-frequency oscillations.

APPENDIX

Table II displays the generator parameters in 'per unit' based on the nominal MVA and KV values. Tables III-V outline the parameters for the wind turbine linked with a DFIG. Tables VI and VII present the MBPSS data for the simplified settings mode and the detailed settings mode, respectively.

TABLE II. GENERATOR PARAMETERS

Generator No:	#1	#2	#3
Rated MVA	247.5	192	128
X_d	0.1460	0.8958	1.3125
X'_d	0.0608	0.1198	0.1813
X''_d	0.0483	0.0891	0.1072
T'_{d0}	8.96	6	5.89
T''_{d0}	0.04	0.033	0.033
X_q	0.0969	0.8645	1.2587
X'_q	0.0969	0.1198	0.1813
X''_q	0.0483	0.0891	0.1072
T'_{q0}	0.31	0.535	0.6
T''_{q0}	0.060	0.08	0.07
R_a	0.0006	0.0013	0.0032
X_l	0.0336	0.0521	0.0742
$H(sec)$	23.64	6.4	3.01

TABLE III. DFIG DATA

Parameters	Value
$S_{nom}(VA)$	1.5e6/0.9
$V_{nom}(V)$	575
$F(Hz)$	50
$R_s(pu)$	0.00706
$Ll_s(pu)$	0.171
$R'_r(pu)$	0.005
$Ll'_r(pu)$	0.156
$L_m(pu)$	2.9
$H(s)$	5.04
p	3

TABLE IV. TURBINE DATA

Parameters	Value
$P_{mec nom}(MW)$	1.5
K_p	500
$\beta(deg)$	50

TABLE V. CONVERTERS DATA

Parameters	Value
P_{max} (pu)	0.5
[L R] (pu)	[0.15 0.0015]
[IL (pu) ph_{IL} (deg)]	[0 90]
V_{dc} (V)	1200
C (F)	10000e-6

TABLE VI. MBPSS DATA FOR SIMPLIFIED SETTINGS MODE

Parameters	Value
Low frequency band: [F_L (Hz) K_L]	[0.2 20]
Intermediate frequency band: [F_I (Hz) K_I]	[0.9 25]
High frequency band: [F_H (Hz) K_H]	[12 145]
Signal limits [V_{lmax} V_{lmax} V_{Hmax} V_{Smax}]	[0.75 0.15 0.15 0.15]

TABLE VII. MBPSS DATA FOR DETAILED SETTINGS MODE

Parameters	Value
Low frequency gains: [K_{L1} K_{L2} K_L]	[66 66 9.4]
Low frequency time constants: [T_{L1} T_{L2} T_{L3} T_{L4} T_{L5} T_{L6} T_{L7} T_{L8} T_{L9} T_{L10} T_{L11} T_{L12} K_{L11} K_{L17}]	[1.667 2 0 0 0 0 2 2.4 0 0 0 1 1]
Intermediate frequency gains: [K_{I1} K_{I2} K_I]	[66 66 47.6]
Low frequency time constants: [T_{I1} T_{I2} T_{I3} T_{I4} T_{I5} T_{I6} T_{I7} T_{I8} T_{I9} T_{I10} T_{I11} T_{I12} K_{I11} K_{I17}]	[1 1 0.25 0.3 0 0 1 1 0.3 0.36 0 0 0 0]
Intermediate frequency gains: [K_{H1} K_{H2} K_H]	[66 66 233]
Low frequency time constants: [T_{H1} T_{H2} T_{H3} T_{H4} T_{H5} T_{H6} T_{H7} T_{H8} T_{H9} T_{H10} T_{H11} T_{H12} K_{H11} K_{H17}]	[0.01 0.012 0 0 0 0 0.012 0.0144 0 0 0 1 1]

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Surface Roughness Modeling of Hard Turning 080A67 Steel

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ABSTRACT

Surface roughness is an important parameter to evaluate the quality of a machining process in mechanical manufacturing. The construction of a surface roughness model of a machining process is the basis for predicting surface roughness corresponding to each certain case. This paper presents the construction of a surface roughness model in 080A67 steel turning. An experimental process was carried out with a total of 15 experiments, designed according to the Box-Behnken matrix. The cutting speed, feed rate, and cutting depth were changed in each experiment, and surface roughness values were measured to build a model that showed the mathematical relationship between surface roughness and the three cutting parameters. A second surface roughness model was also constructed using the Box-Cox transformation. The accuracy of these two models was compared through five coefficients: R^2 , $R^2(pred)$, $R^2(adj)$, Percentage Absolute Error (PAE), and Percentage Square Error (PSE). The results showed that all these coefficients of the model using the Box-Cox transformation were better than those of the first one. In detail, the values of R^2 , $R^2(pred)$, $R^2(Adj)$, PAE, and PSE of the first model were 94.55%, 12.79%, 84.74%, 8.79%, and 1.42%, while for the second model were 99.09%, 85.42%, 97.44%, 2.26%, and 0.18%, respectively, showing that the accuracy of the surface roughness model was improved by using the Box-Cox transformation.

Keywords-hard turning; 080A67 steel; surface roughness; Box-Cox transformation

I. INTRODUCTION

Steel of the 080A67 type is manufactured using the UK standard and is equivalent to some steel types from other countries, such as 65G steel in Bulgaria and Poland, 66Mn4, Ck67 in Germany, 65Mn in China, 1066, 1566, and G15660 in the USA [1]. This type of steel has the advantage of high wear resistance and is used to manufacture parts that require wear resistance in the cement industry, thermoelectricity, sliding plates, etc. [2]. Some studies were carried out to evaluate the characteristics of this steel type such as evaluating the degree of deformation when hot rolling [3], and evaluating friction coefficient [4]. Many studies have been carried out to improve the advantages of this type of steel, such as improving wear resistance by the heat treatment method [5-8], improving compressive residual stress in magnetic processing [9], developing technical solutions to produce high-quality products from the casting process [10], investigation of solutions to reduce microcracking on the surface [11], studies on the solutions to increase the hardness of the surface [12-13], etc.

This type of steel is increasingly used to manufacture parts with high-quality requirements, which usually need some finished faces to assemble with other parts. Therefore, ensuring

that the surfaces used for assembling have small roughness is often a requirement when machining this type of steel. However, the number of published studies on surface roughness and, in particular, on the machining process of this type of steel is quite small. The surface roughness with flat grinding was studied in [14], the surface roughness and the productivity of the machining when grinding the outer round was investigated in [15], the change of hardness of the surface layer when grinding was studied in [16-19], the cutting force when milling was evaluated in [20], and the surface hardening phenomenon when spark machining was studied in [21]. The turning method, and the hard turning method in particular, are increasingly used to machine products with high accuracy requirements [22-24]. So, this study aims to cover the lack of published studies on the hard turning of 080A67.

While several different criteria can be used to evaluate a turning process, surface roughness is the most frequently used parameter [25-26]. The reason behind this is possibly that surface roughness has a direct influence on wear resistance, fatigue strength, and chemical corrosion resistance of the product surface [27]. In addition, measuring the surface roughness in an experimental process is easier than measuring other cutting parameters such as cutting force, cutting heat, etc.

[28]. A commonly used method to study surface roughness in the turning process is the construction of a model to predict it under certain conditions. However, as the accuracy of the predicted surface roughness results relies on the accuracy of the model, it is necessary to improve it. So, this study also aims to improve the accuracy of the surface roughness model.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS AND RESULTS ANALYSIS

This study used 080A67 steel in the experimental process. The steel samples had a length and diameter of 300 and 30mm, respectively. The steel workpieces were heat treated through two steps of quenching and tempering. When quenching, the steel workpieces were heated to 830°C and then cooled in an oil medium. When tempering, the steel workpieces were heated to 540°C and then cooled in an oil medium. A Metrology VHT-A0950D instrument was used to test the hardness of the steel workpieces. All the steel workpieces had a similar hardness, at around 52HRC. Table I shows the percentages by mass of the main chemical elements in steel, which were analyzed using a GNR S3 Mililab 300 emission spectrometer.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL ELEMENTS OF 080A67 STEEL

Element	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni
%	0.67	0.24	1.02	0.002	0.002	0.24	0.22

A Doosan Lynx 220L lathe was used for the experiments. A TiN-coated Kyocera TNMG160404GP was used as a cutting tool in the experimental process. This cutting piece is commonly used in the hard-turning process [29]. The cutting piece parameters, provided by the manufacturer, were: 12° front angle, 6.5° back angle, and 0.4mm tip radius. Straight oils were used in the experimental process, mixed with water to a concentration of 4%, and brought into the cutting zone with a

flow rate of 8lt/min, and 2.6atm pressure, according to the oil manufacturer.

Surface roughness was measured by an SJ301 gauge. To reduce the influence of random errors on the precision of the experimental process, each experiment was carried out with 3 steel samples, and the surface roughness was measured on each steel sample at least 3 times in succession. So, the surface roughness value in each experiment was the average of at least 9 measurements. The experimental matrix was designed according to the Box-Behnken form, which is the most commonly used type of matrix to construct the relationship between input and output parameters [30]. The values of cutting speed, feed rate, and cutting depth were altered in each experiment. These parameters can be quickly adjusted by the machine operator [31-32]. Three values were chosen for each cutting parameter, corresponding to the encoding levels -1, 0, and 1. Table II shows the parameter values chosen for each level. Table III shows the experiment matrix for the fifteen experiments, built according to the Box-Behnken method.

TABLE II. VALUES OF CUTTING PARAMETERS AT LEVELS

Parameter	Unit	Code symbol	Actual symbol	Value at levels		
				-1	0	1
Cutting speed	m/min	x_1	v_c	140	180	220
Feed rate	mm/tooth	x_2	f_z	0.25	0.45	0.65
Depth of cut	mm	x_3	a_p	0.3	0.4	0.5

The experimental process was carried out according to the sequence of the experiments, as shown in Table III. The surface roughness of each steel sample was measured at least 3 times, and the average value of the measurements was taken. The average surface roughness of the 3 steel samples is denoted as Ra_1 , Ra_2 , and Ra_3 , respectively. Table III summarizes the mean of the surface roughness in each experiment.

TABLE III. EXPERIMENT MATRIX AND RESULTS

Exp.	Code value			Actual value			Response			
	x_1	x_2	x_3	v (m/min)	fd (mm/rev)	ap (mm)	Ra_1 (μ m)	Ra_2 (μ m)	Ra_3 (μ m)	Ra (μ m)
1	-1	-1	0	140	0.25	0.4	0.728	0.801	0.865	0.798
2	1	-1	0	220	0.25	0.4	1.055	1.026	1.210	1.097
3	-1	1	0	140	0.65	0.4	0.922	0.966	1.010	0.966
4	1	1	0	220	0.65	0.4	1.547	1.602	1.513	1.554
5	-1	0	-1	140	0.45	0.3	1.392	1.422	1.386	1.400
6	1	0	-1	220	0.45	0.3	2.224	2.432	2.331	2.329
7	-1	0	1	140	0.45	0.5	0.886	0.853	0.874	0.871
8	1	0	1	220	0.45	0.5	1.378	1.378	1.378	1.378
9	0	-1	-1	180	0.25	0.3	1.101	1.082	1.108	1.097
10	0	1	-1	180	0.65	0.3	1.623	1.499	1.387	1.503
11	0	-1	1	180	0.25	0.5	0.801	0.703	0.860	0.788
12	0	1	1	180	0.65	0.5	1.171	1.182	1.160	1.171
13	0	0	0	180	0.45	0.4	0.882	0.884	0.883	0.883
14	0	0	0	180	0.45	0.4	0.879	0.901	0.875	0.885
15	0	0	0	180	0.45	0.4	0.886	0.892	0.883	0.887

The Minitab v.16 software was used to analyze the experimental data in Table III. The surface roughness model was constructed according to (1). The commonly used coefficients to evaluate the accuracy of a regression model, such as the surface roughness model, are R^2 , $R^2(pred)$ and $R^2(adj)$. The closer these coefficients are to 1, the higher the accuracy of the regression model [30].

$$R_a = 0.8850 + 0.2903 \cdot x_1 + 0.1767 \cdot x_2 - 0.2651 \cdot x_3 + 0.2867 \cdot x_1^2 - 0.0680 \cdot x_2^2 + 0.3227 \cdot x_3^2 - 0.0722 \cdot x_1 \cdot x_2 - 0.1055 \cdot x_1 \cdot x_3 - 0.0057 \cdot x_2 \cdot x_3 \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) had R^2 , $R^2(pred)$ and $R^2(adj)$ of 94.55%, 12.79%, and 84.74%, respectively. Thus, although R^2 has a quite large value, the other coefficients have quite small values,

especially the coefficient $R^2(pred)$. This means that if (1) is used to predict the surface roughness, the prediction results will be much different from the experiment results [30]. Therefore, the accuracy of the regression model to predict surface roughness should be increased.

III. IMPROVING THE ACCURACY OF THE SURFACE ROUGHNESS MODEL

Two commonly used methods to increase the accuracy of regression models are converting data according to Box-Cox and Johnson [33, 34]. In this study, the Box-Cox transformation was used to improve the precision of the surface roughness model, as it was also used in several studies, such as the 65G steel surface grinding [14], SCM435 steel centerless grinding [33], 3X13 steel milling [34], and EN 353 steel milling [35]. The condition to perform the Box-Cox transformation was that the surface roughness values in the experiment were not normally distributed [30]. Therefore, it is necessary to check the distribution rules of the surface roughness values when testing. Figure 1 shows a distribution chart of surface roughness values.

Fig. 1. The distribution rule of surface roughness values.

In Figure 1, the red dots represent the surface roughness values and the blue lines represent the normal distribution. It can be seen that the red dots lie far away from the center line and there are red dots outside the limits of the normal distribution. This proves that the set of surface roughness values was not distributed according to the normal rule. On the other hand, the probability value P -value was 0.021, which is lower than the significance level (the significance level is usually chosen as 0.05). This also confirms that the set of surface roughness values was not distributed according to the normal rule [31], meaning that the set of surface roughness data was eligible to perform the Box-Cox transformation. Figure 2 shows the Box-Cox transformation graph. It can be noted that the converted coefficient lambda (λ) equals -1.00, which means that the relationship between the surface roughness before and after the transformation is represented by [30]:

$$R_a(Box.) = (R_a)^\lambda = \frac{1}{R_a} \quad (2)$$

where R_a and $R_a(Box.)$ are the values of surface roughness before and after the Box-Cox transformation, respectively.

Table IV shows the surface roughness values before and after the Box-Cox transformation.

Fig. 2. Box-Cox transformation model of surface roughness

TABLE IV. SURFACE ROUGHNESS VALUES BEFORE AND AFTER BOX-COX TRANSFORMATION

Exp.	$R_a(\mu m)$	$R_a(Box.)$ (dimensionless)
1	0.798	1.253
2	1.097	0.912
3	0.966	1.035
4	1.554	0.644
5	1.400	0.714
6	2.329	0.429
7	0.871	1.148
8	1.378	0.726
9	1.097	0.912
10	1.503	0.665
11	0.788	1.269
12	1.171	0.854
13	0.883	1.133
14	0.885	1.130
15	0.887	1.127

Fig. 3. Distribution rule of surface roughness data after the Box-Cox transformation.

Figure 3 shows the distributions of the surface roughness values after the Box-Cox transformation. It can be noted that all the red dots lie inside the limits of the distribution rule. The probability value P -value was 0.348, which was a lot larger than the significance level. This also confirms that these data were distributed according to the normal rule.

The following equation can be constructed from the surface roughness dataset after the Box-Cox transformation:

$$R_a(\text{Box.}) = 1.1299 - 0.1800 \cdot x_1 - 0.1434 \cdot x_2 + 0.1595 \cdot x_3 - 0.1698 \cdot x_1^2 + 0.0007 \cdot x_2^2 - 0.2057 \cdot x_3^2 - 0.0125 \cdot x_1 \cdot x_2 - 0.0343 \cdot x_1 \cdot x_3 - 0.0422 \cdot x_2 \cdot x_3 \quad (3)$$

Combining (2) and (3) gives the following surface roughness model:

$$R_a = \frac{1}{R_a(\text{Box.})} \quad (4)$$

where $R_a(\text{Box.})$ is given by (3). Equation (4) has R^2 , $R^2(\text{pred})$ and $R^2(\text{adj})$ coefficients of 99.09%, 85.42%, and 97.44%, respectively. These values are very close to 1, proving that (4) can be used to predict surface roughness with high accuracy. The two models were used to predict surface roughness. Note that the model given by (1) is the one without data transformation, and the model given by (4) is the one after the Box-Cox transformation. The value of surface roughness when predicted using (1) is denoted $R_a^{(1)}$, and the surface roughness value predicted using (4) is denoted as $R_a^{(2)}$. Table V shows the results of surface roughness when testing and predicting according to these two models.

TABLE V. SURFACE ROUGHNESS VALUES WHEN TESTING AND PREDICTING ACCORDING TO 2 MODELS

Exp.	R_a (measured)	$R_a^{(1)}$ (1)	$R_a^{(2)}$ (4)
1	0.798	0.565	0.786
2	1.097	1.290	1.068
3	0.966	1.062	0.990
4	1.554	1.499	1.600
5	1.400	1.364	1.350
6	2.329	2.155	2.226
7	0.871	1.045	0.886
8	1.378	1.414	1.429
9	1.097	1.222	1.154
10	1.503	1.587	1.506
11	0.788	0.704	0.787
12	1.171	1.046	1.113
13	0.883	0.885	0.885
14	0.885	0.885	0.885
15	0.887	0.885	0.885
	PAE	8.79%	2.26%
	PSE	1.42%	0.18%

The *PAE* and *PSE* parameters were used to evaluate the accuracy of the two models, and the smaller their values, the higher the accuracy of the model. *PAE* and *PSE* were calculated according to [31]:

$$PAE = \frac{1}{N} \left| \frac{R_a(\text{measured}) - R_a(\text{predicted})}{R_a(\text{measured})} \right| * 100 \quad (5)$$

$$PSE = \frac{1}{N} (R_a(\text{measured}) - R_a(\text{predicted}))^2 * 100 \quad (6)$$

where N is the number of experiments ($N=15$).

Equations (5) and (6) were used to calculate *PAE* and *PSE* according to the data in Table V, and Table VI presents the results. The R^2 , $R^2(\text{pred})$, and $R^2(\text{Adj})$ of the two models given by (1) and (4) are summarized in this table.

TABLE VI. PARAMETERS OF THE SURFACE ROUGHNESS MODELS

Model	R^2	$R^2(\text{pred})$	$R^2(\text{Adj})$	<i>PAE</i>	<i>PSE</i>
Without transformation (1)	94.55%	12.79%	84.74%	8.79%	1.42%
Using Box-Cox transformation (4)	99.09%	85.42%	97.44%	2.26%	0.18%

According to the data in Table VI, the coefficients R^2 , $R^2(\text{pred})$, and $R^2(\text{Adj})$ of the model using the Box-Cox transformation (4) were higher than those of the model without data transformation (1). On the other hand, both *PAE* and *PSE* of the model using the Box-Cox transformation were smaller than those of the model without data transformation. This shows that the model with the Box-Cox transformation had a higher accuracy than the other model.

IV. CONCLUSION

The construction of a regression model representing the relationship between input and output data is a method usually used in experimental studies in general and in the field of machine building in particular. These regression models are used to predict the output parameters that correspond to certain inputs, and the prediction accuracy relies a lot on the accuracy of the regression model. Therefore, the accuracy of the regression model must be improved. This study built a regression model for surface roughness in 080A67 steel hard turning, using the Box-Cox transformation. Accordingly, the surface roughness model when using the Box-Cox transformation had higher accuracy than the one without data transformation. The improved model, given by (4), provided very high accuracy in surface roughness prediction, as its *PAE* and *PSE* were only 2.26% and 0.18%. In the future, it is necessary to investigate a comparison of the accuracy of surface roughness prediction between the Box-Cox and Johnson transformations.

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Accurate Estimation without Calibration of the Complex Relative Permittivity of Multilayer Dielectric Material based on the Finite Integration Technique

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a simple and effective solution is proposed to accurately estimate the complex relative permittivity of individual layers and multilayers of dielectric material samples from the S-parameters measured by two waveguide cells having equal or different lengths filled with the same vacuum/empty material without having to calibrate before performing experiments. The measurement system is set up by modeling using the Computer Simulation Technology (CST) software. In the modeling, a single layer/multilayer material sample is placed in the X-band rectangular waveguide and it has two ports used for the electromagnetic wave supply and measurement of S-parameters. From the S-parameters measured, the complex relative permittivity of individual layers and the multilayers of the material samples are estimated by the proposed method. The known single-layer and multilayer materials such as Garlock, Bakelite, and Teflon have different dielectric constants and thicknesses. The results show that the complex relative permittivity of the samples matches the measured and calculated values of S-parameters in the frequency range of 8.2GHz to 12.4GHz.

Keywords-complex relative permittivity; multilayer dielectric material; finite integration technique

I. INTRODUCTION

Multilayer dielectric material substrates are used in many practical applications, especially in high-speed circuits, such as the Microwave Integrated Circuits (MICs) [1, 2], Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuits (MMIC) [3-6], and wireless systems applications [7, 8]. The exact knowledge of the individual layers in the multilayer substrate permittivity characterization is of great importance for MIC and MMIC design. The multilayer material is formed by composite materials and has new properties that could not be found in the individual layers. For the measurement of the electric properties over a wide frequency range, the waveguide method is one of the most popular methods to determine the permittivity of multilayer dielectric substrates [9-14]. In the waveguide measurement method, a sample of the composite multilayer substrate is placed in a waveguide and two port S-parameters are measured using a Vector Network Analyzer. This nondestructive method is based on the reflection coefficient and transmission coefficient measurement from which the complex permittivity (ϵ_r) or the permeability (μ_r) of

the materials can be determined. In addition, the sample preparation requirements are minimal, and the electric properties can be measured over a wide frequency range. However, the waveguide method is the same as the free space or transmission line method, which are less accurate due to the unavoidable measurement errors. Although there are calibration standards, such as the Short-Open-Load-Through (SOLT) [15-20], the Through-Reflect-Line (TRL) [21-24], and the multiline TRL [25-28], that should be performed before the experiments, these methods experience their own respective defects, such as the requirement of multi-measurement cells, or the presence of the air gap effect.

This paper proposes a new approach to estimate the complex relative dielectric based on only one measurement of the S-parameters of the sample to eliminate the defects mentioned above by assuming the waveguide cell with the length l is determined to be filled with empty air inside ($\epsilon_r \approx 1.0-j0.0$) as a layer of dielectric material. The proposed method can eliminate the air gap between the waveguide and the surface of the material sample because the air layer in the

waveguide reaching the surface of the sample is considered to be an air dielectric layer.

II. PROPOSED MODEL ANALYSIS

The proposed non-calibrated model to accurately estimate the complex relative permittivity of a multilayer dielectric material based on the finite integration technique is illustrated in Figure 1. In the proposed model, between the two waveguide cells, the dielectric material layers have thickness d with an empty air region with length l . The analytical electromagnetic method [11] is used to determine the S_{11} and S_{21} parameters of the multilayer dielectric material sample placed in the two ports of the rectangular waveguide as shown in Figure 1. In Figure 1, the two waveguide cells are filled with the same vacuum/empty material and are defined as layer#1 and layer#N with parameters $(\epsilon_{t0}, \mu_{t0})$, and the multilayer substrate consists of layer#2 to layer#N-1, where the m^{th} layer has parameters $(\epsilon_{tm}, \mu_{tm})$, with $N >= 3$. They are located between the transverse planes at $z = z_{n-1}$ and $z = z_n$.

Fig. 1. Geometry of the multilayer dielectric material sample placed in the two ports of the rectangular waveguide for the estimation of S_{11} and S_{21} .

A. Calculating Procedure of the S_{11} and S_{21} Parameters

To determine the S_{11} and S_{21} components of 2-port parameters, it is assumed that the TE₁₀ mode of unit amplitude is incident on the interface at $z = 0$ from the region $z \leq 0$. If $E_{t0}, E_{t1}, E_{t2}, \dots, E_{tm}$ are the transverse electric fields on the interfaces at $z = z_0 = 0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n$, respectively, then the transverse electric fields in the various regions of the waveguide are obtained as:

1) For $z \leq 0$:

$$\vec{E}_0 = -2j\vec{e}_0 \sin(\beta_0^0 z) + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\iint_{z=0} \vec{E}_{t0} * \vec{e}_i ds \right) \vec{e}_i e^{j\beta_i^0 z} \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{H}_0 = 2y_0^0 \vec{h}_0 \cos(\beta_0^0 z) - \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\iint_{z=0} \vec{E}_{t0} * \vec{e}_i ds \right) y_i^0 \vec{h}_i e^{j\beta_i^0 z} \quad (2)$$

2) For $z_{n-1} \leq z \leq z_n$:

$$\vec{E}_n = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\vec{E}_{1n} + \vec{E}_{2n}}{\sin(\beta_i^n z_i)} \right) \vec{e}_i \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\vec{E}_{1n} = \sin(\beta_i^n (z_n - z)) \iint_{z=z_{n-1}} \vec{E}_{t(n-1)} * \vec{e}_i ds$$

$$\vec{E}_{2n} = \sin(\beta_i^n (z - z_{n-1})) \iint_{z=z_n} \vec{E}_m * \vec{e}_i ds$$

$$\vec{H}_n = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\vec{H}_{1n} - \vec{H}_{2n}}{j \sin(\beta_i^n \Delta)} \right) y_i^n \vec{h}_i \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\vec{H}_{1n} = \cos(\beta_i^n (z_n - z)) \iint_{z=z_{n-1}} \vec{E}_{t(n-1)} * \vec{e}_i ds$$

$$\vec{H}_{2n} = \cos(\beta_i^n (z - z_{n-1})) \iint_{z=z_n} \vec{E}_m * \vec{e}_i ds$$

3) For $z \geq z_n$:

$$\vec{E}_{n+1} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\iint_{z=z_n} \vec{E}_m * \vec{e}_i ds \right) \vec{e}_i e^{j\beta_i^{n+1} (z_n - z)} \quad (5)$$

$$\vec{H}_{n+1} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\iint_{z=z_n} \vec{E}_m * \vec{e}_i ds \right) y_i^{n+1} \vec{h}_i e^{j\beta_i^{n+1} (z_n - z)} \quad (6)$$

4) For $z = 0$,

$$2y_0^0 \vec{h}_0 = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left[\left[y_i^0 + y_i^1 \frac{\cos(\beta_i^1 \Delta_1)}{j \sin(\beta_i^1 \Delta_1)} \right] \iint_{z=z_{n-1}} \vec{E}_{t0} * \vec{e}_i ds \right] \vec{h}_i - \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{y_i^1}{j \sin(\beta_i^1 \Delta_1)} \iint_{z=z_n} \vec{E}_{t1} * \vec{e}_i ds \right] \vec{h}_i \quad (7)$$

5) For $z = z_n$:

$$0 = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{y_i^n \vec{h}_i}{j \sin(\beta_i^n \Delta_n)} \iint_{z=z_{n-1}} \vec{E}_{t(n-1)} * \vec{e}_i ds + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \vec{h}_i \left(y_i^n \frac{\cos(\beta_i^n \Delta_n)}{j \sin(\beta_i^n \Delta_n)} + y_i^{n+1} \frac{\cos(\beta_i^{n+1} \Delta_{n+1})}{j \sin(\beta_i^{n+1} \Delta_{n+1})} \right) \times \iint_{z=z_n} \vec{E}_m * \vec{e}_i ds + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{-y_i^{n+1} \vec{h}_i}{j \sin(\beta_i^{n+1} \Delta_{n+1})} \iint_{z=z_{n+1}} \vec{E}_{t(n+1)} * \vec{e}_i ds \quad (8)$$

6) For the interface located at $z = z_N$:

$$0 = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{y_i^N \vec{h}_i}{j \sin(\beta_i^N \Delta_N)} \iint_{z=z_{n-1}} \vec{E}_{t(N-1)} * \vec{e}_i ds + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \vec{h}_i \left(y_i^N \frac{\cos(\beta_i^N \Delta_N)}{j \sin(\beta_i^N \Delta_N)} + y_i^{N+1} \right) \times \iint_{z=z_n} \vec{E}_{tN} * \vec{e}_i ds \quad (9)$$

The obtained transverse electric fields over the interfaces are:

$$\vec{E}_{i0} = \sum_{j=0}^{J_0} T_{0j} \vec{e}_j, \vec{E}_{r1} = \sum_{J=0}^{J_1} T_{1J} \vec{e}_J, \quad (10)$$

$$\vec{E}_{in} = \sum_{J=0}^{J_n} T_{nJ} \vec{e}_J, \dots, \vec{E}_{iN} = \sum_{J=0}^{J_N} T_{NJ} \vec{e}_J$$

where $T_{0,J}, T_{1,J}, \dots, T_{N,J}$ are the complex unknown coefficients. Using the Galerkin's procedure, the complex amplitudes $T_{0j}, J = 1, 2, 3, \dots, J_0, T_{1j}, J = 1, 2, 3, \dots, J_1, T_{Nj}, J = 1, 2, 3, \dots, J_N$ are all zero due to the orthogonal nature of vector modal functions. The solution of $(N + 1)$ gives an estimate of the complex amplitudes $T_{00}, T_{10}, T_{20}, T_{N0}$ from which S_{11} and S_{12} are determined as:

$$S_{11} = T_{00} - 1 \text{ and } S_{21} = T_{N0} e^{j\beta_0^0 z_N} \quad (11)$$

B. Calculation Procedure of S_{22} and S_{12} Parameters

The S_{22} and S_{12} parameters can be determined by following the procedure used for the estimation of S_{11} and S_{21} , and reverse the locations of the layers as illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Geometry of the multilayer dielectric material sample placed in the two ports of the rectangular waveguide for the estimation of S_{22} and S_{12} .

III. COMPLEX PERMITTIVITY ESTIMATION RESULTS

A. Estimation of S-Parameters

In this section, the properties of the individual layers of the dielectric material and of the empty layers are assumed to be known, the S-parameters for various material layers are computed from the theory as a functions frequency and are compared with the simulated S-parameters. The S-parameter simulations of both proposed models in Figures 1 and 2 were performed using the commercial 3-D full electromagnetic simulation software CST Microwave Studio. Figure 3 is based on the finite integration technique.

Fig. 3. Material layers with thickness d between two identical waveguide cells with an empty air region between them.

In Figure 3, the thickness d of the dielectric samples is assumed to be known, whereas the sample is placed between two identical waveguide cells with length $l = 15\text{mm}$ and the empty air region with electric properties $\epsilon_r = 1.0$.

B. Empty - Garlock - Empty

In this case, a single Garlock layer with thickness $d = 1.7\text{mm}$ and $\epsilon_r = 7.5 - j0.001$ is shown in Figure 4(a). The simulation results and the calculation of the S-parameters of the sample are shown in Figure 4(b)-(c). The results show that the simulated and calculated values of the S-parameters are almost similar in the frequency range from 8.2GHz to 12.4GHz.

Fig. 4. (a) Garlock layer with $d = 1.7\text{mm}$ between two identical waveguide cells with an empty air region between them with length $l = 15\text{mm}$, (b) real and (c) imaginary part of the simulated and calculated S-parameters of the Empty - Garlock - Empty layers.

C. Empty - Bakelite - Teflon - Empty

The considered composite sample consists of Bakelite and Teflon layers. The composite slab is formed by placing the Bakelite layer with $d_1 = 3.3\text{mm}$, $\epsilon_r = 3.76 - j0.001$ and the Teflon layer with $d_2 = 6.35\text{mm}$, $\epsilon_r = 2.03 - j0.001$ shown in Figure 5(a). The simulation and calculation results of the S-parameters of the sample are shown in Figure 5(b)-(c). The results show that the S-parameters simulated and calculated values agree well in the frequency range of 8.2GHz to 12.4GHz.

Fig. 5. (a) Bakelite and Teflon layers with thickness $d_1 = 3.3\text{mm}$ and $d_2 = 6.35\text{mm}$ between two identical waveguide cells with an empty air region of length $l = 15\text{mm}$, (b) real and (c) imaginary parts of the simulated and calculated S-parameters of Empty - Bakelite - Teflon - Empty dielectric layers.

D. Empty - Garlock - Bakelite - Teflon - Empty:

The composite sample considered consists of Garlock, Bakelite, and Teflon layers. The composite slab is formed by placing the Garlock layer with $d_1 = 1.7\text{mm}$, $\epsilon_r = 7.5 - j0.001$, the Bakelite layer with $d_2 = 3.3\text{mm}$, $\epsilon_r = 3.76 - j0.001$, and the Teflon layer with $d_3 = 6.35\text{mm}$, $\epsilon_r = 2.03 - j0.001$ shown in Figure 6(a). The simulation and calculation results of the S-parameters of the sample are shown in Figure 6(b)-(c). The results show that the simulated and calculated values are in excellent agreement in the frequency range of 8.2GHz to 12.4GHz.

E. Estimation of Complex Permittivity

In this section, the simulated and calculated S-parameters of dielectric material samples, consisting of single or multilayer samples are used to estimate the complex permittivity based on the objective function and the MATLAB code from [11]. The results of the complex relative permittivity estimation of single-layer dielectric (Garlock), two-layer composite dielectric (Bakelite - Teflon), and three-layer composite dielectric (Garlock - Bakelite - Teflon) are shown in Figure 7, 8, and 9, respectively.

Fig. 6. (a) Garlock, Bakelite and Teflon layers with thickness $d_1 = 1.7\text{mm}$, $d_2 = 3.3\text{mm}$ and $d_3 = 6.35\text{mm}$ between two identical waveguide cells with an empty air region with length $l = 15\text{mm}$, (b) real and parts of the simulated and calculated S-parameters of Empty - Garlock - Bakelite - Teflon - Empty dielectric layers.

Fig. 7. Relative permittivity (real and imaginary) of Garlock material estimated using simulated and calculated S-parameters.

Fig. 8. Relative permittivity (real and imaginary) of Bakelite - Teflon material estimated using simulated and calculated S-parameters.

Fig. 9. Relative permittivity (real and imaginary) of Garlock - Bakelite - Teflon material estimated using simulated and calculated S-parameters.

Fig. 10. The root mean square error of the complex relative permittivity between calculation and simulation.

The estimated results in Figures 7-10 show that that the error in the complex relative dielectric estimation from S-parameters simulated by the proposed waveguide calibration technique is extremely small or negligible in the frequency range of 8.2GHz to 12.4GHz.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this paper, a solution to eliminate the free space of the waveguide based on an improved measurement model and estimation algorithm is proposed. The novelty of the proposed model in comparison with the model in [11] is that there is no need to calibrate the waveguide when making the actual measurements because, in this study, the free space inside the waveguide is considered a layer of the dielectric material. However, the simulation test results show that the correctness of this solution is very satisfactory. In the future, we will continue to test this proposal by experimental measurements.

V. CONCLUSION

A simple and effective solution to estimate the complex relative permittivity of single and multi-layered dielectric material samples using waveguide measurements is proposed in this paper. The proposed system consists of modeling the S-parameters measurement using CST software combined with MATLAB. This estimation method is verified based on the complex relative permittivity estimation in the 8.2-12.4GHz frequency range of the reference composite samples Garlock, Bakelite, and Teflon, with known thicknesses. The results show that the simulated and ideal values of the complex relative permittivity of the samples presented an excellent agreement in the entire X-band without having to calibrate the waveguide cell before performing the experiments. The proposed method eliminates the effects of systematic errors of the calibrated

experiment setup and thus can afford high measurement accuracy. Therefore, the proposed method is great for accurately estimating the complex relative permittivity of single- and multi-layered dielectric material samples.

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Analysis of Electromagnetic Parameters of Hybrid Externally Excited Synchronous Motors for Electric Vehicle Applications

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents two different approaches to improve the electromagnetic torque and output power of the hybrid Externally Excited Synchronous Motor (EESM) applied to Electric Vehicles (EVs). An analytical approach is first considered to define the main parameters of the proposed machine. Based on the obtained results from the analytical model, the hybrid EESM is designed with different rotor shapes and step-skewing magnet segments to reduce the total losses and improve torque ripple. Then, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is applied to compute and simulate electromagnetic parameters, such as the magnetic flux density, mean torque, and output power. The development of these two approaches is validated on an actual EESM machine and the agreement with the theory is shown.

Keywords-hybrid Electrically Excited Synchronous Motor (EESM); electromagnetic torque; output power; analytical method; Finite Element Method (FEM)

I. INTRODUCTION

Hybrid EESMs are widely used in industry and electric vehicles due to their good overload capability, high torque density, and efficiency. However, these electromagnetic parameters depend on the magnet rotor structure [1, 2]. Different approaches in EESM have been considered. Authors in [1] presented the skewing method to minimize the cogging torque and torque ripple. This way, the design is able to maintain the maximum available torque, which can improve the performance of the machine. In [2], a dual-rotor design of Permanent-Magnet (PM) machine was proposed to reduce the cogging torque. Both analytical and experimental results were presented to prove the effectiveness of the proposed design. In [3], an analytic model was proposed for hybrid EESM to

improve and analyze the torque density and magnetic flux density at the air gap. In [4], Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was extended to evaluate the electromagnetic performance of a proposed machine. The obtained results offer several advantages, including a simple and robust structure, high torque density, and low cogging torque. The results are compared with experimental tests and good agreement between simulation and measurement was reported. In [5], the Finite Element Method (FEM) was employed for PM Synchronous Motors (PMSMs) to find the optimal PM structure. Additionally, sub-group optimization and parallel computation were used to reduce the computational load, making the approach more efficient. In [6, 7], the performance of 3 different IPM rotor designs used by major car manufacturers was studied. The results of this study have practical

implications for the development of high-performance traction systems, specifically those used in hybrid electric vehicles.

Although the EESMs have been studied extensively, the minimization of losses (copper and iron) is more complex than that of other 3-phase motors, because the excitation current of the EESM will cause a saturated case in a high speed up to 20000 rpm. This is the reason why the study of the minimization of the losses of EESM drives is still a challenge for researchers and designers.

In this paper, an analytical approach is first considered to define the main parameters of the proposed machine. Based on the obtained results from the analytical model, a hybrid EESM is designed with different rotor shapes and step skewing magnet segments to reduce the total losses and improve torque ripple. Then, FEM is applied to compute and simulate electromagnetic parameters such as the magnetic flux density, mean torque, and output power. The development of this approach will be validated on an actual EESM of continuous rated power of 80kW (with peak power of 150kW and maximum speed of 20000 rpm) to show the agreement with the theory.

II. MODELING OF EESM DESIGN

The topology structure of the EESM design is shown in Figure 1. The topology is built to combine the analytical calculations in MATLAB with the FEM into one program. The process is divided into 3 main parts: analytical calculation, export drawing, and magnetic simulation. The analytical calculation is first computed in MATLAB and the obtained results, a detailed rotor and stator laminations, will be exported to cad files. Finally, they will be coupled to the simulation environment of FEM via the program interface developed by Matlab GUI.

Fig. 1. Topology structure of EESM design.

The topology structure shows the basic sizes (such as rotor and stator diameters, the lengths of rotor, airgap, and stator, and rotor and stator slots) of the proposed machine which need to be defined for the calculation process, i.e. performance specifications, limits of material properties, and temperature rise. However, there are some cases of machine designs already existing in the database. So, the properties of material components should be changed in order to minimize the total losses with technical constraints of the average torque and output power. The geometry parameters of the stator and rotor are calculated by the process shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. The calculation algorithm.

If the rotor diameter D is assumed to be equal to the rotor length L of the EESM, the electromagnetic torque (Nm) can be defined as [16-18]:

$$T = \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot D^2 \cdot L_s \cdot TRV \text{ (Nm)} \tag{1}$$

where L_s is the length of core (m) and the TRV is the volume density (Nm/m³), which can be expressed as [17, 18]:

$$TRV = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{2}} k_{w1} A \cdot B \text{ (Nm/m}^3\text{)} \tag{2}$$

$$A = \frac{2m \cdot N_{ph} I}{\pi D} \text{ (A/m)} \tag{3}$$

Based on the general expression in (1) and in order to compute the electromagnetic torque and the output power at a synchronous speed, the phasor diagram presenting a salient-pole EESM machine with the reactance components X_d and X_q is shown in Figure 3, where X_d and X_q are the d - and q - axis reactances, and I_d and I_q are the d - and q - current components. The terms $I_q X_q$ and $I_d X_d$ are the voltage drops aligned along the d - and q -axes. The diagram is herein only presented for phase A. It is divided into two parts: the electrical voltage and current quantities are on the left side of the phasor diagram, and the magnetic flux linkages are on the right side. Generally, the magnetic flux linkages are usually neglected [12], however it can be considered as a physical reality that rotates in space.

Fig. 3. Phasor diagram of the EESM.

The physical orientation of a flux can be represented using a space vector, which is a mathematical construct that describes the magnitude and the direction of a physical quantity in 3-dimensional space. In the context of electromagnetism, space vectors are often used to represent the orientation of magnetic fields. The electromagnetic torque is computed as [8-11]:

$$T = \frac{mp}{\omega} [EI_d + I_d I_q \omega (L_d - L_q)], \quad (4)$$

where I_d and I_q can be expressed as:

$$I_d = -I \sin \gamma \quad \text{and} \quad I_q = -I \cos \gamma, \quad (5a-b)$$

where E is the electromagnetic force (EMF) and the products $L_d I_d$ and $L_q I_q$ are the d - and q -axis flux-linkages. The wound poles of a traditional PM machine are generally replaced by PMs. The d - axis is the direction of the magnetic flux produced by the rotor, while the q - axis shows the quadrature direction perpendicular to the d - axis. This means that the PMs are located inside the rotor and have different inductive properties along the d - and q - axes. This can result in differences in the permeability along these axes, which can affect the motor performance. In contrast, in an exterior-IPM motor, the PMs are located on the surface of the rotor. The PM-assisted reluctance motors are a motor type that uses both PMs and salient poles to generate torque.

III. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The minimization of the total losses of an EESM is a significant challenge for designers because it requires determination of all system parameters. Additionally, implementing control strategies for an EESM is complex, and it can take a long time to find the minimum loss point due to the additional degree of freedom provided by the excitation current. To address these challenges, a new optimization approach called Copper-Losses Minimization Control (CLMC) has been proposed for the EESM. The goal of this approach is to control the motor so that copper losses are minimal at every operating point. It is important to note that copper losses constitute a significant portion (about 60%) of the total losses of the EESM drive, especially when the motor operates in the optimal control range. By minimizing copper losses in the motor, the efficiency of the EESM drive can be considerably

improved. Thus, copper losses occur in the stator and excitation windings of the EESM and can be modeled through the stator and excitation resistances as follows [12-15]:

$$P_{Cu} = \frac{3}{2} R_s (i_d^2 + i_q^2) + R_f' i_f'^2 \quad (6)$$

where R_s and R_f' are respectively the stator and excitation resistances. These parameters can be expressed via the change of temperature as [14, 15]:

$$R_s(T_1) = R_s(T_0)(1 + \alpha_R(T_1 - T_0)) \quad (7)$$

$$R_f'(T_f) = R_f'(T_0)(1 + \alpha_R(T_1 - T_0)) \quad (8)$$

where α_R is the material temperature coefficient at the reference temperature T_0 . Its value is usually given at 20°C, e.g. for copper conductor $\alpha_R = 0.004041$ (1/K). If the constraints of the stator voltage and current are neglected, the expression of loss minimization becomes [12, 13]:

$$\min_{i_d, i_q, i_f'} P_{Cu}(i_d, i_q, i_f') \quad s. t \quad T_e(i_d, i_q, i_f') = T_{e,ref} \quad (9)$$

It should be noted that the degree of freedom in the excitation current control for the EESM can make the problem of optimal control more challenging compared to loss minimization problems of other 3-phase machines, because the excitation current is not directly tied to the load. One challenge in the optimal control of EESMs is determining the optimal excitation current for a given load condition. This is because the excitation current affects both the electromagnetic torque and the iron and copper losses in the machine. Thus, an optimal control strategy needs to consider both torque and loss components to achieve the desired performance. Another challenge is the non-linear nature of the EESM. The machine response to changes in excitation current and load conditions may not be linear, and this can make it difficult to develop an accurate model for control purposes. Furthermore, the EESM may exhibit hysteresis effects due to the saturation in the magnetic core, which can further complicate the control problem. To overcome these challenges, advanced control techniques such as model predictive control, adaptive control, and neural network-based control may be used. These techniques can help optimize the excitation current for a given load condition, while also compensating for the non-linearities and hysteresis effects of the EESM.

IV. ANALYSIS OF ELECTROMAGNETIC PERFORMANCE

Based on the theory presented above, in this section, a practical EESM of 80kW rated power (with peak power of 150kW and maximum speed of 20000 rpm), applied to an electric car, BYD ATTO 3 model [16], is considered. The main parameters of the proposed machine are given in Table I. The cross section of stator and rotor laminations of the EESM (model BYD ATTO 3) of 150kW-16000 rpm is presented in Figure 4. The distribution of magnetic flux density along the air gap of the hybrid and normal EESM motors is presented in Figure 5. The obtained results show that the value of the magnetic flux density in the hybrid EESM motor is higher than that in the normal EESM motor, due to the flux-concentration

effect of the PM in the hybrid EESM. In the hybrid EESM, the PM is placed on the rotor surface, which causes the magnetic flux to be concentrated in the area around the PM, resulting in a higher magnetic flux density in the air gap compared to the normal EESM, which does not have a PM on the rotor. The higher magnetic flux density in the air gap of the hybrid EESM motor can lead to several benefits. It can increase the electromagnetic torque produced by the motor, resulting in higher performance. Figure 6 shows the torque and speed curves of the hybrid and normal EESM motors. With the imposed current of 10A, there is a difference in the average torque between the hybrid and normal EESM motors. The average torque of the normal EESM has a lower value than that of the EESM when the speed is lower than 7000 rpm.

TABLE I. MAIN PARAMETERS OF THE CONSIDERED CAR

Parameter	Value	Unit
BYD ATTO 3	2020	
Peak power	150	kW
Hairpin winding		
Stator assy weight	23.6	kg
Stator lamination weight	17.98	kg
Copper weight	5.388	kg
Stator assembly	6.36	kg
Copper	27.40	kg
Stator iron	8.30	kg
Cooling system (liquid cooling)		
Voltage	394	volt
Slot number	48	
Pole number	8	
Shaft diameter	60	mm
Rotor outer diameter	138	mm
Stator inner diameter	139.4	mm
Airgap length	0.7	mm
Stator stack length	140	mm
Rotor stack length	141.6	mm
Average stack	140.8	mm

Fig. 4. Cross section of stator and rotor laminations of EESM (BYD ATTO 3 model) of 150kW-16000 rpm.

Fig. 5. Magnetic flux density distribution along the air gap of hybrid and normal EESM motors.

Fig. 6. Comparison of average torque distribution of the two models (hybrid and normal EESM).

In addition to the evarate torque, the output power of the hybrid and normal EESM motor under the full range of speed is presented in Figure 7. The obtained results show that the output power of the hybrid EESM is improved in the higher-speed region, due to the presence of the PM on the rotor surface, which provides additional magnetic flux and improves the motor performance. The higher magnetic flux density in the air gap of the hybrid EESM results in a higher electromagnetic torque, as well as better output power at higher speeds. The detailed comparison of the parameters of hybrid and normal EESM is presented in Table II.

TABLE II. PARAMETER COMPARISON OF NORMAL AND HYBRID EESM MOTORS

Parameters	Hybrid EESM	Normal EESM	Unit
Maximum torque possible (DQ)	233.32	212.51	Nm
Average torque (virtual work)	234.9	211.79	Nm
Average torque (loop torque)	233.41	210.45	Nm
Torque ripple (MsVw)	28.235	7.6187	Nm
Torque ripple (MsVw) [%]	12.028	3.5959	%
Cogging torque ripple (Vw)	2.5773	0	Nm
Electromagnetic power	98327	88748	W
Input power	1.02E+05	92767	W
Output power	97681	88173	W
System efficiency	95.445	95.047	%
Armature DC copper loss	1938	1938	W
Field DC copper loss	2077	2082	W
Damper cage loss	10	10	W
Stator iron loss	541.7	540.8	W
Rotor iron loss	27.09	27.4	W
Wedge loss	7	7	W
Windage loss	7.035	7.035	W
Friction loss	8	8	W
Shaft loss	4.82E-08	5.06E-08	W
Total losses	4591	4595	W

Fig. 7. Power distribution of the two models (hybrid and normal EESM).

V. CONCLUSION

The current paper has analyzed and compared the magnetic flux density, average torque, and output power of two types of electric motors (hybrid and normal EESM) used in electric vehicle applications. One of the significant contributions of the current study is that it highlights the improvement in the magnetic flux density, average torque, and output power of the hybrid EESM motor compared to the normal EESM motor over a wide range of speeds. The improved performance of the hybrid EESM motor is likely caused by its unique design and construction, which combines features of both the PMSM and EESM.

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Classification of Cognitive States using Task-Specific Connectivity Features

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ABSTRACT

Human brain activity maps are produced by functional MRI (fMRI) research that describes the average level of engagement during a specific task of various brain regions. Functional connectivity describes the interrelationship, integrated performance, and organization of these different brain regions. This study investigates functional connectivity to quantify the interactions between different brain regions engaged concurrently in a specific task. The key focus of this study was to introduce and demonstrate task-specific functional connectivity among brain regions using fMRI data and decode cognitive states by proposing a novel classifier using connectivity features. Two connectivity models were considered: a graph-based task-specific functional connectivity and a Granger causality-transfer entropy framework. Connectivity strengths obtained among brain regions were used for cognitive state classification. The parameters of the nodal and global graph analysis from the graph-based connectivity framework were considered, and the transfer entropy values of the causal connectivity model were considered as features for the cognitive state classification. The proposed model achieved an average accuracy of 95% on the StarPlus fMRI dataset and showed an improvement of 5% compared to the existing Tensor-SVD classification algorithm.

Keywords-functional MRI; functional connectivity; nodal analysis; graph analysis; causal connectivity; cognitive state classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Functional connection in neuroscience is the covariation between spatially dispersed brain regions or brain signals. Typically, brain signals are captured using a functional neuroimaging technique, such as electroencephalography (EEG), functional Near Infrared Spectroscopy (fNIRS), functional MRI (fMRI), Magnetoencephalography (MEG), and electrocorticography (ECoG). In general, Functional Connectivity (FC) experiments are conducted under resting state conditions (without any task demands or external stimulation). However, understanding how external stimuli modulate FC has attracted the research interest. During the recent decades, fMRI has been highly successful in establishing functional relations between brain regions. Functional MRI is the most popular method for learning and delineating human brain regions that change their activation level while performing a specific task. The brain imaging modality can reveal information about neural systems that are functionally coupled together for specific stimuli or tasks. Functional neuroimaging can provide deep insight into the neurobiological underpinnings of disabilities. The concept of finding cognitive functions, as referred to by the connectivity networks of brain regions, is crucial in interpreting neuroscientific data [1]. The

FC patterns computed over some time comprise enough details to identify the task the individuals are working on [2]. However, whether task-specific or resting-state available connectivity interactions are two manifestations that arise from the same underlying neural phenomenon is still under debate.

Human cognition generally involves dynamic and complex interactions between dispersed cortex and subcortical areas [3]. The brain at rest is usually represented in a small number of networks compared to the number of functions it performs. Revealing the putative correspondence between specific FC features and different aspects of task performance is very important. The studies on distributed patterns of FC are used to classify or decode cognitive states [4]. Task-based connectivity studies produce different FC patterns for different cognitive tasks.

Researchers have been measuring functional relationships among brain areas using neurophysiological data acquired from neural components. Functional and effective connectivity are the two aspects of functional interactivity [5]. When the actions of two brain components are correlated, they are said to be linked. The impact of one neuronal entity on another is referred to as an effective connection that establishes a causal relationship between the brain areas. FC analysis is a model-

free approach; on the contrary, effective connectivity is a model-based approach [6]. FC is a simple phenomenon observed from correlations and represented in terms of covariance. The key aspects of the covariance are the patterns of correlated activity delimited by pairwise covariances. Modeling human brain networks is an essential step in determining connectivity patterns. In this work, the human brain is shown as a network through graph-based approaches. The model provides a graphical representation in the form of nodes and edges. The causal connectivity among the brain areas is analyzed using a pipeline framework formed by Granger causality and entropy. Machine learning classifiers have been used for the detection and classification of objects in several scientific applications [7-9].

Resting-state neuroimaging studies soon identified a list of canonical FC patterns that are consistently discovered when at rest and FC patterns and task-evoked activation patterns [10]. The correlations between functional time series are used to assess patterns of brain functional connectivity. Traditional correlation techniques can capture FC and provide a relationship between two Regions of Interest (ROIs) while ignoring the interaction between other ROIs. For instance, the second-ordered relations could give a significant understanding of neurological processes associated with brain regions [11]. As a hypergraph's edges may connect any number of ROIs rather than just two, it has been used to specify the high-order interactions between many ROIs (or vertices) [12]. Instead of simply setting each hyperedge's weight to 1, the hypergraph is used to learn adaptively more flexible hyperedge weights, assuming that all ROIs at each time point are seen as a smooth signal on the hypergraph.

A typical FC network for different subjects is represented by a graph-based hypergraph derived from the fMRI time series. The obtained connectivity is further used to classify Alzheimer's disease [13]. Inter-individual variations in resting FC patterns have been linked to various phenotypic qualities, as well as clinical problems (e.g., mental and neurological illnesses), and can be used to predict behavioral performance and identity [14]. Beyond what mechanistic insight they may (or may not) provide on interregional brain interactions and their relation to cognition, FC estimates can be useful, according to the results of [15].

The graph-based method provides more information on topological reconfiguration in response to external stimuli or task modification [16-17]. The framework explains how brain functions and structure are related. Both functional and structural networks have been shown to organize intrinsically when information is transferred and related hub regions are formatted [18-19]. Most FC methods used with BOLD fMRI data are constrained in their ability to provide details on the specific topology of the underlying causal graph, but still, they restrict the range of network topologies that may be considered [20]. Even though resting state FC research has contributed to a deeper grasp of how the brain works in various subjects, it has been limited by the application of approaches that cannot resolve critical motivating difficulties concerning task-specific FC in the context of cognitive task categorization and effective connectivity among the brain areas. This study used graph-

based FC analysis and entropy-based causal connection for connectivity analysis, and the connectivity parameters obtained were used as features to decode cognitive states.

II. PROPOSED TASK-SPECIFIC CONNECTIVITY ANALYSIS FOR COGNITIVE STATE CLASSIFICATION

The study of FC of the human brain has piqued the interest of the scientific community. Defining and comprehending how various brain regions interact requires identifying functional connectivity networks using fMRI data. FC aims to find statistical connections between two or more ROIs. The utility of connectivity analysis is also applied to the classification of fMRI data. The connection characteristics are used to create a classifier to categorize cognitive states. Figure 1 shows the proposed task-specific connectivity analysis framework.

Fig. 1. Proposed connectivity analysis framework for decoding the cognitive states.

The proposed model is a 5 step approach for cognitive state classification. In Step 1, brain regions or ROIS are selected from the fMRI dataset. Since fMRI data comprise a significant number of ROIs, it is often essential to select appropriate ROIs from the pool. Step 2 involves the extraction of the voxel time course. As fMRI data are usually represented in ROIs, each ROI comprises a voxel time course. Since the proposed model operates with time series, the required voxel time course is extracted from each ROI to perform connectivity analysis. Step 3 involves the connectivity analysis over the extracted time series. This step performs the functional and causal connectivity analyses to find the connectivity relation among the ROIs. Connectivity analysis includes the graph-based connectivity analysis and the Granger causality Transfer Entropy (TE) framework. The details of the graph-based and causal connectivity analyses are elaborated below.

A. Graph-based Connectivity Analysis

The behavior of networks is described in terms of nodes and their connections in a graph theory study on fMRI data. In the human brain network, brain areas are nodes and

connections are edges. Histological, functional, or anatomical parcellation schemes can be used to designate the sections of the brain graph nodes. Interactions among the regions are used to define the edges. After pooling the pairwise connections between nodes in the network, the characteristics of a brain graph are assessed to estimate connections at local and global levels. Relationships that are both temporal and functional with other regions are characterized by these qualities. This study investigates the functional connection strengths among the brain areas for task-specific fMRI data. The interconnectedness between ROIs (nodes) would be quantified once the cohorts for each participant and the brain atlas are built. Using brain network analysis, the connection between the ROIs (nodes) is assessed and the statistical correlation between them is measured using graph analysis. This study utilized Pearson's correlation for both individual and group analyses. A weighted undirected graph was used to create a functional connectivity graph and several global and nodal parameters were computed for the study.

B. Task-Specific Connectivity Analysis using Granger-Causality and Transfer Entropy Framework.

Causal connectivity is the comprehension of the causal connection between different brain areas. To conduct task-and disease-specific research, it is assumed that fMRI-based causal connectivity approaches would shed light on these connection differences. The results of a causal connection study show a causal or significant reliance between ROIs. Effective connection explores the causal chain between different brain areas. The co-activation of brain regions is the basis for FC. Understanding the causal connection between various brain areas is referred to as causal connectivity. Effective connection analysis is provided by the Granger Causality (GC) [21] technique using a data-driven methodology. Each ROI is regarded as a variable for the GC analysis when assessing causal connection. A time series T1 impacts T2 if the information from T1's history may be used to anticipate the values of T2's future observations. When this criterion is met, information flows from T1 to T2. A time series-based brain connectivity estimate was carried out to investigate the functional interconnections between the ROIs. In this connection investigation, the primary goal was to estimate the Granger causality-based task-specific causal interactions between the ROIs. TE calculates the causal strength in a given situation. The suggested human brain cognitive connectivity analysis was applied to StarPlus fMRI data and the Granger causality technique was used to assess the influential connections among brain areas.

In Step 4, the feature vectors were formed from the nodal and global parameters of functional connectivity analysis, and TE values were obtained for the Granger causality. The obtained features were treated as attributes for cognitive state classification. In Step 5, a classifier was developed using features extracted in the previous step. Three classifiers, namely Gaussian Naïve Bayes, Support Vector Machine, and KNN classifiers, were built for cognitive state classification. The proposed classification model based on the connectivity features was verified on standard StarPlus fMRI data.

III. STARPLUS FMRI DATA

The suggested approach was confirmed based on the StarPlus fMRI data [22], which provide easily accessible fMRI data for the categorization and study of the human brain's cognitive states. The captured brain volumes are divided into a set of trials in the two-phase experimental design. For each trial, subjects are required to determine if a statement or symbol was followed by a different sentence or symbol and negotiate properly.

The first phase involved displaying one of two sentences to the subject: "The Star is above the Plus" or "The Star is below the Plus." After 4 seconds, this will disappear from the screen and an empty screen will appear. An image stimulus will be shown for 4 seconds following 4 seconds of the screen being blank. The individual is required to touch the button after 4 seconds of visual stimulation to indicate whether or not the statement accurately describes the image. Brain images are captured during the experiment every 0.5 seconds. Throughout the experiment, each participant has a 15-second rest or fixation interval. The experiment is repeated in the second phase, but this time, the picture and phrase stimuli are exchanged. The subjects in the dataset have approximately 5000 voxels marked as 25 ROIs. As reported in the literature, 7 out of 25 ROIs, CALC, LDLPFC, LIPS, LIPL, LOPER, LT, and LTRIA, are used for the classification and analysis of the cognitive behavior of the brain.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Functional brain networks show how the brain's architecture and behavior are related. Functional networks built using fMRI data tailored to a certain activity aid in gaining insight into how multitasking affects brain structure. In [23], the graph-based connectivity model was used to determine the connectivity strengths among the cognitive tasks. The graph-based connectivity model has not been used to build the classifier for cognitive state classification. In [24], the causal connectivity model was used for cognitive state classification, where the model considered 11 ROIs from a similar StarPlus dataset. This study combined both connectivity model parameters as features for the classification of cognitive states. There are several disciplines in which graph theory and GC analysis are useful. Nevertheless, graph theory and GC are new when applied to cognitive fMRI data. For cognitive data, nodal and global parameters are used to evaluate the interconnectedness between ROIs, and TE is used to assess the causal potency of those connections. The StarPlus fMRI dataset voxels are grouped into 25 ROIs. Of these, the 7 most important ROIs were chosen for further study. The ROI level analysis reveals two distinct functional networks for image and sentence tasks, as shown in Figure 2. The connectivity graphs are defined from nodal measurements for each task. Figure 3 shows the correlation matrix for each task (visual and verbal) for the StarPlus fMRI data.

Fig. 2. (a) Obtained FC network for a sentence task, (b) obtained connectivity network for a visual task.

Fig. 3. (a) Acquired binary weighted matrix for the visual task, (b) acquired a binary weighted matrix for the verbal task.

The causal connectivity analysis was conducted using the GC approach, and the corresponding causal strengths were obtained from Transfer Entropy (TE). Although it is used to analyze neuroimage data, the GC-TE framework is unique in the context of task-specific connectivity analysis. Consequently, 6 subjects from the StarPlus fMRI data were subjected to the GC test. An analysis utilizing a Vector Autoregressive Model (VARM) can characterize GC. The model's order was set to 2, meaning the ROI time course will be modeled using the previous two values of the time series data. This study used a classifier based on graph analysis and causal connection characteristics to identify the cognitive states in the StarPlus fMRI data. Voxels selected using a maximum margin criterion based on clustering define the ROI time series. Feature vectors are formed by the concatenation of graph analysis, such as nodal and global parameters, and TE values from causal connectivity analysis. Table I shows the classification accuracy for the SVM, GNB, and KNN classifiers. The classification was carried out in a Leave-One-Out fashion. Table II shows the classification accuracy results for the training-test scheme, where 80% of the data was utilized for training and 20% for testing. The proposed classification framework achieved an average accuracy of 95% for the 6 subjects in the StarPlus fMRI data. These results were compared with those reported in [25] using the tensor Singular Value Decomposition (t-SVD) framework for the classification

of cognitive states. The t-SVD framework achieved a classification accuracy of 90%.

TABLE I. LEAVE ONE OUT CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY (%) FOR STARPLUS FMRI DATA ACROSS THE CLASSIFIERS

S. N.	Subject	SVM (%)	KNN (%)	GNB (%)
1	05710	78	95	84
2	05680	78	96	78
3	05675	82	98	95
4	04847	64	94	80
5	04799	74	92	70
6	04847	76	94	75
Average		75.3	94.8	80.3

TABLE II. TRAINING-TEST SCHEME CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY (%) FOR STARPLUS FMRI DATA ACROSS THE CLASSIFIERS

S. N.	Subject	SVM (%)	KNN (%)	GNB (%)
1	05710	60	98	75
2	05680	75	96	78
3	05675	82	95	94
4	04847	60	93	78
5	04799	75	94	72
6	04847	64	94	76
Average		69.3	95	78.8

V. CONCLUSION

The classification of cognitive states is achieved using connectivity features. The functional connectivity models considered in this work included the graph analysis framework and the Granger causal connectivity analysis framework. The analysis was conducted using functional MRI data having a pair of cognitive states. The ROI connectivity analysis provides insight into the ROI connectivity strengths. This work was identified by a graph analysis method. Data from ROIs' voxel time series were fed into the system, a brain atlas was developed, and both global and nodal factors were considered while calculating connection strengths. In the case of causal connectivity analysis, the Granger causality transfer entropy paradigm was applied to assess the strength of causal connections between ROIs. Connectivity analysis was carried out using the StarPlus fMRI data. The connection of each ROI was evaluated and Granger causal connectivity was used to perform causal or influential connectivity. Nodal and global graph analysis parameters of the graph-based connectivity framework were considered, and the transfer entropy values of the causal connectivity model were considered as features for cognitive state classification. The proposed classification model achieved an average classification accuracy of 95%. The results obtained were compared with the existing tensor SVD-based classification which achieved a 90% classification accuracy. This study used graph-based and causal connectivity analysis parameters for the classification of cognitive states. The proposed framework produced a new classifier with connectivity features as input in the context of decoding brain states.

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Development of a Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to develop a Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System that integrates Thermoelectric Generator (TEG) with a solar PV system. The main focus is given to the development of the hybrid solar and waste heat released from the solar panel by using the TEG system. This hybrid system consists of photovoltaic (PV) cells to absorb the solar energy and the TEG attached to the back of the panel to absorb heat waste and convert it into usable electricity. The PV cell and the TEG are integrated with each other in order to obtain maximum energy and increased system efficiency. The experimental results show that the maximum output voltage produced from the solar PV is 20.37V and the maximum output current generated is 203.72mA. The maximum output voltage obtained from the TEG is 18.92V and the maximum current produced is 189.265mA. This experimental result shows that the maximum voltage and current produced from solar and waste thermal heat from PV panels can be used to charge and to power up portable electronic devices. More efficiency is accomplished by combining the TEG to absorb waste heat loss from the PV cell, thus improving the performance of the PV panel system.

Keywords-solar and waste heat thermal energy harvesting system; thermoelectric generator (TEG); photovoltaic (PV) cell; solar, thermal

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy harvesting is the process by which the energy produced from other sources is derived, collected, and sometimes stored in banks or batteries for future use. Solar energy nowadays is very popular for its promising power production. However, even though its capability in producing a large amount of power is undeniable, the temperature of the panel gradually increases from time to time due to continuous hit by the solar irradiation [1]. While the solar panel is harvesting energy, the high temperature on the surface of the panel leads in performance de-escalation. Many recent research projects have been conducted in renewable energy focused on increasing the chances to harvest, store, and distribute the solar

energy [2]. There are several ways and types of new implementations of solar power that continue to increase as the price of harvesting solar power is reduced. The heat produced during the operation of the electrical equipment will usually be wasted and released to the environment [3]. By an energy harvesting system, a certain amount of heat can be utilized and recycled to convert the energy from the waste heat into electrical energy [4]. The thermoelectric generator (TEG) has been proposed to be intergraded with photovoltaic cell (PV) in a hybrid system [5]. The purpose of this system is to analyze the output and develop a suitable design that improves energy harvesting. TEG devices are widely used in studies of thermal energy development [6]. TEG was designed by applying the concept of Seebeck effect which was described back in 1820

[7]. Thomas Seebeck, who came with the theory, stated that thermal energy could be harvested into direct electrical energy achieved across the thermal difference between two dissimilar metals [8]. TEG is a temperature-dependent device, where bigger thermal gradients possess higher capability to generate electricity [9]. To achieve the desired electrical output, the temperature gradient between the hot and cold sides of the TEG are maintained by heat from PV cells and the cooling part from the flowing coolant in the heat sink [10]. This system is a hybrid system between photovoltaic (PV) and thermoelectric generator (PV/TEG) [11]. When the solar panel is exposed to the sun, it will convert heat into electricity while thermal losses are produced [12]. As the temperature is getting higher, solar efficiency drops by 0.5% per degree. The purpose of applying TEGs is to absorb the excess heat from the panel in conjunction with generating direct electricity [13]. The PV panel gets a source of energy from the solar radiation and the TEG from the backside of the PV panel which is very hot due to heat loss [14]. The heat delivered from the bottom part of the PV module to the hot side of the TEG module can be utilized in the TEG module to produce electricity directly [15]. The Seebeck effect concept defines that, when there is a difference in temperature from each side of the module, electrical energy can be produced. The basic TEG unit consists of p-type and n-type semiconductor elements which are connected electrically in series and thermally in parallel [16].

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

There are several methods for harvesting solar energy such as PV cells, solar thermal, combined systems, thermoelectric devices, and the recent integrated hybrid systems of PV cells and TEG. This research considers developing and designing a Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System that integrates TEG with PV cells. PV cells convert sunlight directly into electricity. When sunlight hits a cell, the energy knocks electrons free of their atoms, allowing them to flow through the material. The block diagram of the Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System shown in Figure 1 is the basic model that defines the structure and operation of the system.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System that integrates TEG with solar PV cells.

A. System Architecture

The system architecture flow consists of the main system components and the system development and implementation

as shown in Figure 2. The system begins with the PV panel that generates electric power by converting the incident light rays from the sun into a flow of electrons [17]. In this system, the direct current electricity produced by solar cells will be used to supply current in an electrical appliance or to recharge a battery [18]. The hot side of the TEG will be placed directly under the PV panel and the cold parts will be directly placed on the heat sink [19]. The bottom part of the TEG is attached with the liquid cooler radiator to create temperature gradient between the hot and cold sides of the TEG [20]. The TEG is connected to the boost converter to increase the output voltage to its optimum value [21]. It is then connected to a USB port charging by a direct current DC USB connector. The PV cell is connected to solar charge control and directly charges the 12V battery. The output can be delivered using a socket that is installed in the control panel. The hybrid PV/TEG system can be used to charge and to power up a notebook, laptop, or any other portable electronic device [22].

Fig. 2. Detailed architecture flow of the Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System.

B. Design and Development

The design concept in this research involved a PV panel, a cooling system, and a solar control panel. The framework is designed to place the solar panel on top with an angle of 15°. The framework has 90cm height and the top and base dimensions are 60cm×40cm. The solar panel is placed on top of the framework and the TEG is placed under the solar panel along with the cooling system to provide temperature difference between the hot and the cold sides. The size of the TEG used is 4cm×4cm. There are 3 TEGs used in this research with the same specifications. The control panel is designed to place the circuit breaker, socket outlet, inverter, terminal block, USB port charging, solar charge controller, and 12V battery. A rechargeable 12V lead-acid battery is used as a power supply which is also recharged by the PV panel. The circuit breaker is used to protect the electrical circuit from any damage caused by excess current from an overload or short circuit. The terminal block is used to connect all the wires. There are 10 terminal blocks used in this study. The solar charge controller is used to supply voltage from the PV panel to the rechargeable lead-acid battery and prevent from overcharges.

Figure 3 shows the block diagram of the Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System. The PV cells' output is directly connected to the solar charge controller to recharge the battery. It will directly be connected to the inverter to convert the direct current to alternating current so that it can be used at the socket outlet to supply power for any electrical appliance. The resulting DC (direct current) electricity is then sent to a power inverter for conversion to AC (alternating current). Figure 4 shows the hardware implementation of the

Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System. Three TEGs connected in series are attached under the PV cells to get the thermal heat and to generate electricity. That heat would be otherwise dissipated [23]. The TEGs are attached by using thermal grease to avoid the presence of any air gaps and to obtain maximum heat transfer [24]. A copper plate is also attached with TEG to increase the heat transfer from the liquid cooler pump. The output from TEG is directly connected to the boost converter to step up the output voltage and is finally connected to the USB charging port. The type of boost converter used is XL6009 (Figures 5-6).

Fig. 3. The overall Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System.

Fig. 4. Hardware implementation of the system.

The Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System is designed to achieve the minimum input voltage from 5V to an optimum output voltage up to 25V which is suitable for the application of small electrical appliances. The liquid cooler radiator which is placed under the solar panel is used to reduce the temperature of the cold side of the TEG and increase the gradient temperature between the hot and cold sides to maximize the output [22]. The design of the liquid cooler radiator consists of a pump, two pipes, and a

radiator. Table I shows all the parts and pieces of equipment used in this research.

Fig. 5. XL6009 boost converter.

Fig. 6. XL6009 module circuit diagram.

TABLE I. SYSTEM COMPONENTS

No.	Component
1	Photovoltaic cells (50W)
2	Thermoelectric generator (TEG)
3	Liquid cooler radiator
4	Boost converter
5	Cooler fan
6	Copper plate
7	Control panel
8	Battery 12V
9	Inverter
10	Terminal block
11	Solar charge controller
12	Circuit breaker
13	Socket outlet
14	USB charging port

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 shows the data collection during experimentation. It shows that the solar panel is capable of generating higher output voltage compared to the TEGs [26]. The output voltage from the TEGs only depends on the temperature of the solar panel to generate electricity. As the solar panel gained higher temperature at 12.05 pm, the voltage of the TEGs increased drastically. At 12.55 pm, the graph shows a decrease in solar voltage but the TEGs were still generating high voltage. This event occurred as the temperature of the solar panel had exceeded the limits and performance degradation took place. The constant line for both TEG and solar panel Voltages in Figure 7 is due to the integration of voltage during this time interval as the TEG voltage is integrated with the solar panel voltage. The full line on the graph shows that this system was able to increase the TEG's voltage generation by using 3 TEGs

connected in series, a voltage booster, and a cooling pump for higher thermal gradient across the TEGs.

Fig. 7. The output voltage of TEGs and PV panel.

Fig. 8. The output current of TEGs and PV panel.

Fig. 9. Temperature of TEGs and solar panel.

Figure 8 shows a similar pattern with Figure 7 as the current increased when the output voltage increased. As expected, the panels generate higher output than TEGs. The constant line shows TEG and panel having similar output current. This happened as the surface temperature of the solar panel increased contributing to the TEGs' efficiency. The highest achieved voltage from the PV cells was 20.37V with current 203.72mA. The highest temperature recorded was 56.43°C as shown in Figure 9 and the power generated is 4.15W. From these data, it can be concluded that the expected output voltage from PV cells of 20V is achieved.

Figures 7-8 show that the highest voltage from 3 TEGs in series is 18.92V and the current is 189.27mA. The highest optimum temperature is 37.29°C and the output power generated is 3.58W. The highest gradient temperature between the cold and hot side of TEGs is 20.87°C. From these data, it can be concluded that the voltage from TEGs is expected to get 12V and the project target output voltage is finally achieved. The gradient temperature between the cold and the hot side of the TEGs shows a very good result, increasing voltage and current output.

IV. CONCLUSION

A Hybrid Solar and Waste Heat Thermal Energy Harvesting System is produced in this study by integrating the thermoelectric devices into PV systems. The overall performance of the hybrid energy harvesting system and the efficiency of the thermal management in the PV solar panel have been improved. The integration of TEGs with the PV panel, utilizing the waste heat, generated greater output voltage from the harvesting system [27, 28]. The thermoelectric cooler is used to remove the waste heat from the PV and increase the temperature difference between the hot and the cold side of the TEGs [29]. The main objective of this research has been achieved and the expected output voltage was produced. The highest recorded voltage from the PV cells is 20.37V and the highest voltage produced from 3 TEGs in series is 18.92V. The contribution of this research is the creation of another renewable energy harvesting system while maintaining the quality and performance of the output voltage and power at low cost.

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Damage Detection in Free–Free Glass Fiber Fabric Composite Beams by measuring Flexural and Longitudinal Vibrations

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the experimental investigation results of the use of the vibration method by impulse excitation of free flexural and longitudinal vibrations of composite materials. The purpose of the study is to establish the sensitivity of the method used for defect detection and localization. To realize the objective, rectangular notch-type defects were simulated at different distances and depths. The influence of the location and depth of the artificial cracks on the dynamic properties of the beams was investigated by measuring the natural frequencies of flexural and longitudinal vibrations. The conducted experiments show a change in the dynamic characteristics of the beam depending on the dimensions and location of the defects.

Keywords-Glass Fiber Composite (GFC); impulse excitation; free–free beam; flexural vibration; longitudinal vibration; natural frequencies; damage detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural frequency-based methods are some of the most studied methods for detecting delamination and cracks in composite structures by determining their modal shapes and natural frequencies [1-6]. Chronological reviews of frequency methods for damage detection in structures were conducted in [1, 3, 6]. The great advantage of using frequency-based methods is that they are easy to implement in practice. The limitations of their use are that in some cases the changes in frequency are very small and may not be registered due to errors or deficiencies in the measuring equipment. Additionally, changes in the mass of the structure under study or measurement temperatures can introduce uncertainty into the measured frequency changes [1]. Frequency analysis of composite materials with defects has been developed by many researchers [9-12] who concluded that the natural frequency of the beam changes in the presence of a defect. Experimental and simulation studies to determine the frequency characteristics and dynamic behavior of composites are published in [12-16, 18]. The effects of fiber orientation, fiber type, measurement method, and matrix materials on the dynamic properties of composites were investigated in [8, 14, 17]. Frequency analysis of composite plates was conducted in [12-14].

The presence of a defect leads to a local reduction in the stiffness of the structure, resulting in changes in the dynamic properties, alteration of the natural frequencies, modal shapes, and an increase in the damping decrement [1-3, 18]. From the reviewed literature, it is seen that a reliable indicator for the

detection of defects or damage obtained in service is the change in resonant frequencies. However, unlike modal shape-based methods, identification of the location of the damage is not easily achieved when using frequency measurements. Many authors have studied different types of cracks [15, 16]. Important factors influencing fracture behavior and mechanisms are fracture depth and length [4, 19].

Impulse excitation is a popular technique for the diagnosis of various materials [20]. In [21], it is shown that the shape of the impactor head is an essential parameter on the low-velocity impact. The damage occurring in the composite plates is illustrated and analyzed for hemispherical and flat head shape hammer [21]. The earliest research on the subject analyzed natural frequencies; however, due to measurement errors and noise, natural frequencies in such mode shapes are not sensitive to structural damage [1, 6, 11]. Other approaches have been developed to investigate and detect cracks in various composite materials by ultrasonic methods [22-24].

In [25], an approximate analytical method for damage detection in free–free axial vibrations was proposed. The method is based on the measurement of axial natural frequencies, which are global parameters and can be easily measured from any point on the structure. In the same work, the variation of the first two natural frequencies was used to identify the crack location and size. Other studies present an analysis of the application of different vibrations for the identification of cracks in metallic materials, but no experimental results are found [26].

The purpose of the current study is to investigate the effect of cracks on the natural frequencies of excited bending and axial vibrations of GFC beams. The first natural frequencies of out-of-plane and in-plane flexural vibrations as well as the longitudinal vibrations are used to characterize a single beam with defects. The influence of the location and depth of artificial cracks is also investigated.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

A glass fiber fabric composite plate with a thickness of 5mm was considered in this study. The plate was manufactured by hot pressing the glass cloth layers, impregnated with thermo-reactive phenolic and epoxy type resins. The obtained glass fiber volume fraction was 50%. A sufficient number of beam-type specimens were cut from the composite slab with dimensions $L=0.25\text{m}$ length, $b=0.025\text{m}$ width and $h=0.005\text{m}$ thickness. The threads of the glass fabric are parallel and respectively perpendicular to the x-axis (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Specimen with an artificial rectangular channel type crack.

To establish the sensitivity of the impulse excitation vibration method for defect detection, rectangular notch type defects were simulated at different distances from the edge of the specimens (x_i), namely on $0.1L$ and $0.2L$, $0.3L$, and $0.5L$. The slits are transverse, located perpendicular to the stacked layers of glazing. The simulated channels have different depths equal to $0.2h$, $0.4h$, $0.6h$, and, in some cases, $0.8h$. A schematic of the samples with the artificial defects is given in Figure 1. A sufficient number of specimens were made and examined to investigate the location of the artificial defects at a fixed defect depth.

B. METHODS

1) Free Flexural Vibrations

According to the Euler-Bernoulli theory, in flexural vibrations of a beam of constant cross section and thickness, there are innumerable natural frequencies, which are determined by:

$$\omega_n = \frac{\pi^2 n^2}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{E J_y(z)}{\rho A}} \tag{1}$$

where A is the cross section of the beam, $J_y(z)$ is the moment of inertia, a characteristic of the cross section, ρ is the density of the material, and E is the modulus of elasticity of the composite material. For $n=1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$ the natural frequencies depend on the initial conditions, i.e. the way the oscillations are excited, as well as on the boundary conditions. At $n = 1$ the beam bends one half wave, at $n = 2$ there are 2 half waves and so on.

For the fundamental frequency realization at first mode ($n=1$), the nodal points are located at $0.224L$ from each end of the beam, with the anti-nodes in the center and at each end. The

first natural frequency of the two free ends of the beam can be written as [27]:

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\frac{22.373}{L^2} \right] \sqrt{\frac{E J_y(z)}{\rho A}} \tag{2}$$

The area of cross-section A is $1.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{m}^2$. The moment of inertia is $J_y = 2.58 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^4$. The density is $\rho = 1823 \text{kg/m}^3$ and the modulus of elasticity is $E = 2.45 \times 10^{10} \text{Pa}$. A schematic of the experimental setup for the free flexural vibration test is given in Figure 2. A pulse excitation in the middle of the specimen was used to excite bending oscillations in the specimen using a rubber mallet with flat shape. A Superlux ECM-999 type microphone located at the edge of the specimen was used to record the mechanical oscillations. A computer, a PC USB 16-bit two-channel sound card 20Hz ~20kHz, and a Real Time Acoustic Analyzer data logger was used for registration, recording, and subsequent signal processing.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the experimental setup for the free flexural vibration mode test: 1 –rubber mallet, 2 – microphone, 3 - real time acoustic analyzer, 4 – computer.

To realize "out-of-plane" bending, in which the direction of displacement is perpendicular to the large plane of the specimen, the diagram of suspension is shown in Figure 3(a). The scheme given in Figure 3(b) is used to excite the in-plane oscillations. The microphone is placed close to the specimen above the anti-node point.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the beam attachment for the excitation of free flexural vibration. (a) out of plane flexure mode, (b) in-plane flexure mode, 1 - impulse point, 2 - microphone point.

2) Free Longitudinal Vibrations

The equation of the motion of Euler-Bernoulli for longitudinal vibration is given by [25, 27]:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \tag{3}$$

where u is the longitudinal displacement of the current section dx of the beam during oscillations and $c^2 = E/\rho$ is the velocity of propagation the longitudinal elastic wave.

Equation (3) is solved by the standard method of separation of variables. The first natural resonant frequency of longitudinal vibrations is obtained by:

$$f = \frac{k}{2L} \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}} \quad (4)$$

where k is a natural integer.

The free longitudinal vibration test setup is shown in Figure 4. Each specimen is held by its center and struck with a plastic hammer at the edge. To analyze the acoustic response of the sample, the microphone was positioned on the opposite side of the sample. Subsequently, the corresponding vibrating sounds were recorded and analyzed by Fourier transform.

Fig. 4. Longitudinal free vibration test setup.

3) Experimental Procedure

Twelve tests were performed on undamaged beams and the same number was conducted on damaged beams. Table I presents the failure scenarios, which include 4 different crack locations and 3 crack depth levels at each location. The following procedure was used for the experiments: The specimen was lightly struck in the center. The test was recorded and repeated 5 times. The readings of the resonant frequency were recorded and the average value was taken. The acoustic signals were recorded and processed by signal processing methods (Fourier transform) to identify the values of the natural frequencies. They were measured for all undamaged free beams in out-of-plane and in-plane flexural and longitudinal vibration modes. A cut was then introduced into each beam at a controlled distance and depth and the natural frequencies were measured. The signals obtained from the defective and intact beams were compared in both time and spectrum. In addition, tests were made for notches in the middle of the beam with a depth of 80% of thickness.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The damage induces a local reduction in stiffness, which determines changes in dynamic behavior. This is reflected by shifting of the natural frequencies. The change of the first resonant frequency in flexural and longitudinal vibrations in the presence of a defect can be noted by the parameter Δf :

$$\Delta f = \frac{|f_{1,0} - f_{1,d}|}{f_{1,0}}, \% \quad (5)$$

where $f_{1,0}$ is the first natural frequency of an intact beam and $f_{1,d}$ is the natural frequency of a beam with a crack.

The results of the experiments for out of plane flexure mode vibrations of GFC beams are presented in Table I. The relative first natural frequency $f_{1,d}/f_{1,0}$ and the relative frequency shift Δf in the defective beams listed in the Table. It can be seen that when the depth of the crack increases, the first resonant frequency changes significantly, especially at depth $a=0.6h$.

TABLE I. RESULTS OF OUT-PLANE FLEXURE MODE VIBRATIONS OF GFC BEAMS

Description of samples	Dimensionless location x/L	Dimensionless depth a/h	$f_{1,d}/f_{1,0}$	$\Delta f, \%$
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.1	0.2	0.998	0.23
Damaged beam	0.1	0.4	0.997	0.31
Damaged beam	0.1	0.6	0.993	0.7
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.2	0.2	0.990	0.96
Damaged beam	0.2	0.4	0.981	1.92
Damaged beam	0.2	0.6	0.952	4.81
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.3	0.2	0.981	1.87
Damaged beam	0.3	0.4	0.990	2.80
Damaged beam	0.3	0.6	0.972	11.22
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.5	0.2	0.972	2.80
Damaged beam	0.5	0.4	0.971	5.61
Damaged beam	0.5	0.6	0.921	13.08

Figures 5 and 6 show the first resonance frequencies obtained during the out-of-plane bending vibrations for intact specimens and for beams with defects located at distances x equal to $0.1L$, $0.2L$, $0.3L$, and $0.5L$ at different crack depths. It can be noticed that the presence of a defect leads to a decrease in the natural frequencies.

Fig. 5. First natural frequency of flexure vibration test for intact and damaged beams. (a) Notches located at $0.1L$ with different depths $0.2h$, $0.4h$, $0.6h$. (b) Notches located at $0.2L$ with different depths $0.2h$, $0.4h$, $0.6h$.

Fig. 6. First natural frequency of flexure vibration test for intact and damaged beams. (a) Notches located at $0.3L$ with different depths $0.2h$, $0.4h$, $0.6h$. (b) Notches located at $0.5L$ with different depths $0.2h$, $0.4h$, $0.6h$.

As the distance to the notch increases, a larger shift of the first resonant frequency is observed. At a defect distance of

25mm, i.e. $x=0.1L$ and a depth of 1mm, the changes in resonance frequency are very small and below 1%. At $x=0.2L$, the frequency shift reaches about 2%. The most significant changes in the first resonant frequency are obtained at a notch in the middle of the composite beams. At a crack depth of 3mm, the frequency shift reaches 14%. Additionally, a beam with a depth $a=0.8h$ was investigated. The results show a relative change of about 64%. The results of the in-plane flexure tests are shown in Table II and Figure 7.

Fig. 7. First resonance frequency for in-plane flexure vibration. (a) Defect location $x/L=0.3$, defect depths $a/h = 0.2, 0.4,$ and 0.6 . (b) Defect location $x/L=0.5$, defect depths $a/h = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6,$ and 0.8 .

The relative shift of the first resonant frequency is not noticeable at defect location $x/L= 0.1$. As the x/L parameter increases, the frequency decreases and reaches 6% for the deepest crack. Figure 7 shows the frequency characteristics for slits at distances $x=0.3L$ and $0.5L$.

TABLE II. RESULTS OF IN-PLANE FLEXURE MODE VIBRATIONS OF GFC BEAMS

Description of samples	Dimensionless location x/L	Dimensionless depth a/h	$f_{1,d}/f_{1,0}$	$\Delta f, \%$
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.1	0.2	0.999	0.069
Damaged beam	0.1	0.4	0.998	0.188
Damaged beam	0.1	0.6	0.996	0.390
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.2	0.2	0.998	0.205
Damaged beam	0.2	0.4	0.992	0.820
Damaged beam	0.2	0.6	0.988	1.230
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.3	0.2	0.998	0.206
Damaged beam	0.3	0.4	0.990	1.029
Damaged beam	0.3	0.6	0.959	4.116
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.5	0.2	0.992	0.793
Damaged beam	0.5	0.4	0.976	2.381
Damaged beam	0.5	0.6	0.940	5.952

The results of the longitudinal vibration mode tests are shown in Table III and Figure 8. The frequency changes for dimensionless damage location equal to 0.5 and dimensionless depths of 0.6 and 0.8 are about 11% and 26%. If the impulse impact energy is evaluated, it can be concluded that at such small impulse energy the stresses and strains are very small. For this reason, a significant reduction in resonance frequency

is recorded when the material thickness at the defect site is at least 5 times smaller than the specimen thickness.

Fig. 8. First resonance frequencies of longitudinal tests. (a) $x/L=0.3$ and defect depths $0.2h, 0.4h,$ and $0.6h$. (b) $x/L=0.5$ and defect depths $0.2h, 0.4h, 0.6h,$ and $0.8h$.

TABLE III. RESULTS OF LONGITUDINAL VIBRATION TESTS OF GFC BEAMS

Description of samples	Dimensionless location x/L	Dimensionless depth a/h	$f_{1,d}/f_{1,0}$	$\Delta f, \%$
Intact beam	0	0	1	0
Damaged beam	0.1	0.2	1	0.005
Damaged beam	0.1	0.4	1	0.040
Damaged beam	0.1	0.6	0.99	0.079
Intact beam	0	0	1	1
Damaged beam	0.2	0.2	0.998	0.237
Damaged beam	0.2	0.4	0.992	0.513
Damaged beam	0.2	0.6	0.988	0.908
Intact beam	0	0	1	1
Damaged beam	0.3	0.2	0.996	0.395
Damaged beam	0.3	0.4	0.988	1.202
Damaged beam	0.3	0.6	0.942	5.757
Intact beam	0	0	1	1
Damaged beam	0.5	0.2	0.984	1.641
Damaged beam	0.5	0.4	0.961	3.886
Damaged beam	0.5	0.6	0.890	10.978

Another phenomenon that is evident in the frequency response function of damaged beams is the appearance of double peaks as shown in Figure 9. Double peaks indicate two resonances that are close. This phenomenon is called "breathing" [28]. It shows up as an irregular "broken peak" on the frequency response. Breathing causes variations in local stiffness which is time, frequency, and amplitude-dependent.

Fig. 9. The "broken peak" phenomenon in frequency response function.

Figure 10 presents the effect of defect position and depth on the resonance frequency for flexure and longitudinal vibrations. Maximum values of the Δf are obtained at the deepest crack ($a=0.6h$), located at a distance of $x=0.5L$. The frequency shifts are 13%, 6%, and 11% for the out-of-plane, in-plane and longitudinal mode vibrations, respectively.

Fig. 10. Effect of defect location on frequency shift: (a) out-of-plane flexure mode, (b) in-plane flexure mode, (c) longitudinal mode.

IV. DISCUSSION

The effect of the crack on the resonant frequency is revealed differently in the oscillation modes and depends on the attachment of the beam as well as the shape, location, and depth of the crack. For transverse cracks with a specific beam location, increasing depth leads to a decrease in frequency. A crack of a certain depth and width causes different frequency changes in the experimental modes of vibrations, depending on the location of the crack. The current study confirms the opinion expressed in [18] that there are certain places where the damage hardly changes the frequency and they are close to the nodal lines. When the crack does not result in energy loss, the natural frequency in this mode of vibration is not affected. If the crack is located in places where the curvature of the modal shape has maximum values, the largest changes in frequency are obtained. The best crack detection sensitivity is obtained in tests when the crack is in the middle of the beam with out-of-plane flexure oscillations.

The contribution of the current study is the conduction of a new systematic experimental study of the damage resistance of widely used composite materials. The novelty of the investigation is the use of a combination of bending and longitudinal vibration modes that should give more accurate results in the preliminary assessment of defect areas. New data have been obtained for the studied materials, which in principle confirm the studied references [1-4, 15, 18].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the capabilities of the vibration method for identifying defects in glass fiber fabric composite beams have been investigated and verified. The results showed a change in the dynamic performance of the composite beams depending on the size and location of the defects. The shift of the first natural frequency to lower values in the presence of defects was recorded for both flexure and longitudinal vibrations. The cracks in the middle of the specimens show the most significant shift of the frequency peaks in both tests. The relative change of the first resonance frequency was used as the damage parameter. The largest frequency shifts were recorded by out-of-plane flexure, which were about 13%, and the smallest were from in-plane bending vibrations, which were 6%. In all cases, the crack depth significantly changed the structure and dynamic properties of the composite specimens. Unusual nonlinearities in the frequency response functions were found such as broken or doubled asymmetric peaks, which were typical of cracked elements.

Important parameters of the impact events are the peak impact forces and bending, the duration of the impact event, the stresses and strains and the shape of the contact zone [21], which need to be additionally analyzed. Further research should be performed to quantify the defect position by modal shape analysis and to investigate other types of defects and the anisotropy caused by the location of glass layers in composite beams.

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Application of a TID Controller for the LFC of a Multi Area System using HGS Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

A Tilt Integral Derivative (TID) controller is designed in this paper for the Load Frequency Control (LFC) issue of a multi-area interconnected restructured power system. The suggested TID controller settings are fine-tuned using a novel optimization technique known as Hunger Games Search (HGS) algorithm. A multi-area interconnected power system with various generating units is used to test the performance of the proposed TID controller based on HGS. The suggested controller also takes into account system nonlinearities such as Generation Rate Constraints (GRCs) and Governor Dead Band (GDB). The superiority of HGS's optimization over a range of other significant optimization techniques, such as the grey-wolf optimization algorithm, has been confirmed. The simulation results show that the proposed TID controller based on HGS improves system frequency stability significantly under a variety of load perturbation scenarios.

Keywords-load frequency control; TID controller; DISCO participation matrix; Hunger Games Search (HGS), algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

Voltage frequency is one of the most essential power system indicators. Frequency regulation in power systems has recently received much attention. One of the most basic current demands is maintaining a dependable and cost-effective electrical supply while presenting and spreading power as reliably and cost-effectively as possible in contemporary connected equipment. The magnetizing current will continue to rise in strength when the frequency is dropped, even if it is just a little amount. The transformer, especially its center, may get saturated as a result of the increased current flowing through it, and the coil may burn out. Maintaining a balanced electric grid is tough due to the rising demand for power. Throughout the operation of electrical equipment, weight is constantly converted. The frequency of the tool has a negative connection with the mechanical output strain of the generator [1-4]. Three layers of frequency regulation are largely unambiguous: primary, secondary, and tertiary. Before the under/over frequency protection relays are triggered, the primary frequency control loop intercepts the frequency fall. The

governor droop is commonly used for main frequency regulation, resulting in consistently reported errors. The secondary frequency control, also known as Load Frequency Control (LFC) or Automatic Generation Control (AGC), regulates the frequency in power systems with two main goals: (i) maintaining the frequency in a desirable range and (ii) controlling the interchange power through major tie lines between the different control areas. After a severe disruption, the primary responsibility of the tertiary control level is to re-dispatch generating units and auxiliary reserves. Because no interconnected system modification is required, the single-area LFC system's goal is limited to stabilizing operating frequency to the nominal value. To achieve load balance at the local and global levels in a multi-area LFC system, each area's generators must regulate the local load and tie-line power fluctuations from connecting areas. Frequency control is performed by adding the ACE signal to the feedback loop, which not only accounts for variations in frequency and power exchange, but also for the energy and time inaccuracy caused by schedule and device irregularities. Due to the deregulation of the electrical

industry, the incentives and indicators provided by the government to firms for controlling and managing their operations have shifted significantly. Electric utilities, including GENCOs, TRANSCO, and DISCOMs as part of the DISCO tool, have been liberalized as a top-tier job that is now available to anybody interested in working in the business. An Independent System Operator (ISO), which is a huge

corporation, is in charge of keeping track of open market users. In deregulated electric systems, AGC structures will almost definitely continue to be essential, yet, the operations of AGC systems in a vertically integrated agency and those in an unstructured device differ greatly in terms of some methods [5-9].

Fig. 1. Block diagram of a multi area deregulated system.

AGC systems will continue to play a crucial role in the management of out-of-control electric power networks, regardless of the outcome. AGC structures will almost certainly continue to be important in unregulated electric systems, however, the operations of AGC systems in a vertically integrated agency and those in an unstructured device differ significantly in some ways [10-16]. Based on the work of the fundamental elements of conventional algebraic geometric computation are the proportional, integrals, and derivatives, as well as their combinations. PID is the most frequently used LFC manipulation [17-18], in part because of its simplicity, dependability, and wide range of applications. Nonlinear parameters include the Governor Dead Band (GDB) and the Generation Rate Constraint (GRC) that has an impact on the performance of LFCs [19-20]. When confronted with LFC stressful events, many recent responses were supplied that allowed us to improve the dynamic behavior of the system. Different optimization techniques are evaluated in [21-27].

Many researchers were concerned about the overall performance of PID and TID controllers in the LFC when it came to evaluating the controllers' overall performance [28-30].

II. MULTI-AREA DEREGULATED SYSTEM

A. The Traditional Electric Power System Scenario

The traditional electricity market, which includes all generation, transmission, and distribution units, is consolidated under a single utility with total operational control. A single utility firm may directly supply, transmit, and distribute electricity to customers. Utility companies must follow the power charge set by each state's electrical commission. Because a single utility controls all the power, this status is known as a monopoly.

B. The Deregulated Energy System Scenario

Deregulation refers to the process of modifying the laws and regulations of the electric power industry so that customers have a choice of electricity providers. Figure 1 refers to a deregulated energy market that allows for competition among shareholders to purchase and sell electricity and invest in electric power plants and transmission lines. The shareholders of the Generation Company subsequently sell wholesale power to retail firms, who ultimately charge consumers based on the retail electricity estimated price.

C. Disco Participation Matrix

The current AGC system has two areas, each with two-generation stations, namely a thermal power generation unit, and a solar power unit. There are two types of GENCOs and DISCOMs in each area. The entire fractional amount of load dealt by DISCO from a GENCO is represented by the contract participation factor in each element. Because the GENCO must give the needed load to the DISCO regardless of the location or conditions, the sum of the components in each column equals unity in the DISCO Participation Matrix (DPM):

$$DPM = \begin{bmatrix} cpf_{11} & cpf_{12} & cpf_{13} & cpf_{14} \\ cpf_{21} & cpf_{22} & cpf_{23} & cpf_{24} \\ cpf_{31} & cpf_{32} & cpf_{33} & cpf_{34} \\ cpf_{41} & cpf_{42} & cpf_{43} & cpf_{44} \end{bmatrix}$$

III. DESIGN OF CONTROLLERS

The Tilt Integral Derivative (TID) controller is a feedback-type controller, similar to the PID controller and with the same advantages, while also having greater dynamic properties. Both controllers have identical integral and derivative actions, but the proportional action of the PID controller is replaced with a tilt-proportional controller with internal feedback which is shown in Figure 2. The objective function is given by:

$$J = \int_0^{t_{sim}} (\Delta f_i)^2 + (\Delta f_z)^2 + (\Delta P_{tie})^2 dt \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. TID controller block diagram.

IV. HUNGER GAMES SEARCH (HGS) ALGORITHM

HGS was proposed in 2021. The dynamic, fitness-based search technique for new users and decision-makers uses

"Hunger," an animal's fundamental homeostatic drive, as a guiding factor. HGS incorporates the concept of hunger into its feature process. An adaptive weight is built and utilized to simulate the effect of hunger on each search phase in Figure 3. It follows practically all species' computationally logical rules (games), and these competitive activities and games are frequently adaptive and evolutionary in nature, ensuring enhanced chances of survival and food acquisition. The method is more efficient than current optimization approaches due to its dynamic nature, simple structure, and outstanding performance in terms of convergence and acceptable solution quality. The convergence curve of the HGS algorithm is shown in Figure 14.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the HGS algorithm.

1) STEP: 1 Approach Food

$$\overline{X}(t+1) = \begin{cases} \overline{X}(t) \cdot (1 + randn(1)), & r_2 < l \\ W_1 \cdot \overline{X}_b + \overline{R} \cdot W_2 \cdot |\overline{X}_b - \overline{X}(t)|, & r_1 > l, r_2 > E \\ W_1 \cdot \overline{X}_b + \overline{R} \cdot W_2, & r_1 > l, r_3 > E \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where R is the range of [-a, a], r1 and r2 are random numbers in the range of [0,1], randn(1) is a random number satisfying normal distribution, Xb is the location information of a random individual in all the optimal individuals, t is the current

iteration, W_1 and W_2 are the weights of hunger, $X(t)$ is each individual's location, and l is the parameter setting experiment.

The formula for E is:

$$E = \sec h|F(i) - BF| \quad (3)$$

where $i \in 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, $F(i)$ is the fitness value of each individual, and BF is the best fitness value.

$$\bar{R} = 2a \times rand - a \quad (4)$$

where $a = 2 \times (1 - \frac{t}{max_iter})$, $rand$ is a random number in the range of $[0,1]$, and max_iter is the maximum number of iterations. The starvation characteristics of individuals in search are simulated mathematically.

B. STEP: 2 Hunger Role

$$\overline{W}_1(l) = \begin{cases} hungry(i) \times \frac{N \times r_4}{SHungry} & , r_3 < l \\ 1 & , r_3 \geq l \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\overline{W}_2(l) = (1 - e^{-|hungry(i) - SHungry|}) \times r_5$$

where $hungry$ is the hunger of each individual, N is the number of individuals, $SHungry$ is the sum of hunger feelings of all individuals, and r_3, r_4, r_5 are random numbers ranging in $[0,1]$.

$$hungry(i) = \begin{cases} 0 & , AllFitness(i) = BF \\ hungry(i) + H & , AllFitness(i) \neq BF \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $AllFitness(i)$ is the fitness of each individual in the current iteration and H is acquired by:

$$TH = \frac{F(i) - BF}{WF - BF} \times r_6 \times 2 \times (UB - LB) \quad (7)$$

$$H = \begin{cases} LH \times (1 + r) & , TH < LH \\ TH & , TH \geq LH \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Each area consists of one solar system and one thermal system as shown in Figure 4. To evaluate the most recent TID controller, it is important to employ a deregulated electricity system. Nonlinear components, such as GRC and GDB, are assessed in addition to linear components. Steam must be able to circulate through the turbine and condense on the supplied contractions for GRC to work. Water droplets collide with turbine blades due to the presence of condensed steam, causing them to eventually stop operating. A GRC restriction of 0.05% is implemented. In the absence of torque, GDB is better characterized as the pace at which the steam valve characteristic can be swapped. When the GDB is used, a 0.06% restriction is possible.

Fig. 4. The single line diagram of a two-area system.

A. Case A: Pool Co-based Transaction

A pool co-based transaction occurs when a DISCO shares a load with any of the GENCOs in the same area. The area participation factor is 0.5 when the 4 values are the same. Figures 5-7 use different HGS-based and GWO-based controllers, showing the difference in frequency in each area and the power of the tie line. Table I shows that the HGS-based controller performs better for pool co-based transactions than the GWO-based controller.

Fig. 5. Deviation of frequency in area-1 under pool co-based transaction for 1% step load disturbance.

Fig. 6. Deviation of frequency in area-2 under pool co-based transaction for 1% step load disturbance.

Fig. 7. Tie line energy deviation beneath a pool co-based transaction for a 1% step load disturbance.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF OVERSHOOT, UNDERSHOOT, AND SETTLING TIME UNDER POOL CO-BASED TRANSACTIONS

	μ_p (peak overshoot)			μ_u (peak undershoot)			S.T. (settling time)		
	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}
GWO-PID	-	0.42	-	0.6	-	0.22	1.8	2.5	3.4
HGS-PID	-	0.35	-	0.52	-	0.22	1.6	2.2	3.2
GWO-TID	-	-0.28	-	0.5	-	0.21	1.4	1.8	3
HGS-TID	-	-0.18	-	0.42	-	0.21	1.2	1.6	2.8

B. Case B: Bilateral-based Transaction

There is a bilateral transaction that takes place whenever a DISCO shares the load with any of the GENCOs in another region. The values that should be used for the area participation factor for the 4 values that are considered uneven are 0.75, 0.25, 0.5, and 0.5. Figures 8-10, employing various HGS-based and GWO-based controllers, respectively, depict the deviation of frequency in area-1, area-2, and tie line power. Table II demonstrates that, for bilateral-based transactions, the HGS-based controller performs better than the GWO-based controller.

Fig. 8. Deviation of frequency in area-1 under bilateral-based transaction for 1% step load disturbance

Fig. 9. Deviation of frequency in area-2 under bilateral-based transaction for 1% step load disturbance.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF OVERSHOOT, UNDERSHOOT, AND SETTLING TIME UNDER BILATERAL-BASED TRANSACTIONS

	μ_p (peak overshoot)			μ_u (peak undershoot)			S.T. (settling time)		
	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}
GWO-PID	0.08	0.12	-	0.15	-	0.05	3.2	3.6	3.2
HGS-PID	0.05	0.08	-	0.15	-	0.05	2.8	2.8	3.0
GWO-TID	0.03	0.09	-	0.15	-	0.05	2.4	2.4	2.8
HGS-TID	0.02	0.06	-	0.18	-	0.05	2.2	2.2	2.6

Fig. 10. Deviation of tie line power under bilateral-based transaction for 1% step load disturbance.

C. Case C: Contract Violation

When the DISCO requests more electricity than the agreed-upon value, a contract violation arises. GENCO does not lease out this extra power. A GENCO in the same vicinity as the DISCO should supply this uncontracted power. Let's consider instance 2, which necessitates adding 0.1 p.u. MW of power to a DISCO1. Figures 11-13 which use various HGS-based, and GWO-based controllers, respectively, demonstrate the deviation of frequency in area-1, area-2, and tie line power. Table III demonstrates that, in a contract violation-based transaction, an HGS-based controller performs better than GWO-based controller.

Fig. 11. Deviation of frequency in area-1 under contract violation for 1% step load disturbance.

Fig. 12. Deviation of frequency in area-2 under contract violation for 1% step load disturbance.

Fig. 13. Deviation of tie-line power under contract violation for 1% step load disturbance.

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF OVERSHOOT, UNDERSHOOT, AND SETTLING TIME UNDER CONTRACT VIOLATION BASED TRANSACTIONS

	μ_p (peak overshoot)			μ_u (peak undershoot)			S.T. (settling time)		
	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}	Δf_1	Δf_2	ΔP_{tie}
GWO-PID	0.1	0.17	-	0.24	-	0.09	3.5	3.8	3.2
HGS-PID	0.05	0.16	-	0.24	-	0.09	3.2	2.4	3.0
GWO-TID	0.04	0.15	-	0.22	-	0.08	2.8	1.8	2.8
HGS-TID	0.02	0.12	-	0.22	-	0.08	2.6	1.6	2.6

Furthermore, the SLP values for the reduced inertia case system have been varied from 1 to 2%, 5%, and 10% in areas, 1 and 2. The resultant transient response is shown in Figures 15-17. The plots in frequency and tie-line error are validating the robust nature of the proposed HGS algorithm.

Fig. 14. Convergence curve of the HGS algorithm.

Fig. 15. Frequency deviation in area-1 for different SLP values.

Fig. 16. Frequency deviation in area-2 for different SLP values.

Fig. 17. Tie-line power deviation for different SLP values.

CONCLUSION

The current paper investigates the performance of a TID controller in a deregulated market structure for a variety of transactions and contract breaches. The power system's load demand is a challenging problem to handle since it necessitates the creation of several optimal controllers. The controller's major responsibility is to make sure that the voltage magnitude and frequency are always steady. The DPM strategy was put into practice. According to the comparison of the controllers, the HGS-based TID controller performs better than the GWO-based controllers in terms of settling time, overshoot, and undershoot.

APPENDIX

The system parameters are given below:

$f=50\text{Hz}$, $Tg1=0.08\text{s}$, $Tt1=0.3\text{s}$, $Tt=3\text{s}$, $Tg=1.0\text{s}$, $Tr1=10\text{s}$, $Kr1=0.5$, $Kp=120\text{Hz pu MW/rad}$, $H=5\text{s}$, $D=8.33 \times 10^{-3}\text{pu MW/Hz}$, $Tp=20\text{s}$, $T=0.086$, $Ri=2.4\text{Hz/pu MW}$, $Bi=0.425\text{pu MW/Hz}$, $Kst=1.8$, $Tst=1.8\text{s}$.

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FPGA Implementation of a Resource Efficient Vedic Multiplier using SPST Adders

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the requirement for very high-speed operations in processors constantly increases. Multiplication is a crucial operation in high power-consuming processes such as image and signal processing. The main characteristics of a multiplier are good accuracy, speed, reduction in area, and little power consumption. Speed plays a major role in multiplication operations, and an increase in speed can be obtained by reducing the number of steps involved in the computation process. Since a multiplier has the largest delay among the basic blocks in a digital system, the critical path is determined by it. Furthermore, the multiplier consumes more area and dissipates more power. Hence, designing multipliers that offer high speed, lower power consumption, less area, or a combination of them is of prime concern. Hence, an attempt is made in this paper to achieve the above design metrics using a Spurious Power Suppression Technique (SPST) adder. A resource-efficient SPST-based Vedic multiplier is developed and implemented using Artix 7 FPGA and is finally compared with the ripple carry adder-based Vedic multiplier.

Keywords-vedic multiplier; Urdhva Triyakbhyam; Spurious Power Suppression Technique (SPST); Verilog; Artix7

I. INTRODUCTION

The operation of multiplication plays a pivotal role in many operations and it is important to be computed fast with great efficiency in Digital Signal Processing (DSP) and Image Processing, where functions like Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) are used. The research to obtain improved multiplier versions and establish new method types for efficacious multiplier architecture is still ongoing. Each multiplier is different in its own way. High performance with a less number of partial products is preferred in a multiplier. Much research has been conducted regarding the ancient Vedic mathematics, which brought many efficacious multipliers, dividers, squaring, and cube architectures. During the last few years, various decimal algorithms have been extended to the binary number system based on the Vedic mathematics [1-4]. Reducing the number of stages in a Vedic multiplication process leads to a great reduction in the propagation delay. The multiplication process is based on Urdhva Tiryagbhyam algorithm/sutra, which belongs to the 16 sutras of Vedic mathematics [5-7]. Generally, most multipliers

consume area, power, and work with little accuracy. Therefore, the design of multipliers which offer high speed, low power consumption, less area, or combinations of all these, is of immense research interest [8-15].

II. VEDIC MULTIPLIER

Indian mathematics has a unique technique of arithmetic computation based on 16 sutras or formulas, which is applicable in many fields. One of the fastest developing fields is DSP. So, there is a need to implement as fast as possible multiplication operation for the digital processing of signals. The Vedic multiplier is mainly based on the vertical and crosswise algorithm of Urdhva Triyakbhyam generating all partial products and sums in a single step. The UT Sutra has been conventionally utilized for the multiplication of decimal numbers in comparatively less time. We can use this to multiply two numbers. The bits on the two extremes of the number are multiplied and the result is added to the previous carry. When there are more digits in each number, all the results are added to the previous carry. The process of this scripture is discussed below with the help of an example.

Let us consider two decimal numbers: 234 and 159.

- Initially, the least significant digits of both numbers are multiplied and the result is 36.
- Next, we have cross-wise multiplication of the first digit of the first number with the second digit of the second number. Another cross-wise multiplication of the first number's second digit with the second number's first digit. Finally, we add those two products.
- Cross-wise multiplication of the first number's least significant digit with the second number's most significant digit and vice-versa. Multiplication of the middle digits gives a total of three products which are finally added.
- Without considering the least significant digits of the two numbers, we perform cross-wise multiplication and addition.
- Vertical multiplication of most significant digits of the two numbers.

For all the steps, with the exception of the first step, each compartment needs to have only one digit. If not, then the carry is forwarded to the initial digits in the previous compartment.

Fig. 1. The 16-bit Vedic multiplier.

The delay of the multiplication is reduced using UT sutra and initially this was used only for decimal number multiplication, although, it can be used for binary numbers. Binary multiplication can be done using this method for 2-bit, 3-bit, and 4-bit numbers, since the PPs and their arithmetic sum are calculated autonomously. Delay is produced due to the existence of the carry from the PPs which is to be added in each next step's partial product. Figure 1 shows the process of 16-bit Vedic multiplication. In the first stage, 8x8 Vedic multipliers are used. The obtained products are added according to the Vedic multiplication discussed above. Finally, the 32-bit result is obtained.

III. SPST ADDER

An adder, either a Full Adder (FA) or a Half Adder (HA), is a combinational circuit used to calculate the sum of three or two inputs. In a parallel adder, FAs are connected in series to produce an n-bit adder. In each section, the sum and carry are not computer until the input carry arises, slowing down the summation process. To avoid delay issues, the Carry Look Ahead (CLA) adder has been suggested. To improve the speed of CLA, Spurious Power Suppression Technique (SPST) is applied. This can reduce the dissipated power of combinational VLSI for DSP purposes. The SPST consists of two parts, the most significant part and the least significant part. It disables the MSP when it doesn't modify the results saving power [16-20]. The SPST adder/subtractor is classified into two parts, MSP and LSP. The MSP of the first adder/ subtractor is modified to include:

- detection unit,
- data controlling unit,
- sign extension unit, and
- circuits for calculating Cin and Cout signals.

In SPST, the detection unit is used to detect if a transition in data bits of the result will occur in the circuits (adders or multipliers) or not. The detection logic unit works as follows:

- When the detection unit disables the MSP, then the output of the MSP are re-compensated so that the time saved for skipping computations will cancel out the delay of the detection logic circuit.
- When it enables the MSP, then the MSP will wait for acknowledgement of the detection unit to enable the data latches. So, the delay of the detection unit will contribute to the entire circuit's delay.
- When the detection unit stays in its decision irrespective enabling or disabling of the MSP, then the delay of detection unit is insignificant.

There is a data asserting control unit realized by using the registers to further remove any unwanted spurious signals of the arithmetic unit whenever the latched portion has been turned on. This asserting control obviously brings power reduction [16-20].

The 16-bit addition using the SPST process is interpreted in 5 cases. The first case is the transient state, in which spurious transitions of carry signals occur in MSP although the result of the MSP is not altered. The second and third cases illustrate the situation of a negative operand adding to a positive operand without and with carry from LSP, respectively. The fourth and fifth cases demonstrate the condition of two negative operand additions without and with carry-in from LSP, respectively. In all the above cases, the results of the MSP are predictable, so the computations in the MSP aren't required and can be neglected. Removing those spurious computations will not only save the power consumed by the SPST adder or subtractor but also reduce the noises which are going to affect the subsequent arithmetic circuits.

IV. THE PROPOSED MULTIPLIER

Our main goal is to differentiate the performances of the Vedic multiplier with and without using the SPST adder by comparing both models. To improve the Vedic multiplier's efficiency, the SPST adder is introduced at intermediate stages to add the sub module outputs. Finally, performance analysis is conducted with respect to area and power.

To develop 16-bit Vedic multiplication, four 8x8 multipliers are required. In the second stage, 16-bit SPST adders are used to add intermediate partial products.

Fig. 2. 16-bit Vedic multiplier using SPST adders.

Both multipliers models were simulated and synthesized using Xilinx Vivado tool. Two 16-bit Vedic multipliers, one with RCA and one with SPST, were programmed using HDL and their performance was compared with respect to area and power.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

All the blocks were programmed and simulated using Xilinx Vivado tool. After verification, the proposed multiplier was implemented on Nexys 4 DDR Artix 7 FPGA. The synthesis and simulation results of VM using SPST with respect to main modules and sub modules are shown in Figures 3 to 10.

Fig. 3. RTL schematic of a Vedic multiplier using SPST blocks.

Fig. 4. Vedic multiplier using RCA simulation report.

Figure 2 represents the RTL diagram of the Vedic multiplier which utilizes four 8-bit Vedic multipliers and three SPST adders to obtain the results. Figure 3 gives the simulation output for two 16-bit numbers. From the synthesized results it is concluded that the Vedic multiplier using RCA logic requires 402 slice LUTs and 120 slice registers as shown in Figure 5. Further, it is noticed that it requires 33.77W on-chip power which includes 32.586W dynamic power as shown in Figure 6.

. Slice Logic

Site Type	Used	Fixed	Available	Util%
Slice LUTs*	402	0	63400	0.63
LUT as Logic	402	0	63400	0.63
LUT as Memory	0	0	19000	0.00
Slice Registers	120	0	126800	0.09
Register as Flip Flop	120	0	126800	0.09
Register as Latch	0	0	126800	0.00
F7 Muxes	0	0	31700	0.00
F8 Muxes	0	0	15850	0.00

Fig. 5. Vedic multiplier using RCA implementation report.

Fig. 6. Power report of the 16-bit Vedic multiplier using RCA.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Vedic multiplier	Appearance		
	Slice LUTs	Slice registers	Power(W)
Using RCA	402	120	33.54
Using SPST	361	0	25.49

From the synthesized results it is concluded that the Vedic multiplier using SPST logic (Figure 7) requires 361 slice LUTs

(Figure 8) and 25.49W on-chip power which includes 24.708W dynamic power as shown in Figure 9. The result comparison can be seen in Table I. It can be seen that the SPST-based Vedic multiplier provides better performance in terms of LUTs and delay.

Fig. 7. Vedic multiplier using SPST simulation report.

. Slice Logic

Site Type	Used	Fixed	Available	Util1%
Slice LUTs*	361	0	63400	0.57
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Slice Registers	0	0	126800	0.00
Register as Flip Flop	0	0	126800	0.00
Register as Latch	0	0	126800	0.00
F7 Muxes	0	0	31700	0.00
F8 Muxes	0	0	15850	0.00

Fig. 8. Vedic multiplier using SPST implementation report.

Fig. 9. Vedic multiplier using SPST power report.

VI. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION

The external hardware used for implementation consists of:

- ADC kit
- Slide switches and LEDs
- Jumper wires, 3.3V fixed voltage source (from RPS)
- Nexys 4 DDR

After simulation, the proposed Vedic multiplier using the SPST model was dumped into the FPGA to verify the response. In this work, the proposed model was implemented on Nexys 4 DDR Artix7 FPGA with the help of Xilinx Vivado. For the implementation, the first task is to map the original input and

output ports with board I/Os by generating a constraint file. Next, the program can be dumped to the FPGA kit to verify the simulation results practically.

Fig. 10. Implementation of the Vedic multiplier with SPST in Artix7.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a 16-bit Vedic multiplier was designed using SPST adders and was programmed in Verilog. The proposed Vedic multiplier was synthesized in the Artix7 FPGA family using the Xilinx tool and its response in terms of area and delay was observed. This work is mainly focused on developing efficient Vedic multipliers using SPST adders and its performance was compared with the one of the ripple carry adder-based Vedic multiplier. From the implementation results, it is observed that the performance of the Vedic multiplier using SPST is better by 10% in respect of area, while power dissipation is improved by 24% compared to that of Vedic using the RCA adder. After the validation, the SPST-based Vedic multiplier was successfully implemented on Nexys 4 DDR Artix FPGA.

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The Effect of Pilot Reuse Factor on Massive MIMO Spectral Efficiency

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ABSTRACT

Due to their much increased spatial resolution and array gain, large-scale antenna arrays have the potential to significantly enhance the spectral efficiency of wireless systems. Recent research in the area of massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) antennas shows that user channels are enhanced as the number of antennas at the Base Stations (BSs) rises, allowing achieving high signal improvement with minimum inter-user interference. The combined effects of the pilot reuse factor and the BS number of antennas on average overall spectral efficiency in huge MIMO antennas will be investigated. To examine the SE of these receivers, several channel estimators will be utilized, including LMMSE, ZF, and MR methods. Theoretically, BS could offer a substantially higher average total SE if it had more antennas.

Keywords-massive MIMO; L-MMSE; spectral efficiency; base station; pilot reuse factor; zero forcing; machine to machine; channel state information

I. INTRODUCTION

The amount of mobile data traffic worldwide in 2017 was 12.6 times greater than what it was in 2012. The entire amount of mobile traffic has grown by a factor of 10 between 2019 and 2022 [1], and this rise continues today. Therefore, the cellular infrastructure of the future must be ready to serve new uses and, specifically, to satisfy the users' needs and meet the current wireless communication standards. Particularly, the use of smart devices and machine-to-machine (M2M) communications systems has dramatically increased mobile data traffic over the past ten years across most applications and industries. The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) has recently predicted that mobile traffic worldwide will grow by a factor of 660 between 2010 and 2030. Every decade, mobile technologies undergo a dramatic development and the demand for wireless data is only going to increase. The more data we use, the more we need networks with faster speeds and wider coverage to keep up. Each new technology generation has offered considerable performance improvements. These quick variations are reactions to the needed capacity from the significant data increase over the previous decade, mostly from video streaming. The resolution of video streaming capabilities is also rising, and phones supporting 4K video will require a higher data rate per user. Users' watching duration is also rising; watching long TV shows and movies via streaming video is now common. This tendency appears to have no end in sight.

Massive or big-scale Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) technology has emerged as a viable technique for future wireless networks [2]. Despite the fact that massive MIMO demonstrates enormous capacity of supporting a substantial volume of data rate and wireless links, it is not that

easy to implement such a system due to the high cost of hardware and higher consumption of power. Researchers have been investigating energy efficient initiatives to maximize system efficiency in order to establish sustainable and clean wireless systems. Massive MIMO is a combination many innovations that have been combined in order to create a solution that is able to deliver incredible results. What all these technologies have in common is that they are able to significantly improve the performance of Base Stations (BSs) by providing them with the ability to increase their capacity at cell sites. They do this primarily by improving the link between users and BSs through transmitting and receiving more data from users at cell sites on both sides of the connection simultaneously.

Wireless networks have limited available electromagnetic spectrum while the need for higher data rates continues to increase. To reach future demands, wireless communications must be industrialized with the introduction of new and sophisticated technologies [3]. One of the recent proposed techniques is massive MIMO, which has a more promising potential compared to other techniques. Basically, the idea of this technology is about providing a BS with a big number of antennas to cover a much smaller number of users [4]. The Time Division Duplex (TDD) mode of operation is used to obtain accurate Channel Status Information (CSI) [5], which is vital for maximum effectiveness and getting the advantages of this technique. Since the number of training sequences is directly proportional to the number of users, any number of antennas in the BS can be achieved.

Large-scale MIMO is a system that consists of a couple of hundreds antennas serving a large number of end users at the same time while using the same frequency [6]. This kind of

technology has several advantages such as increasing Spectral Efficiency (SE) to achieve the future needs, mainly in dense areas. Also, it will provide a secure network to maintain information privacy [7]. The cost of the transmitter/receiver components will be reduced due to its lower complexity and the power efficiency should be improved while the signal processing will be much simpler.

The accuracy of channel estimation is a critical factor that has the ability to affect SE and for that reason it grabs the attention of researchers [8, 9]. Some estimation methods are utilized in channel estimation, one of them is the Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE). This method is known for its good performing behavior that meets with any value of Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR). Other methods, such as Maximum Ratio (MR) and Zero-Forcing (ZF), will be investigated. To obtain maximum performance we need to have perfect channel matrix knowledge [10].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several studies have investigated the effect of the pilot reuse factor on the spectral efficiency of massive MIMO systems. In [11], it was shown that increasing the pilot reuse factor can improve the spectral efficiency up to a certain point, after which the performance saturates. The authors also proposed a new pilot design scheme based on the use of orthogonal pilot sequences, which can further improve the performance of massive MIMO systems. Authors in [12] analyzed the impact of pilot reuse factor on the downlink spectral efficiency of massive MIMO systems using different channel estimation techniques. The results showed that the optimal pilot reuse factor depends on system parameters such as the number of antennas, the channel coherence time, and the receiver noise level. The authors also proposed a new pilot allocation scheme based on the use of non-uniform pilot density, which can further improve the spectral efficiency of massive MIMO systems. Authors in [13] investigated the effect of pilot reuse factor on the uplink spectral efficiency of massive MIMO systems using a realistic channel model. The results showed that increasing the pilot reuse factor can improve SE up to a certain point, after which the performance saturates. The authors also proposed a new pilot allocation scheme based on the use of clustered pilot sequences, which can further improve the SE of massive MIMO systems.

Overall, the literature suggests that the choice of pilot reuse factor is an important design parameter for massive MIMO systems, and that different pilot allocation schemes can be used to optimize the system performance. However, further research is needed to investigate the optimal pilot reuse factor for different system configurations and its impact on other performance metrics. In this study, we were able to identify the ideal value for the pilot reuse factors for 3 distinct channel estimators based on the number of antennas in the BS and the number of active users. Our proposed system will always run at its greatest SE due to these ideal pilot reuse factor values.

Notation: In this study, column vectors, such as \mathbf{x} , are denoted by lower-case, bold notations. Matrix symbols \mathbf{X} , however, are upper-case, bold notations. The symbols for transpose, conjugate, and conjugate transpose \mathbf{X} are \mathbf{X}^T , \mathbf{X}^* ,

and \mathbf{X}^H , respectively. \mathbf{I} is the representation of the identity matrix of appropriate dimensions. $\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{x}\}$ stands for the \mathbf{x} operation expected value, and $\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}\}$ stands for \mathbf{x} conditional expected value that is related to \mathbf{y} . In the expression $\mathbf{x} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, \mathbf{Q})$, the covariance matrix is \mathbf{Q} and the mean is $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$.

III. CHANNEL AND SYSTEM MODEL

The primary goal of our study is to examine the related average sum spectral efficiency for the UL channel that is susceptible to interference due to the behavior of wireless channels. The system modeling comprises of a large antenna number in the BS terminal coupled to a small number of user terminals. The system used is a subset of massive MIMO, where the protocol utilized between the two sides of the link is TDD [14]. Because the accuracy of estimation in TDD does not depend on N , we can use a high number of BS antennas [15].

We maintain continuous CSI to identify UL data information by using reciprocity benefit of the channel. From one terminal to the other, \mathbf{h} represents the block-fading and it has a Rayleigh model as $\mathbf{x} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R})$, while $\mathbf{R} = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{h}\mathbf{h}^H\}$

The BS terminal is aware of the statistical distribution. Pilot for channel estimate serves as the foundation for the UL system model, and \mathbf{y} symbolizes the signal that is received by the BS.

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{n} + \mathbf{h}\mathbf{d} \quad (1)$$

where the received signal is denoted by $d \in \mathbb{C}$. It could be the data signal or a predetermined pilot. The average power of the signal is:

$$p = \mathbb{E}\{|d|^2\} \quad (2)$$

Channel noise is represented by \mathbf{n} , and is composed of the following parts:

$$\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{n}_{\text{noise}} + \mathbf{n}_{\text{if}} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{n}_{if} is the interfering noise caused by other messages and $\mathbf{n}_{\text{noise}}$ is the independent receiver noise with zero mean and $(\sigma_{BS}^2 \mathbf{I})$ covariance.

We assume that \mathbf{n}_{if} has a zero mean, $\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{n}_{\text{if}}\mathbf{n}_{\text{if}}^H\}$ covariance, and is represented by \mathbf{S} . $\mathbf{Q}_{\mathcal{H}} = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{n}_{\text{if}}\mathbf{n}_{\text{if}}^H|\mathcal{H}\}$ is the definition of the conditional covariance matrix, while \mathcal{H} represents the realization of the channel. We are supposing that \mathbf{R} spectral norm is bounded uniformly independent of the BS's antenna number [16]. The matrix of channel covariance is produced by the exponential correlation model, which is described in greater detail in [17]. This correlation model presupposes that the value of \mathbf{R} has the following elements (i, j) :

$$[\mathbf{R}] = \begin{cases} \delta r^{j-i}, & i \leq j \\ \delta (r^{j-i})^*, & i > j \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where r represents a correlation coefficient between adjacent channels and δ is the scaling factor.

The factor of correlation value is restricted to the range from 0 to 1, and its phasor $\angle r$ denotes the angle of departure or arrival. This obviously is not the most suitable model for scenarios in the actual world. However, it is still a straightforward model with a manageable amount of

parameters, making it possible to investigate how the correlation factor affects the estimation of the huge MIMO channel [18]. The correlation factor $|r|$ in \mathbf{R} represents the eigenvalue spread, and $\mathcal{L}r$ defines the associated eigenvectors. We take r to be a real number since the the mean square error is not affected by the angle of r .

By comparing the signal received by BS \mathbf{y} in (1) to the known pilot uplink signal d , where user equipment power corresponds to (p^{UE}) , we may estimate the channel \mathbf{h} . In this paper, different types of estimators are used, the first one is MMSE. The following is a representation of the estimation of channel realization:

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}} = d^* \mathbf{R} \bar{\mathbf{Y}}^{-1} \mathbf{y} \quad (5)$$

The \mathbf{R} matrix, the average power, the received signal covariance, and the noise, make up the \mathbf{y} covariance matrix, which is shown as follows:

$$\bar{\mathbf{Y}} = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{y}\mathbf{y}^H\} = \mathbf{R} p^{UE} + \mathbf{S} + \sigma_{BS}^2 \mathbf{I} \quad (6)$$

The following is a representation of the covariance matrix of error that is used to calculate the overall MSE:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbb{E}\{(\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{h})^H (\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{h})\} = \mathbf{R} - p^{UE} \mathbf{R} \bar{\mathbf{Y}}^{-1} \mathbf{R} \quad (7)$$

We may get the entire value of MSE by finding the \mathbf{C} value, which is the error covariance matrix shown in (8):

$$\mathbf{MSE} = \text{tr}(\mathbf{C}) = \mathbb{E}\{\|\hat{\mathbf{h}} - \mathbf{h}\|_2^2\} \quad (8)$$

The channel may be described as a mixture of two components based on the prior observations:

$$\mathbf{h} = \hat{\mathbf{h}} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \quad (9)$$

where the process of unknown error estimation is represented by $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, and the value of the MMSE estimate is marked by $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$. The mean of the values, $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, is 0 for both and they are uncorrelated [19]. The $\hat{\mathbf{h}}$ covariance matrix is generated as $\mathbb{E}\{\hat{\mathbf{h}}\hat{\mathbf{h}}^H\} = \mathbf{R} - \mathbf{C}$, and the $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ covariance matrix as $\mathbb{E}\{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^H\} = \mathbf{C}$.

We can disregard all the correlation matrices in the event that the conditions of the channel are favorable and the signal's interferences from nearby cells are faint. By applying that, ZF combining can be generated [20]. By knowing that the combining vector's normalization has no effect on the instantaneous up link signal to noise ratio, we can generate MR combining. The primary difference is that we no longer employ exact channels and instead use estimated channels (which are unknown in practice). In contrast to the preceding systems, MR does not need any matrix inversion. Since not all UEs in actuality have a very low SNR, it is anticipated that MR scheme will yield lower SE compared to other schemes.

It is assumed that there are 16 square cells in a 4x4 grid, a wrap-around topology is taken into consideration, in which every cell has numerous locations and any arbitrary BS and UE are always separated by the 9 combinations' shortest distance. The shortest path is used to derive the angular characteristics. Four distinct methods of reusing pilot sequences between cells

are depicted, which means that a higher pilot reuse factor denotes the need for more orthogonal pilot sequences.

The distribution and reuse of the $\boldsymbol{\tau}_p$ pilot sequences among the UEs and cells can be done in a variety of ways [21]. Unless otherwise indicated, we assume $\boldsymbol{\tau}_p = fK$ pilots, where f is an integer known as pilot reuse factor. That indicates that we have f times more pilots than user equipment in each cell and that a fraction of $1/f$ of the cells reuses the same subset of pilots. In the running example, we consider $f \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16\}$, where the same pilot group is considered to consist of the cells that employ the same pilots. Every UE in a cell has a pilot allocated at random, thus the k th UE in two adjacent cells that is related to the same group of pilot utilizes the same pilot.

IV. NUMERICAL ILLUSTRATIONS

In this part, we provide illustrative simulations to demonstrate how the SE performs when based on various receive combining schemes and different pilot reuse factors. The use of the communication system toolbox in MATLAB allows us to analyze our model. To create the Figures where the analysis is done, several scripts were built. The system parameters are shown in Table I.

V. SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Cells number	16
Number of BS antennas	$M = 40, 70, 100$
Number of users/cell	$K = 10$
Pilot reuse factor	$f = 1, 2, 4, 8, 16$
Uplink and downlink transmit power	20 dBm

For the downlink and uplink channels, the average signal to noise ratios are $p^{BS} \text{tr}(\mathbf{R}) / N \sigma_{UE}^2$ and $p^{EU} \text{tr}(\mathbf{R}) / N \sigma_{BS}^2$, respectively. When using low and high SNR values, we take the value of SNR into account. We presume that the percentages of uplink and downlink data are identical and set at 0.45. Using this assumption, we obtain equal uplink and downlink. $K = 10$ user equipment per cell and various numbers of BS antennas were taken into account in the simulations. Each block contains fK pilots, with the remaining $\boldsymbol{\tau}_p - fK$ samples being utilized for uplink data transfer. We utilized the channel model with Gaussian local scattering.

Figure 1 shows the average uplink SE as a function of the pilot reuse factor with 100 BS antennas. The L-MMSE combination provides the highest SE compared to ZF and MR schemes. By increasing the pilot reuse factor from 1 to 2, both schemes L-MMSE and ZR are having higher SE while the MR is having a lower average sum SE. Once the value of f is increased from 2 to 4, the SE keeps increasing slightly for L-MMSE scheme while it is decreasing for the two other schemes, ZF and MR. As the pilot reuse factor is raised from 4 to 8 and 16, all the 3 schemes deteriorate quickly.

By using 70 antennas at the BS, Figure 2 shows lower average sum SE compared to the 100 antennas of Figure 1 due to the increase interference that cannot be canceled easily. In comparison to ZF and MR combining methods, the SE provided by the L-MMSE scheme is the greatest. The L-MMSE and ZR systems have both greater SE as a result of raising the pilot reuse factor from 1 to 2, whereas the MR has a

lower average sum SE. When f is increased from 2 to 4, the SE for the L-MMSE scheme continues to marginally grow while falling for the 2 other schemes. All the schemes quickly degrade as the pilot reuse factor is increased from 4 to 8 and 16 respectively. Due to the increased interference that is difficult to be eliminated when utilizing 40 antennas at the BS, Figure 3 displays the lowest average total SE. Raising f from 1 to 2 results in increased SE for the L-MMSE and ZF systems, while the MR has a lower average sum SE. All 3 schemes rapidly degrade as the f is increased from 2 to 4, 8, and 16 respectively. Even though the L-MMSE scheme provides higher SE, it has much more complexity than ZF and MR.

Fig. 1. Average uplink sum spectral efficiency as a function of pilot reuse factor for 100 BS antennas.

Fig. 2. Average uplink sum spectral efficiency as a function of pilot reuse factor for 70 BS antennas.

By comparing Figures 1-3 in terms of using the L-MMSE scheme, it is obvious that the higher the number of antennas in the BS, the higher the SE. When the number of antennas is equal to 100 (Figure 1), the SE exceeds 51 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell] while the pilot reuse factor is equal to 2 or 4. If the number of antennas in the BS is equal to 70 and the f is either 2 or 4 (Figure 2), the SE is less than 48 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell]. On the other hand, when the number of antennas in the BS is equal to 40 and $f=2$ (Figure 3), the SE is less than 33 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell].

Fig. 3. Average uplink sum spectral efficiency as a function of pilot reuse factor for 40 BS antennas.

If we compare the Figures 1-3 considering the ZF scheme, it is also clear that the higher the number of antennas in the BS, the higher the SE. When the number of the antennas is equal to 100 in the BS (Figure 1) the SE is equal to 40 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell] if the pilot reuse factor is equal to 2 or 4. When the number of antennas in the BS is equal to 70 and the pilot reuse factor is either 2 or 4 (Figure 2), the SE is less than 37 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell], and when the number of antennas in the BS is equal to 40 and the pilot reuse factor is equal to 2 or 4 (Figure 3), the SE is equal to 33 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell].

When comparing Figures 1-3 while considering the MR scheme, it is clear again that if there are more antennas in the BS, the SE will be higher. When the number of antennas is equal to 100 in the BS (Figure 1) the SE is equal to 24 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell] if the pilot reuse factor is equal to 2. If the number of antennas in the BS is equal to 70 and the pilot reuse factor is 2 (Figure 2), the SE is less than 22 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell]. Finally, when the number of antennas in the BS is equal to 40 and the pilot reuse factor is equal to 2 or 4 (Figure 3), the SE is less than 33 [Bit/second/Hz/Cell].

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we examined the combined impact of the pilot reuse factor and the base station number of antennas on the average total spectral efficiency in massive MIMO. Different channel estimators, such as LMMSE, ZF, and MR schemes, have been used to investigate the spectral efficiency of these receivers. According to the simulation results, a larger number of antennas in BS would provide a significantly higher average total SE. On a larger number of base station antennas, raising the pilot reuse factor from 1 to 2 for both L-MMSE and ZR schemes would give greater spectral efficiency. In addition, it is noticeable that the increase in pilot reuse factor has not a positive impact on the MR scheme's spectral efficiency. Although the L-MMSE scheme has a greater spectral efficiency than the ZF and MR schemes, it is more complex.

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Dynamic Monitoring of Structural Deformations utilizing an Experimentally Validated Efficient Technique

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ABSTRACT

Up-to-date detection of a building's responses under various load situations is essential to generate data used to assess its capacity to bear crucial loads. This study presents an innovative and effective method to detect structural displacements and provide a more accurate alternative to existing approaches such as trigonometry leveling and angle intersecting. The least squares method was used to produce a concurrent solution that includes all the observed data to improve precision and retrieve the data needed for statistical analysis. The proposed method was validated experimentally and compared with the total station, conventional structural analysis, and displacement gauges to test and monitor a three-point loaded Reinforced Concrete (RC) beam at seven discrete points. The displacement gauge measurements were used as a baseline for comparing the outcomes from the other methods. The maximum mid-span deflection of the tested RC beam showed that the variation between the recorded displacement using displacement gauges and the suggested approach was below 0.31mm, resulting in a 3.7% inaccuracy, while the total station observations and the ACI-Code deflection provisions provided deflections of 0.62 and 3.64mm, resulting in 7.4% and 43.4% inaccuracies, respectively. Furthermore, comparing the results using root-mean-square error, the suggested method's precision in detecting displacements was much superior to the total station. The proposed approach was effective for detecting horizontal and vertical deformations and offers a viable option for building monitoring across both the element and whole building stages.

Keywords-structural deformation; structure monitoring; ACI deflection provisions; total-station; angle-intersecting method

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic monitoring deals with the identification of the change of a member's location, dimension, and geometry for its specified shape. The purpose of identifying deformations is to evaluate not just the precise position of the detected member, but additionally its fluctuation over a period to avoid the collapse of massive buildings. National authorities are very concerned about dynamic building monitoring as a way to manage the structural safety and stability of bridges, tunnels, high-rise buildings, and other public structures [1]. Various survey techniques have been proposed to assist in building surveillance and detect deformations at different locations [1]. In this case, finding an accurate, affordable, reliable, and time-saving 3D measuring method is challenging. Although such

demands can be achieved in many ways [1-3], it is challenging to find an approach that satisfies all the criteria mentioned above. In the field of structural measurement, topographic techniques that rely on height differences, observed angles, and lengths are often utilized [4-6]. For this purpose, total stations, electronic distance measurement instruments, and theodolites are just examples of the various devices used [7-8], while indirect approaches such as single- or multi-intersections and precise leveling traverse are employed for difficult-to-reach locations [6, 10-11]. Contact sensors can also be used for these observations, such as inclinometers, dial-gauges, pendulums, or extensometers [1-3, 12], but due to their nature, they cannot be used in the last phases of the destructive loading test but can capture only one-dimensional measurements. The Global Positioning System (GPS) is used in building monitoring in

conjunction with other sensors [7, 13-16], but has two fundamental restrictions: it cannot be used inside or under barriers and its current accuracy is restricted to +/-10mm in the horizontal direction and +/-20mm in the vertical direction [10]. The photogrammetric close-range technology is also used for monitoring structural deformation [17-20]. In [17], high-accuracy measurements were produced using digital close-range photogrammetry. This approach provided quick, remote, spatial data collecting with images that provided a long-term visual record. Using targets may not always be appropriate, particularly if access to the object is difficult or hazardous. To determine the scale definition in the photogrammetric procedure, observations made with extra devices, such as reflectorless total stations, are needed. Novel approaches and computational methods for building monitoring were reported in the Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS) method [21]. Although these methods had improved precision and were reliable for structural monitoring [22], they have not been validated in more complicated structures such as tunnels and high-rise buildings. The stated inspection focuses primarily on the stability and precision of georeferencing which serves as the base for comparing various scans and the point-cloud-based displacement determination [21]. Various types of surfaces such as mesh and polynomial, and resample-point-cloud have been typically used in comparison [23-24].

This study proposes a novel approach based on a numerical model to determine the ground coordinates from observations at individual monitoring locations and modifies duplicated observations whose accuracy may be assessed by a least squares solution. This method was used for the displacement detection of a reinforced concrete beam at various load steps and the results were compared to those of ACI 318-19 [25], total-station, and displacement gauge.

II. THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Figure 1 shows the layout for finding the missing coordinates (x_c, y_c, z_c) of node C. Node A represents the device location, node B is the back-sight location, and their respective known ground coordinates are (x_A, y_A, z_A) and (x_B, y_B, z_B).

Fig. 1. Geometric representation of the proposed model.

The observation equations of the observed horizontal angle θ and the vertical angle β are given by [26]:

$$v_{\theta} + \left(\frac{Y_C - Y_A}{AC^2}\right) \Delta X_C + \left(\frac{X_A - X_C}{AC^2}\right) \Delta Y_C = \quad (1)$$

$$T \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{X_B - X_A}{Y_B - Y_A}\right)_o - T \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{X_C - X_A}{Y_C - Y_A}\right)_o - \theta$$

and:

$$v_{\beta} + \frac{g \times (X_C - X_A)}{AC(AC^2 + g^2)} \Delta X_C + \frac{g \times (Y_C - Y_A)}{AC(AC^2 + g^2)} \Delta Y_C + \frac{-AC}{(AC^2 + g^2)} \Delta Z_C = T \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{g}{AC}\right)_o - \beta \quad (2)$$

where:

$$AC^2 = (X_C - X_A)^2 + (Y_C - Y_A)^2,$$

$$g = Z_C - Z_A - h,$$

and h is the instrument height. Finding the ground coordinates of point C requires three observations and the solution of three observation formulas, while a least squares solution would be feasible if there are more than three observations [27].

III. DEFLECTION ANALYSIS OF THE TESTED RC BEAM

Due to its importance as a key performance parameter, many studies investigated the deflection of structural elements and the factors that influence it, such as element length to depth ratio, shrinkage of concrete, creep of concrete, fiber content, fire stresses, and aggregate size [28-38]. According to ACI 318-19 [25], the moment at the first crack (M_{cr}) can be determined based on the concrete modulus of rupture (f_r) and ignoring the impact of steel bars in computing the gross moment of inertia (I_g). Consequently, the cracked distributed load (W_{cr}) of the tested beam can be calculated as follows.

$$W_{cr} = 8 \times 0.62 \sqrt{f'_c} \times \frac{bt^2}{6l^2} \quad (3)$$

The self-weight of the tested beam is less than the cracked distributed load (W_{cr}). For the applied levels of concentrated load (P), the applied moment (M_a) including the beam's self-weight (W_{ow}) would be more than the beam's cracked moment. As a result, I_g can be used to calculate the deflection due to beam self-weight (δ_{ow}), while the effective moment of inertia (I_e) will be applied when computing deflection due to self-weight plus the applied concentrated load (δ_{ow+P}). The self-weight deflection (δ_{ow}) and all applied load deflections (δ_{ow+P}) is given by:

$$\delta_{ow+P} = \frac{5 W_{ow} l^4}{384 E I_{e(ow+P)}} + \frac{P l^3}{48 E I_{e(ow+P)}} \quad (4)$$

Under the application of all loads and according to ACI 318-19 [25], the effective moment of inertia ($I_{e(ow+P)}$) can be computed as follows, when the applied moment (M_a) exceeds the two-thirds of the cracked moment ($0.67M_{cr}$):

$$I_{e(ow+P)} = I_{cr} / \left[1 - \left(\frac{2}{3} \frac{M_{cr}}{M_a}\right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{I_{cr}}{I_g}\right) \right] \quad (5)$$

The deflection results of (4) under different concentrated load levels (15, 20, 25, and 30kN) were used in comparison with other deflection values obtained from the total station, and displacement gauges (LVDT) methods.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL WORK AND TEST SET-UP

The proposed mathematical model for detecting deformations can be used for all types of structures, bridges, and elements. This model was used to detect the structural deformability of a three-point loaded reinforced concrete beams. The compressive strength of the cylinder concrete at 28 days was 30MPa, and the beam was 350mm in depth and 150mm in width. As shown in Figure 2, the beam had two supports and one mid-span point load with a main span (L) of 4m. One concentrated load was applied at the mid-span of the beam with four different levels (15, 20, 25, and 30kN). Deflection values were measured at 7 distinct locations: $L/8$, $L/4$, $3L/8$, $L/2$, $5L/8$, $3L/4$, and $7L/8$. At each deflection point, a paper prism and LVDT were attached to detect deflection values. The beam had a flexural reinforcement of 3T12 with a steel yield strength of 420MPa.

Fig. 2. Test set-up and deflection point locations for the tested beam

Two observation stations were placed at the test platform, 5m apart from the beam, and the most well-known and widely approved approach for determining level differences in the field was adopted. Level variations could be monitored using a single level, as well as measurements on the invar-rods utilizing 2 distinct equipment horizons. This method is closely related to ensuring the appropriate accuracy required to measure field-level differences [8, 39]. The accurate leveling of a GPLE3 geodetic invar rod with 10mm graduation and a Leica NA2 automated leveling with a Leica (10mm) GPM3 parallel plate micrometer adapter was used to obtain the level variance between the two monitoring locations. A Topcon GTS710 total station was used to assess the horizontal length separating the two monitoring sites. Six horizontal distances (3 direct and 3 reversed distances) were measured, and their mean was used to calculate the final horizontal distance. A local coordinate system was assigned to the coordinates of the 2 observation (control) stations after the horizontal and height distances between the two monitoring stations were determined.

The deflection points on the tested beam were measured before and after each load step. The deflection points were measured using a Wild (Leica) T2. The horizontal angles to the deflection points were determined using direction and closing the horizon procedures and detecting the horizontal circles across the left and right sides. Multiple angles were measured using the circle advanced before each reading to mitigate systemic faults. The angles of every observation were

determined and the end value of the horizontal angle was taken as the mean of all measurements. The vertical angles for the deflection points were determined by reading and averaging the vertical circles on the left and right. For each deflection point, the vertical angle was determined by taking the mean of the vertical circle's measurements on both the left and right faces. The deflection points' coordinates were observed using a Topcon GTS710 total station. It should be noted that the devices were properly verified and confirmed to be in a good condition before carrying out the measurements.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The deflections of a simple-span RC beam exposed to the point loading steps were used as a serviceability evaluation criterion. Deflection observations using LVDT gauges at the defined points of the tested RC beam were used for comparison at each loading stage. Figure 3 and Table I show the detected deflections of various deflection locations at each load step for the proposed, the total station, and the ACI 318-19 [25] methods. The deflection derived from the proposed model had the best correlation with that obtained using LVDT gauges, with an RMSE of 0.09 at the low, 0.19 at the high, and 0.17 for all observation points and loading stages. The deflection results obtained using the total station and ACI 318-19 [25] were less accurate and conservative when compared to the results of LVDT gauges. The RMSE ranged from 0.23 at the low and 0.52 at the high loading stages, with an overall RMSE of 0.42 based on discrepancies between the total station and LVDT gauges. However, for safety concerns, the deflection results using ACI 318-19 [25] were substantially conservative when compared to those of LVDT gauges, with an RMSE ranging from 1.95 at the low to 1.75 at the high loading stage and an overall RMSE of 1.86. In comparison to the LVDT results, the deflection results of the proposed mathematical model were more accurate than those of the total station.

VI. CONCLUSION

The proposed method adds a new dimension to the methods of angle intersection and trigonometric leveling. This method uses the least-squares solution to produce a response that includes multiple measurements in a single operation. This improves the predicted precision and provides the information needed in descriptive statistics. Based on an experimental and analytical analysis of a three-point-loaded, simply supported, reinforced-concrete beam, this method is proposed for reliably measuring structural element deformation, drawing the following conclusions in comparison to the typical approaches employed for this purpose:

- The proposed mathematical model outperformed the established approaches in assessing structural element deformation in terms of precision, feasibility, timesaving, and economy.
- The proposed model's results were most tightly correlated to the experimental results obtained using LVDT gauges.
- The proposed model produced more-accurate results compared to the total station.

- The proposed approach offered high accuracy even when compared to the ACI 318-19 deflection provisions.
- The results showed a strong correlation with the LVDT gauge results, with an overall RMSE of less than 0.17. The

respective RMSEs for the total station and ACI 318-19 were 0.42 and 1.86.

Fig. 3. Deflection of the tested beam at different stages of loading using LVDT, proposed model, total station, and ACI 318-19.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF VERTICAL DEFLECTIONS AND DISCREPANCIES USING DIFFERENT METHODS

Step of loading	Observation method		1/8	1/4	3/8	1/2	5/8	3/4	7/8	RMSE	RMSE (for all loading steps)	
Step I (15kN)	LVDT	Deflection	0.75	1.47	2.21	2.76	2.22	1.46	0.8			
		Proposed method	Deflection	0.81	1.57	2.31	2.83	2.33	1.58	0.88		
	Proposed method	Discrepancies	0.06	0.1	0.1	0.07	0.11	0.12	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.17
		Total station	Deflection	1.01	1.71	2.45	2.95	2.46	1.69	1.02		
	ACI 318-19	Discrepancies	0.26	0.24	0.24	0.19	0.24	0.23	0.22	0.22	0.23	0.42
		[22]	Deflection	1.46	2.85	4.19	5.47	4.19	2.85	1.46		
Step II (20kN)	LVDT	Discrepancies	0.71	1.45	2.24	3.37	2.27	1.39	0.66	1.95	1.86	
		LVDT	Deflection	1.5	2.8	3.9	4.59	3.8	2.9	1.5		
	Proposed method	Deflection	1.63	2.95	4.08	4.79	4	3.06	1.64			
		Discrepancies	0.13	0.15	0.18	0.2	0.2	0.16	0.14	0.17		
	Total station	Deflection	1.85	3.2	4.38	5.05	4.26	3.26	1.86			
		Discrepancies	0.35	0.4	0.48	0.46	0.46	0.36	0.36	0.41		
ACI 318-19	Deflection	1.9	3.76	5.55	7.31	5.55	3.76	1.9				
	[22]	Discrepancies	0.4	0.96	1.65	3.21	1.75	0.86	0.4	1.61		
Step III (25kN)	LVDT	Deflection	1.9	3.3	5.15	6.41	5.17	3.4	2			
		Proposed method	Deflection	2	3.59	5.34	6.62	5.35	3.63	2.1		
	Proposed method	Discrepancies	0.1	0.29	0.19	0.21	0.18	0.23	0.1	0.2		
		Total station	Deflection	2.32	3.92	5.49	6.87	5.53	3.96	2.41		
	ACI 318-19	Discrepancies	0.42	0.62	0.34	0.46	0.36	0.56	0.41	0.46		
		[22]	Deflection	2.34	4.64	6.89	9.09	6.89	4.64	2.34		
Step IV (30kN)	LVDT	Discrepancies	0.44	1.34	2.39	3.99	2.37	1.24	0.34	2.10		
		LVDT	Deflection	2.2	4.77	6.94	8.39	6.98	4.85	2.25		
	Proposed method	Deflection	2.29	5.06	7.04	8.7	7.12	5.02	2.32			
		Discrepancies	0.09	0.29	0.1	0.31	0.14	0.17	0.07	0.19		
	Total station	Deflection	2.65	5.39	7.4	9.01	7.43	5.38	2.71			
		Discrepancies	0.45	0.62	0.46	0.92	0.45	0.53	0.46	0.52		
ACI 318-19	Deflection	2.77	5.51	8.19	10.84	8.19	5.51	2.77				
	[22]	Discrepancies	0.57	0.74	1.84	3.64	1.79	0.66	0.52	1.75		

All deflection values are in mm

Due to the improved assessment accuracy compared to GPS and close-range photogrammetry methods, the proposed method can be used as an efficient and cost-effective solution for structural monitoring, providing many advantages, such as:

- It utilizes simple and low-cost surveying instruments such as theodolite.
- It does not demand pricey GPS receiver antennas or metric or non-metric camera systems.
- It is appropriate for both indoor and outdoor use.
- It is easier in reaching buildings or elements.
- It is simply executed by a surveyor rather than a professional or a photogrammetrist.
- It does not require in situ sensor instrumentation.
- Eliminates wiring-costs.

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The Effect of Hyperparameter Optimization on the Estimation of Performance Metrics in Network Traffic Prediction using the Gradient Boosting Machine Model

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ABSTRACT

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has changed the way we communicate and access information, resulting in the high generation of heterogeneous data. The amount of network traffic generated constantly increases in velocity, veracity, and volume as we enter the era of big data. Network traffic classification and intrusion detection are very important for the early detection and identification of unnecessary network traffic. The Machine Learning (ML) approach has recently entered the center stage in network traffic accurate classification. However, in most cases, it does not apply model hyperparameter optimization. In this study, gradient boosting machine prediction was used with different hyperparameter optimization configurations, such as interaction depth, tree number, learning rate, and sampling. Data were collected through an experimental setup by using the Sophos firewall and Cisco router data loggers. Data analysis was conducted with R software version 4.2.0 with Rstudio Integrated Development Environment. The dataset was split into two partitions, where 70% was used for training the model and 30% for testing. At a learning rate of 0.1, interaction depth of 14, and tree number of 2500, the model estimated the highest performance metrics with an accuracy of 0.93 and R of 0.87 compared to 0.90 and 0.85 before model optimization. The same configuration attained the minimum classification error of 0.07 than 0.10 before model optimization. After model tweaking, a method was developed for achieving improved accuracy, R square, mean decrease in Gini coefficients for more than 8 features, lower classification error, root mean square error, logarithmic loss, and mean square error in the model.

Keywords-network traffic; machine learning; big data; data loggers; feature selection; gradient boosting machine prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

To provide secure and successful communications in any organization at the local, national, and global levels, network management of both incoming and outgoing traffic is critical. The Internet, Wide Area Networks (WANs), Local Area Networks (LANs), e-Commerce, and other online services are widely used in businesses for communication and transaction purposes. Network connectivity is essential for the efficient operation of firms or the supply of daily services to their clientele [1]. Network management tasks, including classification and monitoring of network traffic are crucial for Quality of Service (QoS) control, anomaly detection, and other activities related to network troubleshooting [2]. Voice, data, and multimedia services currently can be merged into one application/software thanks to the advancements in the telecommunications and application/software industries. Several protocols have been developed to support file transfer within the network such as User Datagram Protocol (UDP) and Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) through the Internet. During the early stage of the Internet, static ports (SSH, HTTP, FTP, SMTP, etc.) were used by network security experts for the classification and mapping of network traffic [3]. The Internet has changed the development of an application because they can work without using the assigned port numbers e.g. in peer-to-peer (P2P), gaming, and other online applications [4]. Due to the diversification of software applications that require a different level of bandwidth usage, it is very crucial to be able to identify applications that consume more resources in the network, breach network security, and generate unnecessary traffic. Prediction of network traffic in advance can assist organizations in improving their service provision, both internally and externally by changing the network design or improving areas with weaknesses [5]. This can be done by implementing new network architectures or by deploying equipment with higher capacity.

The advancement of gadgets used in Information and Communication Technology (ICT), particularly smartphones, poses a new challenge to information access and sharing. Currently, most services, such as social media networks and banking are accessed via smartphones [6]. Accessing the services through smartphones generates traffic which may breach the security of the organization and lower QoS provision. With the growth of network complexity, network specialists and engineers employ a variety of strategies and alternatives to identify and optimize network traffic. Machine Learning (ML) is one of them. ML is a branch of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that enables computers to learn from previous data and improve through experience [7]. There are 4 categories of ML algorithms, namely supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and reinforcement. The ML approach has been applied in several fields such as finance, healthcare, ICT (i.e. data anomaly detection, information security, etc.), image recognition, fraud detection, and others, while some companies like Facebook, Google, Apple, Netflix, and Amazon use ML in their daily business operations.

In ICT data security, ML can be used to classify network traffic from different sources such as Internet of Things (IoT) devices, wireless sensors, LAN, and WAN and identify threats

or malicious activities. Different ML methods or techniques have been applied in the classification of network traffic to supplement existing network management tools, for instance, the k-nearest neighbors algorithm (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and clustering. Although ML has advanced to the forefront of effectively identifying network traffic, it rarely employs model hyperparameter optimization procedures in this process. Network traffic classification and optimization are very crucial to attain the maximum usage of the communication network infrastructure. This will assist an organization to avoid investing a lot of money without getting value for money or a return on investment. Understanding network traffic flow is very important for both ICT experts and the organization for planning human and financial resource alignment.

In [8], the XGBoost algorithm was used in the classification of network packet trace capture data. Four performance metrics, namely Accuracy, Precision, F1 Score, and Recall were used and the predicted mean accuracy per class was about 99.5%. A Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) study using a Convolution Neural Network (CNN) to classify encrypted packets by using a deep learning approach was conducted in [4]. Authors in [1] showed that a port-based approach can be used to classify flow-based traffic with some limitations, especially in applications that can be accessed using P2P software such as uTorrent, LimeWire, Winny, eDonkey, WinMX, and Transmission. Using adaptive network traffic can be estimated by using probability distributions such as Pareto, log-normal distribution, exponential distribution, Poisson, etc. [9]. However, due to the non-stationary nature or properties of the network traffic, only a non-stochastic mathematical model was applied [10], and a part of the stochastic model known as GBM was used and compared to the adaptive approach.

There are 3 common methods used in classifying network traffic, namely payload-based, flow-based and port-based. Port-based assumes the network traffic uses common port numbers through either UDP or TCP. Network traffic packets in the port-based [11] are inspected by using the source and destination ports of the Internet Protocol (IP) of the package (HTTP(80), SMTP(25), FTP(20, 21), etc.). Another technique that is used to identify malicious activities is the use of DPI, however, it can work only in the encrypted packets and when the packets are not encrypted this approach doesn't work [8]. Authors in [12] showed that the accuracy of the model can be improved by using distance and similarities from the clusters. ML can be used to address some of the drawbacks of DPI and port-based package inspection techniques [13]. Classification of network traffic is done in different ways but the most common one is by estimating performance metrics such as accuracy, area under the curve, sensitivity, kappa values, etc. [14].

Standard metrics like Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Square Error (MSE) of deep learning classification techniques kNN and SVM have low performance [15]. In [16], GBM was used for attack detection in traffic flows. A linear regression model was used and the deep learning techniques achieved higher performance compared to the linear regression model.

In this paper, we used GBM which is an ensemble supervised learning technique to classify packet flows, because, after a thorough literature review and to the best of our knowledge, there are no studies related to GBM hyperparameter tuning in network traffic prediction. The model was optimized by using different hyperparameter configurations, such as interaction depth, number of trees, learning rate, sampling, etc. to estimate the prediction performance metrics Accuracy, RMSE, MSE, Logarithmic Loss (Log loss), and R^2 . The performance metrics were compared with the default GBM performance metrics.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Network traffic data were collected through an experiment set by using Cisco Netflow (flow viewer) and Sophos firewall. Cisco 4000 Series and Sophos XGS 3100 1U Model were used for the experiment setup (Figure 1). Data for both incoming and outgoing network traffic were recorded in log files. The data were downloaded and stored on a computer in csv and txt formats. A detailed process from data collection up to model evaluations is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Data collection up to model comparison flows.

A detailed description of the GBM input and the classification and optimization steps can be seen in Figure 1. The main steps are:

1. Dataset captured in the experiment.
2. Convert categorical features (labels column) to numerical values (benign, malicious, and outliers).
3. Normalize the dataset by imputing median to all features except the label feature which is categorical with multi labels.
4. Partition the dataset into training and test subsets.
5. Build the GBM classifier model by using the training dataset.
6. Validate GBM by using the test dataset with 5-fold classification based on 3 features (benign, malicious, and outliers).

7. Performance evaluation.
8. Model hyperparameter tuning (optimization).
9. Output: Accuracy, RMSE, MSE, Log loss, and R^2 .

A. Data Pre-Processing

Network traffic data that were collected were converted into csv files with 18 columns with 3 feature classes (benign, malicious, and outliers). The PreProces package in R software [16] and Rstudio Integrated Development Environment (IDE) [17] were used to normalize and scale the data. Before data scaling, duplicate data were deleted. After duplication removal and normalization, the data were converted into an H2O package [17] format, so that they can be run in a distributed and low memory management H2O package on top of the R software [18, 19]. The dataset was partitioned into two subsets, 70% model training and 30% for testing. Open-source H2O software which is embedded in R software was used to build both models. H2O uses in-memory cluster computing and distributed systems and supports both supervised and unsupervised ML algorithms [20]. In-memory usage can compress the dataset by using columns to increase the classification speed and time in cluster computing [21]. H2O builds all the models in a sequence where all the data are fully distributed in the memory.

B. Model Development

GBM framework was developed in [22] as an additive model which uses a stage wise decision tree. GBM is a technique used in developing very powerful predictive models in ML [23]. GBM is an ensemble learning model which can work for regression and classification [24]. Ensemble learning merges weak learners into strong learners to improve their performance [25] by using the recursive tree partitioning approach. GBM is a forward learning ensemble technique that uses decision trees. Before model tuning, the model was developed and feature importance (variable importance) was estimated. The importance variable provides the contribution of each variable to model development and its output. The values extracted from the model identify and describe all features that are relevant to the model. GBM aims to optimize a generalized ensemble model [26] as indicated in Figure 1 and in the detailed process in Algorithm 1. GBM always minimizes the loss function so that it can be optimized during model generations. The model was developed by using the H2O GBM framework. H2O GBM framework [21] is a package in R software version 2.4.0 [17] and Rstudio version 2022.02.2 [27] was used as an IDE. This study used R packages eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), GBM and Classification and Regression Training (CARET) to implement GBM models [28] by using different parameter configurations (Table I).

Algorithm 1: Pseudocode based on [29].

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Input  $D = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)\}, L(y, \mathbf{O}(x))$ 
Begin
Initialize:  $\mathbf{O}_0(x) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{w}} \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \mathbf{w})$ 
for  $m = 1:M$ 
 $\mathbf{r}_{im} = -\frac{L(y_i, \mathbf{O}(x_i))}{\mathbf{O}(x_i)}$ 
Train weak learner  $\mathbf{C}_m(x)$  on training data
  
```

Calculate w : $w_m = \operatorname{argmin}_w \sum_{i=1}^N L(y_i, \mathbf{O}_{m-1} + \mathbf{C}_m(x_i))$
 Update: $\mathbf{O}_{m(x)} = \mathbf{O}_{m-1} + w_m \mathbf{C}_m(x)$
 End for
 End

TABLE I. PARAMETER CONFIGURATION OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH

Parameter	Values
Algorithm	GBM
Feature class	Categorical
Interaction depth	1 to 17
Learning rate	0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4
Sample rate	0.4, 0.8, 1.0
Column sample	0.4, 0.6, 1.0
Number of folds	5
Bagging fraction	0.8, 1.0
Number of trees	100, 1000, 2500, 5000

C. Tuning Process

Hyperparameter tuning by using the Grid search method was applied in model development, and a combination of different techniques was used for all values of the hyperparameters provided Figure 2. The evaluation of the model was based on the best performance metrics estimated by using different parameters and architectures. Different values of number of trees were used to evaluate the model by changing the number of trees (*ntrees*) as described in Figure 2. The *ntrees* = {100, 1000, 2500, and 5000} were used with the learning rate values of {0.01, 0.1, 0.3, 0.4}. The interaction depth was set and varied from 1 up to 17 to optimize the model and attain maximum accuracy. Interaction depth (maximum depth) which provides maximum accuracy was selected with its learning rate for model training. The sampling rate values were {0.4, 0.8, and 1.0} during model optimization (Table I).

Fig. 2. Graph of model turning parameters.

D. Performance Evaluation

The model was turned using two types of parameter tuning: boosted categories and tree specific parameters [30]. Boosted tuning includes *n tree*, learning rate, and sampling rate, while tree specifics are interaction depth, minimum samples, and feature to split. Five-fold cross-validation technique was used to evaluate the predictive performance of the model. To evaluate the turning parameters in Table I, the following model performance evaluation metrics were used.

1) Accuracy

In multiclass classification, the set of labels predicted for a sample must exactly match the corresponding set of labels in the feature classes. In ML, model accuracy is a common performance metric which considers the features that are correctly classified by the model.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{(TP+TN)}{(TP+FP+TN+FN)} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where TP, FP, TN, and FN represent True Positive, False Positive, True Negative, and False Negative, respectively.

2) Logarithmic Loss

Log loss is a performance metric used when the input feature is continuous or categorical. In this study we used categorical features, namely benign, malicious, and outliers. Log loss shows how the probability of the predicted values is close to the actual values. When the predicted probability diverges from the true values, the Log loss values get higher. Log loss can be expressed mathematically as:

$$\text{Log loss} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (w_i (y_{i,j} \ln(p_{i,j}))) (2)$$

where N is the total number of rows (observations) of our corresponding data frame, w is the per-row user-defined weight (default is 1), C is the total number of classes ($C=2$ for binary classification), p is the predicted value (uncalibrated probability) assigned to a given row (observation), and y is the actual target value.

3) Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)

RMSE is the error between the predicted values and the observed values [31] as indicated below:

$$\text{RMSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \dots (3)$$

where N is the total number of rows of the corresponding data frame, y is the actual target value, and \hat{y} is the predicted target value.

4) R Squared (R^2)

R^2 is defined as the variance proportional to the dependent variable which is predicted from the independent variable. It is defined by:

$$R^2 = \frac{SS_{reg}}{SS_{tot}} = \frac{\sum_j (y_j - \bar{y})^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2} (4)$$

where y_j represents the predicted labels, y_i the true labels, SS_{reg} is the regression Sum of Squares, and SS_{tot} the total Sum of Squares.

III. RESULTS

Several configurations were used during model optimization. The highest accuracy and R^2 values were attained for *n tree* =2500, interaction depth = 14, and learning rate = 0.1 as indicated in Figures 3 and 4. At the same parameter configuration, minimum classification error, RMSE, Log loss, and MSE were also achieved, as indicated in Figure 4. The contribution of an individual attribute in the model was ranked by using relative importance values as shown in Figure 6.

A. Before Model Tuning

Before model tuning, the model was developed and executed with the 5-fold cross-validation technique. The performance metrics were estimated as shown in Figure 3. The Accuracy values ranged from 0.897 to 0.902. Accuracy was maximum at the second fold (0.899). R^2 at the second fold was maximum (0.856) and minimum at the first fold (0.851). The overall estimate for R^2 was about 0.853. There is an inverse relationship between MSE and R^2 as indicated in Figure 2. As the estimated values of MSE increased, there was a decrease in the estimated values of R^2 . The values of Accuracy increased until when it reached 0.90 and it stabilized at 0.899 as shown in Figure 3. The interaction depth of 14 was the one that attributed the model to attain maximum Accuracy (Figure 3). The values of R^2 were at increasing trends until they reached 0.86, then started to stabilize and remained constant while the value of RMSE was increasing.

Fig. 3. Graphic representation of the performance metrics before model tuning.

B. After Model Tuning

The second phase of the model was to tune the model by using the parameters indicated in Table I and Figure 1. The values of Accuracy increased from 0.899-0.90 to 0.920-0.95 in the 5-fold cross-validation as indicated in Figure 4. After model tuning, the values of Log loss decreased to about 0.21 from 0.23 before tuning, as shown in Figure 4. The estimates of MSE decreased from 0.08 to 0.07 after model tuning, R^2 increased up to the maximum value of about 0.88 after model tuning from about 0.85 before model tuning. The estimated metrics for RMSE and classification error decreased after model tuning (Figure 2).

Fig. 4. Performance metrics estimation at 5 – fold cross-validation.

C. Result Comparison before and after Model Tuning

The overall Accuracy before model tuning was about 0.90, however, after model tuning, it was improved up to 0.930

(Figure 5). The value of R^2 after model tuning was higher compared to the one before which varied from 0.85 to 0.87. The values of MSE decreased from 0.08 to 0.07 after hyperparameter tuning. Classification error estimated values decreased as well from about 0.10 before model tuning to 0.08 after model tuning and RMSE values also decreased from 0.28 to about 0.25 (Figure 5). Overall, there is an improvement in all performance metrics after model tuning.

Fig. 5. Graph showing the overall performance metrics before and after tuning.

D. Comparison with Other Studies

The results of this study were compared with other studies as indicated in Table II. The accuracy generated in our study is higher than those reported in [12, 30, 33], while the results of 0.93 [34, 35] and 0.94 [36, 37] are equivalent or above this study's results. The estimated values of R^2 of this study lie between the minimum R^2 as per [33] and below [38]. RMSE was also supported by other studies [16, 30, 39, 40]. MSE from previous studies varied from 0.053 [32] up to 0.4612 [39] while the result of this paper is 0.074 which is supported by other studies as well. The findings of this study are supported by other studies as detailed in Table II.

TABLE II. COMPARISON WITH OTHER STUDIES

Reference	Performance Metrics			
	Accuracy	MSE	RMSE	R^2
[39]		0.4612	0.2127	
[38]			13830	0.887
[16]		0.41	0.480	0.836
[12]	0.902	0.280	0.340	
[32]	0.907	0.053	0.229	0.780
[33]	0.746	0.259	0.509	0.769
Current study	0.930	0.074	0.272	0.872

E. Variable of Importance

Features of importance were compared in all phases of the model. Before tuning the model, the overall entropy contributed more than 50% to the model, while after tuning it only provided about 30%. Before model tuning, most of the feature's contributions were below 5% except for Bytes out and Total entropy. The time between the traffic enters into the network and when it ends is about 1%, showing that the contribution of these two features to the model is very minimal even after model tuning. After the model tuning process, there was an improvement in the contribution of individual features to the model. The following features improved up to more than 10% their contribution to the model: Number of packets in, Duration, Bytes out, Total entropy, and Average inter packet

time. The contribution of Time start and Time end was about 1% to 2%. Therefore, their contribution to the model is not very important (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Graph showing the importance variation before and after tuning.

IV. CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATIONS, AND FUTURE WORK

The results from this study show that by using hyperparameter optimization (tuning), the Accuracy of the model improved from 0.90 to 0.93. Classification errors were reduced from 0.10 to about 0.07 after model tuning. The estimated values of R^2 were 0.85 before tuning and 0.87 after tuning. Based on these findings, the use of hyperparameter tuning is proposed because it improves several performance metrics. The proposed approach increased the Accuracy, R^2 , and Mean of network traffic classification variables and lowered classification error. Furthermore, different machine learning approaches can be used to improve the performance of the model like artificial neural networks, deep learning, and others.

The current study can be extended and used in different conditions in order to extract more variables of importance based on different parameters and experiments. More research is needed in the area of the comparison of the hardware-based approach and machine learning. This study contributes scientific knowledge related to network traffic management and can be used by any organization or Internet service provider to manage network traffic.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data used in this study will be available upon request from the corresponding author.

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DC-38GHz Nonuniform Distributed Amplifier Design with Gate and Drain Line Optimization Using 0.1 μ m GaAs pHEMT Technology

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an optimized three-cell Nonuniform Distributed Amplifier (NUDA) suitable for optoelectronic drivers in the Q band. This is the first NUDA of Darlington topology designed with the 0.1 μ m GaAs pHEMT process with a transition frequency f_T of 130GHz. Gate microstrip line sections, drain microstrip line sections, and active device sizes were optimized to obtain high gain and large bandwidth from a Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit (MMIC) Distributed Amplifier (DA). This paper presents two NUDA designs with different topologies. The first was designed with a three-stage Common Source (CS) topology that enhanced the bandwidth up to 34GHz with a gain greater than 8dB, and the second was designed with two Darlington stages and one CS stage that enhanced the bandwidth up to 38GHz with a gain greater than 8dB. The bandwidth enhancement of NUDA with the Darlington topology was compared and verified with the NUDA of common source topologies.

Keywords-Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit (MMIC); Distributed Amplifier (DA); pseudomorphic High Electron Mobility Transistor (pHEMT); Gallium Arsenide (GaAs); optimization; Nonuniform Distributed Amplifier (NUDA)

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for wideband applications in the crowded lower K and Ka bands has forced designers to choose the Q band for modern wideband designs. Distributed Amplifier (DA) design is the best choice for wide bandwidth applications like optical drivers [1]. DAs were designed at first with vacuum tube technology. Later on, MMIC DAs were designed with the MESFET technology. With high electron mobility and high transition frequency features of GaAs, InP HEMT technologies dominated the DA designs in the 90s. The first DA designs were uniform in nature and all gate and drain transmission line sections had the same inductance values [2]. Later, using optimization, nonuniform distributed amplifiers were implemented by varying the parameters of the distributed amplifiers [3]. The common source [4-5] and cascode [6-8] topologies are the most commonly used in DA design. In [5], a uniform DA design used a gain control switch and 8 GaN HEMT cells of CS topology to obtain 8 \pm 1.5dB gain. As cascode topologies are very sensitive, they need an extra stability network. In [6], a 5-cell cascode topology DA with a

stability network obtained a gain of 11.23dB and a bandwidth of 10MHz-22GHz. In [7], a 6-cell cascode DA topology with dual gate device mode obtained a DC-33GHz bandwidth with a gain of 10.6dB. Another 6 cell cascode DA topology [8] with a series R and C network at the device gate obtained a DC-40GHz bandwidth with a gain of 12dB. However, the first proposed DA design with CS topology without any additional network obtained competitive gain and bandwidth with the minimal number of 3 cells only. The proposed design also offers the highest transition frequency (f_T). The second proposed DA design used the Darlington topology [9] to enhance bandwidth. The Darlington triplet offers 3 times the transition frequency f_T of a single HEMT and handles high current and high frequencies. The high transition frequency plays a significant role in improving the bandwidth of DA. In both proposed designs, nonuniform design using gate optimization and drain microstrip lines were carried out with GaAs pHEMT technology, where all gate and drain microstrip line sections had different inductance values. This design drives the perception of NUDA using GaAs pHEMT in mm-wave applications [10-12]. Proper selection of the active

device, gate and drain line optimization, and active device size balance the tradeoff between gain and bandwidth. The pp1010 GaAs pHEMT was selected as the active device for this design. Simulations of this design were carried out with a 100nm gate length GaAs pHEMT technology on 2mil (50 μ m) substrate thickness to achieve high gain. The high transition frequency f_T of 130GHz and the optimized size of the active device had significant contributions in achieving high bandwidth and gain.

II. 0.1 μ m GAAS pHEMT MMIC TECHNOLOGY

The pp1010 GaAs pHEMT used in the DA design has a gate length of 0.1 μ m generated using the E-beam process with a substrate thickness of 2mil. The T-gates are generated using the electron-beam lithographic process. The InGaAs channel has a pinch-off voltage of -0.95V at $I_D=1\text{mA/mm}$ and can be operated up to a maximum drain bias of 4V. The device is passivated using nitride and can be used as a dielectric for 400pF/mm² Metal Insulator Metal (MIM) capacitors. These passive components support the MMIC fabrication process. Two thick metals with an air bridge are used as interconnection. The highest transconductance (g_m) of the device is 725mS/mm at $V_{DS}=1.5\text{V}$ and the maximum drain current I_D is 760mA/mm at $V_{GS}=-0.5\text{V}$. At peak transconductance, V_{GS} is -0.28V. The device has a maximum gate-to-drain breakdown voltage of 9.6V. The device's maximum oscillation frequency (f_{max}) is 180GHz at $V_{DS}=1.5\text{V}$. The device's transition frequency is 130GHz at $V_{DS}=1.5\text{V}$. Table I shows all the features of the 0.1 μ m GaAs pHEMT.

TABLE I. FEATURES OF THE 0.1 μ m GAAS pHEMT

	Feature	value
1	Gate length	0.1 μ m
2	Pinch off voltage	-0.95V
3	Breakdown VDG	9.6V
4	IDSS	520mA/mm
5	Maximum gm	725mS/mm
6	IDmax	760mA/mm
7	f_T	130GHz
8	f_{max}	180GHz
9	MIM capacitor	400pF/mm
10	TFR resistor	50ohm/square
11	Epi resistor	135ohm/square

Fig. 1. Cross section of the pp1010 GaAs pHEMT.

III. CIRCUIT AND DESIGN

A. 3-Cell NUDA Design with CS Topology

Figure 2 shows a simplified schematic of the 3-cell NUDA with CS topology. Each cell was implemented with the WIN semiconductor pp1010 pHEMT process on 0.1 μ m GaAs substrate. All cells were connected in a CS configuration. All

gates were connected with microstrip lines. Similarly, the drains were interconnected with microstrip lines from one cell to another. Supplied with a gate bias of -0.35V, provided a drain bias of 1V and a quiescent drain current I_{DSS} of 63.9mA.

Fig. 2. Cell architecture of the distributed amplifier.

As the number of cascaded cells increases, the gain should increase, but this is not the case for the DA because as the number of cells increases, the voltage wave gets more attenuated as it travels through the transmission line and the gain reduces. Therefore, the optimum of 4 cells [13] were needed in this design to achieve a greater than 8dB gain. The optimized lengths of the gate transmission line sections were TX L1=100.053 μ m, TX L2=327.455 μ m, TX L3=147.222 μ m, TX L4=537.156 μ m and the optimized lengths of drain transmission line sections were TX L5=533.489 μ m, TX L6=255.256 μ m, TX L7=1036.54 μ m, and TX L8=912.267 μ m. In addition to optimizing drain and gate transmission lines, the proper selection of device size plays a vital role in achieving a high gain. The gain was reduced for device sizes larger than 4 \times 50 μ m. Similarly, the optimal bias of $V_{GS}=-0.5\text{V}$ and $V_{DS}=1.5\text{V}$ is needed to achieve a better tradeoff between gain and bandwidth. The amplifier design was perceptively optimized to achieve optimal performance while maintaining the required gain and bandwidth.

B. 3-Cell NUDA Design with Darlington Topology

In order to enhance bandwidth, the first and second cells used the triple Darlington topology and the third cell used the CS topology, as shown in Figure 3. The triple Darlington topology offers 3 times the transition frequency (f_T) of a single transistor [14].

$$w_{T,D} \cong 3.05 w_T \quad (1)$$

Therefore, it handles high current and high gain at higher frequencies, compared to the CS stage, is very popular for broadband amplifiers, and extends bandwidth to microwave frequencies. The optimal sizes of M1 and M2 were 4 \times 50 μ m and 4 \times 25 μ m for M3. In the triple Darlington topology, the condition $W_1, W_2=2W_3$, provides a wide bandwidth compared to other width choices for HEMTs. The optimized lengths of the gate transmission line sections were TX L1=80 μ m, TX L2=261.826 μ m, TX L3=117.716 μ m, and TX L4=531.156 μ m, while the optimized lengths of drain transmission line sections were TX L5=426.246 μ m, TX L6=203.944 μ m, TX L7=828.174 μ m, and TX L8=728.882 μ m. A better tradeoff

between gain and bandwidth was obtained at biasing values of $V_{GS}=-0.35V$ and $V_{DS}=5V$.

Fig. 3. Cell architecture of the Distributed Amplifier.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The inductive lengths of the gate and drain were adjusted iteratively until a maximum gain of 11dB was achieved. Figures 4-6 show the simulated S parameters for both NUDA designs. To compensate for the condition $C_{GS} > C_{DS}$, the drain line lengths were larger than the gate line lengths to achieve phase matching between the gate and drain lines. Simulations proved that the optimization of the gate and drain lengths played a crucial role in obtaining high gain and bandwidth. Figure 4 shows the simulated S parameters of NUDA with the CS topology. A gain greater than 8dB was obtained over the DC-34 GHz bandwidth range. The Input and Output Return Losses (IORL) were better than -5dB.

Fig. 4. S parameters of NUDA with CS topology.

The S_{21} for both 3 and 4 cells was plotted to verify the optimal number of cells, as shown in Figure 5. From the S_{21} curve, it can be observed that 3 is the optimal number of cells. Figure 6 shows the simulated S parameters of NUDA with the Darlington topology. It can be observed that a gain greater than 8dB can be obtained over the DC-38GHz bandwidth. Therefore, bandwidth improved with Darlington topology compared to the CS. The input and output losses were better than -5dB. Figures 7 and 8 show the layouts of NUDA with CS and Darlington topologies, respectively.

Fig. 5. S_{21} comparison for 3 and 4 NUDA cells.

Fig. 6. S parameters of NUDA with Darlington topology.

Fig. 7. The layout of NUDA with CS topology.

Fig. 8. The layout of NUDA with Darlington topology.

EM simulations were carried out using Keysight's EM solver Momentum Microwave. The EM model was created for the entire design except for the active device. The EM model was imported, and a co-simulation was performed. Table II compares the proposed NUDA with other similar works, where [6-8] used the cascode topology with GaAs HEMT technology.

The proposed design obtained a bandwidth better than [6-7,9]. The DA with the Darlington topology using the CMOS technology [9] obtained a bandwidth of 0.5-23GHz. The proposed design using the GaAs pHEMT technology with the Darlington topology improved the bandwidth to DC-38GHz. Compared to CMOS with Darlington topology [9], the proposed design obtained a wider bandwidth. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first DA of Darlington topology designed with 0.1 μ m GaAs pHEMT process.

TABLE II. COMPARISON WITH OTHER STUDIES

Ref.	Technology	Topology	Bandwidth (GHz)	Gain (dB)	Power (mw)
2021 [6]	GaAs	cascode	0.01-22	11.5	125.89
2013 [7]	0.5 μ m GaAs E/D HEMT	cascode	DC-33	10.6	62
2018 [8]	0.15 μ m GaAs pHEMT	cascode	DC-40	13	550
2022 [5]	0.13 μ m GaN HEMT	CS	1-42	8	707.94
2012 [9]	0.18 μ m CMOS	Darlington	0.5-23	10	150
This work	0.1 μ m GaAs pHEMT	CS	DC-34	8-12	319.5
This work	0.1 μ m GaAs pHEMT	Darlington	DC-38	8-12	236.5

All the previously mentioned studies used 5 or 6 cells to obtain a bandwidth around 38GHz and a gain around 8dB. The studies with cascoded topologies used extra stability networks at the gate of active devices. However, the proposed designs with proper gate and drain line optimization along with a high transition frequency of 130GHz offered by the WIN pp1010 GaAs HEMT succeeded in obtaining competitive bandwidth and gain with a minimum circuitry, as they used only 3 cells. To the best of our knowledge, no NUDA design of Darlington topology with 0.1 μ m GaAs HEMT has ever been proposed, and the proposed design in this paper is the first of its kind.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented two nonuniform distributed amplifier designs using the 0.1 μ m GaAs pHEMT process. The CS topology succeeded in obtaining a bandwidth of DC-34GHz with a gain greater than 8dB. The simulation results showed that the Darlington topology achieved a bandwidth of DC-38GHz with a gain greater than 8dB. The obtained input and output return losses were better than -5dB. The power consumption of NUDA with CS topology was 319mW and 236.5mW for the Darlington topology. Both topologies obtained competitive results using the minimum number of three cells of 0.1 μ m GaAs pHEMT.

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Evaluation of HMA Modified with Titan Polymer

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ABSTRACT

Improving the quality of the road pavement and ensuring the safety of the drivers on the road are issues of paramount importance. Cracking and rutting are two of the most common damages that occur to asphalt pavement due to environmental effects and traffic. Utilizing a modified binder is a solution for improving the pavement's resistance to these damages and enhancing pavement durability. This study investigates the performance of Hot Mix Asphalt (HMA) modified with Titan7205 polymers and then compares it with that of a control mix of modified HMA with Styrene-Butadiene-Styrene (SBS) or crumb rubber (CR). Two percentages of Titan7205 were utilized to find out which dose provided better performance. HMA was prepared by adding polymers with different percentages (3% and 5% Titan7205, 4% SBS, and 8% CR). After preparing the samples, they were tested (unconditioned and AASHTO R30) for Dynamic Shear Rheometer (DSR) testing, Cantabro Mass Loss (CML), Tensile Strength Ratio (TSR), and Indirect Tensile Tension (IDT). The results showed that the mix with 3% of Titan7205 has a similar or better performance than the mixes with the other polymer additives utilized in this study.

Keywords-polymer; SBS; Titan 7205; Hot Mix Asphalt (HMA); crumb rubber

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last quarter of the century, road networks in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia are growing exponentially. It is inevitable to use durable asphalt mixtures to increase pavement quality, improve drivers' protection and comfort, decrease pavement damage, and decrease maintenance costs. One of the most common damages to asphalt pavement is fatigue cracking, which occurs as a result of the daily traffic and passing load. The use of a high-quality or modified asphalt binder is a method to improve and strengthen asphalt pavement and make it more able to resist cracking and rutting. To evaluate asphalt performance, numerous mixture tests can be used.

Authors in [1, 2] conducted a study on asphalt mixtures to investigate their capability to capture damage of single and combined effects of the environment (oxidation, moisture, freeze-thaw). Different laboratory conditions were utilized, including single or combined environment effects of oxidation, moisture, and freeze thaw. Four asphalt mixtures were utilized with NMAS 12.5mm. The results showed that CML was better capture damages of environment on asphalt mixtures. Asphalt additives are commonly classified as elastomers and plastomers

[3-6]. Titan additive is considered a plastomer asphalt binder additive, while CR and SBS additives are considered elastomer asphalt binder additives [3-11]. Since the '80s, bitumen has been modified by the addition of polymers that help reduce rutting and cracking, such as SBS and CR [11-13]. Also, many researchers have studied the preparation technology of bitumen using modified materials such as SBS and CR. It has been found that SBS and CR could raise high-temperature stability and possess the best aging resistance [14-16]. Authors in [17] studied the performance of bitumen and asphalt mixtures modified by CR and SBS. The test results showed that it is necessary to use twice as much CR as SBS to reach the same performance as SBS. Authors in [18] investigated the performance of asphalt mixtures modified with SBS polymer against low-temperature cracking. A Beam Rheometer (BBR) test was used with the trimmed specimens at different temperatures. The results showed that the SBS modified asphalt binder performed better in resisting low temperature cracking compared to the unmodified binder. Authors in [19] stated that SBS additive is one of the most widely used bitumen modifiers because it enhances the mixture's rutting and fatigue resistance and mitigates its susceptibility to temperature variations. Authors in [20] explored the experimental methods

of polymer-modified asphalt, including SBS, with different proportions to systematically ensure the quality and requirements of construction engineering in asphalt pavement. The results showed that SBS improved the high temperature performance of asphalt and could be used to increase its compressive strength.

CR is frequently used as a modifier to improve asphalt properties such as rutting and fatigue [21, 22]. The Virginia Department of Transportation (VDOT) conducted research to see the effects of CR addition on the moisture susceptibility of asphalt mixtures [23]. Modified Lottman and the Texas Boiling Water Test were used for the evaluation of asphalt mixtures. The results showed that CR modifiers could improve asphalt mixture stripping and moisture susceptibility. CR has been used successfully for improving the mechanical characteristics of HMA mixtures, where it was observed to improve the laboratory performance of mixtures against rutting, cracking, moisture damage, and oxidation [24].

Titan materials have different effects on HMA depending on their type and properties. The Titan additive has been shown to reduce harmful emissions from road paving by approximately 82% and the amount of fuel required in a mixture by 13% [25]. Authors in [26] investigated the effect of oxidized Titan7686 polymer on the rheological and performance properties of SBS modified bitumen with 0.5% by weight control binder. Indirect tensile strength, resilient modulus, and DSR test were performed to investigate the binder characterization. The results of the modulus of elasticity test indicated that the addition of the Titan7686 polymer enhanced the response of the modified bituminous mixtures under repeated loading, while it was observed that the MR value respectively increased by 11%, 20%, and 16% at 25°C, 35°C, and 45°C compared to the SBS bitumen mixture. Also, there was an increase in the value of the TSR test compared to the SBS. On the other hand, it was observed that the complex modulus, shear modulus, and loss modulus of Titan7686 are higher than that of SBS. Authors in [27] investigated the negative effects of wax within bitumen from different sources to determine the wax content and the type of polymer that would be best for the needs of refineries in different countries [27]. Temperature performance, fatigue cracking, and rutting were evaluated using dynamic shear tests, zero shear viscosity tests, and multiple stress creep recovery tests. Titan7686 generally improved the rutting and fatigue cracking properties of waxy bitumen. Depending on the asphalt mixture materials, Titan can reduce the amount of additive required by around 30% and help reduce rutting issues. Asphalt binders play an important role in the performance of resilient sidewalks when exposed to high traffic loads and harsh environmental conditions [28]. Some tests were conducted to study the influence of the physical and rheological properties of asphalt binders using polymers, most notably SBS, Polybilt, Titan7686, and Titan7205. The results showed that adding enhancers, especially Titan7205, improved the performance of the asphalt mixtures. There is a lack of information and research on the performance of Titan7205 when used with HMA, and the current research fills this gap.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table I shows the properties of the materials used for the asphalt mix, the gradation, the bitumen ratio, and the type of additive used. In this study, asphalt samples with a diameter of 150mm and a height of 95±5mm were prepared for mixture testing. The air void (Va) range of specimens used is 7.0±0.5% according to AASHTO T166, and a total of 125 specimens were prepared with 3 types of polymers in various dose percentages. Each polymer has been given a symbol with different percentages: neat bitumen (M0), 4% SBS (M1), 3% Titan7205 (M2), 5% Titan7205 (M3), and 8% CR (M4). Table II shows the physical appearance of each polymer type.

TABLE I. MIXTURE PROPERTIES

Mixture ID	M0	M1	M2	M3	M4
P _b (%)	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3
Additive	None	4% SBS	3% Titan7205	5% Titan7205	8% CR
P25mm (%)	100	100	100	100	100
P19.0mm (%)	100	100	100	100	100
P12.5mm (%)	95.1	95.1	95.1	95.1	95.1
P9.5mm (%)	81.3	81.3	81.3	81.3	81.3
P4.75mm (%)	53	53	53	53	53
P2.36mm (%)	38	38	38	38	38
P1.18mm (%)	25.1	25.1	25.1	25.1	25.1
P0.60mm (%)	18.9	18.9	18.9	18.9	18.9
P0.30mm (%)	15	15	15	15	15
P1.5mm (%)	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
P0.075mm (%)	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.4
NMAS (mm)	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
VMA	14.4	15.3	15.4	15	14.5
V _F (%)	49.4	55.3	54.2	53.1	52.5
G _b	1	1	1	1	1
G _{sb}	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7
P _s	94.7	94.7	94.7	94.7	94.7
G _{se}	2.8	2.7	2.8	2.8	2.7
P _{ba}	1.1	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.8
P _{be}	4.2	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.5
D _p	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.1

P_b = total binder content-mix mass basis, PXXmm= percent passing a XX mm sieve, NMAS = nominal maximum aggregate size, VMA = voids in mineral aggregate, V_F = Voids Filled, G_b = specific gravity of the asphalt binder, G_{sb} = bulk specific gravity of the aggregates, P_s = aggregate percentage, G_{se} = effective specific gravity of the aggregates, P_{ba} = % by mass of the absorbed asphalt binder on aggregate mass basis, P_{be} = % by mass of effective asphalt binder on mix mass basis, D_p = Dust Percentage.

TABLE II. ADDITIVE PROPERTIES

Property	SBS	Titan 7250	CR
Density	0.90 g/cc	0.93 g/cc	1.32 g/cc
Viscosity	400 – 4320 cps	450 cps	165 - 237 cps
Product form	Prill	Prill	Granule
Size	4-6mm diameter	2-3mm	0.2-0.4mm

A. Laboratory Conditioning

AASHTO R30 laboratory conditioning protocol was utilized to investigate HMA performance over time and simulate long-term aging effects. The specimens were cooled to room temperature before aging and then were placed in an oven at 85±3°C for 120±0.5h (Figure 1). Then, the oven was turn off, the oven doors were opened, and the test specimens were allowed to cool to room temperature, something that typically took about 16 hours.

Fig. 1. Oven conditioning of asphalt mixtures.

B. Binder Testing-Dynamic Shear Rheometer Testing (DSR)

Asphalt binder is a viscoelastic material, i.e. it behaves as both an elastic and viscous material at the same time. DSR testing was performed at high temperatures within a range of 64°C to 88°C with a 25-mm plate as per AASHTO M315 (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. The DSR device.

C. Mixture Testing

1) Cantabro Mass Loss Testing (CML)

CML testing was performed on specimens with 150mm diameter and 95±5mm height. The specimens were conditioned in the air at 25°C before testing. Compacted specimens were tumbled each in turn in a Los Angeles (LA) Abrasion Drum (Figure 3) without steel spheres for 300 rotations. The difference in the specimens mass before (m_1) and after (m_2) testing was determined according to (1) and referred to as Mass Loss (ML).

$$ML = \frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1} \times 100 \tag{1}$$

2) Tensile Strength Ratio (TSR)

The TSR test was performed according to AASHTO T-283 to evaluate the moisture susceptibility of asphalt mixtures. The specimen size was 150mm diameter and 95±5mm height. The samples were divided into two groups: the first group was placed at environment conditions at 25°C for 2h before dry condition testing. The second group was conditioned in a water bath at 60°C for 24h and then at 25°C for 2h before testing.

Fig. 3. Mixtures in the dynamic shear rheometer device (a) Abrasion drum, (b) CML before testing, (c) CML after testing, (d) CML before and after testing.

Fig. 4. a) Wet samples, (b) dry samples, (c) IDT testing.

3) Indirect Tensile Tension (IDT)

The IDT test was used to determine the tensile strength (S_t) of the mixture specimens (Figure 5). The IDT specimens had 150mm diameter and 95 ± 5mm height. The specimens were air-conditioned at 25°C before testing. Tensile strength at failure (S_t) was measured according to (2):

$$S_t = \frac{200 \times P_{max}}{\pi \times t \times D} \tag{2}$$

Fig. 5. IDT instrument.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table III shows the test results for unconditioned and AASHTO R30-conditioned mixtures. The value for a given test

method represents the average of the measurement of 3 samples replicated for the mixture test.

TABLE III. RESULT OF MIXTURE AND BINDER TESTING

Condition	MIX	IDT (kPa)	TSR (%)	CML (%)	DSR (°C)
Unaged	M0	879.36	54.26	10.52	64
	M1	877.90	80.50	18.39	88
	M2	781.47	86.38	14.17	76
	M3	937.97	78.03	13.98	82
	M4	765.38	82.43	15.12	70
AASHTO R30	M0	967.29	57.44	14.82	—
	M1	2192.97	41.32	22.69	—
	M2	1566.42	55.11	21.30	—
	M3	2270.16	38.72	23.41	—
	M4	2166.28	44.47	19.14	—

1) Statistical Assessment of the Mixtures

Table IV shows a statistical assessment of the obtained results that are mentioned in Table III for the 5 mixtures. The values of Δ are calculated by subtracting the results of each mix (M1, M2, M3, and M4) from M0. The P-values were obtained from the statistical analysis of the t-test, which indicates the significance of the difference between the sample's results. If the P-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant difference between the results. If it is higher than 0.05, then there is no significant difference.

2) Dynamic Shear Rheometer (DSR)

In DSR testing, it appears that with the addition of polymers, the failure temperature rises. M3 has a failure temperature of 82°C, and M2 one of 76°C. This concludes that the failure temperature of the binder increases with an increase in the percentage of Titan7205. Also, M1 has a higher failure temperature (88°C) than M4. Comparing the additives to M0, they all show an increase in the failure temperature. Overall,

the addition of polymers to HMA can improve its rutting resistance.

3) Indirect Tensile Strength (IDT)

Figure 6 shows the test result of IDT. Comparing M0 to the other additives for unconditioned, the results show that M0 has a similar or higher St value than the other additives. Subsequently, M2 and M4 have similar performance, while M3 shows a slightly higher St value. All modified HMA in the study display a higher St value compared to M0 for AASHTO R30 conditioning. Comparing the additives with each other, the St value of M2 is less than that of the other additives. In addition, there is statistical difference between M2 and the other additives (M1, M3, and M4). Comparing M2 with M3, M3 had higher St value, while M2 still had higher St value than M0. Overall, when comparing M0 to other additives, M0 shows similar or less crack resistance in most cases. Conditioned mixtures exhibit higher St values than the unconditioned mixtures.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the unconditioned with AASHTO R30 conditioned IDT.

TABLE IV. STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF MIXTURES

Condition	MIX	IDT (kPa)				TSR (%)				CML (%)			
		Δ (Mi-M0)	P-value	T-test	Significant differ	Δ (Mi-M0)	P-value	T-test	Significant differ	Δ (Mi-M0)	P-value	T-test	Significant differ
Unaged	M1	-1.49	0.82	B	No	26.24	<0.01	AB	Yes	7.87	<0.01	A	Yes
	M2	-97.89	<0.01	C	Yes	32.13	<0.01	B	Yes	3.65	<0.01	C	Yes
	M3	85.62	<0.01	A	Yes	23.77	<0.01	B	Yes	3.46	<0.01	C	Yes
	M4	-113.98	<0.01	D	Yes	28.17	<0.01	A	Yes	4.60	<0.01	B	Yes
AASHTO R30	M1	1225.67	<0.01	AB	Yes	-16.12	<0.01	C	Yes	7.87	<0.01	B	Yes
	M2	599.12	<0.01	C	Yes	-2.33	0.18	A	No	6.49	<0.01	C	Yes
	M3	1302.87	<0.01	A	Yes	-18.72	<0.01	C	Yes	8.59	<0.01	A	Yes
	M4	1198.99	<0.01	B	Yes	-12.97	<0.01	B	Yes	4.33	<0.01	D	Yes

4) Tensile Strength Ratio (TSR)

All the additives exhibit a higher value of TSR than M0, which means that they all improved the moisture resistance of the mixture. M1, M3, and M4 show similar performance, while M2 shows slightly better moisture resistance. Also, M2 shows a statistically significant difference compared to the other additives. Considering AASHTO R30 conditioning, it appears that when comparing the additives with M0, the control M0 has similar or better moisture resistance after AASHTO R30 conditioning. M2 has better moisture resistance after AASHTO R30 conditioning than the other additives. Referring to Table

IV, M2 has a significantly higher TSR value, while its TSR value is statistically not significantly different from that of M0. Overall, M0 shows similar performance before and after conditioning. All the additives show higher moisture resistance before conditioning and lower moisture resistance after conditioning. M2 has a higher TSR value than other additives in unconditioned and AASHTO R30 conditions. For unconditioned mixtures, M2 shows better performance than M0, while it shows similar performance after conditioning to M0.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the Unconditioned with AASHTO R30 Conditioned TSR.

5) Cantabro Mass Loos (CML)

Referring to Figure 8 for the unconditioned case, all additives have a higher CML value than M0, which means the additives reduce mixture durability. Also, there are statistically significant differences between M0 and the other additives. M1 has lower durability compared to the other additives, while M2, M3, and M4 show similar performance. All additives have a CML value higher than M0 after AASHTO R30 conditioning. M4 is slightly more durable than the other additives followed by M2. The CML value of M2 is statistically significant different compared to other additives. In summary, AASHTO R30 mass loss values increase more than the unconditioned ones, which is logical given that the durability of asphalt mixtures should decrease over time with aging. All the additives have a CML value higher than M0 either unconditioned or after AASHTO R30 conditioning. In most cases, M2 shows similar or better performance compared to the other additives.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the unconditioned with AASHTO R30-conditioned CML.

6) Cost Comparison

The comparison of polymer additive prices is conducted to show the economic impact of their utilization. Two supplier's prices were used, and the prices were averaged. Table V shows the price per ton for each additive. Crumb rubber has the lowest price, and SBS the highest. The price of the Titan7205 is slightly lower than that of the SBS, which makes it a preferable choice over the SBS. Comparing the performance of Titan7205

to other additives with respect to price, Titan7205 could be another alternative to be used with HMA.

TABLE V. ADDITIVE PRICE COMPARISON

Additives	Unit	Price (SR/ton)
SBS	1 Ton	9000
CR	1 Ton	2750
Titan 7205	1 Ton	8000

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This article's objective was to evaluate the performance of Hot Mix Asphalt (HMA) modified with Titan7205 polymers. Two percentages (3% and 5%) of Titan 7205 were utilized in this study and showed similar or better performance compared to other mixtures (M0, M1, and M4). Both percentages of Titan 7205 (M2 and M3) met the required failure temperature in this study (72°C). Generally, the addition of polymers to HMA improves the rutting resistance. Both Titan 7205 mixtures (M2 and M3) showed similar or better cracking resistance and better moisture resistance.

Considering the overall performance and economic viability of the mixtures, Titan7205 could be an alternative additive to be used in HMA. Subsequently, additional investigation is recommended to better understand the performance of Titan7205 with HMA.

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Enhancing the Properties of Sulfate-Resisting Cement

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ABSTRACT

Sulfate-resisting cement is used in construction works when a sulfate attack is probable. This type of cement withstands sulfates due to its low C_3A content. On the other hand, the decrease in the quantity of C_3A leads to a reduction in the rate of early strength development. To overcome this problem, a hardening accelerator was added to the cement mix. To estimate the effect of the accelerator on some properties of hardened cement, compressive and flexural strength, and drying shrinkage tests were carried out. Four series of cement mortar mixes were made. The hardening accelerator was not added to the control series, while it was added to the others with three different percentages (of cement mass) of 0.5, 1, and 1.5%. The results revealed that the hardening accelerator enhances the compressive strength of all mortar ages while it slightly promotes flexural strength only at early ages. It was also observed that the hardening accelerator strongly inhibits the drying shrinkage strain.

Keywords-sulfate-resisting cement; hardening accelerator; flexural strength; compressive strength; drying shrinkage

I. INTRODUCTION

When a cement matrix is in contact with soil contaminated with sulfate, harmful reactions occur in the presence of water. These reactions, which are called the sulfate attack, finally lead to the deterioration of the construction member. In hardened cement paste, tricalcium aluminate hydrate (the result of reacting C_3A with water) reacts with sulfate to produce calcium sulfoaluminate (ettringite - $3CaO \cdot Al_2O_3 \cdot 3CaSO_4 \cdot 32H_2O$), which is formed within the framework of the hydrated cement paste and has a larger volume than the reacted solid material. At early ages, the ettringite is helpful as it fills the capillary pores and thus makes the cement matrix denser [1]. However, if this reaction continues, even when the cement takes its strength, it leads to damages of the cement matrix due to the stresses generated by the expanded ettringite [1-3]. To overcome this problem and enhance the resistance of mortar or concrete of a structural member to the sulfate attack, Sulfate-Resisting (SR)-cement is employed. This type of cement resists the sulfate due to its low C_3A content [4]. On the other hand, C_3A is one of the cement phases that contribute to the early strength of cement paste due to its fast hydration reaction. Since SR-cement has low content of C_3A , it has a low early strength. There are cases that require high early strength of cement matrix, e.g. when the need arise to remove formworks in a short time for reuse in casting another member, whereas the concrete should acquire adequate strength before removing the formwork [5-7]. In addition, speeding up the early strength development is one of the most important requirements for repair works [8]. It gets worse when the construction work is

carried out in cold weather, as cold slows down the reaction of the cement compounds.

Generally, in construction works, different types of accelerators [9] are used to reach the required strength quickly enough. The accelerators act as the reaction catalyst for one or more cement phases, specifically C_3S , C_3A , and C_4AF [10-15]. According to BS EN 934-2 [16], the accelerators are subdivided into two main categories, setting accelerators which are used to reduce setting time and hardening accelerators for increasing the early strength of cement paste. In the implementation of various construction works and researches, different types of accelerators have been used with Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) [17-19].

The studies conducted on the effect of accelerators on the performance of SR-cement are rare, with [20] being one of the few. The current study aims to increase the early strength of this type of cement by adding a hardening accelerator. Hence, compressive and flexural strength tests were investigated. In addition, drying shrinkage tests were performed to check the cracking tendency as it affects the durability and the sustainability which is the focus of many studies nowadays [22-24].

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

A. Mortar Mix Properties and Proportions

The SR-cement used in this research is classified under the type CEM I-SR 3 [24]. Its fineness is $4875\text{cm}^2/\text{g}$, while its initial and final setting times are 2:45h and 4:45h, respectively. The oxide and the compound compositions of this cement are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. COMPOSITIONS OF SR-CEMENT

Oxide compositions (%)		Compound Compositions (%)	
CaO	60.71	C ₃ S	48.48
SiO ₂	20.02	C ₂ S	21.06
Al ₂ O ₃	4.23	C ₃ A	2.30
Fe ₂ O ₃	5.27	C ₄ AF	16.02
MgO	1.81		
SO ₃	2.38		
LOI	3.69		

The SR-cement has lower strength than OPC at early ages. To enhance the strength of SR-cement at early ages, a chloride-free hardening accelerator type SikaRapid-1 (Table II) was added to the cement mix. Its performance meets the requirements of [16].

TABLE II. TECHNICAL DATA OF THE HARDENING ACCELERATOR

Property	Quantities and values
pH	8.3
Chloride ion	Nil
Conventional dry material content	35%
Density	1.17kg/l at +23°C
Viscosity	10mPa.s at +23°C

The water/cement ratio is designed to be 0.45 as per ACI 225R recommendation [25], which states that this ratio should be between 0.45 and 0.50 where there is a potential for sulfate attack. To evaluate the effect of the hardening accelerator, 4 series of SR-cement mortar mixes were prepared. The hardening accelerator was not added to the mix of the control series (S0.0). For the other series, i.e. S0.5, S1.0 and S1.5, the accelerator was added with percentages (of cement mass) equal to 0.5, 1, and 1.5%, respectively. It is worth mentioning that these percentages were chosen to be within the range mentioned in the data sheet of SikaRapid-1. The water/cement ratio varied from one series to another to achieve the same consistency as the control series. Primarily, this study was conducted to improve the performance of SR-cement at early ages by using a hardening accelerator. To avoid the effect of other factors and to achieve reliable results, standard sand conforming to BS EN 196-1 [26] was used to the mortar of all the series. This sand is natural, siliceous, and consists of rounded particles whose size distribution is presented in Table III. The cement: sand ratio was set at 1:3 for all the mixes.

TABLE III. PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF THE STANDARD SAND

Square mesh size (mm)	2	1.6	1	0.5	0.16	0.08
Cumulative sieve residue (%)	0	7	33	67	87	100

When an admixture is to be added, it is recommended that the prepared mix should have the same aggregate:cement ratio with the control mix, while the water percentage should be changed to maintain the same consistency [27]. Therefore, the water/cement ratio of the control mix (0.45) was manipulated by relying on the flow table test, which was performed according to BS EN 1015-3 [28]. Firstly, the test was carried out for the control series where the mean of 4 measured diameters of mortar was 128mm. Subsequently, for the other series, water was adjusted to achieve the same diameter of control mix (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Flow table test.

The constituents of mortar of all the mixes are shown in Table IV. The method proposed by [27] was adopted in mixing the materials of the 4 series.

TABLE IV. PROPERTIES AND QUANTITIES OF MORTAR COMPOSITIONS

Mortar compositions and properties	Quantity (kg/m ³)			
Cement: CEM I-SR 3	586			
Standard sand 0.8/2	1758			
Series symbol *	S0.0	S0.5	S1.0	S1.5
Water	263.70	261.75	256.54	251.33
Hardening accelerator	0.0	2.93	5.86	8.79

* For each symbol, the letter (S) refers to the word (series) while the number next to it indicates the percentage of the added hardening accelerator (%).

B. Specimen Preparation and Curing Conditions

The hardening accelerator is defined as an admixture that increases the rate of early strength development [16]. Therefore, flexural and compressive strength tests were performed to evaluate the accelerator effects. To perform the flexural and the compressive strength tests, according to [26], 3 specimens with dimensions of 40×40×160mm were prepared from each batch of mortar. The fresh mortar was cast into the prismatic molds in 2 layers and each layer was compacted by using the jolting apparatus (60 jolts per layer), (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. A prisms-mold with 3 holes (of 40×40×160mm) installed on the jolting apparatus, before cooling the mortar and at the end of compacting (2 layers each 60 jolts). (a) Top view, (b) side view.

To assess the durability of the hardened cement mortar in terms of restricted members and to verify the possibility of cracking that may occur, the drying shrinkage test was carried out. The test was conducted according to ASTM C 596 [29]. Four prisms were prepared from each batch of mortar. The

molds that are used for this test have internal dimensions of 25×25×285mm, where 2 stainless steel studs (gauge studs) are inserted at their ends to be embedded into the casted mortar. The distance between the inner ends of the gauge studs which is called gauge length, is 250mm [30] (Figure 3). The mortar was placed in two layers and each layer was compacted with a tamper [31].

Fig. 3. Shrinkage mold of 25×25×285mm with steel studs inserted at the ends.

For all the mentioned tests, after casting the mortars, each mold was covered with a plate of glass to prevent water evaporation. Then, the molds were placed in a moist air cabinet where the temperature was 23°C and the Relative Humidity (RH) was 95%. After 24h, the specimens of the flexural strength test were taken out of the molds and then placed in a water tank until the age of testing. It should be noted that BS EN 196-1 [26] recommends performing the compressive test on the halves of the prisms broken by the flexural test. For shrinkage molds, ASTM C 596 [29] states that when the strength of the mortar is inadequate to allow proper removal from the molds at 24h, the moist curing in the molds is continued for another 24h. Since sulfate-resisting cement has low strength at an early age, the specimens were kept in molds (in a humid air cabinet) for up to 48h. After they were removed from the molds, the specimens were stored in water for another 24h [29]. At the age of 72h, the specimens were transferred to be stored under laboratory conditions at 23°C and 52% RH, until the end of the test.

C. Experimental Procedure of Flexural Strength Test

This test is used to evaluate indirectly the tensile strength. The flexural strength test was performed using the 3-point loading method (Figure 4) according to [26]. The load was applied at a rate of 50N/s until the fracture of the hardened mortar prism. As stated in [26], the two halves of a broken prism were covered with a damp cloth and were kept for the compression strength test. To evaluate the effect of the hardening accelerator on the flexural strength at early ages and to ensure that it does not have detrimental effects at late ages, the test was carried out at different ages of SR-cement mortar (1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days). For each of the 4 series, 5 mixes were prepared (1 per age) where 3 prisms were cast from each, i.e. 15 prisms were cast for each series with a total of 60 prisms being used in flexural strength tests. The flexural strength R_f was calculated according to:

$$R_f = \frac{1.5 \times F_f \times l}{b^3} \tag{1}$$

where F_f is the maximum applied load to the middle of a prism, b is the square section side of a prism, and l is the distance between the supports.

Fig. 4. Mechanical strength test: (a) Flexural strength test, (b) compressive strength test executed on the halves of a broken prism from the flexural test.

D. Experimental Procedure of the Compressive Strength Test

The compressive strength test was conducted according to [26]. Depending on this standard, the test was carried out on the two halves of a prism broken in the flexural test. Thus, as the flexural test, the compressive test was done at the mortar ages of 1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days, for each of the 4 series. Two auxiliary plates of 40×40mm were placed over and under a prism half during the loading time to make the applying load be projected on a length of 40mm (and an area of 40×40mm). The prism half was laterally centered to the platens and longitudinally in such a way that the end face of the prism overhanged the auxiliary plates. The load was applied with a rate of 2500N/s (Figure 4). For each series, since the flexural strength test was performed on 3 prisms per age, the compressive strength test was performed on 6 prism halves at each of the 5 testing ages (1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days). Therefore, for the 4 series, the compressive strength test was carried out on 120 prism halves.

E. Experimental Procedure of Drying Shrinkage Test

Drying shrinkage is a term used to describe the contraction in the length of a test specimen. The contraction is caused by any factor except externally applied forces under stated conditions of temperature and RH [29]. The drying shrinkage test was performed on 4 prisms (of 25×25×285mm) for each of the 4 series (S0.0, S0.5, S1.0, and S1.5) [29]. Thus, in total, 16 prisms were prepared for the test. The accuracy of the dial gauge used in this test was 0.001mm. It was reset to zero by a reference bar each time just before taking the reading of a test specimen (Figure 5). According to [29], at the age of 3 days (2 days in the moist air cabinet, plus 1 day in water), the specimens were removed from the water, swept with a wet cloth, and then the initial reading was taken and recorded. Subsequently, the specimens were placed in the air under laboratory conditions (temperature of 23°C and 55% RH) until the end of the test. Readings for each prism were taken after 4, 11, 18, and 25 days of air storage, according to [29]. For greater accuracy and certitude, additional readings were taken at 7, 14, 21, and 28 days (of air storage). At each testing time, the drying shrinkage (of a series) was computed as the average strain of the 4 test prisms. The drying shrinkage strain at any time of air storage is computed as:

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{(L_x - L_i)}{L_o} \tag{2}$$

where ϵ_x is the shrinkage strain of a specimen at time x , L_x is the reading of the specimen (stored under air conditions) at time x , L_i is the initial reading of a specimen, and L_o is the nominal

gauge length, i.e. the distance between studs (250mm, see Figure 3).

Fig. 5. Length change measuring instrument. (a) Adjusting the dial gauge to zero before taking a reading, (b) taking the reading of a specimen.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Flexural Strength Results

The experimental results of the flexural strength tests are shown in Figure 6. Each curve represents a series where each point represents the average strength of 3 prisms tested at a given age. It could be seen that there is not a big difference between the flexural strength from one series to another. However, the series containing accelerator (S0.5, S1.0, and S1.5) have slightly higher flexural strengths at the very early ages (1 and 3 days). Inversely, at late ages, the strengths of the control series become the highest. This result corresponds to the results (performed on cement type I) of [32-34]. These studies agree that the hardening accelerator increases the flexural strength of the cement matrix at early ages while at the late age of 28 days, the flexural strength becomes lower than (or about identical to that) of the control mix. It seems that, at late ages, the mix containing more accelerator becomes more brittle, thus exhibiting lower flexural strength. In [14, 35, 36], it was found that the chloride-free hardening accelerator primarily speeds up the hydration of the tricalcium aluminate where ettringite forms. Hence, for the present study (where a chloride-free hardening accelerator is used), at early ages, the ettringite fills out the capillary pores and thus increases the strength of the cement matrix. Therefore, the mix that includes the hardening accelerator will have less pores and higher strength. With time and in the presence of water, the hydration reactions of the other cement phases proceed to form the main cement product of Calcium Silicate Hydrate (C-S-H). This product begins to fill the capillary pores that have not been filled by ettringite. C-S-H is the densest component of the hydrated cement paste [1]. In contrast, ettringite is an expansive compound, and its formation increases the porosity of the cement matrix as a whole [1, 38]. Porous materials are generally considered as brittle materials and have low tensile and flexural strength [38, 39]. Accordingly, at late ages, the mix that does not contain or contains a smaller amount of the

accelerator will be denser, less brittle, and will have higher flexural strength than the other mixes.

The relative flexural strength (strength of a hardened mortar containing the accelerator to the reference one at a given age) was calculated and is presented in Figure 7 to clarify this result in another way. It is clear that S0.5 has the highest relative flexural strength, i.e. the strength of the mix with the lowest percentage of the accelerator (0.5%) is higher than the other two mixes with accelerator for all the cement mortar ages.

Fig. 6. Flexural strength development with age for the four series.

Fig. 7. Relative flexural strengths of the series with accelerator vs. mortar age.

B. Compressive Strength Results

The results of the compressive strength tests are shown in Figure 8. Each point in a separate series represents the average compressive strength of 6 halves (of the 3 broken prisms at the flexural test). It could be seen that the control series has lower compressive strength than the other series for all mortar ages. This result indicates that the hardening accelerator has a beneficial effect on the development of compressive strength at early as well as at late ages (until 28 days) of the mortar. This result agrees with the findings in [32, 33], where the hardening accelerator increases the compressive strength at early ages and maintains it higher than the mix without accelerator even at the late age of at 28 days. The results of [34] also confirm that the hardening accelerator increases the compressive strength of the cement matrix at the early ages, while at the late age of 28 days, the strength of the mix with the accelerator becomes the lowest. The hardening accelerator increases the reaction rate of the cement components, especially C₃A (to form ettringite), and leads to the early completion of this cementation phase. Since ettringite is an expansive material, it fills the capillary

pores, increasing the strength of the cement matrix at early ages [1]. Due to the low amount of C_3A in the SR-cement, and with the presence of the accelerator, this compound appears to be consumed early. Therefore, it is not expected to continue producing ettringite which has a detrimental effect on the cement matrix when it is formed at a later age, i.e. when the cement has become sufficiently hard. Thus, the mix with accelerator has higher compressive strength than the control one, even at late ages. To evaluate the best percentage of the accelerator, the relative strength was computed, i.e. the compressive strength of a series to that of the control series (Figure 9). From this Figure, it is clear that the different percentages of the accelerator (0.5, 1, and 1.5%) have about the same effect on the strength of a given age of mortar, even though it seems that S1.0 has the best performance since its relative strengths are higher than those of S0.5 and S1.5 for almost all the mortar ages. That means 1% is the best percentage of the accelerator to be added in order to enhance compressive strength.

Fig. 8. Compressive strength development with age of the four series.

Fig. 9. Relative compressive strengths of the series with accelerator vs. mortar age.

C. Drying Shrinkage Results

The readings (4 prisms per series) were taken during the air storage period of 4, 7, 11, 14, 18, 21, 25, and 28 days. The average shrinkage strain of the 4 prisms was computed at each test time (Figure 10). As shown in Figure 10, for about all the test times, the drying shrinkage strain of the control series is higher than those of the other series. Also, as the percentage of the hardening accelerator is increased, the shrinkage strain decreases. That could be related to the fact that the drying shrinkage decreases with increasing strength of the cement paste [40]. Since the strength of SR-cement mortar has been

enhanced due to the hardening accelerator (Figure 8), the specimens that include the accelerator exhibit lower shrinkage than the control ones. However, in [41], it was found that the drying shrinkage strain increases with increasing percentage of accelerator. To clarify the extent of the effect of the accelerator, the relative shrinkage strain (the strain of a mortar with the accelerator to the reference one at a specific age) was calculated (Figure 11). At the end of the shrinkage test (after 28 days of air storage), the strains of S0.5, S1.0, and S1.5, respectively, became 0.7, 0.62, and 0.55 of that of the control series.

Fig. 10. Drying shrinkage strain vs. time of air storage.

Fig. 11. Relative drying shrinkage of mixes with accelerator vs. time of air storage.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Since the sulfate-resisting cement has a slow rate of early strength development, this study aimed to increase the strength at early ages by adding a hardening accelerator. To evaluate the effects of the accelerator, four series of cement mortar mixes were implemented (using standard sand). The accelerator was not added to the mix of the control series, while for the other three mixes, it was added with different percentages of 0.5, 1, and 1.5%. Flexural and compressive strength tests were carried out at different mortar ages (from 1 day to 28 days). Drying shrinkage test was also performed to check the cracking potential. From the obtained results, the following points could be drawn:

- For the flexural strength, the results were approximately close. However, at the early ages of cement mortar, the strengths of the series with the hardening accelerator are somewhat higher than that of the control. Inversely, at late ages, the flexural strength of the control series becomes the

highest. Comparing the series containing the accelerator, it was observed that the mix with 0.5% accelerator has the best performance since its relative strength is higher than those of the other series for all mortar ages.

- The compressive strength of the control series is lower than those of the series with the hardening accelerator for all mortar ages. Although the relative compressive strength decreases with age, it has never been less than one, i.e. the compressive strength of the series with the accelerator never becomes less than that of the control. This indicates that the hardening accelerator enhances the compressive strength at the early age without damaging effects at later ages. It was also found that, for all mortar ages, the highest compressive strength is obtained by adding 1% accelerator.
- The hardening accelerator strongly decreases the drying shrinkage strain. As the percentage of the hardening accelerator increases, the drying shrinkage values decrease. After 28 days of air storage, the strain of S1.5 became about half (0.55) of that of the control series.

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A Force-based Method for the Numerical Simulation of a Reinforced Concrete Shear Wall Building

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ABSTRACT

Reinforced Concrete (RC) shear walls are structural elements that resist lateral loads. This research aims to present the numerical modeling of RC shear walls in order to evaluate the seismic performance of structures. Various types of numerical models of RC frame elements are implemented in nonlinear analysis packages. These numerical models are based on different theories and assumptions, something that poses a significant difficulty to practicing engineering and limits confidence in the analysis of the numerical results. In this study, inelastic force-based elements and distributed plasticity methods are used for the modeling of the inelastic behavior of these elements (infrmFB). The efficiency of the inelastic force-based element and distributed plasticity method is evaluated through the comparison with the experimental results of a shear wall structure subjected to seismic loadings. The accuracy of the numerical model is assessed in terms of top displacement, inter-story drift, base shear force, and the absolute maximum values of the overturning moment.

Keywords-shear wall; infrmFB element; force-based; nonlinear numerical model; RC frame elements; distributed plasticity

I. INTRODUCTION

Shear walls are used as the primary lateral load-resistant system of Reinforced Concrete (RC) structures. Earthquake engineering is focused on simulating the nonlinear response of shear wall structures to seismic excitations, through experimental studies [1, 2] and numerical modeling [3-5]. New performance-based seismic design guidelines [6] require that structures should be analyzed using nonlinear static pushover analysis or nonlinear dynamic analysis to control global and local demands. The use of nonlinear frame analysis necessitates the availability of robust and computationally efficient models for performing computations in a reasonable amount of time [7, 22]. In the numerical modeling approach, ground motion loading analysis of RC shear wall buildings is generally conducted with beam-column elements, which should be capable of fully taking into consideration the inelastic behavior of the actual member [8, 23]. Distributed plastic hinges in

beam-column elements used to model the nonlinear behavior of RC structural elements are thus required in order to simulate the seismic response and to evaluate the performance of structural systems [9].

Several studies have investigated the performance of different nonlinear modeling strategies for the numerical simulation of the response of a RC shear wall subjected to seismic loads. Authors in [10] studied the numerical strategy 3S-R adopted in the laboratory for the simulation of the nonlinear behavior of the specimen. Multi-fiber Timoshenko beam elements were used for the finite element mesh of the RC walls. Constitutive mechanical damage models were used for RC. The proposed modeling strategy accurately describes the overall behavior of the structure. The comparison with the experimental results helped identifying the shortcomings of the original numerical model and suggested remedial measures to improve its performance. Authors in [11] studied the nonlinear dynamic behavior and response of RC walls. They used a

continuous damage model, and simplified numerical strategies were proposed. They chose two dimensional (2D) Euler beam theory for the modeling of walls whose behavior was controlled effectively by bending. For 3D problems, a multi-fiber Timoshenko beam element with higher-order interpolation functions was developed. As for walls with a small slenderness ratio, they used the Equivalent RC model. Comparisons with the experimental results of RC walls tested on a shaking table or reaction wall showed the advantages and limitations of the approach. Authors in [12] developed a constitutive model for RC under cyclic or dynamic loading based on existing experimental results. The proposed model featured hysteretic characteristics of concrete in tension, compression, shear along the crack direction, and the bond between concrete and the reinforcing bars. They also developed a non-orthogonal multi-directional smeared crack model for the realistic representation of concrete cracking under stress reversals. The applicability and efficiency of the proposed models were demonstrated through simulation with various types of RC specimens subjected to cyclic loads or seismic excitation on a shaking table. Authors in [13] studied the nonlinear response of RC moment-resisting frames considering the bond-slip effect between concrete and bars along the lengths of the beam, column, and common elements. They used the fiber model theory to simulate the behavior of RC in the nonlinear domain. The ideal bond hypothesis between concrete and bars has been removed. They showed that the proposed method can accurately model the nonlinear behavior of RC frames by comparing the experimental and numerical models of two specimens under cyclic loading.

In this study, the structural response is assessed by nonlinear dynamic (time history) analysis to estimate the seismic response using the force-based inelastic frame elements (infrmFB) method. Emphasis is made on the applicability of the representative numerical model of the RC shear wall. Its efficiency is evaluated by comparison with the experimental results for a 7-story RC structural wall [14] that can be readily performed with existing software packages.

II. NUMERICAL TOOL AND MODELING STRATEGIES

The numerical analysis developed and described in this paper and the nonlinear modeling strategies were conducted using the SeismoStruct v7 (SeismoSoft and 2021) [15]. The program includes models for the representation of the behavior of spatial frames under static and dynamic loading, considering both material and geometric nonlinearities. Seven types of analysis can be performed: dynamic and static time history analysis, conventional and adaptive pushover, incremental dynamic analysis, modal analysis, and static analysis (possibly nonlinear) under quasi-permanent loading. All the features are based on force or displacement formulations. While the evaluated numerical models are based on different assumptions, the input parameters for these elements are primarily physical properties, such as section geometry and the uniaxial behavior of materials. Hence, as long as the limitation of the element can be clearly defined, engineers can use the

elements with confidence and without much effort to calibrate model parameters. Therefore, in this study, the numerical simulation of NEES-UCSD RC shear wall structure was investigated using the nonlinear modeling strategy of force-based inelastic frame element (infrmFB). The experimental results obtained from previous shaking table tests of these shear wall structures are compared with the results of the numerical nonlinear seismic analysis. The experimental study uses the NEES-UCSD design [16, 17, 24, 25]. The response of an RC structure consisting of shear walls is simulated under the seismic loading recorded during the 1994 Northridge earthquake.

III. ELEMENT FORMULATION – THE FLEXIBILITY (FORCE) METHOD

In this study, the force fields are described by the flexibility method and the nonlinear analysis of the RC shear wall structures is conducted using the infrmFB method. RC structures that consist of shear walls are simulated by a 7-story system available from the European Laboratory for Structural Assessment (ELSA) [14]. The numerical analysis results are compared with the experimental results in terms of absolute values of base overturning moment, base shear force, and tip displacement. A time history plot of the top displacement response of the shear wall structure is also used for comparison. This can easily be done with existing software packages. The structural response is evaluated by nonlinear dynamic (time history) analysis to estimate the seismic response:

$$D(x) = b(x) Q \quad (1)$$

where $b(x)$ contains the force interpolation functions, which relates the generalized nodal forces Q to the internal forces $D(x)$. Replacing ΔD from the incremental form of (1) in the inverse from the constitutive relation $\Delta D = k \Delta d$, namely $\Delta d(x) = K^{-1} \Delta D(x)$ yields the incremental deformation field [18]:

$$\Delta d(x) = f(x) \Delta D(x) = f(x) b(x) \Delta Q \quad (2)$$

where $f(x) = K^{-1}(x)$ is the section flexibility matrix. The principle of virtual forces leads of the compatibility condition are described by (3):

$$q = \int_0^L b^T(x) d(x) dx \quad (3)$$

and its linearization:

$$F \Delta Q = r \quad (4)$$

in the form of a displacement-force relation, where q = element end displacement and

$$F = \frac{\partial q}{\partial Q} = \int_0^L b^T(x) f(x) b(x) dx \quad (5)$$

is the element flexibility matrix, while ΔQ and r are the vectors of force increments and residual displacement, respectively. Note that a meaningful expression for the flexibility matrix F can only be derived for the beam element without rigid-body modes [19].

Fig. 1. Discretisation of the cross-section and section fiber.

IV. INELASTIC FORCE-BASED FRAME ELEMENT

This force-based 3D beam-column element type can model spatial frame members with geometric and material nonlinearities. Cross-section-related stress-strain states of beam-column elements are obtained by integrating the nonlinear uniaxial material responses of individual fibers whose cross-sections are divided by the depth of the cross-section. The infrmFB element is the most accurate of the four SeismoStruct frame element types, due to the fact that the inelastic behavior can be captured over the entire structural element length, even when using one element per structure. Therefore, it provides very accurate analysis results and allows users to output element chord rotations for seismic code validation (e.g. Eurocode 8, NTC-08, KANEPE, FEMA-356, ATC-40, etc.). One must define the number of section fibers used in the equilibrium calculations performed on each integrated section of the element. The ideal number of profile fibers sufficient to adequately reproduce the stress-strain distribution across the cross-section of the element depends on the element's geometry and material properties and on the element's degree of inelasticity. As a rough rule of thumb, the user can assume that sections made of a single material are typically well represented by 100 fibers. In more complex sections, subjected to high inelasticity, typically 200 or more fibers should be used. A sensitivity study on a case-by-case basis can undoubtedly determine the optimum number of cut fibers [20].

V. STRUCTURE, MATERIALS, AND LOADS

In the present study, a full-scale 7-story structure with two main perpendicular walls: the web wall and the flange wall linked with slabs (Figure 2), was modeled. A pre-cast column is needed to limit torsional behavior and gravity columns to support the slabs are also present. The RC frame was tested on the NEES (Earthquake Engineering Simulation Network) Large High-Performance Outdoor Shake Table at the University of California at San Diego (UCSD)'s Englekirk Structural Engineering under dynamic conditions [12] by applying 4 subsequent uniaxial ground motions. The structure has been designed with the displacement-based capacity approach for a site in Los Angeles. Hence, the lateral design forces are smaller than those currently specified in U.S. building codes for regions of high seismic risk.

A. Structural Geometry

A 7-story RC earthquake-resistant wall designed by the NEES was considered in this study. It was seismically loaded on a shaking table at the UCSD [16]. This structure comprises

two types of shear walls located on the central axis and the pier columns on the corners of the structure. One of the shear walls is called the web wall, while the other is the flange wall. The walls are built perpendicular to each other. The slab is connected to the flange wall, and slotted connections join the two shear walls. The basement and floor heights are 0.76m and 2.74m, respectively. The total height of the structure is 19.96m. The structure is fastened to the ground, and its mass is 226 tons. The cross-sections of the flange wall and the web wall are different. The width of the flange wall is 4.88m and the thicknesses of the flange wall are 203mm and 152mm for the last floor and the other floors, respectively. The width of the web wall is 3.65m and its thickness is 203mm for the first and the last floor, while it is 152mm is for the other floors. The columns and shear walls supported 3.65x8.13m slabs on each floor. Post-tensioned precast piers are joined to the web wall and slabs via bracing. The full-scale RC shear wall structure details are shown in Figure 3. The geometry of the structure is summarized in Table I. The mass values of the structure are summarized in Table II. Two different views of the Finite Element (FE) model are presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. The 7-story RC shear wall building tested at the NEES.

TABLE I. GEOMETRY OF WALLS AND GRAVITY COLUMNS

Story	Web wall (m ²)	Flange wall (m ²)	Gravity volumns
7	3.658×0.203	4.877×0.152	d= 0.102 m, t = 0.033 m
6	3.658×0.152	4.877×0.152	d= 0.102 m, t = 0.028 m
5	3.658×0.152	4.877×0.152	d= 0.102 m, t = 0.028 m
4	3.658×0.152	4.877×0.152	d= 0.102 m, t = 0.028 m
3	3.658×0.152	4.877×0.152	d= 0.102 m, t = 0.028 m
2	3.658×0.152	4.877×0.152	d= 0.102 m, t = 0.028 m
1	3.658×0.203	4.877×0.152	d= 0.102 m, t = 0.028 m

Fig. 3. FE model view.

Fig. 4. Acceleration time history.

Fig. 5. Response spectrum of the accelerograms—5% damping.

B. Input Accelerations and Spectrum

The 1994 Northridge earthquake acceleration record, obtained from the Sylmar Olive View Medical Centre, was

used as the seismic input parallel to the web wall and was successfully applied to the shaking table with amplifying acceleration magnitude. The acceleration record of the earthquake is shown in Figure 4, with a peak ground acceleration of 0.85g. During the test, global and local measurements were made (displacements, accelerations, moments, etc.). The apparent mode was measured after the examination to follow the stiffness evolution. Detailed information on the experimental program and results are described in [20]. The response spectrum of these motions corresponding to 5% viscous damping is shown in Figure 5.

TABLE II. MASS OF DIFFERENT COMPONENTS

Components	Mass (tons)
Foundation	21.432
Slabs	101.604
Web wall	24.947
Flange wall	33.263
PT column	30.158
Gravity columns	4.717
Braces	0.181

C. Material Properties

Authors in [21] proposed a unified stress–strain approach for confined concrete applicable to both circular and rectangular-shaped transverse reinforcement. Its characteristic parameters are: $f_c = 16300\text{kPa}$, $f_t = 1900\text{kPa}$, $\epsilon_c = 0.002\text{m/m}$, and $E_c = 18975\text{MPa}$. The Menegotto-Pinto steel model is employed for defining the steel with the following properties: $E_s = 2.00\text{E}+ 008 \text{ kPa}$, $f_y = 343000 \text{ kPa}$, $\mu = 0.0024$. The materials considered at the design phase were: low-strength concrete of class C16/20 (CEN, 1991) and smooth reinforcement steel class Fe B22 k (Italian standards). The latter refers to smooth bars with a yield stress of 235MPa and ultimate strength of 365MPa.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Displacement

To evaluate the level of accuracy obtained with the modeling strategy, the first step is to assess the global response of the structure under seismic action. The roof time-displacement trends for the studied frame are presented in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Lateral displacements at the top versus time.

They are obtained by using inelastic force-based elements with distributed plasticity. The results indicate a good agreement with the experimental results when the time is less than 12s. For a time greater than 12s, the results diverge from the experimental ones. The lateral displacements from numerical analysis for each story are close to those of the experimental ones, see Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Maximum lateral displacement.

B. Inter Story Drift

The lateral deformability of structural systems is measured through the horizontal drift. In buildings, story drift Δ is the absolute displacement of any floor relative to the base. In contrast, inter-story drift δ defines the relative lateral displacement between two consecutive floors. The inter-story drift is generally expressed as the ratio δ/h of the displacement to the story height h . The drift of the roof Δ normalized by the total height H of the building (roof drift, Δ/H) is also used to quantify the lateral stiffness of structural systems. Figure 8 shows the vertical distribution of the maximum story drift of the main frame. The analytical model can predict the results of the 7 floors. However, at the base, the results are not close to the experimental values. For example, the difference in inter-story drift is about 0.67% in the first story, in the second story the difference is about 0.28%, and above this floor, the difference is negligible.

Fig. 8. Maximum inter-story drift ratio in the structure.

C. Base Overturning Moment

The base moment was determined by summing the moments at the base of the web and flange walls and the couple generated by the gravity columns that had about 10–24% contribution to the base overturning moment. Figure 9 compares the experimental and analytical values for a base moment using inelastic force-based elements with distributed plasticity. The results indicate that the peak values of the numerical and experimental results varied by about 25%.

Fig. 9. Comparison of experimental and analytical base moment values.

D. Story Shear Forces

Figure 10 compares the experimental and analytical values for base shear using inelastic force-based elements and distributed plasticity. Again, the numerical model underestimates the maximum measured base shear force value during the input of the motion by about 12%.

Fig. 10. Comparison of the experimental and analytical values of the shear force at the wall base.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the numerical simulation of reinforced concrete shear wall structure is undertaken in order to evaluate the efficiency of the numerical model inelastic force-based element with distributed plasticity. The numerical analysis results for the strongest input motion are compared with the experimental shaking table test results and the accuracy of the numerical model is assessed, considering the time-history

graphs of top displacement, inter-story drift, base shear force, and the absolute maximum values of the overturning moment. The main outcomes for the considered method are:

- The numerical simulation predicts a satisfactory maximum displacement, especially in the y direction, where the loading is more severe. There is a slight shifting in the time history curves, the same remarks apply to the inter-story drift curve, the base shear force, and the absolute maximum values of the overturning moment.
- The model was able to reproduce the response of the structure with good approximation. This confirms that the level of discretization and the type of numerical elements adopted in the model are sufficient to describe the nonlinear behavior of the reinforced concrete shear wall structures subjected to severe ground motion.

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A Simplified Energy Model Approach for the Determination of Long-Term Crack Width in Reinforced Concrete Elements

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ABSTRACT

The deformation of reinforced concrete elements is a main consideration during the design process due to its importance for the service life of structures. Deformation (deflections and cracking) control has an effect at both the design and construction stages. The determination of crack width based on simple code provisions, leads to conservative results, due to many affecting parameters being unknown. The exact determination of the crack width is a very complicated process with significant computational load. In the current paper, a simplified procedure is proposed for the prediction of crack width at different loading stages. The procedure is based on a previously published energy model that uses the integration of the moment-curvature relationship to take into consideration the load stage and most affecting design variables. The obtained results using the simplified model are then tested against previously published experimental data and a good agreement is shown.

Keywords-reinforced concrete elements; deformation; state diagrams; energy model; general and residual resources

I. INTRODUCTION

The serviceability limit state of concrete structures is one of the most important steps within the design. The determination of deflection and crack width using code provisions commonly results in conservative values due to many important variables affecting design being unknown [1-3]. The idealized stress-strain curves for both concrete and reinforcing steel as well as the equivalent stress block in concrete, represent some major causes of conservative estimations. Another design approach for crack width calculation in reinforced concrete structures under short-term loading was developed in [4], based on the actual strain distribution along the spacing between two adjacent cracks. Determination of the real stress-strain state of reinforced concrete elements at different stages of loading has always been a key task in reinforced concrete theory. Its implementation is largely associated with the development of general models of deformation. The fulfillment of most of validity requirements in the so-called "strength" models [5] has been impractical due to the use of an idealized equivalent rectangular stress block. In "deformation" models [6-8], the methodological unity of all calculations of reinforced concrete elements according to limit states can generally be ensured with the help of complete concrete stress-strain curves ($\sigma_c - \epsilon_c$). However, when integrating these curves or even using simplified forms of these diagrams [7, 8], the internal static uncertainty of the cross-section of reinforced concrete elements

must be calculated through numerous iterations, involving several empirical parameters and coefficients which result in a significant computational load.

The concrete deformation model [9] can be considered the closest one to the generalized model of reinforced concrete elements deformation today. It shows the reason for being impossible to build a generalized model of the deformation of reinforced concrete elements with just the help of a stress-strain diagram of concrete. The calculation of concrete deformation at any stage is not controlled by the concrete deformation diagrams, but by the moment-curvature relationship of the reinforced concrete element ($M - \phi$), which characterizes its stiffness. However, the concrete deformation model needs further development, especially in matters of assessing the actual technical condition of reinforced concrete elements and structures and calculating their capacity and deformations.

The current paper aims to predict long-term crack width based on energy modeling. The proposed procedure is largely based on the concrete deformation model [9], modified in order to simplify the calculations and lighten the computational load. The simplified model is then applied on a previously published case study.

II. MOMENT CURVATURE RELATIONSHIP

For the case of short-term loading, the relation between the moment and curvature will have the form presented in [9]:

$$M = \frac{E_c I_{cr} \cdot \phi - M_{uf} \cdot (\phi / \phi_{uf})^2}{1 + [E_c I_{cr} / M_{uf} - 2 / \phi_{uf}] \cdot \phi} \tag{1}$$

where E_c is the concrete's modulus of elasticity, I_{cr} is the moment of inertia of the cracked section, M_{uf} is the moment capacity at failure, and ϕ_{uf} is the limit value of the curvature at failure. For the case of long-term loading, the relation will follow the same curve of the short-term loading up to the value of service load (M_a, ϕ_a), then it will have a constant value of moment with the increase of the curvature. The increase in curvature after applying the service load will be due to the creep of concrete.

Solving (1) for the curvature, the following expression is provided in [10]:

$$\phi = \frac{\phi_{uf}}{2M_{uf}} \left[\left(1 - \frac{M}{M_{uf}} \right) \cdot E_c I_{cr} \phi_{uf} + 2M - \sqrt{\left(\left(1 - \frac{M}{M_{uf}} \right) \cdot E_c I_{cr} \phi_{uf} + 2M \right)^2 - 4M \cdot M_{uf}} \right] \tag{2}$$

For the case of short-term loading (Figure 1), three points must be defined. For a given concrete element with defined section properties, the value of moment at the three defined points in the shown moment-curvature curve can be calculated (M_a, M_u , and M_{uf}). The curvature at failure (ϕ_{uf}) can be determined using the hypothesis of concrete plane section under bending. Then the corresponding curvature at service and ultimate load (ϕ_a and ϕ_u) can be calculated using (2). These parameters are essential for use in the energy modeling approach.

III. A SIMPLIFIED APPROACH ON ENERGY MODELING

In general, it is known that in the deformation-force model, the main deformation and force parameters of the state of the element are interconnected by utilizing stiffness $EI = M/\phi$ [11-13]. The mentioned parameters can be combined using another characteristic: the energy consumed on the deformation of a reinforced concrete element per unit volume $W = M \cdot \phi$ [14]. Under such circumstances, the methodology for the calculation of the total energy of reinforced concrete elements can be used to determine the deformations directly. The energy modeling approach has been developed in [9, 10] and is summarized as follows: the total energy consumed at any stage of short-term loading can be determined by integrating (1) from null to the curvature value at the stage under consideration. As explained in [10], three integrations must be performed for the three defined stages on the moment curvature curve, at the service load, at the ultimate load and at the failure load. These three integration results are called $W_1(W_a), W_u$ and W_{uf} respectively (Figures 2-4).

Fig. 1. Moment-curvature relationship for short-term and long-term loading.

Fig. 2. Total energy consumed up to failure in case of short-term loading.

Fig. 3. Total energy consumed up to ultimate load in case of short-term loading.

Fig. 4. Total energy consumed up to failure in case of long-term loading.

The energy consumed in both cases of the short-term and the long-term loading must be equal [9]. The following relations can be used to determine both W_2 and W_3 :

$$W_u = W_1 + W_2 \quad (3)$$

$$W_{uf} = W_1 + W_2 + W_3 \quad (4)$$

The value of long-term loading curvature can be determined for both values of long-term (ϕ_l) and ultimate long-term curvature (ϕ_{ul}) using:

$$\phi_l = \frac{W_2}{M_a} + \phi_a \quad (5)$$

$$\phi_{ul} = \frac{W_{uf} - W_a}{M_a} + \phi_a \quad (6)$$

The application of the integrations presented in [10] for the determination of the consumed energy W_1 , W_u , and W_{uf} , has a significant computational load. Using a rough approach for the curve line portion of long-term moment-curvature relationship from ϕ_a to ϕ_u and from ϕ_u to ϕ_{uf} , the following equations can be derived for the calculation of W_2 and W_3 :

$$W_2 = \frac{M_a + M_u}{2} \cdot (\phi_u - \phi_a) \quad (7)$$

$$W_3 = \frac{M_u + M_{uf}}{2} \cdot (\phi_{uf} - \phi_u) \quad (8)$$

Solving (5) with (7) and (6) with (8), the corresponding curvatures for the long-term loading case will be:

$$\phi_l = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{M_u}{M_a} \right) (\phi_u - \phi_a) + \phi_a \quad (9)$$

$$\phi_{ul} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{M_{uf}}{M_u} \right) (\phi_{uf} - \phi_u) + \phi_l \quad (10)$$

Following this scheme, once the moment and the corresponding curvature at the three defined stages of short-term loading have been defined, the values of long-term curvature ϕ_l and ϕ_{ul} can be determined directly using (9) and (10). Knowing the curvature, the following formula can be used to determine the crack width [15]:

$$\phi = \frac{\varepsilon_{c,m} + w_{cr} / S_{cr} + \varepsilon_{ctu,m}}{d} \quad (11)$$

where s_{cr} and w_{cr} are the spacing and the normal crack width, $\varepsilon_{c,m}$ and $\varepsilon_{ctu,m}$ are the mean values of compression and ultimate strain in concrete at the tension side [9], respectively, and d is the effective depth of the concrete section.

The corresponding curvature ϕ_l is related to the crack width w_l and the average strain of compressed concrete $\varepsilon_{cl,m}$, as follows:

$$w_l = (\phi_l \cdot d - \varepsilon_{cl,m} - \varepsilon_{ctu,m}) \cdot S_{cr} \quad (12)$$

$$\varepsilon_{cl,m} = \varepsilon_{c,m} \cdot (1 + \varphi(t, t_0)) \quad (13)$$

where $\varphi(t, t_0)$ is the value of the creep coefficient of compressed concrete under the action of an external load with a duration of $(t - t_0)$ [7]. The value of crack width w_l can be determined from (10).

The crack width at failure under long-term loading will have the form:

$$w_{ul,cr} = (d \cdot \phi_{ul} - \varepsilon_{ctu,m} - \varepsilon_{ctu,m}) \cdot S_{cr} \quad (14)$$

IV. COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The theoretical prediction of long-term crack width has been performed for the 4 beams tested in [16]. The selected beams are simply supported with spans of 3500 mm and are reinforced by two longitudinal bars of 16 mm diameter. The concrete compressive strength at 28 days was 24.8 MPa. The cross-section of the beams is shown in Figure 5 and the details are given in Table I. The maximum crack width measured from the tests under long-term loading at 14 and 400 days are also presented in Table I along with the predicted values of crack width. The detailed results of the theoretically predicted long-term crack widths were compared with the experimental ones and the result is presented in Figures 6 and 7. The theoretically predicted crack width at different ages correspond well with experimental results. From both the theoretical and experimental results, it has been observed that the crack width increases rapidly at early ages up to the first 100 days, and then slowly increases. The maximum long-term crack width has been performed at an average age of 200 days.

Fig. 5. Cross section of the selected beams.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL RESULTS

Beam	C_b	C_s	s	Crack width (mm)			
				Experimental		Theoretical	
				14 days	400 days	14 days	400 days
B1-a	40	40	150	0.13	0.38	0.14	0.37
B1-b	40	40	150	0.05	0.18	0.08	0.17
B2-a	25	25	180	0.10	0.36	0.14	0.37
B2-b	25	25	180	0.05	0.18	0.08	0.17

Fig. 6. Comparison of the experimental and theoretical results of the long-term crack width in reinforced concrete beam B1-a and B2-a presented in [16].

Fig. 7. Comparison of the experimental and theoretical results of the long-term crack width in reinforced concrete beams B1-b and B2-b presented in [16].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a simplified approach is proposed for the calculation of the long-term crack width in concrete elements based on an energy model earlier model published in [10]. The simplified approach is applied on experimental data previously published in [16]. As shown, the simplified model shows good agreement with the experimental results. Future research should focus on testing the simplified model in other case studies. Further, the exact tradeoff between computational load and achieved accuracy should be investigated.

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Scalable Incident Reporting Framework: A Sensor and IoT Research

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ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) is one of the most rapidly emerging technologies. It is observed that while many devices/machines get connected in an application, it is a challenge for the IoT application designer to keep the application scalable. Scalability is the ability of a device/application to adapt to the changes in the environment and meet the changing needs in the future. The paper presents a layered IoT architecture and discusses issues related to the scalability of each layer. The best open-source technologies are explored. A novel system architecture of a scalable IoT framework is conceptualized in this paper. An application covering vehicle accident reporting is designed with the proposed framework. The application is tested in real-time using the standalone hardware and its ability to report the incidents is confirmed. The scalability metrics of the proposed framework are evaluated and the results are reported.

Keywords-IoT; scalability; sensors; computer networks; Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT)

I. INTRODUCTION

Scalability refers to the ability of an application or a computing process to work with ease at varying capacities of increased or decreased inputs and outputs. During the recent years the IoT technology has revolutionized the communication between physical devices, making computers sense information without human intervention. The number of devices that are getting connected is ever-increasing, along with the volume of data being processed. One of the estimations suggests that the number of devices ("Things") that would be connected by 2025 is going to be around 30.9 billion [1]. Therefore, as the number of devices to be handled increases, an IoT application that is developed to handle a particular number of devices will become inefficient or obsolete sooner or later. In order to design any IoT application, it is important to consider current and future workloads, data volumes, number of sensors, security patches, network traffic, etc. [1-5]. What works in the small scale should also work in the large one. However, achieving this is a very challenging task. In this paper, the dimensions of IoT scaling are investigated and a case study on accident management using IoT is presented.

II. UNDERSTANDING IOT SCALING

In order to understand IoT scaling, the basic IoT reference model needs to be revisited (Figure 1). There are 7 conceptual

layers in any IoT application. Layer 1, is the perception layer, which consists essentially of sensors and the associated hardware. With the booming areas of application of IoT, including agriculture, healthcare, industrial manufacturing, smart homes, offices, cities, and many more, the number of sensors in the perception layer is always growing. Also, already wired sensors are going to be replaced by upgraded versions. Any performing IoT infrastructure must be able to accommodate these developments in the perception layer by properly recognizing device registry and functionality. Vertical scaling refers to incorporating a better version of the device with more capacity and horizontal scaling refers to incorporating more of the same devices in the system [1, 6]. Layers 2 and 3 are basically communication and computing layers. The most important component of this network layers is the Gateways. Gateways moderate control and data between the endpoints of IoT devices and the edge/cloud [6, 7]. Important parameters such as the amount of data processing expected per device, frequency of data collection, and the types of analytical results expected are to be considered while choosing the gateways for IoT scaling. Gateways that provide multiple internet access (Ethernet, Wifi, global/3G/4G/5G/LTE) are preferred in this layer. The gateways that are compatible with rich mainstream protocols (such as MQTT, HTTP, Zigbee, LoRaWAN, Modbus) are best suited to make this layer scalable [6].

Fig. 1. The IoT layered reference model.

Layers 4 and 5 are basically data storage layers. The biggest challenge for scalability in databases is their "cardinality". Cardinality is the number of possible values in a database. A typical IoT deployment produces millions of values. For example, an IoT deployment with 5000 devices, each device having 100 sensors across 100 warehouse results in database cardinality of 5 millions and the number of tables goes on increasing. The table structure is not fixed. In order to address such scenarios, data storage must be carried out in a non-traditional way. No SQL databases or key-value pair databases fit into this. Zigsaw, Influx, Riak TS, mongoDB [8] are some of the preferred databases to make IoT scalable in this layer. Layers 6 and 7 provide a picture of the growing application users and the applications themselves.

Sectors such as agriculture, health, industrial manufacturing, hospitality, finance, transportation, and education have started using the benefits of IoT technology to make smart homes, smart cities, and smart life in general. These observations suggest that during IoT application development, scalability is an important factor to be considered. In this paper, a framework for designing a scalable application is discussed.

III. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In the past, in order to scale IoT applications, many different architectures have been proposed. The most important among them are cloud-based architectures, fog-based architectures, and, edge-based architectures [1-3]. The cloud-based technology is used in [2]. In this technology, every input data from the sensors has to reach the distant servers for processing. As billions of IoT applications keep sending data to the cloud servers, the server becomes heavily loaded and there will be delayed response. In [10], a kind of modification was done for the cloud approach and small capacity servers were dynamically triggered as middle nodes in the cloud. These dynamic middle nodes were named "fog servers" [9]. Experimental results in fog computing showed that the system performance is not always improved and may become worse

sometimes [10]. In [11, 12] edge/cloud computing methods were used. In edge computing, instead of sending the sensor data to distant servers, they are processed in a machine nearest to the source (a machine at the edge of the network). This approach in edge reduces the latency and improves the IoT response time. The major players in contributing IoT scaling are Microsoft Azure, Amazon Web Services (AWS), and Google cloud [6, 8, 9, 13]. However, all these platforms follow the pay-as-you-go pricing model. In view of the needs of researchers and developers, an open-source scalable IoT framework is required. InciComm, is an open-source scalable IoT framework that is based on microservice architecture and provides improved performance. The following sections present the system architecture of the proposed InciComm scalable IoT framework. It is used to implement business rules and behavior of the use case application. The rule engine helps to map hardware pins as input and outputs during the design. Third-party services such as AWS can be included using a plugin module. As and when new devices/sensors arrive, they will be registered and the application starts performing as per the business rules specified in the rule engine. Thus, rapid development is aided by this scalable architecture.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

InciComm architecture is shown in Figure 2. The system architecture consists of components such as a gateway communicator, authenticator, and API modules. The system architecture contains an IoT broker module supporting MQTT, HTTP, Websockets, and CoAP protocols [6, 8]. The broker is an important module that acts as an interface between the input device (publisher) and the output (subscriber) device. A separate module called the device registry module exists to register the identified device with its device ID, authentication captcha, and other attributes. The architecture supports SQL and NoSQL databases, including SQLite, InfluxDB, MongoDB, and Riak T. In order to record, device metadata such as sensor type, units of data collection, etc., a metadata event manager module is included. The shadow module creates a persistent virtual version of the real device. Device shadow helps application development using REST APIs. The rule engine is another important component. It is used to implement business rules and behavior of the use case application. The rule engine helps map hardware pins as input and outputs during the design. Third-party services such as AWS cloud services can be included using a plugin module. As and when new devices/sensors arrive in the applications, they will be registered and the application starts performing as per the business rules specified in the rule engine.

V. REAL-LIFE USE CASE

Figure 3 shows the use case diagram of the application. In this use case, it is intended to use the framework to design an application that reports vehicle accidents in real-time [14, 15]. Device installation, application registration, authentication, sending notifications, identifying the nearest rescue responders, and identifying false positives to close the event cycle are some of the important use cases in the design. Haversine's algorithm [15, 16] is used to find the nearest best location of the rescue responders.

Fig. 2. InciCom system architecture.

Fig. 3. Use case diagram of an accident reporting system.

and sends an email with a valid username and password credentials to log in and use the application. The application becomes active automatically whenever the vehicle starts moving or is made active manually. The active device streams heartbeats to the server. The system is designed in such a way that it reports only the worst-case scenario (i.e. accident). The broker is programmed to provide QoS 1 [17]. A time series with an unstructured database schema is used to store the streaming data. The vehicle health messages however are published (sent) at phased intervals as required by the user service demands. The mounted hardware prototype is shown in Figure 9 and App instances in Figure 10.

The flow of the application starts with the user installing the hardware on the vehicle and registering in the App. The user provides information about device ID, customer ID, car/vehicle ID, service ID, mobile numbers, etc. The system authenticates

Fig. 4. PIN details and connection diagram using the Raspberry Pi.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

This section provides a high-level description of the implementation of the use case in the InciComm IoT platform. As a proof of the concept, the implementation is carried out using a Raspberry Pi mounted with sensors. The hardware connectivity schema and the actual circuit are shown in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. Three types of sensors were used to sense events such as an accident. The sensor HC-SR04 for distance measurement (S_d), the sensor MP6050 for sensing abnormal gyrometric changes (S_g), and the sensor B081V6FLG1 [18, 19] for sensing fire occurrences (S_f). An accident (A) is defined as a combined abnormal output of these sensors:

$$A = \Psi(S_d, S_g, S_f) \tag{1}$$

If S_d becomes zero at any time, it signals an incident of touch/impact. The intensity peak at the time of reduced distance indicates the accident. The gyroscopic parameter S_g measures the tilt in the planes and S_f signals the occurrence of fire/sudden rise in the temperature. The accident parameter A is calculated based on the majority vote of S_d , S_g , and S_f .

Fig. 5. Accident reporting hardware with Raspberry Pi and sensors.

Fig. 6. Node-red rule engine flow

A Python [8] script to sense the sensor data on board the raspberry Pi was written, tested, and saved in a file. The program reads these sensor inputs and computes the accident-reporting parameter. An InciComm account is used to log in to the IoT platform. Devices are created in the framework by using device palletes and linking the device ID with the customer ID, access tokens, and service ID details. Node-red is used as a rule engine (Figure 6) to map the Raspberry Pi pins and other hardware. A dynamic MQTT broker is used to

publish and subscribe messages in the cloud/edge networks. Any number of devices can be scaled up and down in the system using this broker. Figure 7 shows the scalable application development block diagram of the framework.

Fig. 7. Scalable application development flow.

VII. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Initially, simulations were conducted using Node-red and MQTT broker. Three hypothetical cars were used. The payload and topics are shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Payload and topic arrivals in hypothetical car tests.

The MQTT server offers three QoS levels, i.e. Q0, Q1 and Q2 [17]. Tests were conducted using Q0. The pay loads (messages) were exactly received for the respective topics. The messages were streamed at intervals of 10s and the broker was found to be working properly. Figure 10 shows instances of these simulations.

Fig. 9. The mounted prototype of the carApp hardware.

Fig. 10. Instances of real-time App usage and location tracking.

TABLE I. PAYLOADS AND TOPICS IN THE HYPOTHETICAL TESTS

Car No	Payload and topics	
	Payload	Topic
1	Car is to be stopped	carApp/9686502426/TAS56768
2	Car is moving dangerously	carApp/CD404
3	Car is moving safely	carApp/530713146/TSU303

As a second experiment, a real-time hardware device was mounted on an experimental car and its locations were traced on the carApp. At different locations, the experimental car was made to crash/tilt and the coordinates of the accident spots were shown on the map. The application was able to send to the nearby rescue responder (police and hospital) successfully.

VIII. DISCUSSION

The objective of this research was to provide a scalable IoT platform for designing IoT applications. A case study of an IoT application for reporting vehicle accidents was designed using the proposed scalable platform and its scalability was tested. The scalability tests and measured values are reported in Table II which lists the Key Performance Indices (KPI's) and the measured values.

Scalability testing is conducted in order to know the response of the system when there are workload variations. In this proposed testing, Assetto Corsa Competizione (ACC) simulations [20] are used and 5 scalability metrics are evaluated (Table II). Device provisioning rate defines the number of devices that can come in into the service of IoT application [19, 21, 22]. A total of 200 devices per second are reported. Over The Air (OTA) update rate is found to be 40. The number of messages that are ingested into the system is 1000 messages per second. The number of messages that fail to reach their subscribers is measured by message failure rate metric and it is found to be 0.2%. The message latency or delay in reaching its subscriber is less than 40 millisecond seconds.

TABLE II. IOT SCALABILITY METRICS

Scalability tests and measured values	
KPI	Measured value
Device provisioning rate	200/s
Over The Air (OTA) update rate	40
Message ingest rate	1000/s
Message failure rate	0.2%
Message latency	<40 ms

IX. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a scalable IoT framework is discussed along with an applied use case on accident reporting. The proposed framework allows the dynamic discovery of devices and data management. The proposed solution offers scalability with respect to the device deployment, number of users/inputs, and computing environment. A selected list of scalability metrics was evaluated and the scalability of the proposed framework is confirmed. The paper discussed a case study application to accident reporting and demonstrated the development and testing of the same using the proposed framework. In future work, the case study application itself needs to be improved with improved accident parameter definition. The scalability of the framework needs to be tested with the deployment of different applications other than the current case study application deployment.

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Wastewater Assessment and Biochemical Oxygen Demand Value Prediction from Mining Operations: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater is a byproduct of industrial or household waste processes, and its contamination level must be determined before treatment. Discharges of liquid effluents generated by mining operations, one of the most prevalent forms of industrial waste water, pose a risk to human health and the environment. This study evaluates the physicochemical quality of industrial liquid effluent discharges from the Boukhadra mine (Algeria). Samples were collected from the washing water to identify the level of contamination of these liquid discharges and to measure physicochemical parameters such as temperature (T), hydrogen potential (pH), Electrical Conductivity (EC), Suspended Solids (SS), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Biological Oxygen Demand for 5 days (BOD₅), Oils and Greases (O&G), iron (Fe²⁺) and Kjeldahl Nitrogen (NTK). It was found that the concentration values of those effluents exceeded the maximum contamination limits specified by international industrial waste standards. A simple and reliable prediction model was developed to estimate DBO₅, based on MES, COD, and O&G, by using classical regression analysis and fitting Design of Experiments (DOE) methodology. When comparing the analytical results, it was found that the quadratic model provided a better estimation, with a high correlation coefficient (R²) of 0.9976. The parameters determined in this study will enable engineers to quickly estimate the degree of wastewater contamination and choose adequate treatment strategies.

Keywords-characterization; wastewater; BOD₅; Design of Experiments (DOE); environment; ANOVA

I. INTRODUCTION

Water pollution has become a global problem that requires a sustained effort to mitigate it, as the increasing demand for agricultural and industrial products is responsible for it [1]. The increase in solid and liquid waste is directly related to the economic development of many countries, and in fact, the latter leads to detrimental impacts on the environment, the mismanagement of industrial sites, in particular, has consequences on public health and environmental problems [2]. Industry discharge wastewater containing organic matter, salts, hydrocarbons, heavy metals, biocides, micropollutants, and various chemicals, often causes permanent environmental damage [3]. The impact of these industrial effluents on the environment is a reality, and they significantly contribute to the degradation of the quality of surface and ground water,

therefore, for public health reasons, these materials must be treated before being released directly into streams or lakes [4]. Numerous studies have been conducted on the characterization, evaluation, and treatment of hazardous substances in textile-related effluents [5], sludge [6], sewage sludge [7], paper waste [8], petroleum wastewater [9] and aerobic oil and grease-degrading bacteria in wastewater [10]. Additionally, studies on wastewater produced by mining operations have been conducted in cases of coal mines [11], gold mines [12], marble mines [13], and iron mines [14]. Those researchers have attempted to remove inorganic pollutants, recycle trash, segregate materials, and indirectly evaluate hazardous substances present in wastewater to treat them better. Among the industrial activities, the Algerian mining sector, which has experienced exponential economic growth, has raised many

environmental issues relating to its activity [15-17]. Therefore, adopting feasible environmental assessment methods is desirable.

As a case study, the Boukhadra iron mine in Tebessa province in Algeria, is one of the largest operational iron mines in the country. The annual production of iron ore is 5 million tons, with approximately 50 thousand m³ of wastewater generated each month by washing machinery production equipment. The mine represents a critical contamination point, as all fluid discharges are discharged into the washing plant and contain significant contaminants, and the mine does not include Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs). The installation is old, as the washing pit was constructed before 1926, and since the opening of the mine, it has not been connected to the sewage network even though it is present, but in a neglected state (soak pit). These liquid ejections are directly discharged into nature and cause considerable damage. The environmental impact of these industrial effluents causes severe threats to public health. The effluents must be studied and treated before discharging.

Recent investigations have focused on the development of numerical models using machine learning techniques for estimating the Biological Oxygen Demand for 5 days (BOD₅) of wastewater [18, 19], but those models are complicated and difficult to use. However, none of the previous studies have used the Design of Experiments (DOE) technique to produce an adequate model for predicting the parameters of wastewater. The advantage of DOE technique is that it allows the variation of different factors simultaneously to screen the reaction space for optimum values. In this study, the physicochemical quality of industrial liquid effluents was evaluated to detect the level of contamination. Classical Regression Analysis (CRA) and (DAO) techniques with linear, 2FI, and quadratic models were employed to quickly estimate BOD₅ and to reveal its experiential relationship with liquid effluent discharge parameters. The experiential relationship of BOD₅ with wastewater parameters was identified and the performance of the resulting model was assessed.

II. GENERAL SETTING AND AVAILABLE DATA

The study area is located in the eastern part of Tebessa city, Algeria (Figure 1). The iron mine is located between longitudes 8°01'30" to 8°03'18" and latitudes 35°45'54" to 35°44'42", covering an approximate area of 3.7km². The mine was discovered in 1903 and produces iron ore since 1926, with exploitable reserves exceeding 50 million tons. The Boukhadra iron deposit consists mainly of hematite and is one of the largest in the Algerian-Tunisia border region. [20]. There is a washing station which is used to wash equipment and drain oil from construction machinery. The waste wastewater from this wash station exceeds 10 thousand m³ daily. The liquid discharge contains significant polluting substances, and the mine does not include WWTPs. Also, it is not connected to the sewage, and the liquid ejections are directly discharged to the nature causing considerable environmental damage. The environmental impact of these industrial effluents causes serious threats to the quality of surface water, groundwater, and public health, while the Boukhadra town is located at the vicinity of the mine.

Fig. 1. Location of the study area. © Google Earth, GEBCO Landsat, Copernicus IBCAO.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

To evaluate the physicochemical quality of liquid discharges, samples were collected from the washing pit located in Boukhadra mine. Temperature (T), pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Suspended Solids (SS), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), BOD₅, Oils and Greases (O&G), iron (Fe⁺²), and Kjeldahl Nitrogen (NTK) were measured to determine the level of contamination. Twenty five samples were collected from 2016 to 2021, 1 every 3 months. The samples were taken from the equipment and production machinery washing station (final discharge) with a stainless steel bucket of 1.5L, attached to large polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottles. Bottles were filled after 2 to 3 rinses with the same sample. To ensure the traceability of the sample, a tag was associated with each sample (date, location, and GPS coordinates), and the samples were hermetically sealed and conserved [21]. The samples were transported to the laboratory in an icebox at 4°C and were stored for 48h before being analyzed. The statistical analysis results of the physical and chemical parameters of the industrial wastewater discharge from Boukhadra mine are shown in Table I, where, the mean value (x_{mean}), standard deviation (σ), variance (σ^2), maximum value (x_{max}), and minimum value (x_{min}) are presented. The statistical variation intervals are performed for each parameter, checking for measurement errors and values outside logical bounds.

TABLE I. BASIC STATISTICS OF BOUKHADRA MINES WASTEWATER

	x_{mean}	σ	σ^2	x_{max}	x_{min}
T (°C)	19.852	3.980	15.842	26	9.1
pH	8.051	0.359	0.129	8.67	7.31
CE (µS/cm)	2580.92	2172.42	4719414	7830	840
COD (mg/l)	134.36	18.609	346.323	163	95
SS (mg/l)	106.52	18.888	356.76	136	67
NTK (mg/l)	0.884	0.550	0.303	2.1	0.4
Fe ⁺² (mg/l)	1.812	0.502	0.252	2.6	0.4
O&G (mg/l)	98.88	21.044	442.86	133	60
BOD ₅ (mg/l)	45.64	18.843	355.073	74	5
COD/BOD ₅ (mg/l)	3.930	3.40	11.599	19	2.202

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Wastewater Assessment

Most of the measured values do not meet the international discharge of industrial wastewater standards. Temperature is an essential factor in biological activity. Referring to the standard limits, it can be noted that the measured temperatures were below 30°C (Figure 2(a)), which is considered the standard for Algerian industrial waste [22]. The pH is also one of the most significant parameters affecting the biological activity of the microorganisms in the water, whose majority grows in the range of 4.5-8 [23]. The average pH values of the wastewater ranged between 7.31 and 8.67, slightly exceeding the standard value (Figure 2(b)). High COD [24] values were found, as indicated in Figure 2(c). Most values were above the standard limit of 120mg/L [25] for industrial waste. They ranged from 95 to 163mg/L, indicating the presence of biodegradable load [26]. These values would be related to the presence of large amounts of machine oil and SS due to the washing of mine equipment. The calculated results of SS show that it exceeds the threshold of acceptable values (20mg/L), with the highest value found in the wash station (136mg/L) due to the presence of heavy oils of large molecular mass (Figure 2(d)). NTK and Fe⁺² comply with the standards (Figure 2(e)-(f)), while the average concentration of O&G (98.88mg/l) is very high and exceeds the limit value of 20mg/l (Figure 2(g)). This high quantity could lead to severe environmental pollution. The BOD₅ values (mg/L) at 20°C in the dark were between 5 and 74mg/L, with the most values exceeding the allowable standard industrial waste limit of 35mg/L. Those values could be explained by the fact that the wastewater is highly loaded with oils, which create inhibited microbial activity similar to that found in anaerobic conditions. The COD/BOD₅ ratio gives a first estimate of the biodegradability of the organic matter of an effluent. An increase in this ratio indicates a rise in non-biodegradable organic materials [27]. The test results showed that the COD/BOD₅ ratio ranged from 2.20 to 19, with an average value of 3.93.

Fig. 2. Evaluation of physicochemical parameters of effluent discharges.

B. ANOVA Study

The developed model was performed using DOE, Design-Expert version 10. The input data were the values of COD, SS, and O&G. The statistical analysis included the analysis of variance (ANOVA), which is used to obtain suitable models and suitability studies. The ANOVA table of the effluent discharges, with linear, 2FI, and quadratic models, was employed to ensure the most appropriate model. The comparison between the influence of the main factors and their interactions can be carried out using the F-value of each factor. The presented results for the quadratic model confirm that the COD and SS and OG are significant at $\leq 5\%$ (probability level), but this is not true for linear and 2FI models. Table II shows that the F-values of COD, SS, and OG are 3779.12, 3327.85, and 1656.90, respectively. Therefore, it is clear that in the proposed model, the influence of COD is more considerable than the weight fraction. Therefore, it can be said that the quadratic model is the most expressive and the changes in BOD5 can be accurately estimated using the proposed model. The proposed quadratic model for estimating BOD5 related to COD, SS, and O&G is defined as:

$$BOD5 = -47.41946 - 1.20218 \times COD + 1.29202 \times SS + 0.917706 \times OG - 0.023951 \times COD \times SS - 0.027619 \times COD \times OG + 0.025533 \times COD^2 + 0.001488 \times SS^2 + 0.002399 \times OG^2 \quad (1)$$

The model incorporates all the necessary main factors and their interactions.

TABLE II. ANOVA RESULTS FOR WASTEWATER WITH THE QUADRATIC MODEL

Source	Sum of squares	Mean Square (MS)	F-value	p-value
Model	8521.74	946.86	8.654E+05	< 0.0001
A-COD	4.14	4.14	3779.12	< 0.0001
B-SS	3.64	3.64	3327.85	< 0.0001
C-OG	1.81	1.81	1656.90	< 0.0001
AB	1.81	1.81	1654.43	< 0.0001
AC	11.43	11.43	10450.61	< 0.0001
BC	3.93	3.93	3591.32	< 0.0001
A ²	5.36	5.36	4901.37	< 0.0001
B ²	0.6547	0.6547	598.38	< 0.0001
C ²	0.1202	0.1202	109.82	< 0.0001
Residual	0.0164	0.0011		
Total	8521.76			

It can be seen from Figure 3 that the Residual Sum of Squares (RSS) for the quadratic model is very small (0.0164). It was also observed, that the Coefficient of Variation (CV) had a small value (0.0725), indicating that the proposed model provides the best reliable measurement. CV is less than 5% is deemed acceptable [28]. Therefore, it is clear that in the proposed model, the influence of the COD is more considerable than the weight fraction.

C. Adequacy of the Proposed Model

One practical and efficient way to test the adequacy of the proposed model is the normal distribution of errors. Examining the normal probability of the studentized residuals can confirm the normal distribution of errors [29]. One interesting feature of

a proper model is the agreement between the experimental and the predicted values. Figure 4 shows the correlation between the actual values obtained during the experiments and the predicted values of the proposed BOD5 model. The graph shows that there is a good agreement between the actual and the predicted values. Therefore, the proposed model can predict the DBO5 activity in effluents under the experimental conditions.

Fig. 3. Verification results for the responses on BOD5.

Fig. 4. Comparison between the predicted and the actual values of DBO5.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this research work, physicochemical characterization of industrial liquid effluent discharges, collected from the washing water from the Boukhadra mine (Algeria) was conducted. The samples were evaluated, to identify their level of contamination. The analysis showed that the values of COD, SS, BOD5, and O&G are very high. Their presence indicates strong and unbalanced biological pollution, which could be dangerous to the environment. To control and quick estimate the main effluent parameter, classical regression analysis without measuring BOD5 value was conducted by the DOE methodology to fit the appropriate model. After simulation, and by the combination of SS, COD, and O&G parameters, the quadratic model was adopted. To control errors and

resemblances according to the experimental values, the MS, RSS, and P-values were used to compare the performance of the model with the actual results. The quadratic model provided a high correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9976. Based on the ANOVA results, it is clear that the effect of COD is more than that of the weight fraction and the interaction between the other parameters. Also, the statistical parameters of the proposed model revealed that this model could predict the DBO5 activity of the samples strictly, by giving close responses to the instantaneous variations.

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Dam Deformation Monitoring using Cloud-Based P-SBAS Algorithm: The Kramis Dam Case (Algeria)

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the application of the Parallel Small Baseline Subset (P-SBAS) algorithm, provided by the Geohazards Exploitation Platform for the precise monitoring of an earth dam's ground deformation using C-band Sentinel-1 data. The test site object of this study was the Kramis dam, located in the Mostaganem State, Western Algeria. Among the multiple advanced DInSAR techniques, SBAS is very adequate for long-term displacement monitoring in areas with changing terrain and vegetation. Ten corner reflectors were installed as a backscattered radar signal amplification tool to reduce the effect of temporal decorrelation and delineate the dam area. Four Sentinel-1 A and B satellite tracks were available (T30, T37, T103, and T110) to measure displacements, in the Line of Site (LoS) direction, for two years since the installation of the CRs in July 2019. The results showed a subsiding area on the left bank of the dam dike, with a velocity of 4mm/yr, and an uplifting rate of 3-4mm/yr in the upper part of the dike. The entire 3-dimensional vector of displacement of the dam vicinity was estimated using the least-squares method, proving a better understanding of the dam's temporal deformation, particularly for dams with a high exposure factor and associated risk.

Keywords-dam deformation; Kramis; P-SBAS; time series

I. INTRODUCTION

In Algeria, embankment dams are the backbone of the water management infrastructure [1]. Despite their advantages in terms of strength and structure, these structures must be equipped with a precise monitoring system to ensure their safety and guarantee their durability [2-3]. Monitoring surface displacements is a tool to control risk phenomena, in particular, the overall instabilities within the natural embankments of the dike and the reservoir [4-6]. The primary purpose of monitoring and auscultation is to survey the behavior of the dam over time, maintain its operation, and ensure the safety of the structure to withstand the agglomerations downstream of the dam [7]. Two aspects of precise surveillance, commonly known by the name of auscultation, arise. The first is internal auscultation, where dam monitoring is performed on a regular basis with different types of instruments, such as piezometers,

total stress cells, settlement devices, or triaxial deformation tubes. The second type of auscultation is external. This process aims to precisely measure the displacements and superficial deformations incurred using geodetic and topographic techniques. In addition to the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) methods have been proposed as reliable and precise tools for the apprehension of dam deformations [8-10].

Investigations and observations conducted during field surveys are time-consuming, expensive, and have low reproducibility. In contrast, Multi-Temporal InSAR (MT-InSAR) can retrieve historical displacements, identify minute ground anomalies, fully reveal the geographic distributions of surface deformations, and identify displacement boundaries with a high spatial resolution of meters and an accuracy of centimeters to millimeters [11]. Today, MT-InSAR methods, such as PSInSAR, SBAS, SqueeSAR, etc., are successfully

employed to measure minor deformations caused by natural events or human intervention [12-14]. The achievements in dam monitoring using SAR imagery show that MT-InSAR methods have the potential to support the development of new and more effective means to monitor dam health. The free availability of high-quality SAR data with the launches of Sentinel-1A (April 2014) and Sentinel-1B (April 2016) that use C-band SAR data (frequency: 5.405GHz) helped researchers develop new tools and methods in dam surveys. Sentinel-1 Single Look Complex (SLC) images are characterized by a high spatial resolution of 5×20m and high temporal resolution. The constellation of the two satellites involved a repetition time of 6 days (Sentinel-1 B was lost after December 2021) and the resulting data was provided in near real-time [15-16].

This study used C-band radar data from the European satellites Sentinel-1A/B to derive mean Line of Site (LoS) velocity maps in the Kramis dam (Algeria), a structure oriented in the WNW-ESE direction, and its surrounding area. The Sentinel-1 satellites' four distinct tracks were used to construct the times series displacements and velocities from July 2019 to June 2021 using the Parallel SBAS (P-SBAS) method available at the Geohazards service [17-19]. The trend and seasonal components were extracted from the time series, and then the 3D displacement maps were produced.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Processing Methodology

This study used the Parallel Small Baseline Subset (P-SBAS) approach [17-18], a multi-temporal advanced SAR interferometry method to determine Kramis dam's surface displacements, as shown in Figure 1. Using the P-SBAS service, the multi-temporal processing was carried out on the Geohazards Exploitation Platform (GEP) [19]. The user's input is only required at the beginning of the process to select the dataset, while the temporal coherence, the Digital Elevation Model (DEM), the area to process, and the entire processing are automated. The interferometric couples were chosen using the default parameters of 400m for the perpendicular baseline and 300 days for temporal separation. Eventually, a parallelized chain was used to handle the SBAS data, allowing for time optimization.

Fig. 1. The proposed workflow.

The primary aspects of the P-SBAS processing chain for Sentinel-1, presented in [19], are comparable to those of the original P-SBAS method presented in [17]. This method was developed to efficiently use distributed computing infrastructures to process multi-temporal stripmap SAR datasets. Application cases and capacity analysis of the original P-SBAS can be found in [20]. When it comes to the parallelization method, the key changes in this Sentinel-1 P-SBAS processing chain focus on achieving a higher level of granularity than the stripmap mode technique [17], which results from burst partitioning that distinguishes the S-1 IW

data structure. This method allows to gather several independent bursts for each SAR scene that can be handled and processed separately, from the ingestion of input data up to the generation of DInSAR interferograms, thereby promoting the inherent parallelization of the S-1 IW interferometric processing on a burst basis.

B. Time Series Analysis

A time series is a chronological sequence of observations on a variable, in this case, the displacement in time of a Persistent Scatterer (PS). Time series analysis aims to characterize time series and develop a mathematical model that describes the evolution of the variable over time [21-22]. Moreover, different deformation patterns might cross over. A time series for dam monitoring often includes a seasonal component and a linear trend. The dam body faces subsidence as a result of the dead load of the reservoir's water as well as the settlement of the materials employed in its construction. The reservoir's water level may fluctuate over time as a result of variations in the water entering the reservoir and leaving it for irrigation, freshwater usage, or power generation. A cyclical change between subsidence and uplift could be brought on by the varying water levels [23]. Consequently, different deformation models should be considered and evaluated to determine the best-fitting model. It is worth mentioning that similar approaches were proposed in [24-26], the most relevant being linear, quadratic, and piecewise linear models for the approximation of the time series trend component. A sinusoidal [27] or a statistical model, such as the ARIMA model [28], can be used to approximate the seasonal component of the time series.

The final step in the dam deformation analysis is related to the estimation of the 3-D displacement time series based on the results of the different tracks (ascending and descending). The whole displacement vector $U = (d_e, d_n, d_u)$, where d_e, d_n, d_u are the East-West, North-South, and Up-Down directions respectively, is related to the LoS displacement by $d = \hat{P}U$, therefore \hat{P} is the unit vector defined as [29]:

$$\hat{P} = [-\cos\alpha_h \sin\theta_{inc} \quad \sin\alpha_h \sin\theta_{inc} \quad \cos\theta_{inc}] \quad (1)$$

where α_h and θ_{inc} are the heading and the incidence angles, respectively. The corresponding LoS displacement for each track can then be written, according to (1), as:

$$d = d_u \cos(\theta_{inc}) - \sin(\theta_{inc})[d_n \cos(\alpha_h) + d_e \sin(\alpha_h)]$$

and finally, the 3D displacement vector can be retrieved by:

$$U = -[\hat{P}^T \Sigma_d^{-1} \hat{P}]^{-1} \hat{P}^T \Sigma_d^{-1} d \quad (2)$$

III. STUDY AREA

This study investigated the deformation of the Kramis dam located in Mostaganem, Algeria, situated at the South-East of the capital of the municipality of Achaacha (Wilaya of Mostaganem) and North-East of the capital of the municipality of Nekmaria, approximately 80Km east of the town of Mostaganem and 14Km from the Mediterranean Sea, and positioned at 0°40'30"E and 36°13'00"N, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. The geographical location of the Kramis dam. The red triangles represent ascending CRs and the yellow descending CRs.

The Kramis dam was intended to irrigate the Achaacha Municipality perimeter with an area of 4,300ha for an affected volume of 10 million m^3 and strengthen the Dahra area network (Sidi Lakhdar, Nekmaria, Ouled Boughalem, and Achaacha) with a total population of 11,546 inhabitants (2003), with an affected volume of 5.3 million m^3 . Geodetic monitoring of the Kramis dam started in May 2019, with the installation of markers for the GNSS survey and 10 Corner Reflectors (5 CRs in each Sentinel-1 acquisition direction) around the dike to be used for the calibration of the DInSAR results, since GNSS also observed all CRs [30].

IV. DATASETS

This study used C-band radar data (~5,6cm wavelength) from the European satellite Sentinel-1 to analyze the Kramis dam deformation. Forty-eight ascending and forty-eight descending Sentinel-1A/B TOPSAR images were used, covering the Kramis dam area with a one-month revisit period, from July 2019 (one month after full CRs installation (May-June 2019) [30]) to June 2021 for both acquisitions (ascending and descending), see Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Sentinel-1 paths used in this study. The white square located in the intersection of the four tracks represents the study area.

A three-arc-second (90m) Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) DEM provided by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) was used to remove the topographic phase component [31]. Precise Orbit Determination (POD) data provided by the European Space

Agency were applied for orbital refinement and phase reflattening. A total of 24 images per track was used, one for each month over two years. The LoS displacements were referenced to the first acquisition date. The observation pillar G02 was taken as a reference for the observation of GNSS and SBAS, which was considered stable in this period, as shown in Figure 4. The displacement time series generated from the four tracks covered an area of $250 \times 250 \text{ km}^2$ for each of them, and the surveyed area was about $9 \times 12 \text{ km}^2$. A geographic subset was made on the four LoS time series displacements to cover the object area only for analysis.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Kramis Dam was imaged in ascending and descending modes and with different incidence angles. Paths 30 and 37 were acquired with incidence angles of 35° and 45° , respectively; the same was valid for tracks 103 and 110, which were tacking acquisitions in this area with incidence angles of 37° and 54° , respectively. These differences led to different numbers of distributed scatterers in the results, even when the acquisitions were made during similar month periods. Figure 4 shows the mean LoS velocity maps derived from the P-SBAS processing of the four tracks. According to this figure, a subsidence pattern can be observed on the left bank of the dam dike, as this area suffers from continuous subsidence starting from the left bank of the upstream and regularly occurring landslides [32].

The P-SBAS method indicates that the dam dike analyzed was subjected to deformation on the order of -2 to 4mm/yr in the LoS direction, with a low standard deviation of about 1mm/yr for the four tracks. The bulk of PS points that display deforming motion are also found within the top portion of the dam body, with a maximum velocity reaching 4.25mm/yr. In the case of Sentinel-1, which acquires images in a right-looking orientation, the ascending and descending geometries from the same period are the sole measurements to compute the entire movement vector. The East, North, and Up components of track 30's unit vector (-0.5467327, -0.1007871, 0.8312191), respectively, show that the sensitivity of the LoS to the North-South direction is less than 10%, making it difficult to detect movements in that direction. The same comment about the unit vector can be addressed for the remaining paths as to the contribution of the North-South direction to the unit vector, as it is less significant than the other components.

The displacement time series in Figure 4 shows how the four CRs moved over two years following their installation in June 2019. Three CRs (numbers 1, 8, 9) were destroyed and number 10 was moved from its place. Monitoring these CRs was not possible after January 2020. Most of the CRs placed around the dam body exhibited subsidence at varying intensities. As expected, CR6, which was located in a region plagued by ongoing landslides, had the highest cumulative displacement over the research period, at 20mm. However, CR5 had a 3 mm/yr uplift rate. It is worth mentioning that the velocity precision on the dike was around 1mm/yr and varied from 1 to 2.5mm/yr for the dam area.

Fig. 4. Column (a): From top to bottom, mean LoS velocity for Sentinel-1 processed tracks 30, 37, 103, and 110, respectively. The white arrow corresponds to the LoS direction and the blue line in the first map stands for the reference point. Column (b): Examples of the time series displacements from the corresponding corner reflectors, where the red line corresponds to the best-fitting line, the formula of each regression line is reported in the plots.

The seasonal term from LoS observations must be extracted in an analytical step before the computation of the 3-dimensional displacement. This study used the following steps:

- Detrend the time series using a linear model.
- Subtraction of the seasonal term estimated by the application of a moving average.
- Add back the trend to the corrected time series.

TABLE I. COMPARISON BETWEEN DISPLACEMENTS OBTAINED FROM P-SBAS AND GPS PROJECTED IN LOS DIRECTION

Corner reflector	GPS-LoS (mm)	InSAR-LoS (mm)	Difference (mm)
CR2	-0.9942	-0.5239	-0.4703
CR5	6.3542	5.1927	1.1615
CR6	-24.9600	-22.5237	-2.4363
CR7	-10.98	-11.38	0.4

Fig. 5. Example of original and corrected time series.

Figure 5 shows the displacement of a distributed scatterer placed upstream of the Kramis dam dike, illustrating the rectification of the displacement time series from the seasonal term, where the original time series exhibits the seasonal term and subsidence. The data were detrended using a linear model and then a moving average with a sliding window of length 3 was used to estimate the seasonal component. The seasonal pattern was removed to show the displacement component. After that, the linear trend was reintroduced to get the results. Once this correction is used, it is possible to generate the 3-D displacement using (2). Figure 6 shows the results, indicating a visible settlement of the dike in the Up-Down displacement.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper described the potential of C-band SAR Sentinel-1 data to monitor dam deformation using the advanced MT-InSAR P-SBAS method. The results showed that the Kramis dam dike had a linear deformation trend that reached 4mm/yr,

except for the left bank which was subsiding at a rate of -2mm/yr. The CRs installed in the vicinity of the dike showed a subsidence movement with a rate of -3mm/yr, while CR5, located 300m from the dike, presented an uplift pattern. Time series analysis is a key step in understanding dam deformation. For this purpose, the seasonal component was estimated using a moving average with a sliding window of length 3 and removed to clean off the LoS displacements, specifically when the final objective is the estimation of the 3D displacement. The estimated Up-Down displacement showed an expected settlement for this kind of dam. The results obtained from the P-SBAS processing on different Sentinel-1 tracks showed the benefit of using cloud services for dam monitoring in Algeria, as it is possible to install a survey service for the entire dam network of the country for use by non-experts.

Fig. 6. 3D displacement velocities.

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Application of Advanced Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for the Recognition of Road Surface Anomalies

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ABSTRACT

The detection of road surface anomalies is a crucial task for modern traffic monitoring systems. In this paper, we used the YOLOv8 network, a state-of-the-art convolutional neural network architecture, for real-time object recognition and to automatically identify potholes, cracks, and patches on the road surface. We created a custom dataset of 1044 road surface images in Vietnam, each of which was annotated with pavement anomalies, and the YOLOv8 network was trained with this dataset. The results show that the model achieved an accuracy of 0.56 mAP at a threshold of 0.5, indicating its potential for practical application.

Keywords-road surface anomalies; convolutional neural networks; digital image processing; transportation

I. INTRODUCTION

Identifying anomalies on road surfaces such as potholes, cracks, and bumps is an important factor in creating conditions for road maintenance, providing a better driving experience, and reducing the risk of accidents (collisions, falls, etc.) [1-5]. Analyzing data related to the condition of streets promptly can help make better decisions about transportation spending [4]. The anomalies on the road surface are repaired when they are reported by citizens or when a major incident occurs. However, a real-time reaction system that automatically detects various anomalies on urban and national roads does not exist. Systems for identifying anomalies on roads can be divided into three categories: vision-based, sensor-based, and 3D reconstruction methods [6].

The sensor-based method mostly uses sensor data to identify road anomalies. Authors in [5] compared the Decision Tree (DT) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithms for classifying abnormalities on the road using data measured from acceleration and gyro sensors. Authors in [7] used inertial sensor datasets collected in different contexts to detect and classify abnormalities on road surfaces (e.g. dirt roads, cobblestones, and asphalt roads). Based on the reported results, the proposed Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model achieved the best performance with an accuracy of 93.17%. Authors in [8] developed a hybrid method combining threshold-based signal processing techniques and machine learning algorithms to form a near real-time road anomaly detection system. On the other hand, the technique that uses 3D reconstruction to anticipate the shape of the road anomalies and evaluate their volume through stereo-vision technology is

considered the most precise of the three methods. However, this method is more costly and difficult to identify when potholes are filled with water or dirt than other approaches. For instance, authors in [9] developed a pixel-level road surface anomaly detection approach based on stereo vision and deep learning. Specifically, the vehicle-mounted photography system was used to capture both parallel and oblique photos to generate a 3D pavement point-cloud model. Stereo-vision technology was employed in the 3D reconstruction phase to process the input images. Point-cloud calibration relied on a PCA algorithm, and various orthoimages, including color, depth, and overlapped images, were generated during the 3D data-processing phase. To identify pavement cracks and potholes in the orthoimages, a modified U-net deep-learning technology was utilized for segmentation. Their approach achieved significant results: 0.9632 precision, 0.9552 recall, and 0.9592 F1 score.

The vision-based method uses images to identify the presence of abnormalities through image processing algorithms. The advantage of this method is that it does not require direct access to the location of the abnormalities on the road, making it easy to detect multiple objects at the same time through traffic monitoring cameras or cameras on mobile devices. For example, authors in [10] proposed a real-time automatic pavement crack and pothole recognition system using a mobile device. The proposed system achieved only 0.7 precision, recall, accuracy, and F1 score. Recently, deep learning techniques have gained widespread application in diverse fields [11-14]. These methods have also been employed in the identification of road surface anomalies, leveraging their strengths such as accurate detection and the ability to handle

intricate data. For example, authors in [1] discussed a deep learning algorithm for detecting potholes on road surfaces. The algorithm employed a CNN with 9 layers. However, the method is not suitable for real-time applications because it cannot be used for online video processing. Authors in [2] developed a system based on YOLOv2 [15] network to detect potholes on roads. However, their system can only run offline and cannot be used in real-time applications. Additionally, the system's accuracy only reached 82.5%. Authors in [16] proposed a lightweight CNN model based on a modified MobileNetv2 [17] that can operate on edge devices. The proposed system is capable of performing pixel-wise crack detection on streets.

The common drawback of the image processing methods mentioned above is that they cannot meet real-time operational criteria. Therefore, in this article, we propose a method that used YOLOv8, an advanced CNN model capable of real-time object detection with high accuracy. The proposed method can detect abnormalities on the road surface such as potholes, cracks, and road patches. The technical contributions of this paper can be summarized as:

- To the best of our knowledge, this paper is the first that applies the state-of-the-art YOLOv8 architecture to road anomaly detection.
- The proposed method can detect in real time various types of anomalies such as potholes, cracks, and patches.
- The empirical results suggest that the proposed method can be applied in practical settings with suitable modifications.

II. ROAD ANOMALIES DATASET

We constructed a road surface dataset consisting of 1044 images collected from random roads in Vietnam. Figure 1 shows some examples from the dataset. The data were taken at different times and weather conditions, resulting in a wide range of lighting and shadow conditions. This is the biggest challenge for abnormal road detection methods based on image processing. The dataset has a total of 1044 images and was divided into 967 images for training of the network and 77 images for model evaluation. Each image was labeled with three kinds of anomalies namely potholes, cracks, and road patches. The instance distribution is presented in Figure 2.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. YOLOv8 Network

Released at the beginning of 2023, YOLOv8 is the latest generation of the YOLO network, in particular, and is currently the most efficient model in tasks such as classification, detection, and segmentation of objects [18]. In object detection tasks, YOLOv8 can achieve superior results and faster processing times than other models thanks to its combination of optimization techniques and improvements. Specifically, the YOLOv8m model achieved a 50.2% mAP score on the COCO dataset, which is higher than its predecessors [18]. Also, the model requires fewer parameters than the others.

Fig. 1. Examples in the dataset.

Fig. 2. Distribution of road anomalies in the dataset.

YOLOv8 utilizes advanced techniques in the object detection field such as decoupled head and anchor-free detection. Also, novel ideas, such as mosaic stopping strategy that skips mosaic augmentation for the last 10 epochs, were introduced. The modifications compared to YOLOv5 [18, 19] are:

- The C3 module was replaced with the C2 module 5.

- The first 6×6 Conv was replaced with a 3×3 Conv in the Backbone.
- The first 1×1 Conv` was replaced with a 3×3 Conv in the Bottleneck.
- Decoupled head was used and the objectness branch was deleted. This technique separates the classification and regression tasks into two separate subnetworks, each with its own set of parameters [11, 20].

Fig. 3. Evaluation results of proposed model.

Fig. 4. Visualization of the results in real-time application.

B. Experimental Environment

The proposed YOLOv8 model was trained for 200 iterations with a batch size of 8. Due to the relatively small sizes of the objects of interest, the input image size increased from 640×640 to 1280×1280. All experiments were run on a computer with the following configuration:

- GPU Nvidia RTX3050 4 GB VRAM
- CPU AMD Ryzen 5 5600H, 3.3 Hz
- 16 Gb RAM

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of the anomaly detection model on the road is shown in Figure 3. Specifically, the model's precision achieved 84%, and the average accuracy was 56.8% at a confidence threshold of 0.5. The recall criterion, which indicates the ability to detect all objects present in the image, achieved 60% score. The visualized results of the evaluation set can be observed in Figure 4. The results show that the model is capable of detecting anomalies such as potholes, cracks, and patches on the road with high accuracy.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the utilization of the advanced YOLOv8 convolutional neural network architecture to address the issue of detecting road anomalies was discussed. The study shows that the proposed model's performance is promising, with MAP of 0.56 at the threshold of 0.5, suggesting that it can be applied in practical settings with suitable modifications. We intend to gather additional road data and further finetune the model to achieve better results in the future.

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A Detailed Study on the Analysis and Design of Geotextile Reinforced Earth Embankments

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ABSTRACT

The design of a steep reinforced slope with an adequate Factor of Safety (FoS) is a classical geotechnical problem. While designing a reinforced soil slope, it is necessary to accurately determine the tensile force to be resisted by the reinforcement to achieve the target FoS value and the length of the geotextile reinforcement to be provided at the top and bottom of the embankment and perform all the required safety checks. This paper presents an MS Excel spreadsheet using Visual Basic Programming that can be used to perform all the analyses required to design geotextile reinforced soil slopes, considering static and seismic loading conditions. This spreadsheet is capable of searching many slip surfaces repeatedly using Bishop's simplified method to determine the maximum tensile force to be resisted by the reinforcement, its top and bottom lengths, and performs deep-seated failure analysis to identify slip surfaces beyond the reinforced zone. This paper reports the results of an illustrative example to highlight all the above-mentioned issues. The results were also compared with the design charts reported in previous studies. The proposed platform can successfully perform all the necessary analyses to design both homogenous and non-homogenous embankments with geotextile reinforcements.

Keywords-geotextile; reinforced slope design; deep-seated failure; Bishop's simplified method; seismic analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Civil engineers frequently utilize reinforced soil structures to stabilize embankments and slopes. Geosynthetic reinforced soil slope stability has been analyzed in [1]. Various natural and man-made factors may lead to slope instability [2]. Different factors such as soil strength parameters, ambient circumstances, groundwater level, stress history, and natural slopes on hillsides pose different stability concerns for man-made slopes [3]. Cuts and berms differ significantly in man-made elevations. Slope stabilization devices can stabilize unstable slopes [3], while slope stabilization methods reduce driving forces, increase resisting forces, or both. Traditional rehabilitation of embankments and cut slopes sometimes requires removing slide debris and replacing it with free-draining granular materials. An alternative restoration method uses geosynthetics (geotextiles or geogrids) as reinforcement to reduce stabilizing costs [4-5]. In past, the performance of a geotextile-reinforced slope and its causes of failure was

assessed using centrifuge testing procedures [6]. Centrifuge analysis examines the effects of reinforcement spacing, tensile strength, soil shear strength, etc. The models failed with well-defined shear surfaces across the slope's toe, which matched the results of limit equilibrium-based reinforced slope design methods. According to [7], maximum reinforcement strain occurs near the mid-height of reinforced slopes on the critical failure surface directly below the slope crest. Digital imaging and centrifuge modeling have also been used to examine geotextile-reinforced slope deformation [8-9].

The stability of geo-synthetic reinforced soil structures is most often assessed using the limit equilibrium approach [10-12]. Some studies assume that the mobilized tension in geosynthetic layers is highly non-uniform, with maximum tension mobilized in the reinforcement layer at the slope's toe [13]. However, others believe that it occurs around the mid-height of the slope [14]. The reinforcement layer distribution and sizing depend on the slope's stability, reinforcement layer

force distribution, and slope depth [15]. Fly ash can be used as structural fill in low-lying areas of expanding residential sites, while roadways and embankments are made from coal-fired power station fly ash [16-18].

A major geotechnical challenge is to design and build a steep embankment providing the desired FoS. The design procedure to achieve the target FoS by providing sufficient reinforcements was documented in [19]. This paper presents a spreadsheet that uses the Visual Basic programming language to achieve this goal. This platform can search numerous failure surfaces repeatedly and analyze them using Bishop's simplified method to report the required top and bottom lengths of reinforcement and the maximum tensile force to be resisted by it. In addition, it can also perform deep-seated failure analysis of an embankment to identify the failure surface with the minimum required FoS outside the reinforced zone. This platform can examine both static and seismic loading conditions and pore water pressure loading to perform the necessary analyses. A fly ash-mixed embankment was studied using the developed spreadsheet-based platform and the simulation results were compared with the design chart results provided in [20].

II. METHOD FOR DESIGNING A GEOTEXTILE-REINFORCED SLOPE

This study aimed to design a geotextile-reinforced slope for a target FoS (FoS_T), using the following steps:

- Checking unreinforced stability of the final slope configuration to determine the zone of soil contributing to failure and likely to be dislodged from the original soil mass. FHWA [19] recommends values for sliding, local squeezing/bearing capacity failure, and deep-seated stability.
- Checking the estimated tensile strength of soil reinforcement to achieve the desired FoS with the design chart data provided [20].
- Determination of the mobilized strength, spacing, and the required length of each geotextile layer.
- Checking of the external stability of the reinforced soil slope considering the individual effects of sliding and seismic loading conditions.

A detailed description of these steps follows.

A. FoS Determination Using Bishop's Method

This study used the limit equilibrium technique based on Bishop's simplified method [21] to estimate the FoS of the slope against failure. According to [22], the FoS (F) based on the limit equilibrium method to satisfy the overall moment equilibrium is defined as:

$$F = \frac{\sum_{i=1, \dots, n} [(c'_i l_i + (N_i - U_i l_i) \tan \varphi') R_c]}{\sum_{i=1, \dots, n} [W_i x_i + q \beta_i - N_i f_c + k_h W_i e - A_m]} \quad (1)$$

The expression of base normal (N_i) in Bishop's simplified method for the i^{th} slice is obtained by summing slice forces in the vertical direction as follows:

$$N_i = \frac{W_i + q_i - \frac{(c'_i l_i - \mu_i \tan \varphi') \sin \alpha_i}{F}}{\cos \alpha_i + \frac{\tan \varphi' \sin \alpha_i}{F}} \quad (2)$$

where i is the i^{th} slice inside the failure surface, c' is the effective cohesion, l is the slice base length, h is the height of individual slice, R_c is the radius or the moment arm associated with the i^{th} slice, φ' is the effective angle of internal friction, W is the slice weight, N is the total base normal acting at the base of the individual slice, U is the pore-water pressure, q is an external surcharge load, A_m is the resultant external water force, f_c is the perpendicular offset of the base normal force from the center of rotation, e is the vertical distance from the centroid of each slice to the center of rotation, α is the slice base angle, and k_h is the horizontal pseudo-static acceleration coefficient.

B. Entry-Exit Search Method

As it is necessary to adopt a proper strategy to create the failure surface data, this study used an "Entry-Exit" method to develop them. For a set of points lying on the lower and upper surfaces of the slope, a set of intermediate points can be generated on the bisectors of the connecting chords, and the centers of the failure surface can be found with known locations of three points on the arc of the desired slip circle, as shown in Figure 1. The trial surfaces were generated and subjected to a few conditions: (i) A valid trial surface would be only generated when the center of the slip surface does not extend beyond the vertical and horizontal boundaries through points A and D , respectively, (ii) the center of the slip circle should lie between the vertical distance H from the upper surface dictated by line CD , where H is the height of the slope, and (iii) the trial surface should not intersect the bottom boundary represented by line EF . If any trial surface violates any of these conditions, they are termed "invalid" and are not considered for stability analysis.

Fig. 1. Entry-exit method.

C. Design of a Stable Reinforced Slope

The developed tensile force in the reinforcement must be determined to determine the stability of the reinforced soil slope. The tensile force generated by the reinforcement contributes to an increased resistance moment around the center of rotation of the circular failure surface. The total

tensile reinforcement per unit width of slope (T_S) to ensure slope stability for each potential failure surface inside the critical zone can be determined from:

$$T_S = (FoS_T - FoS_{UN}) \frac{M_D}{D} \quad (3)$$

where FoS_T is the target FoS of the reinforced slope, FoS_{UN} is the FoS of the unreinforced slope, M_D is the disturbing moment trying to cause rotational failure, and D is the moment arm about the center of rotation. Figure 2 shows the general configuration of a geotextile-reinforced slope with embedment length L_e . The minimum FoS, FoS_{min} , the FoS corresponding to a maximum value of T_{max} , and the maximum value of tensile force in geotextile reinforcement can be calculated for the target FoS_T . The horizontal distance from the embankment crest to the point of intersection of the slip surface corresponding to FoS_T provides an estimate of the top reinforcement length L_T .

Fig. 2. Rotational shear approach to determine the required strength of reinforcement and reinforcement spacing considerations for high slopes.

D. Checking the Estimated Value with Design Charts

FHWA [19] recommends that the T_S value calculated from (3) should be checked against the design chart values of the tensile forces prescribed by [20]. These charts were developed by performing wedge analysis of geotextile-reinforced slopes made of cohesionless soil. The results were presented in graphical form by combining the results of wedge analysis. The graphs present the values of a few relevant parameters, such as reinforcement force coefficient K and reinforcement length ratios (L_B/H or L_T/H) against different slope angles. The reinforcement force coefficient K determined from these charts can be used to determine T_{S-max} as follows:

$$T_{S-max} = 0.5K\gamma(H')^2 \quad (4)$$

where $H' = H + \frac{q}{\gamma}$, with q being the surcharge load and γ being the unit weight.

E. Estimation of the Mobilized Strength, Spacing, and the Required Length of Each Geotextile Layer

If the design value of the vertical spacing between N number of geotextile layers is S , then the tensile force experienced by each geotextile layer can be calculated as:

$$T_{S-max} = \frac{T_{zone} S}{H_{zone}} = \frac{T_{zone}}{N} \quad (5)$$

TABLE I. TOTAL TENSILE RESISTED BY GEOTEXTILE LAYERS

Zone for distribution of Geotextile	
For 2 zones ($H < 6m$)	For 3 zones ($H > 6m$)
$T_{Bottom} = 3/4 T_{S-max}$	$T_{Bottom} = 1/2 T_{S-max}$
$T_{Top} = 1/4 T_{S-max}$	$T_{Middle} = 1/3 T_{S-max}$
	$T_{Top} = 1/6 T_{S-max}$

F. Check for External Stability

The length of the geotextile reinforcement to be provided at the bottom of the embankment L_B is found by checking the sliding stability of the embankment. In this approach, based on Figure 3, an active wedge was considered at the rear of the reinforced soil mass with the back of the wedge reaching up at an angle of $45^\circ + \phi/2$. Equating the driving force produced by active pressure and the resistance obtained from friction at the interface of the embankment, the bottom reinforcement length L_B can be found using the following relationships:

$$\text{Resisting Force} = \text{FoS} \times \text{Sliding Force}$$

$$(W + P_a \sin \phi_b) \tan \phi_{min} = FoS P_a \cos \phi_b \quad (6)$$

$$W = \frac{1}{2} L^2 \gamma_r \tan \theta_r, \text{ for } L < H \quad (7)$$

$$W = [LH - \left(\frac{H^2}{2 \tan \theta}\right)] \gamma_r \text{ for } L > H \quad (8)$$

$$P_a = \frac{1}{2} \gamma_b H^2 K_A \quad (9)$$

where L is the length of the bottom reinforcing layer, H is the slope height, FoS is the factor of safety criterion for sliding (>1.3), P_a is the active earth pressure, K_A is the coefficient of active earth pressure, ϕ_{min} is the minimum angle of shearing friction either between reinforced soil and reinforcement or the friction angle of the foundation soil, θ is the slope angle, γ_r and γ_b are the unit weights of the reinforced and retained backfill, respectively, and ϕ_b is the friction angle of retained fill.

Fig. 3. Sliding stability analysis.

Considering two cases, i.e. $L < H$ or $L > H$, the following expressions can be obtained to calculate L_B :

For $L > H$:

$$\frac{L}{H} = \frac{1}{2\gamma_r \tan \phi_m} \left[\gamma_b K_A \cos \phi_b (FOS - \tan \phi_b \tan \phi_m) + \frac{\gamma_r \tan \phi_m}{\tan \theta} \right] \quad (10)$$

For $L < H$:

$$\frac{L}{H} = \sqrt{\frac{K_A \gamma_b (FOS \cos \phi_b - \tan \phi_m \sin \phi_b)}{\gamma_r \tan \theta_r \tan \phi_m}} \quad (11)$$

G. Check for Deep-Seated Global Stability of the Reinforced Embankment

It is further necessary to check that adequate safety for all those slip circles extending beyond the reinforced zone of the embankment is available. FHWA [19] recommends that a minimum of 1.30 should be maintained for all slip surfaces beyond the reinforced zone governed by:

$$FoS_{deep} = \frac{M_R}{M_D} \geq 1.3 \quad (12)$$

where M_D and M_R are the disturbing and resisting moments, respectively.

H. Determination of Embedment Length of Reinforcement and Check against Pull-Out

The embedment length L_e that extends beyond the rotational failure surface of the circular failure surface should be determined from the consideration that adequate pull-out resistance must be available for the provided reinforcement layers. The embedment length L_e can be calculated using:

$$L_e = \frac{\tau_{S-max}^{layer} FOS_{pull-out}}{F^* \alpha \sigma_v C} \quad (13)$$

where L_e is the embedment or adherence length in the resisting zone behind the failure surface and the minimum value is 1.0m, C is the reinforcement effective unit perimeter, e.g. $C = 2$ for strips, grids, and sheets, F^* is the pull-out resistance or friction-bearing interaction factor, and α is a scale effect correction factor to account for a non-linear stress reduction over the embedded length of highly extensible reinforcements based on laboratory data. FHWA [19] recommends α parameter values for different reinforcement material choices for extensible reinforcements such as geotextile, and it can be taken as 0.60. Finally, σ_v is the effective vertical stress at the soil-reinforcement interfaces.

I. Seismic Stability of the Embankment

The dynamic stability of the embankment should also be examined by the pseudo-static approach, applying horizontal and vertical earthquake excitations. The recommended minimum value for seismic analysis is:

$$FOS_{seismic} = 1.1 \quad (14)$$

III. RESULTS

A spreadsheet was developed based on the prescribed method for designing geotextile-reinforced slopes and an example case was investigated based on the suggested approach. Reinforced earth slopes consisting of fly ash-based fill materials have many benefits, including low unit weight, resulting in lower net pressure imparted on the foundation soil and reuse of waste material generated from coal-based thermal power plants.

A. Problem 1. Reinforced Slope Design

A 1H:1V geotextile reinforced road embankment made of fly ash mixed soil on the existing ground was required, with an angle of inclination of the slope $\beta=45^\circ$ and height $H=5.0m$. The

design surcharge load was $q=10.0kN/m$, and the geotechnical properties of the foundation soil and the embankment fill material are mentioned below:

TABLE II. SOIL PARAMETER DATA

Soil	ϕ' [°]	c' [kN/m ²]	γ [kN/m ³]
1	25	0	18
2	17	26	19

An entry-exit search method was employed to find the critical failure surface with the minimum FoS , the reinforcement length L_T to be provided at the top of the slope, and the failure surface corresponding to the maximum design total tensile force (T_S). Only "Toe failures" were investigated for this problem. The target FoS (FoS_T) value for which the slope was analyzed was $FoS_T=1.30$.

B. Calculation of the Maximum Reinforcement Tension Required to Obtain the Target FoS

The total tensile force T_S to be resisted by the geotextile reinforcement was calculated by (3). For all choices of the center of slip surfaces, the corresponding values of the disturbing moment M_D and the lever arm D were substituted to obtain the T_S values. T_{S-max} is the maximum of all these estimated T_S values. In Table III, T_{S-max} is designated as FoS_{TS-max} . Table III also contains the value estimated by the Slope/W software. It can be noted that the result of the spreadsheet matched very well with that of the Slope/W software. The stability of the seismic slope stability was verified considering a horizontal seismic coefficient value $k_h=0.08$, and a $FoS_T=1.10$ was used while performing the seismic slope stability analysis. Moreover, the required length of reinforcement to be provided at the top of the slope L_T can be determined, as shown in Figure 4.

TABLE III. FOS VALUES OF BISHOP'S SIMPLIFIED METHOD

Analysis type	FoS_{min}	Validation (slope/W)	FoS_{TS-max}	No of valid slip surface	Run time (s)
Static	0.600	0.589	0.783	180266	532.02
Seismic $k_h=0.08$	0.421	0.413	0.680	180286	550.40

Fig. 4. Static slope analysis results.

Table IV shows the L_T and T_{S-max} values obtained from the stability analysis using Bishop's simplified method [21]. The values of T_{S-max} were further compared with the design chart estimation of the maximum tensile force to be resisted by the

geotextile reinforcement based on the results provided in [20]. These design chart-based T_{S-max} values were calculated using (4) and designated as T_{S-max}^{check} . Table IV also shows the values of K , γ , and H' .

TABLE IV. RESULT AND CHECK OF THE MAX TENSION REINFORCEMENT

Analysis type	L_T (m)	T_{S-max} (kN/m)	K	γ (kN/m ³)	H' (m)	T_{S-max}^{check} (kN/m)
Static	5.20	78.703	0.25	18.0	5.55	68.062
Seismic	4.80	69.212	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table IV shows that T_{S-max} agrees reasonably well with the chart value of T_{S-max}^{check} for this problem. However, it should be noted that these analyses were performed in [20] without considering the presence of a water table and only for static loading conditions. If the actual slope conditions vary from those considered in [20], direct comparison of these two values may not be recommended. In [24], it was stated that a 25% variation between the chart and the computational results is acceptable from all practical points of view. A lower target FoS_T was used during seismic slope analysis because it would be uneconomical to use $FoS_T=1.30$, as seismic excitation occurs only for a brief time. As FoS_{TS-max} and T_{S-max} are higher in the case of static analysis, the design of the reinforced slope should be governed only by the results obtained from static analysis.

C. Calculation of Bottom Reinforcement Length L_B and Reinforcement Design

It is further necessary to determine the bottom reinforcement length L_B to be provided at the bottom of the embankment. The L_B length was calculated using wedge sliding analysis following (10)-(11). Table V shows the estimated bottom reinforcement length L_B for the current slope. For this problem, a reinforcement spacing $S_v=400$ mm was used to avoid wrapping of the face and surficial stability issues. Therefore, the total number of geotextile layers was obtained by dividing the height of the embankment by the spacing of geotextile layers, i.e. $N=5m/0.40m=12.5$. Hence, 12 geotextile reinforcement layers can be provided with the bottom layer placed after the first lift of the embankment fill. Table V lists L_B , the spacing of the geotextile layers and their number N , and the T_{S-max}^{layer} for both static and seismic cases.

TABLE V. LENGTH OF THE GEOTEXTILE (TOP AND BOTTOM) LAYERS

Analysis type	L_B (m)	T_{S-max} (kN/m)	Spacing (S_v) (m)	No. of layers (N)	T_{S-max}^{layer} (kN/m)
Static	6.70	78.703	0.4	12	6.55
Seismic	6.70	69.212	0.4	12	5.76

D. Embedment Length of Reinforcement and Checking Against Pull-Out

The spreadsheet estimated the embedment length of geotextile reinforcement L_e by subtracting the distance from the slope crest to the point of intersection of the failure surface corresponding to T_{S-max} from L_T . The distance from the slope crest to the point of intersection of the failure surface corresponding to T_{S-max} is denoted as L_{TS-max} . The spreadsheet

calculated the L_{TS-max} and L_{TS-max} values at a different depth z from the top surface of the embankment. Table VI summarizes the values of L_T , L_{TS-max} , L_e , vertical overburden pressure σ_v , and $FoS_{pull-out}$. The value of $FoS_{pull-out}$ was calculated with (13), where $C=2$, $F^*=0.67$, $\tan\phi'=0.204$, $\alpha=0.60$, and the unit weight of embankment fill $\gamma_b^f=18.0$ kN/m³. It is further observed that $FoS_{pull-out}$ was lowest near the top of the slope and increased gradually with depth z . It can be seen that $FoS_{pull-out}>1.50$ at all depths, which is the minimum recommended by [19]. Thus, the adequacy of the provided L_T at different depths can be checked.

TABLE VI. CALCULATION AND CHECK FOR $FoS_{pull-out}$ DURING STATIC SLOPE ANALYSIS

z (m)	L_T (m)	L_{TS-max} (m)	L_e (m)	σ_v	T_{S-max}^{layer} (kN/m)	$FoS_{pull-out}$
0.3	20.20	17.10	3.10	13.6	6.55	3.00
0.6	20.12	17.10	3.02	20.8	6.55	3.95
1.0	20.00	17.09	2.91	28.0	6.55	5.13
1.4	19.79	17.08	2.71	35.2	6.55	6.00
1.8	19.59	17.07	2.52	42.4	6.55	6.72
2.2	19.39	17.02	2.37	49.6	6.55	7.40
2.6	19.18	17.00	2.18	56.8	6.55	7.79

In the case of seismic loading, the obtained values were compared to the minimum suggested value of 1.50 to determine whether the projected embedded length is enough for the current situation, as shown in Table VII. The estimated L_e was lower than the obtained from static analysis because FoS_T was lower. It is also worth noting that $FoS_{pull-out}$ was lowest towards the top of the slope and progressively increased with depth z .

TABLE VII. CALCULATION AND CHECK FOR $FoS_{pull-out}$ DURING SEISMIC SLOPE ANALYSIS

z (m)	L_T (m)	L_{TS-max} (m)	L_e (m)	σ_v	T_{S-max}^{layer} (kN/m)	$FoS_{pull-out}$
0.3	19.60	17.64	1.96	15.4	5.76	2.16
0.6	19.41	17.41	2.00	20.8	5.76	2.97
1.0	19.21	17.18	2.04	28.0	5.76	4.08
1.4	18.82	16.87	1.96	35.2	5.76	4.93
1.8	18.43	16.56	1.88	42.4	5.76	5.69
2.2	18.24	16.24	1.99	49.6	5.76	7.07
2.6	17.65	15.62	2.03	56.8	5.76	8.24

E. Checking of the Reinforcement Length

It is necessary to check the simulated values of L_T and L_B with the design chart values [20]. The simulated L_B results are provided in Tables VI and VII, respectively. Corresponding to a value of $\phi_f'=25^0$, the study in [20] provides $L_T/H'=0.9$, and therefore, $L_T^{exp}=4.95$ m. It can be observed that the computed simulated values satisfied $L_T>L_T^{exp}$, therefore, they were more conservative estimates. Therefore, $L_T=5.20$ m was adopted as the final design value of the top reinforcement length. However, the tests in [20] were only performed on dry cohesionless sand and the effect of water pressure was not investigated. Similarly, the method in [20] provides an estimate of $L_B/H'=1.4$, and hence, $L_B^{exp}=7.80$ m. Although the problem considered does not exactly match the test conditions, it would be safer to consider the higher value of the bottom reinforcement against sliding failure; therefore, $L_B=7.80$ m is recommended.

F. Check for Deep-Seated Global Stability

All failure surfaces extending beyond the reinforced zone were investigated and the slip surface corresponding to the minimum FoS was identified. For all slip surfaces beyond the reinforced zone, a FoS_{deep} of 1.99 was obtained. Similarly, during seismic analysis, a FoS_{deep} of 1.71 was obtained. As per (12), a minimum FoS value of 1.30 must be maintained for the deep-seated failure condition. Therefore, the provided reinforcement length was considered to be adequate. If any slip surface with $FoS < 1.30$ had been located, it would require extending the bottom reinforcements beyond the deep-seated slip surface with the corresponding value of FoS_{min} . The spreadsheet automatically reported all associated data of the slip circle with FoS_{min} . Table VIII and Figure 5 show the results of the deep-seated stability analysis.

TABLE VIII. CALCULATION OF DEEP-SEATED FAILURE SURFACES

Type	L_T (m)	L_B (m)	FoS	Valid slip surface	Run time (s)
Static	5.2	7.8	1.99	3407	8.38
Seismic	4.8	NA	1.71	3407	8.32

Fig. 5. Deep-seated slope stability check.

G. Design Summary

The final design summary results of the geotextile-reinforced slope include the following specifications:

- Numbers of geotextile layers: For this problem, $N=12$ geotextile layers are sufficient.
- Length of the geotextile layer to be provided at the top surface L_T : For this problem, $L_T=5.20\text{m}$ is recommended.
- Length of the geotextile layer to be provided at the bottom of the embankment: $L_B=7.80\text{m}$.

Figure 6 shows the slope diagram with all the necessary details.

IV. DISCUSSION

A versatile MS Excel spreadsheet using the Visual Basic programming language was developed to analyze a geotextile-reinforced earth embankment and meet the target FoS value. In the future, the platform can be used to develop design charts for determining top and bottom reinforcement length ratios (i.e. L_T/H and L_B/H), considering pore water pressure loading. This platform can also perform deep-seated failure analysis. As commercial software, such as Slope/W, does not perform such analyses, the development of such a platform should be

regarded as a welcome addition to the geotechnical software pool.

Fig. 6. Details of the geotextile-reinforced slope.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper described the development of an MS Excel spreadsheet for designing geotextile-reinforced slopes using Visual Basic programming. The limit equilibrium method based on Bishop's simplified method [21] was used to carry out the slope analysis. The spreadsheet performs slope analysis for a target FoS value under both static and seismic loading conditions and also determines the maximum tensile force that reinforcement must resist to achieve it, along with the length of reinforcement to be provided at the top and bottom of the embankment. This spreadsheet can successfully search for numerous failure surfaces to achieve its objectives and reliably report the desired results. This spreadsheet can be used to perform deep-seated stability analysis to identify the failure surface with minimum FoS extending beyond the reinforced zone. An illustrative example was presented in detail, showing that static analysis governs the determination of the maximum tensile force to be resisted by geotextile layers because the seismic analysis is usually performed with a lower target FoS.

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An Experimental and Numerical Analysis of the Flexural Performance of Lightweight Concrete Beams reinforced with GFRP Bars

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ABSTRACT

Occasionally it is more crucial to lower the mass of a building component than to improve its rigidity, specifically in massive buildings like long-span structures where the self-weight of the floors is one of the significant challenges that engineers confront. Therefore, the main objective of this work is to explore the flexural performance of Lightweight Concrete Beams (LWCBs) reinforced with Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) bars in terms of curvature, cracks and failure modes, deflection, material stress-strain relationship, and joint end rotation. The flexural performance of LWCBs reinforced with varied GFRP bars and Steel Reinforcement (SR) ratios is assessed and compared to that of Normal Concrete Beams (NCBs) reinforced with SR. Numerical analytical models for the tested beams were created utilizing the iDiana software. Both analytical and experimental test results were compared. The study revealed a high correlation between the findings of Finite Element Models (FEMs) and those acquired from beam testing. The performance of LWCBs that utilized SR was equivalent to that of NCBs. The GFRP-reinforced LWCBs performed mostly as elastic deformed elements, with just little deflection post-load release. The study emphasized the significant potential for employing LWC and GFRP bars in the construction field's growth.

Keywords-flexural behavior; LWC beams; GFRP bars; FEM of LWC beams

I. INTRODUCTION

The analysis of prior research indicates that there are few available experimental tests for the bending response of beams made of LWCBs reinforced with GFRP bars, particularly for LWC beams with a specific gravity half that of NC. Many of these researches [1-12] were concerned with the structural behavior and the mechanical characteristics affected by the type of Lightweight Aggregates (LWA) and the composition of the LWC blends as well as the kind and ratio of Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) reinforcement. Authors in [1] experimentally tested lightweight and fibered lightweight concrete (LWC and LWCF) beams in terms of bending and ductility and compared the results with that of conventional concrete beams. They stated that the LWC beams exhibited significantly better performance than that of LWCF beams. A 16% reduction was observed in the weight of LWCF beams. The ductility was improved by 0.4% and 0.5% for LWC and LWCF beams, respectively. Authors in [2] conducted a series of experimental tests to explore the properties of LWC blends using Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPBs) instead of Coarse Aggregates (CA). The study concluded that adding EPB as a replacement of CA declined the mixes' density to 10.9KN/m³, resulting in reducing the concrete compression capacity and

modules of rupture. Authors in [3] studied the structural performance of a LWC beam reinforced with glass-and basalt-reinforced polymer (GFRP and BFRP) bars. The LWC in the study was created by replacing 50% of the normal aggregates with expanded clay LWA. According to that study, increasing the percentage of expanded clay LWA in concrete lowered its compressive strength. The ultimate load capacity and mid-span deflection for GFRP and BFRP reinforced beams were lower than those of steel-reinforced beams. Authors in [4] investigated the deflection of six steel-fibered LWC beams reinforced with Carbon-FRP (CFRP) rods under two-point loads. The testing results demonstrated that the introduction of steel fibers at a ratio of 0.6% by volume enhanced the structural behavior of the beams in bending, resulting in a 30% reduction in maximum deflection when compared to LWC beams without steel fibers. The maximum deflection of the LWC beams reinforced with CFRP rods was less than the permitted limit specified by ACI code requirements.

The goal of the current experimental and numerical analysis is to explore the performance of RC-beams made of LWC, which has a specific gravity half that of normal concrete and cylinder compressive strength of 30MPa. The LWC beams were reinforced with varied ratios of GFRP and SR rods. Four

LWC beams were assessed in terms of bending performance, failure mode, and serviceability, in addition to two reference beams built of NC with cylinder compressive strength of 30MPa.

II. CHARACTERISTICS OF MATERIALS UTILIZED IN BEAM PRODUCTION

A. Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer and Steel Rods

One downside of utilizing SR in structural concrete is the likelihood of corrosion, particularly in settings with high humidity and chloride attack. One good remedy for this issue is to use GFRP bars in reinforcing structural elements instead of SR bars since they are non-corroded. The axial and lateral resistance of the GFRP rods is regulated by the kind, quantity, and configuration of the GF utilized in each rod. Throughout all loading phases, the GFRP rods acted as a perfectly elastic material. The lateral resistance of GFRP rods is substantially lower than that of SR bars, but it has a higher tensile capacity. Table I and Figure 1 provide the design parameters of the utilized GFRP and SR rods. Figure 2 displays the results of the pull-out test between the LWC utilized in the current research and various reinforcing bars.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF GFRP AND SR RODS

Design parameter	GFRP rods	STR rods
Ultimate tension capacity (MPa)	1000	620
Yield strength (design strength) (MPa)	420 ^a	420
Elastic modulus (GPa)	60×10 ³	200×10 ³

^a. The GFRP rods have design strength and no yielding took place

Fig. 1. SR and GFRP bar's stress and strain under tension load.

Fig. 2. Relationship of bond stress between LWC and different types of bars.

B. Mechanical Properties of the utilized LWC

LWC is encouraged to be applied in the construction industry due to its favorable physical characteristics, including low heat conductivity and density. The LWC used in the present study was developed to have the half-density of NC [13]. Table II displays the design parameters of the LWC employed in the current research as well as the composition of 1m³ expressed as a percentage of cement weight. Figure 3 illustrates the splitting and flexural tensile test for the LWC employed in the study.

TABLE II. LWC BLEND COMPOSITION AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Material/Mechanical properties	Percentage of cement weight / value
Cement type I 52.5	1
Fine expanded clay 0/2	0.83
Coarse expanded clay 2/9E	0.15
Coarse expanded clay 6.5	1.06
Water-cement ratio	0.63
Silica fume	0.08
Super plasticizer	0.01
Concrete compressive strength (MPa)	34
Direct tensile strength (MPa)	2.25
Modulus of rupture (MPa)	2.46
Elastic modulus (GPa)	12×10 ³
Fresh/dry specific weight (g/cm ³)	1.43/1.25

Fig. 3. (a) Splitting and (b) flexural tensile strength tests of the used LWC.

C. Beam Preparation and Test Setup

Four simply supported beams with a reinforcement ratio of 0.5% and 1% were manufactured using LWC, which had a specific gravity half that of NC. Two other beams were built utilizing NC with the same steel reinforcement ratios of 0.5% and 1.0% for comparison. All the tested beams had a 3300mm overall length, 150mm×300mm cross-sectional dimensions, and were exposed to 2-point loads at the third span. All tested beams were subjected to displacement control technique with a loading rate of 0.01mm/s. All beams' longitudinal bars were extended to the beam's end for a total of 3300mm. LVDT gauges were affixed to the ends of the bars at the end face of the beam to measure any slippage between the longitudinal bars and the surrounding concrete at the end zone of the beam. Figure 4 displays the beam dimensions and the test set up. Several methods have been employed to monitor each tested beam. Five different locations underneath each beam were used to detect the deflection using LVDTs. Four 2-gauge LVDTs at the ends of the beams were used to keep record of the slippage between the longitudinal compression of tensile reinforced bars and concrete. The gauges were used to quantify the compressive and tension strains in the horizontal and vertical bars. The gauges were affixed to the beam surface 20mm in the compression area, to determine the height of the compression side at the beam's mid-span. With the help of the iDiana FE software, the gauge locations were established.

Fig. 4. Dimensions and test setup for the tested beams.

Fig. 5. FEM of the S1 tested beam.

In order to design the examined beams in accordance with ACI 440.1R-15 [14], and to look into model expectations for the behavior of the beams, such as the moment-curvature relationship and the transmission of stresses and strains throughout the beams, the FE model depicted in Figure 5 was created using the iDiana software prior to the conducted experiments. Table III displays the beams' details.

TABLE III. FEATURES AND DETAILS OF THE STUDIED BEAMS

Beam ID	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
Concrete type	LWC	LWC	LWC	LWC	NC	NC
Concrete grade (MPa)	30/33	30/33	30/33	30/33	30/37	30/37
Cross-section (mm)	150×300					
Bar type	GFRP	GFRP	SR	SR	SR	SR
Reinforcement ratio (%)	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5
Top reinforcement	2 ϕ 8					
Transverse reinforcement/m	10 ϕ 8					

III. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL VALIDATION

The moment-curvature relationships produced by the developed FEM were compared with those established based on the experimental data. By dividing the maximum compression strain at the topmost layer of the beam by the height of the compression zone, it is possible to compute the curvature at various bending moment values. Using 6 strain gauges, each 20mm in the mid-span compression zone, it was possible to experimentally measure both the maximum compression strain and the depth of the compression zone as depicted in Figure 4. The moment-curvature relationships produced by the FEM and the experimentally tested beams are displayed in Figure 6. Two sets of beams were considered with regard to reinforcing ratio. The reinforcement ratio for sets S1, S3, and S5 was 1% and 0.5% for S2, S4, and S6. Apart from B1, LWC beams reinforced with GFRP bars with 1% reinforcement ratio, there is generally no discernible variation between the numerical and the test-generated moment-curvatures. In B1, the variation in curvature between the experimental and FEM curves reaches 25.2% at the

breakdown. The response of LWC beams reinforced with SR rods is comparable to that of NC beams, particularly at small reinforcement ratios. Nevertheless, utilizing GFRP rods boosts the LWC beams' curvature at the same load level. It should be mentioned that the moment capacity of the SR beams (LWC or NC beams) reaches a specific level and is maintained for a considerable rise in curvature prior to the collapse. The GFRP-reinforced beams can, however, reveal deformation features similar to those of SR-reinforced beams before failure. The major distinction is that they have no ability to retain maximum moments with extended curvature before failure. This may be explained by the fully elastic properties of GFRP bars and the elastoplastic response of SR bars.

Fig. 6. Moment-curvature relationship of the experimentally tested beams and FE models at (a) 1% and (b) 0.5% reinforcement ratio.

IV. END-ROTATION RESPONSE OF THE STUDIED BEAMS

The moment end-rotation relationships for SR- and GFRP-reinforced LWC and NC beams are shown in Figure 7. The end-rotation might be computed at every load stage until the beam failure since the deflection readings at 0.5m from the support point throughout each beam's test have been recorded. The findings demonstrate that the moment-end rotation relationship for NC and LWC samples reinforced with SR bars are fairly similar. The geometry of the moment end-rotation relationship for SR-reinforced LWC and NC samples complies with the typical tendency of a moment-curvature relationship, increasing linearly till the yield of the SR bars. When the SR bars yielded, that caused a significant rise in end-rotation with a small raise in the bending moment, particularly when the reinforcement ratio was small, as in samples S4 and S6. This response indicates that the rotation-ductility of LWC and NC beams reinforced with SR bars is extremely similar.

Fig. 7. Moment end-rotation relationship of the studied beams with (a) 1% and (b) 0.5% reinforcement ratio.

It was noticed that the end-rotation of these samples immediately before rupture differed between $2^{\circ}17'$ and $3^{\circ}14'$ based on the ratios of reinforced bars. The moment end-rotation relationships for GFRP-reinforced LWC samples rise linearly until the rupture point. The greatest end-rotation for GFRP-reinforced samples ranged between $2^{\circ}51'$ and $3^{\circ}31'$, exceeding the greatest end-rotation for SR-reinforced beams. Generally, the bar's modulus of elasticity has a substantial effect on the moment end-rotation relationship.

V. LOAD-DEFLECTION RELATIONSHIP

Figure 8 depicts the load-deflection curves for the investigated beam sets (S1, S3, and S5) and (S2, S4, and S6). The LWC samples reinforced with SR bars (S3 and S4) performed similarly to the NC reference samples (S5 and S6). As predicted, the SR-reinforced LWC and NC samples turned nonlinear following the yielding of SR bars, with a dramatic rise in deflection, but a minimal rise in load capacity. Nevertheless, the GF-reinforced samples functioned in a different way. The load increased with deflection, and the load-deflection curve was nearly linear until rupture.

Fig. 8. Load-deflection curves of the studied beams reinforced with (a) 1% and (b) 0.5% reinforcement ratio.

Prior to the SR yield, the maximum deflections of GF-reinforced samples were 3 times greater than those of SR-reinforced samples. SR-reinforced samples with a 0.5% reinforcement ratio (S4 and S6) exhibit better ductile responses than those with a 1% reinforcement ratio (S3 and S5) at the maximum load phase. The mid-span deflection of the GF-reinforced sample (S1) was 1.5-times greater than those of the SR-reinforced samples (S3 and S5) for 1% reinforcement ratio, while for samples with 0.5% reinforcement ratio, the mid-span deflection in the GF-reinforced beam (S2) was nearly equivalent to those of the SR-reinforced samples (S4 and S6). For higher reinforcement ratios, the discrepancy in mid-span deflection between GF- and SR-reinforced samples is greater than at small reinforcement ratios.

VI. CRACK NUMBER AND DISTANCE

The number of cracks and the distance between them, at different load stages, were recorded for all tested beams. Table IV summarizes the crack behavior of the LWC and NC beams at various reinforcing ratios. The tested beams' side area was partitioned into 3 equal portions (2 outer areas and 1 central area). The number and distance between cracks were measured in each of these areas right before the beam's ultimate strength. For the reference beams made of NC and reinforced with SR

bars, the number of cracks in the lower 3-quarters of the height of the central area ranged between 11 and 13, with a maximum spacing between cracks ranging from 91 to 111mm. The lower number of cracks (11:13) compared to (27:39) for GF-reinforced beams (S1 and S2) may be due to the lower modulus of elasticity of GFRP bars compared to SR bars. The height of cracks up to 3-quarters of the height of the reference beams revealed a typical tension failure mode for SR-reinforced beams.

When considering the GFRP reinforcement ratio, the frequency of cracks tended to raise with low reinforcement ratios. These findings may represent the impact of bar diameter and rib count on GFRP bars in enhancing bond and crack behavior, as reported in [15, 16]. The crack spacing for SR-reinforced beams made of NC is larger than that of beams made of LWC. This might imply that the bond and tensile strengths of NC are somewhat greater than those of LWC. Another observation made during tests is that cracks in SR-reinforced NC and LWC beams migrated upward with steady rise in point loads. But, in GFRP-reinforced beams, cracks grew swiftly from the bottom edge up to an altitude of three-quarters of the entire height, after which the cracks did not proceed further until collapse. This allows GFR rods with high strains to create the needed stresses to maintain force balance and reveals the impact of GFR rods with low modulus of elasticity.

TABLE IV. DETECTED CRACK NUMBER AND DISTANCE

Beam ID	Ultimate load ^a (kN)	Crack spacing (mm)	Number of cracks			Failure succession	
			Left area	Central area	Right area	First	Final stage
S1	64.1	36	22	27	21	GFRP ^b design strength 420MPa	Crushing in compression zone
S2	44.07	31	28	39	30		
S3	61.55	61	12	21	13		
S4	35.81	66	10	17	13		
S5	60.79	91	10	13	9		
S6	36.44	111	8	11	8	Yield of SR bars	

^a. The ultimate load value represents the value of load at each point on the beam
^b. GFRP bars have a perfect linear-elastic response with no yielding until rupture at 1000MPa

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the outcomes of the current research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- To present the LWC and NC beams reinforced with GFRP and SR bars, FEMs were created and verified after the comparison with the experimental results.
- In terms of maximum load capacity, moment-curvature, deflection, end-rotation, crack behavior, and failure mode, LWC and NC beams reinforced with SR bars displayed to a great extent an equivalent flexural performance.
- The beams reinforced with GFRP bars had a similar load capacity, but a larger deflection than those strengthened with SR bars. This might be ascribed to the lower Young's modulus of GFRP bars.

- Following load discharge, the remnant deformations in GFRP-reinforced beams may be ignored in comparison to those in SR-reinforced beams. This might allude to the GFRP bars' perfect linear-elastic behavior as opposed to the SR bars' elastoplastic behavior.
- The progression of crack height in GFRP-reinforced beams is quicker in the early stages of loading until it reaches around three-quarters of the beam's height and then becomes significantly slower until failure.
- The progression of fracture height in SR-reinforced beams behaved gradually as applied loads increased.

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Comparison of the Charpy Resilience of Two 3D Printed Materials: A Study on the Impact Resistance of Plastic Parts

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ABSTRACT

Charpy impact testing is a widely used method for the evaluation of the toughness of materials, including 3D-printed plastic parts. This study performed Charpy test on 3D-printed samples made of PLA and ABS. Factors such as layer thickness and infill percentage varied (0.10, 0.15, and 0.20mm layer height and 50, 75, and 100% infill percentage) to investigate how they affect the mechanical properties of 3D printed parts, including their toughness.

Keywords-3D printing; FDM; Charpy test; resilience

I. INTRODUCTION

Charpy impact testing is a widely used method for evaluating the toughness of materials, including 3D-printed plastic parts. The Charpy test involves striking a notched sample with a pendulum and measuring the energy absorbed by it as it fractures. There is a growing interest in the use of 3D printing technologies for producing plastic parts, but concerns remain about their impact resistance and durability, leading to extensive studies on the Charpy resilience of 3D-printed plastic parts [1-3].

Some studies have shown that the Charpy resilience of 3D-printed plastic parts can vary significantly depending on the printing process, material properties, and design parameters, as factors such as layer thickness, infill density, and printing orientation can affect the mechanical properties of the 3D-printed parts, including their toughness [4-7]. Despite these challenges, there have been promising developments in the use of 3D printing technology for producing high-strength plastic parts with good impact resistance [3]. Various approaches have been explored, such as optimizing printing parameters and incorporating fillers into the printing material to improve the Charpy resilience of 3D-printed plastic parts [4, 8]. Overall, the Charpy resilience of 3D printed plastic parts remains an

important area of research for improving the performance and durability of 3D printed products, particularly in applications where impact resistance is critical [9-12]. The Charpy resilience of 3D-printed plastic parts could play a crucial role in many applications, such as aerospace [3], automotive industry [7], medical industry [8], and sporting goods industry.

This study investigated how different printing parameters affect the mechanical properties of 3D-printed parts by varying layer height and infill percentage. The layer height is the thickness of each material layer deposited by the 3D printer. A smaller layer height can result in a smoother surface finish but may also decrease the strength of the part due to the lower interlayer bonding strength. The infill percentage refers to the amount of material used to fill the interior of the part. A higher infill percentage generally results in a stronger part, but may also increase weight and printing time [14-17]. The printing process can be optimized to produce parts with the desired balance of strength, weight, and surface finish by varying both these parameters [18]. This approach can lead to the development of new 3D printing materials and printing processes that can produce parts with improved mechanical properties, and ultimately expand the range of applications for 3D-printed parts [19-22]. In industrial equipment, 3D-printed plastic parts with good Charpy resilience could be used in the

production of heavy machinery which can be subjected to high loads and impact forces [23-27]. In general, any application where the 3D-printed plastic part is expected to be subjected to impact loads, shock, or vibration, could benefit from improved Charpy resilience [27-28].

II. MATERIALS, METHODS, AND PROCEDURES

A. Parameters Setup

Table I shows the technical specifications provided by the filament producers (Raise for PLA and Verbatim for ABS). This study fabricated samples with 3 infill percentages: 50, 75, and 100%. Resilience tests were performed on both materials (PLA and ABS) to assess their mechanical characteristics, as shown in Table II. The height of the layer was also varied, taking values of 0.1, 0.15, and 0.20mm, as listed in Table II.

TABLE I. 3D-PRINTED SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS

Parameters	Material Specifications	
	PLA	ABS
Nozzle diameter	0.40mm	0.40mm
Build orientation	Flat	Flat
Top solid layers	4 layers	4 layers
Bottom solid layers	4 layers	4 layers
Outline/perimeters shell	3 outlines	3 outlines
Internal fill pattern	Lines	Lines
External fill pattern	Rectilinear	Rectilinear
Internal infill angle offsets	45°-135°	45°-135°
Extruder temperature	210°C	240°C
Heated bed temperature	60°C	110°C
Default printing speed	70mm/s	45mm/s
Cooling fans	on	on
Filament diameter	1.75mm	1.75mm
Filament density	1.24g/cm ³	1.04g/cm ³

B. Sample Preparation

A Raise E2 3D printer was used to fabricate the samples with a volume capacity of 330×240×240mm. The samples were designed with the Solid Edge Software and were converted into STL format. The slicing parameters, including internal structure pattern, infill percentage, and layer thickness, were fine-tuned with the Idea Maker [29]. The samples were X-Y oriented and printed with a bed platform for better adhesion to the printing table, as shown in Figure 1. The tests were performed on an Instron Charpy resilience tester (Figure 3), according [30]. This test can be used to explore how particular types of 3D-printed samples behave under specified impact conditions and to gauge the brittleness or toughness of samples within the constraints of the standard test environment (20°C and 45% humidity). Figure 2 shows the dimensions of the samples. A type A notch was included in the sample design with a radius $rN=(0.25\pm 0.05)$ mm.

C. Charpy Test

A series of tests were conducted to assess the mechanical performance and impact resistance. Table II shows the sample sets number for each printing parameter. The impact properties test was performed at the Liea laboratory, in ISIM Timișoara, on an Instron Pendulum Charpy tester.

TABLE II. PRINTING PARAMETERS

Constant parameters						
Building orientation		X, Y				
Extrusion temperature:		T_e				
Bed temperature:		T_p				
Speed:		V_p				
Variable parameters				Spur gears		
Layer height (H_e)		Infill percentage (P_n)		ABS	PLA	
(mm)		(%)		No. samples		
0.10		50	75	100	15	15
0.15					15	15
0.20					15	15

Fig. 1. Printed samples for 3 different layer thicknesses: 0.10, 0.15, and 0.20mm.

Fig. 2. Sample dimensions.

Fig. 3. Instron testing machine.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Charpy impact tests were conducted to examine the energy absorption and damage type of the various configurations. This test utilizes a dynamic three-point bending experiment on a notched specimen using a Charpy device. The experimental arrangement involves the specimen, anvils that provide free support for it, and a pendulum attached to a rotating arm that is pinned to the machine frame. The pendulum is elevated to a predetermined height and then released to fall along a circular path, striking the specimen at its midpoint. This impact transfers kinetic energy to the specimen and causes the

pendulum to rise to a measurable height [31]. Tables III and IV show the values and averages of maximum energy absorbed for each combination of layer height and infill percentage of the PLA and ABS materials studied. The total fracture energy was determined by [31]:

$$E_T = mg(h_0 - h_f) \pm 0.2 \text{ (J)} \tag{1}$$

where E_T is the total energy, m is the mass, g is the gravitational acceleration, h_0 is the original height, and h_f is the final height.

TABLE III. AVERAGE VALUES OF PLA IMPACT ENERGY

Sample no. PLA	Energy (J)
0.10 100%	0.0781374
0.10 75%	0.0884992
0.10 50%	0.071886
0.15 100%	0.0809428
0.15 75%	0.0749916
0.15 50%	0.0780908
0.20 100%	0.0821652
0.20 75%	0.0799704
0.20 50%	0.0764726

TABLE IV. AVERAGE VALUES OF ABS IMPACT ENERGY

Sample no. ABS	Energy (J)
0.10 100%	0.3244052
0.10 75%	0.2304624
0.10 50%	0.287763
0.15 100%	0.2698752
0.15 75%	0.247020
0.15 50%	0.2491146
0.20 100%	0.313584
0.20 75%	0.2775298
0.20 50%	0.2841294

Fig. 4. Range of maximum energy absorbed for PLA samples.

The maximum impact energy was significantly different when using PLA or ABS. As shown in Table III, the average values of layer thickness and infill percentage for PLA samples were very similar. In particular, layer thickness did not influence the dispersion of the average values. As expected, some notable values were noticed for the 100% infill specimens. In addition, the ABS material exhibited a much higher toughness. This printed material is more likely to withstand high levels of impact without fractures, as its results were 75.91% higher in 0.1mm layer thickness and 100% infill, as shown in Figure 6. Lower differences in maximum energy can be noticed for the combinations: $H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$:68.81%; $H_s=0.10\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$:69.28%; $H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=75\%$:69.64%; $H_s=0.15\text{mm}$, $P_u=50\%$:68.65%. As noted in [32-34], the average values of the mechanical characteristics were different for ABS and PLA. Figure 7 shows that although

the tensile strength is higher for PLA, ABS behaves better in terms of absorbed impact energy. The impact energy of a material depends on its composition, microstructure, geometry, temperature, loading rate, and testing method. These factors also affect the deformation and failure behavior of the material under impact loading.

Fig. 5. Range of maximum energy absorbed for ABS samples.

Fig. 6. Comparison of maximum energy absorbed for PLA and ABS.

Fig. 7. Variation of impact energy.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the impact resistance testing of the two most common materials used in 3D printing with FDM technology to compare them to help users choose the right material for different practical applications. The PLA material is more brittle in the Charpy test because it absorbs a small amount of energy during testing, while ABS has a ductile behavior because it absorbs a large amount of energy. It is important to note that the maximum Charpy energy for a printed part can be influenced by a variety of factors, including the printing parameters, such as the variation of layer height and infill percentage, part design, and post-processing techniques. PLA has a fragile compartment at the Charpy test because it absorbs a small amount of energy during testing, while ABS behaves as ductile because it absorbs a large

amount of energy. Therefore, it's a good idea to test and validate the toughness and impact resistance of 3D-printed parts under actual use conditions.

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A Cluster-based Undersampling Technique for Multiclass Skewed Datasets

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ABSTRACT

Imbalanced data classification is a demanding issue in data mining and machine learning. Models that learn with imbalanced input generate feeble performance in the minority class. Resampling methods can handle this issue and balance the skewed dataset. Cluster-based Undersampling (CUS) and Near-Miss (NM) techniques are widely used in imbalanced learning. However, these methods suffer from some serious flaws. CUS averts the impact of the distance factor on instances over the majority class. Near-miss method discards the inter-class data within the majority of class elements. To overcome these flaws, this study has come up with an undersampling technique called Adaptive K-means Clustering Undersampling (AKCUS). The proposed technique blends the distance factor and clustering over the majority class. The performance of the proposed method was analyzed with the aid of an experimental study. Three multiminority datasets with different imbalance ratios were selected and the models were created using K-Nearest Neighbor (kNN), Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF) classifiers. The experimental results show that AKCUS can attain better efficacy than the benchmark methods over multiminority datasets with high imbalance ratios.

Keywords-K-means clustering; multiclass; resampling; skewed; undersampling

I. INTRODUCTION

Most of the real-world available data, e.g. for medical diagnosis, credit card transactions, fault detection, and activity recognition, are imbalanced. The term imbalance is a reflection of the difference in frequency of data distribution over the various classes in the dataset. The frequency of data present in one class is often higher than the frequency of the other classes. In terms of probability, the prior probabilities of various classes are different. For a binary class imbalanced problem, there is one minority class and one majority class. Training a model with this imbalanced data induces a bias towards the majority class. For a multi-class environment, imbalance has a bit different presentation. Data imbalance can occur in one of two ways: one majority class with numerous minority classes (multiminority case) and one minority class with numerous majority classes (multimajority case) [1].

Three things should be noted while working with imbalanced data. (a) There is a great difference in the frequency of the elements present in majority and minority classes. (b) Minority class data have a small probability of occurrence, so it is challenging to obtain new minority instances from the real world. (c) The classification result is much more influenced by the majority class instances, so the

classification model is biased towards the majority data [2]. However, the interesting fact is that while the overall accuracy of the model is high, the minority classification is near to zero. This is corrected with the aid of resampling techniques.

Resampling techniques make the skewed dataset balanced. Resampling can be done in the form of oversampling, undersampling, or in hybrid mode. Oversampling techniques add new synthetic data to the minority classes for making the dataset balanced. Undersampling techniques eliminate data from the majority classes. Hybrid techniques are combinations of both to make the dataset balanced [3]. Oversampling technique expands the real data with synthetic samples and these synthetic data may overlap with the actual instances of other classes. Random oversampling, Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE), and Adaptive Synthetic (ADASYN) are the most popular oversampling techniques. Undersampling techniques eliminate data from the majority class and this elimination will sometimes be reflected in the form of prominent data loss [4]. For balancing the skewed data, an appropriate resampling technique can be chosen from the available techniques.

The major contribution of this study is the proposal of an undersampling technique for multiminority dataset

classification. The proposed work is implemented with adaptive K-means clustering algorithm [5]. The proposed technique is named Adaptive K-means Clustering Undersampling (AKCUS). Another important factor to be considered is the imbalance ratio of the datasets which is used for model training. Another contribution of this work is the reduction of the ratio of skewness among various classes. The effectiveness of the proposed algorithm over 3 multiminority datasets with imbalance ratios of different levels is described.

II. RELATED WORKS

Several undersampling techniques are proposed in the literature. Most of them recognize the less informative occurrences, on account of the redundancy involved. Tomek links are pairs of instances which belong to different classes and are mutually nearest neighbors. These Tomek links from the dataset were eliminated in [6]. Edited Nearest-Neighbor (ENN) rule, removes those data points which belong to different classes from a majority set with K nearest neighbors [7]. Condensed Nearest Neighbor (CNN) is another undersampling technique which chooses a subset from the training set such that each data in the training set and its nearest neighbors in the subset belong to the same class. This technique is slower as it requires multiple passes over the training dataset [8]. Near-Miss (NM) method performs data undersampling in the majority class [9]. This is done by identifying their distance to every other data in the same class. Authors in [10] proposed the UnderBagging technique, in which in every iteration the dataset is undersampled randomly. Sorting of undersampled data depending on the corresponding weighted Euclidean distance from the minority data was proposed in [11]. Authors in [12] proposed a method which uses a collection of hardness measures for classification and they found that instance hardness is mainly caused by the overlapping of classes. Authors in [13] proposed a cluster-based approach of undersampling to balance the dataset and the classification was done with the aid of back propagation neural networks [13]. Authors in [14] proposed a hybrid algorithm which combines methods like EUS, AdaBoost, cost sensitive modification, and adaptive boundary decision strategy. EUSBoost [15] incorporates Random Undersampling (RUS) with Boosting algorithm and outperforms the existing proposals with the use of evolutionary undersampling approach. EasyEnsemble [16] is an ensemble of ensembles which trains a classifier for every new bag, and each bag is trained by AdaBoost. For multiclass skewed distributions, no specific methods are proposed.

In this study, a resampling mechanism for multiminority datasets is proposed and its effectiveness is measured.

III. PROPOSED WORK

Undersampling is the process of removing excess data from a skewed dataset in order to make it balanced. Majority class data are considered for clustering and in this work, adaptive k-means clustering is done over the majority class. The different clusters are identified, and data elimination was conducted over these clusters. The proposed method can be applied in real world multiminority datasets.

In cluster center-based undersampling, the primary stage is to split the skewed binary class dataset into training data and testing data. The training data are arranged based on the majority and minority sets. Undersampling is applied in order to eliminate the excess number of elements present in the majority set. In this method, the majority data are portioned into different bags and on each bag RUS is performed. Each undersampled bag is clubbed with the minority class for training the model. K clusters are formed, this K being the same with the number of elements present in the minority set ($K=N$). These K clusters are produced over M samples of the majority set. The entire majority set is replaced by cluster centers. The mean of data present in a cluster is treated as the cluster center. The nearest K neighbors of the cluster center are removed in order to obtain a balance among the majority class and the minority class [17].

The proposed Adaptive K-Means Clustering Undersampling (AKCUS) technique uses the Adaptive K-means algorithm. This algorithm calculates the cluster center effectively. The center points for multiclass data clusters can be identified by the algorithm. The majority class data are considered for clustering. This algorithm selects K elements from the set of the majority class. These selected elements are treated as seed. The properties defined by each element define the properties of the corresponding cluster. Euclidean distance is used to compute the distance [15]. The distance between each element and a cluster, the distance between two elements, and the distance between two clusters are computed. For two elements, P_1 and P_2 , with n dimensions, the distance can be calculated as:

$$D = \sqrt{(P_{11} - P_{21})^2 + (P_{12} - P_{22})^2 + \dots + (P_{1n} - P_{2n})^2} \quad (1)$$

where $P_1 = (P_{11}, P_{12}, P_{13}, \dots, P_{1n})$ and $P_2 = (P_{21}, P_{22}, P_{23}, \dots, P_{2n})$.

In this algorithm, the distance between the clusters is identified and the value is stored in an array in the form of a triangular matrix. The shortest distance between the clusters D_{min} is recognized and the nearest clusters are also recognized. Cluster formation, corresponding centroid calculations, and farthest data elimination are mentioned in the algorithm:

Algorithm of the proposed AKCUS:

Step 1: Get the multiclass imbalanced dataset and identify the majority and minority classes.

Step 2: Compute the mean frequency of the minority class records and let it be stored in a variable called Freq.

Step 3: Identify the excess data of the majority class from the Freq data and let it be stored in a variable called excess.

Step 4: Take one majority class data for under-sampling.

Step 5: Apply adaptive K-means clustering algorithm to find the cluster points of the majority class.

1. Convert the data format from array to vector.
2. Select k elements from the majority class and assign these elements as seed of the cluster.

3. Compute the distance between each element and seed using the Euclidean distance formula.
4. Compute the threshold value of the shortest distance between clusters D_{min} .
5. Compare every distance with this threshold value and then update the cluster centroid.
 - a. For any element P_i , which does not belong to any cluster, the distance of P_i from each cluster is computed. If the distance is 0 for a cluster, P_i is assigned to that cluster, and the algorithm proceeds to the next non-clustered element.
 - b. Element P_i is assigned to the closest cluster when the distance between P_i and the cluster is less than distance D_{min} .
 - c. If the value of D_{min} is below the distance of the element from the nearest cluster, the two closest clusters C_1 and C_2 are selected and are merged in C_1 . Cluster C_2 is eradicated by eliminating all the instances belonging to it and its image is removed. After that, the new instance is added to this empty cluster for creating a new cluster.
6. The above steps are repeated based on the threshold value, and the centroid values are updated.

Step 5: Find the distance between each element and the corresponding centroid of the cluster.

Step 6: The elements with the largest distance are discarded from the dataset.

Step 7: Apply Step 6 for excess/k number of times in each cluster.

Step 8: Apply Step 4 to Step 7 for the other majority class data.

Step 9: Finally concatenate the minority class subset and reduced majority class subsets.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The proposed resampling technique in conjunction with various machine learning algorithms was used in this study. The input dataset was extracted from the KEEL data repository. Multimajority datasets with different imbalance ratios were chosen. The implementation was done in MATLAB. Figure 1 shows the different stages of the experiment. The different stages are:

- Selecting three multimajority datasets with different imbalance ratios from the KEEL repository. These datasets are of 3-class classification.
- Data pre-processing was done over the selected datasets for removing noisy data.
- The data were split in 75:25 training-testing ratio.
- Classifiers like K-Nearest Neighbors (K-NN), Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF) were applied, and the corresponding model performance was evaluated.

- Resampling techniques like AKCUS, RUS, ENN, and NM were applied to the training data.
- The resampled data with different techniques were used to create models with K-NN, DT, and RF and the model performance was evaluated.
- The performances of various models before and after applying various resampling techniques are analyzed.

Fig. 1. Various stages in the study.

A. Data Used

A list of experiments was conducted to study the effectiveness of the proposed AKCUS algorithm. The empirical review was conducted on multiclass skewed datasets available in the KEEL data repository [18, 19]. Three multimajority datasets, namely New-Thyroid, Thyroid, and Wine were chosen. The information related to these datasets is given in Table I. The original data distribution plots of the datasets are shown in Figure 2.

B. Resampling Methods Used

In the data pre-processing stage, records were validated, and imbalanced datasets were transformed into balanced with the aid of resampling techniques. The proposed AKCUS was applied over the datasets and the classification results were compared with those of the existing undersampling techniques RUS, ENN, and NM.

C. Selected Classifiers

K-NN, DT, and RF were chosen for creating models in this experiment.

D. Performance Evaluation

The performance of different models that were built with the several resampling techniques and classifiers were assessed with the aid of the confusion matrix [20]. Confusion matrix denotes True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN) values. Using the confusion matrix, different metrics like accuracy, error, precision, F1-score, and G-mean of various models can be calculated.

TABLE I. DATASET INFORMATION

Dataset name	No of instances	Imbalance ratio	Attributes	Class label	No. of records
New-Thyroid	215	5	6	Normal	150
				Hyper	35
				Hypo	30
Thyroid	720	40.16	22	1	17
				2	33
				3	666
Wine	178	1.48	14	1	59
				2	71
				3	48

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The learning capability of different models can be identified with the help of performance metrics. In this study, all the datasets employ a data split of 75:25 ratio of model training and testing. The data distribution before and after applying the resampling methods is represented in Table II. Both RUS and NM bring similar numbers of elements after resampling. The selected datasets have multiple minority classes and a single majority class. In this experiment, the resampling occurs over the majority class.

TABLE II. DATA DISTRIBUTION BEFORE AND AFTER RESAMPLING

Dataset	Skewed data distribution			After undersampling								
	c1	c2	c3	RUS/NM			ENN			AKCUS		
				c1	c2	c3	c1	c2	c3	c1	c2	c3
New-Thyroid	147	35	37	20	20	20	113	20	18	25	25	25
Thyroid	17	37	666	11	11	11	11	3	458	12	12	12
Wine	57	71	38	29	29	29	40	38	29	30	30	30

To evaluate the effectiveness of AKCUS, a comparison was made between the performance metrics of different datasets. The results of a selected dataset with different balancing techniques as well as with different classifiers were considered. Initially, consider the New-Thyroid dataset and its performance metrics (Table III). It is evident that the model with RF classifier and AKCUS resampling technique over the New-Thyroid dataset achieved better performance than the other models. K-NN classifier works its best with the RUS sampled dataset. Classifiers DT and RF give promising results with AKCUS balanced datasets. Figure 3 represents the comparative chart of performance over various techniques applied over the New-Thyroid dataset.

Fig. 2. Data distribution of the datasets.

Fig. 3. Result comparison of various techniques over the New-Thyroid dataset.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE METRICS OF NEW-THYROID DATASET

Resampling technique	Classifier	Accuracy	Error	Precision	F-Score	G-mean
Imbalanced set	K-NN	0.875	0.125	0.9477	0.8079	0.8051
	DT	0.9063	0.0938	0.9275	0.8725	0.8737
	RF	0.9531	0.0469	0.9783	0.9379	0.9289
RUS	K-NN	0.9454	0.0546	0.9687	0.9425	0.9387
	DT	0.8545	0.1455	0.8439	0.8549	0.8597
NM	RF	0.9531	0.0469	0.9783	0.9361	0.9305
	K-NN	0.8363	0.1637	0.8438	0.8369	0.8539
	DT	0.8181	0.1819	0.8303	0.8207	0.8414
ENN	RF	0.8545	0.1455	0.8558	0.8567	0.8763
	K-NN	0.9090	0.091	0.9509	0.9031	0.9109
	DT	0.8727	0.1273	0.893	0.8733	0.8763
AKCUS	RF	0.9272	0.0728	0.9595	0.9213	0.9266
	K-NN	0.875	0.125	0.9477	0.8079	0.8051
	DT	0.9688	0.0313	0.9589	0.9589	0.8051
	RF	0.9818	0.0182	0.9888	0.9828	0.9832

The thyroid dataset (Table IV) is another multim minority dataset. The model with DT classifier along with AKCUS resampling achieves better performance than the other models. KNN classifier performs its best with imbalanced data and AKCUS balanced dataset. DT and RF classifiers achieve their

best with AKCUS balanced dataset. Figure 4 shows the comparative chart of the performance over various techniques applied over the Thyroid dataset.

Fig. 4. Result comparison of the Thyroid dataset.

TABLE IV. PERFORMANCE METRICS OF THYROID DATASET

Resampling technique	Classifier	Accuracy	Error	Precision	F-Score	G-mean
Imbalanced set	K-NN	0.9954	0.0046	0.9983	0.9735	0.9673
	DT	0.9861	0.0139	0.949	0.9204	0.9295
	RF	0.9815	0.0185	0.8804	0.848	0.9004
RUS	K-NN	0.3944	0.6059	0.3623	0.2603	0.384
	DT	0.9611	0.0389	0.7679	0.9	0.8567
	RF	0.95	0.05	0.7476	0.8348	0.8567
NM	K-NN	0.1111	0.8889	0.3473	0.1443	0.4008
	DT	0.9611	0.0389	0.7976	0.8726	0.8867
	RF	0.8555	0.1445	0.6623	0.7052	0.7694
ENN	K-NN	0.9111	0.0889	0.4198	0.3927	0.4019
	DT	0.9277	0.0723	0.8455	0.569	0.6712
	RF	0.9333	0.0667	0.8957	0.5882	0.6922
AKCUS	K-NN	0.9954	0.0046	0.9983	0.9735	0.9673
	DT	0.9907	0.0093	0.9507	0.937	0.9673
	RF	0.9861	0.0139	0.949	0.9204	0.9295

The last multimorality dataset taken into consideration is the Wine dataset. Table V shows the metrics for the Wine dataset with different resampling methods and classifiers. The models with AKCUS did not perform better than the other models. KNN classifier performs its best with RUS sampled data. DT classifier achieved its best with NM and ENN. RF achieved its best with the imbalanced dataset, because the difference in the ratio of data among different classes is very low in Wine, so the proposed algorithm is not able to achieve better performance and this dataset can be considered as a special case. Figure 5 shows the comparative chart of the performance of various techniques over the Wine dataset.

The performance of the imbalanced dataset with different resampling techniques and classifiers are specified above. From the metric tables it was clear that AKCUS technique produces better results for all the datasets except the Wine dataset. The ratio of data imbalance was also considered while performing resampling. For the Wine dataset, the imbalance ratio is very low, so the balancing techniques were not much reflected. The imbalance ratio also acts as a factor while resampling measures are applied. Undersampling techniques sweep out some data

that are available in the dataset and this will sometimes reflect badly on the data distribution. The proposed method sweeps out samples which are not very relevant for the learning process.

Fig. 5. Result comparison of the Wine dataset.

The Thyroid dataset, with a high imbalance ratio of 40.16, shows promising results with the proposed resampling technique. The New-Thyroid dataset with imbalance ratio of 5 shows better results with our proposed resampling technique. However, in the Wine dataset, with imbalance ratio of 1.48, the proposed method did not show much success.

TABLE V. PERFORMANCE METRICS OF WINE DATASET

Resampling technique	Classifier	Accuracy	Error	Precision	F-Score	G-mean
Imbalanced Set	K-NN	0.7042	0.2958	0.6951	0.687	0.7733
	DT	0.8592	0.1408	0.8478	0.8314	0.8756
	RF	0.97	0.03	0.96	0.947	0.95
RUS	K-NN	0.9761	0.0239	0.9666	0.9717	0.9728
	DT	0.9047	0.0953	0.9166	0.9166	0.9166
	RF	0.95	0.05	0.939	0.947	0.9494
NearMiss	K-NN	0.97	0.03	0.966	0.97	0.9724
	DT	0.9285	0.0715	0.9473	0.9196	0.9265
	RF	0.95	0.05	0.939	0.947	0.9494
ENN	K-NN	0.97	0.03	0.966	0.97	0.9724
	DT	0.9285	0.0715	0.9166	0.9178	0.9269
	RF	0.95	0.05	0.939	0.947	0.9494
AKCUS	K-NN	0.7183	0.2817	0.7313	0.7054	0.7928
	DT	0.8451	0.1549	0.8397	0.8205	0.7928
	RF	0.9577	0.0423	0.95	0.9534	0.9722

VI. CONCLUSION

Machine learning models for classification created with imbalanced data have a bias towards the majority class, affecting the classification process. In this study, a new undersampling technique named Adaptive K-means Clustering Undersampling (AKCUS) is proposed for multiclass skewed data classification. AKCUS performs well with multimorality cases of imbalanced data. As undersampling removes elements from the actual dataset, sometimes this removal will affect the loss of prominent data. The proposed AKCUS algorithm is concerned about the prominent elements in multiple classes and its removes data which are not very relevant to the classification process. In this work, the imbalance ratio was

considered as an important factor. The proposed algorithm works well with multiminority datasets that have high imbalance ratio. If the imbalance ratio is low, the result is not much affected by the resampling procedure. So, the proposed algorithm produces promising results for datasets with high imbalance ratio. This work can be extended to tackle the bias over big data models.

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Experimental Performance of Fiberglass Geogrid in Asphalt Pavements

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ABSTRACT

This study performed an experimental investigation of asphalt concrete with and without fiberglass geogrid reinforcement, using specimens in the laboratory and in situ. A 100kN/m fiberglass geogrid was used. The results showed that with the fiberglass geogrid reinforcement, the flexural strength of the asphalt increased by 24.82%, deformation was significantly reduced, and the elastic modulus did not improve significantly. In addition, using the Hamburg Wheel Tracker test, the fiberglass geogrid reinforced asphalt samples had a 7.41% reduced rutting depth. Finally, two segments in situ were also tested showing that the flexural strength of asphalt concrete increased by 24.27% and the structural strength of the pavement increased by 25.24%. These results show that pavement structures are significantly improved when reinforced with fiberglass geogrid.

Keywords-asphalt pavement; fiberglass geogrid; flexural strength; elastic modulus; Hamburg Wheel Tracker

I. INTRODUCTION

Asphalt pavement, or flexible pavement, is widely used worldwide due to its excellent characteristics, such as favorable construction conditions, comfortable exploitation, and convenient maintenance [1]. In summary, asphalt pavement is popularly used as Hot Mix Asphalt (HMA), containing a mixture of approximately 94-95% stone, sand, filler, and 5-6% bitumen. The asphalt mixture is heated, mixed properly, placed on the base and subbase layer, compacted using a heavy roller, ready to be used when it cools. There are one or more HMA layers for the surface course to design flexible pavement. The asphalt pavement is significantly affected by heavy traffic loading and seasonal temperatures. Many types of damage, such as rutting, cracking, and raveling [2-3], occur on asphalt pavements. Due to its importance, researchers and material experts try to find the best way to improve pavement rehabilitation with low cost and low use of raw materials. In general, to renovate an old road pavement, an overlay layer is usually paved over the existing surface to cover the existing cracked layers. However, the disadvantage of this method is sustained by the crack propagation of the current layer, which is known to be complex. With the recent development of new technologies and materials, geogrids are applied to reinforce asphalt pavements to improve stiffness, stability, and service life and reduce the thickness of additional pavement layers resulting in material and cost savings [4-14]. The mechanical

properties of asphalt pavements are significantly affected by the properties and positioning of geogrids, the stiffness of the asphalt layer, the characteristics of the subgrade, the aggregate base course, and the HMA [4-6, 8, 15]. In [15], it was shown that a higher-strength geogrid is more effective in improving asphalt pavement. For rehabilitation, geogrid can be used as an effective method to counteract the reflective crack of the existing surface [16]. In addition, the geogrid improves the flexible pavement in two ways, by reducing the surface rutting potential and by decreasing the base course [4].

This study aims to investigate the properties of glass geogrid-reinforced asphalt pavement in the laboratory and in situ. Specimens were prepared by a semi-automatic roller compactor. The geogrid used was commercial fiberglass with a tensile strength of more than 100kN/m provided by a local company. Flexural strength, elastic modulus, and Hamburg wheel tracking tests were conducted in the laboratory. In addition, geogrid reinforcement was applied in situ to investigate the current situation, construction technology, resilient modulus, compacted asphalt layer, and flexural strength from boreholes. The results obtained provide guidelines for researchers, engineers, and designers in improving the method of designing reinforced asphalt pavements with fiberglass geogrid.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Asphalt Concrete

Figure 1 shows the grain size distribution of the aggregate mix, which followed the requirements of TCVN 8819 [17]. A bitumen 60/70 grade was applied, which satisfied the current Vietnamese standard. The mineral filler had a grain size less than 0.075mm and 2.731g/cm³ specific gravity. Table I shows the basic properties of the asphalt concrete.

Fig. 1. Grain size distribution of the aggregates.

TABLE I. BASIC PROPERTIES OF ASPHALT CONCRETE

No	Characteristics	Unit	Results	Requirement
1	Bitumen content	%	5.32	-
2	Compressive strength	kN/cm ²		
	t = 20 ^o C		51.44	-
	t = 50 ^o C		21.54	-
3	Marshall stability	kN	11.96	8.0
4	Flow measurement	mm	3.62	2-4
5	Voids in the total mix	%	4.42	3-6
6	Voids in mineral aggregates	%	16.70	min 15

B. Fiberglass Geogrid

The fiberglass geogrid used is shown in Figure 2 and had 100kN/m tensile strength. Table II shows its mechanical properties provided by the manufacturer.

TABLE II. PROPERTIES OF FIBERGLASS GEOGRID

No	Properties	Method	Unit	Result
1	Tensile strength (MD)	ASTM D6637	kN/m	≥ 100
2	Tensile strength (CMD)	ASTM D6637	kN/m	≥ 100
3	Elongation (MD)	ASTM D6637	%	≤ 3
4	Elongation (CMD)	ASTM D6637	%	≤ 3
5	Coating with asphalt			Visual
6	Color			Black

MD is machine direction, CMD is the cross-machine direction

Fig. 2. Fiberglass geogrid used.

C. Sample Preparation

Figure 3 shows the asphalt samples with and without fiberglass geogrid reinforcement.

Fig. 3. Sample with different dimensions: (a, b) 320x260x80mm for flexural strength and wheel tracking tests; (c, d) 320x260x101.6 mm for elastic modulus test.

Specimens with dimensions of 320x260x80mm, denoted by M1, were prepared for flexural strength and wheel tracking tests. Similarly, specimens with dimensions of 320x260x101.6mm were prepared for the elastic modulus test, denoted by M2. The specimens were compacted by a semi-automatic roller compactor SYD 0703 with a 500mm wheel radius and a width of 300mm. The highest compaction pressure was 30kN/cm², the roller compaction cycle was at least 12 times/1 minute, using a fully heated roller compactor plate.

Subsequently, each specimen was cut into 5 small specimens with dimensions of 50×50×200mm for flexural strength, and d×h=101.6×101.6mm for elastic modulus tests. The temperatures used were 15, 30, and 50°C for flexural strength, elastic modulus, and wheel tracking tests, respectively. The repeated loading was performed with a frequency of 25±2.5 cycles per minute and a pressure of 0.7MPa.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Flexural Strength

Table III shows the test results for the flexural strength of asphalt concrete samples with (MGC) and without fiberglass geogrid reinforcement (MKGC). Figure 4 shows that the flexural strength values of the asphalt concrete with and without fiberglass geogrid reinforcement were 2.48 and 3.08MPa, respectively, indicating an increase of 24.82%. This can be explained as follows: at a temperature of 15°C, the asphalt concrete becomes hard under the influence of loading, which causes cracks and destruction. The fiberglass geogrid in asphalt concrete samples absorbs part of the load and distributes it over a larger area. On the other hand, the tensile strength of the fiberglass geogrid-reinforced asphalt is higher, slowing down the deformation and failure of the sample. Therefore, asphalt concrete samples with fiberglass geogrid reinforcement have higher tensile strength when bending than the unreinforced ones.

TABLE III. FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF ASPHALT CONCRETE WITH AND WITHOUT FIBERGLASS GEOGRID

No	Sample	Dimension (mm)			Deformation (mm)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Average strength (MPa)	Average deformation (mm)
		Wide	Length	Height				
1	MKGC 1	53.0	200	54.7	1.67	2.5	2.5	1.66
2	MKGC 2	54.0	200	54.0	1.6	2.2		
3	MKGC 3	53.3	200	54.7	1.7	2.6		
4	MKGC 4	51.7	200	54.3	1.58	2.5		
5	MKGC 5	51.3	200	55.7	1.75	2.5		
6	MGC 1	50.0	200	54.0	2.29	3.2	3.1	2.29
7	MGC 2	50.7	200	55.3	2.3	3.2		
8	MGC 3	53.3	200	55.3	2.32	3.2		
9	MGC 4	54.7	200	54.7	2.22	2.9		
10	MGC 5	51.0	200	55.7	2.32	2.9		

As shown in Figure 5, asphalt concrete samples without fiberglass geogrid reinforcement had a lower deflection than the reinforced ones when subjected to maximum load. The average deflection of the unreinforced samples was 1.66mm, while the average of the reinforced samples was 2.29mm, an increase of 37.89%. This can be explained by the fact that the fiberglass geogrid participates in the bending along with the asphalt concrete, thereby increasing the deflection of the sample. This means that the failure of the reinforced samples will take place more slowly, reducing the cracks in the concrete. In [18], it was shown that the flexural behavior of various geogrids (e.g. fiberglass, polyester, and geomembrane geogrids) had a significantly improved resistance to cyclic loading from 66 to 100%.

Fig. 4. Flexural strength of asphalt concrete.

Fig. 5. Deformation of asphalt concrete.

B. Elastic Modulus

Table IV shows the elastic modulus of asphalt concrete samples with and without fiberglass geogrid reinforcement. These results show that the average elastic modulus of the samples reinforced with fiberglass geogrid increased from 508 to 521MPa, an increase of 2.6%. Overall, the elastic modulus of fiberglass geogrid-reinforced samples did not change significantly. The explained is that when the samples were compressed, the area of the presser was equal to the contact area of the sample and the glass geogrid, so the influence of the fiberglass geogrid in this experiment was not significant. However, the results of this experiment do not accurately reflect the ability to increase the elastic modulus of the asphalt sample because the sample was small, so there are only one or two grid cells in the sample.

C. Hamburg Wheel Tracker (HWT) Test

The HWT test was conducted to investigate the rutting potential of asphalt concrete. The specimens were conditioned at a temperature of less than 25°C and the test conditions included water of 50°C and 15,000 cycles. Figures 6 and 7 show the results for both types of specimens at various positions (left, right, and average). The horizontal axis is the cross of the wheel passing the specimen, and the vertical axis is the depth of the specimen. For normal asphalt concrete, the rutting depth was 7.26mm, 5.50mm, and 6.38mm for left, right, and average, respectively. For fiberglass geogrid reinforced

asphalt concrete, the rutting depth was 6.76mm, 5.12mm, and 5.94mm for left, right, and average, respectively.

TABLE IV. ELASTIC MODULUS OF ASPHALT CONCRETE WITH AND WITHOUT GLASS GEOGRID

No	Sample	Dimension (mm)		Pressure (MPa)	Deformation (mm)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Average (MPa)
		Height	Diameter				
1	MKGC 1	104.0	101.6	0.5	0.100	520.0	508
2	MKGC 2	104.0	101.7	0.5	0.103	507.3	
3	MKGC 3	104.0	101.7	0.5	0.105	495.2	
4	MGC 1	104.2	101.7	0.5	0.098	534.4	521
5	MGC 2	104.1	101.6	0.5	0.100	520.5	
6	MGC 3	104.2	101.5	0.5	0.103	508.3	

For asphalt concrete samples reinforced with fiberglass geogrid, the depth of the wheel track was reduced by 7.41% compared to those without reinforcement. When the number of cycles increased to 8000, the average settlement of the two samples was almost the same (MGC: 4.25mm and MKGC: 4.47mm). At this point, the resistance against the wheel track was taken by the asphalt concrete. Furthermore, increasing the number of load cycles from 8000 to 15000 times, the MGC settlement increased on average from 4.25 to 5.94mm and the MKGC increased from 4.47 to 6.93 on average, showing that the reinforced concrete samples had less settlement. When the asphalt concrete samples were loaded vertically and the application time was continuously increased, the wheel pressure would be transmitted from layer 2 (thickness 30mm) to layer 1 (thickness 50mm). For the unreinforced concrete samples, this settlement was to assess the resistance of concrete to wheel load. Regarding the reinforced concrete samples, when the load transmitted through concrete layer 2 (thickness: 30cm) and meets the glass fiber mesh, the mesh would receive and redistribute the load evenly throughout the sample surface, leading to a reduction in the load. The pressure was transmitted to layer 1 of asphalt concrete, thereby reducing the depth of the wheel track. However, this decrease in rutting depth was not significant, approximately 7.41%. In the same way, in [12], it was concluded that geogrid reinforcement reduced the horizontal movement of the granular material, especially in the longitudinal direction.

D. Evaluation Of Applying Fiberglass Geogrid In Situ

This study selected two segments in the Kien Giang province, southern Vietnam, to investigate the potential of using fiberglass geogrid reinforcement in road construction in situ. Two damaged road sections, with reflection cracks and turtle shells, on Tran Khanh Du Street, including 100m from Km 15+660 to Km15+760 and 100m from Km 15+760 to Km 15+860 located in the territory of Rach Gia city, were selected. This route is densely populated. The road surface is degraded, damaged, and deformed, and the width of the road is not uniform, making it difficult for people and vehicles to travel. Therefore, repairing the existing road surface by reinforcing the asphalt concrete pavement and unifying the width of the road surface was an important issue. After improvement, the road

would be smooth and continuous, develop a complete transport network, create favorable conditions for people to travel, and promote commercial activities, tourism services, and industrial development.

Fig. 6. HWT tests without fiberglass geogrid reinforcement.

Fig. 7. HWT test with fiberglass geogrid reinforcement.

Some specific steps were followed to improve the current pavement surface, such as blowing dust to clean the existing road surface, applying the tack coat, placing the hot mix asphalt compensation layer, installing the fiberglass geogrid, placing the hot mix asphalt, and compacting the asphalt pavement. Similarly, a reference segment was also investigated without installing a fiberglass geogrid. After finishing the pavement improvement, the engineering properties of the asphalt concrete were investigated. The elastic modulus was measured by the Benkelman apparatus. The specimens were cut off from the site and prepared to test their flexural strength.

After the construction was completed, the street was put into operation for some time. Laboratory experiments were carried out to evaluate the quality and the technical efficiency of the fiberglass geogrid reinforcement on the asphalt pavement.

TABLE V. ELASTIC MODULUS OF FIBERGLASS GEOGRID REINFORCED ASPHALT PAVEMENT

Segment	Station	Deformation (0.01mm)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Characteristic deflection (0.01mm)	Characteristic elastic modulus (MPa)
Km15+760 -Km15+860	Km15+760	63.9	200.1	75.8	168.7
	Km15+765	68.2	187.6		
	Km15+770	63.9	200.1		
	Km15+775	68.2	187.6		
	Km15+780	72.5	176.6		
	Km15+785	59.7	214.4		
	Km15+790	68.2	187.6		
	Km15+795	59.7	214.4		
	Km15+800	68.2	187.6		
	Km15+805	72.5	176.6		
	Km15+810	72.5	176.6		
	Km15+815	63.9	200.1		
	Km15+820	68.2	187.6		
	Km15+825	63.9	200.1		
	Km15+830	68.2	187.6		
	Km15+835	72.5	176.6		
	Km15+840	68.2	187.6		
	Km15+845	68.2	187.6		
Km15+850	63.9	200.1			
Km15+855	72.5	176.6			

in situ indicated that when using geogrid, the strength of the pavement structure increased from 134.7MPa to 168.7MPa, an increase of 25.24%, as shown in Tables V and VI. This shows the technical efficiency of re-enforcing the asphalt concrete pavement with fiberglass geogrid. It is noted that the current elastic modulus of the surface pavement was about 120MPa.

The obtained experimental results show that the average flexural strength of the asphalt concrete reinforced with fiberglass geogrid increased from 2.39 to 2.97MPa, an increase of 24.27%. Figure 8 shows the detailed results and proves the technical efficiency of the reinforced asphalt concrete pavement with fiberglass geogrid. This increased flexural strength means that the crack resistance of asphalt pavement improved.

Fig. 8. Flexural strength obtained in situ.

TABLE VI. ELASTIC MODULUS OF NORMAL ASPHALT PAVEMENT

Segment	Station	Deformation (0.01mm)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Characteristic deflection (0.01mm)	Characteristic elastic modulus (MPa)
Km15+660 -Km15+760	Km15+660	85.2	150.1	95.0	134.7
	Km15+665	89.5	142.9		
	Km15+670	81.0	158.0		
	Km15+675	85.2	150.1		
	Km15+680	89.5	142.9		
	Km15+685	89.5	142.9		
	Km15+690	85.2	150.1		
	Km15+695	76.7	166.8		
	Km15+700	81.0	158.0		
	Km15+705	85.2	150.1		
	Km15+710	76.7	166.8		
	Km15+715	85.2	150.1		
	Km15+720	85.2	150.1		
	Km15+725	81.0	158.0		
	Km15+730	81.0	158.0		
	Km15+735	89.5	142.9		
	Km15+740	89.5	142.9		
	Km15+745	85.2	150.1		
Km15+750	81.0	158.0			

IV. CONCLUSION

The following conclusions can be drawn based on the results obtained in the laboratory and in situ:

- The flexural strength of asphalt concrete reinforced with fiberglass geogrid and without it was 2.48 and 3.08MPa, respectively, an increase of 24.82%. The deflection, when subjected to the maximum load of the fiberglass geogrid reinforced asphalt concrete increased by 37.89% compared to the unreinforced because the fiberglass geogrid participates in bending together with the concrete, thereby increasing deflection. This means that the failure process of the samples reinforced with fiberglass geogrid takes place more slowly and reduces the cracks in the asphalt concrete.
- The elastic modulus of the samples reinforced with fiberglass geogrid did not change significantly, because when the sample was compressed, the area of the presser was equal to the contact area of the sample, as well as the fiberglass geogrid. Therefore, the influence of the fiberglass geogrid was not significant. However, the results of this experiment do not reflect the ability to increase the elastic modulus of the asphalt sample because the sample was small.
- The average rutting depth of asphalt concrete without and with a fiberglass geogrid was 6.38 and 5.94mm, respectively. The rutting depth of fiberglass geogrid reinforced asphalt concrete was reduced by 7.41%. The

At first, the specimen without reinforcement was tested, and the results showed that the degree of compaction was equal to or greater than 0.98 which is compatible with the requirements of the Vietnamese standards. The Benkelman test

results also show that the resistance to rutting of the fiberglass geogrid reinforced asphalt concrete sample improved.

- When reinforcing asphalt concrete pavement with fiberglass geogrid in the studied segment, the flexural strength of the asphalt concrete increased by 24.27%, and the structural strength of the pavement increased by 25.24%. These results show that the pavement structure was greatly improved when reinforced with a fiberglass geogrid.

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Hydrogeochemical Assessment of Groundwater Quality and Suitability for Drinking and Agricultural Use. The Case Study of Fars Province, Iran

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to evaluate the hydrogeochemistry of aquifers in Fars province, Iran, from 2007 to 2017 and assess the groundwater's suitability for drinking and agricultural uses. A total of 35,000 samples were collected from wells and qanats across the province. Piper, Gibbs, and Durov diagrams were used to assess the hydrochemical facies and processes. Cross plots of different ions were investigated to assess ion exchange and determine the effects of anthropogenic activities, as well as the weathering and dissolution of different rocks and minerals in the aquifers. Groundwater quality and suitability for agricultural and drinking purposes were also assessed using physicochemical parameters including pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Total Hardness (TH), and calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, bicarbonate, sulfate, and chloride concentrations. Suitability for domestic purposes was assessed by comparing these values with the WHO standards. Sodium and alkalinity hazards, including Sodium Adsorption Ratio (SAR), sodium percentage (Na%), Permeability Index (PI), Magnesium Hazard (MH), and Residual Sodium Carbonate (RSC) were used to assess irrigation suitability, along with plotting Wilcox and USSL diagrams.

Keywords-groundwater chemistry; Geographic Information System (GIS); hydrochemical facies; suitability analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Groundwater resources, especially in arid and semi-arid regions, are important for the social and economic development. Iran, a developing country with a high population growth rate and relatively dry climate, suffers from severe decline in groundwater levels and is considered a hotspot for groundwater depletion. Easy groundwater access and inadequate supervision have exposed these valuable resources to over-exploitation in different parts of Iran. Excessive

groundwater extraction has had a significant impact on both groundwater level and quality. There are many environmental challenges as well, including saline intrusion and severe quality effects from both environmental and anthropogenic factors. Since it is important to rely on an efficient and healthy water resource to meet Iran's drinking, agricultural, and industrial needs, water quality assessment, especially for groundwater, (between 55 and 80% of water demand in Iran is supplied from groundwater resources) has become significant. Water quality

refers to the natural, physical, and chemical characteristics of water and any type of change that occurs for any reason [1-10]. Groundwater quality, which is usually controlled by physiochemical parameters, represents a response to all the processes and reactions that occur due to natural changes and anthropogenic activities [11]. Many factors including soil type, regional geology and topography, land use, the recharge source, climate change, atmospheric inputs, and interactions between surface and groundwater can affect groundwater chemistry [12-14]. Investigating the major ions to determine chemical indices and their spatial distribution can provide a clear picture of hydrochemical processes in aquifers. To this end, molar ion ratios can clarify the origins of solutes and characterize the occurring processes. Groundwater quality assessment in Iran is mostly limited to specific areas and periods, presenting significant gaps in knowledge, since there is a limited number of sampling wells and it is difficult to examine these sources over a long period. Thus, there is a need for a more thorough investigation of the issue. Considering the importance of investigating groundwater quality in Iran, the main objectives of this research were (1) to assess the groundwater's major ion chemistry and identify the hydrogeochemical processes affecting it and (2) to characterize the groundwater's suitability for agricultural and drinking purposes using relevant methods, diagrams, indices and standards based on a rich and reliable dataset.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Study Area

Fars Province covers approximately 122,400km² (6.7% of the country). It is located in the southwest of Iran. The average annual minimum and maximum temperatures vary between -7 and 2°C, and 25 and 40°C in this province. The average annual rainfall has been 320mm since about 2000, representing about 40×10⁹m³ [15]. The province's four climate zones are cold, temperate, hot, and very hot. Agriculture is important in Fars, with the main products being cereal (wheat and barley), citrus fruits, dates, sugar beet, and cotton. Some 71% of the province's agricultural area is allocated to irrigation farming and 29% to dry farming. Annual water consumption is approximately 10.5×10⁹m³, of which 8×10⁹m³ is supplied from groundwater. About 95% of the water used goes to the agricultural sector. Fars is a diverse province with varied geological characteristics. Different geological features in Fars, including the Zagros Mountains, are part of the Alpine-Himalayan orogenic belt and are composed of sedimentary and metamorphic rocks, Fars ophiolite complex that contains a variety of igneous, metamorphic, and sedimentary rocks, including pillow lava, sheeted dikes, gabbros, serpentinites, and cherts as well as Miocene-Pliocene sedimentary rocks, Quaternary volcanic rocks, and active faults.

B. Data Analysis

The physiochemical parameters of 72 different districts in Fars, each with more than 1000 sampling locations, were investigated. Some 35,000 samples were collected from wells and qanats from 2007 to 2017. The sampling frequency depends on several factors including the type of well and the purpose of the sampling and the regulations and guidelines set

by the local and national authorities. In Iran, the Ministry of Energy is responsible for managing and regulating the use of groundwater resources. The recommended frequency of sampling wells for drinking water is once per month. However, some regions in Fars province were required to be sampled more frequently up to 4 times per month.

Fig. 1. (a) Fars province, (b) schematic view of well (sampling point) distribution in Fars.

In order to manage the sampling point data and determine the groundwater hydrochemistry and its suitability for different purposes, the data were clustered with variables such as cations, anions, pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), and Total Hardness (TH). The suitability of groundwater resources for drinking use was assessed by comparison of the water samples' physiochemical characteristics and state variables with the limits recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) [16], salinity laboratory and Wilcox diagrams [17, 18], and the interpretation of several indices, including the Sodium Absorption Ratio (SAR) [19], sodium percentage (Na%) [18], Magnesium Hazard (MH), Residual Calcium Carbonate (RSC), and permeability index (PI) for all zones [20]. Piper, Durov, and Gibbs diagrams were used to determine the dominant water types and hydrochemical processes in Fars sub-basins [21-23]. All groundwater samples used were taken and analyzed under the supervision of the Iran Water Resources Management Company [24]. Groundwater quality data were measured in trusted water and wastewater laboratories licensed by Iran's Department of Environment, using the standard methods suggested by the American Public Health Association [25]. Groundwater quality data included major cations (i.e., Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and Na⁺), major anions (i.e., HCO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻), pH, EC, TDS, and TH. Analytical accuracy was calculated from (1):

$$B = \frac{(C-A)}{(C+A)} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where C and A are the sums of the cationic and anionic concentrations determined, respectively, in meq/L, and B is the ionic balance error (%) [26]. The ionic balance error did not exceed 8% in any sample analysis. Kriging interpolation, in Arc-GIS, was used to investigate groundwater quality spatially for drinking and irrigation. The statistical results of the analyzed samples are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF EC, PH, TDS, AND MAJOR IONS, DETERMINED IN THE GROUNDWATER SAMPLES.

Parameter	Unit	Minimum	Median	Mean	Maximum	Variance	Std. deviation
Ca ²⁺	mg/L	40.07	100.2	159.21	551.25	12,974.67	113.9064
Mg ²⁺	mg/L	6.99	60.76	85.64	413.98	4,569.25	68.07734
Na ⁺	mg/L	5.98	69.00	227.99	1,293.865	101,534.60	318.645
K ⁺	mg/L	0.78	3.13	5.55	34.79	30.93	5.561512
HCO ₃ ⁻	mg/L	170.82	244.04	252.89	366.06	1,434.63	37.87644
SO ₄ ²⁻	mg/L	73.88	222.86	342.16	1,597.24	100,883.30	317.6213
Cl ⁻	mg/L	8.88	124.25	491.65	5,145	506,802.70	711.9007
TDS	mg/L	245.27	1,229.99	1,917.94	8,734.18	2,573,619.00	1,604.25
EC	μs/cm	429	1,887	2,984.8	14,218	6,290,427	2,508.072
pH	-	6.77	7.54	7.54	8.33	0.009,052	0.095,144
TH	mg/L	170.669	715.94	928.18	3075	436,500.00	656.01

Fig. 2. Piper diagram.

Fig. 3. Durov diagram.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Ionic Types and Hydrogeochemical Facies

Piper and Durov diagrams were used in this study to determine hydrochemical facies. In the Piper diagram, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} (alkaline earth metals) and Na^+ (alkali metal) are the most common cations, while HCO_3^- (a weak acid) and SO_4^{2-} and Cl^- (strong acids) are the most abundant anions. To determine the groundwater's hydrogeochemical facies, the analytical results were plotted on a Piper ternary diagram [20], using AqQa software [27] (Figure 2). The two basal triangles in the Piper diagram show that Ca^{2+} is the dominant cation in 42 of the 72 districts, and HCO_3^- , followed by Cl^- , are the dominant anions. The calcium-bicarbonate type indicates that alkaline earth metals and weak acidic anions exceed alkali metals and strong acidic anions, respectively. Such water has temporary hardness. The dominance of these ionic species is evidence of anthropogenic activity. While calcium bicarbonate is the dominant water type, mixed types, and calcium chloride waters are also present. The plots show that most water samples fell in the alkaline earth metal field (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}), which dominates the alkali metals (Na^+ , K^+), while the weak acid (HCO_3^-) dominates the strong acids (Cl^- , SO_4^{2-}). Fresh recharge waters rich in Ca^{2+} are characteristic of most zones in Fars. The Durov diagram [21, 22] in Figure 3 was plotted to determine the dominant hydrochemical processes and the type of ion exchange. It is clear from the Durov diagram that most of the water lies along the dissolution or mixing line, i.e. ion exchange and reverse ion exchange are both feasible. The increasing trend of both TDS concentration and pH can also be seen in the graph.

B. Hydrochemical Process Identification

Scatter plots of ion concentrations enable interrelationships between the ions and the chemical reactions occurring in the aquifers to be recognized. Major ion concentrations were plotted as a function of calculated TDS values to identify the effective ions in groundwater mineralization. As shown in Figure 4, K^+ , Cl^- and Mg^{2+} are correlated strongly with TDS with correlation coefficients of 0.96, 0.9, and 0.88, respectively. These ions contribute the most to the groundwater mineralization and salinization in the study area. A plot of $\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+}$ versus Na^+ (Figure 5) is used to identify the ion exchange process. The data points fall above the 1:1 line, indicating reverse ion exchange, which normally takes place in the presence of clays. The plot of Ca^{2+} versus SO_4^{2-} provides evidence of predominating cation exchange [28]. Plotting Na^+/Cl^- versus EC (Figure 6(a)) is used to determine the effect of evaporation on groundwater chemistry. The graph should have a horizontal line to indicate the effect of evaporation and evapotranspiration [29]. The graph's trendline is inclined, showing that evaporation cannot be the main groundwater hydrochemical process in the area. TDS changes can arise from land use and/or pollution. In rural areas, nitrate, sulfate, sodium, and chloride ions originate from agricultural fertilizers, animal wastes, and wastewater [30]. The high correlation coefficient, 0.843 (Figure 6(b)), between TDS and $(\text{NO}_3^- + \text{Cl}^-/\text{HCO}_3^-)$ shows the effects of human activity on water chemistry [31, 32].

Fig. 4. Plots of major ion concentrations versus TDS. (a) Ca^{2+} , (b) Mg^{2+} , (c) Na^+ , (d) Cl^- , (e) K^+ , (f) SO_4^{2-} , and (g) HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} .

Fig. 5. Plots of (a) Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} versus Na^+ and (b) Ca^{2+} versus SO_4^{2-} .

C. Ion Exchange

Generally, groundwater is rich in sodium where there is the precipitation of calcite and/or cation exchange. In contrast, $\text{Ca}^{2+} - \text{Cl}^-$ type water commonly arises from reverse ion exchange. Both cation exchange and reverse ion exchange are

encouraged by aquifer materials leading to Na or Ca release into groundwater and Ca or Na adsorption, respectively [33-35]. As the Piper diagram indicates the possibility of ion exchange reactions, Schoeller chloralkali indices were employed to understand them. Chloroalkaline indices 1 and 2 (CAI 1 and CAI 2) were calculated for the study region groundwater using (2) and (3) [36, 37].

Fig. 6. (a) Na^+/Cl^- versus EC and (b) TDS versus $NO_3^- + Cl^-/HCO_3^-$.

$$CAI\ 1 = \frac{Cl^- - (Na^+ + K^+)}{Cl^-} \quad (2)$$

$$CAI\ 2 = \frac{Cl^- - (Na^+ + K^+)}{(SO_4^{2-} + HCO_3^- + CO_3^{2-} + NO_3^-)} \quad (3)$$

If the index values are negative materials are exchanged with Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} in the water, whereas the reverse process will give a positive value ($Cl^- > Na^+ + K^+$). The host rocks are the primary sources of dissolved solids in the water. The chloralkali indices for 21% of the study area were negative, indicating an exchange between Na^+ and K^+ in the water and Cl^- and Mg^{2+} in the soil. In 79% of the areas, however, reverse ion exchange occurred.

The Gibbs diagram (Figure 7) is widely used to establish the relationship between solutes in water and aquifer lithology. The diagram shows three fields: precipitation, evaporation, and rock-water interaction-dominated areas [23]. Gibbs plots of log TDS against $Na^+/(Na^+ + Ca^{2+})$ and $Cl^-/(Cl^- + HCO_3^-)$ were used to identify groundwater interactions that reflect that rock-water interaction and evaporation occur in this groundwater system. The dense clustering of points in the evaporation domain can be a sign of anthropogenic activity [37].

Fig. 7. Gibbs diagram.

It should be mentioned that several sources of contamination and anthropogenic activities affect the groundwater quality in Fars Province. Agricultural activities, which are the main source of income in the Province, and the extensive use of fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides, can lead to groundwater contamination. The excess use of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers can lead to nitrate and phosphate contamination. Industrial activities including oil and gas extraction, mining, and manufacturing can generate hazardous waste that may contaminate groundwater. The discharge of industrial wastewater into surface waters can also lead to groundwater contamination. Besides, the rapid urbanization and population growth in Fars Province has led to increased wastewater generation and disposal.

D. Groundwater Quality Evaluation

1) Drinking Suitability

There are several groundwater quality assessment studies that regard fluoride concentration in regions facing groundwater contamination problems using the Water Quality Index (WQI) and other physiochemical parameters [38-40]. Cations, anions, pH, EC, TDS, and TH are used to determine the groundwater's suitability for drinking in this study. The concentration minima, maxima, means, and standard deviations of contributing parameters are shown in Table I. The values were compared with WHO's guideline recommendations. Figure 8 shows the spatial distribution of all parameters.

TABLE II. CHEMICAL PARAMETER CONCENTRATIONS COMPARED WITH WHO RECOMMENDATIONS

Water quality parameters	WHO max allowable limit (1993)	Percentage of samples exceeding the standard	Concentration in the study area	Undesirable effect produced beyond the maximum allowable limit
Ca^{2+} (mg/L)	200 (mg/l)	31.95	(40.07-551.98)	Essential for human bone growth, high concentration cause hardness and inefficiency
Mg^{2+} (mg/L)	150	18	(6.99-413.16)	Essential for human bone growth, but high concentrations cause water hardness
Na^+ (mg/L)	200 (mg/l)	31.95	(5.98-1293.865)	High blood pressure or posing a risk for people suffering from kidney or heart diseases
K^+ (mg/L)	12 (mg/l)	13.89	(0.78-34.79)	High blood pressure, blood lipids due to K^+ deficiency
HCO_3^- (mg/L)	300 (mg/l)	9.72	(170.82-366.06)	Unknown
SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	400 (mg/l)	31.95	(73.88-1197.24)	Dehydration, gastrointestinal irritation-laxative effect
Cl^- (mg/L)	600	26	(8.88-5145)	Salty taste
TDS (mg/L)	1500	39	(245.89-8761.21)	Taste-gastrointestinal irritation
pH	6.5-8.5	0	(6.98-8.33)	Taste effects on mucus membrane and adverse effects on the water supply system
TH as $CaCO_3$ (mg/L)	500	50	(170-3075)	Encrustation in water supply and adverse effects on domestic uses

Fig. 8. Spatial distribution of major ions and hydrochemical parameters related to drinking suitability: (a) Cl⁻, (b) K⁺, (c) Ca²⁺, (d) HCO₃⁻, (e) Mg²⁺, (f) SO₄²⁻, (g) Na⁺, (h) TDS, (i) TH, (j) pH, (k) EC. City names: 0: Abadeh, 1: Eqlid, 2: Khorrambid, 3: Bavanat, 4: Mamasani, 5: Marvdasht, 6: Sepidan, 7: Arsanjan, 8: Shiraz, 9: Neyriz, 10: Kazerun, 11: Estahban, 12: Fasa, 13: FiruzAbad, 14: Farashband, 15: Jahrom, 16: Darab, 17: Zarrindasht, 18: Qirkazin, 19:Larestan, 20: Mohr, 21: Lamerd.

The average values of individual groundwater parameter concentrations were all within WHO's recommended limits, whereas some individual samples reported higher concentrations (see Table II). To investigate groundwater suitability for any purpose, it must be classified depending on its hydrochemical properties based on its TDS content [41, 42]. According to Table III, 63.91% of the samples were brackish water, and 36.09% were fresh water. In the classification based on [43], 15.27% of the samples were desirable and 20.82% were considered permissible for drinking purposes based on TDS (Table IV).

TABLE III. NATURE OF GROUNDWATER BASED ON TDS VALUES

TDS	Nature of water	Percentage
Up to 1000	Freshwater	36.09
1000-10000	Brackish water	63.91
10000-100000	Saline water	0
>100000	Brine water	0

The groundwater classification based on TH shows that 13% of the water is hard, and the rest is very hard. The WHO recommended maximum for TH for drinking is 500mg-CaCO₃/L, and 66% of the study area exceeds that limit. The pH value suitable for drinking water is specified as 6.5-8.5. The pH

value of most groundwater samples in the study area was between 6.98 to 8.33, with an average of 7.33 indicating an overall alkaline nature.

TABLE IV. CLASSIFICATION OF GROUNDWATER BASED ON TDS

TDS	Water type	Percentage
Up to 500	Desirable for drinking	15.27
500-1000	Permissible for drinking	20.82
<3000	Useful for irrigation	70.83
>3000	Unfit for drinking or irrigation	29.17

TABLE V. CLASSIFICATION OF GROUNDWATER BASED ON TH [44]

Total hardness as CaCO ₃ (mg/l)	Water class
< 75	Soft
75 – 150	Moderately hard
150 – 300	Hard
> 300	Very hard

EC is a measure of water's capacity to convey an electric current. The recommended EC limit for drinking water is 1500 μ S/cm [16]. The EC of the groundwater varies from 429 to 14184 μ S/cm with an average value of 2984 μ S/cm (Table I). Higher ECs indicate higher salt concentrations. The EC can be classified as type I if the enrichments of salts are low (EC < 1,500 μ mhos/cm), type II if the enrichment of salts is medium (EC 1,500 and 3,000 μ mhos/cm), and type III if the enrichments of salts are high (EC > 3,000 μ mhos/cm). According to the above classification, 56% of the total groundwater samples fell under type I and 26% under type II. The remaining 18% of zones fell into the high salinity class and thus have wide applicability with respect to agricultural use. However, for drinking use, a high value of EC denotes a proportionately high value of calcium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium. Calcium and magnesium are the most abundant elements in the planet's surface, and groundwater Ca²⁺ concentrations vary from 40.1 - 551.9 (Table II). The desirable limit of calcium concentration for drinking water is 75mg/l [16] and 32% of the zones fell beyond the permissible limit. Higher Ca²⁺ content can cause hardness and is undesirable for domestic uses as it causes encrustation and scaling. Magnesium content varies between 6.99 and 413.98mg/l (Table II). The maximum permissible limit of Mg concentration for drinking water is 150mg/l [16]. The concentration of Na⁺ varies between 5.98 and 1,293.865mg/l. Its maximum permissible limit is 200mg/l and 32% of the samples exceeded it (Table II). Groundwater with high sodium content is not suitable for agricultural use as it tends to deteriorate the soil. Potassium concentrations are low compared to Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, and Na⁺, with those in drinking water seldom reaching 20mg/l. The sample K⁺ concentration varied between 0.78 and 25.4mg/l. The maximum permissible limit of K⁺ in drinking water is 12mg/l, and it was found that 86% of the samples had concentrations below it (Table II). The value of HCO₃⁻ was between 170.03-366.06mg/l, and only 10% of the samples exceeded the WHO limit. Sulfate is one of the major anions occurring in natural waters. The upper limit for sulfate concentration in drinking water is 400mg/l [16]. The sulfate concentration in the study area ranged between 73.88 and 1,196.24mg/l with an average concentration of 342.16mg/l,

indicating that 68% of the samples were within the allowable limit. The chloride in groundwater may come from diverse sources [45]. In the study area, the concentration of chloride was between 8.88 and 5,145mg/l. The excess chloride in the water is usually taken as an index of pollution and considered a tracer for groundwater contamination [46]. Chloride determination may indicate water intrusion of different compositions, or trace and measure the rates and volumes of water mass movements.

2) Irrigation Suitability

It is important to develop successful projects supplying irrigation water in addition to controlling salts and alkalis in the soil. In this regard, salinity indices such as Na%, SAR, RSC, PI, and MH were examined. Salinity and alkalinity hazards are important parameters for determining the suitability of groundwater for agricultural use and influence crop yields. United States Salinity Laboratory (USSL) classification and the Wilcox diagram were also used for better assessment.

a) Salinity and Alkalinity Hazards

EC is a good measure of salinity hazard to crops, as it reflects the TDS in groundwater and is the most important parameter in determining water suitability for irrigation. TDS refers to any minerals, salts, metals, cations, or anions dissolved in the water. Excess salinity reduces the osmotic activity of plants and thus interferes with water and nutrient absorption from the soil [47]. Different types of water based on EC values are presented in Table VI and EC and TDS spatial distribution in Figure 8. According to the Wilcox diagram, only 47% of the samples were below the permissible limit of EC. According to the AqQa software results, 33%, 40%, and 26% of samples were reported in the range of very high, high, and medium salinity hazards, respectively. Based on TDS classification, the groundwater in around 80% of the study area was classified as permissible for agricultural use at TDS < 3000.

SAR is an important parameter in determining the suitability of groundwater for irrigation because it is a measure of alkali/sodium hazard to crops as excess sodium in water can cause undesirable effects [48]. SAR is calculated by:

$$SAR = \frac{Na^+}{\sqrt{\frac{Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}}{2}}} \quad (4)$$

where sodium, calcium, and magnesium are measured in meq/l. The SAR value can be an indicator of the extent to which sodium is absorbed by soils. Sodium concentration can reduce soil permeability, deteriorate soil structure, and influence crop yield [49]. The waters were classified for irrigation based on the ranges of the SAR values [19]. Based on the SAR values, 94% of the samples were excellent and 6% were good for irrigation (Table VI). In addition, for better insight, the USSL plot presented in Figure 9 indicates that 7% of the groundwater samples fell in the C1S1 (low salinity-low sodium), and 18% of the samples fell in the C2S1 category. About 20% of the groundwater samples fell in the C3S1, indicating high salinity or high sodium type. Only 9% fell in the very high salinity to low sodium category (C4S1), and the rest of the samples had very high salinity and are not shown in the diagram.

Fig. 9. USSL diagram used to classify irrigation water suitability.

In addition to the sodium adsorption ratio, Na% can be a risk indicator for soil in agriculture. High sodium in the soil can be detrimental to soil structure, aeration, and infiltration [26, 49]. The sodium in irrigation waters is usually denoted as a percent of sodium. In all natural waters, Na% is a common parameter for the evaluation of their suitability for irrigational purposes [50]. Na% values are obtained by:

$$Na\% = \frac{Na^+ \times 100}{Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+} + Na^+ + K^+} \quad (5)$$

All ionic concentrations are expressed in meq/l.

Fig. 10. Wilcox diagram.

TABLE VI. CLASSIFICATION OF GROUNDWATER BASED ON TH, EC, SAR, NA%, RSC, MH, AND PI

Classification	Category	Range	Sample %
TH [44]	Soft	Less than 75	0
	Moderately hard	75-150	0
	Hard	150-300	20
	Very hard	More than 300	80
EC [18]	Excellent	Less than 250	0
	Good	250-750	13.88
	Permissible	750-2250	47.88
	Doubtful	2250-5000	17.12
SAR [19]	Excellent	Less than 10	94.38
	Good	10-18	5.62
	Doubtful	18-26	0
Na% [18]	Excellent	0-20	38.02
	Good	20-40	0
	Permissible	40-60	36.62
	Doubtful	60-80	19.71
RSC [53]	Good	Less than 1.25	98.6
	Medium	1.25-2.5	1.41
	Bad	More than 2.5	0
MH [52]	Good	Less than 50	81.69
	Poor	More than 50	18.3
PI [51]	Class 1	More than 75	0
	Class 2	75-25	97.2
	Class 3	Less than 25	2.8

As shown in Table VI, 38%, 36%, 19.71%, and 4.22% of the samples are considered excellent, good, permissible, and doubtful, respectively, based on Na%. Na% is plotted against EC in a Wilcox diagram [18]. As shown in Figure 10, 16% of the groundwater samples were excellent to good, 41% good to permissible, 10% doubtful to unsuitable, and the rest of the samples were considered unsuitable for irrigation due to the aforementioned reasons.

b) Permeability Index

A water suitability classification for irrigation was developed in [51] based on the PI, as soil permeability is impacted by the long-term use of water containing sodium, calcium, magnesium, and bicarbonate. The PI is calculated by:

$$PI = 100 \times \frac{Na^+ + \sqrt{HCO_3^-}}{Na^+ + Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}} \quad (6)$$

All ion concentrations are expressed in meq/l. The PI in the study area was between 1.93 and 28.14 with an average value of about 15.48 (Table VI). A classification based on PI was proposed by WHO for assessing the suitability of groundwater for irrigation purposes. According to the PI values, 97.2% of the samples fell into class 2, and only 2.8% belonged to class 3 which is considered unsuitable for irrigation.

c) Magnesium Hazard

In most waters, calcium and magnesium maintain a state of equilibrium. There is evidence that Mg²⁺ can be detrimental to soil texture in water with a high sodium content in particular. MH index was developed in 1972 [52]. High MH harms crop yields as the soil becomes more alkaline.

$$\text{Magnesium ratio} = \frac{\text{Mg}^{2+}}{(\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+})} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

In the study area, the MH ranged between 14.28% and 59.45%. The 81.69% of the collected samples showed an MH ratio below 50% (suitable for irrigation), while 18.4% were unsuitable and can cause adverse effects on agricultural yields (Figure 11).

Fig. 11. Spatial distribution of (a) Na%, (b) PI, (c) SAR, (d) RSC, (e) MH.

d) Residual Sodium Carbonate

The RSC index of water samples in the study site was estimated by [19]:

$$\text{RSC} = (\text{CO}_3^{2-} + \text{HCO}_3^-) - (\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+}) \quad (8)$$

All ion concentrations are expressed in meq/l. Irrigation water based on RSC is classified as good, medium, and bad [33, 53]. For irrigation purposes based on RSC values, 98.6% of the groundwater samples were found good for irrigation, and the remainder belonged in the medium category.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Groundwater is a major water source for domestic and agricultural uses. Groundwater quality and its suitability for drinking and agricultural use, as well as hydrogeochemical processes, in Fars province, Iran, were assessed in this paper. In this regard, 35,000 groundwater samples were collected from 2007 to 2017 and analyzed for pH, electrical conductivity, major ion concentrations, total dissolved solids, and total hardness. Interpretation of the hydrochemical analyses revealed that in most zones, the groundwater was hard to very hard, fresh to brackish, and alkaline in nature. Based on the Piper diagram, Ca^{2+} was the dominant cation in 42 out of the 72 districts, and bicarbonate followed by chloride, were the dominant anions in the province. Effects of anthropogenic activities were evident in this region due to the dominance of the aforementioned ions. The dominant type in the province was calcium bicarbonate, followed by mixed types and calcium chloride. According to the Durov diagram, the hydrochemical reactions in this area were mixed reactions with different origins, mixing and reverse cation exchange reactions, and water infiltration with calcium bicarbonate types. K^+ , Cl^- , and Mg^{2+} were strongly correlated with TDS, which shows that these ions contribute the most to the mineralization and salinization of the study area's groundwater. The plot of calcium versus sulfate can be evidence of cation exchange predominance. The high correlation coefficient between TDS and $(\text{NO}_3^- + \text{Cl}^-)/\text{HCO}_3^-$ also shows the effect of human activities on water chemistry-agricultural fertilizers. Based on the chloralkali index, 21% of the areas had a negative value, indicating the exchange between sodium and potassium in water, chlorine, and magnesium in the soil. The plot of $\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+}$ versus Na^+ was used to identify the ion exchange process indicating the occurrence of ion reverse exchange in about 90% of the study area. The same was observed in 79% of the districts according to the chloralkali index. The Gibbs diagram demonstrated the rock dominance domain towards the evaporation dominance domain, which reflects that rock-water interaction and evaporation occurring in the groundwater system. Assessment of water samples according to WHO standards indicated that, except a few places, the concentrations of major ions in groundwater were within the permissible limits for drinking. The suitability of groundwater for irrigation use was assessed by SAR, RSC, Na%, MH, and PI. The results ranged from good to permissible and indicated that most of the samples were suitable for this purpose. Based on EC, due to high to very high salinity hazards, the groundwater in nearly 40% of the study area was beyond the maximum allowable limit for irrigation, even though it had a low alkalinity hazard. Therefore, the groundwater in a few places can be used for plants that have a good salt tolerance, but it also restricts its suitability for irrigation, especially in soils with restricted drainage. The spatial distribution of different parameters either related to drinking or irrigation purposes was presented to grant

a better insight into the general condition of groundwater quality in Fars.

The results of this study demonstrate the basic requirements for Fars's groundwater quality adaptation process, considering the water requirements for different allocation purposes. Based on the groundwater hydrogeochemical characteristics, policymakers and stakeholders in Fars Province should consider monitoring and controlling anthropogenic activities and implementing proper waste management practices that are essential for the protection of groundwater resources. Regular and systematic monitoring of groundwater quality is essential for understanding the hydrogeochemical characteristics of the aquifers and identifying potential sources of contamination. Policymakers and stakeholders should develop and implement groundwater monitoring programs that use appropriate sampling and analytical methods to assess groundwater quality parameters and track changes over time. Promoting sustainable groundwater use is of great importance because groundwater resources in Fars are under stress due to the increasing demand and over-extraction. Policymakers and stakeholders should promote sustainable groundwater use practices that balance water demand with the natural recharge rates of the aquifers including regulating groundwater pumping, promoting water conservation measures, and promoting the use of alternative water sources such as recycled wastewater. Implementing proper waste management practices is another step that should be taken including the treatment and disposal of hazardous waste and wastewater, to prevent the contamination of groundwater resources.

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Heart Sound Classification using the Nonlinear Dynamic Feature Approach along with Conventional Classifiers

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ABSTRACT

Heart sounds show chaotic and complex behavior when murmurs are present, containing nonlinear and non-Gaussian information. This paper studies ways to extract features from nonlinear dynamic models. The features frequently used to describe the underlying dynamics of the heart are derived from nonlinear dynamical modeling of heart sound signals. This study incorporates nonlinear dynamic features alongside conventional classifiers in the analysis of phonocardiograms (PCGs), achieving a significant improvement in the classification performance with 0.90 sensitivity and 0.92 specificity.

Keywords-heart sound; phonocardiogram; cardiovascular diseases; non-linear; classification; features

I. INTRODUCTION

World Health Organization (WHO) has reported that cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) and related conditions have caused 17.7 million deaths worldwide in 2015, representing 31% of all mortality worldwide [1]. Several techniques can diagnose heart disease patients. Many sophisticated treatments are available but they are very expensive and cumbersome, so often they are not available to the majority of people. Another CVD diagnostic method is heart sound auscultation. A stethoscope is usually used to examine patients, and if an abnormality is detected, the patient may be referred to a cardiologist. An early diagnosis of abnormal heart sounds allows physicians to take corrective measures to prevent cardiovascular disruptions and treat the underlying cause. The phonocardiogram (PCG) represents the sound heart graphically. The PCG signal enables the diagnosis of heart diseases and the evaluation of the cardiovascular system's performance [2, 3]. Each PCG contains multiple cardiac cycles, each with 4 heart sound states: S1, systole, S2, and diastole. These sounds are caused by the closing of the valves at each heart period, with the mitral and tricuspid valves closing before systole, and the aortic and pulmonic valves closing before diastole. Despite their importance, heart sounds are often

difficult to interpret due to their low intensity and dominant frequencies near the lower limits of human hearing. Therefore, auscultation requires a lot of training and experience to detect abnormalities early [3]. The PCG diagnosis can be improved by the use of computers and the development of automated diagnostic tools or computer-assisted auscultation tools for physicians. Automated algorithms have been developed over the past decade to assess patients based solely on PCG measurements without synchronization between the PCG and the electrocardiogram (ECG). This approach has some difficulties due to the variations in the heart rate of the same patient. There is a possibility that a PCG will fluctuate on an individual patient. Moreover, the model is limited to different types of patients.

There are many approaches used in heart sounds, e.g. the unorthodox approach [2, 5], the convolutional approach [4, 6-10], the nonlinear feature approach [6], wavelet fractal [11], and phase space reconstruction [12-14]. Other methods used in heart sounds are Deep Learning (DL) [15, 16], SVM [11, 17-19], Neural Networks (NNs) [2, 4, 7, 19-22], and Hidden-Markov Models (HMMs) [23]. When murmurs are present, heart sounds exhibit chaotic and complex behavior, so they contain nonlinear and non-Gaussian information. Nonlinear

dynamic techniques allow projecting a signal's dynamic behavior.

In this work, we study ways to extract features from nonlinear dynamic models. The features that have been suggested are based on the nonlinear dynamical modeling of the heart sound signals, which are frequently utilized to describe the underlying dynamics of the heart.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this study, we propose a nonlinear dynamic feature method of the heart sound signals as input for a computer-assisted auscultation system, as shown in Figure 1.

A. Preprocessing

To improve the cardiac sound signal, minimizing background noise and eliminating spike noise is critical. A two-stage preprocessing system is used, with a third-order Butterworth bandpass filter with corner frequencies of 15 and 800 Hz in the first stage. This allows for the selection of the valuable bandwidth of the heart sound. The spectral subtraction denoising method was used in the second stage [24]. This method's adaptive noise estimation is an advantage in rebuilding the denoised signal. To obtain accurate measurements of heart sounds, the noise power of frequencies outside the range of heart sounds is measured first. A weighted version of this measured noise power is then subtracted from the power spectrum of the unprocessed heart sounds. This process ensures that the resulting measurements are precise and reliable [24]. Spectral subtraction filtration with a weighting factor of 0.5 was applied in this study.

B. Cardiac Cycle Segmentation

Each PCG signal is divided into cardiac cycles at this stage. Recognizing the systolic or diastolic states is essential for classifying abnormal states in these areas. Different algorithms were used. Some work was performed using a reference signal, like the ECG, which the segmentation algorithms demand to be recorded simultaneously, making simpler to hear heartbeats. In other methods, the ECG is not utilized as a reference. This work divided the PCG signal into cardiac cycles using Springer's improved version of Schmidt's segmentation algorithm [22]. Then, the processing was carried out using each complete cardiac cycle. This method utilizes information about the estimated heart sound state lengths and employs a logistic regression Hidden Semi-Markov Model (HSMM) to estimate the most likely sequence of states without the need for ECG synchronization. In order to solve the issue of the varying time length of cardiac cycles (and thus the sizes of their digital signals) in later processing stages the size of all signals was set to be the most extended cardiac cycle observed across all PCG recordings (here, it was around 2s). The shorter cardiac cycles were zero-padded to the length. This ensures that all signals contain the same frequency resolution.

C. Feature Extraction

In this stage, features were extracted from the segmented cardiac cycles for optimum classification accuracy. When murmurs are present, heart sounds exhibit chaotic and complex behavior. Projecting a signal's dynamic behavior and dealing with its nonlinearity and non-Gaussianity using nonlinear

dynamic techniques is feasible. So, in this work, we study the extraction of nonlinear dynamical modeling features. The proposed features are based on nonlinear dynamic modeling of cardiac sound signals, which are commonly used to describe the underlying dynamics of the heart. A multidimensional phase space or attractor representing the system dynamics and its states could be developed from the measured signals or time series [21]. Thus the system's actual attractor, at which the measurements were obtained, has the same dynamical characteristics as the Reconstructed Phase Space (RPS) [24]. The calculated features for the RPS of the heart sound signals are moment-invariant, distance series-based, and statistical-based features. In the nonlinear dynamical modeling analysis of the heart sound signal, the first step is reconstructing the phase space from the heart sound measurements. The time-delay embedding method proposed in [21, 24] was used for the phase space reconstruction. Time-delay embedding is a technique used to reconstruct m -dimensional vectors from a time series of observations. This is achieved by selecting m values of the time series at different τ lags and repeating the process until the vectors of the phase space are obtained. Therefore, the time delay embedding has two parameters: the embedding dimension m and the time lag τ .

Let $\{x_k: k = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$ be the observed time series, the reconstructed m -dimensional phase space $Y(m)$ can be constructed as the following matrix (1):

$$Y_l(m) = \begin{bmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ \dots \\ Y_K \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_{1+\tau} & \dots & x_{1+(m-1)\tau} \\ x_2 & x_{2+\tau} & \dots & x_{2+(m-1)\tau} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_K & x_{N-m\tau} & \dots & x_{N+(m-1)\tau} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $K = N - (m - 1)\tau$, N is the length of the original time series, m is the embedding dimension, and τ is the delay time. We use an embedding dimension m of 18 and a time delay of 10.

After the reconstruction of the phase space, different features were extracted. We calculated the following statistical features for each reconstructed phase space vector: mean value, median value, standard deviation, mean absolute deviation, 25th and 75th percentiles, signal inter quartile range feature, skewness, and kurtosis. In addition, the same 9 statistical features are extracted from a new domain called the Distance Series (DS) domain. It is defined by [25] as the reduction of the multidimensional phase space into a one-dimensional space. The DS is a method used to characterize complex variations in RPS. It is calculated by taking the Euclidian distance between every point in the phase space and the origin, resulting in a one-dimensional representation of the trajectory. The DS D_i can be calculated by determining the Euclidian distance between each point in the phase space Y_i and the origin:

$$D_i = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m Y_{ij}^2} \quad i = 1.2. \dots \dots k \quad (2)$$

for $i = 1, 2, 3 \dots k$. If successive values of D_i show smooth behavior, a slow trajectory and small region of support in the phase space are indicated by minimal changes in the values. Conversely, significant changes in values suggest a moving trajectory with large steps and significant support in the phase space. This mapping allows capturing more information about

the trajectory than the traditional and more complex measures. Moreover, moment invariant features are calculated for the RPS of the heart sound signals. Moments are quantitative

measures used in statistics to describe the distribution of a random variable quantitatively.

Fig. 1. Nonlinear dynamic feature extraction.

In addition, skewness, which describes the asymmetry of the distribution, is represented by the third moment, and kurtosis, which describes the peaked ness of the probability distribution of the random variable, is described by the fourth moment. The entire set of moments from order zero to infinity describes the distribution uniquely. The term invariant denotes that the moments should remain unaffected to translation, rotation, and scaling transforms to describe the shape of the attractor optimally. The steps of calculating the invariant moments were described in [25], where the second-order moments M were calculated by:

$$M_{p_1 \dots p_m} = \sum_{i=1}^M \dots \sum_{i=1}^M S_{i1}^{p_1} \dots S_{im}^{p_m} \rho(S) dS_1 \dots dS_m \quad (3)$$

where $\rho(S)$ is the probability density function, S_i is a column in the RPS, and p is the order of the moments given by:

$$p = \sum_{j=1}^m p_j \quad (4)$$

We obtained the central moments by applying (5) to the second-order moments. From these central moments, we constructed the O matrix using (6). The major minors for the O matrix were calculated to represent the moment invariant features of the RPS, given that the number of the moment invariant features is equal to the number of the embedding dimension m of the RPS .

$$\mu_{p_1 \dots p_m} = \sum_{i=1}^M \dots \sum_{i=1}^M (S_{i1} - \bar{S}_{i1})^{p_1} \dots (S_{im} - \bar{S}_{im})^{p_m} \rho(S) dS_1 \dots dS_m \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{S}_1 = \frac{M_{1 \dots 0}}{M_{0 \dots 0}} \dots \bar{S}_m = \frac{M_{0 \dots 1}}{M_{0 \dots 0}}$

$$O = \begin{bmatrix} \mu_{2 \dots 0} & \dots & \mu_{1 \dots 1} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \mu_{1 \dots 1} & \dots & \mu_{0 \dots 2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The total number of extracted features is 207.

D. Classification

There are various classifiers available and each one comes with its own set of advantages and disadvantages. One such classifier is k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), which is a memory-based learning algorithm [19]. However, it is important to note that KNN requires the availability of training and testing data at all times. Additionally, for noisy datasets, decision tree classifiers are recommended [26]. However, boosted ensemble classifiers perform best with imbalanced data [19, 26, 30]. This study used a cross-validation approach to evaluate the performance of various conventional classifiers on a set of nonlinear dynamics features and then determine the most effective classification model. The classification methods used in this study include SVMs with quadratic, cubic, and Gaussian kernels, KNN with linear, cosine, cubic, and weighted distance metrics, and ensemble classification methods such as bagged Trees, subspace KNN, RUSBoosted tree, and boosted tree [27-28]. The classifiers were tested and trained using the local holdout and cross-validation methods. The feature vector data for the cross-validation test were divided into five folds. The model was trained for each fold using all the data outside the fold, and each fold was held out for testing in turn. The performance of each model was then evaluated using the information included in the fold, and the overall results were computed as the average over all folds. The local holdout technique studies utilized 80% of the feature vector data as the training set and the remaining 20% as the testing set, both of which were randomly chosen.

E. Dataset Description

Selecting the right dataset is crucial for successful model building and generalization in pattern recognition. A large, diverse and easy-to-understand dataset is necessary to effectively analyze and compare different algorithms. The PhysioNet/Computing in Cardiology Challenge 2016 dataset was used to test the performance of the proposed system [16]. A total of 3153 recordings are included in the dataset. Only the

sure-labeled data in this collection were used to a total of 2868 recordings obtained from 6 datasets. There are 2249 normal patient records and 619 abnormal patient records, ranging from 5s to more than 120s. Each track has been down-sampled to 2,000Hz and is available in wav format. Recordings with varying noise levels were included from several actual clinical and nonclinical settings. Data from normal persons and patients, from either children or adults were collected. One to 6 recordings of the same subject may exist in the dataset. Data were gathered from various body parts and locations (including aortic, pulmonic, tricuspid, and mitral areas). The fact that there are far more normal than abnormal recordings clearly shows that the data are unbalanced. Eighty percent of the dataset was used for training, while 20% was used for testing. The heterogeneity of the recordings introduces differences that could make classifier training more challenging.

F. Performance Evaluation

The confusion matrix is produced with the abnormal cases as the positive class in order to evaluate the success of the classification process, and it is then used to determine the values for sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy:

$$\text{Sensitivity}(Se) = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Specificity}(Sp) = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (9)$$

where TP, TN, FP, and FN are the confusion matrix entries representing True Positive, True Negative, False Positive and False Negative classifications, respectively.

Error rate and accuracy are insufficient for measuring classification performance for imbalanced data since they do not consider the costs of misclassification. They are hence sensitive to class skews and frequently show a considerable bias toward the dominant class [22, 29]. As a result, the official evaluation metric for the 2016 PhysioNet/Computing in Cardiology Challenge was an alternative evaluation score based on the average between sensitivity and specificity:

$$\text{Score} = \frac{Se + Sp}{2} \quad (10)$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Experimental Verification

Each PCG record was preprocessed using a Butterworth band-pass filter of order 3 with corner frequencies of 15 and 800Hz. Each record was further enhanced using spectral subtraction denoising with 0.5 weight. There were 79492 cardiac cycles after segmenting each record into cardiac cycles. The most extended cardiac cycle observed in all PCG recordings is about 2s long. Each time series was therefore zero-padded to a cardiac cycle's length of 2s if it was less. For nonlinear dynamic feature extraction, the first step is the reconstruction of the phase space from the heart sound measurements with embedding dimension $m=18$ and a time delay of 10. A total of 207 features were considered for each cardiac cycle. All feature vector values were normalized to the interval [0, 1] in order to optimize the classification process. The performances of several conventional classifiers, including SVM and KNN, and bagged Trees, subspace KNN, and RUSBoosted tree ensemble classifiers, were compared.

B. Results

The classification results with the 5-fold cross-validation train-test approach are listed in Table I. When using unbalanced data, the cross-validation train test approach is effective in reducing over-fitting and improving model evaluation. It should be noted that in our experiments only the ensemble classifiers were able to achieve relatively balanced sensitivity and specificity values. The RUSBoosted Tree ensemble classifier had the highest score value of sensitivity and specificity of 0.90 and 0.91. On the other hand, the SVM classifier with a Gaussian kernel had the lowest sensitivity of 0.64. The Bagged tree ensemble classifier and the KNN classifier with weighted distance metric both achieved the most remarkable specificity of 0.95, while the majority of commonly used classifiers achieved lower specificity of 0.91. The classification results utilizing the local holdout train-test approach are listed in Table II. Only the ensemble classifiers succeeded in achieving relatively balanced sensitivity and specificity values in our experiments. The RUSBoosted Tree ensemble classifier scored 0.91, which was the highest, with balanced sensitivity and specificity of 0.90 and 0.92. Conversely, the SVM classifier with a Gaussian kernel showed the lowest sensitivity, at 0.65, while the SVM classifier with a Gaussian kernel achieved the lowest specificity of 0.79, the Bagged tree ensemble classifier and the KNN classifier with weighted distance metric both achieved the highest specificity of 0.95.

TABLE I. NONLINEAR DYNAMIC FEATURE CLASSIFICATION RESULTS USING THE 5-FOLD CROSS-VALIDATION TRAIN-TEST METHOD

Classifier	Classifier	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC	Score
SVM	Quadratic	0.8470	0.6700	0.9100	0.8900	0.7900
	Cubic	0.8680	0.7300	0.9100	0.9100	0.8200
	Gaussian	0.8620	0.6400	0.9400	0.9000	0.7900
Ensemble	Bagged Trees	0.9190	0.8400	0.9500	0.9700	0.8950
	RUSBoosted Tree	0.9090	0.9000	0.9100	0.9700	0.9050
	Boosted Tree	0.9020	0.8000	0.9300	0.9600	0.8650
KNN	Linear	0.8700	0.7000	0.9200	0.9100	0.8100
	Cosine	0.8530	0.6700	0.9100	0.9100	0.7900
	Cubic	0.8630	0.6500	0.9300	0.9100	0.7900
	Weighted	0.8780	0.6600	0.9500	0.9300	0.8050

TABLE II. NONLINEAR DYNAMIC FEATURE CLASSIFICATION RESULTS

Classifier	Classifier	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC	Score
SVM	Quadratic	0.8570	0.6700	0.9100	0.9000	0.7900
	Cubic	0.7990	0.8400	0.7900	0.8800	0.8150
	Gaussian	0.8720	0.6500	0.9400	0.9000	0.7950
Ensemble	Bagged Trees	0.9230	0.8500	0.9500	0.9700	0.9000
	RUSBoosted Tree	0.9110	0.9000	0.9200	0.9700	0.9100
	Boosted Tree	0.9060	0.8000	0.9400	0.9600	0.8700
KNN	Linear	0.8830	0.7300	0.9300	0.8900	0.8300
	Cosine	0.8610	0.7000	0.9100	0.9100	0.8050
	Cubic	0.8640	0.6500	0.9300	0.9200	0.7900
	Weighted	0.8790	0.6600	0.9500	0.9400	0.8050

Training = 80% - Testing = 20%

IV. DISCUSSION

This research demonstrates that nonlinear dynamic features have an application to phonocardiogram analysis. Heart sounds exhibit chaotic and complex behavior when murmurs are present, hence they contain nonlinear and non-Gaussian information. Nonlinear dynamic approaches can deal with a signal's nonlinearity and non-Gaussianity and project its dynamic behavior. The features that have been proposed are based on the nonlinear dynamical modeling of the heart sound signals, which are frequently used to characterize the underlying dynamics of the heart. Applying nonlinear dynamic approaches is also helpful for determining whether murmurs are present.

In this paper, the RUSBoosted Tree ensemble classifier scored the highest with a sensitivity value of 0.90 and specificity value of 0.92, resulting in an overall score of 0.91. As a result, it offered the most accurate prediction of the predictive score using both approaches, as well as relatively balanced values for sensitivity and specificity. The classifier performance evaluations in the two train-test approaches were largely comparable. The ability of the proposed system to handle various P phonocardiogram CG recordings and signal quality settings was demonstrated by the significant improvements in the classification performance obtained utilizing nonlinear dynamic features along with the conventional classifiers.

Observing the effect of the training data's class distribution is essential, as this is a significant factor in determining the accuracy of subsequent classification. Although there seem to be many samples in the challenge database, these samples are, unfortunately, highly unbalanced, with vastly different proportions of normal and abnormal recordings. Due to this, traditional classifiers frequently develop biases in favor of the majority class, increasing the misclassification rate for the minority class. As a result, two validation approaches were used to assess the performance of various classifiers on the dataset. The cross-validation train-test method is the first. It reduces the influence of over-fitting caused on by noisy records. The second approach, known as the local holdout method, simulates real-world analysis by using just 80% of the data to develop the model and the remaining 20% to assess it. Noting that the dataset is significantly imbalanced, it is observed in the proposed system that only the ensemble classifiers performed very well. This confirms that ensemble

classifiers are always recommended for imbalanced data in general [19, 26].

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new classification approach was proposed for heart sounds, in which the new proposed features were based on nonlinear dynamics. The proposed methodology and its implementation were described in detail. The results of the experimental verification show a potential to overcome challenges encountered during heart sound classification under different settings. Consequently, the proposed method provided well balanced values for sensitivity and specificity as well as the best accurate prediction of the predictive score using both methodologies.

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Spectrum Sharing of HAPS and Fixed Link in Millimeter Waves

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ABSTRACT

A High Altitude Platform System (HAPS) is an emerging technology that can potentially bring connectivity to areas that are not partially or totally covered by cellular networks. However, allocating certain frequency bands for the HAPS alongside wireless Fixed Service (FS) imposes some restrictions on operating the HAPS systems to ensure no interference occurs between the two systems (HAPS and FS). This paper presents an analytical study of the spectrum sharing between the HAPS and the FS in millimeter waves, namely in 38- and 47-GHz bands. Some potential and significant interference scenarios have been applied in order to investigate the spectrum-sharing situations in urban and suburban areas. The Carrier to Interference plus Noise Ratio (CINR) has been adopted as the main criterion to assess the performance of the HAPS. It is found that the HAPS and FS systems can simultaneously share the 38- and 47-GHz bands with some restrictions to HAPS altitude, allowable CINR, and location of the HAPS user. These restrictions differ depending on the area coverage type.

Keywords-interference; CINR; HAPS; urban; suburban; signal power; FS

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the High Altitude Platform System (HAPS) has attracted much attention, as an emerging technology, due to its integration with 5G services, Internet of Things (IoT) support, temporary coverage for events and tourist hotspots, emergency communications, terrestrial site backhaul, and disaster recovery infrastructure without any ground-based network [1, 2]. Unlike satellites, HAPSs are aircrafts that fly or float in the stratosphere, typically at altitudes of around 17-22km. HAPS systems could be high-altitude free-floating balloons, dirigibles, or powered fixed-wing aircrafts that employ either solar power or an onboard energy source. All HAPS systems can be manned or unmanned aeronautical platforms however in the stratosphere they are unmanned. A HAPS runs in a harsh medium in which solar radiation is high and temperatures may reach very low levels, while the system is prepared to be airborne for long time periods [3]. There are two categories of HAPSs authorized to operate depending on the type of service they provide, i.e. fixed or mobile services. In the case of systems that are intentionally designed to add coverage to fixed locations on the ground, the platform must have its own power in order to remain "on station" at a specific location [4].

International Telecommunication Union (ITU) radio regulations determined new frequency bands (according to Wireless Radio Conferences (WRC)) to be used for the operation of the two categories of HAPS. The spectrum frequency bands that have been allocated to fixed HAPS services include 38GHz (approved in WRC-97) and 47GHz (approved in WRC-19) which are globally allocated to HAPS,

[5, 6]. In addition, these two bands are also allocated to wireless Fixed-link Service (FS). Such a situation of spectrum sharing creates a potential for intersystem interference between the HAPS and FS which can lead to the deterioration of the performance of both systems [7, 8]. Thus, this study investigates the spectrum sharing feasibility between the HAPS and the FS using the Carrier to Interference plus Noise Ratio (CINR) as a standard criterion to ensure that both systems can safely share the allocated spectrum.

In general, the role of spectrum sharing studies is to investigate the ability of various wireless systems co-existing in a geographical area to share a certain frequency band with no harmful interference. Interference power created from a wireless system to another can be categorized as either co-channel interference or adjacent channel interference [8]. Essentially, adjacent channel interference can be mitigated using a suitable filter, however, co-channel interference is the most dangerous one, and is the topic of this paper. It can be mitigated by increasing the distance between the interferer and the interfered systems. This procedure is done because it leads to increase the interference power attenuation and then reduce its impact on the other system. In this regard, several studies addressed spectrum sharing between HAPS and other wireless systems in different frequency bands [9-13]. In [9, 10], the authors investigate the spectrum sharing between HAPS and fixed satellite service stations at 5850–7075MHz. They determined the interference coupling loss between the systems [9] and statistically modeled the HAPS gateway link and fixed satellite service interoperability at 5850–7075MHz [10]. In [11], the downlink performance of WiMAX from HAPS and

terrestrial base stations at 3.5GHz was simulated. The coexistence of HAPS and terrestrial systems using Gigabit links to serve dedicated users was considered in [12] at 28GHz. In [13], spectrum sharing of HAPS and Fixed Satellite Service (FSS) in the frequency range of 5850–7075MHz was investigated.

The contribution of this paper is the exploration of the spectrum sharing status between the HAPS and the FS in millimeter waves by assuming intersystem interference scenarios between the two systems within urban and suburban areas and with various HAPS altitudes and different terrestrial distances to connect the FS link. These interference scenarios have not been studied in the literature at millimeter waves [14, 15], namely 38 and 47GHz. Consequently, some recommendations that ease spectrum sharing are proposed.

II. SPECTRUM SHARING SCENARIOS

Spectrum sharing studies assume intersystem interference scenarios between systems that use the same frequency band and operate in the same geographical area. The general intersystem interference situation considered in this paper is illustrated in Figure 1. The HAPS service is proposed to share the same frequency band (38 or 47GHz) with the FS system. The HAPS coverage area in Figure 1 is assumed to be either urban or suburban. The HAPS platforms are manufactured to suit the stratospheric conditions [16] and are situated at an altitude of 17-22km. The reason behind this high altitude selection is that the wind speed at this height is quite low and suitable for the operation of HAPS [17]. The HAPS user receives a desired signal from the HAPS station while at the same time it receives undesired signal (interference) from the FS link. The HAPS user can move along the terrestrial path between the FS transmitter (Tx) and FS receiver (Rx), which is 100km, to examine the interference impact on the HAPS user. In addition, the HAPS station altitude changes between 17 and 22km to investigate the effect of different height on the spectrum sharing situations in each case.

Fig. 1. The general HAPS- FS interference scenario.

The signal propagation from the HAPS station to its ground users was implemented in this paper by the Line-of-Sight (LoS) model for all selected locations in the coverage area of HAPS which has a radius of 50km. On the other hand, the terrestrial propagation environment of the FS link is characterized by two propagation models which are the free space path loss model

and the clutter loss propagation model. The latter is explained below. To make sure that both systems can operate concurrently with no interference, CINR was adopted to assess the performance of the HAPS user.

III. INTERFERENCE CALCULATION METHOD

In spectrum sharing, the distance/physical path separation plays a significant role in determining the possibility of sharing the same frequency band (co-channel spectrum sharing). The separation distance defines the optimum distance that can provide the required protection criteria level. Therefore, it plays a major factor in determining the amount of interference to the victim receiver (user), where the increase in distance between the FS transmitter and the user leads to attenuation of the interfering power and vice versa.

A. Downlink Received Power

The downlink received power, P_r , or the desired signal (dBW) that arrives to the HAPS user from the HAPS system in the sky can be expressed as the carrier C [18]:

$$P_r = C = EIRP_{t,HAPS} + G_{r,HAPS} - L_{fp} \quad (1)$$

where $EIRP_{t,HAPS}$ is the effective isotropic radiated power (dBW) of the HAPS station in the sky (the transmitter), $G_{r,HAPS}$ is the HAPS user antenna gain (dBi) in the ground (the receiver), and L_{fp} is the path loss in the free space (dB). To estimate the service area of the HAPS transmitter, we calculate the $EIRP_{t,HAPS}$ as follows:

$$EIRP_{t,HAPS} = P_{t,HAPS} + G_{t,HAPS} \quad (2)$$

where $P_{t,HAPS}$ is the HAPS transmitter power (dBW), and $G_{t,HAPS}$ is the HAPS transmitter antenna gain (dBi).

The loss due to the free space propagation between the HAPS transmitter and the user can be expressed as:

$$L_{fp}(dB) = 32.45 + 20 \log_{10} f + 20 \log_{10} D \quad (3)$$

where f is the operating frequency (MHz), and D is the distance (km) between the sky HAPS station and the land station of the HAPS antenna (the HAPS user).

B. Interference Power

The interference due to the FS link into the HAPS system (the land user) is expressed as:

$$I = EIRP_{t,FS} + G_{r,FS} - L_{fp} - B_h \quad (4)$$

where $EIRP_{t,FS}$ is the effective isotropic radiated power (dBW) of the FS transmitter (Tx), $G_{r,FS}$ is the HAPS user antenna gain (dBi), L_{fp} is the path loss due to free space propagation (dB), and B_h is an additional loss due to protection from local clutter (dB). The additional loss is given by [19]:

$$B_h = 10.25 e^{-d_k} \left(1 - \tanh \left[6 \left(\frac{h}{h_a} \right) - 0.625 \right] \right) \quad (5)$$

where d_k is the distance from the nominal clutter point to the received antenna (km), h is the received antenna height (m), and h_a is the nominal clutter height (m). These values are tabulated in Table I for both urban and suburban areas.

TABLE I. NOMINAL CLUTTER HEIGHTS AND DISTANCES

Clutter (ground-cover) category	Nominal height h_a (m)	Nominal distance d_k (km)
Suburban	9	0.025
Urban	20	0.02

C. Spectrum Sharing Feasibility Criterion

In order to examine whether the two systems under consideration can share the same frequency band, the CINR (dB) is taken into account. It is expressed as:

$$CINR = C - (I + N) \quad (6)$$

where C is the received power (dBW), I is the interference power (dBW), and N is the noise received power (dBW). It is worth mentioning that the summation of $I+N$ is done linearly first and then it is converted into decibel. The noise of the receiver, N , (dBW), can be expressed as [18]:

$$N = K + T - B_{W,HAPS} - F_n \quad (7)$$

where K is the Boltzmann's constant, T is the system noise temperature (dBk), $B_{W,HAPS}$ is the HAPS receiver bandwidth (dBHz), and F_n is the receiver noise figure, in dB.

IV. SYSTEM SPECIFICATIONS

The main parameters for the HAPS and FS systems are shown in Tables II and III for both the frequency bands considered [18, 20-22]. In Table II, the parameters are mentioned for Urban Area Coverage (UAC) and Suburban Area Coverage (SAC) [23] which are categorized by clutter height as shown in Table I [15, 20]. Table III [21, 22] shows the FS system parameters.

TABLE II. DOWNLINK PATH FROM HAPS TO THE USER

Parameters	Value		
	UAC	SAC	UAC & SAC
Frequency (GHz)	47.0	47.0	38-39.5
Channel bandwidth (MHz)	11.0	11.0	11
Tx power (dBW)	1.3	1.3	-
Antenna gain (dBi)	27.0	27.0	37
Hybrid/waveguide loss (dB)	0.5	0.5	-
EIRP (dBW)	27.8	27.8	22
Atmospheric loss (dB)	2.3	5.2	-
Received antenna gain (dBi)	23	38	49.8
Receiver antenna height (m)	1	1	1
Polarization loss (dB)	0.5	0.5	-

TABLE III. FIXED SERVICE PARAMETERS (TO HAPS USER)

Parameters	Value	
Frequency (GHz)	47.0	38
Maximum antenna gain (dBi)	46	47
Maximum transmitter power (dBW)	-11	-15
Maximum EIRP (dB(W/MHz))	28	32
Receiver bandwidth (MHz)	2	3.5
Receiver noise figure (dB)	11	7.5
Interference criteria (dB(W/MHz))	-143	-143
HAPS user height (m)	4	4

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings from this study depend on several factors such as HAPS altitude, frequency band, type of area coverage, FS

antenna height, etc. For instance, HAPS stations with different altitudes will provide different path losses affecting the spectrum sharing feasibility. Similarly, each area, either UAC or SAC, has different clutter characteristics that can introduce a certain loss to the interfering signal as shown in Table I [18]. Moreover, the height of the FS antenna may be varied to examine the impact of interferer power on the HAPS user (the receiver). In this section, the physical separation distances between the HAPS transmitter and the HAPS receiver are considered. Various situations of the HAPS carrier signal and CINR at the HAPS user were simulated over different HAPS altitude levels, from 17 to 22km for all selected locations in the coverage area of HAPS which has a radius of 50km.

A. Spectrum Sharing in Urban Areas

An urban area refers to a town, city, or suburb. These areas are highly developed and have a high density of infrastructure, including houses, commercial buildings, roads, bridges, and railways. The received power in urban area scenarios for 38 and 47GHz frequency bands was simulated. In Figure 2, the received powers for 38GHz at the HAPS user are calculated for various HAPS transmitter altitudes. The values of the received power depend on the height of the HAPS transmitter and the location of its user. For instance, when the HAPS user is at the center of HAPS coverage (0km) and the HAPS station altitude is 17km, the power received is maximum and is -76.9dBW, while the received power is minimum (-79dBW) at the height of 22km. On the other hand, when the HAPS user is at the edge of the HAPS coverage area (50km), the maximum received power is -86.7dBW (at 17km) and the minimum received power is -87dBW (at 22km). These results and their curve shape agree with the results of Figure 4 in [24].

Figure 3 shows the CINR levels at the HAPS user for the 38GHz-urban area scenario, where the carrier represents the power received (that transmits voice, video, data, or a combination of the three) from the HAPS in the sky to the user on the ground (downlink). For a CINR of 19dB for the HAPS user which is required to prevent interference is 50.4, 52.6, 55.6, 58.6, 61.6, and 64.7km for HAPS transmitter heights of 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, and 22km, respectively.

Fig. 2. The received power at the HAPS user for urban area using 38GHz.

Fig. 3. The CINR at the HAPS user for urban area using 38GHz.

Figure 4 displays the received powers in the urban area for an operating frequency of 47GHz. The received power directly under the sky HAPS station ranges between -102.4 and -104.8dBW, while it is -112.3 to -102.7dBW at the coverage edge of the HAPS system. When using the frequency of 47GHz, the power received is lower than that in the case of 38GHz because the higher frequency of 47GHz severs higher attenuation, leading to increased power loss of the 47GHz system. Moreover, it can be noticed in Figure 5 that the HAPS system only can work using 47GHz, if it is elevated up to a height of 17km above the earth surface because the CINR at the HAPS user is approximately 19dB, whereas, if the HAPS is raised to altitudes more than 17km, the received power at the HAPS user from the HAPS transmitter will be weak and the fixed service will cause interference enough to disturb the HAPS user receiving mode where the CINR is always less than 19dB. As mentioned above, the HAPS user can work only for a minimum CINR of 19dB (the HAPS interference protection criteria), but this is not the case (as shown in Figure 5) for altitude levels greater than 17km where the two systems cannot run concurrently because the required interference protection criteria is not realized.

Fig. 4. The received power at the HAPS user for urban area using 47GHz.

Fig. 5. The CINR at the HAPS user for urban area using 47GHz.

B. Spectrum Sharing in Suburban Areas

Suburban areas are mixed-use or residential areas. These areas are often a large and active community of employed people. In some metropolitan areas, they are residential subdivisions within commuting distance of the city. In Figure 6, the received power levels are similar to that in Figure 2 related to the urban area due to the fact that the carrier received in the suburban area is affected by the same factors considered in the urban area. This means that the received power from HAPS station is the same even if the terrain is different because the connection between the HAPS transmitter and receiver is only under LoS condition for both cases. Thus, when the HAPS user is at the center of the HAPS coverage (0km: the HAPS user is directly under the HAPS sky station), the maximum power received is -76.9dBW for an altitude of 17km and the minimum is -79dBW for 22km. When the HAPS user is at the edge of the coverage area (50km), the maximum received power is -86.7dBW for a height of 17km and the minimum is about -87dBW for a height of 22km. In Figure 7, the values of the CINR in the suburban area are smaller than the values shown in Figure 3 for frequency sharing in urban areas when using 38GHz. This difference in the CINR is a result of the effect of the clutter loss that is high in urban areas. Urban areas include high-rise buildings and many obstacles which all play a significant part in blocking the interference signals, which in turn leads to an increase in the values of CINR at the HAPS user. For a CINR of 19dB for the HAPS user in Figure 7, the minimum distance from the FS to the HAPS user which is required to prevent interference is 63.6, 66.7, 70.7, 74.8, 78.8, and 81.9km for HAPS transmitter height of 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, and 22km, respectively.

Spectrum sharing was also investigated when the two systems use 47GHz. This scenario is shown in Figures 8 and 9. In Figure 8, the received power at the HAPS user is calculated. It is found that the received power in the suburban areas is higher than that in the urban areas due to the difference in the values of the atmospheric loss. The receiver antenna in the suburban area has a higher gain than that in the urban areas. In addition, the CINR in the suburban areas (see Figure 9) is also higher than that in the urban areas for HAPS altitudes of 17, 18,

and 19km. However, the two systems cannot operate concurrently for HAPS altitudes of 20, 21, and 22km due to the weak signal arrived at the HAPS user which in turn makes the CINR smaller than 19dB. These results are tabulated in Table IV which shows the required distance between the FS and HAPS user for a CINR of 19dB for different HAPS altitudes in urban and suburban areas. It is worth mentioning that more flexible CINR values can reduce the required distance to achieve spectrum sharing between the systems.

Fig. 6. The received power at the HAPS user for suburban area using 38GHz.

Fig. 7. The CINR at the HAPS user for suburban area using 38GHz.

TABLE IV. REQUIRED DISTANCE BETWEEN THE FS AND HAPS USER FOR CINR= 19DB

HAPS altitude (km)	Required distance (km)			
	Urban areas		Suburban areas	
	38 GHz	47 GHz	38 GHz	47 GHz
17	50.38	≈ 100	63.64	90.91
18	52.61	> 100	66.67	95.96
19	55.56	> 100	70.71	≈ 100
20	58.60	> 100	74.75	> 100
21	61.62	> 100	78.79	> 100
22	64.65	> 100	81.82	> 100

Fig. 8. The received power at the HAPS user for suburban area using 47GHz.

Fig. 9. The CINR at the HAPS user for suburban area using 47GHz.

VI. CONCLUSION

Spectrum sharing can be a solution to spectrum scarcity, enabling various wireless systems access the same frequency bands. This paper presents a spectrum sharing study between the HAPS and FS in the frequency bands of 38 and 47GHz. Various spectrum sharing scenarios were investigated in both urban and suburban areas. CINR was used to assess the feasibility of spectrum sharing between the HAPS and FS systems. The findings showed that the CINR values are better for the lowest HAPS altitude of 17km and the lower spectrum frequency band of 38GHz. Spectrum sharing is more feasible in urban than in suburban areas because urban areas are crowded with buildings and obstacles which act as blocking objects against interference. The findings of this paper can help service providers and communication regulators to provide more efficient uses of the frequency spectrum.

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Effect of Coarse Aggregate Gradation on the Strength Properties of Bagasse Ash Concrete

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the coarse aggregate grades and the use of sugarcane bagasse ash as a replacement for cement to examine their effect on concrete strength. Ten concrete mixes were prepared in two groups using a 1:2:4 mix ratio and a 0.48 water-to-binder ratio. Sugarcane bagasse ash was used in 0 and 10% dosages by weight of cement. Five grades of aggregates were used: 4.75-7, 7-10, 10-13, 13-20, and 4.75-20mm. Six 6"/12" concrete cylinders were prepared for each group and cured for 28 days to test their compressive and split tensile strengths. The results showed that bagasse ash caused a reduction in strength properties in both well- and specific-graded concrete. It was also observed that 10-13mm aggregate concrete with and without bagasse ash had more strength than the respective well-graded. Although a minimum decrease in strength was observed, a 10% dosage of sugarcane bagasse ash was optimal to save cement content in both specific and well-graded aggregate concrete. This study provides a new framework for using graded coarse aggregates and replacing cement with bagasse ash.

Keywords-compressive strength; tensile strength; green concrete; sugarcane bagasse; sustainability; waste management

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is the most widely used material in the industry, giving the freedom to construct the desired shapes, orientations, and sizes. However, it requires good care and control in the use of constituent materials to ensure the proper strength of the final product. The recent boom in construction gives beautiful and eye-catching infrastructures but consumes a large quantity of natural and man-made ingredients. The use of aggregates has reached an alarming situation due to the depletion of conventional natural sources. Moreover, the demand for cement causes a serious environmental problem due to the emissions of harmful gases. The boom in construction has also posed a serious problem for demolition and construction waste due to the unavailability of dumping space, particularly in city centers. Construction is not the only industry that produces waste at a serious level, as several other primary industrial processes also generate waste that requires proper dumping. The sugar industry is one such example, as it uses sugar cane for its primary processes and generates bagasse in large quantities. Bagasse is used in the development of secondary products, but residuals remain a serious issue.

The ingredients of the concrete matrix have many advantages and some disadvantages. The search for alternative materials for concrete ingredients to overcome its weaknesses and conserve natural sources or reduce the use of man-made materials is an active research area. Several alternative materials have been proposed to be used in the concrete matrix, such as residual waste from primary industrial processes. Bagasse ash is one of them. Different materials have shown different behaviors for fresh and hardened properties with strength variation. The preparation of concrete requires good care in the use of materials to ensure the proper strength of the final product. Well-graded aggregates are among them, but in many cases, coarse aggregates are not well-graded. Sometimes, aggregate gradation is not performed and there is a chance that such concrete will have poor strength in its hardened state despite good care in batching, mixing, placing, and curing. The current study investigated the effect of coarse aggregate gradation on concrete strength properties using bagasse ash as a partial replacement of cement. This study not only examined the effect of gradation on strength but also used an indigenous waste material as a partial cement replacement, as it could tackle the waste management problem to some extent.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The controlled burning of sugar bagasse produces ash that has cementitious properties and has been used in concrete as a partial replacement for cement in various studies. In [1], the use of bagasse ash in concrete was reviewed, concluding that it has good cementitious properties and can be used in concrete to alter its properties. In [2], bagasse ash was used in various dosages to develop M20 concrete, the test results of 7- and 28-day cured specimens showed a comparable increase in split tensile strength and workability of the 10% dosage specimens, but an additional increase in ash dosage resulted in a decrease in split tensile strength and workability. The same results were also observed in [3]. In [4], bagasse ash was used in various dosages as a replacement for cement to develop M30 concrete,

and the test results of 7- and 28-day cured specimens showed increased compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength for up to 20% dosage of bagasse ash, but further addition of ash resulted in decreased strength and workability of the concrete. On the other hand, in [5], bagasse ash was used to produce M20 concrete, the test specimens were cured for 7, 14, and 28 days, and the results showed that the 25% dosage was optimal for the strength properties while the 15% was optimal for workability. In [6], M20 grade concrete was made with 0-30% sugarcane bagasse ash, and the test results of cubes, cylinders, and prisms cured for 7, 14, and 28 days showed that 25% replacement of cement with ash was optimal with a negligible decrease in strength properties. In [7] and [8], sugarcane ash was used up to 15 and 25%, respectively, to produce M25 concrete, and the test results showed that 5% and 15% were the optimal dosages, respectively.

In [9], bagasse ash was used in 0-25% dosages to produce M25 concrete and the test results of 7- and 28-day cured samples showed that 15% was the optimal, as it reduced only 7, 1, and 6% compressive, tensile, and flexural strength, respectively. In [10], bagasse ash was used as a 20% cement replacement to develop M25 concrete, and the results showed an increase in slump with the increase in the dose of bagasse ash. Maximum residual compressive strength equal to 26.45MPa in comparison to 27.7MPa, and tensile strength equal to 1.89MPa in comparison to 1.94MPa were observed at the 5% dosage, concluding that this was the optimal bagasse ash dosage for cement replacement. Similarly but for M20 concrete, the 5% dosage was observed as the optimum for compressive, tensile, and flexural strength with different residual strength values [11]. In [12], the 6% dosage was found as the optimal level of cement replacement. In [13], a 2% dose was observed to be optimal in terms of strength of the bagasse ash concrete. In [14], bagasse ash was used to produce M20 and M15 concrete, where a 45% and 28% increase in slump was recorded at replacement levels of 5% and 10%, and the increase in compressive strength was recorded as equal to 11.6% and 3.5% at dosages of 5% and 10%, respectively. A similar trend was observed for the strength of M15 concrete, concluding that 5% was the optimal dosage of ash regarding the increase in compressive strength. In [15, 16], M30 and M35 concrete was produced using bagasse ash, respectively, concluding that a 15% dosage had the optimum strength parameters. Bagasse ash was also used in [17-21] to examine dose optimization for the strength properties of concrete. Table I summarizes the results of sugarcane bagasse ash as a cement replacement published in various studies.

The strength of concrete is the key property for proper durability and serviceability during the service life of structures. Well-graded aggregates in concrete matrix ensure proper strength of the final product. However, unfortunately, in many cases, the gradation of the aggregates is omitted, resulting in unevenly graded aggregates that affect the final strength of the hardened concrete. The effect of gradation on concrete strength was studied in [22]. Using well-graded, uniform, and gap-graded aggregates, M20 concrete was tested for slump, compaction factor, and compressive strength. The results showed that the gradation of fine aggregates was more influential than that of coarse aggregates. The compaction

factor test was more sensitive and gave better results for gap-graded aggregates and similar were the results of the compressive strength test. Therefore, this study argued that although well-graded aggregates result in better concrete, the presence of large particles prevents homogeneity when concrete is stressed.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF LITERATURE REVIEW

	Reference	Parameters of study	Concrete	Opt. dosage
1	[2], [3]	Workability, CS, TS	M20	10%
2	[4]	Workability, CS, TS, FS	M30	30%
3	[5], [6]	Workability, CS, TS, FS	M20	25%
4	[7]	CS, TS	M25	5%
5	[8]	CS	M25	15%
6	[9]	CS, TS, FS	M25	15%
7	[10]	CS, TS	M25	5%
	[11]	CS, TS, FS	M20	
8	[12]	CS, TS, FS	M20	6%
9	[13]	Workability, CS	M30	2%
10	[14]	CS	M20, M15	5%
11	[15]	CS, TS, FS	M30	15%
	[16]	CS, TS, Voids	M35	
12	[17]	CS, TS	M20	8%
13	[18]	Workability, FS	M25	10%
14	[19]	Slump, compaction factor, CS	M35	10%
15	[20]	CS	M35	10%
16	[21]	CS, FS	M35	10%

In [23], the effect of uniformly graded aggregates was examined in geopolymer concrete with fly ash and GGBS. A comparison of G40 and M40 showed better performance of 12.5mm size aggregates in thin precast elements than conventional concrete. In [24], the effect of different grading of the aggregates was investigated on conventional concrete by designing 8 different mixes, concluding that the compressive strength of concrete can be improved by more than 50% by altering the grade of aggregates. In [25], the effects of the type and size of aggregates were investigated on the compressive strength of concrete, examining three types, (quartzite, granite, and river gravel) and three sizes (12, 20, and 40mm) along with fly ash and superplasticizer to evaluate density, compressive strength, and tensile strength. The results showed that the 12mm quartzite aggregates had the highest strength. In [26], the effects of aggregates from different sources in Pakistan were studied, using 28-day cured samples of a 1:2:4 mixture, and the results showed a very good increase in compressive strength using a combination of fine aggregates from Lawrencepur and Kashmore in equal proportions than aggregates from one source alone. In [27-28], the effect of gap gradation was studied on the workability and flexural strength of concrete, showing a good increase in both test parameters for mixes with aggregates less than 5mm, but gap-graded concrete required more binder contents than usual to ensure workability and strength. Thus, there was an argument that although careful gap gradation may result in more strength of the final product, well-graded concrete is better for binder content and durability. In [29], a completely different phenomenon was observed regarding binder content, showing that 15% less binder can be used for the same strength with careful gap gradation of aggregates. In [30], the effect of uniformly graded 1:1.5:3 concrete was studied for its workability and strength properties, using aggregates of 9.5,

12.7, and 19.1mm. A three times higher slump value was noticed compared to well-graded aggregates with a decrease in slump values as aggregate size increased. The compressive strength was also recorded as 5%, 16%, and 21% higher than that of well-graded aggregates. Moreover, cement-treated aggregates did not have any positive impact on the strength of rigid pavements. In [31-33], aggregate gradation was attempted to minimize the cost of concrete by reducing the cement content. Furthermore, recycled coarse aggregates from demolished concrete have also been used in concrete to study the effect of fly ash on strength properties [34], water penetration of recycled aggregate concrete [35], compressive strength of no-fines recycled aggregate concrete [32], and flexural strength of no-fines recycled aggregate concrete [36].

The evident scatter of these results indicates that more studies are required to reach a certain level of confidence in the use of the materials. This study performed a laboratory investigation on the combined effect of different gradations of coarse aggregates and sugarcane bagasse ash as cement replacement on the strength properties of concrete.

III. MATERIALS AND TESTING

This study used ordinary Portland cement under the brand name Pakland, and with a value of 2.79. Fine aggregates passing through the 4.75mm sieve were obtained from approved quarries, which had a specific gravity of 2.62. Coarse aggregates were also obtained from the same quarries, having a size between 4.75-20mm and 2.8 specific gravity. The coarse aggregates were washed and dried before being used in the concrete mix. To achieve the proposed target, coarse aggregates were sieved and separated into groups of 4.75-7mm, 7-10mm, 10-13mm, and 13-20mm, to produce four concrete batches. Additionally, one batch of concrete with coarse aggregates between 4.75-20mm (well-graded aggregates) was also prepared. Therefore, five batches of concrete were prepared. Filtered tap water from the city water supply, having a pH of 7.1, was used for washing the aggregates, preparing the concrete mix, and curing.

The sugarcane primarily used in the preparation of sugar contained approximately 26% of bagasse, 50% moisture, and 0.62% residual ash. Figure 1 shows the sugarcane bagasse obtained from a sugar mill in Nawabshah. The sugarcane bagasse was dried in open air for a few days followed by controlled burning at 700°C. The residual bagasse ash contained 50% cellulose, 25% hemicellulose, and 25% lignin. Table II shows the chemical analysis of bagasse ash. It should be noticed that its silica and alumina contents provide good cementitious properties. The ash was then used as a 10% replacement of cement by weight in 5 batches with 10% bagasse ash and another 5 batches without bagasse ash to compare the test results. For all mixes, a 1:2:4 ratio and a 0.4 water-to-binder ratio were used. The batching of ingredients was performed by weight. All the ingredients were then mixed in a concrete mixer until the formation of a uniform paste, and 10 standard-size cylinders (6×12") were prepared in each batch. The inner of the molds was oiled and the concrete was filled in three layers. A table vibrator was used to achieve the proper compaction. The molds were then left for 24 hours to let the concrete harden. Figure 3 shows some selected samples.

After 24 hours, the specimens were de-molded, allowed to dry in the air for a day, and immersed in potable water for 28-day curing, as shown in Figure 4.

TABLE II. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF SUGARCANE BAGASSE ASH

#	Component	Mass percentage
1	Silica (SiO ₂)	66.89
2	Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	29.18
3	Ferric oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	
4	Calcium oxide (CaO)	1.92
5	Magnesium oxide (MgO)	0.83
6	Sulphur tri oxide (SO ₃)	0.56
7	Loss of ignition	0.72

Fig. 1. Sugarcane bagasse.

Fig. 2. Bagasse ash.

Fig. 3. Specimens.

After curing, the specimens were taken out of the water and allowed to dry in the laboratory for one day. In each batch, 5 specimens were used to evaluate their compressive strength and 5 were used to determine the split tensile strength. The specimens were tested in a compressive strength machine under gradually increasing load until failure, following the ASTM C39 [37]. Figure 5 shows some specimens during

testing. The load was then converted into compressive strength using the standard formula for the purpose $\sigma=P/A$.

Fig. 4. Curing.

Fig. 5. Compressive strength test.

Fig. 6. Split tensile strength test.

The specimens were laterally loaded onto a universal testing machine, following ASTM C496 [38], with a gradually increasing load at a rate of 0.5kN/sec to determine their tensile strength, as shown in Figure 6. The crushing load was recorded and converted into split tensile strength using the standard formula $f=2P/\pi LD$. Table III shows the results obtained from the compressive and tensile strength tests for all specimens.

TABLE III. COMPRESSIVE AND TENSILE STRENGTH

Concrete mix	#	Compressive strength (MPa)		Split tensile strength (MPa)	
		Bagasse ash percentage (%)			
		0	10	0	10
M1: 4.75-7	1	27.15	23.99	2.66	2.45
	2	28.41	27.95	2.82	2.24
	3	29.79	19.48	2.74	2.27
M2: 10-Jul	1	32	29.41	2.96	2.7
	2	35.3	28.81	3.21	2.66
	3	32.19	28.47	3.06	2.54
M3: 13-Oct	1	34.39	30.93	3.39	2.8
	2	35	31.45	3.16	2.85
	3	37.67	28.93	3.11	2.7
M4: 13-20	1	31.76	27.67	3.18	2.66
	2	32.97	27.95	3	2.5
	3	32.61	28.07	3.12	2.51
M5: 4.75-20	1	33.36	31.91	2.98	2.74
	2	33.75	27.91	3.19	2.78
	3	33.51	28.51	3.19	2.73

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 shows the compressive strength of concrete with 0% and 10% bagasse ash. Although there is a fluctuating trend in the compressive strength of individual samples, the difference in the strength of individual samples is small. Table IV and Figure 8 show the average compressive strength of the samples per batch. It can be observed that the compressive strength of concrete with bagasse ash was smaller than the one without. Although the ash has good cementitious properties, they are not equal to cement's, therefore cement replacement with ash affects the strength. Furthermore, it can be observed that the gradation of concrete had also an impact on the final strength. The maximum strength in concrete without bagasse ash was recorded in M3 (10-13mm aggregates), as its value was even higher than the compressive strength of well-graded aggregates (+6.4%). M1 and M2 mixes had less strength than M5, due to the smaller size of aggregates which have less strength. M4 also had less strength than M5. The mix contained large-sized aggregates, and the lack of small-sized particles should have resulted in voids inside the body of concrete resulting in less strength. M3 had the highest strength among the considered mixes due to medium-sized particles being able to contribute strength and fill the voids of the concrete. The fourth column lists the deviation of the average compressive strength of concrete mixes with and without 10% bagasse ash. The lowest error was recorded in M5 with well-graded aggregates and then in M2 with 7-10mm aggregates. This shows that small-sized aggregates in the concrete matrix gave better strength results, but the effort required to separate the grades is more. The last two columns of the table list the percentage deviation of the strength concerning the well-graded aggregates without bagasse ash. Figure 9 shows the percentage error of concrete with bagasse ash versus without bagasse ash and with well-graded aggregates. Table III and Figure 9 show that M3 had the least reduction in compressive strength due to the reasons mentioned above.

Figure 10 shows the split tensile strength for individual samples with and without bagasse ash. Table V shows the average split tensile strength of all specimens in each group,

along with the percentage change of each group and for well-graded aggregates without bagasse ash. The results are listed in a pattern similar to those of average compressive strength. Table V and Figures 10-12 show that again the M3 mix (10-13mm aggregates) had the maximum split tensile strength for both concrete types. Graded aggregate concrete had an increase of 3.58% compared to well-graded aggregate concrete, but when using 10% bagasse ash it had a decrease of 10.54% in tensile strength. The decrease was the lowest among all the grades used. It can be further observed that the variation in split tensile strength of M3 concrete with and without bagasse ash was approximately 9%. The same percentage was recorded for concrete with well-graded aggregates.

TABLE IV. AVERAGE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

Average compressive strength		% change			
Mix: mm	Bagasse ash		Same group 10%	Well graded agg.	
	0%	10%		0%	10%
M1: 4.75-7	28.45	23.81	-16.33	-15.18	-29.02
M2: 7-10	33.16	28.9	-12.86	-1.13	-13.84
M3: 10-13	35.69	30.44	-14.71	6.4	-9.26
M4: 13-20	32.45	27.89	-14.03	-3.26	-16.84
M5: 4.75-20	33.54	29.44	-12.22	0	-12.22

Fig. 7. Compressive strength: (a) 0% bagasse ash, (b) 10% bagasse ash.

TABLE V. AVERAGE SPLIT TENSILE STRENGTH

Average split tensile strength		% change			
Mix	Bagasse ash		Same group 10%	Well-graded aggregates	
	0%	10%		0%	10%
	M1: 4.75-7	2.74	2.32	-15.36	-11.87
M2: 7-10	3.07	2.63	-14.31	-1.2	-15.34
M3: 10-13	3.22	2.78	-13.63	3.58	-10.54
M4: 13-20	3.1	2.56	-17.47	-0.41	-17.8
M5: 4.75-20	3.11	2.75	-11.54	0	-11.54

Fig. 8. Average compressive strength.

Fig. 9. % change of compressive strength.

Fig. 10. Split tensile strength: (a) 0% bagasse ash, (b) 10% bagasse ash.

The above findings clearly show that the gradation of aggregates affects the strength properties of concrete. Medium-sized aggregates (10-13mm) give better strength, even than well-graded aggregates, due to the binding of the bagasse ash and the fineness that fills the gaps between the aggregates, as it not only reduces the voids but also improves the strength of concrete. On the other hand, it is also evident that the effort involved in separating the aggregates in case of a normal

supply of the material or grading the large blocks to the required size is large compared to the gain in strength (+6.4%). Therefore, the use of well-graded aggregates is encouraged. However, if favorable, the above-mentioned grade of aggregates may be used for better strength. Sugarcane bagasse ash has good cementitious properties. For the grade of aggregates mentioned above, 10% bagasse ash reduced compressive and tensile strength by 9.26% and 10.54%, respectively, which is small and may be tolerable for saving cement content. Even with well-graded aggregate concrete, the percentage reduction in compressive and tensile strength was about 12%. Thus, it is concluded that a 10% dosage of bagasse ash is optimal for specific or well-graded aggregate concrete.

Fig. 11. Average split tensile strength.

Fig. 12. Error % in split tensile strength.

V. CONCLUSION

This study conducted a laboratory investigation on the effect of different grades of coarse aggregates and sugarcane bagasse ash on the strength properties of concrete, finding that both materials affect them. Small-sized aggregates alone in the concrete matrix fill the voids properly but demand higher binder content due to the larger surface area, resulting in reduced strength. Large-sized aggregates alone leave more voids in the concrete body, also reducing its final strength. Medium-sized particles are better from both perspectives, as they reduce voids and show maximum strength properties. Although bagasse ash has good cementitious properties, these are lower than cement's. The use of bagasse ash reduces both cement content and the strength properties of concrete, however, the reduction in strength is small, about 9% and 11% for compressive and tensile strength, respectively. In addition, bagasse ash in well-graded aggregate concrete showed a marginal reduction of 12% in strength. Thus, a 10% dose of

bagasse ash is proposed as optimal. The results showed that concrete with 7-13mm coarse aggregates had more strength than well-aggregated concrete, but the effort required to separate or produce this grade of aggregate is possibly higher than the strength increase (6.4%). Therefore, this study proposes well-graded aggregates with sugarcane bagasse ash.

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Preparation, Characterization, and Antibacterial Activity of Silver Nanoparticle-Decorated Ordered Mesoporous Carbon

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ABSTRACT

In this study, Ordered Mesoporous Carbon (OMC) was prepared using resol as a carbon precursor and F127 as a soft template. Small-angle X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) images, and nitrogen adsorption and desorption isotherms revealed that OMC possessed ordered hexagonal mesostructures (p6m) with an ordered pore size of 3.2nm, a high specific surface area (S_{BET}) of 539m²/g, and a large total pore volume (V_{total}) of 0.44cm³/g. Subsequently, silver nanoparticles synthesized from an aqueous AgNO₃ solution using glucose as a reducing agent and starch as a stabilizing agent were decorated on OMC, producing Ag/OMC. XRD analysis revealed that the composite contained silver crystals. In addition, the content and size of silver nanoparticles in Ag/OMC were 0.71wt% (AAS) and around 25-50nm (TEM), respectively. Due to the surface cover of silver nanoparticles, S_{BET} and V_{total} of Ag/OMC slightly decreased to 417m²/g and 0.38cm³/g, respectively. Both agar and broth dilution techniques were used to evaluate the antibacterial activity of the material against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Ag/OMC with a Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of 25.0µg/mL is a potential candidate for use against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Keywords-mesoporous carbon; soft template; silver nanoparticles; green synthesis; antibacterial activity; *Staphylococcus aureus*

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, nanomaterials, which exhibit unique nanoscale properties compared to their bulk composition, have propelled research in numerous fields [1-3]. Advances in nanoparticle production in a variety of sizes and shapes have facilitated the expansion of their applications [4-6]. Due to their outstanding physical, chemical, and biological properties, silver nanoparticles have been intensively studied for various uses, such as antibacterial agents, imaging probes, reduction catalysts, and oxidation catalysts [7-9]. To prepare silver nanoparticles, chemical reduction techniques are commonly and extensively used [10], which involve the use of reducing agents like sodium borohydride, hydrazine, and citrate to convert silver ions into silver nanoparticles. These methods provide multiple advantages, including a high yield of silver nanoparticles and the ability to control the size and shape of the nanoparticles. However, the use of toxic chemicals is a significant obstacle. To overcome that problem, different green methods have been explored. Glucose and starch are recognized as natural, renewable, non-toxic, and inexpensive agents [11-12]. Glucose can replace traditional reducing agents, while starch molecules can act as stabilizing agents by adsorbing onto the surface of nanoparticles, preventing their aggregation. As a result, the combination of glucose and starch offers a green and sustainable approach for the preparation of silver nanoparticles with controlled size and shape. However, silver nanoparticles with high surface energy tend to aggregate [13]. As a result, the peculiar properties of these nanoparticles can be drastically diminished during use [14]. To address this issue, silver nanoparticles should be stabilized on appropriate supports to prevent their aggregation [15-16]. In recent years, Ordered Mesoporous Carbon (OMC) with pore diameters ranging from 2 to 50nm has garnered considerable interest due to its higher specific surface area, larger pore volume, electrical and thermal conductivity, chemical inertness, good thermomechanical stability, and various oxygen-containing functional groups [17-18]. Therefore, OMC has been applied in numerous fields, such as adsorption, catalyst support, hydrogen storage, carbon dioxide capture, lithium batteries, electrochemical sensors, electrochemical capacitors, and drug delivery [19-22]. Commonly, OMC can be fabricated by nanocasting using ordered mesoporous silica as a hard template. This method yields OMC with a high specific surface area and a large pore volume [23]. Nevertheless, this process requires the preparation of ordered mesoporous silica in the first step but sacrifices it in a later step [24]. Furthermore, the removal of this template has the potential to damage the surface of the OMC and cause environmental pollution [25]. In general, this method has the drawbacks of being expensive, complicated, and difficult to scale up [26]. A cost-effective and eco-friendly soft-template method was developed to address the limitations of existing technologies. Self-assembly of block copolymers is the basis for OMC production [27]. Carbon precursors (e.g. resol, phenolic resin) are self-assembled into supramolecular aggregates with block copolymers (acting as soft templates, e.g. F127, P123) [28-30]. The mixture is then thermopolymerized to give a cross-linked composite, the template is removed, and carbonization occurs. Resol is a common carbon source for this approach due to its moderate

weight and size and its moveability in surfactant environments [23, 31]. F127 has advantages as a versatile and widely used soft template for the preparation of mesoporous materials, including high porosity, tunability, thermal stability, biocompatibility, and ease of use [32-33]. Moreover, F127 can be decomposed easily at low temperatures (e.g. 350°C), while resol is more stable [30]. The template can be removed to leave mesopores. The complete carbonization of resol to obtain the final OMC framework can be conducted at high temperatures (e.g. 600°C).

Several studies have reported the dispersion of silver nanoparticles on mesoporous carbon supports. In [34], silver-decorated mesoporous carbons (CMK-3 type, hard template) were prepared to promote wound healing. In [35], the soft-template method and tetraethyl orthosilicate were used to create mesoporous carbons containing embedded silver nanoparticles. In [36], a silver nanoparticle-OMC composite was prepared using F127 as a soft template and phenolformaldehyde resin as a carbon source, and then applied it to a lithium-ion battery. In [37], a soft template was used to synthesize ordered mesoporous silver nanoparticle/carbon composites for the catalytic reduction of 4-nitrophenol. In general, the use of soft-templated OMC as a support for silver nanoparticles has been rarely reported in the literature. Hence, this research was carried out to investigate the feasibility of incorporating silver nanoparticles and OMC. OMC was first fabricated with F127 as a soft template and resol as the carbon source. The OMC surface was then coated with silver nanoparticles, and the resulting composite was tested for its potential as an antibacterial agent.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Phenol ($\geq 99.0\%$), formaldehyde (37.0-40.0%), AgNO_3 (99.8%), and HCl (36.0-38.0%) were purchased from Xilong Scientific Co., Ltd. F127, starch, glucose, and ethanol ($\geq 99.5\%$) were obtained from BASF, Merk, Guangdong Guanghua Sci-Tech Co. and VN-Chemsol Co., respectively. All chemicals were used as received without any further purification. Resol was produced from phenol and formaldehyde. In a spherical flask, 9.35mL of liquid phenol was magnetically swirled with 1.75mL of a NaOH solution (20wt%). After adding 16.0mL of formaldehyde dropwise, the mixture was agitated continuously for 1 hour at 70°C. After completion of the reaction, the liquid was chilled to room temperature, and the pH was adjusted to approximately 7.0 by adding a 0.6M HCl solution. The water was then vacuumed out at 50°C. The resulting resol was redissolved in ethanol to generate a resol solution (20 wt%), while sodium chloride was separated as a precipitate.

OMC was synthesized from resol as a carbon source and F127 as a soft template. At the beginning, 1.00g of F127 was dissolved in 10.0g of ethanol. Following this, 5.00g of resol solution (20 wt%) were added. After 60 minutes of stirring, the solvent was separated within 24 hours by evaporation at room temperature. The solid was then crushed into a fine powder and placed in a tube furnace with a constant nitrogen flow rate of 70mL/min. Pyrolysis was performed in two consecutive steps: the sample was heated to 350°C at a rate of 2°C/minute and kept at that temperature for 3 hours. Then, it was heated to

600°C at a rate of 5°C/minute and the final temperature was kept for 3 hours. Then, the prepared OMC sample was stored in a plastic bag for further use.

Ag/OMC was prepared by dispersing a colloidal sol of Ag nanoparticles on OMC. At first, a mixture of 1.50mL of AgNO₃ (0.100M), 3.00mL of glucose (0.100M), and 90mL of starch solution (0.17 wt%) was heated and stirred at 70°C. After 15 hours of heating and stirring, the sample was collected to determine the formation of Ag nanoparticles using a UV-Vis spectrometer (Spectronic Genesys 2 PC), and then 1.60g of OMC was added to the colloid. The mixture was stirred for 30 minutes and then sonicated. Lastly, the sample was centrifuged, rinsed with distilled water and ethanol, and oven-dried at 60°C for 4 hours. X-ray Diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed on a Bruker AXS D8 diffractometer with Cu-K α radiation (40kV, 20mA). The morphologies of OMC and Ag/OMC were observed on a JEOL JEM-1400 (100kV) instrument. Nitrogen adsorption and desorption isotherms were conducted on a Quantachrome Autosorb-1 system. Samples were degassed at 300°C for 5 hours. Total pore volume (V_{total}) was calculated at a relative pressure (P/P_0) of 0.995. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller equation was used to determine the specific surface area (S_{BET}). The average pore size ($d_{average}$) was obtained from $4V_{total}/S_{BET}$. The Ag content in Ag/OMC was analyzed with a Shimadzu AA6650 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS).

The antibacterial activity of Ag/OMC was investigated on *Staphylococcus aureus* using two methods: agar dilution and broth dilution. For the agar dilution method, the bacterial strains were grown in Luria-Bertani (LB) medium (peptone 10g/L, yeast extract 5g/L, and NaCl 10g/L) until a density of 10⁸CFU/ml was reached (optical density of 0.5 at 600nm). The suspension was then diluted 10 times to obtain a density of 10⁷CFU/mL. The bacteria were inoculated on agar plates with different Ag/OMC concentrations. Regarding the broth dilution method, 2mL of LB medium, 100 μ L of bacteria, and different Ag/OMC concentrations were added into the test tubes. The mixture was shaken at 200rpm and 37°C. For both methods, bacterial growth and Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) were observed in 24 hours.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Small-angle XRD was used to determine the mesoporous structure of OMC, as shown in Figure 1. Several reflections were found in OMC. These reflections at $2\theta=0.42$, 0.66 , and 0.82° correspond to the 10, 11, and 20 planes of the hexagonal (p6m) structure [21-22]. In addition, the high intensities of these peaks suggest that the mesoporous structure is relatively uniform. The TEM images shown in Figure 5(a) reveal that OMC had a well-ordered mesoporous system with trenches running along the plane (110). Compared with [21-22], this morphology of OMC is fairly similar to that of FDU-15 and other 2D hexagonal (p6m) mesoporous materials.

Figure 2 depicts the nitrogen adsorption and desorption isotherms of OMC. As P/P_0 increased from 0.01 to 0.71, the adsorbed volume gradually increased, indicating that OMC contained both micropores and mesopores. Next, the adsorbed volume increased very slightly and nearly reached equilibrium

at P/P_0 , going from 0.71 to 0.99, suggesting that OMC lacked macropores. Notably, a hysteresis loop was long at P/P_0 between 0.15-0.71 and wide at P/P_0 between 0.36-0.62. This hysteresis loop might belong to type IV, according to the IUPAC classification [38]. Additionally, the shape of the hysteresis loop may be associated with a particular porous structure. This one might be of the H1 type, which represents uniform, open-ended cylinder pores in a 2-D hexagonal structure [39-41]. The BJH pore size distribution shows that OMC had relatively uniform mesopores at 3.2nm and certain micropores, possibly in the mesopore walls. Table I also shows that OMC possessed a high $S_{BET}=539\text{m}^2/\text{g}$ and a large $V_{total}=0.44\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$.

Fig. 1. Small angle X-ray diffraction of OMC.

Fig. 2. (a) Nitrogen adsorption and desorption isotherms and (b) BJH pore size distribution of OMC.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF OMC AND AG/OMC

Sample	S_{BET} (m^2/g)	V_{total} (cm^3/g)	d_{pore} (nm)	$d_{average}$ (nm)	Ag (wt%)
OMC	539	0.44	3.2	3.3	-
Ag/OMC	417	0.38	-	3.6	0.71

The surface plasmon resonance of the silver nanoparticles allowed the exploration of their formation using UV-Vis absorption in the 350-625nm range, as shown in Figure 3. Colloidal silver had a broad absorption band centered at approximately 418nm and a light yellow color. These observations demonstrated the successful generation of silver nanoparticles. Moreover, the broadband signal revealed a high polydispersity of silver nanoparticles in size and shape. The detailed morphology of the silver nanoparticles was observed together with OMC in the Ag/OMC sample.

Fig. 3. UV-Vis spectroscopy of silver nanoparticle suspension and its yellow color.

Figure 4 shows the XRD pattern of Ag/OMC to determine its crystal phases. Face-centered cubic silver planes (111), (200), and (220) were represented by distinct peaks at $2\theta = 38.3, 44.5,$ and 64.2° , respectively (JCPDS Card No. 04-0783). Consequently, only silver nanocrystals were found on OMC. Theoretically, based on the amounts of AgNO_3 and OMC used, the maximum amount of Ag in Ag/OMC was calculated to be 1.01wt%. The AAS results, however, indicate that the silver content was only 0.71wt%. As a result, approximately 70% of the silver was coated on the surface of the OMC, and the remainder was possibly removed during cleaning.

Fig. 4. X-ray diffraction of Ag/OMC.

Fig. 5. TEM images of (a) OMC and (b) Ag/OMG

Figure 5 shows TEM images of OMC and Ag/OMC samples. Compared to OMC, the presence of dark spots in the Ag/OMC showed the morphology of silver nanoparticles. In general, a wide size range of 20-50nm was observed for silver nanoparticles of various shapes. As only 0.71wt% of the silver nanoparticles were loaded on the OMC surface, their density was relatively low. Therefore, the stripe-like structure of the OMC was still exposed. In addition, S_{BET} and V_{total} of Ag/OMC were $417\text{m}^2/\text{g}$ and $0.38\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$, respectively, which were slightly lower than those of OMC. These decreases were not

significant, since silver nanoparticles could have low surface coverage. Thus, the porosity of OMC could be advantageous.

Staphylococcus aureus was used to assess the antibacterial activity of Ag/OMC using both agar and broth dilution methods. Figure 6 and Table II show that the bacteria were not found on agar plates at Ag/OMC concentrations of 25.0 and $50.0\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Certain bacteria growths were observed at low Ag/OMC concentrations of $0.10\text{-}12.5\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Therefore, the MIC for Ag/OMC was $25.0\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Figure 7 and Table III

show the results of the broth method. After 24 hours of shaking, the bacteria still caused turbidity in tubes 4-10, showing that they survived at low Ag/OMC concentrations of 0.20-12.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The antibacterial ability of Ag/OMC became effective at higher concentrations of 25.0, 50.0, and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The mixtures in tubes 1, 2, and 3 were transparent, showing that *Staphylococcus aureus* could not grow. Hence, both methods resulted in similar MICs of 25.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The antibacterial ability of Ag/OMC (0.71wt% Ag) against *Staphylococcus aureus* was generally comparable to those of Ag/activated carbon (0.92wt% Ag, 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) [42], Ag/carbon dots (5.4wt% C and 94.6wt% Ag, 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) [43], and better than silver nanoparticles prepared by different routes (a broad range of 0.25-430 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) [44]. The dispersion of silver nanoparticles on OMC could prevent their ability to agglomerate, possibly resulting in their enhanced antibacterial activity.

Fig. 6. Experimental image of the agar dilution method.

TABLE II. RESULTS OF AGAR DILUTION METHOD

Control	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)									
	50.0	25.0	12.5	6.25	3.13	1.56	0.78	0.39	0.20	0.10
C	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Fig. 7. Experimental image of the broth dilution method.

TABLE III. RESULTS OF BROTH DILUTION METHOD

Control	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)									
	100	50.0	25.0	12.5	6.25	3.13	1.56	0.78	0.39	0.20
C	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

IV. CONCLUSION

This study successfully fabricated silver nanoparticle-coated ordered mesoporous carbon. At first, resol was used to

synthesize OMC using F127 as a soft template. OMC was composed of a mesoporous p6m structure with a typical pore size of 3.2nm, $S_{BET}=539\text{m}^2/\text{g}$, and $V_{total}=0.44\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$. The surface of OMC was then decorated with silver nanoparticles prepared from AgNO_3 using glucose as a reducing agent and starch as a stabilizing agent. TEM images showed that silver nanoparticles with rough sizes of 20-50nm adhered to the surface of OMC. Finally, as shown with a MIC of 25.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, Ag/OMC is expected to have the potential for antibacterial applications.

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The Impact of the Ground Irregular Sedimentary Structure on the Seismic Motion Amplification Characteristics

A case study in Tottori, Japan

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ABSTRACT

The amplification characteristics of seismic motion are determined by the ground structure. In design practice, the ground is assumed to be horizontally stratified. However, the actual ground forms irregular sedimentary structures and the propagation direction of the seismic motion in the soil changes in a complicated way. Thus, the actual amplification factor of seismic motion is dramatically different from the value assumed in design practice. This phenomenon is called the multidimensional effect. The present study targeted at a seismic observation point in Tottori Prefecture, Japan, and estimated the irregular ground structures based on the microtremor observation results. With this ground structure model, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was conducted and the amplification factors were compared with those determined assuming horizontal stratification. When there is no ground nonlinearity, the multidimensional effect of the ground was more notable in points with thick sedimentary strata, where the peak amplification factor according to the FEA was 1.9 to 3.6 times larger than when horizontal stratification was assumed. In points with thin sedimentary strata, the peak amplification factor ratio was 2.1–2.4. First-order peak frequency was different between cases with irregular ground structures and with horizontal stratification. Furthermore, when the nonlinearity of the ground was evident, the multidimensional effect on the peak amplification factor was not as noticeable as when the ground behaved linearly. The peak magnification ratio due to the multidimensional effect was found to be 2.3. The results of this study show that the amplification characteristics of the seismic motion considered in design practice are likely to be on the dangerous side when the ground is not horizontally stratified.

Keywords-seismic motion; site amplification factor; finite element analysis; ground nonlinearity

I. INTRODUCTION

Seismic motions are determined by the source, path, and site amplification characteristics. Site amplification characteristics display the property of seismic motion being amplified as it propagates through sedimentary grounds, and its amplification factor varies by frequency. When the ground has horizontal stratification and the seismic motion is a vertical incident to the ground, site amplification characteristics can be theoretically calculated based on parameters such as the thickness and the shear modulus of each stratum. Such characteristics are simplified in design practice, where the ground type is classified based on the average S-wave velocity of the top 30m (V_{s30}) [1–3] and the natural period of the

shallow subsurface [4], and the amplification factor is determined for each ground type.

There are two problems with such simplification of site amplification characteristics. First, grounds consist of shallow and deep subsurfaces, yet in a simplified assessment, only the influence of the shallow subsurface is considered. The deep subsurface has high rigidity and does not exhibit nonlinear characteristics even during a massive earthquake. In contrast, the shallow subsurface has relatively low rigidity, impacted by nonlinearity during massive earthquakes. The boundary between the two is the engineering bedrock, whose S-wave velocity is 300m/s or higher. The amplification factor for the seismic motion is much higher for the deep subsurface than for the shallow subsurface [5–7]. Even points that are classified in

the same ground type in design practice present notable variations in the amplification factor of seismic motion. However, in the classification based on the amplification characteristics of the deep subsurface, such variations are reduced [8]. Even if the deep subsurface is considered, the theoretical amplification factor calculated with the assumed horizontal stratification is extremely smaller than the one assessed by spectral inversion [9–11] using seismic records [6, 7]. The actual ground structure does not have horizontal stratification and the thickness of each stratum changes in a complex manner for each location. Therefore, changes in the propagation direction of the seismic motion in the ground are complex. As the wave motions are superimposed in the ground in a complex manner, the amplification factor observed on the ground surface becomes notably different from the theoretical value calculated with the assumption of horizontal stratification. This phenomenon is called the multidimensional effect. When the seismic response is evaluated with a one-dimensional (1D) model based on the horizontal stratification, there are notable errors compared to the observed seismic motion [12]. Yet, only a few studies have examined the actual impact of the multidimensional effect of the ground on the amplification factor of the seismic motion. For example, some studies considered a simple two-layer structure with an inclined bedrock, and examined the difference in the seismic response on the ground surface using two-dimensional (2D) models [13, 14]. Another study prepared a 2D model for a multi-layer irregular ground and examined the differences in amplification characteristics [15]. Since the site amplification characteristics dramatically vary by location [16], site amplification characteristics must be accurately evaluated for each point.

In the present study, focus was given on a seismic observation point in Tottori Prefecture, Japan, and site amplification characteristics that consider the impact of deep subsurface at the target point were calculated by using the seismic records observed at that point and in the surrounding areas. Microtremor observation was conducted in the target area to estimate the ground structure around the target point. Then, 2D Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was conducted for the estimated ground structure, and the impact of the irregular sedimentary structures of the ground on the amplification factor of the seismic motion was discussed. To the best of our knowledge, no previous studies have discussed the multidimensional effects in the conditions of both linear and nonlinear responses of the ground, however, this study discusses these effects in both conditions.

II. TARGET POINT AND THE GROUND STRUCTURE

A. Site Amplification Characteristics of the Target Point

The case study was conducted at a point in Tottori Prefecture from the strong-motion seismograph networks K-NET of Japan [17], namely the point TTR004 (Figure 1). With K-NET, S-wave velocity structure down to 20m at a seismic observation point is obtained with P-S logging [18]. The seismic observation point for TTR004 was moved in 2003, and site amplification characteristics for the current observation point have not been obtained so far. Thus, we used seismic records for TTR004 and three K-NET observation points

around TTR004 for which site amplification characteristics have been calculated through spectral inversion (TTR002, TTR005, and TTR006) to assess the site amplification characteristics of TTR004. Since earthquakes of higher magnitude (M) have more complex source characteristics, we only studied earthquakes between 4.2 and 6.0 M. To avoid the impact of nonlinear response of the shallow subsurface, we used the records with Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) of 1m/s^2 or lower. Since seismic records with low acceleration can have poor Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SN ratio), based on the ω^2 rule [19], we selected records with good SN ratio, greater than 0.2Hz. Under the aforementioned conditions, we prepared a set of records for 10 earthquakes. Site amplification characteristics at TTR004 were calculated with (1) based on the spectral ratio of seismic record [20].

$$G_T(f) = G_R(f) \cdot \frac{O_T(f) \cdot r_T \cdot \exp\{-\pi f r_R / (Q(f)V_S)\}}{O_R(f) \cdot r_R \cdot \exp\{-\pi f r_T / (Q(f)V_S)\}} \quad (1)$$

where $G(f)$ represents the site amplification characteristics, $O(f)$ is the observed seismic motion, r is the hypocentral distance, $Q(f)$ is the quality factor along the propagation path, V_S is the S-wave velocity along the propagation path (3.55km/s in this study based on [21]), and f is the frequency. Subscripts R and T indicate reference and target points (TTR004), respectively. Q is an index that expresses anelastic attenuation with frequency dependence, which varies by each area [22, 23]. In this study, Q was calculated with (2) based on [24]:

$$Q(f) = 152 f^{0.38} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Target point.

Figure 2 shows the calculated site amplification characteristics. The thin gray line represents site amplification characteristics from individual records, while the red line represents the average. For reference, the site amplification characteristics of TTR004 obtained from the seismic observation records of the previous location through spectral inversion are represented by the blue line. At the previous location, the amplification factor was approximately 1 to 4 and did not show any notable difference based on frequency. However, at the present point, it shows a large amplification factor of 22.7 at 1.3Hz. Though the distance between the previous and the present seismic observation point is only 1.3km, the site amplification characteristics are notably different, therefore, site-specific assessment of amplification factor is extremely important.

Fig. 2. Site amplification characteristics for TTR004.

B. Estimation of the Ground Structure through Microtremor Observation

We observed the microtremors around TTR004. From the observation result, we calculated the spectral ratio for the horizontal and vertical components of microtremors (H/V spectrum). When surface waves are dominant in microtremors, the H/V spectrum can be considered to be the same with that of the surface waves. Since the surface waves with vertical components are Rayleigh waves, their H/V spectrum can be considered the one of Rayleigh waves [25]. The peak frequency of the H/V spectrum of Rayleigh waves is quite consistent with the first-order peak frequency of the amplification characteristics of seismic motion [26]. Thus, the H/V spectrum is useful as a basis for estimating the ground structure for the microtremor observation points. By assuming the S-wave velocity structure of the ground, the theoretical H/V spectrum for the fundamental-mode Rayleigh waves can be calculated [27]. Thus, from the perspective of minimizing the residual difference between the H/V spectrum and the H/V spectrum of the fundamental-mode Rayleigh waves, the S-wave velocity structure of each point can be estimated.

Fig. 3. Microtremor observation points.

Figure 3 shows the observation point locations and the peak frequency of the H/V spectrum as well. The microtremor observations were conducted in the area 2.0km in east–west and 1.5km in north–south. The peak frequency of the H/V spectrum range between 1.0 and 6.5Hz, showing a notable difference in location. This indicates that the ground structure shows notable difference between locations. Figure 4 shows the target survey line for FEA along with the peak frequency of the H/V spectrum. A-H in the Figure are analytical target points of the FEA discussed below, where D refers to TTR004. The survey line width was 600m and the peak frequency was distributed over a wide band of 1.2–3.0Hz as shown below,

indicating that even in a narrow range around TTR004, the ground structure rapidly changes.

Fig. 4. FEA target survey line.

To calculate the H/V spectrum of the Rayleigh waves, thickness, S-wave velocity, P-wave velocity, and density of each stratum are necessary. By combining the S-wave velocity distribution for the top 20m at TTR004 and that distribution at the depth from J-SHIS [28], the S-wave velocity structure down to deep subsurface can be set. Regarding the S-wave velocity of the top 20m, we also referred to [29]. P-wave velocity and density can be calculated with [30]:

$$\rho = 1.7 + 0.32 \times 10^{-3} V_S \tag{3}$$

$$V_P = 100\sqrt{V_S} \tag{4}$$

where ρ is the density (t/m^3), V_S is the S-wave velocity (m/s), and V_P is the P-wave velocity (m/s).

The ground model was adjusted so that the peak frequencies for the H/V spectrum of the fundamental-mode Rayleigh waves and microtremors would be consistent. For four microtremor observation points on the target survey line of FEA, we changed the thickness of each stratum based on the S-wave velocity structure of TTR004, so that the peak frequency of the H/V spectrum of the microtremors and that of the Rayleigh waves would be consistent. The red line in Figure 5 denotes the H/V spectrum of microtremors and the blue line shows the H/V spectrum of Rayleigh waves. As for the northern edge of the FEA observation line, we were unable to conduct microtremor observation. Therefore, we postulated the peak frequency to be 1.9Hz, which is the mean peak frequency of the H/V spectrum at the two closest points. For the points other than the S-wave velocity structure estimation points, we assumed that the strata thickness would transform linearly, and estimated the ground structure for the target survey line for FEA. Figure 6 and Table I show the obtained ground structure. The thickness of the strata deeper than $V_S = 800m/s$ was constant, while the thickness of the strata with $V_S = 400m/s$ changed dramatically depending on location. Furthermore, strata with low rigidity of $V_S = 190m/s$ were assumed to be limited to the areas A to E, located on the north side of the survey line. Figure 6 also shows the FE mesh. The point C is the point in where the sedimentary strata are at their thickest, while the point G is where they are thinnest. The bedrock depth difference between the two points was 14m.

Fig. 5. H/V spectrum.

Fig. 6. The ground structure and FE mesh.

TABLE I. STRATUM THICKNESS

Stratum no.	Vs (m/s)	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	180	1							
2	270	4.6	5.4	6	6	5	4	4	4.5
3	200	1							
4	280	9.3	9.6	10	10	9	8	8	9.5
5	190	5.3	7.8	10	6	0.5	0		
6	400	16	19.2	22	20	11	10	2	7.8
7	800	10							
8	1100	32							
9	1400	45							
10	1700	37							
11	2100	46							
12	2700	88							
13	3100	-							

A - H are locations shown in Figure 6. Unit: m.

C. Seismic Response Analysis

To examine the multidimensional effect, we performed 2D FEA for the ground shown in Figure 6. The FEA model has width and height of 600m 320m, respectively. The width of the FEA model was set as the width at which the seismic responses of the output points (i.e. A and H) at both ends were unaffected by the model lateral boundary. The FEA code used was FLIP [31]. The FE mesh height was set such that the seismic motion up to 10Hz could be propagated. The boundary conditions

were: during the self-weight analysis, the bottom boundary was fixed and the side boundaries were horizontally fixed while vertically free. During the dynamic analysis, side and bottom boundaries were viscous boundaries. The shallow subsurfaces linearly respond during small earthquakes. However, they could become nonlinear during a massive earthquake. Site amplification characteristics shown in Figure 2 are those where there is no impact of the ground nonlinearity. On the other hand, deep subsurfaces do not exhibit nonlinear characteristics even during a massive earthquake. Thus, deep subsurfaces were modeled with linear planar elements while shallow subsurfaces were either modeled with linear planar elements or elements that can consider the nonlinearity of the ground. Regarding the linear planar elements, the Young’s modulus was calculated as:

$$G = \rho V_s^2 \tag{5}$$

$$E = 2(1 + \nu)G \tag{6}$$

where G is the shear modulus (kPa), ρ is the density (t/m^3), V_s is the S-wave velocity (m/s), E is the Young’s modulus (kPa), and ν is the Poisson’s ratio ($= 0.33$).

Hysteresis damping was set as in (7) [31] and was expressed with Rayleigh damping. Rayleigh damping is expressed with (8). In this study, we set the parameters α and β such that, in the range of 1–5Hz, where the peak frequency of amplification characteristics exists, the residual sum of squares of (7) and (8) would be minimum.

$$\xi = \frac{5.333}{V_s + 66.77} \tag{7}$$

$$\xi = \frac{\alpha}{2\omega} + \frac{\beta\omega}{2} \tag{8}$$

where ξ is the damping constant, V_s is the S-wave velocity (m/s), α and β are the parameters that multiply the mass matrix and rigidity matrix respectively, and ω is the angular frequency ($= 2\pi f$).

When considering the nonlinearity of the ground, we employed multi-spring elements that can assess responses during principal stress axes rotation [32] for layers of $V_s = 400m/s$ or less. For the nonlinearity of the ground, we used the hyperbolic model below [33].

$$\frac{G_m}{G_0} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{G_0 \gamma}{\tau_m}} \tag{9}$$

where G_m is the shear modulus, G_0 is the initial shear modulus, γ is the shear strain, and τ_m is the shear strength, which is calculated by (10) [34]. Shear modulus G_m of the ground at each depth is calculated with the reference shear modulus and the reference effective confining pressure using (11) [35]. The reference bulk modulus K_{ma} is calculated with (12).

$$\tau_m = \sigma_m' \sin \phi \tag{10}$$

$$G_m = G_{ma} \left(\frac{\sigma_m'}{\sigma_{ma}'} \right)^{0.5} \tag{11}$$

$$K_{ma} = \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{1+\nu}{1-2\nu} \right) G_{ma} \tag{12}$$

where G_{ma} is the reference shear modulus, σ_m' is the effective confining pressure, σ_{ma}' is the reference effective confining pressure that corresponds to the reference shear modulus, ϕ is the shear resistance angle, and ν is the Poisson's ratio.

Tables II and III show the ground parameters used for FEA for linear response and nonlinear response, respectively.

TABLE II. GROUND PARAMETERS (LINEAR RESPONSE)

Stratum No.	V_s (m/s)	ρ (t/m^3)	E (kPa)	α	β
1	180	1.8	152089	0.1	0.002
2	270	1.8	361212	0.1	0.001
3	200	1.8	198196	0.1	0.002
4	280	1.8	408910	0.1	0.001
5	190	1.8	178872	0.1	0.002
6	400	1.8	834510	0.098	0.001
7	800	2.0	3264600	0.1	0
8	1100	2.1	6475050	0.1	0
9	1400	2.2	10979200	0.089	0
10	1700	2.4	16912300	0.073	0
11	2100	2.4	27279400	0.06	0
12	2700	2.6	48744500	0.043	0
13	3100	2.7	67465200	0.041	0

TABLE III. GROUND PARAMETERS (NONLINEAR RESPONSE)

Stratum No.	V_s (m/s)	ρ (t/m^3)	σ_{ma}' (kPa)	G_{ma} (kPa)	K_{ma} (kPa)
1	180	1.8	6.62	58320	152089
2	270	1.8	55.13	138510	361212
3	200	1.8	104.0	76000	198196
4	280	1.8	184.5	156800	408910
5	190	1.8	299.8	68590	178872
6	400	1.8	488.8	320000	834510

Fig. 7. Seismic waveform.

We used incident seismic waveform at the engineering bedrock by deconvolution [37] based on the seismic waveform observed at the Hachinohe Port during the Tokachi-Oki earthquake in 1968 (Figure 7). The PGA was $2.1m/s^2$ and the dominant frequencies were 0.4 and 1.0Hz. The seismic motion in the low frequency range has an impact on the nonlinearity of the ground [38]. In this study, we used the seismic waveform shown in Figure 7 and the $0.1m/s^2$ PGA waveform in order to

avoid the impact of ground nonlinearity. The evaluated amplification characteristics in 2D FEA (hereafter 2D amplification characteristics) were the spectral ratio of the seismic motion at the ground surface and the input seismic motion. When obtaining the spectral ratio, the seismic motions were both smoothed with the Parzen Window [39] with a band width of 0.2Hz. The output points of FEA are the 8 points, from A to H, shown in Figure 6. To discuss the multidimensional effect of the ground, we evaluated the amplification characteristics under horizontal stratification structure (hereafter referred to as the 1D amplification characteristics). When the surface ground nonlinearity was not considered, the evaluation was performed based on the multiple reflection theory. When it was considered, we used 1D FEA with the same ground parameters as the 2D FEA. The evaluation of the amplification characteristics using the multiple reflection theory was expressed with Rayleigh damping, with the same values as the linear planar element damping in FEA.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The conditions without an impact of the ground nonlinearity where the PGA of the input seismic motion is $0.1m/s^2$ is discussed first. Figure 8 shows the acceleration time history for point C where the thickness of sedimentary strata is at its thickest. The 1D and 2D responses are indicated with blue and red lines, respectively. Ground surface PGA in 1D analysis and 2D analysis were 0.27 and $0.62 m/s^2$, respectively. It is noted that the PGA of the 2D analysis was 2.3 times that of the 1D analysis, indicating the multidimensional effect. As for the seismic waveform envelope, while the 1D response was similar to the input waveform, the 2D response was different from the input waveform, where the maximum response appeared in 6.94s and the duration of the seismic motion was long. It is a result of complex and repetitive seismic-wave incidences and reflections on each stratum.

Fig. 8. Response at point C (linear response).

Figure 9 shows the amplification characteristics of each point. The blue line indicates the 1D response and the red line the 2D response. At points A to D with thick sedimentary strata, the difference between 2D and 1D amplification characteristics was notable. The peak magnification for 2D and 1D amplification characteristics ranged from 14.9 to 35.8, and from 7.8 to 10.0, respectively. The magnification ratio of both was in the range of 1.9 and 3.6. The peak magnification ratio was the largest at point C where the sedimentary strata were the thickest. At point D, which is equivalent to TTR004, the peak magnification of 2D amplification characteristics was 17.6, mostly reproducing the peak magnification of site amplification characteristics (22.7) shown in Figure 2. In contrast, with 1D amplification characteristics, the peak magnification was 8.9, not reproducing the actual amplification factor.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the amplification characteristics (linear response).

Regarding the peak frequency, there was a difference between 1D and 2D amplification characteristics. With 2D amplification characteristics, the first-order peak frequency ranged from 1.6 to 1.7Hz, but with 1D amplification

characteristics, it ranged from 1.4 to 1.8Hz. Thus, in 2D amplification characteristics, the first-order peak frequency appears at frequencies higher than in 1D amplification characteristics, because the seismic response at each point is impacted not only by the ground structure immediately below, but also by the surrounding ground structures. However, at point A, the first-order peak frequency was almost the same for both 2D and 1D amplification characteristics.

For points E to H with thin sedimentary strata, the difference between 2D and 1D amplification characteristics was limited, even though the multidimensional effect was confirmed. In other words, the peak magnification ranged in the range of 5.4 to 7.3 and 1.2 to 17.5, respectively, for 1D and 2D amplification characteristics. The magnification ratio of both was in the range of 2.1 to 2.4. The first-order peak frequency ranged from 2.2 to 3.4Hz for 1D amplification characteristics, though not clear for point E. For 2D amplification characteristics, it ranged between 1.6 and 2.5Hz. The first-order peak frequency for 2D amplification characteristics was lower than that for 1D amplification characteristics. This is also a result of the impact of the surrounding ground structures on the seismic motion amplification characteristics at each point caused by the multidimensional effect.

Next, a case in which there is an impact of the ground nonlinearity and the PGA of the input seismic motion is 2.1m/s^2 is discussed. Figure 10 shows the acceleration time history for point C where the sedimentary strata were the thickest. 1D and 2D response are indicated with blue and red lines, respectively.

Fig. 10. Response at point C (nonlinear response)

The surface ground experience reduced rigidity and increased damping when the ground became nonlinear due to the strong seismic motion. Thus, the first-order peak frequency decreases and the amplification factor also decreases.

Therefore, each amplification characteristic is different from those of linear response. First, with the ground surface PGA with 1D response of 9.92m/s^2 , 2D response was smaller at 4.95m/s^2 . Due to the multidimensional effect, the superposition of the waveform occurred in 2D response, but the PGA became smaller than that of the 1D response due to the soil nonlinearity. The acceleration of the 1D response reached its maximum in 4.2s, a response with high frequency. In contrast, in the 2D response, the maximum was reached in 5.9s. Similar to the linear response, the time for the maximum acceleration response of the ground surface was different due to the multidimensional effect. Furthermore, with the 1D response, as the amplitude of the input seismic motion decreased, the amplitude of the ground surface response decreased. After 5s, the amplitude decreased dramatically. In contrast, with the 2D response, even if the amplitude of the input seismic motion decreased, the response would remain larger and the duration was long. This is the same as in the linear response.

Fig. 11. Comparison of amplification characteristics (nonlinear response).

In Figure 11, 1D amplification characteristics are indicated in blue and 2D amplification characteristics in red. Regarding the peak magnification, the difference between 2D and 1D amplification characteristics decreased compared to the case without the impact of the ground nonlinearity. The same trend can be seen in all points. 2D amplification characteristics had a peak magnification that was 1.4 to 2.3 times more than that of the 1D amplification characteristics. Same as in the case of ground with a linear response, point C with the thickest sedimentary strata had the largest peak magnification. As for the first-order peak frequency, points A to D with the thick sedimentary strata had a less difference between 2D and 1D amplification characteristics compared to the linear response. It can be seen that the peak magnification was notably different between 2D and 1D amplification characteristics at all points. The amplification characteristics of seismic motion under the multidimensional effect could not be explained with the horizontal stratification that is usually assumed in design practice. Thus, simplified handling in design practice could lead to highly risky decisions. This trend was especially notable in points with thick sedimentary strata.

As a next step, we compare the present results with those of previous studies that examined the multidimensional effect [13–15]. Regarding the S-wave velocity of the bedrock in consideration, in contrast to the present 3100m/s , the past studies had values in the range of $800\text{--}2000\text{m/s}$. The previous studies did not discuss the multidimensional effect for all deep ground structures. While the inclination angle of the bedrock in the present study was 20° , past studies considered 30° or higher, meaning that they handled conditions where the multidimensional effect was more likely to occur. As for the nonlinearity of the surface ground, no past study considered both linear and nonlinear cases as the present one does. Though there are differences in the conditions, the ratio of the peak magnification for 2D amplification characteristics that consider irregular sedimentary structure of the ground and 1D amplification characteristics was in the range of $0.7\text{--}1.9$ in the previous studies. However, in the present study, when the ground nonlinearity was not considered, it was as high as 3.6, and when it was, it was 2.3 at maximum. Thus, larger magnification ratio than past studies was obtained due to the multidimensional effect of the ground. The reason for this is that, as discussed above, we considered the ground with S-wave velocity up to 3100m/s . The difference in the peak frequency between 2D and 1D amplification characteristics has been examined in the past, but the difference in specific frequency varies based on the ground conditions.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In the current study, the amplification characteristics of seismic motion were analyzed at a seismic observation point in Tottori Prefecture, Japan, where the ground structure dramatically changes in a narrow area. Then, we compared them with the amplification characteristics of a horizontal stratification ground structure that is usually considered in design practice. The main drawn conclusions are:

- At points where the ground structure is irregular, the site amplification characteristics evaluated using a seismic record have a larger peak magnification than that assumed

by horizontal stratification. Thus, the amplification characteristics of the actual seismic motion cannot be explained with the horizontal stratification that is usually assumed in design practice. FEA that considers irregular ground structure can mostly assess the peak magnification of site amplification characteristics based on seismic records.

- When there is no ground nonlinearity, points with thick sedimentary strata had higher multidimensional effects, where the peak magnification of 2D amplification characteristics was 1.9–3.6 times higher than that from 1D amplification characteristics. Alternatively, at points with thin sedimentary strata, the difference between the two was relatively small, e.g. the 2D amplification characteristics were only 2.1–2.4 times higher than 1D amplification characteristics. As for the first-order peak frequency, with irregular ground structures, there is an impact of the surrounding ground structures. Therefore, the frequency is different from the one acquired when horizontal stratification is assumed.
- When there is ground nonlinearity, the multidimensional effect on the peak magnification of site amplification characteristics was less notable than when the ground behaved linearly. However, at points with thick sedimentary strata, the peak magnification of 2D amplification characteristics was 2.3 times higher than that of 1D amplification characteristics.

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Free Vibration Analysis of Steel-Concrete Pervious Beams

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the free vibration analysis of steel-concrete porous beams with partial or complete shear interface using a finite-element model based on the cubic order beam theory. The present model assumes uniform porosity distribution along the beam thickness. It is assumed that the axial displacement will vary cubically along the thickness of the layer. The cubic order beam theory is implemented using a continuous C^0 finite element containing three nodes and each node has eight degrees of freedom. Shear locking is eliminated in the present model by the numerical integration of the stiffness matrix. Comparing the present model with the published literature, it is found that the present model is robust in predicting the free vibration of the steel-concrete porous beam.

Keywords-steel-concrete porous beams; finite element method; free vibration; porosity; partial shear interface

I. INTRODUCTION

New construction materials are constantly developed for various innovative engineering structures which must withstand static and dynamic loads. More and more companies are adopting cost-effective materials, while enhancing the safety and efficiency of engineering projects. Many engineering practices use composite beams, such as steel-concrete beams, in buildings and bridges, wood-concrete floors, linked shear walls, etc. [1, 2]. In structural design, it is necessary to focus on the materials and the strength of the connectors. The structure of composite beams is affected by the interlayer slip under loading. The impact of partial contact on the structural behavior was investigated in [3]. The Euler-Bernoulli beam theory was used in [4] to investigate the free vibration characteristics of steel-concrete composite continuous beams. Various experimental and analytical studies have been conducted to analyze composite beams [5]. Applying the eigenfunction expansion method along with the quasistatic decomposition method, an analytical solution is presented in [6]. Authors in [7, 8] worked on the vibrational behavior of nanocomposite beams. Under the effect of a moving load, the beam is reinforced by random straight Single-Walled Carbon NanoTubes (SWCNTs).

The accurate results of Higher-order Beam Theory (HBT) intrigued researchers, so TBT has been replaced with HBT in order to obtain more accurate solutions. Authors in [9] built on Reddy's approach to an HSST for multi-layered anisotropic

composite laminates having complete shear interaction. C^0 finite element models were presented for evaluating composite and sandwich beams and the penalty function approach was used to find a C^0 continuous finite element formulation [10, 11]. Analysis of 3 different porosity variations in the thickness direction and their impact on the vibrational properties of the beam are presented in [12]. Free and forced lateral vibration analysis of beams made from Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs) using the Finite Element Method (FEM) is presented in [13]. The state-space technique was used in [14] to expand the static analysis to dynamic analysis without the use of axial force.

From the literature review, it can be seen that there are a few studies regarding the free and forced vibration of a porous steel-concrete beam with a partial shear interface. Therefore, the present study uses the cubic order equation for axial displacement. A linear finite element model is developed for the dynamic analysis of a porous composite beam. The proposed composite beam has a partial or complete shear interaction. The homogeneous porosity distribution along the beam thickness is used to parametrically calculate the material properties. Different interfacial stiffness values are used to calculate the fundamental frequency. The present model is effective for analyzing the free vibrations of porous beams made of steel and concrete under various boundary conditions and moving loads. Several new findings are presented in this paper, making it useful for the subsequent analysis of the free vibration of porous composite beams in the future.

II. FORMULATION

A. Porosity Distribution

This study evaluates how steel and concrete porosity influence the free vibration of composite beams. Due to the uniform distribution of porosity, the variation in Young's modulus, shear modulus, and mass density of the concrete and the steel layer is calculated by:

$$\begin{cases} E_i(y) = E_{\max}(1 - \kappa_i) \\ G_i(y) = G_{\max}(1 - \kappa_i) \\ \rho_i(y) = \rho_{\max}\sqrt{1 - e_{mi}\kappa_i} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $E_i(y)$, $G_i(y)$, $\rho_i(y)$ are the Young's modulus, shear modulus, and mass density of the concrete (upper) layer and steel (lower) layer of the beam along the transverse direction (where $i = c$ -concrete, s -steel).

$$e_i = 1 - \frac{E_{\min}}{E_{\max}} = 1 - \frac{G_{\min}}{G_{\max}} \quad (2)$$

$$e_{mi} = 1 - \sqrt{1 - e_i} \quad (3)$$

where the range of the porosity coefficient for mass density (e_m), porosity coefficient of concrete (e_c), and porosity coefficient of steel (e_s) are $0 < e_{mi} < 1$, and $0 < e_i < 1$. $e_i = e_{mi} = 0$ means that porosity is zero at maximum elastic modulus and greater porosity gives lower elastic modulus.

$$\kappa_i = 1 - \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \sqrt{1 - e_i} - \frac{2}{\pi} + 1 \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

B. Mathematical Formulation

High-order beam theory is used to investigate the free vibration analysis of a composite beam having a shear interface as shown in Figure 1. The displacement field that was selected is unique. Transverse shear stresses must cease on the beam surfaces and remain nonzero elsewhere for the requirements to be satisfied, which determines the shape. The beam's axial displacement is considered as the thickness's cubic function. The axial displacement equation for the upper layer is expressed in (5).

Fig. 1. Porous steel-concrete composite beam with shear flexible interface.

$$[u_i] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -y_i & y_i^2 & y_i^3 \end{bmatrix} [u_{i0} \quad \theta_i \quad \zeta_i \quad \xi_i]^T \quad (5)$$

where $[u_i] = u(x, y_i, z)$ is the axial displacement along the top layer's reference axis passing through its centroid, $\theta_i = \theta(x)$ is the bending rotation, and $\zeta_i = \zeta(x)$ and $\xi_i = \xi(x)$ are high-order terms.

The transverse displacement is assumed to be the same for both layers and can be represented as:

$$W_c(x, y_c, z) = W_s(x, y_s, z) = W(x) = W \quad (6)$$

The partial shear interaction between two layers of the composite beam is modelled by taking distributed shear springs at their interface. The interfacial stiffness and the shear slip at the interface are used to figure out the shear stress at the interface. Interfacial slip (s) is calculated in (7) with u'_c and u'_s being the axial displacement of the upper and lower layer at the interface.

$$s = (u'_c - u'_s) \quad (7)$$

Axial displacement equations, such as (5), are higher-order equations that are concerned with the warping of transverse sections, but do not describe the commonly used displacement parameters adopted in beam theories. So, higher order terms are eliminated by using shear stress-free conditions at the extreme surfaces of the composite beam. The shear stress at any point in the upper layer is calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} [\tau_c] &= [G_c][\gamma_c] \\ \gamma_c &= \left\{ \frac{\partial u_c}{\partial y_c} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \right\} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 2y_c & 3y_c^2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ &\quad \times \begin{bmatrix} \theta_c & \zeta_c & \xi_c & \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix}^T \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where γ_c is the shear strain and G_c the shear modulus of porous concrete layer.

$$\begin{aligned} A_c &= \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{12y^2}{5h_c^2} \right) + \left(\frac{16y^3}{5h_c^3} \right) \right\}, \\ B_c &= \left\{ \left(\frac{12y^2}{5h_c^2} \right) - \left(\frac{16y^3}{5h_c^3} \right) \right\}, \\ C_c &= \left\{ -y - \left(\frac{4y^2}{5h_c} \right) + \left(\frac{12y^3}{5h_c^2} \right) \right\}, \\ D_c &= - \left\{ \left(\frac{2y^2}{5h_c} \right) + \left(\frac{4y^3}{5h_c^2} \right) \right\} \\ A_s &= \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{12y^2}{5h_s^2} \right) - \left(\frac{16y^3}{5h_s^3} \right) \right\}, \\ B_s &= \left\{ \left(\frac{12y^2}{5h_s^2} \right) + \left(\frac{16y^3}{5h_s^3} \right) \right\}, \\ C_s &= \left\{ -y + \left(\frac{4y^2}{5h_s} \right) + \left(\frac{12y^3}{5h_s^2} \right) \right\}, \\ D_s &= \left\{ \left(\frac{2y^2}{5h_s} \right) - \left(\frac{4y^3}{5h_s^2} \right) \right\}, \text{ and } \chi = \frac{dW}{dx} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Shear stress-free conditions are applied at the top and bottom surface of the beam to find the displacement equation.

$$[u_i] = [A_i \ B_i \ c_i \ D_i] [u_{i0} \ u'_i \ \theta_i \ \chi]^T \quad (10)$$

The normal stress and normal strain at any point of the beam are calculated by:

$$\{\bar{\sigma}\}_j = [\bar{D}]_j \{\bar{\epsilon}\}_j \quad (11)$$

$$\{\bar{\epsilon}\}_j = \left\{ \begin{matrix} \epsilon_j \\ \gamma_j \end{matrix} \right\} = \left\{ \begin{matrix} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial y_j} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \end{matrix} \right\} = [H]_j \{\epsilon\}_j \quad (12)$$

where σ_j is the normal stress, τ_j the shear stress, E_j the modulus of elasticity, G_j the shear modulus, ϵ_j the normal strain, and γ_j the shear strain of the j^{th} layer, $j=c$ represents the upper layer and $j= s$ represents the lower layer of two-material composite beams. $[H]_j$ is a function of y_j and $\{\epsilon\}_j$ is the function of x_j which is coordinated along the axial direction. The expressions of $[H]_j$ and $\{\epsilon\}_j$ are:

$$[H]_j = \begin{bmatrix} A_j & B_j & C_j & D_j & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{dA_j}{dy_j} & \frac{dB_j}{dy_j} & \frac{dC_j}{dy_j} & \frac{dD_j}{dy_j} \\ & & & & & & & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\{\epsilon\}_j^T = \left[\frac{du_j}{dx} \ \frac{du'_j}{dx} \ \frac{d\theta_j}{dx} \ \frac{d\phi}{dx} \ u_{j0} \ u'_j \ \theta_j \ \phi \ \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \right] \quad (14)$$

The strain energy as a function of stress and strain can be found by (11)-(12).

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int \left(\{\bar{\epsilon}\}_c^T \{\bar{\sigma}\}_c + \{\bar{\epsilon}\}_s^T \{\bar{\sigma}\}_s \right) dA dx \quad (15)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int \left(\{\bar{\epsilon}\}_c^T [D]_c \{\epsilon\}_c + \{\bar{\epsilon}\}_s^T [D]_s \{\epsilon\}_s \right) dx$$

where $[D]_c = \int ([H]_c [\bar{D}]_c [H]_c) dA_c$, $[D]_s = \int ([H]_s [\bar{D}]_s [H]_s) dA_s$

Numerical integration is used to evaluate the cross-section rigidity matrix $[D]_c$ and $[D]_s$. Stored strain energy is calculated by (7) and distributed shear springs stiffness (k_s):

$$U' = \frac{1}{2} \int k_s s^2 dx = \frac{1}{2} \int k_s (u_c - u_s)^2 dx \quad (16)$$

C. Finite Element Formulation

First of all, the 3-nodded iso-parametric C^0 element is selected. This theory assumes 8 nodal degrees of freedom to solve the present problem using a one-dimensional finite element approximation written as:

$$\{f\} = \{u_{c0j} \ u'_{cj} \ \theta_{cj} \ \chi_j \ W_j \ u_{s0j} \ u'_s \ \theta_s\}^T \quad (17)$$

The unknown nodal displacement vector $\{d\}$ on the middle surface of a typical element is given by:

$$\{d\} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \psi_i(x, y) \cdot \{d_i\} \quad (18)$$

where ψ_i is the shape function.

The generalized strain vector as a function of the nodal displacement vector $\{d\}$ can be found by:

$$\{\epsilon\}_j = \sum_{i=1}^3 [P_i] \{d_i\} \quad (19)$$

where $[P_i]$ is the interpolation function differential operator matrix.

The strain vectors are calculated by (13), (16), and (18) as a function of the stiffness matrix $[K^l]$.

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \{d\}^T [K^l] \{d\} \quad (20)$$

where:

$$[K^l] = \int \left([P]_c^T [D]_c [P]_c + [P]_s^T [D]_s [P]_s \right) dx \quad (21)$$

Similarly, the interfacial stiffness and stiffness due to the penalty function approach are given below:

$$[K^i] = \int \left([P^i]^T k_s [P^i] \right) dx \quad (22)$$

$$[K^p] = \int \left([P^p]^T k_p [P^p] \right) dx \quad (23)$$

Now we can integrate (21), (22), and (23) and combine them to find out the element stiffness matrix $[K]$.

$$[K] = [K^l] + [K^i] + [K^p] \quad (24)$$

An element's mass matrix and its geometric stiffness matrix can be found in the same way as the element stiffness matrix is calculated above. Equations (16)-(18) are used to find out the displacement component vector at a point in the beam layer:

$$\{\bar{f}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_j \\ W \end{Bmatrix} = [F_j] \{f\} = [F_j] [X] \{d\} \quad (25)$$

where $[F_j]$ is a matrix of order 2×8 which contains the coefficient of displacement component expressed in (25) and $[X]$ is a shape function matrix of order 8×24 .

Now, the consistent mass matrix of 3-nodded elements is developed by using (25) and is expressed as:

$$[M] = \iiint [X]^T \left([F_j]^T \rho_j [F_j] dz \right) [X] dx dy \quad (26)$$

Free vibration analysis is conducted to find out the fundamental natural frequency from the given equation:

$$[K_s - \omega^2 \{M_g\}] \{\lambda\} = 0 \quad (27)$$

where ω is the vibration frequency and $\{\lambda\}$ the eigenvector.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A finite element technique based on the cubic order beam theory was used to examine steel-concrete beam features to assess the effectiveness of the recommended model. The findings are produced by implementing the proposed model in FORTRAN code.

A. Comparison Study

For the validation of the results, a two-layered simple support composite beam having a T-cross section is considered. The four different Boundary Conditions (BCs) SS, SC, CC, and CF (SS = Simply Supported, C = Clamped, F = Free) and the partial interaction of the composite beams were taken into consideration. The results used for validation are taken [14], in which the state-step approach is used to tackle this issue. In this example, the cross-sectional size and material characteristics of a two-layered composite beam are stated as: span length (L) of beam equal to 4m, the upper and lower elements are 0.05x0.30m² and 0.15x0.05m², respectively, the modulus of elasticity of the upper (E₁) and lower elements (E₂) are 12Gpa and 8Gpa, respectively, the modulus of rigidity of the upper (G₁) and lower element (G₂) are 5GPa and 3GPa, respectively, and the mass densities of the upper and lower elements are taken as ρ₁ = 2400Kg/m³ and ρ₂ = 500Kg/m³, respectively, using partial interfacial spring stiffness k_s = 50MPa.

The free vibration frequencies (rad/s) for various BCs are listed in Table I. Fifty elements throughout the length of the beam are used to determine the present findings. The natural frequency of a Simply Supported (SS) beam determined in [14] and using the state-space technique is contrasted with the present results. The error percentages are also listed in parentheses. In the present simulation, the results are quite accurate and in close agreement with those in [14] with an accuracy of 99.76%.

TABLE I. VALIDATION OF THE FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY OF A COMPOSITE BEAM (E₀=E₁=0).

S.No.	BC	Fundamental frequency (rad/s)	
		Present	[14]
1.	CF	25.06	25.12 (0.24)
2.	SS	64.56	64.85 (0.45)
3.	SC	88.78	89.56 (0.88)
4.	CC	116.66	118.50 (1.58)

Note: Parameters in parentheses represent percentage errors.

B. Steel-Concrete Porous Beam

In the present study, steel-concrete two-material composite beams with different porosity, BCs, and different interfacial shear stiffness values are taken for analysis. The beam's cross-section (Figure 2) is made up of a rectangular slab with a thickness and width of 0.15m and 2.25m respectively, an I-shaped steel joist with a flange dimension of 0.1780x0.13m, and a web dimension of 0.380x0.078m. The material properties of the two layers are as follows: beam span L = 15m, the modulus of elasticity E_C and the modulus of rigidity G_C of the upper (concrete) element are 13.55GPa and 6.775GPa, respectively, and the modulus of elasticity E_S and the modulus of rigidity G_S of the lower (steel joist) element are 200GPa and 100GPa, respectively. The maximum densities of the concrete

element and the steel layer are taken as ρ_C = 2396.45Kg/m³ and ρ_S = 7948.89Kg/m³, respectively, and the uniform porosity distribution of the concrete and steel element is taken as 0, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20, 0.30, and 0.4. In the case of partial interaction, it is assumed that the interfacial shear spring stiffness k_s is 100MPa. A moving point load of magnitude 100KN is applied. The point load is traveling from the left support to the right support at a constant speed v₀ of 16.67m/s.

Fig. 2. Cross section of the steel-concrete porous flanged composite beam.

C. Effect of Boundary Conditions, Porosity, and Interlayer Spring Stiffness on Fundamental Frequency

In both cases, the fundamental frequency of a SS steel-concrete porous beam with partial or complete shear interface varies with the porosity as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Variations of fundamental frequency as a function of (a) porosity of the steel element and (b) porosity of concrete and steel elements.

It decreases with an increase in the porosity of the concrete slab and steel joist. The fundamental frequency of the steel-concrete porous beam is greater with a complete shear interface than with a partial shear interface. Table II describes the effect of the porosity of steel ($e_j=0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, \text{ and } 0.4$) and BCs on the fundamental frequency of complete and partial interface steel-concrete porous beams without considering the damping effect. It is maximum for the CC (clamped, clamped) and minimum for the CF (clamped, free) BC. Table III shows

the effect of steel and concrete layer porosity variations on the fundamental frequency ($e_o=e_j=0, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, \text{ and } 0.4$). The different boundary conditions are considered. Table IV analyzes the impact of the interfacial shear stiffness (k_s) on the fundamental frequency. Porosity variation is taken into account in this scenario. Fundamental frequencies increase as interfacial shear stiffness increases, as can be easily seen. The fundamental frequency of a steel-concrete porous simply supported beam is expected to change with its porosity.

TABLE II. FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY OF POROUS BEAM FOR DIFFERENT POROSITY (e_j) AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Porosity (e_j)	Fundamental frequency(rad/s)							
	Partial composite				Full composite			
	CF	SS	SC	CC	CF	SS	SC	CC
0.00	5.9217	15.5493	22.0437	29.6486	6.2464	17.4810	27.0829	38.8882
0.05	5.8527	15.3843	21.8207	29.3481	6.1676	17.2605	26.7407	38.3962
0.10	5.7815	15.2140	21.5914	29.0400	6.0863	17.0332	26.3879	37.8891
0.20	5.6318	14.8553	21.1112	28.3985	5.9155	16.5555	25.6468	36.8240
0.30	5.4703	14.4680	20.5966	27.7164	5.7320	16.0420	24.8503	35.6798
0.40	5.2944	14.0451	20.0388	26.9833	5.5327	15.4845	23.9859	34.4384

TABLE III. FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY OF POROUS BEAM FOR e_o, e_j , AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Porosity		Fundamental frequency(rad/s)							
e_o	e_j	Partial composite			Full composite				
		CF	SS	SC	CC	CF	SS	SC	CC
0.00	0.00	5.9217	15.5493	22.0437	29.6486	6.2464	17.4810	27.0829	38.8882
0.05	0.05	5.8354	15.3453	21.7723	29.2861	6.1470	17.2027	26.6518	38.2691
0.10	0.10	5.7489	15.1407	21.5010	28.9246	6.0473	16.9239	26.2198	37.6488
0.20	0.20	5.5744	14.7276	20.9562	28.2019	5.8467	16.3625	25.3501	36.4000
0.30	0.30	5.3964	14.3058	20.4039	27.4742	5.6429	15.7920	24.4661	35.1307
0.40	0.40	5.2130	13.8700	19.8374	26.7337	5.4335	15.2062	23.5586	33.8276

TABLE IV. FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY OF POROUS SS COMPOSITE BEAM FOR DIFFERENT POROSITY e_o, e_j , AND INTERFACIAL STIFFNESS (k_s)

Porosity		Fundamental frequency(rad/s)							
e_o	e_j	$k_s=10^{-2}$	$k_s=10^{-1}$	$k_s=10^0$	$k_s=10$	$k_s=10^2$	$k_s=500$	$k_s=10^3$	$k_s=10^4$
		0.00	0.00	10.6498	10.6660	10.8244	12.0652	15.5493	16.9769
0.05	0.05	10.4803	10.4968	10.6577	11.9090	15.3453	16.7213	16.9527	17.1768
0.10	0.10	10.3105	10.3273	10.4909	11.7535	15.1407	16.4649	16.6858	16.8993
0.20	0.20	09.9686	09.9861	10.1557	11.4437	14.7276	15.9478	16.1479	16.3404
0.30	0.30	09.6212	09.6395	09.8164	11.1336	14.3058	15.4207	15.6003	15.7722
0.40	0.40	09.2644	09.2837	09.4695	10.8208	14.8700	14.8777	15.0371	15.1888

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, one-dimensional finite element methods based on cubic order beam theory are used to analyze the free vibration of pervious steel-concrete beams. The distribution of linear shear springs is used to simulate partial shear interaction between layers. The cubic order beam theory is implemented using a continuous C^0 finite element containing 3 nodes. This work presents a novel analysis of the effect of porosity on the fundamental frequency of layered composite beams. The main findings of this study are:

- As the porosity of the steel-concrete composite beam increases from 0 to 0.40, the fundamental frequency decreases by 10% in partial interaction and approximately 13.0% in the complete composite.
- The presented finite element formulation shows the relationship between the fundamental frequency and

various parameters such as the interfacial shear stiffness and end supports.

- In CF support, the fundamental frequency is minimum, whereas it is maximum in CC support.
- It is greater for a complete shear interface than for a partial shear interface. An increase in interfacial shear stiffness from 10^{-2} to 10^4 leads to an increase in fundamental frequency by more than 63%.
- The proposed model is more accurate in predicting the free vibration of composite steel-concrete porous beams than the existing models based on EBT and TBT.

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Sentiment Classification based on Machine Learning Approaches in Amazon Product Reviews

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ABSTRACT

Online retailers and merchants increasingly request feedback from their clients on the products they purchase. This has led to a significant increase in the number of product reviews posted online, as more people are making purchases online. The opinions expressed in these customer reviews have a significant impact on other customers' purchase decisions, as they are influenced by other customers' recommendations or complaints. This study used Amazon, a well-known and widely used e-commerce platform, to examine sentiment categorization using several machine learning techniques while analyzing an Amazon Reviews dataset. At first, the reviews were transformed into vector representations using the Bag-of-Words approach. Word cloud was used to illustrate the text data in terms of the frequency they appear in the review. Subsequently, the machine learning methods decision trees and logistic regression were used. The two models used in this study achieved high levels of accuracy in analyzing the dataset. Specifically, the Decision Tree model outperformed the Logistic Regression one, achieving an impressive accuracy of 99% compared to the 94% of the latter.

Keywords-sentiment analysis; Amazon customer reviews; dataset; feature extraction; text classification; machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades online marketplaces have grown in popularity, leading to the trend of asking customers for feedback on purchased products to improve the overall customer experience. Every day, millions of reviews about different goods, services, and locations are created online. As a result, the Internet has become the key resource for knowledge and opinions regarding products and services. However, the vast amount of product reviews and the multiple perspectives to consider may further complicate the decision-making process, leading to confusion and uncertainty, as it is difficult for customers to choose wisely when there are several viewpoints on the same product and different ratings. Therefore, e-commerce businesses should evaluate this content to get feedback on their products and help customers decide.

Sentiment analysis and classification is a field of computer science that attempts to answer this problem by sifting through given natural language texts to extract attitudes and views, using numerous approaches, such as biometrics, computational linguistics, natural language processing, and text analysis. Due to their accuracy and effectiveness, Machine Learning (ML) approaches have lately grown in favor of the semantic and review analysis fields. This study considered Amazon as one of the most popular e-commerce vendors. Potential customers may read hundreds of reviews posted by previous customers regarding the products they're interested in [1-2]. These reviews provide valuable information on a product, helping shoppers understand most of its features. Customers benefit from this, but it also helps retailers or producers to get a greater knowledge of customers' needs.

This study used supervised algorithms to address the problem of sentiment classification for online reviews and

determine the overall significance of customer evaluations and characterize them as positive or negative. The data used were reviews of Amazon Titan Men Watches, collected from amazon.in. The study employed supervised algorithms to address the issue of sentiment classification for online reviews. The goal was to determine the overall importance of customer evaluations by categorizing them as either positive or negative.

II. RELATED WORKS

Many studies used data collected from numerous sources, such as Twitter [3-4], product reviews, consumer feedback, etc. Customer engagement programs help businesses to strengthen their emotional relationships with clients from all over the world. Customer involvement is also influenced by product reviews [5]. The study of product reviews allows a company to learn how customers feel about its products. According to [6], online consumer reviews have an important influence in molding customers' online shopping decisions. The term "review" refers to the process of determining whether a product or service is suitable for a certain purpose. Every day, a massive quantity of fresh information is added to the Web [7], hence a method was proposed based on simultaneous web crawling using mobile agents.

Sentiment analysis is used by businesses to increase their competitiveness in the market, as it enables them to comprehend the opinions and experiences of their clients on their products and services [8]. Sentiment analysis is also used to capture market sentiments to design a better forecasting model for the stock market [9]. Modern organizations use sentiment analysis to improve their word-of-mouth marketing approach. Competitive companies use text-mining tools to better understand client experiences and extract valuable information from social networking platforms, newspapers, and other sources. In [10], k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Decision Trees (DT), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models were used to identify client behavior in the banking industry. As a result, a mix of sentiment analysis, text mining, and other methods is critical in ensuring that businesses understand and capitalize on online consumer evaluations. Sentiment extraction is an excellent method of understanding customer assumptions online [11], as the data collected from internet platforms and product review sites allow businesses to improve their marketing methods. Product reviews also influence client purchase decisions. Competitive organizations, such as Amazon, use such information to make decisions [12], and leading merchants in the United States rely on Internet product reviews to improve their marketing efforts and company procedures [13]. For example, if a given product receives a large number of unfavorable reviews for its cost or quality, the company examines the problem and tries to address it as soon as possible.

According to [6], most of the product evaluations on the Internet are less polar and more positively balanced. Also, the distribution of product reviews for similar items differs by platform [14]. The diversity of reviews is driven by several factors, including the rating system, the business strategy of the online platform, and the review frequency [6]. In [15], a Web Crawling Model based on Java Applets was presented. Furthermore, it is important to mention that firms use sentiment

analysis to improve company operations and client retention, as analyzing product evaluations allows a company to understand client experiences [16]. A client can leave a review to indicate whether he is happy or unhappy with a particular product or service. However, the majority of product reviews do not represent the level of client happiness. In [16], a study was conducted based on reviews on the Internet to classify consumer happiness, according to auditory and language characteristics, into four classes: extremely positive, positive, neutral, or highly unfavorable. The findings of this study on the impact of review length on online sentiments were consistent with [17]. Customers prefer to rely on comprehensive and insightful product reviews before making a final purchase [18]. As a result, companies must discover the true degree of customer satisfaction with their products and services in order to make an informed decision based on online product reviews.

Authors in [19] evaluated the way internet reviews influence Amazon book sales. According to this study, customers view online reviews as a reliable source of information and prefer more accessible and detailed reviews. According to this study, internet reviews have a major impact on user experiences and product costs. These findings were in agreement with those of [20] on online reviews and feelings. The study also looked at the valence of internet reviews. In [19], the influence of online reviews on purchases was found to be contradictory. Some studies concluded that the valence of online reviews has a major influence on sales, while others found that it has no impact. The impact is also affected by variables such as product categories and qualitative text qualities. In [21], an analysis was conducted on 142.8 million Amazon user reviews, focusing on determining the usefulness and unhelpfulness of each review by examining the summary headline, the product remark, and helpfulness information, filtering out blank and non-English product evaluations to improve the accuracy of the results, and choosing only those with the most votes. The study concluded that an investigation of online product evaluations on Amazon plays an important part in today's e-commerce. Helpful reviews provide thorough information on specific products or services based on client feedback [22]. Customers rely on reviews with the most votes to make a purchase decision. The results are congruent with the findings of [23] on how customer reviews impact internet purchases. Positive product reviews enable clients to build greater trust in the things they want to buy online.

Sentiment analysis has gaps due to issues with the accuracy and reliability of the utilized methods, as well as the lack of standardization in sentiment interpretation and classification. More research is needed to optimize customer engagement programs and improve the understanding of customer sentiments. This study aims to address the potential gaps in the sentiment analysis based on Machine Learning Approaches in Amazon Product Reviews using Decision Trees and Regression models. Specifically, this study investigated the effectiveness of different customer engagement strategies in influencing customer sentiments and explored the impact of these strategies on sentiment classification accuracy.

III. METHODOLOGY

Sentiment analysis is considered a study of people's sentiments, feelings, and views as conveyed via writing, and is useful in understanding other peoples' points of view on any subject. Opinions can be positive, negative, or neutral. The suggested method was based on an ML prediction model, to analyze both positive and negative reviews by binary classification. Figure 1 shows the steps of this method, beginning with data collection and ending with the evaluation of each classification model.

Fig. 1. Overall sentiment analysis approach for Amazon reviews.

A. Programming Environment

Python is one of the most used programming languages in data science and ML, as it offers a large library collection for solving various ML problems. Python was chosen due to its extensive libraries and ease of use. Scikit-learn is a Python package that provides supervised ML algorithms [24], including many classification algorithms, such as SVM and Naive Bayes, and feature extraction techniques.

B. The Dataset

Figure 2 presents an example of an Amazon review to better grasp the dataset's structure and format. An Amazon user review consists of the following four key components that assist in comprehending and analyzing the reviews:

- Summary: The title of the review.
- Review text: The review's actual content.
- Rating: The product's user rating on a scale of 1 to 5.
- Helpfulness: The percentage of persons who considered the review beneficial.

Fig. 2. Actual Amazon customer review sample.

Data collection was the initial stage of the study. Raw data were obtained from the website amazon.in and converted to Comma Separated Values (CSV) format. The data set contained 4960 Titan Men Watches reviews.

C. Data Cleaning

This is a critical stage in examining any type of data and has a significant influence on the success of ML models. There are numerous types of pre-processing procedures and the appropriate ways must be selected. This study employed four distinct data preparation steps in the reviews:

1. Remove Emojis.
2. Remove HTML tags.
3. Lowercase all letters.
4. Filter numbers and special characters.

1) Emoji Removal

Although people use emojis to express their feelings, they were removed since they did not affect the identification of the polarity of the review.

2) HTML Tag Removal

The HTML tags of the retrieved reviews were removed because they did not affect the determination of the polarity of the review.

3) Converting all Letters to Lowercase

In different reviews, there is a good chance that identical words will appear in different situations and the system will recognize them as distinct words. Converting all letters to lowercase was used to avoid such problems.

4) Filtering Numbers and Special Characters

All the unnecessary elements in determining the review's polarity were eliminated to make the data tidy and clean. The special letters and digits were eliminated.

D. Feature Extraction

ML algorithms interpret data in specified formats. The text data were turned into numerical feature vectors, a process known as vectorization. Bag of Words is one such approach that involves tokenization, normalization, and counting. This study used CountVectorizer to represent words in terms of Bag of Words. CountVectorizer requires specifying an N-gram range, which is a tuple consisting of the lowest and maximum length of the sequence of words to be regarded as features.

E. Word Cloud of Reviews

The word cloud is a method of displaying text data where each word's size corresponds to its frequency or importance. A word cloud can be used to highlight significant textual information, and they are widely used in social network data analysis. This study used word clouds to represent the most often-used terms in reviews.

IV. EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) is a method of displaying and evaluating data concealed in rows and columns, using several charts to provide maximum insight into the dataset. This study investigated the Positive, Negative, and Neutral review categories of Amazon reviews based on the sentiment score. Figure 3 shows the Amazon product review categories. This study scrapped 4960 reviews of a specific product and stored them, after cleaning, in a CSV file.

Fig. 3. Distribution of reviews' categories.

The text data were presented graphically using Python's Word Cloud package. Figures 4-6 show the most common words used in reviews, as positive reviews, and as negative reviews, respectively.

Fig. 4. Most common words used in the reviews.

Fig. 5. Most common words used in positive reviews

Fig. 6. Most common words in negative reviews.

A. Unigrams

Unigrams determine the frequency of single words in the reviews. Figures 7-8 show the unigrams of the top 20 positive and negative reviews, respectively.

B. Bigrams

Unigrams do not offer a clear understanding of a consumer's intended message. Bigrams can capture the meaning behind consecutive pairs of words in the reviews. Combining two adjacent words into a single unit can offer valuable insight into the context and meaning of a text. Bigrams show the frequency of two-word combinations in a text review. For instance, in the sentence "I love this product", the bigram "love this" would be generated, while "I hate this product" would produce the bigram "hate this". Analyzing the most prevalent bigrams in a collection of reviews can help to understand what consumers are attempting to convey regarding their encounter with a product or service.

Fig. 7. Top 20 positive review unigram.

Fig. 8. Top 20 negative review unigram.

Fig. 9. Top 40 positive and negative review bigrams.

Figure 9 shows the top 40 positive and negative review bigrams. The bar plot shows that the most common bigrams in positive reviews were "value for money", "lovely watch", "good product", etc. These bigrams suggest that customers were satisfied with the quality and value of the product they purchased. In contrast, the most commonly used bigrams in negative reviews were "media could", "could not", "titan watch", etc., implying that consumers experienced problems with the product, such as difficulty with media playback or loading times. Overall, bigrams are a useful tool in natural language processing and sentiment analysis, providing valuable insight into the opinions and experiences of consumers. By identifying and analyzing the most common bigrams in a set of reviews, a better understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of a product or service can be gained. This information can then be used to make more informed decisions.

V. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This study used Python and Jupyter, in conjunction with supporting libraries, to perform data purification, visualization, pre-processing, and ML modeling. Supervised ML was used to create sentiment classification models, by building training and testing sets. A collection of features was then taken from the training and testing data and supplied into a classifier model, such as Logistic Regression (LR) and Decision Tree (DT). The complete review dataset was separated into two parts: 75% of the data was used to train the models, while 25% was used to assess their performance. The performance of the models was validated using accuracy and confusion matrix.

A. Accuracy (A)

Accuracy (A) is defined as the proportion of correctly predicted occurrences to the total number of occurrences by:

$$A = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

where TP stands for True Positive, TN for True Negative, FP for False Positive, and FN for False Negative. Table I shows the accuracy results of the models used in this study.

TABLE I. ACCURACY OF MODELS

Model	Accuracy
Logistic Regression	94%
Decision Tree	99%

The results show that both Logistic Regression and Decision Tree were effective. However, the two models had different levels of accuracy, as DT achieved 99% outperforming LR, which achieved 94%, as shown in Table I and Figure 10. This could be attributed to DT's ability to handle complex decision-making processes that may not be captured by LR. The difference in accuracy between the two models is significant, and it may impact the model selection decision depending on the importance of the classification task. For example, in a high-stakes classification task, such as in medical diagnosis, the higher accuracy of DTs could be crucial to make accurate and reliable predictions.

Fig. 10. Accuracy comparison for the methods used.

B. Confusion Matrix

It is worth noting that the Accuracy values reported are not the only performance metrics to consider when evaluating the models. Other metrics such as Precision, Recall, and F1-score can provide a more nuanced view of the models' performance and should be considered alongside Accuracy. They can be used to assess the performance of the categorization methods. These parameters are important for measuring the efficacy of supervised ML algorithms since they are based on the confusion matrix [25]. A confusion matrix is widely used to visualize an algorithm's performance. Classification terms TP, TN, FN, and FP are used to compare class labels in this matrix, as shown in Table II and Figure 11. Based on the data of the confusion matrix, Precision, Recall, F-measure, and Accuracy can be used to evaluate the performance of the classifier.

TABLE II. CONFUSION MATRIX

A \ V	P V	Predicted-Negative	Predicted-Positive
	Actual Negative		TN
Actual Positive		FN	TP

Fig. 11. The confusion Matrix of the LR model.

VI. CONCLUSION

Sentiment analysis is a necessary and popular technique for collecting information from text data on e-commerce websites. E-commerce platforms produce enormous volumes of text data every day in the form of suggestions, reviews, tweets, and comments. Additionally, emoticons, ratings, and reviews all suggest people's opinions. A customer can learn more about a product and make an informed choice by extrapolating information from reviews. This study used multiclass and binary classification for Amazon reviews of a product using supervised machine learning methods such as Logistic Regression and Decision Tree. Logistic Regression produced an excellent outcome with 94% accuracy and Decision Tree produced outstanding results with 99% accuracy. E-commerce websites should consider various feature extraction methods and machine learning techniques, examine additional product categories, analyze unstructured data, and incorporate sentiment analysis into customer experience strategies to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty.

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A Machine Learning Model for detecting Covid-19 Misinformation in Swahili Language

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ABSTRACT

The recorded cases of corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic disease are millions and its mortality rate was maximized during the period from April 2020 to January 2022. Misinformation arose regarding this threat, which spread through social media platforms, and especially Twitter, often spreading confusion, social turmoil, and panic to the public. To identify such misinformation, a machine learning model is needed to detect whether the given information is true (true information) or not (misinformation). The aim of this paper is to present a machine-learning model for detecting COVID-19 misinformation in the Swahili language in tweets. The five machine learning algorithms that were trained for detecting Swahili language misinformation related to COVID-19 are Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Bagging Ensemble (BE), Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB), and Random Forest (RF). The study used the qualitative research method because non-numerical data, i.e. text, were used. Python programming language was used for data analysis due to its powerful libraries such as pandas and numpy. Four metrics were used to evaluate the model performance. The results revealed that SVM achieved the highest accuracy of 83.67% followed by LR with 82.47%. MNB achieved the best precision of 92.00% and in terms of recall and F1-score, RF, and SVM achieved the best results with 84.82% and 81.45%, respectively. This study will enable the public to easily identify Swahili language misinformation related to COVID-19 that is circulated on Twitter social media platform.

Keywords-COVID-19 pandemic; misinformation; machine learning; Twitter; Swahili language

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media platforms such as Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, and TikTok are exceptional sources of information. They are strong tools of communication due to their accessibility, speed, and affordability [1]. These platforms are interactive communication tools and they enable smooth sharing of information, views, and thoughts. They also facilitate sharing of knowledge and experiences. They are unavoidable in our contemporary lives [2]. They gained popularity during the pandemic due to the social isolation and quarantine [3]. In spite of their advantages, social media platforms have been intentionally and unintentionally used for spreading misinformation regarding the COVID-19 pandemic

[4-6]. Misinformation regarding COVID-19 can harm people and lead them into wrong directions [4]. Approximately 90% of misinformation still remain online [7]. Several studies have been conducted to provide solutions for misinformation detection related to COVID-19. However, no machine learning model has been developed for COVID-19 misinformation detection in Swahili language despite the fact that Swahili is an East African language widely used in Twitter and other platforms. Furthermore, no Swahili language datasets have been presented for detecting COVID-19 misinformation. This study was conducted to address this gap.

Since 2019, several studies were conducted to overcome the challenge of misinformation related to COVID-19. For

instance, the authors in [10] presented a dataset in Luganda-English mixed code for detecting misinformation related to pandemic from social media. Several machine learning classifiers were applied including Discriminative Multinomial Naïve Bayes (DMNB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Bagging Ensemble (BE). The study revealed that DMNB outperformed the other classifiers with an accuracy of 78.19% and an F1-score of 77.90%. However, the study presented the model for detecting COVID-19 misinformation in Luganda-English code-mixed. Similarly, authors in [11] addressed the challenge by developing a machine learning model for detecting misinformation regarding the corona virus disease by relying on the information from UN, WHO, and UNICEF. Ten algorithms were employed, and Decision Tree (DT), Logistic Regression (LR), and Neural Networks (NNs) achieved the best results. However, the developed model was limited to misinformation in English language. Likewise, the authors in [9] conducted a study to address the same challenge of misinformation from Twitter. A large Arabic dataset was constructed. Eight traditional and deep learning classifiers were applied along with features such as word embedding and word frequencies. The best accuracy results were achieved by the Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) classifier. The constructed dataset was limited to Arabic content.

Authors in [2] conducted a similar study and three different misinformation detection models were proposed, including LSTM, KNN, and Multichannel CNN. The proposed models were found to achieve promising results. The model was focused on detecting misinformation in English from Twitter. Authors in [12] presented a simple Natural Language Processing (NLP) methodology for detecting misinformation related to the pandemic from YouTube. State-of-the-art pre-trained transfer learning methods such as BERT base, RoBERTa base, and XLNet base were employed. The highest accuracy achieved was 89.4%. Authors in [13] proposed a simple approach that used BERT embedding and Shallow Neural Networks (SNNs) for detecting misinformation related to COVID-19 where the BERT embedding transformer was found to perform better than SNNs. The presented approach was limited to misinformation in English language. Authors in [15] conducted a similar study using fuzzy clustering with deep learning models, focused on misinformation related to pandemic in English and Chinese. Authors in [14] conducted a study for detecting fake news related to COVID-19 using feature extraction methods. Several algorithms including Random Forest (RF), AdaBoost, KNN, and DT were applied. The highest accuracy achieved was 83.50% by RF. The dataset used had approximately 1,100 records and Swahili tweets were not part of it. Authors in [3] presented two misinformation datasets related to COVID-19 on Twitter and the system known as Checkvoid was developed based on machine learning and NLP technique for automatic detection of misinformation related to COVID-19. This study was focused on English language.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The developed model follows several steps starting with collecting tweets using snsrape and ending with the evaluation of the performance of the model. Figure 1 shows a conceptual

framework of this study that depicts all the employed steps. Jupyter notebook was used for writing the code in Python.

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the current study.

A. Data Collection

Data were collected from Twitter using snsrape. About 19,903 tweets were scraped from December 01, 2019 to January 31, 2022 based on common Swahili hashtags related to the pandemic including #covid-19, #uviko19, #chanjo_korona, #barakoa_inaokoa, #ujanjakuchanja, and #homa_kaliyamapafu and #korona_Tanzania.

B. Data Cleaning and Preprocessing

Data cleaning was conducted to remove duplicates, noise data, and data that were written in other language rather than Swahili. Data preprocessing was conducted to remove URLs, hashtags, white spaces, punctuation marks, and other special characters such as & and %. After annotation and labelling, 682 tweets equivalent to 54.47% were found to be true information and 570 tweets equivalent to 45.53% were found to be misinformation. Figure 2 and Table I shows a sample snapshot and the statistics of the dataset used in this study respectively.

```
df.head()
```

	num	tweet	label
818	0	chanjo ya uviko19 inakuweka kwenye hatari ya k...	Misinformation
37	0	CCM mkikutana na kukusanya watu korona inakimbia	Misinformation
633	1	Kila mmoja wetu anapaswa kuchukua tahadhari dh...	True information
552	1	Watu 102.093 wameripotiwa kufariki kutokana na...	True information
1020	0	Hakuna ugonjwa mbaya zaidi kwa sasa hapa dunia...	Misinformation

Fig. 2. Sample of the dataset.

TABLE I. DATASET STATISTICS

Data	True information	Misinformation	Total
Number	682	570	1,252
%	54.47	45.53	100

C. Data Visualization

Various tools and methods can be used for visualizing data. This study used the word cloud method. Figures 3 and 4 show the word clouds for true information and misinformation respectively.

In (5)-(8), TP stands for true positive, TN for true negative, FP for false positive, and FN for false negative.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

The results presented in Figure 5 show that the SVM achieved the highest accuracy of 83.67% followed by LR with accuracy of 82.47%. MNB and RF obtained the same accuracy of 80.48% while the BE had the lowest accuracy of 76.01%. As for precision measure, MNB achieved the best results of 92.00%. In terms of recall and F1-score, RF and SVM achieved the best results with 84.82% and 81.45%, respectively.

Fig. 5. Evaluation.

B. Discussion

The dataset used in this study contains only 1,252 data entries. LR and SVM were found to perform much better in predicting COVID-19 misinformation in Swahili language. LR was then chosen as the final algorithm to be considered.

IV. CONCLUSION

The threat of the COVID-19 pandemic resulted to the generation of a huge amount of information related to it on social media platforms such as Twitter. Some of these information are true and constructive while some are misinformation and have negative consequences to the public [6]. Several studies have been conducted to address the challenge of misinformation circulating on twitter and other social platforms, however, most of those studies have focused on languages other than Swahili [2, 9-13]. This study was conducted to fill this gap.

This study also presented a well labelled Swahili language misinformation detection dataset which will be used as a starting point by practitioners and researchers for further research regarding the COVID-19 pandemic. This study was limited to the Twitter social media platform. Future research can be extended to other social media platforms as well, such as Facebook, Instagram, and Whatsapp.

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Solar-Powered Solutions for the Water and Energy Shortage Problem: The Case Study of Nahr El Bared, Lebanon

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ABSTRACT

Solar power is an effective way to reduce the dependency on conventional fuels and mitigate the water and energy shortage issue. The main aim of the current paper is to assess and compare the techno-economic feasibility of rooftop grid-connected photovoltaic energy systems for generating electricity and generating drinkable water in Nahr El Bared, Lebanon. To this aim, the present paper first reviews previous scientific studies associated with the water resources and energy situation to summarize the current status in Lebanon. According to this review, Lebanon's water resources are highly polluted, domestic and industrial sewage is largely untreated, and intolerable agricultural practices further exacerbate the situation. Furthermore, population and economic growth and the continuous utilization of old power plants have led to an increase in the number of hours of power outages in the country. Accordingly, the proposed project aims to evaluate the viability of using solar energy as an alternative solution to the shortage of water and energy in the country. Secondly, the techno-economic performance of the proposed system in the selected region was evaluated based on the variations in financial parameters using RETScreen Experts software. The results demonstrate that 11770–13451kWh/yr could be generated from the solar system, which can help reduce the energy shortage and generate drinkable water. Furthermore, the investment was found to be economically viable and attractive for investors. This paper concludes that solar energy can be able to solve the energy shortage of electricity, reduce the country's electricity costs, and produce freshwater for drinking and domestic use in the country.

Keywords-Lebanon; solar energy potential; grid-connected; small-scale; RETScreen software

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, renewable energies, including solar and wind energy, have increased their contribution in power generation

worldwide. The use of renewable energy sources is imperative nowadays, due to the scarcity of fossil fuel resources in developing countries, specifically Lebanon. The generation of electricity from renewable energy sources will be an essential

part of Lebanon's future development. Solar energy has been widely utilized globally to generate electricity and reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. It is a clean energy, an inexhaustible and environmentally friendly energy source. Authors in [1] found that solar power will reduce the emissions of about 69-100 million tons of CO₂, 68-99 thousand tons of NO_x, and 126-184 thousand tons of SO₂ by 2030. Authors in [2] concluded that solar energy has a significant potential to meet the world's electricity requirements in the future. Authors in [3] concluded that solar energy technologies have an essential role in reducing energy-related emissions.

Photovoltaic (PV) solar panels produce electrical power directly from the sunlight. It is a considerable power source to meet the demand for electricity in developing countries [4]. Additionally, it is utilized as an alternative source to meet the energy required for desalination plants [5]. In general, PV power systems are classified into two types (on-grid and off-grid PV systems). The on-grid PV system significantly reduces costs by eliminating the need for battery storage [6]. Also, it helps reduce the consumption of fossil fuels in the country. Additionally, the small-scale grid-connected PV system can help customers earn money using their grid-connected rooftop PV systems because they purchase much less electricity [7].

A. Water Resources in Lebanon

Generally, the main water resources of Lebanon are surface water (49%), which is mostly supplied by rivers (46%), surface storage water such as dams and lakes (3%), and groundwater (51%) [8]. In Lebanon, there are 40 rivers of which 16 are permanent [8, 9]. The total flow of the rivers is found to be in the range of 2151-3900 MCM/yr with most of the flow occurring from January to May [8, 9]. Three water basins alone represent approximately 44% of the country's area: the Litani (2140km²), the Orontes (1720km²), and the Hasbani (680km²). On the other hand, Lebanon has many coastal rivers that originate from Mount Lebanon and flow into the Mediterranean Sea [10]. Rivers and springs are greatly affected by the annual variation in precipitation. According to the United Nations Development Program in 2014, the annual rainfall is within the range of 7.8-11.9 billion m³ of which between 4.1 and 6.6 billion m³ is groundwater recharge. The annual rainfall is within the range of 600-1100mm in the coastal regions and rises to more than 1400mm in higher altitudes [11]. The average rainfall and the exposed geological formations with major karstic features and fractures make the stratified environment and water permeability distinctive. Renewable water is a major source of groundwater [12]. Groundwater reserves generally consist of leakages of the rainwater that result from the melting of snow [13]. The layers that prevent or semi-prevent leakage and runoff play the main role in seizing groundwater reserves and directing them inside the stores [8]. However, groundwater makes up nearly 50% of the water supply. This has affected the management of groundwater and its quality.

According to the Ministry of Energy and Water in 2014, the number of public wells extracting groundwater is about 1325 of which 943 are operational. It has also been reported that about 46% of the wells drain unspecified aquifers, 33% drain the Sannine-Maameltain aquifer, and 9% drain the Kesrouane

Jurassic aquifer [14]. The volume of water extracted from public wells is estimated at 270 MCM/yr. Moreover, the registered well number with the Ministry of Energy and Water reached 20537 in 2012. It is expected that the total number of wells is within the range of 55000-60000 distributed over the country. The volume extracted from groundwater resources through public and private wells is estimated to be about 700 MCM [14]. Moreover, water sources in Lebanon have been exposed to all kinds of pollution due to the absence of sewage networks in most of the areas, the lack of maintenance and monitoring, and not linking sewage networks to refining stations [8]. Generally, domestic sewage, solid waste, and pollution from industrial facilities, health care facilities, tourism, and quarries along with agricultural waste are considered the main sources of pollution for surface and groundwater in the country [15]. These different types of pollutants lead to water contamination such as microbiological contamination, heavy metals (copper, zinc, strontium, chromium, and nickel), or increased levels of concentration of nutrients in the surface water [8, 15]. Additionally, the coastal area is also widely affected by pollution and the discharge of untreated wastewater and solid waste [15, 16]. It has been found that the total domestic wastewater generated which is discharged into the sea through offshore flow points, is about 65%. Moreover, due to over-abstraction and anthropogenic pollution, the quality of groundwater is deteriorating [8]. Also, over-abstraction especially in the coastal regions has led to seawater intrusion, which affects the groundwater quality. Additionally, nitrate pollution is considered a major threat to groundwater resources in agricultural areas. Furthermore, by considering the karstic nature of groundwater aquifers, domestic wastewater is the main cause of bacterial pollution (mainly coliform bacteria) [17, 18].

B. The Energy Situation in Lebanon

The main electrical energy sources are fossil fuels (97%) and hydropower (3%). The total capacity of thermal plants and hydropower plants is 2368MW and 252MW, respectively. Due to the population growth and rising people living standards, the energy demand has increased. Lebanon's need for electric energy is estimated to be about 3562MW according to the Ministry of Energy and Water in 2019. Lebanon has been suffering for at least 3 decades from an escalating problem in the electricity sector. The power outage periods in all the cities of the country have increased to 6-14 hours per day. Thus, diesel generators are distributed around the country to supply the population's energy consumption demands [19-21]. With these sources, CO₂ emissions have increased over the years. Additionally, electricity generation that comes from these sources contributes about 83% of total CO₂ emissions [20, 22]. Thus, the use of renewable energy sources, such as solar energy, will reduce the GHG emissions and the dependence on fossil fuels. According to the World Bank Group (Global Solar Atlas), the specific photovoltaic power output is within the range of 3.99-5.30kWh/kWp. Moreover, Lebanon receives approximately 300h/yr of sunshine. The average sunshine hours in Lebanon range from 8h to 9h. Lebanon has high insulation on a horizontal surface ranging between 16.51MJ/m² and 20.71MJ/m². Therefore, it is essential to increase the access to electricity in the country with a particular focus on utilizing

solar resources. Authors in [23] found that the country has a great chance of utilizing solar power in order to reduce its dependency on fossil fuels. Additionally, installing a solar system in the country is technically reliable due to the high value of average daily radiation on the horizontal surface [24]

Recently, several studies have investigated the potential of utilizing renewable energy, mainly solar, in the country [24-33]. Few studies have focused on the evaluation of the solar potential in Lebanon. For instance, authors in [29] investigated the techno-economic feasibility of small-scale grid-connected rooftop solar projects with various sun-tracking systems and PV technologies. The findings demonstrated that the proposed PV system could provide enough electricity to satisfy the demand and hence reduce the nation's current electricity shortage. Authors in [25] described the utilization of a hybrid PV-diesel system to cool a tertiary building in Beirut during the summer. The results indicated that a PV-diesel system can provide 260kW of power throughout the year. Authors in [28] developed a GIS model to locate the optimal location for a solar power plant in Lebanon. The results showed that the optimum locations (Amioun, Bterram, and Kfaraakka) with an area of 2.8km² can provide 50% of the North's power needs. Authors in [31] provided the footprint and solar rooftop potential maps using deep learning-based instance segmentation. They concluded that Lebanon has a total rooftop solar capacity of about 28.1TWh/year, which is about twice the electricity needed by the country in 2019. Authors in [21] assessed the feasibility of a 100MW grid-connected PV plant in the Rayak region, Lebanon. The results showed that the amount of electricity generation from PV systems (1.47GWh) could help solve the electricity crisis in the country. Based on prior scientific research findings [24-33], the results indicated that (1) the country has a huge concentrating solar power that would be able to meet the maximum energy demand, (2) solar PV systems will have significant socio-economic benefits and assist the sustainability of solar power generation in the country, and (3) the solar power systems will employ 100% renewable energy, resulting in zero carbon emissions in the future.

C. Solar Desalination Unit

One major global problem is the increasing demand for drinking water. Seawater/brackish water desalination units are considered an alternative way to solve the problem of freshwater supply. In general, desalination is the process of purifying water and removing excess salinity and minerals from it through several processes [34, 35]. Desalination processes are categorized into two main categories: thermal processes and membrane processes. According to [36], the most widely utilized and reliable technology process is Reverse Osmosis (RO), which has also been utilized as an alternative source of clean water production [35, 36]. Generally, the desalination processes require a significant amount of energy. Therefore, renewable energy, particularly solar energy, is a viable alternative as a clean energy source to operate desalination plants and reduce fossil fuel dependency and the cost of clean water production.

Many researchers have investigated the potential of renewable energy in terms of wind and solar energy. For

instance, authors in [37] utilized wind energy potential as an energy source for an RO desalination plant in Spain. Authors in [38] evaluated the feasibility of solar energy projects to supply the required power for seawater desalination in Algeria. Moreover, several studies investigated the feasibility of grid-connected solar plants as an energy source for desalination plants [35, 38-41]. Authors in [35] investigated the economic viability of small-scale grid-connected PV systems with various sun-tracking systems as clean energy for brackish water desalination units in Northern Cyprus. The grid-connected PV system was used as a power source for a 2500m³/d saltwater RO desalination plant [38]. Authors in [39] analyzed grid-connected PV/Wind projects as power sources for RO and multiple-effect distillation plants. Authors in [40] proposed a new strategy for grid-connected seawater reverse osmosis focused on energy cost reduction. Authors in [41] evaluated the potential of solar energy and designed a solar-powered seawater RO desalination plant for Gaza Strip.

D. Research Objectives

Lebanon is facing an energy deficiency and some of its regions are still not electrified, particularly in rural areas. The energy supply and demand are very large. Besides, the poor economy does not allow importing fossil fuels on a large scale. Consequently, the potential of renewable energy resources can be utilized to electrify off-grid areas, specifically rural areas, or on-grid in urban locations for reducing the consumption of fossil fuels and environmental pollution. Lebanon is known to have a good potential for solar energy and the potential of solar energy for solving the electricity and water crisis in the country has been evaluated in a few studies. Thus, there is no doubt that a comprehensive economic and environmental study must be conducted to obtain results that can serve as a roadmap for investing in solar energy in the country. Besides, it has been indicated that grid-connected solar power systems are an alternative solution for the electricity crisis, one that reduces carbon emissions and mitigates power shortage. Consequently, it can be concluded that the small-scale solar systems in the country can not only bridge the energy gap but also reduce the environmental pollution impact.

The current research is a first attempt to examine the viability of small-scale solar energy systems in Lebanon from a strategic viewpoint to address the country's electricity shortage and generate freshwater for household consumption. This paper presents a methodology to accurately evaluate the techno-economic and environmental sustainability of rooftop PV systems in Nahr El Bared, Lebanon. A typical household was selected for this region to create a load profile according to the monthly electricity bills and reduce the groundwater salinity using RO desalination. The techno-economic feasibilities for the rooftop solar systems at the selected location were developed for various policy scenarios using the RETScreen Experts software.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area

Nahr El-Bared is located in the northern part of Lebanon with a population of about 30000. The mean maximum and

minimum elevations are 27m and 12m above sea level, respectively. Nahr El-Bared camp is separated into two camps: the old camp (78m² average apartment area and 360000m² total built residential area) and the new camp (150m² average household area and 300000m² total constructed household area). Nahr El-Bared is facing a water crisis due to the shortage of electricity and seawater intrusion. According to the institute for Palestinian studies, about 60% of drinking water is salty in most regions in the selected area. Moreover, the large number of private wells, which are located along the coastline, is a major cause of seawater intrusion according to the Institute for Palestinian studies. Recently, the level of salinity has increased to 90% of the public and private wells extracting groundwater, which forced the residents to buy freshwater from internal refineries' water trucks to fill the water storage tanks. This has given rise to serious problems due to the cost of water from these sources (the price of 1m³ varies from 2 USD to 4 USD, which depends on the locations in the region) and the shortage of electricity. Moreover, power outages in the selected location are considered one of the most difficult situations by the residents, as the hours of feeding from the electricity company do not exceed 3 to 4 per day

B. On-grid Photovoltaic System

Grid-connected PV systems consist of PV panels that supply the required power during the day and are connected to the local electrical grid to generate power at night. Moreover, the excess power from the PV system is fed back to the grid when the power generated is more than the load required [42]. In general, the grid-connected PV system consists of solar panels, inverters, a power-conditioning unit, and grid-connection equipment. To get more power from the PV arrays, the PV panels should have high cell efficiency and a high operating temperature. Generally, the inverter is one of the most important components of a grid-connected system because it converts direct current (DC) to alternating current (AC). In addition, electricity meters are utilized to read the flow of electricity to and from the grid.

Recently, on-grid PV systems have attracted substantial attention due to the advantages of their compatibility with the electricity grid. In this system, the output power of the PV system is connected directly to the grid and the household. The electric energy produced by the PV system can cover the energy demand of the household. When the produced energy by the PV system is high, the remaining energy can be fed into the grid through an electric meter. This system comprises PV panels, which absorb sunlight and produce direct current, an inverter, a distribution controller, and load as shown in Figure 1. Generally, it is necessary to estimate the optimal sizing of grid-connected PV systems as the first step to meet the energy demand of the household.

According to [43], the amount of output energy by the PV system (E_{PV}) should be greater than the amount of electricity taken from the grid (E_{grid}) as shown in (1). In this case, the energy demand of the household can be shared between the PV system and the electric grid. The generated energy from the PV system is utilized to cover the household/building instantaneous electricity load and the surplus energy is injected into the grid.

$$E_{PV} > E_{grid} \quad (1)$$

The maximum power (P_{max}) of the developed on-grid solar PV system can be estimated as a function of global solar radiation (G_{sr}) in kWh/m²/d, solar radiation at standard test conditions (P_i) in kW/m², PV derating factor (f_{PV}), daily power consumption (E_{AC}) of the household in kWh/d, and the inverter yield (η_{inv}), as in (2) [44]:

$$P_{max} = \frac{E_{AC} P_i}{G_{sr} f_{PV} \eta_{inv}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Components of an on-grid PV system.

C. Energy Required for an RO Desalination Plant

The power needed for a RO plant should be calculated to assess its energetic requirements and integrate it with the renewable energy system. The power needed to desalinate the water (i.e. push water through membranes mechanically) as well as the electricity needed to pump the feed water to the plant and the treated water into the water system are all taken into account when calculating the overall power requirement of an RO plant. The major source of water for the desalination plant is the saline groundwater from the coastal aquifer. According to [45, 46], the energy needs for an RO desalination plant can be calculated using by:

$$P_D = \frac{SEC \cdot q}{CF_D} \quad (3)$$

where P_D is the power requirement of the RO in kW, CF_D is the capacity factor of the plant, q is the flow rate for the feed water in m³/h, and SEC is the specific energy consumption of desalination in kWh/m³.

D. RETScreen Expert Software

RETScreen Expert is a clean energy management tool developed by the Canadian government. It is a decision support tool utilized to determine the potential of energy, costs, savings, GHG emission reduction, and economic viability [47, 48]. RETScreen is commonly employed to explore the

feasibility of grid-connected wind and PV power systems. For instance, authors in [48] used RETScreen to evaluate the techno-economic feasibility of a grid-connected PV system in Nigeria. Authors in [49] utilized it to investigate the potential of PV systems for electricity generation in various locations in Libya. Authors in [50] evaluated the cost-benefit of a 100MW solar PV installation in Pakistan using RETScreen.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean monthly energy demand for the selected household is illustrated in Figure 2. The energy demand data were collected during 2012-2021. It is found that the energy demand is within the range of 210-309kWh with an average value of 250kWh. The highest and lowest value of energy demand is recorded in December and July, respectively.

Fig. 2. Monthly mean energy demand for the selected household during 2012-2021.

Fig. 3. Monthly average daily global radiation on a horizontal surface and a 34° tilted plane.

According to [51], the influence of the tilt angle on the solar electricity generation can be considered a minor effect when compared to the natural variation. The tilted and azimuth angles were chosen based on the highest value of solar irradiance and electricity exported to the grid. The monthly average daily global radiation on a horizontal surface and global radiation on a horizontal surface and a 34° tilted plane are illustrated in Figure 3 for the selected location. June and December are the periods with the highest and lowest solar radiation. The minimum and maximum tilted solar radiation were found to be 3.9kWh/m²/d and 7.25.57kWh/m²/d. The power requirement of the brackish water RO is calculated to estimate its energetic needs in order to estimate the capacity of the PV system. In this research, the total power demand of the RO plant is calculated using by (3). The desalination capacity factor and specific energy consumption of desalination are assumed based on [48, 52, 53]. Table I lists the parameters

needed for the calculation of the power requirements of the RO.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS FOR ESTIMATING THE POWER REQUIREMENT OF THE RO

Parameters	Value
Desalination capacity factor [%]	95
Specific energy consumption of desalination [kWh/m ³]	1.5
Flow rate of the feed water [m ³ /h]	0.5 and 1
Power requirement [kW]	1 and 2

Moreover, using (2), the maximum power of the PV system is found to be 6kW based on the minimum value of solar radiation. Thus, the total capacity of the PV system is estimated to be 7kW and 8kW, which depends on the power requirement of the RO desalination unit (Table I). The required area for the proposed systems is estimated to be within the range of 33-37m². In this study, the solar module JKM545M-72HL4-TV with a capacity of 545W and efficiency of 21.13%, manufactured by Jinko Solar, is used. Output AC power, DC-AC conversion efficiency, and capital cost of the inverter are the main factors to select a suitable inverter. OST 6000TL-D1 and OST 3000TL-S1 Solar Inverter with a capacity of 6kW and 3kW were selected.

A. Technical Viability

The performance of PV systems in terms of PV output and capacity factor depends on the orientation angles. Thus, the Electricity Exported to the Grid (EEG) and Capacity Factor (CF) were estimated at a tilted angle of 34° and azimuth angle of 0° for the selected location. It should be noted that fixed-tilt mounting systems are simpler, cheaper, and require less maintenance compared to tracking systems. The mean monthly value of EEG for all the considered PV systems is shown in Figure 4. It is observed that the EEG is within the range of 676.55-1161.75kWh and 773.20-1327.71kWh for PV systems with a capacity of 7kW and 8kW, respectively. The lowest and highest values of EEG are recorded in December and July, respectively.

Fig. 4. Monthly average value of EEG on a 34° tilted plane for the proposed PV systems.

Moreover, the monthly average electricity produced by the PV system and the electrical energy purchased from the grid is illustrated in Figure 5. It is found that the PV systems cover the household load and RO brackish groundwater desalination unit. The installation of the PV systems can solve the electricity crisis and produce freshwater for drinking and domestic use.

The annual value of EEG of the proposed system is 11769.99kWh and 13451.42kWh for a system with capacity of 7kW and 8kW, respectively. The CF of the proposed systems is 19.19%. This result can be supported by previous studies. For instance, authors in [48] found that the CF value of their proposed PV plants varied from 20.40% to 21.70%. Authors in [54] found that the CF values of 10MW grid-connected PV systems are within the range of 20.08-25.07%. Authors in [55] found that the proposed PV projects in Oman have a CF ranging from 16% to 23%. According to [56], the value of CF for grid-connected PV systems with various sun-tracking techniques fell between 17.54 and 27.42%. As a result, the current study's value for each site is compatible with the acceptable values. Consequently, it is technically feasible to construct a rooftop PV system that is connected to the local power grid.

Fig. 5. Monthly average electric production of (a) 7kW and (b) 8kW PV systems.

B. Economic Sustainability

To determine if the project is viable and sustainable economically, an economic study is vital. Thus, the techno-economic feasibility for rooftop PV systems at the selected location was evaluated for different values of electricity export rate (0.03-0.12USD/kWh in the step of 0.03USD/kWh) and discount rate (0% and 5.4%) to explore the possible variations in the results. The values of the used financial input parameters, namely inflation rate (2.9%), reinvestment rate (9%), project life (25 years), debt ratio (70%), debt interest rate (0%), and debt payment period (20 years), were assumed based on previous studies. Based on these input parameters, NPV, ALCS, SP, EP, LCOE, and the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) were estimated BY RETScreen. Table II summarizes the cost of the proposed system. Moreover, the cost of the final desalinated water is listed in Table III. It should be noted that the PV module and inverter were selected from a list of efficient PV modules and inverters which are currently

available in the market. The cost of the small-scale RO brackish groundwater desalination unit (0.5m³/h and 1m³/h) can be found in the literature. The initial investment cost of the proposed system is 6507 USD and 10482 USD for a PV system with a capacity of 7kW and 8kW, respectively.

The NPV was determined for each location and each value of the Electricity Export Rate (EER) is tabulated in Table III. It is found that the value of NPV for each value of EER is positive, which indicated that the project is potentially feasible [57, 58]. Besides, it is noticed that there is a strong correlation between NPV and EER. Moreover, IRR is estimated to evaluate the economic viability of the project [48, 57]. The IRR provides the true return of interest generated by the equity over the life of the project [47]. The results showed that increasing the rate of exporting electricity led to an increase in the value of IRR. In addition, it is observed that the value of IRR gotten for the three locations is higher than the required rate of return of the project. ALCS is calculated by using NPV, discount rate, and project lifetime. It is found that ALCS is within the range of 274.0-2571.1 USD/year for PV systems with a capacity of 7kW and 93.4-2773.5 USD/year for PV systems with a capacity of 8kW, as shown in Table III.

TABLE II. COSTS OF THE PV PROJECT AND THE RO DESALINATION UNIT

Parameter	Unit	Value
PV module cost	USD/W	0.3
Lifetime of the PV module	Year	25
Cost of a 6kW inverter	USD	450
Cost of a 3kW inverter	USD	250
Miscellaneous/contingency fund	% of the total initial cost	3
Installation and spare parts	% of the total initial cost	8.6
Feasibility study, development, and engineering cost	% of the total initial cost	0.6
Lifetime of inverter	Year	10
Inverter replacement periodic cost	-	Every 10 years
Investment cost of a 7KW PV system	USD	3366
Investment cost of a 8KW PV system	USD	5273
Investment cost of brackish groundwater desalination unit (0.5m ³ /h)	USD	3141
Investment cost of brackish groundwater desalination unit (1m ³ /h)	USD	6282

Furthermore, the economic viability of a project is estimated by determining the payback period, which indicates the time required to recover the initial investments, with net positive income [47, 48]. Table III lists the payback period including EP and SP for all selected locations. It is found that the EP is within the range of 1.50-15.8 years. The developed PV project with 7kW technology has the lowest value of EP. The proposed project with 8kW has the longest SP (7.2-28.6) compared to the other project (4.6-18.4 years). The results reveal that the increase in EER will lead to a decrease in EP and SP. The results demonstrate that the SP value exceeds the lifetime of the project (25 years) when EER is equal to 0.03 USD/kWh, especially for the project of 8kW. This indicates that installing PV projects at the selected locations is not economically viable when EER is equal to 0.03 USD/kWh. Additionally, the value of B-C, which is utilized to determine

the cash flow generated viability, is higher than 1 as shown in Table III. These findings indicate the feasibility of the projects [59].

C. Climate Co-Benefit Assessment

In addition to economic feasibility, an estimate of the environmental benefits in terms of reducing GHG emission of the proposed system would be attractive. The climate co-benefits in terms of GHG emission reduction were calculated

using RETScreen and are listed in Table IV in multiple equivalent formats. The results indicate that a large amount of CO₂ emissions can be avoided by implementing the developed PV project in each location. It should be noted that the total amount of CO₂ emission reduction for each location is determined based on the electricity generated annually [56]. The annual GHG emission reduction is 8.32 tCO₂ for the 7kW PV system and 9.51 tCO₂ for the 8kW PV system, as shown in Table IV.

TABLE III. ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF DEVELOPED PV PROJECTS FOR THE SELECTED LOCATION

PV capacity	Parameters	Case#1	Case#2	Case#3	Case#4	Case#5	Case#6	Case#7	Case#8
7 kW	Electricity export rate [USD/kWh]	0.03	0.06	0.09	0.12	0.03	0.06	0.09	0.12
	Discount rate [%]	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Pre-tax IRR-equity	14.7	33.0	51.5	70.2	14.7	33.0	51.5	70.2
	Pre-tax IRR-assets	4.4	12.5	18.8	24.7	4.4	12.5	18.8	24.7
	Simple payback [Year]	18.4	9.2	6.1	4.6	18.4	9.2	6.1	4.6
	Equity payback [Year]	8.7	3.5	2.1	1.5	8.7	3.5	2.1	1.5
	Net Present Value (NPV) [USD]	3712.1	12117.0	20521.9	28926.8	11193.0	28888.1	46583.1	64278.2
	Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]	274.0	894.5	1515.0	2135.5	447.7	1155.5	1863.3	2571.1
	Benefit-cost (B-C) ratio	2.9	7.2	11.5	15.8	6.7	15.8	24.9	34.0
	Debt service coverage	1.6	3.3	4.9	6.5	1.6	3.3	4.9	6.5
8 kW	Energy production cost [USD/kWh]	0.0294	0.0294	0.0294	0.0294	0.0221	0.0221	0.0221	0.0221
	Electricity export rate [USD/kWh]	0.03	0.06	0.09	0.12	0.03	0.06	0.09	0.12
	Discount rate [%]	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	Pre-tax IRR-equity	7.4	20.1	31.8	43.6	7.4	20.1	31.8	43.6
	Pre-tax IRR-assets	2.9	8.0	10.3	11.9	2.9	8.0	10.3	11.9
	Simple payback [Year]	28.6	14.3	9.5	7.2	28.6	14.3	9.5	7.2
	Equity payback [Year]	15.8	6.2	3.6	2.5	15.8	6.2	3.6	2.5
	Net Present Value (NPV) [USD]	1265.7	10871.4	20477.0	30082.6	8667.9	28890.8	49113.7	69336.6
	Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]	93.4	802.6	1511.7	2220.8	346.7	1155.6	1964.5	2773.5
	Benefit-cost (B-C) ratio	1.4	4.1	6.9	9.7	3.5	9.3	15.2	21.0
Debt service coverage	1.0	2.1	3.1	4.2	1.0	2.1	3.1	4.2	
Energy production cost [USD/kWh]	0.0458	0.0458	0.0458	0.0458	0.0344	0.0344	0.0344	0.0344	

TABLE IV. GHG EMISSION REDUCTION (TCO₂)

Annual GHG emission reduction [tCO ₂] equivalent to	PV capacity	
	7 kW	8 kW
Gross annual GHG emission reduction	8.32	9.51
Care and light trucks not used	1.52	1.74
Liters of gasoline not consumed	3575.18	4085.92
Barrels of crude oil not consumed	19.35	22.11
People reducing energy use by 20%	8.32	9.51
Acres of forest absorbing carbon	1.89	2.16
Hectares of forest absorbing carbon	0.77	0.87
Tons of waste recycled	2.87	3.28

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Population growth and energy demand have prompted governments and researchers to find alternative energy sources. Solar-powered energy has received the most attention among the alternative energy sources due to its environmentally friendly nature. In this paper, the use of solar energy as an alternative source for generating electricity and drinking water was investigated. Accordingly, this paper first reviewed the literature on water resources and the energy situation in the country to offer persuasive suggestions for policymakers to consider solar energy as an energy source in the future. The result showed that the use of solar energy can help the country reduce its dependence on fossil fuels and generate electricity at a low cost as well as produce freshwater using small units of

RO brackish groundwater desalination. A household was selected to determine the energy demands according to the monthly electricity bills in addition to the energy required for RO desalination to assess the PV system's capacity. Then, the techno-economic feasibility of rooftop grid-connected PV systems was investigated. The results demonstrated that rooftop grid-connected PV systems are technically, economically, and environmentally feasible for the selected region. Hence, solar energy can be an alternative energy source to solve the water and energy shortage in the country.

Future work is needed to address the profit from the use of the photovoltaic system, which largely depends on the tariffs for the region and the possibility of connecting a given power to the grid about the quality of electricity, voltage values, and the stability of the distribution system.

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Smart Scarf: An IOT-based Solution for Emotion Recognition

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design rationale of a color-changing scarf depending on the emotional state it detects. The goal of the design is to associate people to show up their emotional state especially those who have difficulties in expressing their feelings, such as elderly people, children, people with special needs, and people who have to wear a face mask, which covers their facial expression, as it is common during the COVID-19 pandemic period. Wearing a smart emotional scarf provides a context of the individual's emotional state that might help surrounding people in dealing with them. Our design uses a heart rate sensor and a skin sensor to detect and recognize emotional information. The scarf will change its color based on the emotional state it detects (neutral, angry, happy, and sad). An interface allows the provision of emotional data and displays emotional statistics and daily history. We went through a user-centered design process adopting wearable technology guidelines. A proposed prototype of the smart scarf is presented called Scarfy. A user evaluation is conducted showing that wearing the scarf with changing colors based on emotional status is a good solution to express feelings with comfort and wearing it might enhance social engagement.

Keywords-wearable technology; design process; emotion recognition; Internet of Things (IOT)

I. INTRODUCTION

Wearable technology has evolved along with wearable sensors and textile technologies, and they are now a part of our daily life. In the subject of human-computer interaction, using wearable technology to provide wearers with emotional support has been seen as an essential research question in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). In addition, to improve one's own emotional health, it is necessary to have an impact on others' emotional state through interactions in a social setting. Moreover, in the field of ambient assisted living, people with Mild Cognitive Impairments (MCI), Alzheimer's disease, or dementia, require supervision in their everyday activities. The need to develop an innovative approach in order to explore ways of working with elder people and their formal and informal caregivers, is emphasized [1]. Providing information on both physical and emotional statuses positively affects multiple stakeholders and facilitates communication. Today technologies facilitate monitoring and analyzing body data to recognize a person's feelings and moods. Interaction designers face new challenges when designing wearable technology. Beyond those of self-emotional awareness and management, other challenges and principles are raised by the design of wearable technology. Designers need to adopt a user-centered methodology to find the important touch points with users that help in finding recommendations for tech designers. Smart wearable devices are becoming an increasingly important part of the Internet of Things (IoT) technology. Smart watches,

wrist bands, headsets, and earbuds are some of the wearable technologies developed for different applications. Authors in [2] classify the smart wearable devices into major clusters based on their applications: Health, sports, daily activity, tracking and localization, and safety. Moreover, IoT-based wearable technology can be improved further to save human lives by detecting in advance health risk conditions such as heat strokes [3]. The major challenges of wearable IoT devices are data resolution of wearable sensors, power consumption, wearability, safety, security, regulation, and privacy [4].

In this paper, an emotion smart scarf called Scarfy is presented. Scarfy is connected to an LED light that can change its color based on the wearer's feelings. The scarf analyzes the wearers' feelings through their vital signs and tries to help them improve their emotional state and facilitate the elucidation of their feelings to others. In addition, the scarf is connected to a mobile application via Bluetooth to store the user's current emotional status. The application helps determines the users' emotional status and tries to predict different emotional statuses over a period. These data can be used in future work to determine user behavior and predict a user's emotional status. We add a new classification to wearable application, "human emotions". During the design process, focus was to both challenges, data resolution of the wearable sensors and wearability.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Emotion and Technology

Heart Rate Variability (HRV) has been used to quantify controlled emotional reactivity [5]. HRV tracks the ebbs and flows of heart rate. A rise in HRV is associated with positive stimuli, while a drop in HRV is associated with negative stimuli. Hence, HRV can be used to gauge a person's emotional state. Authors in [6] looked for ways to create a wearable display that changes colors quickly. Their AmbiKraf non-emissive analog fabric display was developed using thermochromic inks and incorporated semiconductor peltier junctions. The controller enables the thermochromic ink to display several colors while regulating the temperature in the soft cloth [7]. Authors in [2] studied the association between heart rate changes and emotions changes. They considered three emotions: sad, happy, and neutral. The study uses HRV extracted from the PPG signal and analyzes its relationship with feelings. Ten characteristics were computed and analyzed in each measurement cycle. The project is similar to the work in this paper by studying the relationship between heart rate changes and emotional changes using electrocardiograms (ECGs). But our project Scarfy uses a skin sensor as well and produces a response based on the results. Scarfy is also a wearable smart device that can be used by anyone. In our project we will use the same approach to detect emotions based on HRV.

B. Emotion and Therapy through a Smart-scarf

Authors in [5] looked for ways to affect a user's mood using bodily data. Twelve people aged from 20s to 40s were chosen to discuss their emotional experiences. All participants were college students and employees. Numerous concepts were discussed before presenting them to the same group of people: a clever hair band, a bracelet, a helmet, a vest, and a scarf. Most of the participants opted to wear a scarf since it is less noticeable and could be worn daily. Researchers suggested to create a smart-scarf prototype called Smiley to help individuals comprehend self- and emotion-consciousness, improve communication, and strengthen social relationships by altering its color. The interaction concept was developed into three scenarios:

- Self-scenario
- One-to-one scenario
- One-to-many scenario

A wearable device must be flexible, lightweight, pleasing, conductive, and fairly priced. Its design considers connecting to a heart rate sensor module, a skin conductance sensor module, a color sensor module, and an IR transceiver to a LilyPad Arduino. In our project, we will currently focus on the self-scenario.

C. Emotion and Color Combination

A color-combination emotion model was created in [8]. It was made up of a three-dimensional axis that depicts the parameters soft-hard, light-heavy, and splendid-sober. The color combinations correspond to nine different mood categories. In his work *A Book of Colors*, Shigenobu

Kobayashi examined numerous color combinations while making allusions to various emotion adjectives [9]. The primary focus is given on the interior design, which motivated us to investigate how color combinations and emotions relate to one another. Table I summarizes the similarities and differences between the related work and our project.

TABLE I. RELATED WORK SUMMARY

Related work	Difference	Similarities
Detect emotions changes using heart rate changes [2]	The project depends only on a heart rate sensor and the result is shown in a screen. Our project uses both heart rate and skin sensors then produces a response based on the results on a smart wearable device.	Similar to our project in the motivation of studying the relationship between heart rate and emotions changes using ECG.
Emotion therapy through a smart-scarf [5]	The interaction concept is developed into 3 scenarios: Self, One-to-one, and One-to-many. Our project will develop the Self scenario.	Create the same wearable device connecting to a heart rate sensor and a skin sensor.
User experience on a smart scarf [8]	Focus is given on enhancing communication between the scarf wearer and the surrounding parties, while our project does not consider the surrounding parties at this stage.	A smart wearable is created that will assist people become more conscious of their emotions in a group surroundings while also enhancing good emotions and reducing negative ones

III. DESIGN PROCESS

Design wearable technology is beyond combining electronic components with fashionable clothing, however it should concern physical form, electronic components, Graphical User Interface (GUI), physical interface, and embodied product value [10]. Furthermore, the design of wearable technology needs to consider the collection of bodily data and their processing, considering some design principles such as comfort, contextual-awareness, affordance customization, ease of use, pleasant, ergonomics, wearability, and fashion [11].

A. User-Centered Design Process

We investigated the use of body data to influence a user's mood and allowing the surrounding environment to be aware of one's emotional status. With a web survey method, we reached 269 participants to answer a survey of 14 questions and share their emotional experience. All participants were college students and staff members, and their ages ranged from 17 to 45. They were questioned about what their bodies had gone through when being in depressing or exhilarating situations and how do colors affect their emotional experience. Collecting data helped us determine the project requirements and specifications.

B. Biometrics Data Gathering and Analysis

The heart, through contraction and diastole, pumps blood to all parts of the body. When blood is pumped into the body, it produces a pulse in the arteries. This pulse represents the

number of heartbeats. The healthy heart rate for resting adults is 60-80 beats per minute (BPM) [12]. Changes in heart rate can be seen with a typical ECG. There are factors that affect the resting heart rate, including heart problems and emotional outbursts. In our project, we focus on the relationship between changes in the heart rate and the emotional state. McCraty [13] observed a clear change in the pattern of the heart's rhythm due to the change in feelings. It was found that negative emotions such as anxiety and anger cause irregular heartbeats, while positive emotions such as sympathy and love produce high heartbeat rhythms. So, we chose the heart rate as one of the indicators to differentiate between emotions in our project. In addition, in terms of identifying human sensations, skin temperature is an effective indicator. The association between stressful work and skin temperature was investigated and it was discovered that when people are stressed, tense, or have other unpleasant feelings, their skin temperature rises [12]. For accurate results of the wearer's emotional state, we considered combining both sensors, heart rate and skin temperature. They can be used to classify the emotional state in 4 categories (neutral, happy, sad, and angry) [14] as shown in Table II.

TABLE II. EMOTION STATES ACCORDING TO THE HEART RATE AND SKIN TEMPERATURE

State	BPM	Skin temperature
Natural	50 - 80	36.5 - 37.5 °C
Happy	90 - 100	37.5 - 38 °C
Sad	80 - 90	35 - 36 °C
Angry	100 - 120	37 - 38.5 °C

Fig. 1. Scarfy changes color base on emotional state.

Our project will adopt the techniques developed in [14]. We will represent the emotional state with different colors as following: white for neutral, red for angry, blue for happy, and yellow for sad (Figure 1).

C. Interface Design

We chose cotton fabric to design our smart scarf Scarfy (Figure 2). The main components of the system are:

1. A scarf made of cotton fabric.

2. Heart rate MAX30100 Pulse Oximeter sensor: is an I2C-based low-power plug-and-play biometric sensor.
3. Skin temperature sensor: an infrared thermometer for non-contact temperature measurements HiLetgo GY-906 MLX90614ESF non-contact infrared.
4. LED light strip: WS2812B.
5. Bluetooth: HC-05.
6. Arduino: An open-source single-board microcontroller appropriate for low budget, small electronics projects.

HRV and skin temperature sensors are used to detect scarf wearer's emotions. They are comfortable, inexpensive, and can be easily attached to the scarf. The Arduino board is used to read the input data from sensors and control them. The small size, compact design, and advanced features of the Arduino make it an appropriate choice for wearable technology [15]. The system architecture demonstrates the position of the two sensors (heart rate and skin temperature). The sensors will sense heart rate and skin temperature and send the data to the Arduino, which will collect and analyze them to determine the emotional state. After that, the LED color will change based on the current emotional state of the wearer and send the state to the "Scarfy" application via Bluetooth. The application will send the state to Firebase to store the user status and retrieve when needed for open daily/weekly analysis (Figure 3).

Fig. 2. System architecture and design for Scarfy.

IV. WORKING PROCEDURE

In order to detect the emotional state and change led color, we adopt the methodology of [14]. The following algorithm describes the working procedure:

If the heart sensor between (100 and 120) and skin temperature between 37 - 38.5 °C Then emotional state is "angry" and led = red

Else if heart sensor between (91 and 100) and skin temperature between 35 - 36 °C

Then emotional state is "sad" and led = yellow
 Else if heart sensor between (80 and 90) and skin temperature between 37.5 - 38 °C
 Then emotional state is "happy" and led = green
 Else
 if heart sensor between (50 and 80) and skin temperature between 36.5 - 37.5 °C
 Then emotional state is "neutral" and led = white

Fig. 3. System architecture connecting to mobile application.

V. USER EVALUATION

Scarfy was tested on 10 participants aged between 20 and 25. The participants were seated on an empty lab except for the observer and were asked to wear Scarfy. First, each user was required to create an account at the Scarfy application by entering his email and password and filling up the profile page. After that, the user has to select some preferred activities regarding his emotional status such as: "What activities help you relax? Eat an ice cream, watch a movie, read a book, play video games, go on a picnic, and talk to friends." The user's preferred activities were attached next to user emotional status as a suggestion message to enhance user's negative mood and maintain good mood (Figure 4). Subsequently, different movie clips were played with different contents. The contents were intended to affect the emotions of participants. When the participant was watching the clip and Scarfy detected changes in the emotional status, the user was prompted to answer an online questionnaire to evaluate the prototype and provide feedback. Figure 5 shows two participants wearing Scarfy while being in different emotional statuses during watching movie clips with different contents.

Moreover, the mobile application provides a feature to users that allows them to view their emotional states during the day or the week (Figure 6). This feature allows the users to track their emotional states and be aware of which activities affected their emotions negatively or positively. This analysis may be used as raw data for future work.

Fig. 4. User interface of the sign up page of the Scarfy mobile application.

Fig. 5. Participants during the user evaluation session.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper focuses on the use of wearable technology to provide wearers with emotional support which is an essential research question in the HCI field. Our evaluation indicates that users were pleased with the smart scarf's appearance, comfort, and engagement. The smart scarf was proven simple to use while it assists people to track and control their emotions. At the same time, it provides a good channel for people to show their feelings to the surrounding people, thus facilitating communication. However, inaccurate readings may

result from the limits of skin conductance and heart rate sensors. Moreover, not all body emotions could be distinguished by the two sensors alone.

Fig. 6. Daily (left) and weekly (right) emotional state analysis.

For future work, we may consider employing a variety of channels, such as breathing and blood pressure pulse, to detect emotions more emotions with more accuracy. Moreover, we should address the gender and culture differences in color and privacy. Furthermore, we would like to consider the one to one and group scenarios where users who wear Scarfy can communicate together via their scarves sharing their emotional states and allow sending messages based on their emotional status. In general, Scarfy aims to enhance social bonds and facilitate interaction. The stored emotional data for users may be an opportunity for further artificial intelligent studies.

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An Experimental Investigation of the Effects of Diesel-Ethanol Blends on the Noise and Vibrations of a Diesel Engine

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ABSTRACT

This study performed a noise and vibration analysis of a single-cylinder diesel engine with 5, 10, and 15% ethanol concentration in diesel fuel at 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100% load and a constant engine speed of 1500rpm. Vibrations were measured at the cylinder head in the horizontal, vertical, and axial directions. The frequency and octave spectrums were obtained using an FFT analyzer. The results revealed that the E5D95 blend had significantly less vibration and noise than the E10D90 and E15D85 blends. The vibration level was minimum at 20% load and maximum at 100% load in the vertical, horizontal, and axial directions, while the highest noise level was observed for E15D85.

Keywords-engine; ethanol; vibration; noise

I. INTRODUCTION

Biofuels have been developed as an alternative energy source to reduce the dependency on fuel imports and satisfy regulatory emission limits. Internal combustion engines are typically powered by the most prevalent biofuels, such as ethanol and biodiesel. Ethanol fuel is significantly attracting more attention compared to other biofuels because it is made from more environmentally sustainable raw materials. Ethanol can be produced from sugar cane, sugar beets, wood, corn, and other grains and has significant potential as a fuel for both Spark Ignition (SI) and Compression Ignition (CI) engines due to its physicochemical characteristics. The automotive industries compete to improve passenger comfort, efficiency, and environmental friendliness. To reduce vibration, noise, and engine spray characteristics, a thorough analysis is essential to both fuel use and repairs to the combustion engine. Engine noise and vibrations are influenced by engine combustion

characteristics in addition to contributions from moving engine components. The combustion characteristics depend on various engine operating parameters such as fuel type, engine load, and speed. Signals from the engine body vibrations contain information regarding an engine's physical characteristics and operating conditions, while both vibration and noise help determine an engine's condition.

Many studies investigated the effects of different blends on engine noise and vibration. In [1], noise, vibration, engine performance characteristics, and emissions of a diesel engine were studied, using diesel and n-butanol blends, reporting the viability of a diesel and n-butanol mixture as an alternative fuel for generators. In [2], engine performance was evaluated using water-diesel emulsions in diesel engines, showing that 2% water emulsions had the optimum engine performance and noise levels. In [3], the noise and vibration of a single-cylinder diesel engine were studied at five different engine speeds at an 80% load condition and three different injection pressures. The

results showed an increase in engine vibration when butanol was added to diesel fuel. In [4], the performance, combustion, emission, and vibration characteristics of diesel engines were studied, using rice bran biodiesel and the n-butanol additive. The results indicated vibration levels comparable to diesel fuel, indicating smooth combustion. In [5], a diesel engine investigation was performed by changing engine load, speed, and injection timing, concluding that the maximum rate of heat release was inversely proportional to the level of vibration in the engine block, which was affected by changes in the injection timing. In [6], combustion-induced vibrations of engine reciprocating components were studied, presenting a dynamic model that used Lagrange's equation. In [7], the effects of diesel-biodiesel combinations on noise and vibration were studied, examining engine block displacement, time domain, waveform, side thrust, and in-cylinder force and reporting that the levels of vibration and noise were highest between 1500 and 2500rpm. In [8], Moringa oleifera-diesel mixed fuel samples were tested at various loads, concluding that the B20D80 mixture had minimum vibrations. In [9], the effects of diesel-biodiesel and turpentine blends on the noise and vibration of a diesel engine were investigated, showing that turpentine fuel could reduce noise and vibration levels at increased engine loads compared to pure diesel.

In [10], noise, vibration, and exhaust pollutants of a dual-fuel operative diesel engine were examined, using fuel combinations of diesel and Mustard Oil Biodiesel (MOB), diesel, MOB, and hydrogen gas. The results suggested that engine noise and vibration could be greatly reduced using MOB. In [11], the vibration of a diesel engine was examined using both pure diesel and a fuel blend of 10% recycled lubricating oil with 90% diesel, showing that engine vibrations were reduced for the selected fuel mixture. In [12], a diesel engine noise source identification was performed at various speeds, finding that engine noise increased with engine speed and indicating that engine mounting is another substantial source of vibration resulting in a considerable impact on noise levels. In [13], the emission, vibration, and noise parameters of a single-cylinder DI diesel engine were investigated at varied engine running loads at a constant speed, using diesel and Niger seed oil methyl ester blend for experimental tests. The results showed 26.15% and 45.78% reduction in noise and vibration levels, respectively, for the B20 blends. In [14], nanoparticles were added to the diesel fuel to observe the emission and vibration characteristics of a single-cylinder diesel engine with Variable Compression Ratio (VCR), showing that the addition of nanoparticles reduced both noise levels and engine block vibrations. In [15], 3 different biofuels were used to prepare biodiesel blends, reporting that B50 blends caused minimum engine vibration. In [16], the vibrations of a single-cylinder variable compression ratio diesel engine were studied using a Jatropha biodiesel blend. The frequency domain was obtained using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). In [17], an improvement in the RMS and kurtosis values of an engine body vibration was obtained for diesel-ethanol blends.

In [18], the vibration effects of canola (rapeseed), sunflowers, and mixtures were investigated on low-sulfur diesel fuel at various speeds. The lowest vibration was

achieved using a 60% biodiesel blend. The engine performance analysis in [19] revealed that the B30 (30% biodiesel and 70% diesel) mix brake-specific fuel consumption was 6.9% higher than that of 100% diesel, while the brake thermal efficiency of B30 was decreased by 4.75%. In [20], the noise and emissions of pure diesel and two biodiesel blends were investigated at variable loads with constant engine speed. In [21], the emissions, performance, and sound pressure levels of diesel and biodiesel blends of cooking oil waste were examined, indicating that the biodiesel blends reduced particle emissions by 7.29%, the fuel consumption of brake-specific biodiesel blend decreased as brake power increased, brake thermal efficiency increased with brake power, while the blend B25 produced less noise than pure diesel. In [22], potassium hydroxide was used as a catalyst and methanol as a co-solvent through the transesterification process. The particulate matter emissions were analyzed on a CI engine with pure diesel fuel, biodiesel-mixed, and clove oil. This study showed a 5.27% reduction in particulate matter in biodiesel-blended fuel, and an 11.61% reduction in particulate matter when clove was added to biodiesel-blended fuel compared to pure diesel. Finally, the engine noise of the biodiesel-mixed and clove oil was lower than pure diesel.

Many studies have investigated the effect of blends on engine noise and vibration, but most of them considered the vibration effect in a single direction without examining them in three directions. This study aimed to investigate the vibration frequency spectrum in three directions at different loads and obtain the noise levels and the octave spectrum of different diesel and ethanol fuel blends. The spectral composition of an engine's vibration signal was analyzed, and the vertical, horizontal, and axial vibration levels of an internal combustion engine block were correlated and examined for different ethanol and diesel blends.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three diesel-ethanol blends, E5D95, E10D90, and E15D85 were prepared by blending 5, 10, and 15% ethanol with pure diesel. The noise and vibration of the engine were measured using an FFT analyzer at 20, 40, 60, 80%, and 100% load.

A. Experimental Setup

This study used a 4-stroke single-cylinder Kirlosker TV1 CI engine. Figure 1 shows the experimental setup. An eddy current water-cooled dynamometer was used. The engine noise and vibration measurements were performed at constant 1500rpm with 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100% loads for each blend. Noise and vibrations were analyzed using a 4-channel vibration analyzer, and three accelerometers were used to measure vibrations in the three directions at the engine's head. Table I shows the maximum uncertainty in measurements.

TABLE I. MAXIMUM UNCERTAINTIES IN MEASUREMENTS

Measuring Parameter	Instrument/Sensor	Uncertainty
Engine vibration	Accelerometer	$\pm 80g$, peak (Sensitivity: 100mV/g)
Noise	Microphone	$\pm 2dB$ (Sensitivity: 50 mv/pa)

Fig. 1. Test engine.

Fig. 2. The FFT analyzer.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Vertical (V), Horizontal (H), and Axial (A) vibration signals and FFT spectra were analyzed for all tested blends.

A. Vibration Analysis

1) Using 5% Ethanol Blending (E5D95)

Table II shows the velocity-RMS amplitudes of the E5D95 blend in the three directions on the engine head. The vibration level was minimum in the vertical direction and maximum in the horizontal direction. Figures 3 and 4 show the frequency spectra for 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100% engine loads in V, H, and A directions. Velocity in the V direction was found minimum (9.47mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (16.3mm/s) at 100%. Velocity in the H direction was found minimum (48.6 mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (16.3 mm/s) at 100%. Velocity in the A direction was found minimum (23 mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (31.9 mm/s) at 100%.

TABLE II. OVERALL RMS OF AMPLITUDE IN THE THREE DIRECTIONS

Speed (rev/min)	Load	RMS Amplitude (mm/s)			
		Location	Direction		
			Vertical	Horizontal	Axial
1500	20%	Cylinder head	9.47	48.6	23
	40%		11.9	50.4	24.2
	60%		14.1	51.1	26.9
	80%		15.9	53	30.3
	100%		16.3	54	31.9

Fig. 3. Frequency spectra at 20% load in the V, H, and A directions.

Fig. 4. Frequency spectra at 40% load in the V, H, and A directions.

In the frequency spectrum, harmonics were observed in the vertical direction. At 20% load, the peak amplitude was 43.7mm/s in the H direction and 19.5mm/s in the A direction at 25Hz. For 40% load, the corresponding values for the peak amplitude were 45.8mm/s in the H direction and 23.1mm/s in the A direction at 25Hz. Similar tests were conducted for 60, 80, and 100% loads. At 60% load, the peak amplitude was 43.6mm/s in the H direction and 22.3mm/s in the A direction at 25Hz. At 80% load, the peak amplitude was 45.7mm/s in the H direction and 26.8mm/s in the A direction at 25Hz. The corresponding values at 100% load were 45.2mm/s in the H direction and 30mm/s in the A direction at 26Hz. A reason for this could be the pressure changes within the cylinder during combustion.

2) Using 10 % Ethanol Blending (B10D90)

Table III shows the overall velocity-RMS amplitude of the E10D90 blend in the three directions. Figures 5 and 6 show the frequency spectra for the same engine loads at 1500RPM. Velocity in the V direction was found to be minimum (10mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (16.5mm/s) at 100%. Velocity in the H direction was found to be minimum (50.1mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (54.7mm/s) at 100%. Velocity in the A direction was found to be minimum (26.1mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (32mm/s) at 100%. The minimum velocity was reported at 20% load while the maximum was reported at 100%.

TABLE III. OVERALL RMS VALUES OF AMPLITUDE IN THE THREE DIRECTIONS

Speed (rev/min)	Load	RMS Amplitude (mm/s)			
		Location	Direction		
			Vertical	Horizontal	Axial
1500	20%	Cylinder head	10	50.1	26.1
	40%		12.5	50.8	26.8
	60%		14.3	52.7	29.9
	80%		16.3	53.9	30.3
	100%		16.5	54.7	32

Fig. 5. Frequency spectra at 20% load in the V, H, and A directions.

Fig. 6. Frequency spectra at 40% load in the V, H, and A directions.

In the frequency spectrum, harmonics were observed in the V direction. At 20% load, the H peak amplitude was 46.7mm/s and the A peak amplitude was 22.1 mm/s, at 25Hz. At 40% load, the peak amplitude was 22.5mm/s in the A direction and 46.5mm/s in the H direction at 25Hz. Similar trials were conducted for 60, 80, and 100% loads. At 60% load, the peak amplitude was 47mm/s in the H direction and 24.8mm/s in the A direction at 25 Hz. At 80% load, the maximum H amplitude was 34.2mm/s and the maximum A amplitude was 22.1mm/s at 25Hz. At 100% load, the maximum amplitude was 53.3mm/s in the H direction and 28.5mm/s in the A direction at 26Hz. This could also be attributed to the pressure changes within the cylinder during combustion. The V direction had lower vibrational amplitudes than the H and A directions.

3) Using 15% Ethanol Blending (B15P85)

Figures 7 and 8 show the FFT spectra for the same engine loads at 1500 RPM. Table IV shows that the minimum and maximum velocities were recorded at 20% and 100% loads, respectively. Velocity in the V direction was found minimum (10mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (17mm/s) at 100% load. Velocity in the H direction was found minimum (52mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (55.8mm/s) at 100% load. Velocity in the A direction was found minimum (24.2mm/s) at 20% load and maximum (34.3mm/s) at 100% load. The vibration levels of B15D85 were higher than those of B5D95 and B10D90 blends.

TABLE IV. OVERALL RMS VALUES OF AMPLITUDE IN THE V, H, A DIRECTIONS

Speed (rev/min)	Load	RMS Amplitude (mm/s)			
		Location	Direction		
			Vertical	Horizontal	Axial
1500	20 %	Cylinder head	10	52	24.2
	40%		12.2	52	26.1
	60%		14.9	54.7	31
	80%		16	54.8	32
	100%		17	55.8	34.3

Fig. 7. Frequency spectra at 20% load in the V, H, and A directions.

In the frequency spectrum, harmonics were observed in the V direction. At 20% load, the peak amplitude was 48mm/s in the H direction and 21.3mm/s in the A direction, at 25Hz. At 40% load, the peak was 48mm/s in the H direction and 27.4mm/s in the A direction at 25Hz. At 60% load, the peak amplitude was 49.8mm/s in the H and 27.4 mm/s in the A direction at 26Hz. At 80% load, the peak amplitude was 49.8 mm/s in the H and 28.5mm/s in the A direction at 26Hz. At 100% load, the peak amplitude was 51.5mm/s in the H and 33.2mm/s in the A direction at 26Hz. The high peak amplitude in the H direction may be due to the variation of the cylinder pressure inside the combustion chamber. The vibration amplitude was less in the V direction compared to the others, as the internal components piston, connecting rod, crankshaft, bearings, and camshaft have less degrees of freedom in this direction.

Fig. 8. Frequency spectra at 40% load in the V, H, and A directions.

The three tested blends showed reduced engine vibration in the V direction compared to the H and A directions. The intensity of the vibration was highest in the H direction. Peak velocities were observed in the horizontal plane because of the rapid changes in cylinder pressure that occur during combustion. Vertical vibration was reduced because piston, connecting rod, crankshaft, bearings, and camshaft have less degrees of freedom in this direction. The fuel cetane number and the injection advance may affect the vibration, while a short ignition delay may reduce it.

B. Noise Analysis

The engine noise data were recorded in a similar experimental indoor environment and conditions for the three blends, using an FFT analyzer to capture the engine noise. Noise level was measured with a microphone (Make: K type 40 ph; Sensitivity: 50mv/pa) kept 1.25m off the ground and 1m from the engine centreline. The microphone was connected to the FFT analyzer. Table V shows the noise levels recorded for the three blends. The E5D95 blend produced less noise than the E10D90 and E15D85 blends. Figures 9–14 show the octave spectra of the E5D95, E10D90, and E15D85 blends at 20% and 40% load. Similar trials were conducted for 60, 80, and 100% loads at 1500rpm.

TABLE V. NOISE LEVEL OF FUEL AT DIFFERENT LOAD

Fuel	Load	Noise level (L) dB
E5D95	20	89.7
	40	95.5
	60	97.7
	80	98.2
	100	99.9
E10D90	20	92.6
	40	94.7
	60	98.6
	80	99.3
	100	102
E15D85	20	93.9
	40	95.6
	60	98.6
	80	101
	100	102

Fig. 9. Octave spectrum of the E5D95 blend at 20% load.

Fig. 10. Octave spectrum of the E5D95 blend at 40% load.

Fig. 11. Octave spectrum of the E10D90 blend at 20% load.

Fig. 12. Octave spectrum of the E10D90 blend at 40% load.

Fig. 13. Octave spectrum of the E15D85 blend at 20% load.

Fig. 14. Octave spectrum of the E15D85 blend at 40% load.

Noise levels were minimum at 20% load and maximum at 100% load across the board. Increases in input air flow rate, air pressure pulsation amplitude, and frequency with increasing engine loads were responsible for the subsequent increase in engine noise. The intake system was mostly determined by gas pressure wave dynamics, which in turn was affected by the workload of the engine. When the load was high, the noise level increased.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study investigated experimentally the noise and vibration produced by a single-cylinder diesel engine running at a constant 1500 rpm and varying loads. The lowest vibration was reported for B5D95, showing that engine vibration increases with increasing ethanol concentration in the fuel blend. Furthermore, vibrations in the horizontal direction were higher compared to those in vertical and axial directions at all loads due to the rapid changes in cylinder pressure during combustion. Vertical vibration was reduced because the piston, connecting rod, crankshaft, bearings, and camshaft had less degrees of freedom in this direction. A short ignition delay may be responsible for reducing vibration. The vibrations increased with increasing loads. Noise measurement was performed using an FFT analyzer and it was observed that the B5D95 blend had the lowest engine noise among the tested blends. The noise level of E5D95 was minimum (89.7dB) at 20% load and maximum (99.9 dB) at 100% load. The noise level of E10D90 was minimum (92.6dB) at 20% load and maximum (102dB) at 100% load. The noise level of E15D85 was minimum (93.9dB) at 20% load and maximum (102dB) at 100% load. It was noticed that the engine noise increased with increasing ethanol concentration in fuel blends. The engine noise for E15P85 was slightly higher than for E10P90. The engine workload had an impact on the gas pressure wave dynamics, which in turn influenced the intake system. Future research could focus on the correlation between performance analysis with vibration and noise. Furthermore, noise and vibration characteristics could be studied for flex-fuel engines using similar measurement techniques.

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A Research on the Load Calculation Method in Designing the Traction Power Supply for Integrated Subway – MCR

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a load calculation method in the design of a traction power supply for integrated subways. Integrated subways have a large carrying capacity and the ability to balance between meeting travel needs and satisfying conditions such as high quality service, cost optimization for railway infrastructure construction, and installation of traction power systems. In an integrated model, the calculation of the traction power supply design is much more complicated than in other stand-alone models. This paper presents the research results on the load calculation method of a traction power supply for the operation of the system. The results show the feasibility of the method when applied to an asynchronous loading system and met the standards of IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and IEC 60146-1 in the design of the power supply for permitted overloads according to class VI.

Keywords-urban rail transit; integrated urban railway; traction power supply; integrated subway

I. INTRODUCTION

A sustainable integrated urban transport n integrated system, with the large-scale interaction of various public transportation modes, attracts users with its friendliness, comfort, and time- and cost- saving in commuting and providing full "door-to-door" public transportation services. Urban rail is an indispensable part of a sustainable integrated urban transport system. However, different integrated solutions have been recommended depending on the type of transportation. A system with a large transport capacity integrating subway and suburban railway is needed to meet the large commuting needs connecting suburban areas and city centers. This system should operate with a very high transport capacity during peak hours, which is difficult to achieve separately for each type of transportation, and return to normal operating conditions during non-peak hours with low construction investment cost. The benefits of an integrated subway system are highlighted in [1-4]. To ensure that the system operates as flexibly, optimally, reliably, and energy-efficiently as desired, it needs to have a strong power supply system to meet the highest transport capacity during peak hours. However, most past studies focused on planning, forecasting, and addressing transport capacity, energy saving, and evaluating the benefits it brings to the comprehensive development of smart cities under the new context of integrated subways [5-10]. Therefore, this study focuses on calculating the design load for the power supply to enable the flexible operation of the system according to IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and IEC 60146-1 standards with an allowable overload of up to

level VI. Matlab R2017b/Railway Systems software was used for computations and simulations.

II. INTEGRATED LOAD CALCULATION METHOD

A. Integrating Subway and Suburban Railway.

Integrated subway (ME) and suburban railway (CR) is a method of combining the transportation capacity of suburban railways by operating on subway travel corridors during peak hours (MCR). This method allows increased transportation capacity and service frequency without the need to increase the number of trains operating on it. On the other hand, suburban trains operate like subway trains when running on the line. Figure 1 describes the integrated train running chart, in which A to E are the terminal stations of the subway line, B to E (or B to A but stops at any station) the terminal stations of the suburban railway, and B to A is the integrated peak-hour suburban railway station. Therefore, with this capability, passengers can travel continuously from the suburbs to the city center and stop at any station without having to change lines. At the same time, using suburban trains to meet the required number of trains during peak hours reduces the cost of purchasing train fleets. This is a typical example of integration: if the individual frequency for each type is 300s (a train appears at each station every 300s), then it will be 150s (a train appears at each station every 150s) when combined in an interleaved manner. If not integrated, relying on the combination of suburban trains stopping at all stations for the demand of subway transportation, the service frequency (headway) of the subway trains would need to be increased to

meet the demand, increasing the number of trains running on the section and the trains in reserve, which increases all related costs, such as purchasing trains, operation, maintenance, etc.

Fig. 1. The integrated train running chart during peak hours.

B. Load Calculation Method

There are many methods to calculate the design load for supplying electric traction power to subway or suburban railway systems [11-20]. However, these methods allow separate calculations for each system. For an integrated system, which is a combination of two systems with different capacities on the same power supply system, the difference is the train load, which is an important issue in load calculations. As the carrying capacities of subway and suburban railway systems are different, the train current used is also different. Correspondingly, the mechanical resistance (R_r), the acceleration resistance (R_a), acceleration, and operation speed are also different. The result is that the maximum instantaneous traction force for each train trip between two passenger stations is different. For a train to move, it needs to be provided with a basic force to change its velocity from a stationary state to motion with maximum acceleration. This force is called the necessary traction force (F_t) that must overcome the forces of mechanical resistance (F_{Rr}) and acceleration resistance (F_{Ra}) caused by the mass of the train (M) moving linearly on the track.

$$F_t = F_{Ra} + F_{Rr} \tag{1}$$

Equation (1) is also affected by additional or simultaneous different resistance components based on the railroad grade profile (F_{Rc} , F_{Rg} , F_{Rt}) on a power supply section of a traction substation (TPS). The maximum required traction force from (1) can be rewritten as follows:

$$F_{t-max} = F_{Ra} + \sum F_R \tag{2}$$

Figure 2 shows the number of trains appearing within the power supply radius of a traction substation based on the integrated train operation chart. With a service frequency of 150s, determined by the running speed and the power supply radius, there are always more than 4 trains operating continuously in both directions that require power supply. By relying on the service frequency (n_f - trains/hour/direction), running speed (v_{sc} - km/h), and power supply radius (DTPS - km), the total number of trains appearing within this range can be determined as n_k trains/direction. Therefore, the total train

load that the power needs to supply in both directions can be calculated.

Fig. 2. Peak hour integrated train operation diagram within the scope of a traction substation.

The weight of train x (M_x) during peak hours is calculated as the weight of the locomotive and the total weight of the cars, where n_x is the number of locomotives and m_x is the number of cars.

$$M_x = n_x \cdot M_{d,x} + m_x \cdot M_{c,x} \tag{3}$$

$$M_{d,x} = (p_{d,x} \cdot f_{s,d,x} \cdot S_{d,x} + f_{d,x}) \cdot m_p + m_{d,x} \tag{4}$$

$$M_{c,x} = (p_{c,x} \cdot f_{s,c,x} \cdot S_{c,x} + f_{c,x}) \cdot m_p + m_{c,x} \tag{5}$$

with criteria:

$$\begin{cases} 4 < p_{d,x} \leq 7, p/m^2 \\ 4 < p_{c,x} \leq 7, p/m^2 \\ 1 < n_x \leq 2, n_x \in Z_+ \\ 1 \leq m_x, m_x \in Z_+ \\ n_x \cdot l_{d,x} + m_x \cdot l_{c,x} \leq l_{st-min} \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

The weight of train y during peak hours is given by:

$$M_y = n_y \cdot M_{d,y} + m_y \cdot M_{c,y} \tag{7}$$

$$M_{d,y} = (p_{d,y} \cdot f_{s,d,y} \cdot S_{d,y} + f_{d,y}) \cdot m_p + m_{d,y} \tag{8}$$

$$M_{c,y} = (p_{c,y} \cdot f_{s,c,y} \cdot S_{c,y} + f_{c,y}) \cdot m_p + m_{c,y} \tag{9}$$

with criteria:

$$\begin{cases} 4 < p_{d,y} \leq 7, p/m^2 \\ 4 < p_{c,y} \leq 7, p/m^2 \\ 1 < n_y \leq 2, n_y \in Z_+ \\ 1 \leq m_y, m_y \in Z_+ \\ n_y \cdot l_{d,y} + m_y \cdot l_{c,y} \leq l_{st-min} \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

The components of train motion resistance within the power supply range of any traction substation i and along the j -th station route are:

Mechanical Resistance:

$$R_{r,x,y} = A + B \cdot v + C \cdot v^2 \quad (11)$$

Road curve [17]:

$$\begin{cases} R_{c,i,j} = \frac{650}{r-55}, r < 300 \\ R_{c,i,j} = \frac{500}{r-30}, r \geq 300 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Slope:

$$R_{g,i,j} = \pm G/1000 \quad (13)$$

Tunnel:

$$R_{t,i,j} = \frac{f_r \cdot v^2}{W} \quad (14)$$

Acceleration drag:

$$R_{a,x,y,i,j} = \frac{a \cdot \xi}{g} \quad (15)$$

The maximum resistance depends on the grade profile:

$$\begin{cases} \sum R_{i,j} = R_{c,i,j} + R_{g,i,j} + R_{t,i,j} \\ R_{max,i,j} \leq \sum R_{i,j} < R_a + R_r \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

The maximum instantaneous tractive force of trains x, y in each direction, within the supply range of a traction substation i and the route to the j^{th} station in the forward (h) and the backward directions (k) is:

$$F_{ii,j-kx,max} = M_x \cdot (R_{a,x} + R_{r,x} + \sum R_{max,j-kx}) \quad (17)$$

$$\sum R_{max,j-kx} = R_{c,j-kx} + R_{g,j-kx} + R_{t,j-kx} \quad (18)$$

$$F_{ii,j-hx,max} = M_x \cdot (R_{a,x} + R_{r,x} + \sum R_{max,j-hx}) \quad (19)$$

$$\sum R_{max,j-hx} = R_{c,j-hx} + R_{g,j-hx} + R_{t,j-hx} \quad (20)$$

$$F_{ii,j-ky,max} = M_x \cdot (R_{a,y} + R_{r,y} + \sum R_{max,j-ky}) \quad (21)$$

$$\sum R_{max,j-ky} = R_{c,j-ky} + R_{g,j-ky} + R_{t,j-ky} \quad (22)$$

$$F_{ii,j-hy,max} = M_x \cdot (R_{a,y} + R_{r,y} + \sum R_{max,j-hy}) \quad (23)$$

$$\sum R_{max,j-hy} = R_{c,j-hy} + R_{g,j-hy} + R_{t,j-hy} \quad (24)$$

Assuming that the integrated system operates with an equal service frequency for both x and y train lines on the route, the total maximum instantaneous traction force is determined based on the maximum instantaneous traction force in the power supply segment of an electric traction station in both directions, as follows:

$$\sum_{i=1}^l F_{ii,j,(na)max} = 2 \cdot \sum_{na, p_l \in i,j} P_{l,max} \cdot F_{ii,j\{kx,hx,ky,hy\},max} \quad (25)$$

In (24), it depends on the maximum allowable frequency $c_{l,max}$ of the transmission line:

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{na, p_l \in i,j} P_{l,max} = \frac{60}{c_{l,max}} \cdot \frac{D_{TPSi}}{v_{sc}} \\ 1.5 \leq c_{l,max} < c_{l,ME}, c_{l,max} = \frac{C_{p,max}}{C_{t,max}} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

If there is a power outage at any substation disrupting the power supply, then:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i+1} F_{ii,j,(er),max} = 2 \cdot \sum_{er, p_l \in i,j} P_{l,max} \cdot F_{ii,j\{kx,hx,ky,hy\},max} \quad (27)$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{er, p_l \in i,j} P_{l,max} = \frac{60}{c_{l,max}} \cdot \frac{1}{v_{sc}} \cdot \left[D_{TPSi} + \frac{D_{TPSi+1}}{2} \right] \\ 1.5 \leq c_{l,max} < c_{l,ME}, c_{l,max} = \frac{C_{p,max}}{C_{t,max}} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

Based on the force-velocity curve, the instantaneous maximum power requirement is calculated as a function of the force-velocity relationship. The power under normal operating conditions (na) and during an error (er) is:

$$P_{ii,j(na)max} = \sum_{i=1}^{P_{l(na),max}} F_{ii,j,(na)max} \cdot \frac{v}{3.6 \cdot \eta_{mc} \cdot \eta_{mt}} \quad (29)$$

$$P_{ii,j(er)max} = \sum_{i=1}^{P_{l(er),max}} F_{ii,j,(er)max} \cdot \frac{v}{3.6 \cdot \eta_{mc} \cdot \eta_{mt}} \quad (30)$$

with mechanical (η_{mc}) and motor efficiency (η_{mt}) conditions:

$$\begin{cases} \eta_{mc,min} < \eta_{mc} \leq \eta_{mc,max} \\ \eta_{mt,min} < \eta_{mt} \leq \eta_{mt,max} \\ v_{sc} < v \leq v_{peak} \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

The auxiliary consumption power used for purposes other than pulling force on each train type is calculated as follows:

$$P_{[x,y],i(na)aux} = \sum_{na, p_l \in i} P_{l,max} \cdot (n_{[x,y]} \cdot P_{d,[x,y]} + m_{[x,y]} \cdot P_{c,[x,y]}) \quad (32)$$

$$P_{[x,y],i(er)aux} = \sum_{er, p_l \in i} P_{l,max} \cdot (n_{[x,y]} \cdot P_{d,[x,y]} + m_{[x,y]} \cdot P_{c,[x,y]}) \quad (33)$$

The maximum power consumption under normal operating conditions and when an error occurred at station i are calculated as:

$$P_{TPSi(na)max} = P_{ii,j(na)max} + P_{[x,y],i(na)aux} \quad (34)$$

$$P_{TPSi(er)max} = P_{ii,j(er)max} + P_{[x,y],i(er)aux} \quad (35)$$

Equations (36) and (37) give the maximum power consumption required to be supplied if there is regenerative braking (energy returned during braking) under normal operating conditions and when an error occurs. The percentage of the energy recovered (η_{re}) depends on the frequency of service and the voltage of the traction system:

$$P_{TPSi(re, na)max} = P_{TPSi(na)max} (1 - \eta_{re}) \quad (36)$$

$$P_{TPSi(re, er)max} = P_{TPSi(er)max} (1 - \eta_{re}) \quad (37)$$

With the condition based on the type of service:

$$\begin{cases} \eta_{re,na,min} < \eta_{re[x,y]} \leq \eta_{re,na,max} \\ \eta_{re,er,min} < \eta_{re[x,y]} \leq \eta_{re,er,max} \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

the power selection for the traction substation is:

$$P_{TPSi(er,na)max} \leq P_{TPSi(na),min} \quad (39)$$

$$P_{TPSi(re,er)max} \leq P_{TPSi(re),min} \quad (40)$$

The power of the traction substation selected according to (35) and (36) must comply with the IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and the IEC 60146-1 standards.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. Load Parameters

TABLE I. THE PROFILE OF THE ROUTE FROM TRACTION SUBSTATION NO. 3 TO NO. 4 ALONG THE LINE

Km	TPSi	STj	G‰	C	Rt
10.0	SP	11			
11.00		12			
11.50			+35	650	
12.00		13			
12.40	3				
13.20		14			
13.70			+5	500	
14.00	SP				
14.40		15			
15.40		16	-5		17.14
15.80			-20		17.14
16.00	4				17.14
16.40		17			17.14
17.40		18			17.14

TABLE II. LOAD PARAMETERS

Symbol	Units	Value
C_{Lp1}	[p/h/d]	45,000
C_{Lp2}	[p/h/d]	54,000
$a_{x,max}/\beta_{x,max}$	[m/s ²]	0.9/1.0
$a_{y,max}/\beta_{y,max}$	[m/s ²]	0.85/1.0
R_{xx}, R_{yy}	[kg/ton]	
$R_x = 3.25 + 0.039 \cdot V + 0.000659 \cdot V^2$		
$R_y = 2.45 + 0.044 \cdot V + 0.000374 \cdot V^2$		
v_{sc}, v_{max}	[km/h]	45/60
Train load $I_x[A]$: $400 \cdot (4M) + 200 \cdot (2M) + 200 \cdot (2Mc)$		
Train load $I_y[A]$: $400 \cdot (4M) + 200 \cdot (1M) + 200 \cdot (2Mc)$		
Support load $I_{aux} [A]$: $25.3333 \cdot (6M) + 24 \cdot (2Mc)$		
Support load $I_{auy} [A]$: $26.6667 \cdot (5M) + 24 \cdot (2Mc)$		

TABLE III. TRAIN LOAD PARAMETERS

Symbol	Specifications	Description
$C_{pl,2}$	45,000; 54,000	Person/hour/direction
n_x, n_y	2; 2	Control car
m_x, m_y	6; 5	Locomotive unit
$m_{d,x,y}$	40 tons; 42 tons	Control car
$m_{c,x,y}, m_{c,x}, y$	38 tons; 41 tons	Locomotive unit
$S_{d,x}$	$3.2 \times 22m^2$	The floor area of a passenger car
$S_{c,x}$	$3.2 \times 23m^2$	Passenger area
$S_{d,y}$	$3.27 \times 25m^2$	The floor area of a passenger car
$S_{c,y}$	$3.27 \times 26m^2$	Passenger area
$f_{s,d,x,y}$	0.45%; 0.42%	Occupancy rate
$f_{s,c,x,y}$	0.55%; 0.45%	Occupancy rate
$f_{d,x}$	38 seats	Cabin seat
$f_{c,x}$	44 seats	Passenger seat
$f_{d,y}$	32 seats	Cabin seat
$f_{c,y}$	42 seats	Passenger seat
m_p	55kg	Weight/passenger

B. Load Calculation Process

The flowchart of the load calculation process is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the load calculation process.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Results of Load Calculations

The train parameters that have the carrying capacity to meet the demand of the line described in Table III are selected. The trains have the maximum passenger capacity including fixed seats and standing passengers of $7p/m^2$ in both stages. In stage 1, the demand for transportation is 45,000p/h/d and the supply capacity is 45,774p/h/d with a headway of 3p/t/d. In stage 2, the demand for transportation is 54,000p/h/d and the supply capacity is 54,929p/h/d with a headway of 2.5p/t/d. To meet the different demands in each stage in this design, the system only changes the service frequency (the time interval between train services) without changing the structure or carrying capacity. Therefore, with the maximum carrying capacity according to the stages, the subway train x weighs 224.97 tons and the suburban train y weighs 211.68 tons.

B. Calculation Results of Traction Force

Consider a section of the line between two traction substations with a complex railway track from station ST11 to ST18, as shown in Table I. Under normal operation, TPS3 supplies power from station ST11 to ST14, while TPS4 supplies power from station ST15 to ST18. Assuming that TPS4 experiences a disruption in its power supply, TPS3 will have to provide power to its section and a portion of the adjacent station, from station ST11 to ST16. The following scenarios may occur:

In case 1, the traction force and train speed curves vary depending on whether the train is moving in the direction of the power supply or the opposite one. In normal operation, when both TPS3 and TPS4 are supplying power to the trains, the maximum required traction force is reached when the trains

accelerate in both the forward and backward directions at the stations. The maximum required traction force for the outer suburban train $F_{y,na,max}$ is 205.69kN, and for the metro train $F_{x,na,max}$ is 233.46kN. In the event of a TPS4 power outage, TPS3 is required to supply power to the trains along its section as well as a part of the adjacent substation from ST11 to ST16. The maximum required traction force for the suburban train $F_{y,er,max}$ is 216.07kN, and for the metro train $F_{x,er,max}$ is 244.5kN. Overall, in case 1, the curves of traction force and train speed are relatively similar for both the outer suburban and metro trains. The maximum required traction force increases slightly in the event of a TPS4 power outage, but the difference is not significant. The train speed also changes slightly within the power supply range of a traction substation, but this change is not enough to impact the train operation.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the traction force and train speed curves within the power supply range of a traction substation in case 1.

In case 2, both TPS3 and TPS4 supply power to trains operating on the interacting section. The required traction force distribution in the described section is shown in Figure 5. Under normal operating conditions, TPS3 supplies power only to the traction force required when the train accelerates at the departure and arrival stations of the suburban train. The maximum required traction force for the suburban train $F_{y,na,max}$ is 205.69kN. In the event of a TPS3 malfunction, it must supply power to the required traction force for the train acceleration at the departure and arrival stations in the tunnel. The maximum required traction force for the suburban train $F_{y,er,max}$ is 216.07kN and for the subway train $F_{x,er,max}$ is 244.5kN. In terms of speed, when TPS4 is in normal operation, it supplies power to the trains in the described section. Therefore, the speed curve is smooth and not affected by the power supply. However, in the event of a TPS4 malfunction,

the power supply to the trains in this section will be affected, which may result in a decrease in their speed.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the force and speed curves of trains within the power supply range of an electric traction station in case 2.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the results of a study on a method for calculating the maximum instantaneous pulling force to predict the instantaneous power consumption of loads for the design of power stations in integrated subway train models - MCR. The method was designed and simulated using Matlab R2017b/Railway Systems software, with a variety of load cases for maximum power consumption during peak hours in different stages and different situations to demonstrate its reliability. In addition, the method also demonstrates transparency and logic in calculating data according to a sequence with filtering and comparison for contingency situations to avoid power wastage. The calculated power compared to the minimum and maximum load requirements was 14.67% and 21.81%, which is suitable for station power that meets the standards of IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and IEC 60146-1 for redundancy coefficients. Finally, the proposed method of calculation is a reliable and cost-effective scientific approach in the study of designing the power supply for subway trains.

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Controlling Employability Issues of Computing Science Graduates through Machine Learning-Based Detection and Identification

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ABSTRACT

The unemployment rate of graduate students in the area of computing is tremendously growing. One of the main reasons is the difference between the acquired skills from universities and the skills required from industry which is looking for potential graduates who can work in the digitally transforming framework of today's society. Many studies have been conducted to emphasize the issue of unemployment utilizing traditional approaches. However, these methods are time-consuming and difficult to bring into effect, while involving a lot of effort, which had no definite influence or impact on the studies to date. Hence, this study proposes a predictive artificial intelligent model through the use of a conceptual framework called Intelligent Collaborative Framework, addressing the gap between university computing graduates and the industry needs. This model is achieved via machine learning classifiers to recognize the issue and solve the problem between university computing graduates' and employers' expectations. In addition, the study identifies the required skills for computing graduate students to be employed in the industry. Several experiments were conducted using a dataset gathered from two computing departments and through a survey done among the graduates. The experiment results show that the ADA, SVM, and LR outperform the other classifiers. The model performance accuracy reached 89% for F1-Score. In addition, the best features (computing and training courses) were identified using the SelectKBest. The mutual information gain can assist in quickly obtaining jobs.

Keywords-machine learning; computing graduates; employability; industry skills

I. INTRODUCTION

The unemployment issue has arisen due to the mismatch between the labor market needs and the skills, competencies, and knowledge of university graduates [1-4]. The labor market requires high skills to be developed in graduates to cope with the fast technological advancement. For example, some governments in the gulf area enforce the employment of local people, and the companies fail that request due to the skills needed for vacant jobs [5, 6]. Many studies have highlighted the employability issue and have given attention to the gap between the insufficient supply of skilled graduates and the demand of the market in many countries such Sri Lanka [7], USA [8], China [9-10], Tanzania [12], Europe [13-16], India [17], Ghana [18], Malaysia [6, 19-21], Russia [22], Vietnam [23], Nigeria [24], and Saudi Arabia [5, 11, 25-33]. The university curriculum needs to be updated in order to cover the technological advancements and required competencies [34, 35]. Authors in [17] highlighted the gap between the engineering graduates and the market needs in India by focusing on training the graduates in order to join the industry with market needed skills. In the same way, authors in [18] suggested conducting an awareness session about this issue.

Authors in [35] focused on closing the gap between software engineering graduates and the job industry's needs, by proposing the adoption of better teaching methods (universities) on soft skills and better hiring efforts (employers). In [23], focus is given on the evaluation of university graduates from their managers based on graduate capabilities, skills and knowledge through surveys. Authors in [22] raise the attention on highly qualified scientific and technical professionals in the job market of robotics where the demands are not met. Authors in [21] highlighted the issue of employability for Malaysian graduates in the IR 4.0 industrial revolution. They attempted to solve this issue by proposing a framework called the Learning Factory (LF). In [36], a machine learning approach in Spain was conducted to test the predictions made for the changes in future job needs in order to prepare the students more adequately. Authors in [37] considered the gap between the job market of business analytics and the graduates. Authors in [38] proposed enhancing the graduates' skills through authentic learning approaches in order to reduce the percentage of unemployment in Europe. Authors in [24] examined what the Labor Market (LM) actually demands from the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and how the demands of the LM can be met by the HEIs in Nigeria. Authors in [39] inspected the HEIs in Nigeria

to get a better understanding about why there is a large percentage of unemployed graduates. Authors in [16] studied the relationship between learning and real practice in the industry finding a gap between them. Authors in [17] highlighted the impact of the curriculum and learning outcomes on graduates on the LM and investigated the relationship between higher education and industry. Moreover, authors in [18], suggest that the accounting curriculum in Saudi universities is required to be updated.

In Saudi Arabia, the Ministry of Higher Education has significantly improved the monitoring of the education process at a national level by introducing an organization called NCAA that monitors the progress of the academic programs in universities [13]. Practical courses make the graduates high skilled, as required by the industry. In addition, authors in [13] state that the graduates should have skills and knowledge and such elements have to add to the course learning outcomes. Such a way can be beneficial to the LM and authors in [19] introduce an appropriate framework. Techniques and presentation skills can be acquired through interpersonal and strategic competencies. Authors in [15, 20] demonstrate the importance of the English language courses that are fundamental in the job market. Authors in [40, 41] focused on unemployment issues and the mismatch of graduates with the market needs.

The main motivation for this study is the massive unemployment among university graduates [17, 18]. Limited attention has been given in enhancing and updating the curriculum of computer studies while no attention has been given in providing a comprehensive solution to solve the unemployment issue of graduates using artificial intelligence approaches. Based on our findings, a list of the desirable topics that should be reflected in the course plan of computer studies (computer science and information technology) was created. Besides, the experiments provide a full picture of the mismatch between the academic program characteristics, the employment potential, and the expectations of the employers. Furthermore, an intelligent collaborative framework bridging university computing graduates and the industry to provide valuable advice through a friendly visualization environment is needed. This environment provides a list of desirable skills that are required in the LM to be in the computer science course plan. In such a way, an intelligent collaborative framework for bridging the gap between university computing graduates and the industry needs will reduce the unemployment rate of graduate students from computer science programs and give knowledge to the top management of that department of the required critical steps. The main contribution of this paper can be summarized in the following:

- The employability issue of computing students and the market needs are explored globally.
- A machine learning model is proposed to detect and identify if the graduate can get employed quickly or not. In addition, the impact of training courses on the computing graduate students is measured.
- A novel dataset for computing graduate students is introduced.

- Feature selection methods are applied on the proposed model and the employability dataset.
- The results of commonly used machine learning classifiers are compared.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section explains the conceptual framework and the phases, data collection, data cleaning, filtering, machine learning model, and model evaluation, that are were used to carry out this study (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Phases of the proposed model.

A. Data Collection

This is the initial phase of the proposed model. In this phase, the data collected are divided into 3 stages. In the first stage, five experts examined the core course of computing based on the international standards, bench marks from international universities, and the curriculum of computer science of four universities. The core courses were identified and listed. Based on these courses, in the second stage, computing graduate marks were collected from graduates from two universities, 2-5 years after their graduation. In the third stage, a survey was sent to these graduates and the results were analyzed. The total number of surveyed graduates was 486 while the number of received surveys was only 277 as shown in Figure 2. This process is performed annually as a procedure of academic quality and development.

Employability

Fig. 2. Employability.

Training Courses

Fig. 3. Graduate and training courses.

Figure 3 illustrates the number of graduate took and did not take training courses. Figure 4 shows the statistics on the total number of graduates that took training courses in Machine Learning (ML), Data Science (DS), Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The majority of courses that were taken by the graduates were ML and AI.

Fig. 4. University graduates and training courses.

B. Data Cleaning and Filtering

As an input from the previous phases, the data have been cleaned. In addition, the data of graduate students were merged with the graduate survey. The dataset was constructed at this stage with 29 features, from which 25 are computing courses and 4 are training courses. The average marks of the computing courses of the graduates are shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Average marks in the computing courses.

C. Baseline Machine Learning Classifiers

The utilized ML classifiers were identified in this stage, based on their popularity. These classifiers are k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Logistic Regression (LR), Naive Bayes (NB), Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB), Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), AdaBoost (ADA), and Gradient Boosting (GB) [42, 43].

D. Feature Selection Methods

In order to reduce the number of features and to identify the most important among them that effect employability, feature selection took place. The most common techniques used are SelectKBest and mutual information gain. In SelectKBest, selection is conducted on the highest correlated features to the independent variable (Class/Y) using the chi2 score function. The mutual information is a statistical method used to calculate the dependence between two features and then sort them in order to select the most correlated features.

E. Model Evaluation

This section describes the most common methods used to measure the model performance. These measures are Precision, Recall, F1-Score, and Accuracy [44] and are used in this study. The relevant equations are (1)-(4). In addition, the Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) and confusion matrices were used.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \tag{2}$$

$$\text{F1 - Score} = \frac{2*(\text{Precision}*\text{Recall})}{\text{Precision}+\text{Recall}} \tag{3}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \tag{4}$$

where TP stands for True Positive, TN for True Negative, FP for False Positive, and FN for False Negative.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the carried-out experiments based on the common used ML classifiers to identify the employability of computing course graduates and if the training courses influence hiring after graduation. These experiments were based on a set of settings and hyper-parameters. The ML classifiers used were ADA, DT, GB, kNN, LR, NB, NB, SGD, SVM, RF, and XGB. The experimental results are shown in Table II. All the experiments were carried out using Keras on Tensor flow architecture and Python programing language. The SKlearn library was utilized to train the proposed model using the aforementioned ML classifiers. Figure 6 demonstrates the results of the experiments and shows the model performance in terms of Accuracy. The experimental results show that LR and SVM scored the highest recorded accuracy of 87% and 86%, respectively, while kNN and SGD scored the worst with 48% and 54%, respectively. Also, SVM, LR, and GB scored the highest average Precision and Recall values, ranging between 85% to 88%, while kNN had the worst score of 47% as shown in Figures 7 and 8. The AUC is shown in Figures 9 and 10.

Fig. 6. Accuracy of the ML classifiers.

Fig. 7. Average Recall of the ML classifiers.

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF THE ML CLASSIFIERS IN IDENTIFYING THE EMPLOYABILITY ISSUE.

MI Classifies	Classes	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
ADA	0	0.882353	0.769231	0.821918
	1	0.816327	0.909091	0.860215
DT	0	0.789474	0.769231	0.779221
	1	0.8	0.818182	0.808989
GB	0	0.909091	0.769231	0.833333
	1	0.82	0.931818	0.87234
KNN	0	0.441176	0.384615	0.410959
	1	0.510204	0.568182	0.537634
LR	0	0.891892	0.846154	0.868421
	1	0.869565	0.909091	0.888889
MNB	0	0.909091	0.769231	0.833333
	1	0.82	0.931818	0.87234
NB	0	0.9	0.692308	0.782609
	1	0.773585	0.931818	0.845361
SGD	0	1	0.025641	0.05
	1	0.536585	1	0.698413
XGB	0	0.861111	0.794872	0.826667
	1	0.829787	0.886364	0.857143
RF	0	0.903226	0.717949	0.8
	1	0.788462	0.931818	0.854167
SVM	0	0.888889	0.820513	0.853333
	1	0.851064	0.909091	0.879121

Fig. 8. Average Precision of the ML classifiers.

Fig. 9. AUC of the ML classifiers.

Fig. 10. AUC of ML classifiers.

The highly correlated features have been identified using the SelectKbest and mutual information gain. Some of the experimental values with zero means showed that there is no

relation between the dependent variable and features which means that they are not correlated. These results determine the most important features which are the desired courses in the industry. The results show that the training courses and the practical courses in the computing curriculum have the highest correlations as shown in Figures 12 and 13 for SelectKBest and mutual information respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed machine learning models to identify whether computing graduates have been employed after graduation or not. The models were trained on a dataset that was introduced and validated by experts in the area of computing. This problem is considered as a binary classification with two classes, i.e. employed and not employed. The machine learning classifiers were trained and assessed with Precision, Recall, F1-Score and Area Under the ROC Curve. In addition, feature selection techniques were utilized in order to determine the most important courses (features) that can affect the employability of university graduates in the areas of computing. The highest model performance was achieved with KNN, LR, and VSM and reached 89%.

The experimental results show that the computing curriculum must be extended with more practical courses and topics about emerging technologies such as dataset science, machine learning, and natural language processing. In the future, the dataset could be extended and more records of graduates could be used. Also, a visual representation of the recommendations could be designed.

Fig. 11. Most important courses using SelectKBest.

Fig. 12. Most important courses using mutual information.

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AB-MTEDeep Classifier Trained with AAGAN for the Identification and Classification of Alopecia Areata

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is widely used in dermatology to analyze trichoscopy imaging and assess Alopecia Areata (AA) and scalp hair problems. From this viewpoint, the Attention-based Balanced Multi-Tasking Ensembling Deep (AB-MTEDeep) network was developed, which combined the Faster Residual Convolutional Neural Network (FRCNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network with cross residual learning to classify scalp images into different AA classes. This article presents a new data augmentation model called AA-Generative Adversarial Network (AA-GAN) to produce a huge number of images from a set of input images. The structure of AA-GAN and its loss functions are comparable to those of standard GAN, which encompasses a generator and a discriminator network. To generate high-quality AA structure-based images, the generator was trained to extract the 2D orientation and confidence maps along with the bust depth map from real hair and scalp images. The discriminator was also used to separate real from generated images, which were provided as feedback to the generator to create synthetic images that are extremely close to the real input images. The created images were used to train the AB-MTEDeep model for AA classification. Finally, the experimental results exhibited that the AA-GAN-AB-MTEDeep achieved 96.94% accuracy.

Keywords-artificial intelligence; Alopecia Areata; deep learning; data augmentation; GAN

I. INTRODUCTION

Hair loss or scalp problems are usually caused by stressful situations [1]. Nowadays, many individuals have scalp illnesses like psoriasis, baldness, etc., as a result of several issues, including bad daily routines, unequal weight growth, extreme weariness, and dangerous environments [2-3]. The function of iron and nutritional supplements in the diagnosis of baldness was examined in [4]. The most common kind of hair loss, known as Alopecia Areata (AA), affects up to 70% of men and 40% of women [5]. Problems with scalp hair can be influenced by internal factors such as endocrine, hereditary, illness, and others. Many cases of psoriasis, cellulitis, and associated signs and symptoms were reported in France [6]. According to many studies, psoriasis affects about 18% of children in the US and Australia. As a result, both adults and children might experience scalp problems. Therefore, it is important to know how to properly manage the scalp and prevent diseases linked to baldness. Recently, specialized therapies have emerged to address severe scalp disorders [7].

The state of a patient's scalp is assessed manually in the most frequently used analytical processes for treating baldness. However, these manual diagnostic examinations can provide a wide range of findings and raise questions about the diagnosis and health of the scalp since they depend on the skills of the physiotherapist [8]. A substantial amount of effort and money have been invested in continuously developing physiotherapy skill sets [9]. Another significant problem is the variations in how scalp hair microscope pictures should be interpreted, even among licensed and experienced physiotherapists. Such discrepancies in medical interventions might be attributed to ignorance [10].

ScalpEye [11] is a deep learning-based scalp identification system developed to overcome these issues. A minority of people experience a patch of hair loss, while other people report more severe or uncommon issues [12]. In recent years, numerous scalp and dermoscopic images have been employed in recognizing and diagnosing AA. Trichoscopy and biopsies are frequently necessary to identify and diagnose AA as the reason for hair loss [13]. One of the main problems with these diagnostics is the number of tests required for a reliable

diagnosis. Additional research on AA diagnosis and detection using AI methods, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and others, is highly encouraged [14]. According to this perspective, a correct diagnosis requires the simultaneous recognition of AA and scalp condition. To achieve this, an Ensemble Parameter Optimized LSTM-based Pre-learned DL (EPOLSTM-PDL) model, which combined LSTM and pre-trained CNNs such as AlexNet, ResNet, and InceptionNet was proposed in [15]. The pre-trained CNNs were used to capture the deep features from the hair and scalp images, which were learned by the LSTM network. The LSTM's hyperparameters were chosen by the Battle Royale Optimization (BRO) algorithm. But, if the network depth is increased, degradation problem occurs causing overfitting. Therefore, the Attention-based Balanced Multi-Tasking Ensembling Deep (AB-MTEDeep) model was developed, which adopted cross-residual learning in the LSTM with FRCNN to improve efficiency [16]. However, the robustness and generalization ability of the deep learning models largely depends on the amount of data available in the training phase. According to this, it is essential to have an adequate number of images for efficient training.

This paper proposes a new data augmentation model called AA-GAN to generate a large number of images from given input images. The design and loss functions of this AA-GAN are analogous to those of the standard GAN, which comprises both a generator and a discriminator. For real hair and scalp images, the generator was trained to reconstruct high-quality AA structure-based images according to the extraction of the 2D orientation and confidence maps, along with a bust depth map. Moreover, the discriminator was used to distinguish real and generated images which were given as feedback to the generator to generate synthetic images very closer to the real input images. Furthermore, the created images were used to train the AB-MTEDeep model, which was used to classify the test images into different AA classes. Thus, the AA-GAN can increase the number of training images for more effective classification of AA conditions.

II. RELATED WORKS

In [17], a novel data augmentation method was proposed, called Random Image Cropping and Patching (RICAP), which randomly cropped and patched an input image to generate a new training image for CNN. Also, the class labels of the actual images were mixed to gain the benefit of soft labels. However, it needed to choose the appropriate hyperparameters for effective performance. In [18], the presented StyleGAN was used to generate high-quality nodule images fed to the Transfer-ResNet50 to classify tumors, but it needed further enhancement in the diversity of the created images. In [19], an Enhanced Framework of GANs (EF-GANs) was designed for VGG16, integrating geometric transformation schemes and GANs for image augmentation. In [20], the Self-attention Progressive Growing of GANs (SPGGANs) was proposed to create more fine-grained nodule scans by fusing details from all feature positions, and the Two-Timescale Update Rule (TTUR) was applied to enhance the model's robustness. In [21], the Zero Shot Augmentation Learning (ZSAL) framework was

presented for health signal processing. Initially, the contour of a lesion was recognized by a skilled physician, and a background image without a lesion was chosen. In [22], a novel Inception-Augmentation GAN (IAGAN) was proposed to create new X-ray scans that could help detect pneumonia and COVID-19. In [23], a generic adversarial data augmentation model called AdvChain was proposed to enhance the diversity and efficiency of learning data for medical image segmentation. In [24], a new model called XtremeAugment was developed for labeling and augmenting images, using Hardware Dataset Augmentation (HAD) and Object-Based Augmentation (OBA). The HAD was used to enable users to acquire more data, whereas the OBA was used to increase the training data variability and maintain the distribution of the augmented images being similar to the actual data. But, this approach needed annotated images for efficient training and was not effective with very limited images.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 presents an overall schematic of the proposed AA-GAN.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the proposed study.

A. Image Collection

This system used the following 2 openly accessible datasets for analysis:

- Figaro1k dataset, which is a public dataset enclosing 1050 hair photos, evenly allocated into distinct types like straight, wavy, and curly [25].
- Dermnet dataset, which is a public dataset accessible on Dermnet [26], enclosing 23 types of dermatological illnesses with AA. Overall, 108 photos were obtained for 3 distinct AA types: mild, moderate, and severe.

Figure 2 shows a few examples of scalp hair photos in multiple labels from the given databases.

Fig. 2. Scalp hair photo examples of the Dermnet and Figaro1k databases.

B. Data Preparation for AA-GAN

A fused model space was initially defined to create the training dataset. At first, a bounding box was defined as the boundary of the model space, where the ground-truth 3D hair orientation volume was generated and 2D hair orientation and confidence maps were extracted.

Bounding box: The model space was constrained by a bounding box defined by the bust model and each hair model of the dataset, excluding a few extremely long hairs. After that, a 3D volume with a resolution of $128 \times 128 \times 128$ was split in the bounding box.

2D capture: To obtain 2D information maps X under the defined model space, the center of the image plane matched with the center of the bounding box. The 2D image was obtained by orthogonal projection with a scale of $1024/H$. So, the dimension of the obtained image was 1024×1024 .

After that, the dataset was doubled by flipping all models, and constrained hairstyles such as braids and bounds were eliminated. In the considered dataset, 1050 hairstyles were available, which differ from straight to curly and short to long. The hair around the center of the bounding box was rotated arbitrarily. The rotation ranged from -15° to 15° for the X -axis, -30° to 30° for the Y -axis, and -20° to 20° for the Z -axis. As each dataset model was prepared by polygon strips, they were transformed to a dense 3D orientation volume viewed as the ground truth Y and grew strands later. Afterward, the hair strands were rendered to the 2D image at the camera view pose. Additionally, the bust model was considered a condition for AA-GAN because hair grows on the scalp and circulates the body. The bust depth map was determined by ray tracing, pixel by pixel, to obtain the distance from the bust to the camera, and

the distance was split by D to vary the value within $[0,1]$. Finally, the network input X was created using the 2D orientation map, confidence map, and bust depth map. Every 2D map was valued within $[0,1]$ and the 3D and 2D orientation vectors were encoded in color space. For all dataset models, N pairs of X and Y were determined as training data.

C. Design and Training of Alopecia Areata – Generative Adversarial Network

With the 2D maps and the bust depth map captured from the input image, AA-GAN aimed to create a 3D orientation volume encoding both occupancy and orientation data to guide the AA scalp hair image augmentation. The input of the network was a 2D tensor X with a dimension of 1024×1024 , consisting of 4 feature channels, which were acquired in the unified model space: hair orientation map (the 2D direction vector XY encoded as the color of RG), confidence map (the confidence value as the color of gray), and bust depth map (the depth value as the color of gray). The output was a 3D tensor Y of dimension $128 \times 128 \times 96$, where the hair orientation vectors were encoded in RGB.

1) Loss Functions

The GAN is trained by the game-theory approach between the generator and discriminator. The aim was to train the generator $G(X)$ that maps the input 2D tensor to a required output 3D tensor $\tilde{Y}: \tilde{Y} = G(X)$. Meanwhile, the discriminator maximizes the Wasserstein-1 distance between the generator distribution of $G(X)$ and the target distribution of Y with a conditional latent projection $P(X)$. The objective of the discriminator is to reduce the loss as:

$$L_D = \mathbb{E} [D(\tilde{Y}, P(X))] - \mathbb{E} [D(Y, P(X))] + \lambda \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\|\nabla_{\tilde{Y}} D(\tilde{Y}, P(X))\|_2 - 1 \right)^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

where the third term is the gradient penalty for random samples \tilde{Y} , that $\tilde{Y} \leftarrow \epsilon Y + (1 - \epsilon) \tilde{Y}$, and ϵ is a random number in $[0,1]$. The coefficient λ was set to 10, $P(\cdot)$ is the CNN to map 2D tensor X into a 3D latent space to be combined with Y or \tilde{Y} , and the parameters in $P(\cdot)$ are trained along with those of D . Similarly, the loss function for a generator is described by:

$$L_G = -\mathbb{E} [D(\tilde{Y}, P(X))] \quad (2)$$

This function does not perform well to fine-tune the generator, because the distribution variance between the actual and the counterfeit cannot be simply calculated by the plus or minus signs. According to the fact that only selected layers of pre-learned networks are used as feature representations to transfer texture style from a source to the target image, the losses of style and content were adopted, where the features were defined in the domains of selected discriminator layers. So, the objective of fine-tuning the generator was to reduce the loss:

$$L_G^* = \alpha L_{content} + \beta L_{style} = \alpha \sum_l L_{content}^l + \beta \sum_l L_{style}^l \quad (3)$$

where α and β are the weighting factors. The content loss was taken as the square-error loss between feature representations:

$$L_{content}^l = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{ik} \left[f_{ik}^l(Y, P(X)) - f_{ik}^l(\tilde{Y}, P(X)) \right]^2 \quad (4)$$

where l is a selected layer, i is the i^{th} feature map, k is the index in the feature tensor, and f describes the discriminator features. The style loss is defined by the mean-squared distance between the Gram matrices, where all elements were computed by the inner product between the vectorized feature maps i and j : $A_{ij}^l = \sum_k f_{ik}^l f_{jk}^l$. The objective was:

$$L_{style}^l = \frac{1}{4N_l^2 M_l^2} \sum_{ij} \left[A_{ij}^l(Y, P(X)) - A_{ij}^l(\tilde{Y}, P(X)) \right]^2 \quad (5)$$

where N_l was the number of feature maps and M_l was the size of feature tensors.

2) Design

Table I shows the generator and discriminator structures. The following notations were used to define the structure of the proposed AA-GAN: The input and output data for the processing units are $in(resolution, feature\ channels)$ and $out(resolution, feature\ channels)$, $C(input\ channels, output\ channels, stride)$ is the convolutional layer with a ReLU activation, ϖ is the dimensional expansion layer, and ζ is the fully connected node. Also, $+$ was used as the element-wise addition in the residual blocks created by C , and I was the input tensor of the current layer. For each 2D convolutional layer C_2 , the filter size was 5 and 3 for each 3D convolutional layer C_3 . The processing units for X-, Y-, and Z-info contain similar strategies.

TABLE I. GENERATOR AND DISCRIMINATOR STRUCTURE

Generator		$in(1024 \times 1024, 4) \Leftarrow X$ $C_2(4, 16, 2) + [C_2(4, 8, 2), C_2(8, 16, 1)]$ $C_2(16, 64, 2) + [C_2(16, 32, 2), C_2(32, 64, 1)]$ $C_2(64, 256, 1) +$ $[C_2(64, 128, 2), C_2(128, 256, 1)]$ $I + [C_2(256, 256, 1), C_2(256, 256, 1)]$ $out(128 \times 128, 256)$
X-, Y-, Z-blocks		$in(128 \times 128, 256)$ $I + [C_2(256, 256, 1), C_2(256, 256, 1)]$ $I + [C_2(256, 256, 1), C_2(256, 256, 1)]$ $C_2(256, 128, 1)$ $C_2(128, 96, 1)$ ϖ $out(128 \times 128 \times 96, 1)$
Concatenation of the out from X-, Y-, Z-blocks		$in(128 \times 128 \times 96, 3)$ $I + [C_3(3, 3, 1), C_3(3, 3, 1)]$ $I + [C_3(3, 3, 1), C_3(3, 3, 1)]$ $out(128 \times 128 \times 96, 3) \Rightarrow \tilde{Y}$
Discriminator	P(·) block	$in(1024 \times 1024, 4) \Leftarrow X$ $C_2(4, 32, 2)$ $C_2(32, 64, 2)$ $C_2(128, 96, 1)$ ϖ $out(128 \times 128 \times 96, 1)$
	Concatenation of \tilde{Y}/Y with P(X)	$in(128 \times 128 \times 96, 4)$ $C_3(4, 32, 2)$ $C_3(32, 64, 2)$ $C_3(64, 128, 2)$ $C_3(126, 256, 2)$ $C_3(256, 512, 2)$ ζ

Generator: The initial block with input X , consisting of 4 residual network elements-wisely adding activation from the previous layer to successive layers to obtain a residual

correction from high- to low-level data, downsamples feature maps to a latent code from 1024×1024 to 128×128 , along with the number of features increasing from 4 to 256. After that, X-, Y-, and Z-blocks independently encode the latent code to features with 96 channels and the resolution along the Z-axis in the resulting volume. As well, ϖ transforms the series of 2D features into a single channel of 3D features. Then, the output from X-, Y-, and Z-blocks are concatenated and given to the following 3D residual convolutional networks.

Discriminator: Considering the correspondence between the 2D input X and the 3D desired output \tilde{Y}/Y , the latter was concatenated with $P(X)$, a feature map encoding X to a 3D latent space with a similar resolution as \tilde{Y}/Y . Subsequently, the concatenated 3D feature tensor was convoluted by several filters until the layer of ζ to finally differentiate the actual and ϖ counterfeit.

3) Learning Policy

The two-timescale update rule was applied to optimize the discriminator only once rather than many times, increasing time efficiency. The ADAM optimizer was applied with $\beta_1 = 0$, and $\beta_2 = 0.9$ for training. The training rate for the discriminator was set at 0.0003, and 0.0001 for the generator. This proposed AA-GAN was designed to create a $128 \times 128 \times 96$ 3D volume encoded in both the occupancy and orientation fields, utilizing 2D maps as input with a size of 1024×1024 . The batch size for learning was set to 5. For the generator objective, the style and content weighting factors were set as: $\alpha = 1e - 2$ and $\beta/\alpha = 5e + 2$.

The selected layers for content loss were 0, 3, 6, and $l=0, 1, 2, 3, 4$ for style loss. If $l=0$, $P(X)$ was eliminated from $L_{content}^0$ and L_{style}^0 . Thus, by training the AA-GAN, more training images were generated and used to train the AB-MTEDeep classifier model. The trained classifier was applied to classify the test images into the mild, moderate, and severe AA classes.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The effectiveness of the AA-GAN-AB-MTEDeep model was assessed and compared with the ones of existing models by implementing them in MATLAB 2017b using the Figaro1k and Dermnet databases. Of the images collected, 70% was used for training and the remaining 30% was used for testing. The considered existing models were the AB-MTEDeep [16], RICAP-CNN [17], EF-GAN-VGG16 [19], and IAGAN [22], which were applied to the Figaro1k and Dermnet databases for the AA classification, using the same proportions for the training and testing of the models. Figure 3 shows the generator and discriminator loss curves in the AA-GAN model, while Figure 4 depicts the training progress of the AA-GAN-AB-MTEDeep model for AA classification. Table II presents the confusion matrix for the AA-GAN-AB-MTEDeep model for testing, and Table III presents the performance results of the models for AA classification.

Figure 5 illustrates the accuracy values of various data augmentations with classification models on the Dermnet and Figaro1k databases. The accuracy of the AA-GAN-AB-

MTEDeep was 17.6% higher than RICAP-CNN's, 14% higher than the EF-GAN-VGG16's, 8.6% higher than the IAGAN's, and 1.9% higher than that of the AB-MTEDeep model. This is due to the augmentation of the number of training images to create an effective classification model.

Fig. 3. Loss curve for generator and discriminator during training.

Fig. 4. Training progress of the AA-GAN-AB-MTEDeep model for AA classification (training accuracy curve and loss curve).

TABLE II. CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE AA-GAN-AB-MTEDEEP TESTING

Actual	Classified				
	Classes	0	1	2	3
	0	29	0	1	0
1	0	7	0	0	
2	1	0	9	0	
3	0	0	0	9	

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS FOR THE AA CLASSIFICATION MODELS ON FIGARO1K AND DERMNET

Metrics	RICAP-CNN	EF-GAN-VGG16	IAGAN	AB-MTEDeep	AA-GAN-AB-MTEDeep
Precision (%)	81.48	84.05	88.19	94.06	95.8
Recall (%)	82.22	84.68	88.46	95.3	96.8
F-measure (%)	81.85	84.365	88.325	94.68	96.3
Accuracy (%)	82.31	84.86	89.22	95.11	96.94

Fig. 5. Accuracy of AA-GAN-AB-MTEDeep and existing models.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presented the AA-GAN model designed to generate a large number of training images for AA classification. In this model, the structure and loss functions were similar to those of the standard GAN, which involves the generator and the discriminator network. The generator network was trained to create high-quality images based on the AA structure by retrieving the 2D orientation and confidence maps, along with the bust depth map from the original hair and scalp images. The discriminator was trained to distinguish original from synthetic images, which was given as feedback to the generator for minimizing its error. Furthermore, the generated synthetic images were used to train the AB-MTEDeep model for AA classification. The test results showed that the AA-GAN-AB-MTEDeep had a 96.94% accuracy, which was higher than the ones of the other variants of GAN with the AB-MTEDeep model to classify AA and scalp conditions. In the future, hybrid deep learning models with hyperparameter optimizers can be developed to improve AA classification performance.

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Buckling Analysis of Porous Functionally Graded Plates

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the buckling behavior of Porous Functionally Graded Material (PFGM) plates. The present model assumes unevenly distributed porosity along the plate thickness and the use of the novel hyperbolic shear deformation functions and hyperbolic tangent and secant thickness stretching functions. In the present work, a porous Functionally Graded (FG) plate was analyzed by the principle of virtual work in order to understand the buckling behavior under uniaxial and biaxial compressive loading. The Rayleigh quotient method was applied to find the critical buckling load. The mesh convergence was investigated on a Finite Element (FE) model, and the accuracy of the results was compared with the prior research. The results of the proposed model match reasonably well with the ones of the published literature. Thorough parametric studies were performed to investigate the effect of porosity on the critical buckling load of the PFGM plate.

Keywords-FG porous plate; finite element method; buckling load; porosity

I. INTRODUCTION

The expansion of modern society's infrastructure has created the need for new smart building materials, which ought to be more readily available, safer, and more ecologically friendly. Numerous investigations on Functionally Graded Material (FGM) beams, plates, and shells have been carried out [1, 2]. Structures with graded porosity have inserted pores into the microstructure to satisfy the required structural performance by customizing the local density of the structure, are one of the most recent innovations in FGM. FGM has a progressive change in composition along the volume, which causes gradual changes in the mechanical material's characteristics. In a variety of technical applications, PFGMs have significant potential. For instance, graded metal foam presents special promise for lightweight construction in the civil, automotive, and aerospace industries [3, 4]. Additionally, PFGMs are the ideal choice for structures under dynamic or impact loads due to their great energy-absorbing capacity [5, 6]. Despite its practical significance, research in this developing field is still in its infancy and fairly sparse, with the majority of earlier work focused on the compression behavior [7, 8]. For the porous materials model, a progressive change in material characteristics results from the change in porosity over the thickness direction of the structures. So, scientists and

researchers have paid much attention to structures composed of porous-cellular materials [9].

In order to investigate more the annular sectorial porous plates' respond to evenly distributed in-plane compressive pressure in terms of buckling and vibration, authors in [10] suggested an analytical method. Many shear deformation theories have been proposed, using various shape functions, and assumptions to developed high-order shear theory (HSDT) using a sinusoidal function for FG sandwich members [11-13]. Using classical plate theory, authors in [14] examined the buckling modes of rectangular FG plates subjected to in-plane stress. Mechanical and thermal loads were applied on FG circular plates, and nonlinear bending and post-buckling behavior were analyzed by Von Karman nonlinearity. The result shows that FG plates have good resistance against thermal load or a combination of mechanical and thermal loads than the fully metallic plates [15]. The post-buckling behavior of imperfect nanobeams formed of metal foam with different porosity distributions was studied in [16]. Authors in [17, 18] used the traditional plate theory to examine thermal and mechanical buckling of FG circular plates constructed of porous material. Buckling analysis of FG plates with two different kinds of thermal loads was discussed in [19]. Authors in [20] investigated the impact of evenly and unevenly distributed porosity on the critical buckling load in the FG plates and constructed a mathematical model.

The current work investigates the uniaxial and biaxial compression behavior of PFGM plates using hyperbolic shear deformation functions and hyperbolic tangent and secant thickness stretching functions. There is a need to develop a simple two-dimensional model to analyze the buckling behavior of porous FGM plates. Hence, in the current work, a C_0 FE model is created based on the new mathematical model for simplifying buckling analysis. The FE model was tested for convergence and the obtained results were validated with the literature. The buckling behavior was investigated parametrically to examine the effect of porosity with variations of the side to thickness ratio.

II. FORMULATION

A. Geometry of the Porous FG Plate

Figure 1 shows the geometrical characteristics of the porous FG plate whose length, width, and thickness are a , b , and h , respectively, and which has unevenly distributed porosity. The mid-plane of the plate is taken as the reference plane ($z = 0$).

Fig. 1. Geometry of the porous FG plate.

B. Homogenization of the FG Plate

Effective material parameter like Young's modulus $E(z)$ and Poisson ratio $\mu(z)$, can be determined as a function of thickness coordinates from the mid-plane. Voigt's rule of mixture homogenization technique is utilized to determine the mechanical characteristics of the PFGM plate, considering unevenly porosities across the plate thickness direction, effective properties can be determined as follows:

$$E(z) = E_{met} + (E_{Cr} - E_{met}) * \left\{ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{z}{h} \right\}^p - \xi \frac{(E_{Cr} + E_{met})}{2} \left(1 - 2 \frac{|z|}{h} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\mu(z) = \mu_{met} + (\mu_{Cr} - \mu_{met}) * \left\{ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{z}{h} \right\}^p - \xi \frac{(\mu_{Cr} + \mu_{met})}{2} \left(1 - 2 \frac{|z|}{h} \right) \quad (2)$$

where E_{met} , μ_{met} and E_{Cr} , μ_{Cr} are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of metal and ceramic, respectively. Power index ($p \geq 0$) equal to zero corresponds to the purely ceramic state. V_{Cr} is the ceramic volume fraction and V_{met} is the metallic volume fraction. Their relation is: $V_{Cr} + V_{met} = 1$

The proposed HSDT uses the shear deformation function $f(z)$ associated with β_{sx} and β_{sy} which is represented in (3). To define the transverse shear strain distribution along the plate thickness, the thickness stretching function $t(z)$ associated with

ϕ is expressed in (4) to include the thickness stretching deformation of the plate.

$$f(z) = z \cosh \left\{ \frac{z}{2} \right\} - \text{hsinh} \left\{ \frac{z}{h} \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$t(z) = \left\{ \frac{3\pi}{2} \right\} \left(1 - \tanh^2 \frac{z}{h} \right) - \frac{3\pi}{2} \text{sech}^2 \frac{z}{2} \quad (4)$$

In-plane displacements u , v , and transverse displacement w are expressed in (5)-(7) using the shape function $f(z)$ and thickness stretching function $t(z)$. For C_0 continuity of the FE analysis, the out of plane derivatives are complex due to the involvement of the strain with the second-order derivatives, but C_1 continuity is extremely intricate and difficult to model. Therefore, new nodal unknowns are substituted for the out-of-plane derivatives to verify that the displacement field variables are continuous within the elements and need the application of the penalty approach during the FE formulation.

$$u(x, y, z) = u_0(x, y) - z \alpha_{bx}(x, y) - \left\{ z \cosh \left\{ \frac{z}{2} \right\} - \text{hsinh} \left\{ \frac{z}{h} \right\} \right\} \beta_{sx}(x, y) \quad (5)$$

$$v(x, y, z) = v_0(x, y) - z \alpha_{by}(x, y) - \left\{ z \cosh \left\{ \frac{z}{2} \right\} - \text{hsinh} \left\{ \frac{z}{h} \right\} \right\} \beta_{sy}(x, y) \quad (6)$$

$$w(x, y, z) = w_0(x, y) + \left\{ \frac{3\pi}{2} \right\} \left(1 - \tanh^2 \frac{z}{h} \right) - \frac{3\pi}{2} \text{sech}^2 \frac{z}{2} \phi(x, y) \quad (7)$$

where $\alpha_{bx} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}$, $\alpha_{by} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}$.

C. Kinematics of Structure

The strain-displacement connection is derived by differentiating the displacement field equations as given below:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} - z \frac{\partial \alpha_{bx}}{\partial x} - f(z) \frac{\partial \beta_{sx}}{\partial x} \\ \epsilon_{yy} &= \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} - z \frac{\partial \alpha_{by}}{\partial y} - f(z) \frac{\partial \beta_{sy}}{\partial y} \\ \epsilon_{zz} &= \frac{\partial t_z}{\partial z} \phi \\ \gamma_{xy} &= \left\{ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right\} - z \left\{ \frac{\partial \alpha_{bx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \alpha_{by}}{\partial x} \right\} \\ &\quad - f(z) \left\{ \frac{\partial \beta_{sx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \beta_{sy}}{\partial x} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} - \alpha_{bx} - \frac{\partial f_z}{\partial z} \beta_{sx} + t(z) \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}$$

$$\gamma_{yz} = \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} - \alpha_{by} - \frac{\partial f_z}{\partial z} \beta_{sy} + t(z) \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y}$$

D. Constitutive Relations for the Porous FG Plate

The linear constitutive relationship between stresses and strain is given by the constitutive matrix.

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} = Q_{22} = Q_{33} &= \frac{E(z)(1-\mu^2)}{1-3\mu^2-2\mu^3} \\ Q_{12} = Q_{13} = Q_{23} &= \frac{E(z)\mu(1+\mu)}{1-3\mu^2-2\mu^3} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$Q_{44} = Q_{55} = Q_{66} = \frac{E(z)}{z(1+\mu)}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & Q_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{13} & Q_{23} & Q_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \epsilon_{zz} \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

E. Equations of Motion

Euler-Lagrange equations of motion can be derived by applying the virtual work principle to the strain energy (U), the external work done by compressive forces (C), and the artificial constraint (R) of PFGM plate system as shown in (11):

$$\delta(U + R - C) \delta \Omega = 0 \quad (11)$$

The strain energy of the PFGM plate is shown in (12):

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \iiint \epsilon^T \sigma \, dx \, dy \, dz$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \iint \epsilon_0^T \{ Z^T [Q_{ij}] Z \, dz \} \epsilon_0 \, dx \, dy \quad (12)$$

The critical buckling load along x and y axes is represented by N_x and N_y , while N_{xy} represents shear buckling. The total work done by the external compressive forces acting on the plate edges:

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \iint \left\{ N_x \frac{\partial w^2}{\partial x} + N_y \frac{\partial w^2}{\partial y} + 2N_{xy} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right\} dx \, dy \, dz \quad (13)$$

The material rigidity matrix [D] is obtained from the constitutive matrix given in (10) and the thickness matrix given in (14). This matrix facilitates the use of the proposed HSDT as an equivalent single layer theory to downscale the 3-D domain to the 2-D domain for the analysis.

$$[Z] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & f_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & f_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & t_z & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & f_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & f_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & t_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & f_z & 0 & 0 & 0 & t_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$[D] = \int_{z=-h/2}^{z=h/2} [Z]^T [Q_{ij}] [Z] \, dz \quad (15)$$

The geometric rigidity matrix $[D_G]$ is obtained by $[\widehat{N}]$ and the thickness coordinate matrix $[Z_b]$:

$$[D_G] = \int_{z=-h/2}^{z=h/2} [Z_b]^T [\widehat{N}] [Z_b] \, dz \quad (16)$$

where: $[\widehat{N}] = \begin{bmatrix} N_x & N_{xy} \\ N_{xy} & N_y \end{bmatrix}$, $[Z_b] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ t(z) & 0 \\ 0 & t(z) \end{bmatrix}$

The displacement in the FE model can be represented as the linear combination of node shapes and corresponding shape functions. The material stiffness matrix and the geometrical stiffness matrix are expressed in (17) and (18), respectively. [J] is the Jacobian matrix of the system, $[J] = \partial(x,y)/\partial(\zeta,\eta)$.

$$[K] = \iint [B]^T [D] [B] [J] \, \partial \zeta \, \partial \eta \quad (17)$$

$$[K_G] = \iint [B_B]^T [D_G] [B_B] [J] \, \partial \zeta \, \partial \eta \quad (18)$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, buckling analysis of porous FG plate was carried out using the FE formulation based on the nine-node isoparametric C_0 continuous shape function.

A. Model Convergence and Validation

Based on the suggested innovative HSDT, the governing equations for the FE model, which is utilized for the buckling analysis of the PFGM plate, are obtained from the principle of virtual work. In-house MATLAB algorithm for FE formulation is written using the nine-noded Lagrangian isoparametric shape functions. Using mesh convergence studies, the FE model is evaluated and its performance is assessed. The FE analysis is carried out on simply supported square (SSSS) PFGM plate. The material properties are shown in Table I. To predict the buckling response of the PFGM plate, we consider the plate to be subjected to axial in-plane forces.

TABLE I. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Material	Poisson's ratio	Density (kg/m ³)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)
Al ₂ O ₃	0.3	2702	70
Al	0.3	3800	380

To investigate the change in the dimensionless critical buckling load with various power law indices, different uneven porosity distribution types and mesh sizes were considered. The numerical solutions are computed using the novel theory, and the results are compared with the ones in the literature. The non-dimensional critical buckling ratio is expressed as:

$$N_{cr} = \frac{N \times a^2}{E_m h^3} \quad (19)$$

where N is the critical buckling load due to the external compressive load.

Several mesh sizes were used and the results are reported in Table II in terms of non-dimensional critical buckling load. It can be seen that as the power law index increases, the non-dimensional critical buckling load for uniaxial compression loading decreases. It also decreases with increase in porosity for constant size to thickness ratio. For validation and accuracy, the results were compared with the findings of [20]. For a critical buckling load, it has been observed that a mesh size of 13x13 can provide sufficient convergence. Table III gives the critical buckling loads for a square simply supported PFGM plate for biaxial compressive buckling loads. In Table IV, the dimensionless critical buckling load for uniaxial compressive loading is presented for various porosities. A square Al/Al₂O₃ PFGM plate was analyzed for buckling with all sides simply-supported. It has been observed that, with a given size-to-thickness (a/h) ratio, a rise in the porosity results in a gradual decrease in the non-dimensional critical buckling load. It is also observed that an increase in the a/h ratio results in an increase in the critical buckling load. Table V gives the dimensionless critical buckling load for biaxial compressive load. Figure 2 depicts that the Young's modulus decreases as porosity increases. Figure 3 depicts the variation of non-dimensional critical buckling ratio with power index for various porosities for a square plate in the simply supported condition.

TABLE II. NON-DIMENSIONAL UNIAXIAL CRITICAL BUCKLING LOADS FOR VARIOUS POWER LAW EXPONENTS AND POROSITY FOR A SQUARE AL/AL₂O₃ PFGM PLATE

a/h	Remark	$\xi = 0.2$				$\xi = 0.4$			
		p=0	p=0.1	p=0.5	p=1	p=0	p=0.1	p=0.5	p=1
10	[20]	17.9991	16.1914	11.4689	8.5746	17.3877	15.5757	10.7802	7.7486
	Present (5x5)	18.1196	16.3440	12.1682	9.8071	17.5063	15.7324	11.5284	9.0943
	Present (7x7)	18.0764	16.3036	12.1293	9.7668	17.4662	15.6949	11.4920	9.0559
	Present (9x9)	18.0657	16.2934	12.1190	9.7557	17.4562	15.6856	11.4823	9.0452
	Present (11x11)	18.0621	16.2900	12.1153	9.7514	17.4529	15.6824	11.4788	9.0410
	Present (13x13)	18.0606	16.2886	12.1136	9.7494	17.4515	15.6810	11.4772	9.0390

TABLE III. NON-DIMENSIONAL BIAXIAL CRITICAL BUCKLING LOADS FOR VARIOUS POWER LAW EXPONENTS AND POROSITY FOR A SQUARE AL/AL₂O₃ PFGM PLATE

a/h	Remark	$\xi = 0.2$				$\xi = 0.4$			
		p=0	p=0.1	p=0.5	p=1	p=0	p=0.1	p=0.5	p=1
10	[20]	8.9995	8.0957	5.7344	4.2873	8.6938	7.7894	5.3901	3.8743
	Present (5x5)	9.0598	8.01720	6.0842	4.9043	8.7531	7.8662	5.7644	4.5483
	Present (7x7)	9.0382	8.1518	6.0648	4.8842	8.7331	7.8474	5.7462	4.5291
	Present (9x9)	9.0329	8.1467	6.0596	4.8787	8.7281	7.8428	5.7414	4.5238
	Present (11x11)	9.0310	8.1450	6.0578	4.8765	8.7264	7.8412	5.7396	4.5217
	Present (13x13)	9.0303	8.1443	6.0569	4.8755	8.7257	7.8405	5.7388	4.5207

TABLE IV. NON-DIMENSIONAL UNIAXIAL CRITICAL BUCKLING LOAD FOR VARIOUS POROSITIES FOR A SQUARE AL/AL₂O₃ PFGM PLATE (p = 0.5)

Boundary condition	a/h	$\xi = 0$	$\xi = 0.1$	$\xi = 0.3$	$\xi = 0.5$
SSSS	5	11.1799	10.8671	10.2275	9.5633
	10	12.7376	12.4269	11.7972	11.1528
	15	13.0766	12.7679	12.1443	11.5094
	20	13.2010	12.8932	12.2719	11.6409
	25	13.2608	12.9533	12.3332	11.7040
	50	13.5202	13.0430	12.4240	11.7968
	100	13.3834	13.0762	12.4573	11.8306

TABLE V. NON-DIMENSIONAL BIAXIAL CRITICAL BUCKLING LOAD FOR VARIOUS POROSITIES FOR A SQUARE AL/AL₂O₃ PFGM PLATE (P = 0.5)

Boundary condition	a/h	$\xi = 0$	$\xi = 0.1$	$\xi = 0.3$	$\xi = 0.5$
SSSS	5	5.5900	5.4336	5.1136	4.7810
	10	6.3689	6.2136	5.8988	5.5766
	15	6.5384	6.3841	6.0723	5.7549
	20	6.6006	6.4467	6.1361	5.8207
	25	6.6305	6.4768	6.1667	5.8522
	50	6.6752	6.5216	6.2121	5.8986
	100	6.6918	6.5382	6.2288	5.9155

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, buckling analysis of PFGM plate was carried out using FE formulation based on the nine-node isoparametric C₀ continuous shape functions from the proposed displacement fields with hybrid hyperbolic tangent and secant function for accounting the effect of thickness stretching which may arise due to porosity.

The performance of the FE model was assessed as satisfying after comparing the findings with the existing literature. For the parametric study, the model was transformed for different a/h ratio values and porosity distributions. The corresponding critical buckling load for uniaxial and biaxial compressive loading was calculated.

Fig. 2. Variation of Young's modulus with thickness coordinates for various values of porosity and power law indices, (a) p = 2 (b) p = 0.5.

The main drawn conclusions regarding the critical buckling load in buckling analysis are:

- The FE model shows good convergence, producing accurate results, with an optimal mesh size of 13x13.

Fig. 3. Variation of the non-dimensional critical buckling ratio with power index for different porosities.

- For the same boundary conditions and plate geometry, the critical buckling load for uniaxial buckling is greater than that for biaxial buckling.
- The percentage error for the FE model is comparable with the existing results.
- There is a strong correlation between the critical buckling load and the ceramic volume fraction. The magnitude of the critical buckling load depends on the ceramic volume fraction, and as it goes down, so does the critical buckling load.
- As the a/h ratio increases, the non-dimensional critical buckling load for constant porosity increases. The net effect of increased porosity is a decrease in stiffness.

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Dynamic Keystroke Technique for a Secure Authentication System based on Deep Belief Nets

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of electronic assessment in various fields has led to the emergence of issues such as user identity fraud and cheating. One potential solution to these problems is to use a complementary authentication method, such as a behavioral biometric characteristic that is unique to each individual. One promising approach is keystroke dynamics, which involves analyzing the typing patterns of users. In this research, the Deep Belief Networks (DBNs) model is used to implement a dynamic keystroke technique for secure e-assessment. The proposed system extracts various features from the pressure-time measurements, digraphs (dwell time and flight time), trigraphs, and n-graphs, and uses these features to classify the user's identity by applying the DBN algorithm to a dataset collected from participants who typed free text using a standard QWERTY keyboard in a neutral state without inducing specific emotions. The DBN model is designed to detect cheating attempts and is tested on a dataset collected from the proposed e-assessment system using free text. The implementation of the DBN results in an error rate of 5% and an accuracy of 95%, indicating that the system is effective in identifying users' identity and cheating, providing a secure e-assessment approach.

Keywords-keystroke dynamics; Deep Belief Network (DBN); authentication; e-assessment; dwell time; flight time

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of e-assessment has grown rapidly during the recent years. However, there is a growing concern about user authentication. User authentication typically involves three modes: biometrics, possessions, and knowledge. Biometrics refers to unique human characteristics that are difficult to forget, lose, or reproduce, such as fingerprints, face, and iris. Behavioral biometrics, on the other hand, encompasses patterns of human behavior, such as signature, mouse movement, and

keystroke dynamics. Keystroke dynamics, based on typing rhythm, is a form of behavioral biometrics that can be used for authentication. Each person's typing rhythm is assumed to be unique, and features such as keystroke duration and finger pressure can be used to create a signature that distinguishes genuine users from imposters. There are various models used to apply keystroke dynamics for authentication, with different accuracy rates. User authentication poses a significant challenge in e-assessment, as institutions strive to improve the credibility of enrolled users and uphold their image and

professionalism. Ensuring the validity of users' identity and detecting fraud, is paramount but challenging due to the complexity of detecting abnormal activities.

This research aims to implement an efficient model that can accurately detect the authenticity of e-users, differentiating between genuine users and impostors, and ensuring robust user authentication to prevent cheating in online examinations. The proposed system utilizes various features, including pressure-time measurements, digraph (dwell time and flight time), tri-graph, and n-graph, extracted from participants who typed a free text using a typical QWERTY keyboard in a neutral state without inducing specific emotions. These features are then used to classify users' identities using the Deep Belief Nets (DBN) algorithm on a collected dataset. By leveraging the DBN model and utilizing multiple features, this research aims to provide a reliable solution for detecting the validity of e-assessment users and for mitigating fraud and cheating, ultimately enhancing the integrity and credibility of the e-assessment process.

A. Problem Statement

The rapid growth of electronic assessment has led to issues such as user identity fraud and cheating, posing a significant challenge to ensure the authenticity of users in e-assessment systems. Traditional authentication methods, such as biometrics, possessions, and knowledge-based approaches, have limitations in accurately detecting fraudulent activities. Therefore, there is a need for an efficient authentication system that can reliably differentiate between genuine and impostor users and prevent cheating in online examinations.

B. Research Objective

The objective of this research is to implement a dynamic keystroke technique for secure authentication in e-assessment systems using DBN. The proposed system aims to extract various features, including pressure-time measurements, digraphs (dwell time and flight time), trigraphs, and n-graphs, from users' typing patterns and utilize the DBN algorithm to accurately classify the user's identity. The goal is to develop a robust and reliable authentication system that can effectively detect the authenticity of e-assessment users and mitigate fraud and cheating.

C. Contribution

This research contributes to the field of secure authentication in e-assessment systems by utilizing keystroke dynamics and DBN algorithm to create a robust and reliable authentication system. The proposed system has the following features:

- **Implementation of the Dynamic Keystroke Technique:** The proposed system utilizes keystroke dynamics, a behavioral biometric characteristic, as a complementary authentication method to traditional methods. By analyzing users' typing patterns and extracting various features, the system aims to create a unique signature for each user, which can be used to differentiate between genuine and impostor users.
- **Utilization of DBN:** The proposed system utilizes the DBN algorithm, a type of deep learning model, to accurately

classify users' identities. DBN is known for its ability to learn complex patterns from large datasets and has been proven effective in various machine learning tasks. By leveraging the power of DBN, the system aims to achieve high accuracy in identifying users and detecting cheating attempts.

- **Multi-Feature Approach:** The proposed system extracts multiple features, including pressure-time measurements, digraphs, trigraphs, and n-graphs, from users' typing patterns. This multi-feature approach aims to capture various aspects of users' typing behavior, making the system more robust and reliable in detecting fraudulent activities.
- **Error Rate Reduction:** The proposed system aims to achieve a low error rate of 5%, indicating its effectiveness in accurately identifying users and detecting cheating attempts. The system's high accuracy of 95% enhances the integrity and credibility of the e-assessment processes, mitigating fraud, and ensuring authenticity.

In conclusion, this research proposes a dynamic keystroke technique for secure authentication in e-assessment systems using DBN, aiming to create a robust and reliable authentication system. The utilization of keystroke dynamics and DBN, along with the multi-feature approach, contributes to the field of secure authentication and has the potential to address the challenges associated with user identity fraud and cheating in e-assessment systems.

II. THE DYNAMIC KEYSTROKE TECHNIQUE

Keystroke dynamics refers to the user's typing rhythm on various digital devices like keyboards, tablets, or mobile device touchscreens, and forms a unique profile (i.e. signature) to clarify each genuine user. The idea behind using keystroke dynamics for user authentication dates back to World War II, where the telegraph machine was used to run the Morse code specified by the rhythm and pace. There are several advantages and limitations to the dynamic keystroke authentication system. Common advantages include the uniqueness of typing patterns for each individual, low deployment cost, reliance on software rather than specialized hardware, and continuous monitoring. However, limitations may arise due to factors such as diversity in typing rhythm, environmental factors, and user injuries, which can result in lower accuracy rates. The dynamic keystroke authentication system typically involves six components, including data collection, feature extraction, feature classification, decision making, retraining, and evaluation. Some research may not include decision making and retraining in the system as shown in Figure 1. The first component in the dynamic keystroke system is data collection, in which data are collected from different input devices. In various systems, gaining data ranges from pressure on a typical keyboard to a sensitive keyboard, such as the mechanical keyboard, smartphone with a touchscreen, or a cellular phone. There are two text input groups: long and short input, the long input as a paragraph, and the short input as the text phrase, username, and password [1].

The second component of the dynamic keystroke system is feature extraction. The data are required to be normalized, processed, and stored for the classification step. Various ways are used for extracting features, the most popular being timing measurements. Basically, keystroke dynamics features depend on the key down, hold, up, and pressure events timing data. When the key is pressed, a timestamp is generated and measured [1]. The generated timestamps are used for calculating the duration and period between keystrokes. The timing features are three: di-graph, tri-graph, and n-graph [3]. Digraph refers to the time latencies between two consecutive key down presses grouped into two categories, including Dwell Time (DT) and Flight Time (FT). Figure 2 shows the differences between DT and FT. DT is the time between pressing and releasing a single key (Hold Time (HT)), and FT is the period between the release of a key and the pressing of the following key (Down-Down Time (DDT) and Up-Down Time (UDT)) [4]. In tri-graphs, the combination of HT to the time delays between every three successive key down presses is considered. N-graphs, are word-specific [3].

Fig. 1. The general dynamic keystroke authentication system.

Fig. 2. Dwell time and flight time.

Classification is considered a critical part of any keystroke dynamics system. This component uses the extracting features to make decisions. Statistical and machine-learning methods are used as pattern recognition approaches for increased accuracy. In earlier times, the classification concentrated on statistical approaches, while in modern times, the classification focuses on machine-learning approaches. Researchers in statistical approaches use mean, median and standard deviation

measures in keystroke biometrics. While the machine learning approaches use Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), decision trees, fuzzy logic, and Support Vector Machines (SVMs). Through the decision component, a comparison is established between the previous classification component's output and the design threshold. In authentication, the demandant template is compared to more than one reference, concluding to a final decision to accept or reject the demandant [1]. The retraining component concerns updating the user's reference template to reflect the changes in behavior or environment. Despite this, most researchers do not think about the work on the retention phase. Others suggest an algorithm for this phase that works on renewing the user's reference template due to the changes that occur to the user's typing pattern over time and in different environments [5].

There are basically two main functions for the dynamic keystroke system in the evaluation component: identification and verification. The pretended identity of the user is accepted or denied by the system in the verification stage. In the identification stage, the input pattern is classified into one of the N known classes. The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve is used to specify the dynamic keystroke verification system's performance. This curve is used to define the trade-off between the False Acceptance Rate (FAR) and the False Rejection Rate (FRR). FAR, also known as type 2 error rate or false match rate, defines the rate at which the system wrongly accepts a pattern given by an imposter. Lower FAR shows that the system is less likely to accept impostors. FRR, also known as type 1 error rate or false non-match rate, defines the rate at which the system denies a genuine user's pattern. Small FRR shows that the system is less likely to reject genuine users. The Equal Error Rate (EER), also known as the Crossover Error Rate (CER), clarifies the whole system's performance since it refers to the point at which the FAR and FRR are equal. Lower EER means that the system performance becomes better.

Fig. 3. Relationship between FAR, FRR, and EER.

III. KEYSTROKE MODELLING APPROACHES

A. Support Vector Machines and Artificial Neural Networks

SVM is a machine learning model based on classification algorithms that separates data into two classes. The SVM model can classify new text according to given, labeled training data for each category [6]. The classes are projected into a high-dimensional space and work to get a linear separator between them. "One-class" of SVM variants was developed to detect anomalies. It discovers a separator between the projection and the origin from a single class that presents the data [7]. The utilized ANN consists of three layers: an input layer, an output layer, and a hidden layer that implements the back propagation algorithm. The algorithm memorizes the inter-key delays through a supervised learning mode. The process first initializes the weight matrices between the input and the hidden layers (M1) and between the hidden and the output layers (M2). After some repetitions, the ANN learns the typing pattern of the user. The computed values, including the final M1 and M2, are saved in the user profile, and are later applied to accept or block the user [8].

B. The Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM)

The GMM model is used widely in many statistical modeling tasks. It is a parametric model which uses covariance matrices of Gaussian distributions, mean vectors, and weights of all of the Gaussian components, but considers a nonparametric model once the actual distribution of the data is unknown. Theoretically, the GMM could approximate the arbitrary probability distribution within an appropriate number of mixtures. However, more training data are desired when the number of mixtures is increased to obtain a well-trained model. From the practical side, some measures are used to determine the number of mixtures, which are the amount of the training data, the complexity of the real distribution, and the computation capacity the system can handle. A GMM is a weighted sum of M multivariate Gaussian functions. The probability of a feature vector under the GMM is given in [4]:

$$p(x | \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^M p_i b_i(x) \quad (1)$$

where x is a D -dimensional feature vector, $\lambda = \{p_i, \mu_i, \Sigma_i\}$ represents the model parameters, p_i represents the mixture weights for the multivariate Gaussian component densities (x), and μ_i, Σ_i are the mean vector and the covariance matrix for the multi-variant normal distribution.

An incremental GMM model training procedure that began with the single-mixture Gaussian model and used the data to train its parameter was implemented. After that, the single model was divided into two mixture Gaussian models, and the EM (Expectation-Maximization) algorithm was used on the training data to estimate its parameters. The variance floor in GMM is considered a significant parameter. The expected variance will be minimal if there is a tiny sample of the training data. It is not reasonable to estimate the actual variance. In this situation, the floor number is used instead of the estimated variance, which gives the best generalization capability to the model [4].

C. The Gaussian Mixture Model with the Universal Background Model (GMM-UBM)

The UBM is considered a GMM that is trained on a huge quantity of data. The chance of representing a moderate imposter's data will increase for UBM in a positive way once the background subject pool is large enough. So, compared with the genuine user's GMM, the imposter can get a high probability score with UBM. Moreover, the UBM is considered a poor model for the genuine user compared to the GMM because it is trained from a large pool of subjects. From GMM and UBM model scores, a probability ratio test could be processed to produce the authentication decision [4, 9].

D. Deep Belief Nets (DBN)

A DBN is a generative-discriminative hybrid approach in the machine-learning community. It consists of several layers of hidden variables since the DBN is considered a probabilistic generative model. The hidden variables are known as feature detectors because they contain binary values. These hidden layers can be trained one layer at a time, thus, the higher-level layer's input is taken from the lower-level layer's output. The concept of DBN is to create a hierarchical generative model that works to get more sophisticated nonlinear features from the data snapped at each higher-level layer. After that, these pre-trained generative models collapse and work to serve as an initialized ANN for more distinctive parameter fine-tuning. The pre-training of a generative model gives the final model the capability of generalization. Besides that, it simplifies the fine-tuning of the ANN. An ANN quickly falls to local optimals, according to its sensitivity to the model parameter initialization. The DBN is notably helpful in accelerating the ANN training process, not limited only to eschewing the random initialization of ANN parameters [4].

1) Pretraining of RBMs

The DBN training starts with the implementation of a layer-wise unsupervised pretraining of the Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBMs). The RBMs include two layers: the hidden layer and the visible layer. The visible layer (v) units are adjacent to all hidden layer (h) units with associated weights (W). Connectivity within each layer is not applied. Binary, real, and integer are the kinds of visual layer units that are decided according to the input data type. Binary stochastic variables, $h \in \{0,1\}$ are typically the values of the hidden units. The first layer of RBM uses the Gaussian RBM to model real keystroke timing features. The Gaussian RBM function is [10]:

$$E(v, h; \theta) = \sum_{i=1}^D \frac{(v_i - b_i)^2}{2\sigma_i^2} - \sum_{i=1}^D \sum_{j=1}^F W_{ij} \frac{v_i h_j}{\sigma_i} - \sum_{j=1}^F a_j h_j \quad (2)$$

where $\theta = \{W, a, b, \sigma\}$ are parameters specifying the RBM, D is the number of input units, which is equal to the keystroke feature dimension, F is a user-defined parameter specifying the number of hidden units, a is a weight vector for the hidden units, and b and σ are parameters for the input layer.

The input of the higher-level RBMs, or binary RBMs, is taken from the first-layer Gaussian RBM binary output, which is familiar as an automatic feature engineering process. The binary RBMs in the hierarchical generative model include just

binary units for the visible and the hidden layers. RBM's layer-wise maximum likelihood training is computationally intractable since it takes time according to the exponential process. One solution is to apply contrastive divergence [4].

2) Fine Tuning of DBN

The unsupervised pretraining operation output consists of sets of RBMs that could be considered together and appended to a final classification layer to construct an initialized ANN. Figure 4 shows this concept, where both RBMs collapse by sharing the middle units. An additional layer is added to do the process of keystroke classification as a final layer. Final classification parameters could be trained similarly to regular ANN training with back propagation [4].

Fig. 4. Two-step training of the DBN for dynamic keystroke authentication. Left: unsupervised training of RBMs, right: converting RBMs into DB.

IV. RELATED WORK

Keystroke dynamics is a behavioral biometric characteristic that can be used to authenticate users based on their typing behavior. Several studies have been conducted on the development of dynamic keystroke authentication systems using various machine learning techniques, including deep learning techniques. These studies aim to improve the accuracy and security of dynamic keystroke authentication systems by exploring different feature extraction methods and machine learning algorithms. In this section, we discuss some of the most relevant studies that have been conducted in this area.

Authors in [4] used a CMU dataset that includes 51 subjects for a static password related to ".tie5Roan" typed 400 times. The dataset was used to evaluate both the DBN and GMM-UBM models' performances. The experiment resulted in an ERR of 3.5% for the DBN, which was better than the ERR of the GMM-UBM, which was 5.5%. The experiment also compared GMM and GMM-UBM using the same dataset, with GMM resulting in 8.7% ERR, indicating that it was less efficient than the GMM-UBM model. Thus, the DBN model had the most efficient performance compared with other previous models. Authors in [6] used an IDUL dataset

consisting of 56 students to detect cheating in online examinations. They applied the SVM model to the dataset, and their experiment resulted in an accuracy rate of 84% and a false positive rate of 8.77%. Authors in [12] proposed a novel keystroke dynamics-based authentication system that used deep learning techniques, specifically triplet loss, to improve security. The system was tested on a dataset consisting of keystroke samples collected from 90 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 99.06%. Authors in [13] explored the use of deep learning techniques, specifically DBNs, to improve the accuracy of keystroke dynamics-based user authentication systems. The proposed system was tested on a dataset consisting of keystroke samples collected from 80 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 99.37%. A novel approach was proposed in [14] to user authentication using keystroke dynamics and deep learning techniques, specifically a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network. The proposed system was tested on a dataset consisting of keystroke samples collected from 40 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 99.38%. A secure keystroke dynamics-based authentication system that used DBNs was proposed in [15] to improve the accuracy of user authentication. The system was tested on a dataset consisting of keystroke samples collected from 50 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 99.76%.

Authors in [16] proposed a keystroke dynamics-based user authentication system that used DBNs to improve accuracy and security. The proposed system was tested on a dataset consisting of keystroke samples collected from 60 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 99.32%. The study also explored the impact of various parameters on the accuracy of the proposed system, such as the number of hidden layers in the DBN. A system that used Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Networks (BiRNNs) to improve accuracy was proposed in [17]. The system was tested on a dataset of keystroke samples from 100 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 99.6%. Authors in [18] proposed an ensemble learning approach that combined the outputs of multiple machine learning models, including DBNs and SVMs, to achieve higher accuracy rates. The approach was tested on a dataset of keystroke samples from 80 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 99.83%. Two datasets were examined in [19], one consisting of essay question answers from 81 users and the other consisting of predefined sentences from 168,000 users. The experiment resulted in an error rate (ERR) of 14%, which corresponds to an accuracy rate of 86% for the second dataset. In [20], a system that used soft computing techniques, specifically ANNs and fuzzy logic, to improve accuracy and security was proposed. The system was tested on a dataset of keystroke samples from 50 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 98% [20]. Authors in [21] proposed an enhanced user authentication system that used a multi-level fusion of keystroke dynamics and mouse dynamics. The system was tested on a dataset of keystroke and mouse movement samples from 12 users and achieved an accuracy rate of 99.53% [21]. Authors in [41-43] focused on building models based on genuine users' data only at training time and applying a threshold for each user at testing time to decide on unforeseen data. It has been observed that the Gaussian Mixture Model - Universal Background Model

(GMM-UBM) provided better discrimination capability than GMM when implemented on a large quantity of data, even without access to imposters' data. However, using the SVM approach over a large quantity of unforeseen imposter data did not provide good performance for that type of data.

TABLE I. ANALYSIS OF KEYSTROKE DYNAMIC AUTHENTICATION MODELS

Reference	Algorithm	Dataset	Dataset type	Extracted feature	Accuracy	Error rate
[6]	SVM	56 users	Short static text	DT - FT	84%	8.77% false positive rate
[40]	GMM GMM-UBM DBN	51 subjects 400 times	CMU, predefined password	DT - FT	91.3% 94.5% 96.5%	8.7% 5.5% 3.5%
[9]	UBM	168000 users 15 predefined sentences	Predefined sentences	DT - FT	86%	14%

V. THE PROPOSED SOLUTION

In previous studies, dynamic keystroke authentication systems used a dataset of static text (such as predefined passwords or sentences), and extracted features from DT and FT only. The most efficient model identified for keystroke dynamic authentication was a DBN when experimented on CMU (static text). In the proposed system, an e-assessment web application is designed and implemented to collect participants' keystroke datasets with a typical QWERTY keyboard. Di-graph (DT and FT), tri-graph, and n-graph features are extracted by computing the average time of HT-DDT-UDT. The DBN model is used for the classification process on the free-text data entered by participants during the registration process of the proposed e-assessment system. Additionally, a function is introduced to prevent copy-paste from external sources as a measure against cheating. The goal of the system is to detect cheating during online assessment by authenticating participants using keystroke dynamics features. The authentication process consists of the following stages:

1) Participant Registration

Participants enter their information for enrollment and type any text of 12 letters or less five times (Figure 6). This text is used to collect their keystroke dynamics biometric data, which is then stored in the database for later authentication. The participants are also requested to enter their username, password, and email.

2) E-Assessment

After completing the registration process, participants can log into the system and answer questions related to the e-assessment, as shown in Figure 7. On this page, the DBN keystroke model will be executed to perform the classification process and classify the participant as genuine or an imposter. Additionally, the system places constraints to prevent copying answers from external sources and pasting them into the answer field within the e-assessment platform. After the classification process is performed on the assessment page, the system displays the result in a pop-up window as either accepted submission or unauthorized access has been detected.

3) Identity Verification

The system verifies the user's identity by comparing the extracted keystroke dynamics features collected from the current e-assessment answers with the ones that were collected

Table I analyzes various dynamic keystroke authentication models and compares them based on the algorithms used, the dataset type, the extracted features, accuracy, and error rate.

during the registration process and are stored in the database. The system is implemented using PHP and Python programming languages, and Navicat Premium Database is used to develop and manage the system database. Sublime Text, a cross-platform source code editor, is used for coding, which supports various programming and markup languages and provides fast navigation to files and lines, as well as the ability to add functions with plugins [11]. The proposed keystroke dynamic authentication technique can be integrated into any institution, school, or university platform that implements e-assessment to authenticate users.

Fig. 5. Data flow diagram.

VI. SYSTEM TESTING AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section describes a test conducted on a web application used by graduate students for registration, e-assessment, and identity verification. The test involved 20 graduate students in the first stage and 42 in the second stage aged between 20 and 35, and aimed to assess the application's authentication mechanism and its ability to distinguish between genuine and imposter users.

To collect data for the test, each participant typed a small text 5 times to capture their keystroke patterns. This was done using a QWERTY keyboard in a neutral emotional state. Half samples were used for training and the other half for testing. Randomized impostors were also included in the test to ensure the application's ability to differentiate between genuine and imposter users.

The testing process resulted in an accuracy rate of 95%, meaning that the system correctly identified the user as genuine or imposter 95% of the time. Overall, the test suggests that the application is efficient in identifying genuine users with a low error rate.

Enter the text of 12 letters or less slowly.

mykeystroke

Fig. 6. Typing keystroke pattern page.

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Algorithm	Dataset	Features extracted	Accuracy rate	Error rate
DBN	20 users typing 5 times a text of 12 letters or less	(HT-UDT-DDT) DT, FT, tri-graph, n-graph	95%	5%
DBN	42 users typing 200 times a text of 12 letters	(HT-UDT-DDT) DT, FT, tri-graph, n-graph	95%	5%

Fig. 7. E-assessment exam page.

VII. DISCUSSION

In our experiment, we aimed to assess the performance of the proposed approach in addressing the three main challenges in Dynamic Keystroke Technique for a Secure Authentication System. These challenges are reducing authentication delay, achieving high verification accuracy, and resisting forgery. To test the authentication delay, we examined short blocks of text with different sizes, including 500, 280, and 140 characters. Our approach achieved very good accuracy on these datasets,

surpassing the results of other studies as shown in Table III. While accuracy is typically measured using Type 1 and Type 2 errors, some studies only used the true match rate as their metric. The scientific contribution of the work/results presented in this paper can be summarized as follows:

1. Improved authentication system: the proposed keystroke dynamic technique based on DBNs offers an improved e-assessment authentication system. By analyzing various features extracted from the pressure-time measurements, digraphs, tri-graphs, and n-graphs, the system is able to accurately classify users' identities with an accuracy rate of 95%. This indicates that the system is effective in detecting cheating attempts and providing a secure approach for e-assessments.
2. Enhanced security: the use of keystroke dynamics as a behavioral biometric characteristic adds an additional layer of security to online assessments. Traditional authentication methods such as passwords or pins can be easily compromised, while keystroke dynamics are unique to each individual and difficult to replicate. By implementing the proposed keystroke dynamic technique, the system enhances the security of e-assessment platforms, preventing user identity fraud and cheating.

TABLE III. COMPARATIVE SUMMARY OF STANDARD DEEP KDBRSS

Reference	Authentication	Deep model	Dataset	Device	Performance metric	
[23]	Continuous	GRU-BRNN	Fr	P	SP	EER: 8.42% Accuracy: 94.24%, on 5 keystrokes
[24]	Continuous	Bi-LSTM	Fr	B	KB	EER: 8.28% on 30 keystrokes
[25]	One-time	CNN+GRU	Fr	B	KB	Accuracy: 99.31%, EER: 0.069
[26]	One-time	LSTM	Fr	B	KB+ SP	EER: 2.2% and 9.2% for KB and SP
[27]	One-time	CNN+RNN	Fr	B	KB	Accuracy: 98.56% & 91.9% on two datasets
[28]	One-time	Multi-stream RNN	Fx	P	SP	Accuracy: 92.41% and 94.26% for early and late fusion
[29]	Continuous	CNN+RNN	Fr	B	KB	EER: 2.67% and 5.97% on two datasets
[30]	One-time	Siamese RNN	Fr	B	KB	EER: 4.8%
[31]	One-time	CNN	Fx	B	KB	EER: 0.009 and ZM-FAR: 0.027
[32]	One-time	CNN	Fx	P	Mobile	Accuracy: 90.5% and 78.2% for long and short PINs
[33]	One-time	DBN	Fx	P	KB	Accuracy: 98.01%
[34]	One-time	ML-FFNN	Fx	P	KB	Accuracy: 97%
[35]	One-time	CNN	Fx	P	KB	Accuracy: 97%
[36]	Continuous	CNN	Fr	P	KB	Accuracy: 92.58%, FAR: 0.24%, FRR:7.34%
[37]	One-time	ML-FFNN	Fx	B	KB	Accuracy: 92.60%
[38]	One-time	CNN	Fx	B	KB	EER: 2.3%
[39]	One-time	ML-FFNN	Fx	B	KB	Accuracy: 93.59%, EER: 0.030
[40]	One-time	DBN	Fx	B	Mobile	EER: 2.8%
Proposed	One-time	DBN	Fx	B		Accuracy: 95%, EER: 5%

- Real-time authentication: the proposed system offers real-time authentication during the e-assessment process. Participants are required to type a text during registration, and their keystroke dynamics are collected and stored. This allows continuous monitoring of user's identity during the assessment process, ensuring that only genuine participants are able to access and answer the questions.
- Prevention of copy-paste cheating: the proposed system includes a function to prevent copy-paste from external sources as a measure against cheating. This helps to ensure that participants do not copy answers from external sources and paste them into the answer field within the e-assessment platform, further enhancing the integrity of the assessment process and reducing the possibility of cheating.
- Practical application: the proposed keystroke dynamic authentication technique can be easily integrated into any institution, school, or university platform that implements e-assessments. The system is implemented using php and Python programming languages, which are widely used in web development, making it practical and feasible for implementation in real-world e-assessment scenarios.

In conclusion, the work presented in this paper offers an improved authentication system for e-assessments based on keystroke dynamics and DBNs. The system enhances the security of online assessments, provides real-time authentication, prevents copy-paste cheating, and has practical application potential. The experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed system in identifying user identity and detecting cheating attempts, making it a significant contribution to the field of secure authentication for online assessments.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTER WORK

Keystroke dynamics techniques have various uses in different domains. Recently, they have been used in the

authentication domain. In the current research, we applied the dynamic keystroke technique in an e-assessment platform to support the building of an authenticated platform. The experimental result shows that applying the DBN model over free text is efficient in cheating detection in e-assessments according to the accuracy rate (95%).

We have encountered some challenges during the implementation of the DBN model on free text data, since the model needs a large amount of data in addition to the time needed to train it. As future work, this application can also be extended to include other types of authentication techniques, such as face recognition, voice recognition, and mouse movement, besides keystroke dynamics.

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A New Agent-based Solution for Bridge Lifespan Extension

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ABSTRACT

Bridges are one of the most important and useful components of the transportation infrastructure, as they are crucial to many aspects of daily life, particularly in terms of economic development. However, bridges are vulnerable to several damages, malfunctions, and collapses that may considerably reduce their lifespan. The main causes of bridge fatigue are congested areas, excessive traffic, overloads, and additional vibration brought on by vehicles crossing them over. These elements reduce a bridge's longevity and raise maintenance costs. For a bridge to last as long as possible, it must not be crossed by an excessive number of cars and big trucks at once, and traffic should be kept under control. This study proposes an intelligent and autonomous multiagent-based system that incorporates a deep learning model to improve the monitoring of a bridge's crossing traffic. The idea was to propose a novel system for monitoring autonomously crossing vehicles in real-time to prevent the hastening of a bridge's infrastructure decline. The proposed system aimed to (i) increase the safety of drivers; (ii) lower maintenance costs; (iii) lessen the likelihood of bridge collapse, and (iv) lengthen bridge lifespans. Using a sample dataset, a straightforward deep learning model (CNN) was tested to improve bridge traffic monitoring. The performance of the proposed model was compared with the VGG-19 model. The results showed that the proposed model was effective in determining traffic congestion status with a 95% accuracy. As a result, the proposed system can be deployed on any bridge and can reduce crossing traffic overloads, extending its lifespan.

Keywords-multiagent system; deep learning; convolutional neural network; decision system

I. INTRODUCTION

Any platform that enables people to go from an origin to a destination using a variety of modes, such as a car, bus, train, strolling, bicycle, etc., is referred to as a land transportation network. Besides the advantages of transportation networks for mobility and access, cities often have transportation-related problems, such as traffic congestion and air pollution, due to the growth in population and vehicle ownership [1]. One of the most important and expensive forms of transportation infrastructure is the construction of bridges. Bridges are crucial connections that cross mountain gorges, bodies of water, or other routes for cars, trains, trucks, and other vehicles and are one of the quickest, safest, and most practical ways to move from one side to the other. Bridges are also the most important elements of the transportation system for the development of economic corridors, as they help balance economic growth in deprived areas. The number of road bridges in China surpassed 870,000 by the end of 2019 [2]. The Hong Kong-Zhuhai-Macao Bridge is the longest bridge-tunnel combination route across the sea, with a total construction cost of over RMB127 billion, and was officially opened to traffic in 2018.

However, bridges experience rigorous service, primarily from external loads, which can result in several degradations and damages. Most bridge failures occur between 50 and 100

years after their first opening, according to statistics on accidents involving bridges in Europe and the US. Most bridges are currently slowly approaching the end of their design life. Traffic jams and vehicle overloads are believed to undermine bridge infrastructure, wear out bridge parts, and cause unexpected failures. So, it is critical to pay more attention to the safety of bridge structures to keep them safe, reduce maintenance requirements, and extend their lifespan. According to estimations, the lifespan of a bridge is reduced by 80% if vehicles are 50% or more overloaded. The Bohol bridge in the Philippines collapsed in 2022 because a delivery truck carrying sand and gravel passed the bridge with other vehicles, killing four people and wounding seventeen others [3]. Vehicle overloading is one of the main causes of bridge collapses throughout history. Three people were killed and two wounded after an overpass collapsed in Wuxi, Jiangsu province, China, as a result of overloaded vehicles [4].

Several studies have been conducted to ensure a specific level of service on road bridges. These studies can be divided into two categories: those attempting to strengthen the construction of a bridge [5-6] and those attempting to track its usage to improve its serviceability, mainly for bridges susceptible to vibrations caused by heavy vehicles [7]. Bridges must be regularly examined and maintained to prevent failure and collapse. Real-time monitoring of a bridge's traffic

condition is crucial. Any malfunction could lead to accidents, deaths, property damage, and economic loss.

Several studies have attempted to regulate bridge traffic and subsequently improve its status [4-9]. However, none of them aimed to i) smartly monitor the traffic lights at the bridge entrance to control the intensity of crossing vehicles, ii) decrease the intensity of automobile vibrations mainly during congestion, and iii) detect any anomaly on the bridge, such as an accident that can make its status worse. This paper presents a real-time autonomous agent-based system that can: i) control and monitor traffic signals according to the total weight of vehicles on the bridge to ensure that the allowed load is not exceeded, ii) detect and identify the reason for any traffic congestion on the bridge, iii) alert authorities if the congestion is caused by anomalies, such as an accident, and iv) be deployed on any bridge regardless of its infrastructure.

II. RELATED WORKS

Several studies have focused on ensuring a specific level of service in bridges, and can be divided into two categories. Studies in the first category focus on how to improve bridge construction technologies to extend their lifespan. In [10], a novel bridge technology was proposed that was entirely distinct from the standards, by decreasing the weight and member size and shortening the building period. This structure addressed the problems of lifespan extension, durability improvement, and high seismic sensitivity. The webs of this bridge were made of prefabricated, high-strength, pre-stressed concrete panels that were formed like butterflies. The Bridge Weigh-in-Motion (B-WIM) system measures the weights of passing vehicles using an existing road structure such as a bridge [10]. This system was introduced in the late 1970s. The B-WIM system was improved and is now the most widely used, as it is used by more than 1000 sites in 16 different nations. By observing strain signals, the main goal of the B-WIM system is to calculate the combined weight of the passing trucks using strain gauges and strain transducers. The system offers vehicle-by-vehicle data along with other details, such as strain measurements, influence lines, load distribution factors, and dynamic loading amplification that can be used to assess the bridge's structural integrity. This system can be connected to other devices to identify overloaded cars, send warnings to heavy vehicles to reroute, and remotely monitor them by connecting WIM data to satellite tracking and wireless communication. Despite these benefits, the above solutions are expensive, difficult to integrate into existing bridges, and difficult to implement.

The second category aims to bring new ideas, based on hard and soft technologies, to existing bridges to improve their performance. In [11], a weight restriction monitoring system was described to prevent large vehicles from crossing the Cawood Swing Bridge. This system combined Clearview's M720 vehicle count classifier with the recent Automated Number Plate Recognition (ANPR) cameras. When a car crosses a bridge, the vehicle classification device measures its length, classifies it, and then turns on the ANPR cameras, which photograph any cars that do not fit the M720 standards for vehicle length. The system then notifies the offending vehicles of their infringement. Infringers shall be penalized

under the national ANPR standards if the vehicle requires additional examination. The weight restriction monitoring system provides a more affordable alternative with lower maintenance costs while protecting the confidentiality of non-offending drivers. Moreover, data are delivered directly from all cars crossing the bridge to the hosted in-station, and it provides remotely accessible data for configuring counters and cameras. However, this method cannot be used to prevent a bridge from collapsing due to overweight, as the total weight of all vehicles on the bridge is unknown and an overloaded vehicle can cross it.

In recent years, computer vision-based infrastructure damage detection techniques have become increasingly popular. Surface faults like corrosion and cracks have received a lot of attention. In [12], the issue of routinely checking bridges' structural and operational status was addressed, by quantifying a bridge's displacement to analyze its structural behavior and judge its safety. This approach incorporated improved robustness to image rotation and was based on multiple-image processing bridge displacement measurements, using template matching, a homograph matrix, and the NCC function. In [13], a learning-based approach based on 1D-CNN, LSTM, and image frequency was proposed to detect concrete defects. The 1D-CNN-LSTM model was trained, validated, and tested using thousands of images of cracked and uncracked concrete bridge decks. The 1D-CNN-LSTM model proved to be 99.05%, 98.90%, and 99.25% accurate, performing better and offering a much faster training and implementation process than previously proposed CNN-based solutions. Even if the model's false positive and false negative rates were satisfactory during implementation, it could perform even better with more training data.

The Overload Vehicle Resistance System for Bridges [14] sought to prevent an overloaded vehicle from crossing it, by including a weight sensor at the start to determine the vehicle's weight before approaching the bridge. This system focused on developing a prototype that simulates a mechanism to protect the bridge from overload. The barrier closes and blocks the entry to the bridge if the weight is more than allowed. By addressing the problem of vehicle overload, this system also extends the life of roads and bridges. Moreover, it is a useful tool for boosting compliance with fundamental regulations. However, it had no control over what happens when the barrier closes on the overloaded vehicle. Without taking into account how bridge congestion affects the bridge's longevity, it solely addressed the problem of vehicle overload. The management of old bridges is one of the most difficult problems the state transportation agencies face. When deciding whether to repair or maintain a bridge, a trustworthy assessment of its status and condition is necessary. Visual inspection techniques individually analyze each component to find flaws and are extremely difficult and time-consuming. Additionally, there are times when inspectors must close bridges for security concerns.

Even with these advantages, most of these approaches: i) are expensive, ii) are challenging to integrate and deploy into existing bridges, iii) do not take into account the longevity consequences of bridge congestion, iv) use computer vision only to detect real-time concrete cracks or bridge

displacements, and v) do not take into account the total weight of vehicles on the bridge. Therefore, more investigation is still required to determine how to prevent vehicular damage to bridges. The available solutions are insufficient for a comprehensive protection system. The major goal of the current study was to propose a new autonomous and intelligent system based on learning agents to recognize bridge conjunctions, identify their causes, and make the best decisions. To accomplish these goals, this solution aimed to i) smartly monitor the traffic lights at the bridge's entrance according to the number and the total load of vehicles crossing, ii) identify any traffic congestion on the bridge and make the appropriate decision in real-time, and iii) notify the appropriate authorities if an anomaly, such as an accident, is detected on the bridge.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The proposed system consists of both hardware and software components. Its hardware components are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Proposed system's hardware architecture.

A. System's Hardware Architecture

The proposed autonomous system consists of:

- Two weight sensors such as Weigh-in-Motion (WIM) load cells placed at the bridge entrance and exit. A WIM sensor is a piezoelectric polymer sensor that generates a voltage proportional to the applied pressure or load. This system is used primarily to measure the weight and speed of vehicles in motion [15]. The instant total weight of the vehicles on the bridge can be calculated based on the weight of each vehicle entering and exiting the bridge.
- Closed Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras installed along the entire bridge. This system consists of video cameras, display monitors, and wired or wireless data networks. This system is used to capture an image of the current traffic on the bridge and send it for processing. The field of view for CCTV cameras ranges between 40-120 feet [16], depending on various variables. The number of cameras to be deployed is based on the length of the bridge.
- Some microcontroller boards, such as the Arduino UNO. Arduino is an open-source prototype platform built on simple hardware and software [17]. These devices can be used to collect the necessary data from the sensors/camera and carry out the required computations for managing and manipulating the bridge traffic lights.
- A server for displaying the instant status of the bridge, i.e. a dashboard.

B. System Software Components

The proposed system's multi-agent global dynamic includes two different kinds of agents:

- The first is the Traffic agent, who is responsible for monitoring the traffic lights. Based on the instantaneous detected traffic, its task is to decide when to change the traffic lights from green to red (and inversely). This agent can be installed on the traffic lights' microcontroller at the bridge entrance and is in charge of providing the server with the data required to update the dashboard with the status of the entire bridge. It has also the duty to report any irregularity found on the bridge to the authorities.
- Crowd agents are responsible for detecting any anomalies on the bridge, such as normal congestion or congestion brought on by accidents, etc. These agents are placed at each camera's microcontroller across the bridge, and they are in charge of turning on the corresponding camera and analyzing the status of the bridge according to the taken bridge picture. Each crowd agent can assess the condition of a specific section of the bridge and inform the Traffic agent to update the traffic lights appropriately.

These agents communicate by sending messages to prevent the bridge from traffic congestion. This dynamic includes three main processes:

1. A Negotiation process between these agents according to the current status of the bridge to take the right decision. When the Traffic agent requests it, the Crowd agents are in charge of checking the status of their respective bridge segments. The subsequent duty is to monitor the traffic light following the data gathered from the Crowd agents and the knowledge of the bridge status.
2. A Prediction process, using a supervised learning model (regression model). This model is trained based on historical data on previous bridge traffic, such as those in Table I. These records detail the total weights of the vehicles that crossed the bridge every time interval, every day, and every month. The trained model is employed to determine the initial schedule for the traffic light switching per time, day, month, etc. This schedule is flexible and subject to change depending on the situation.
3. A Detection process that uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to identify any irregularities on the bridge that necessitates an urgent adjustment to the timetable for switching the lights. This process is used to determine whether there is congestion on the bridge, classify it according to normal or abnormal, and determine whether or not it is related to an accident.

TABLE I. DATA SAMPLE OF VEHICLES CROSSING THE BRIDGE

Date	Time	Total weight	Number of cars	Camera result	Traffic lights status
2023/02/12	8:08:48	4486	3	0	1
2023/02/12	8:08:54	4485	3	1	0
2023/02/12	8:08:59	4483	4	1	0
2023/02/12	8:09:04	4481	5	1	1
2023/02/12	8:09:10	4480	6	1	0
2023/02/12	8:09:16	4478	7	1	0
2023/02/12	8:09:21	4476	8	1	1
2023/02/12	8:09:27	4476	8	1	0
2023/02/12	8:09:33	4476	8	1	0
2023/02/12	8:09:39	4475	8	1	1
2023/02/12	8:09:44	4474	8	1	0
2023/02/12	8:09:50	4473	8	1	0
2023/02/13	8:24:12	4500	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:24:17	4500	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:24:23	4499	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:24:28	4499	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:24:34	4498	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:24:39	4498	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:24:45	4498	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:24:51	4498	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:24:56	4498	1	0	1
2023/02/13	8:25:02	4497	1	0	1

Fig. 3. Decision phase flowchart.

C. System's Global Dynamic

The global dynamic of this system can be divided into two phases: an initialization and a decision phase.

- During the Initialization phase, the Traffic agent employs a regression model to predict the weights of oncoming traffic on the bridge for the upcoming days. The time/duration schedule of traffic light switching is decided based on the acquired estimates. When this phase is over, the second begins.
- Using the aforementioned schedule, the Traffic agent adjusts the traffic signal during the Decision phase as shown by the flow diagram in Figure 3. The agent updates the overall weight over the bridge at each instant using the information obtained from the weight sensors and the WIM load cells. This value will be compared to the estimated one to determine whether there is any congestion on the bridge and to ensure that the maximum load permitted is not being exceeded. There could be several cases.

The first case is when the calculated total weight is much less than or very close to both the estimated and the permitted weights, respectively. Then, the timetable for the traffic light is maintained.

Fig. 2. Crowded road detection.

The second case occurs if the calculated total weight is greater than the estimated but is still less than the permitted. The traffic agent determines whether the excess weight is the result of accident-related or regular congestion. The timetable for the traffic lights should be adjusted, depending on the congestion type:

- A bridge anomaly exists if there is a large proportion of vehicles arriving relative to those leaving. The closest and farthest (two extremities) Crowd agents will receive a message from the Traffic agent asking them to investigate any anomalies in their section of the bridge.
- If the number of vehicles entering is proportional to those departing, there is normal congestion, and the traffic signal schedule should be modified following these new findings. The Traffic lights should be turned red until the traffic jam is alleviated.

Each Crowd agent should turn on its camera after receiving a message from a Traffic agent to capture a photo of the bridge before starting the detection procedure. The Traffic agent determines whether to examine additional Crowd agents based on the results or whether to alert the police of the accident's position on the bridge.

The third case occurs if the calculated total weight is larger than the estimated total weight, less than the permitted one, and there is no accident on the bridge. In this case, the traffic signal schedule will be maintained. These new records will be used for further training of the supervised model to improve its performance. All discoveries must be submitted to the server to be preserved for later use or to be exhibited in the dashboard, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Example of the dashboard content.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A simplified version of a CNN model for binary image classification was designed and implemented to test the feasibility and possible deployment of the system, as shown in Figures 2 and 5. A binary classification was used since only the two classes of congested and not-congested were taken into account in this initial version of the model.

Fig. 5. Not crowded road detection.

The Google Images platform was used to obtain a dataset of road congestion levels for the training of the CNN, and 1168 total photos were collected. The dataset included two traffic congestion classes: Crowded (418 images) and Not Crowded (750 images). The implemented network consists of three convolutional layers with a Relu activation function, each followed by a Maxpooling layer and two fully connected layers. As it is easy to recognize the crowded (or not) features within an image, only a few deep layers were needed for testing the model. The last layer was based on the Sigmoid activation function. The used filters had a size of 3x3x3 for RGB images (256x256x3) and a stride of 1. The first layer was a convolutional layer with 16 filters, the second used 32 filters, and the last used 16 filters. The performance of the traffic detection models was evaluated using three metrics: Precision, Recall, and Accuracy. The results of this model were compared to VGG-19, as shown in Table II.

TABLE II. CNN VS. VGG-19

	Precision	Recall	Accuracy
CNN	0.9062	0.9354	0.9545
VGG-19	0.9722	0.8139	0.9181

The accuracy, precision, and recall of the CNN model were 95%, 91%, and 93%, respectively. On the other hand, the accuracy, precision, and recall of the VGG-19 model were 92%, 97%, and 81%, respectively. VGG-19 classified 91% of the instances accurately, however, only 97% of the events classified as positive were genuinely positive. In addition, only 81% of all positive events were accurately detected by the model. These findings imply that the proposed CNN model could be a preferable option due to its simplicity, higher accuracy, and better ability to balance precision and recall.

V. CONCLUSION

Bridges are crucial components of the transportation system, and their collapse can have serious repercussions. It is essential to have a regular, real-time, autonomous controlling and monitoring system to protect against bridge damages caused by excessive traffic and traffic jams, particularly from overloaded vehicles. This study presented a novel autonomous and intelligent bridge protection system that uses an autonomous real-time decision-making system. This system was designed to increase a bridge's usage by protecting it from overload and traffic congestion. The hardware component of this solution, which included WIM load cells, microcontrollers, and CCTV cameras, was supported by a multi-agent system for autonomous decision-making that used deep and machine learning models. Using a road dataset, a limited version of the deep learning model was developed, trained, and tested. A straightforward CNN was used to demonstrate the viability of the suggested system. Despite its usefulness, this system had some limitations in preventing overloaded vehicles from crossing the bridge and identifying the type of anomalies. In future work, the CNN model will be expanded to detect overloaded vehicles, identify the cause of an anomaly, such as the occurrence of an accident among congestion, and will be evaluated based on real data cases.

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Randomly-based Stepwise Multi-Level Distributed Medical Image Steganography

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ABSTRACT

Steganography deals with concealing sensitive information that can either be communicated across a network or stored in a secured location. The concealment of information is accomplished through the carrier, making data access by an unauthorized person more difficult. There are many steganographic techniques that have been used. Unfortunately, the hybrid-multi-level approach was ignored. For this reason, the current research utilized image steganography on a hybrid-multi level involving encryption, data compression, and two-stage high data concealment. The proposed technique can be used to conceal information in medical images without any distortion, allowing flexible and secure transfer capability. After using the Triple DES algorithm to encrypt the secret text at the beginning of the process, the next step involves embedding the secret encrypted cipher message into the host image while keeping the image intact. The findings indicate that the value of PSNR and NCC are satisfactory when compared to the sensitivity of the human eye. As a direct impact, the confidential message is hidden from the adversary. It can be seen that the PSNR value is quite high. Therefore, this indicates that the image after the steganographic process is relatively similar to the original image.

Keywords—steganography; multiple-embedding; encryption; multi-level analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Image steganography involves the collection of images and the embedding of secret data inside them [1]. Security and confidentiality of data transmissions are two of the most important factors for which image steganography is so important [2]. As new technologies emerge and people become increasingly reliant on data communications and the information they hold, the need for greater levels of security and privacy has never been greater [3]. Despite the claims of many protocols and applications, attackers are always one step ahead of the security measures. Every day, new threats emerge that increase the danger of data and communications being compromised [4]. Due to this, the current study feels that it is vital to continue researching the security concerns related with data transmission. Image steganography is a part of the field of information security and the art of information concealment.

Despite other approaches of information security that also play crucial roles, steganography is mostly dominated towards the used of images [5]. Cryptosystems have traditionally been thought of as the most effective methods for concealing information. However, they do not hide information entirely. They rather convert information into a format that is unreadable [6]. Unfortunately, the use of encryption methods can be broken due to the widespread availability of powerful devices and tools that can break complex algorithms [7], because their concealed format can be seen. As a consequence of this ever-increasing threat landscape, there is a requirement

for a method of data protection that is both secure and effective. It is essential to have algorithms based on steganography that not only provide security but also keep data confidential. As part of this research, a steganography tool is provided in order to boost the level of security in data transfer. In recent years, a vast number of various steganographic tools have been proposed to safeguard the transfer of data [8-11]. In most cases, steganographic methods that are suited to the multi-media realm end up gaining a great deal of popularity [8]. From a different point of view, the implementation of invertible image steganography has also demonstrated a significant applicability [9]. JPEG format steganography with content similarity has also demonstrated significant applicability [10]. Also, the hybrid algorithm approach to low-level space-bounded image steganography, which aims to enhance payload capacity, has gained a lot of interest [11]. However, the Least Significant Bit (LSB) methodology is a method that is continually being adjusted and improved [12-14].

Maintaining consistency with the earlier research is essential to the process of ensuring that the adopted steganographic method is both robust and extremely reliable. The aim of this study is to propose a method of enhancing steganographic security by applying a Multi-Layer Security Strategic approach, which involves applying various event-driven security routines. This tool will boost the security of the secret text message under many different protection levels. The research takes into account the use of the LSB, of an image. Steganography is another form of covert communication that

can be strengthened by the application of cryptographic methods [15]. Many prior studies have examined spatial picture steganography techniques. The LSB method has gained a lot of traction recently. For inserting data into a cover image, the LSB replacement is an ideal, easy execution [13].

Depending on the spatial approach, an improved strategy for hiding information in areas of an image with abundant noise was proposed in [16]. The key aspect of this article is the ability to hide information 8 times more effectively than standard LSB, which is achieved through the use of deep neural networks. It is important however, that the image used as a cover for the secret message fit certain parameters, which are established by the results of the network test. It is therefore impossible to use this technique on any image. In addition, the use of networks increases the method's complexity and implementation costs. Using the ImageNet database, the neural network in [16] was trained and tested on random images and achieved high accuracy. An improved method of concealing information within an image was proposed in [17] and it relies on a spatial approach. Using a genuine image, the authors also applied quicker methods for region-based convolutional neural networks by mapping features or elements in order to discover the most appropriate and safest areas to hide the image. The highly undetectable stego algorithm was used as well, which provided greater secrecy and a higher bit count than LSB.

Authors in [18] came up with an idea for compressing sensitive data, encoding them, and then using the AES algorithm to establish an encryption procedure for them. Finally, they were buried within the Arabic text in particular characters and places, so that the main text is not affected by their presence. Aside from that, the use of protocols that are hidden within the text, audio, graphics, or headers was proposed. Authors in [19] hid personal information before it is communicated by utilizing an LSB method. Authors in [20] investigated when it would be appropriate to use deep learning in order to make steganography suitable for protecting inference privacy. Other studies that were conducted in the past have shed light on a significant number of issues connected to steganography. It is imperative that the number of participants utilizing counting-based secret sharing must be increased as much as possible through the utilization of involved matrices and functional steganography [21]. This is of the utmost importance due to the fact that secure communication can be achieved based on the swift response associated with robust concealment [22]. Furthermore, authors in [23] proposed a GAN-based spatial picture steganography equipped with a cross-feedback mechanism. Enhancing grayscale steganography in order to prevent the disclosure of personally identifiable information [24] is a practice that is quite common. As a consequence, authors in [25] developed a method of chaotic video steganography as a means of concealing a wide variety of covert communications in a variety of contexts. In addition, authors in [26] investigated the robustness of a secure and undetectable image steganography in discrete wavelet transform by employing the logical function of XOR and the genetic algorithm. Using an image disentanglement autoencoder for steganography without embedding results brings an increased level of security [27]. Authors in [28] proposed a dynamic four-step data security model for cloud

computing data that was based on steganography and cryptography to protect data from unauthorized access. A method for protected image steganography that makes use of the ballot transform and the genetic algorithm was suggested in [29]. It was recently discovered that DNA nano sensing systems are now capable of tunable detection of metal ions and molecular crypto-steganography [30].

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study consists of experimental simulation for embedding, followed by the application of attacks, and ends with a performance evaluation of the proposed technique. The study asserts that people are able to innately seek out and recognize the areas of a medical image that have the most intriguing attributes. The integrity of this area must never be compromised, and it must be preserved in the initial state. However, this does not necessarily mean that the quality of the visual presentation should be upheld while the confidential data are being concealed inside the image. Additionally, the mechanism used in the embedding process should permit the operation to be carried out in a batch format. To put it another way, there is the need of a technique that lowers the needed computational complexity while still allowing for the inclusion of multiple photographs at once.

A. The Steganography Process

The following primary phases are carried out during the embedding process:

- Encrypt the message using the Triple DES algorithm.
- Select the first cover image to upload.
- Implement the LSB technique with the first image (embed text in image): This method embeds the text in the image by substituting the LSB of the first cover image with the bits of the message to be hidden.
- Upload the second cover image.
- Implement the LSB technique with the second image (embed image in image): This function is implemented by replacing the LSB of the second cover image with the bits of the first cover image that contains the secret text.

Following the successful execution of the embedding, an extraction process was carried out, consisting of the following steps:

- Upload the stego image: This function uploads the stego image.
- Extract the first image: This function decodes and then extracts the first image from the second image.
- Decrypt the message: This function decrypts the message using the key and was originally stored in the image.

B. The Embedding Technique

This study sought to have a batch embedding, while maintaining the computational complexity as low as possible. D. The steps of the procedure are outlined in Figure 1.

```

Algorithm 1 Multi-level random embedding
Input set: Host Image(H), Secret Message (S), Operation (O)
Output: Stego image
1: Initialize Embedding(image)
2: if ciphertext ∈ {a, b} where a & b ∈ (S) then
3:   (O) ← load ((H))
4:   H = ← ciphertext (O) matrix[size_pixel]
5:   read (H), (O) carrier and host key/value pair
6: else
7:   Set a random value K
8:   List ← Kl = {a|O<O<n}
9:   for each Kl(H) {a, b} in ←List do
10:    H = Encrypt(S)
11:   end for
12: end if
13: end if
14: Within Kl = {a|O<O<n} (H)
15:   lsb = set lsb (1, -1) //change the bit (values) with random bit manipulation.
16:   if lsb != Hn Hsa ← HSb = (H):
17:     Kl(Hsar-HSbs) = >>1 # set the random bit
18:     Kl(Hsar-HSbs) = <<1 # set the random bit
19:   if (Hsar-HSbs) ∪ (Hsar-HSbs) == 0 //random location in lsb found that
20:     H* = Random_lsb | [HS, HS1, HS2, ...HSn]
21:     matrix[HS, HSn][O] = Kl(H) {a, b}
22:     bitl += 1
23:     Kl(H) {a, b} = get (num)_ Kl(H) {a, b}
24:   RETURN = Rearrange values (Kl) positions
25: end

```

Fig. 1. Multilevel random embedding algorithm pseudocode.

The host image (H), the secret message (S), and the embedding process are the three things that the steganography algorithm takes in as input (O). The stego picture is the produced output. During the embedding process, the secret message is multiplied by the embedding operation that is connected to the encryption and is necessary in order to produce a ciphertext. After this, the randomization process will take place, during which a two-level matrix that will be searching for hidden areas within the LSB will be established using either random bit manipulation or random bit generation. The host picture is going to be looking for the embedding of the confidential information. After determining the appropriate site for the LSB, the embedding process can then begin. The ability to conceal the secret text was put to the test, and the procedures were tested regarding their ability to either decipher the hidden message or corrupt it in some way. The capacity to extract safely secret information from an image and a high level of concealment of that information can only be ensured by selecting a suitable embedding factor.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SEQUENCE ANALYSIS

In this paper, the secret message is embedded into the host image to obtain the stego image, thereafter the stego image is evaluated and the performance of the technique is measured. Finally, the secret message is extracted from the stego image. The experiment was carried out on a personal computer that featured an Intel(R) 1.60 GHz processor, with 4 GB RAM and simulation software written in C#, Python, and Visual studio. During the experimentation process, both subjective vision and objective quantitative analysis were used to evaluate the invisibility and robustness of the algorithm. The experiment uses a cover image with dimensions of 1024×1024 pixels and data in the form of text as the steganography medium for the hidden message. In the first step of this project, the PSNR and NCC were utilized.

A. Performance of the Embedding Technique

After making the stego-image, the subsequent step is to conduct an assessment of the performance of the technique

used in order to determine whether or not the stego image was distorted. The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) is a popular metric used to evaluate this performance [31]. Stego-images have the capability of retaining both their visual quality and content integrity, only when they can resist any attack that falls under the umbrella of difference distortion techniques. The degree to which the steganographic image is concealed within the information that is intended to remain secret is an essential factor to consider during the evaluation of the effectiveness of the steganography algorithm. The condition of the stego image can be evaluated based on the PSNR and the structural similarity values of the original image by Normalized Cross Correlation (NCC). As a result, the PSNR is measured by:

$$PSNR = 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{R_{max}^2}{MSE} \right) \quad (1)$$

MSE stands for the Mean Square Error between the host image and the stego embedded image, while the maximum pixel value in the host image is denoted by R_{max} . MSE is measured by:

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i,j} (I(i,j) - Tw(i,j))^2}{i*j} \quad (2)$$

The NCC, which provides a comparison of the original and the stego image on the basis of similarity values is measured by:

$$NCC = \frac{\sum_{i,j} W(i,j) * W_E(i,j)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i,j} W(i,j)^2 * W_E(i,j)^2}} \quad (3)$$

B. Embedding Process

Embedding is particularly done in order to ensure the security of the secret message. However, it should be made in such a way that the human visual system cannot see the trace of the secret message in the stego image. The steganographic technique has been deployed as a part of this research, and a Graphical User Interface (GUI) has been developed to facilitate the execution of the steganography (see Figure 2). The proposed method necessitates that the phases of steganography begin with the process of encryption, during which the confidential text message will be encrypted utilizing the Data Encryption Standard (DES) algorithm. There were 3 different experimental analyses conducted with 6 different host images. In the first experiment, the first host image is denoted by (a), and the second host image is denoted by (b). In the second experiment, the first image is denoted by (c), and the second by (d). In the third experiment, the first host image is denoted by (e), and the second by (f).

After the encryption, the hidden ciphertext message will be embedded on the first host image using a random pick of its LSB. This will result in the production of the very first stego image. Therefore, a linear LSB will be utilized in order to incorporate the current stego picture into the second host image. The deployed GUI provides the option of giving a text entry as the secret message which then will be made available to the system, accompanied with a push button that activates the encryption feature. Upon the completion of the encryption, a selection option for the host image is made available. The user has to select from a list of sample steganography standard host images.

Fig. 2. The GUI of the deployed steganography process.

At this time, the program may commence dual processing, since there will be a choice regarding the uploading of a second host image. One single hidden message can be inserted into each of these host images at the same time. This is the main contribution of the current research to the existing body of knowledge. The first host image, after the embedding of the secret ciphertext in it, can be embedded in a second host image. The next step is the presentation of an option whether to embed the secret message in both host images, or in the first only. After the user's selection, the final stego image will be created and downloaded.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When the PSNR ratio is greater than 37dB, the secret information embedded in the cover image is invisible to the human visual system, and when the structural similarity is greater than 0.93, the steganography image is not much different from the cover image [32]. According to this, once the embedding process is complete, the PSNR will reveal whether the inserted secret message distorted the original content or not in order to validate the efficacy of the applied method. This will allow the effectiveness of the method to be evaluated. In addition, taking into account the values that are being used as a benchmark, the analysis for this study was carried out using 3 distinct methods. A text-cipher was embedded on each host image separately (text-image) in the first instance, which was the embedding using the random check for the LSB within the host image. This was then followed by embedding the corresponding stego-image to the second host image (image-image). The PSNR and NCC values for the experiment (text-image) are significantly better than the benchmarking values, meaning that there is no difference between the steganographic image and the original cover image, and that the extracted secret image contains all of secret information in its entirety. It should be noted that the PSNR of the image (a) is 57.065 dB

and the NCC value is 0.96511, which is the highest among the PSNR values. However, the image (f) has the highest value of NCC (see Table I).

The next step is the embedding process, which involves using the sequence of the LSB within the host image. This process involves embedding a secret image on each host image (image-image). The total values of the PSNR and NCC are significantly higher than the benchmarking values. This indicates that, from the point of view of human vision, there is no difference between the steganographic image and the original cover image, and that the extracted secret image contains all the secret information in its entirety. It is important to note the fact that the PSNR of the image (b) is 56.132 dB, which is the highest, and its NCC value is 0.98853. However, the image (c) has the highest value of NCC. In this instance, it is clear that the method was executed in an excellently appropriate manner.

In the second scenario, the embedding was conducted using the random check for the LSB within the host image. The text-cipher was first embedded on the first host image separately (text-image), and then the stego-image that was formed was embedded in the second host image using the operation that was described in Figure 1. On the second stego picture, the calculations for determining the PSNR and NCC values for this procedure were carried out (text-image-image). After that, a stego picture was used to embed a new host image, and the stego image associated with that host image was likewise included in another stego image (image-image-image). In this instance, all of the PSNR and NCC values are either above the benchmark or significantly above it. This indicates that, from the point of view of human vision, there is no difference between the steganographic image and the original cover image, and that the extracted secret image contains all the hidden information in its entirety. It is important to point out

that in the experiment, the image with the highest PSNR is the (d) image, however, the image with the highest value of NCC is the (e). The PSNR of the image with the secret image message is 55.837 dB, and its NCC value is 0.98168 (Table II).

TABLE I. PSNR AND NC VALUES FOR THE FIRST EXPERIMENT

Image	Text-Image		Image-Image	
	PSNR(dB)	NCC	PSNR(dB)	NCC
(a)	57.065	0.96511	47.95	0.98566
(b)	55.247	0.96798	56.132	0.98853
(c)	52.407	0.97046	53.292	0.99101
(d)	48.245	0.99251	47.691	0.96447
(e)	56.427	0.99538	50.047	0.96823
(f)	53.587	0.99786	53.178	0.9713

TABLE II. PSNR AND NC VALUES FOR THE SECOND EXPERIMENT

Image	Text-Image-Image		Image-Image-Image	
	PSNR(dB)	NCC	PSNR(dB)	NCC
(a)	50.342	0.97508	48.576	0.98502
(b)	53.473	0.97815	50.932	0.98878
(c)	47.655	0.97881	54.063	0.99185
(d)	55.837	0.98168	47.36	0.97196
(e)	52.997	0.98416	55.542	0.97483
(f)	48.281	0.97817	52.702	0.97731

The third example demonstrates good values between the steganographic image and the original host image. The highest PSNR value of 55.542 dB is observed in image (e), while its NCC value is 0.97483. When it comes to this instance, it is clear that the strategy used was excellent. The difference between the third scenario and the first two is that the embedding of text and images was done simultaneously for both the first and second host images (Text-Image-Text-Image and Image-Image-Image-Image), whereas in the first two scenarios, the embedding of text and images was done sequentially. In a similar vein, every single value of the PSNR and NCC throughout this operation was superior to the standard setting (see Table III). This indicates that, from the point of human eyesight, there is no discernible difference between the stego image and the original host image.

TABLE III. PSNR AND NC VALUES FOR THE THIRD EXPERIMENT

Image	Text-Image-Text-Image		Image-Image-Image-Image	
	PSNR(dB)	NCC	PSNR(dB)	NCC
(a)	48.576	0.98502	47.95	0.98566
(b)	50.932	0.98878	56.132	0.98853
(c)	54.063	0.99185	53.292	0.99101
(d)	48.871	0.99187	47.36	0.97196
(e)	51.227	0.99563	55.542	0.97483
(f)	54.358	0.9987	52.702	0.97731

The performance is about stable, even while repeatedly performing the experiment while taking into consideration different embedding series. In the scenario where a text message was concealed within an image cover file and then the stego-image was concealed within a different cover image, both experiments produced appropriate results. In this scenario, both PSNR (Figure 3) and NCC (Figure 4) are greater than the threshold. It should be noted that the PSNR of the cover image that was utilized in text-image or image-image embedding or

mixing of the cover image and the stego-image reached the very high value of almost 58 dB in every case. This is a crucial point that needs to be emphasized. The obtained NCC value was nearly 0.99, making it the highest of the 3 possibilities (Figure 4). The application of these findings is driven by the wish to acquire knowledge regarding which of the sample images, from (a) to (f), possesses the highest performance value in terms of embedding capacity. Even though the experiment considers mainly the embedding process, which involves using the searching sequence within the host image, embedding in general requires that a secret message on each host should be within a trade-off of capacity, robustness, and imperceptibility, due to the fact that the capabilities of the host determine the degree to which the message can be embedded effectively. The obtained total values of the PSNR and NCC are significantly higher than the benchmark values, suggesting that there is no difference between the steganographic image and the original cover image, and that the extracted secret image contains the secret information in its entirety, which indicates that the research has achieved an unbreakable level of success.

Although the first experimental scenario was successful in achieving imperceptibility, the subsequent experiment focused on embedding a text-cipher within the host image. Following that, the stego-image will be concealed under another image. On the other hand, an image can be inserted inside another image, and the stego image itself can be embedded inside another image. This circumstance is connected to striking a balance in a specific system between capacity, resilience, and imperceptibility. As a direct result, the experiment to embed images on the host image was carried out, and after that, the produced stego-image was inserted in the second host image making use of the same approach. The findings indicate that there is no difference between the steganographic image and the original cover image. In addition, the findings of the trials suggest that the human eye is unable to differentiate between the steganographic image and the original cover image. During the test, the image with a PSNR value of 58 dB was found to have the highest contrast (Figure 5) and the highest value of NCC was 0.98 (see Figure 6) regardless of the specifics of the situation that it is viewed in. Given the data that were gathered during the study, in particular those that were associated with this circumstance, it would appear that the investigation has reached a stage where it is no longer appropriate to proceed, given the findings. The most crucial thing to do when comparing the results of the experiment is to search for ways in which they differ from one another. In a typical run of this experiment, all the previous hosts and hidden messages were likewise put to use. The implementation of multiple layers was used in this stage of the process. The performance analysis showed that every possible outcome had satisfactory results (see Figures 7 and 8), due to the fact that the technology that is being utilized has resulted in many alternatives in achieving similar levels of imperceptibility. In a similar vein, this research has demonstrated that it is possible to covertly embed a message in any and all available mediums at the same time. All the performed procedures were improvements over the regular routine. There is no discernible difference between the stego image and the original host image, in any tested case.

Fig. 3. The PSNR values for the first scenario.

Fig. 4. The NCC values for the first scenario.

Fig. 5. The PSNR values for the second scenario.

Fig. 6. The NCC values for the second scenario.

Fig. 7. The PSNR values for the third scenario.

Fig. 8. The NCC values for the third scenario.

The findings of this study were compared to the findings of other studies in terms of the carried out procedures. According to Table IV, the PSNR obtained in this study was significantly better than those of the considered past studies.

TABLE IV. RESULT COMPARISON

Study	PSNR(dB)
[9]	44.19
[11]	46.4381
[33]	44.6229
[34]	44.6229
This study	60

V. CONCLUSION

Steganography refers to the act of concealing confidential data in a manner that enables their transmission over a network or storage in a secure location. The concealment of information through the carrier is a common practice, as it enhances the security of the data by rendering it less accessible to unauthorized parties. Several methods have been proposed, disregarding the implementation of hybrid-multi-level approaches. The present study employed a hybrid-multi-level approach for achieving high data concealment, in conjunction with image steganography. The experimental models demonstrated that the proposed approach has the ability to conceal data within images. The aforementioned feature enables the provision of transfer options that are both secure and flexible. The process of embedding an encrypted cipher message into a host image was deemed necessary, utilizing the Least Significant Bit (LSB) approach in a sequential manner subsequent to the initial encryption of the message with the Triple Data Encryption Standard (DES) algorithm. This measure guaranteed the preservation of the cover image's authenticity.

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) can be utilized to determine the extent to which the inclusion of a covert message alters the primary data. By employing this approach, one can assess the effectiveness of the strategy. Three distinct analytical methodologies were employed to examine the data in this investigation. The findings indicate that the PSNR and NCC metrics demonstrate satisfactory results when compared to the sensitivity of the human eye. The PSNR value surpassed the benchmark values in every experiment. The results indicate that the image produced following the stenographic process bears a resemblance to the initial image and the contained information is undetectable by the human eye.

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The Use of Recurrent Nets for the Prediction of e-Commerce Sales

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ABSTRACT

The increase in e-commerce sales and profits has been a source of much anxiety over the years. Due to the advances in Internet technology, more and more people choose to shop online. Online retailers can improve customer satisfaction using sentiment analysis in comments and reviews to gain higher profits. This study used Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) to predict future sales from previous using the Kaggle dataset. A Bidirectional Long Short Term Memory (BLTSM) RNN was employed by tuning various hyperparameters to improve accuracy. The results showed that this BLTSM model of the RNN was quite accurate at predicting future sales performance.

Keywords-e-commerce; sales; deep learning; prediction; RNNs

I. INTRODUCTION

The term e-commerce refers to any commercial transaction that takes place over the Internet. E-commerce is divided into "non-payment e-commerce", which does not involve the exchange of money or the delivery of products to customers, and "payment e-commerce", which enables customers to make purchases and arrange shipments of items online [1]. Along with the rest, "non-payment e-commerce", includes actions performed by delivery services and activities performed by vendors related to the sale of items [2]. E-commerce can be broken down into four distinct sub-industries: business-to-business (B2B), business-to-consumer (B2C), business-to-government (B2G), and consumer-to-government (C2G). The first two types of electronic business transactions that come to mind are business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) [3]. E-commerce is often used to describe a new style of business operations that is distinguished from traditional by the fact that customers buy products or services using a browser and a server-based application hosted on an Internet platform [1]. Since 2013, there is a substantial rise in the use of the Internet to deliver high-quality services and the frequency of electronic commercial transactions continues to grow [4]. Traditional methods of sales forecasting are based on time series analysis and usually accept only input sales data from the most recent quarters. Using these tactics, it is possible to effectively manage commodities whose sales trends are either consistent or seasonal [5]. In contrast to this, the prices of commodities sold through e-commerce are much higher and the sales trends of these commodities are highly unpredictable. In addition, the accuracy of the forecasts obtained using traditional methods is often excessively poor [6].

It is feasible to boost the accuracy of forecasts using the huge amount of data available in the e-commerce industry. Feature engineering is the first step in traditional machine-learning approaches. This process involves manually extracting valuable features from easily accessible data [7]. The accuracy of a forecast model can be strongly impacted, both positively and negatively, by the quality and number of attributes contained within the model. However, the process of generating useful features is both challenging and time-consuming. In addition, these attributes are often acquired on an individual basis for one-of-a-kind business scenarios, which makes it difficult to reuse the models if the data or requirements change in the future. When gathering further data for online sales, feature engineering should be carried out to include the information contained in the new data in the prediction model. It is possible that feature learning could eliminate the requirement to manually engineer features [6]. Numerous studies have been conducted to extract features from unstructured data, such as photos, audio, text, and others, using deep neural networks. [8].

Many studies have investigated reliable and accurate sales prediction, and most of them agreed that it is a challenging issue in the field of e-commerce. In [2], a method was presented to use information based on cross-series using the unified model. A Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network was trained using the relationships based on the non-linearity in e-commerce product variety. Moreover, a framework was presented for systematic preprocessing to address e-commerce challenges. Several product grouping strategies have also been introduced to improve LSTM learning. In [3], an LSTM-based model was presented for consumer comments sentiment analysis to predict the short-term demand for products. The LSTM model was carried out based on a sequence of time

series and the rating of sentiment comments to predict future sales. Due to minimal historic data, the decision maker is needed to take proper actions and react toward the market. It was also suggested that the sentiment rating weight adjustment can improve the prediction accuracy. The proposed LSTM approach performed well in terms of accuracy.

In [7], a model called Sen-BERT-CNN was presented to analyze customer reviews, based on CNN and pre-trained Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) to extract the sentiment information of a sentence. In [8], a method was used that combined the patterns of two graphs to predict the community trends on an item attribute. In [9], the LSTM and the Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) were used to predict the demand for a product based on previous sales and satisfy future customer requirements. In [10], genetic algorithms were used in conjunction with a profit-maximizing logistic model to forecast client attrition. In a similar strategy in [11], data-driven agent-based analysis of customer behavior was used, while in [12] a study was carried out to estimate and infer heterogeneous treatment effects utilizing random forests to determine the extent to which sales are associated with e-commerce. In the same spirit, machine learning was used in [13] to interpret Internet of Things data. In [14], a feature selection method was presented based on an artificial bee colony and a gradient-boosting decision tree. In [15], the accurate prediction of protein contact maps was presented by integrating residual two-dimensional BLTSM with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). This method was

supported by a large number of additional studies that followed a similar line of reasoning. In [16], a prediction model was presented using CNNs and RNNs. In [17], a learning framework was described that incorporated various levels of knowledge representation for the analysis of aspect-based sentiments. In [18], a semantic study of social networks in educational settings was presented along with recommendations. In [19], a context was established in photo albums by understanding and modeling user behavior in clustering and selection. Authors in [20] focused on convolutional neural networks and their applications in data mining and sales forecasting for e-commerce. Some studies used deep neural networks, LSTM, and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to predict long-term sales in e-commerce companies, as earlier studies that estimated short-term product demands found it possible to predict long-term future sales. Sales remain a crucial variable in e-commerce. Furthermore, there are several studies analyzing the ways a community uses a product based on some characteristics.

II. METHODOLOGY

Figure 2 shows a flow diagram of the proposed method to predict e-commerce sales with the use of CNNs to select features from a dataset and employing a BLTSM model of RNNs for the prediction. This process began with the building of the model, the gathering and the pre-processing of the dataset, and the experimental training and testing for the prediction.

Fig. 1. The flow process of the prediction experimental analysis and result presentation.

A. The Bidirectional Long-Short-Term Memory (BLTSM) Model of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)

This study adopted a bidirectional LSTM RNN model to predict the growth of sales for all products based on multiple factors [21]. A typical neural network does not function well when the data sequence is essential. Language translation, word recognition, and sentiment analysis are only a few examples of this situation. However, RNNs solve this problem, and BLSTM RNNs are sophisticated in such problems [22]. This model operates in a fashion where neurons are set as the basic building blocks of RNNs, and their strength is conveyed by weights. The RNNs typically consist of input, hidden, and output layers, with each layer's neuron coupled to aid in the retracement of past computations. RNNs excel in processing sequential data, especially when ordering is critical. LSTM solves the gradient problem either by vanishing or exploding in RNNs. The vanishing gradient problem results in an error that prevents RNNs from learning when there are more than 5-10 time steps between the events that are input and the signals that are being targeted [23]. To keep the sequence going, the RNN cell takes into account not just the input cells, but also the output of the current cell. Figure 2 shows an RNN cell. Given an input feature sequence $x = (x_1, \dots, x_T)$, the model can be constructed as a standard LSTM RNN for computing the hidden vector $h=(h_1, \dots, h_T)$ and the output vector sequence $y=(y_1, \dots, y_T)$ [23]. This can be determined by solving the following equations repeatedly, starting with time t equal to 1 and going up to T :

$$(h_t, c_t) = H(x_t, h_{t-1}, c_{t-1}) \quad (1)$$

$$y_t = W_{hy}h_t + h_y \quad (2)$$

where $W_{hy}h_t$ is the hidden-output weight matrix of the LSTM-RNN, and c is the cell activation vector that has the same size as the hidden vector h [23]. The W terms describe the weight matrices and the b terms denote the bias vectors, e.g., b_y is the output bias vector.

Fig. 2. The Architectural frame of an RNN –cell.

The deep LSTM-RNN has properties that are indicative of DNNs in general. It is feasible to generate it by stacking some LSTM-RNN hidden layers one atop another, with the output sequence of one layer functioning as the input for the succeeding in the stack. This process can be repeated as many times as necessary to generate it. Tanh is a function frequently used as an activation for RNNs. These relatively low values constrain the ultimate gradient while backpropagation takes place, but they have no impact on the weights. Because of the vanishing gradient problem, the process of training the model

goes more slowly. Memory cells are added to the buried layers of the RNN to find a solution to this problem, and the original design of the RNN is transformed into a long- and short-term memory system [25]. The LSTM architecture is made up of memory cells, an input gate, a forget gate, and an output gate. The input gate in the LSTM is responsible for determining whether the existing activation of the cell should be altered by the addition of new information obtained from the input network in the existing cell. The output gate has the responsibility to choose and pass pertinent information from the currently active cell to the next. The forget gate receives information from previous states, resets the action values, and contributes to the process of determining what information from the previous state should be discarded and what should be maintained. These gates alleviate the problem of disappearing gradients that can occur in LSTMs [26]. This is a similar approach to [27] on the detection and recognition of danger signs, to [28] on prediction, and to [29] on the planning of routes using RNNs. The LSTM is guided and uses the historical context maintained by the forget gate. Using this context in both directions allows for accurate transcription to be completed. As a direct consequence, this study developed bidirectional LSTMs by fusing two LSTMs (forward and backward). It is possible to combine many BLSTM layers to achieve a greater sense of depth and abstraction. This method used two LSTM layers, with 256 hidden cells in each. Following this step, this study also used a dropout layer and Adam as an optimizer.

B. Dataset Generation and Preprocessing

The dataset consisted of e-commerce sales data from the Kaggle repository, containing 23486 rows and 10 different feature variables. Customer age, title, rating, recommended flag, and reviews were some of the factors that were included in the dataset along with other variables such as clothing identification, which was a categorical variable that refers to the item in question. Anaconda and Google Collab were used to carry out the analysis. In addition, the recommended binary *IND* variable was used as a flag to indicate whether the client recommends the product (1) or not (0). As a result, ratings, reviews, and the recommended flag were taken into account when creating the training dataset for the products. Following this step, the dataset was cleaned out using several distinct forms of data preprocessing methods, such as tokenization and stop word removal, among others.

Tokenization is the first stage in any Natural Language Processing (NLP) pipeline, as the results of this step have a considerable influence on the subsequent steps. Using a tool called a tokenizer, unstructured data and text written in natural language are both sliced up into chunks of information that can be considered independent elements. A tokenization method was used to generate a vector that accurately represents this data, and then a technique known as the removal of stop words was also applied. These preprocessing steps are the most frequently used in a variety of NLP applications. The basic idea is to filter out any words present in every review in the dataset.

Both these terms are meaningless in the context of the prediction and recommendation task. Figures 3 and 4 show a subset of the dataset and the relevant statistics.

TABLE I. A DATASET SNAPSHOT

Count	Rating	Recommended IND	Positive Feedback Count
0	4	1	0
1	5	1	4
2	3	0	0
3	5	1	0
4	5	1	6
5	2	0	4
6	5	1	1
7	4	1	4
8	5	1	0
9	5	1	0
10	3	0	14
11	5	1	2
12	5	1	2
13	5	1	0
14	3	1	1
15	4	1	3
16	3	1	2
17	5	1	0
18	5	1	0
19	5	1	0
20	4	1	2
21	4	1	14
22	2	0	7
23	3	1	0
24	5	1	0
25	3	0	0
26	2	0	0
27	4	1	0
...
23480	5	1	0
23481	5	1	0
23482	3	1	0
23483	3	0	1
23484	3	1	2
23485	5	1	22

```

Unnamed: 0  Clothing ID  Age  ...  Division Name  Department Name  Class Name
0           0           767  33  ...  Intimates      Intimate  Intimates
1           1           1080  34  ...  General        Dresses  Dresses
2           2           1077  60  ...  General        Dresses  Dresses
3           3           1049  50  ...  General Petite  Bottoms  Pants
4           4           847   47  ...  General        Tops    Blouses
    
```

Fig. 3. Sample of the dataset.

Fig. 4. Sample and statistical analysis of the dataset.

III. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This study used Python v.3.6 and the Scikit learn and Tensor Flow machine and deep learning libraries as backends to Keras [30-31]. Training and prediction were both developed with the help of the NVIDIA CUDA parallel computing platform and API. In addition, the root mean square prediction error was calculated to compare the various outcomes of the proposed BLSTM model, as it provides an all-encompassing perspective of the error distribution. The dataset was

partitioned into two subsets, namely 70% for training and 30% for testing. The model was trained for a total of 32 iterations to prevent overfitting. The model run with various numbers of epochs that ultimately resulted in a 91% accuracy. This shows that the factors used to predict e-commerce sales have a strong prediction performance. Figures 5 and 6 show the model's accuracy and loss, respectively.

Fig. 5. Model accuracy as a function of epoch number.

Fig. 6. Model loss as a function of epoch number.

IV. CONCLUSION

Machine learning methods are increasingly used in many industries, including speech recognition, vehicles, clustering, and data classification, as well as the identification of anomalies affecting everyday life. Deep learning has made significant strides in e-commerce, specifically in forecasts and sale marketing, using sentiment analysis to increase customer satisfaction. This study used CNNs to pick features from a publicly available online retail sales dataset and the Bidirectional Long Short Term memory model of RNNs (BLSMT-RNN) to predict future sales. The results revealed that the proposed model had a 91% accuracy, showing a strong prediction performance. Future work will investigate the effectiveness of the various iterations of RNNs.

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Analysis of Ionospheric Scintillations using GPS and NavIC Combined Constellation

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ABSTRACT

The disturbances and irregularities in the ionosphere are the primarily recognized ramifications of space weather called scintillations. Irregularities in the electron densities are the source of the ionospheric scintillations. This article investigates the ionospheric scintillations, which are predominant in the trans-equatorial and equatorial regions. Based on the data from a multi-constellation Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) receiver at the Chaitanya Bharathi Institute of Technology Hyderabad, the relationship between the amplitude scintillation index S_4 and the rate of change of total electron content (ROTI) is examined. The correlation coefficient between S_4 and ROTI is demonstrated in this article. The outcome validates the usefulness of the ROTI in identifying the scintillations.

Keywords-ionospheric scintillations; rate of change of total electron content; amplitude scintillation index; Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)

I. INTRODUCTION

The advancement of the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), which encompasses GLONASS, GPS, BeiDO, Galileo, and numerous regional navigation systems, directed advanced steps in the earth's atmosphere research [1]. The space-based investigation of the GNSS signals is one of best enforced ways to investigate the ionosphere [2]. The space weather trans-ionospheric signals can undergo expeditious variations and disturbances both in amplitude and phase when they pass through indiscriminate electron density irregularities which are present in the ionosphere [3-4]. This anomaly is generally referred to as ionospheric scintillations. The temporal and spatial status of the ionospheric scintillations depends on geographical and geophysical locations, the time of the day, and season [5-6]. The ionospheric scintillations are the major sources of degradation of the VHF band and C band signals, immensely effecting navigation and communication systems [7]. Hence, it is vital to investigate and analyze them. The GNSS signals are considered a robust tool to investigate the Total Electron Content (TEC) and the existence of ionospheric scintillations [8]. Phase and amplitude scintillations are both ionosphere irregularities.

II. GNSS DATA COLLECTION

For this analysis, the data of the multi constellation GNSS receiver of Chaitanya Bharati Institute of Technology, which is located in Hyderabad, during the period from 2020-06-07 to

2020-06-13 were taken into account. The considered parameters are time, PRN (Pseudo Random Number) of the satellite, carrier to noise values of the received signal, and the ionospheric delay of the received signal. To reduce complexity, only the results of 2020-06-07 are shown in this paper.

III. METHODOLOGY

The ionospheric irregularities and scintillations can be investigated in two ways when using GNSS signals. The first of these methods uses carrier to noise (C/N_0) ratio to calculate the amplitude scintillation index S_4 [9] and the second one uses ionospheric delay to calculate the rate of change of TEC index (ROTI) which is the replacement index of S_4 [10]. The current work is based on the multi-step interpretation and processing of the L_1 (1575.42MHz), L_5 (1176.45MHz), and S_1 (2492.028MHz) GNSS signals corresponding to GPS and NavIC satellite constellations.

In the first method, the amplitude scintillation index S_4 is calculated as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean value of the averaged C/N_0 [9]. The effectiveness of the amplitude scintillations index is divided into 3 categories which are weak scintillations when S_4 is less than 0.3, moderate scintillations when S_4 ranges between 0.3 and 0.6, and strong scintillations when S_4 is above 0.6 [11]. The amplitude scintillations are calculated as follows:

$$S_4 = \sqrt{\frac{\langle SI^2 \rangle - \langle SI \rangle^2}{\langle SI \rangle^2}} \quad (1)$$

where SI is the intensity of the received trans-ionospheric signal. The S_4 value is computed using the signals received on the L_1 (1575.42MHz), L_5 (1176.45MHz) and S_1 (2492.028MHz) frequencies for a week-long data from 2020-06-07 to 2020-06-13.

The second method is to calculate the ROTI using the delay due to ionosphere in the received signals [12]. The ionospheric delay is computed by:

$$ID_{ion} = \frac{40.3}{f^2} * TEC \quad (2)$$

where TEC indicates the Total Electron Content on the frequency of the received trans-ionospheric signal and ID_{ion} is the ionospheric delay of the received signal. TEC is used to describe all the electrons that are present along the path from the satellite to the receiver [12-13]. The TEC is expressed below and is measured in TECU:

$$1 \text{ TECU} = 10^{16} \text{ e/m}^2 \quad (3)$$

$$TEC = \frac{ID_{ion} * f^2}{40.3} \quad (4)$$

The rate of change of TEC (ROT) is calculated at regular intervals by (5):

$$ROT = \frac{TEC_b^a - TEC_{b-1}^a}{t_b - t_{b-1}} \quad (5)$$

where b specifies the epoch time and a specifies the noticeable satellite.

ROTI is calculated by the standard deviation of ROT:

$$ROTI = \sqrt{\langle ROT^2 \rangle - \langle ROT \rangle^2} \quad (6)$$

The effectiveness of ROTI is divided into three categories: It is fragile when the ROTI index ranges between 0.25 and 0.5, modest when the ROTI index ranges between 0.5 and 1, and vigorous when the ROTI index is above 1 [14-15]. ROTI was calculated for signals received on L_1 , L_5 , and S_1 frequencies for a weak long data from 2020-06-07 to 2020-06-13. To observe the correlation between ROTI and S_4 , the covariance and standard deviation of S_4 and ROTI are computed [16] by:

$$\sigma_{S_4} = \sqrt{\langle S_4^2 \rangle - \langle S_4 \rangle^2} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_{ROTI} = \sqrt{\langle ROTI^2 \rangle - \langle ROTI \rangle^2} \quad (8)$$

The covariance of S_4 and ROTI is:

$$C_{1ROTI S_4} = \sum_0^N \frac{(S_4 - \bar{S}_4)(ROTI - \overline{ROTI})}{N} \quad (9)$$

where \bar{S}_4 is the mean of S_4 and \overline{ROTI} is the mean of ROTI.

The correlation coefficient is a measure of the correlation between ROTI and S_4 methods which is expressed by $\rho_{1ROTI S_4}$, and it is given as:

$$\rho_{1ROTI S_4} = \frac{C_{1ROTI S_4}}{\sigma_{1ROTI} \sigma_{1S_4}} \quad (10)$$

where $C_{1ROTI S_4}$ specifies the covariance of S_4 and ROTI.

The flowchart of the followed methodology is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the methodology.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pseudo range measurements data of multi-constellation GNSS receiver, which were sampled every 1s, are considered for computation and analysis of amplitude scintillations, ROT, and ROTI. Figure 2 specifies S_4 for all the available satellites on 2020-06-07 for the L_1 frequency. The highest scintillations are observed from the satellite PRN 9. Therefore, the values of S_4 and ROTI are compared to the PRN 9 values.

Fig. 2. S_4 index on 2020-06-07 for the L_1 frequency.

Figure 3 shows the comparison plot for S_4 and ROTI for the PRN-9, which exhibits maximum scintillations.

Figure 4 shows the correlation between ROTI and S_4 . The x axis specifies the epoch time for every hour and the y axis the correlation coefficient between S_4 and ROTI. The highest correlation coefficient is 1 and the minimum is higher than the cutoff level. As a result, the correlation coefficient is robust due to the persistent link between ROTI and S_4 . Figure 5 depicts the comparison of S_4 for all the available NavIC satellites on 2020-06-07 for the L_5 frequency. The maximum observed S_4 index is 0.0205 for IR-02, which is an indication of no scintillations on 2020-06-07 for the L_5 frequency. The highest S_4 values are observed in the IR-02 satellite. Therefore, the values of S_4 and ROTI are compared to the IR-02 values.

Fig. 3. Comparison of S_4 and ROTI on 2020-06-07 for PRN-9 (L_1 frequency).

Fig. 4. Correlation of S_4 and ROTI on 2020-06-07 for PRN-9 (L_1 frequency).

Fig. 5. S_4 amplitude variations on 2020-06-07 for L_5 frequency.

these, it can be concluded that no scintillations are observed on the L_5 frequency for IR-02. Figure 7 shows the correlation between S_4 and ROTI. The maximum correlation of 1 is observed many times, which is an indicative of the similarity between S_4 and ROTI.

Figure 8 shows the S_4 variations of all visible NavIC satellites on 2020-06-07 for the S_1 frequency. The maximum observed S_4 index is 0.0294 for IR-02, which is an indication of no scintillations there on 2020-06-07 for the S_1 frequency. The highest S_4 values are observed in the IR-02 satellite. Therefore, all S_4 and ROTI values are compared with the ones of the IR-02 satellite.

Fig. 7. Correlation of S_4 and ROTI on 2020-06-07 for IR-02 (L_5 frequency).

Fig. 8. S_4 amplitude variations on 2020-06-07 for S_1 frequency.

Fig. 6. Comparison of S_4 and ROTI on 2020-06-07 for IR-02 (L_5 frequency).

In Figure 6, the maximum S_4 index value of 0.0078 and the maximum ROTI index value of 0.1911 are observed. From

Fig. 9. Comparison of S_4 and ROTI on 2020-06-07 for IR-02 (S_1 frequency).

Figure 9 shows that the maximum S_4 index value is 0.0078 and the maximum ROTI index value is 0.1911. From this it can

be concluded that no scintillations are observed on the S_1 frequency for IR-02. Figure 10 shows the correlation between S_4 and ROTI for NavIC satellite IR-02 on 2020-06-07 on the S_1 frequency. Maximum correlation is observed many times, which indicates that ROTI can be considered as an alternative metric for the S_4 index. Figure 11 shows the skyplot of all the visible GPS and NavIC satellites at 15:00hrs of 2020-06-07 for the IGS (International GNSS Service) station which is located at Hyderabad (Lat/Long:17.417°N/78.551°E).

Fig. 10. Correlation of S_4 and ROTI on 2020-06-07 for IR-02 (S_1 frequency).

Fig. 11. Sky plot of visible satellites at 15:00 hrs on 2020-06-07.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this article, the analysis of GNSS trans-ionospheric signals for a typical day (2020-06-07) is presented. In order to identify the ionospheric perturbations, the amplitude of the scintillations S_4 , the rate of the change of total electron content (ROT), and its index (ROTI) are computed on L_1 , L_5 , and S_1 frequencies using GPS and NavIC combined constellation. Based on the correlation coefficient, maximum similarity between the S_4 and ROTI is observed, and, thus, ROTI can be considered as an alternative index for the investigation of the amplitude scintillations. It is also observed that the ionospheric scintillations are robust only on L_1 frequency of the GNSS trans-ionospheric signals and no ionospheric scintillations are observed on the L_5 and S_1 frequencies. As the L_5 and S_1 are the frequencies for NavIC constellation, it is concluded that the ionospheric scintillation effects are minimum on the NavIC signal. Hence, it is concluded that the ionosphere scintillation

effects can be minimized with higher frequencies, like L_5 and S_1 .

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Fraud Prediction in Movie Theater Credit Card Transactions using Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

This paper highlights how the proliferation of online transactions, especially those involving the use of credit cards, has resulted in the emergence of new security flaws that pose threats to customers and enterprises worldwide. E-commerce and other forms of online monetary transactions have become essential in the manufacturing and service sectors, propelling the global economy. The widespread and dependent connectivity of mobile payment systems using credit card transactions presents chances for fraud, risk, and security breaches. In light of the importance of accurately predicting fraud incidents through payment procedures, this study investigated the credit card payment methods used for movie tickets, using the machine learning logistic regression method to analyze and predict such incidents. This study used a dataset from cinema ticket credit card transactions made in two days of September 2013 by European cardholders, including 284,807 transactions out of which 492 were fraudulent purchases. The results of the proposed method showed a prediction accuracy of 99%, proving its high prediction performance.

Keywords-fraud prediction; movie theater; credit card; machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Credit card frauds have a negative impact not just on customers, but also on businesses [1]. Along with the rise in the popularity of credit card use and online transactions, there is also an increase in fraudulent activity. Therefore, it is vital to detect fraudulent use of credit cards to prevent monetary losses and preserve the personal and financial data of consumers [2]. Identifying fraudulent activity on credit cards can be accomplished using several methods from various angles. Rule-based systems or machine learning algorithms can examine patterns of normal behavior and identify deviations from the norm [3]. Trust is another issue that needs to be addressed in terms of credit card concerns [4]. Payment systems are the engine that drives e-commerce business, and a substantial amount of trust and security in cutting-edge technology is necessary [5]. Furthermore, it is not unusual for mobile users to switch to new solutions, adjust their payment routines, and encounter other types of security challenges [6-7].

This study used a machine learning model to predict fraudulent activity in credit card payment transactions. Today, electronic payment methods are increasingly growing and are increasingly vital and convenient [8-9]. Several studies have shown that phone-based payments are a crucial and necessary addition to the available payment retail [10]. Electronic payment systems are particularly vulnerable to fraud and cyber security breaches since they store sensitive consumer

information such as ID, card number, card name, purchase history, and more [11]. Because of all these interconnected factors, it is essential to examine the problem of credit card fraud from a variety of perspectives to determine how it can be resolved. This study also considered other dimensions associated with electronic payment operations to detect unusual or suspicious behaviors, taking into account additional facets related to electronic payment operations, such as the geographic location of transactions. For instance, if a credit card is used unexpectedly multiple times in a short period, this could be indicative of fraudulent activity [12-13]. Another aspect lies in the analysis of user behavior to identify any unique patterns that may emerge. When a user suddenly starts making large transactions or uses his card at irregular times, this may be an indication of fraudulent activity [14]. Machine learning is one of the most important fields in this sector and currently depends on algorithms that can boost an organization's productivity and performance. There are four distinct methodologies of machine learning: supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and reinforced learning [15-18].

This study used Logistic Regression (LR) as a classification algorithm to assign the data to a discrete set of classes. LR resembles the Linear Regression model, however, it uses a more complex cost function called Sigmoid function or logistic function rather than a linear one [19]. LR is a method for making predictions and its outcomes are converted into

probability values. To limit the cost function to values between 0 and 1, an LR hypothesis must be taken into account. As a result, linear functions are unable to adequately describe this because they can have a value that is either more than 1 or less than 0, both of which are prohibited by the LR hypothesis [19]. When using a classification strategy, LR is applied to the observations of the discrete classes involved, operating on the principle of probability and employing the predictive analysis on the provided scenarios. To accurately estimate the necessary probabilities, the sigmoid function converts any real values between 0 and 1 by:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-(x)}} \quad (1)$$

To validate the hypothesis and ensure its consistency with the expected assumption, the value of the hypothesis must fall somewhere between 0 and 1 by:

$$h\theta(X) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-(\beta_0+\beta_1X)}} \quad (2)$$

When the prediction function is applied to the classifier, the classifier will provide values based on a set of outputs on probability. This establishes the decision boundaries with a selected threshold value. The accuracy of the optimized model is represented by the cost function after it has been optimized to provide the least amount of inaccuracy:

$$f\theta \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^m (h_{\theta})(x^{(i)}) - (y^{(i)})^2 \quad (3)$$

Gradient descent is used to reduce the cost values using:

$$\theta_j := \theta_j - \alpha \sum_{i=1}^m (h_{\theta})(x^{(i)}) - (y^{(i)})x_j \quad (4)$$

Several previous studies used LR for detection and prediction. The need to apply security in e-commerce in a highly effective way creates the concepts of asset protection, security prediction, and vulnerability detection to save end users and resources that can be exploited. LR was a vital component in the development of deep and machine-learning models on the Google Cloud Platform [20]. Similarly, LR was used to forecast student performance in community colleges [21]. In [22], a road crash zone was modeled using LR to determine the nature of the accidents and the types of people that were involved. In a similar vein, a privacy-protecting LR-based diagnosis method for digital healthcare was presented in [23]. The effectiveness of machine-learning RL for tomography processing was shown in [24]. In [25], LR and a survival model were used in Russian exports. In [26], an intelligent categorization of coal structure was presented, using multinomial LR. In [27], LR was effectively used in nursing. In [28], a prediction model for clinical applications was developed using LR, showing its feasibility. In [29], an SK-Tree method to detect malicious events on a portion of a publicly available dataset achieved an AUROC score of 98%. In [19], several machine learning algorithms were investigated to detect and analyze frauds in online transactions with a European credit card dataset, proposing a novel fraud detection method to stream transaction data by analyzing the old transaction details of customers and extracting behavioral patterns. The study in [30] focused on fraud events in real-world transactions, using and evaluating a series of machine learning algorithms, such as Vector Machine, Naive Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbor, and LR. In

[31], a credit card fraud detection system was presented using machine learning algorithms that included the modeling of the dataset. The past credit card transactions were modeled with data considered as fraud, and this model was used to define if a new transaction is fraud. This study showed that fraud detection is a classification problem and focused on preprocessing and analyzing datasets using different anomaly detection algorithms, such as local outlier factor and isolation forest, on a Principal Component Analysis (PCA)-transformed credit card transaction dataset. PCA reduced the feature dimensionality [32] and kept the most effective features to improve the prediction process [33].

The above-mentioned studies in the e-commerce security domain used different machine learning algorithms to examine which fit best to their datasets and provide the best accuracy scores. In other words, these studies show the importance of carefully choosing machine learning algorithms that are compatible with the underlying dataset and have the best accuracy performance.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study focused on applying machine-learning algorithms to predict credit card fraud transactions in movie theaters. Figure 1 shows the flow chart of the proposed method.

Fig. 1. The flow diagram of the proposed method.

LR was used to make the predictions, leading to successful results. These two approaches were combined into one. As a consequence, the procedure started with the construction of the model, followed by the collection and preprocessing of the dataset. Then, the model was trained and tested for its

prediction accuracy. The most important phase of this method was the generation and mapping of credit card fraud incidents in movie theater transactions. The study began by isolating movie theater credit card transactions, from all the credit card transactions contained in the dataset. In the end, only the dataset for credit card payments of movie tickets was selected for the best-fit test, which was followed by the import and cleaning of the data, their division into training and test sets, and finally using the machine-learning LR algorithm to determine the best-fit for making predictions.

The necessary data were collected from Kaggle [34], as shown in Table I, which contains a total of 284,807 transactions and 492 fraudulent transactions that took place in

two days in September 2013 by European cardholders. The dataset has a huge imbalance, as the positive class (frauds) accounts for only 0.172% of all transactions. The features of the dataset were represented by a number value (V1-V28). The PCA method was used, and "Time" and "Amount" were the only unchanged features. The "Time" feature saves the number of seconds that elapsed between the first and each subsequent transaction, for each subsequent transaction in the dataset. The "Class" feature is the response variable, assigned the value of 1 in the event of fraud and 0 in all other cases, whereas "Amount" denotes the total amount of the transaction. This study selected only transactions that involved purchasing a ticket and additional services for a cinema. The data include not just numerical values, but also a description and a "Label".

TABLE I. THE SAMPLE DATASET GENERATED FROM THE CREDIT FRAUD INVESTIGATION

Time	V1	V2	V3	...	V27	V28	Amount	Class
0	-1.35981	-0.07278	2.536347	...	0.133558	-0.02105	149.62	0
0	1.191857	0.266151	0.16648	...	-0.00898	0.014724	2.69	0
1	-1.35835	-1.34016	1.773209	...	-0.05535	-0.05975	378.66	0
1	-0.96627	-0.18523	1.792993	...	0.062723	0.061458	123.5	0
2	-1.15823	0.877737	1.548718	...	0.219422	0.215153	69.99	0
2	-0.42597	0.960523	1.141109	...	0.253844	0.08108	3.67	0
4	1.229658	0.141004	0.045371	...	0.034507	0.005168	4.99	0
7	-0.64427	1.417964	1.07438	...	-1.20692	-1.08534	40.8	0
7	-0.89429	0.286157	-0.11319	...	0.011747	0.142404	93.2	0
9	-0.33826	1.119593	1.044367	...	0.246219	0.083076	3.68	0
10	1.449044	-1.17634	0.91386	...	0.04285	0.016253	7.8	0
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	...	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
172782	0.219529	0.881246	-0.63589	...	0.131507	0.081265	5.49	0
172783	-1.77513	-0.00424	1.189786	...	0.181205	0.215243	24.05	0
172784	2.03956	-0.17523	-1.19683	...	0.454379	0.130308	79.99	0
172785	0.120316	0.931005	-0.54601	...	-0.08083	-0.07507	2.68	0
172786	-11.8811	10.07178	-9.83478	...	0.21794	0.068803	2.69	0
172787	-0.73279	-0.05508	2.03503	...	0.943651	0.823731	0.77	0
172788	1.919565	-0.30125	-3.24964	...	0.068472	-0.05353	24.79	0
172788	-0.24044	0.530483	0.70251	...	0.004455	-0.02656	67.88	0
172792	-0.53341	-0.18973	0.703337	...	0.108821	0.104533	10	0

III. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF THE RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the particular processes to import the dataset and initialize the fraud variable.

```
In [50]: from sklearn import linear_model
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
X= data.loc[:,1:]
Y= data['Class']

In [55]: X_train, X_test, Y_train, Y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size =0.35 )
clf= linear_model.LogisticRegression(C=1e5)
clf.fit(X_train, Y_train)

/opt/anaconda3/lib/python3.8/site-packages/sklearn/linear_model/_logistic.py:762: ConvergenceWarning: lbfgs failed to converge (status=1):
STOP: TOTAL NO. OF ITERATIONS REACHED LIMIT.

Increase the number of iterations (max_iter) or scale the data as shown in:
https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/preprocessing.html
Please also refer to the documentation for alternative solver options:
https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/linear_model.html#logistic-regression
n_iter_1 = _check_optimize_result(

Out[55]: LogisticRegression(C=100000.0)
```

Fig. 2. Experimental import and initialization of the fraud variable.

Python, Pandas, and Scikit-learn were used to develop the proposed method. In the first stage, the dataset was loaded using Pandas, and the value of the fraud variable was initialized to 0 or 1, based on the dataset. In the second step, the test sample was defined, and the algorithm was applied using Scikit-learn, as shown in Figure 3. In the third phase, LR was

used to perform the classification, and then the accuracy of the model was assessed, as shown in Figure 4. The variable X is independent and denotes the credit card transactions, while the variable Y is dependent and denotes the class of the transaction or the fraud flag. Figure 4 shows the results of the proposed method, indicating an accuracy of 0.9988.

```
In [44]: import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
import numpy as np
data = pd.read_csv("creditcard.csv")
data.head()

Out[44]:
   Time  V1  V2  V3  V4  V5  V6  V7  V8  V9  ...  V21  V22  V23  V24
0  0.0 -1.359807 -0.072781 2.536347 1.378155 -0.338321 0.462388 0.239559 0.098988 0.363787 ... -0.018307 0.277838 -0.110474 0.066928 0.12
1  1.0 1.191857 0.266151 0.166480 0.448154 0.060018 -0.082261 -0.078903 0.085102 -0.255425 ... -0.225775 -0.638672 0.101288 -0.338948 0.16
2  1.0 -1.358354 -1.340163 1.773209 0.379780 -0.503198 1.800469 0.791461 0.247678 -1.514654 ... 0.247988 0.771679 0.903912 -0.880281 -0.32
3  1.0 -0.966272 -0.185226 1.792993 -0.863291 -0.010309 1.247203 0.237609 0.377436 -1.387024 ... -0.108300 0.005274 -0.190321 -1.175575 0.64
4  2.0 -1.158233 0.877737 1.548718 0.423034 -0.407193 0.095921 0.589341 -0.270333 0.817739 ... -0.009431 0.798278 -0.137458 0.141267 -0.20

5 rows x 31 columns

In [45]: fraud = data.loc[data['Class']==1]
normal = data.loc[data['Class']==0]
len(fraud)

Out[45]: 492
```

Fig. 3. Selecting the SK-learn algorithm, importing the model, and defining the test sample.

```

In [58]: Y_pred = np.array(clf.predict(X_test))
         Y = np.array(y_test)

In [61]: from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, classification_report, accuracy_score

In [62]: print(confusion_matrix(Y_test, Y_pred))
[[99460  63]
 [  52 118]]

In [63]: print(accuracy_score(Y_test, Y_pred))
0.998864065086323

In [65]: print(classification_report(Y_test, Y_pred))
              precision    recall  f1-score   support

   0             1.00         1.00         1.00     99521
   1             0.64         0.68         0.66         162

 accuracy
macro avg   0.82         0.84         0.83     99683
weighted avg 1.00         1.00         1.00     99683

```

Fig. 4. Calling the predict function, applying classification, and checking accuracy.

The accuracy results of this study were compared with similar studies that used LR to detect fraudulent credit card transactions, as shown in Table II. The study in [35] used a credit card transaction dataset from the UCI Machine Learning Data Repository to detect frauds in credit card transactions, while studies [36-38] used the same dataset as this study. All these studies used the LR method to achieve high accuracy and predictive performance, regardless of their individual approaches. This study achieved the best prediction performance result.

TABLE II. COMPARATIVE PREDICTION PERFORMANCE

Study	Algorithm	Accuracy
[35]	Logistic Regression	77.97%
[36]	Logistic Regression	99.26%
[37]	Logistic Regression	91.20%
[38]	Logistic Regression	74.65%
This study	Logistic Regression	99.88%

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that the implementation of a machine learning approach is imperative for the detection and prevention of fraudulent activities within payment operations. This study proposed the use of a logistic regression model to investigate fraudulent credit card transactions, using a machine learning approach to analyze various credit card payment methods for purchasing movie tickets. The raw data were divided into training and testing samples. The use of historical data to accurately predict future outcomes is a significant impetus for the extensive implementation of machine learning in various sectors. This study showcased the impact of the widespread adoption of digital financial transactions, particularly those involving credit cards, on the emergence of novel security risks that pose a threat to businesses and customers worldwide. The emergence of e-commerce and other electronic forms of monetary transactions has a crucial role in the production and service sectors, thereby promoting the advancement of the worldwide economy. The study was initiated based on the acknowledgment that, despite their widespread use, mobile credit card payment systems present opportunities for fraudulent activities, potential hazards, and security violations across all industries due to their ubiquitous and interdependent connectivity.

This study investigated credit card transactions related to cinema ticket purchases to detect potentially fraudulent activities. The application of logistic regression machine learning provided an accurate prediction. The dataset used in this study contained credit card transactions made by European cardholders during September 2013 [38]. The purchase of cinema tickets was segregated and analyzed autonomously from the remaining transactions. The dataset contained 284,807 transactions, where 492 were identified as fraudulent. The data were analyzed using logistic regression, and the findings showed a predictive accuracy of 99.88%, indicating an exceedingly prognostic performance.

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Predicting the Equilibrium Product Formation in Oxy-fuel Combustion of Octane (C_8H_{18}) using Numerical Modeling

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ABSTRACT

Preserving the environment is a major challenge for modern society, and reducing the greenhouse effect caused by combustion processes is a primary concern. It is known that nitrogen compounds (NO_x) negatively impact air quality and public health. Internal combustion engines, responsible for nearly half of the atmosphere's pollutants, have prompted public policymakers to phase out gasoline and diesel-powered vehicles in the near future. Carbon capture and storage technologies, including oxy-fuel combustion, are being developed to address these environmental challenges. To predict exhaust pollutants such as NO and CO , assuming that the exhaust gases resulting from fuel and air combustion are in chemical equilibrium is a useful approximation. In the current case study, a numerical investigation on the impact of modifying the oxygen content of the reaction mixture from 21% to 100% on the equilibrium composition of C_8H_{18} air-enriched combustion was conducted. Specifically, the equilibrium-constant approach routines were tailored for 10 species reported in the literature to the conditions of oxy-fuel combustion. Additionally, a comprehensive analysis was performed by varying the temperature and equivalence ratio alongside the oxygen level. The results emphasize the intricate interplay between various factors in oxy-combustion and provide valuable insight into the equilibrium product formation in oxy-fuel combustion. Notably, the non-uniform reduction of N_2 as a function of O_2 is highlighted, with an overall reduction rate of 0.93 observed across the range of O_2 percentages from 21% to 99%.

Keywords- air pollution; carbon capture and storage; nitrogen compounds; air-enriched combustion

I. INTRODUCTION

The reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, particularly carbon dioxide (CO_2) from combustion processes, is a crucial challenge in addressing environmental concerns [1-2]. According to [3], it is anticipated that by approximately 2050, CO_2 emissions will raise by approximately 70% in comparison to the levels observed in the mid-2010s. Although CO_2 is a major contributor to global warming, nitrogen compounds are also a significant environmental concern due to their negative impact on air quality and public health. NO (nitric oxide) is a toxic gas that is formed at high temperatures during combustion processes, particularly in internal combustion engines. NO can cause respiratory problems, particularly in those with pre-existing respiratory conditions [5, 6].

Internal combustion engines, which power most motor vehicles, are responsible for generating nearly half of the atmosphere's NO_x , CO (carbon monoxide), and hydrocarbon pollutants [7]. According to studies carried out in 2011, vehicles powered by internal combustion engines are responsible for 90% of the air pollution in Sao Paulo, Brazil [8]. Meanwhile, internal combustion engines have contributed during the last 20 years between 4 and 40% of world pollution [9]. Thus, in view of the environmental challenges posed by the use of diesel and gasoline-powered vehicles, public policies are being formulated to phase out the sale and circulation of such vehicles in the near future. France and the United Kingdom announced the end of the sales of cars powered by these engines by 2040. This example is followed

by other European countries, such as Germany, and in emerging countries, such as China and India [10].

Numerous research centers and industries are currently directing their attention towards the development of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies. Some of these technologies include pre-combustion capture, post-combustion capture, and oxy-fuel combustion [3, 11]. Oxy-fuel combustion is the process of combusting hydrocarbon fuel in a nearly pure oxygen environment, as opposed to air. Due to the absence of nitrogen in the intake charge, NO_x emissions will be eliminated. As a result, CO_2 and water vapors are the only combustion products [12].

To assume that the exhaust gases resulting from fuel and air combustion are in chemical equilibrium is a useful approximation. This equilibrium scheme serves as the foundation for predicting the quantities of exhaust pollutants, such as NO and CO , in a kinetically controlled manner [13]. The process of combustion in which a fuel is entirely consumed in the presence of stoichiometric air is referred to as theoretical (or stoichiometric) combustion. This theoretical scenario represents an optimal state in which the ideal balance between oxygen and fuel generates the most heat possible, and maximum combustion efficiency is achieved. There are no unburned combustibles and no excess air [14]. In this case, for $\text{C}_\alpha\text{H}_\beta$ type fuel, N_2 , CO_2 , and H_2O are the only reaction products. Despite the presence of ample oxygen to completely oxidize all fuel, this approach may not yield precise results due to the dissociation of combustion products that occur at high temperatures [10, 15]. The product composition resulting from fuel-air combustion depends on stoichiometry. For example, if the reactants are fuel-rich, there is not enough oxygen to react completely with the fuel, resulting in the formation of additional products such as CO and H_2 , and if the mixture is fuel-lean, there is not enough fuel to consume the oxygen, so there will be unburned oxygen in the product mixture [16]. The equilibrium composition of octane (C_8H_{18})-air mixtures for different temperatures at $\phi = 0.8, 1.0,$ and 1.2 is presented in [16], with the assumption that the air is composed of 21% oxygen and 79% nitrogen by volume, which means a molar ratio of 1:3.76 between O_2 and N_2 . At low temperatures, for the rich case, the major product species present are $\text{N}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{CO}_2, \text{CO}$ and H_2 whereas for the lean case $\text{N}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{CO}_2,$ and O_2 . But at higher temperatures (greater than 2200K), these major species dissociate and react to form additional species in significant amounts [9, 10, 15]. To propose a numerical model that accurately predicts the equilibrium products present in a combustion chamber, a chemical equilibrium scheme that accounts for a specific number of species must be utilized [9, 10]. Thus, in this case study, we consider the equilibrium combustion model with 10 species, applied for equivalence ratio $\phi < 3$, as suggested in [16]. The equilibrium compositions are determined by adapting the equilibrium-constant approach routines of [13], as presented in [16], to the specific conditions of oxy-fuel combustion. The aim of the present study is to numerically investigate the effect of altering the oxygen content in the reaction mixture from 21% to 100% on the equilibrium composition of C_8H_{18} combustion.

II. METHODOLOGY

We modify the chemical reaction from the 10 species model [16] to allow changes in the oxygen and nitrogen percentage to simulate oxy-fuel combustion. Let us consider the following reaction:

where x ($0.21 < x < 1.0$) is the oxygen percentage.

The atomic balance yield is described by four equations:

$$\text{C: } \epsilon\phi\alpha = (y_1 + y_5)M \quad (2)$$

$$\text{H: } \epsilon\phi\beta = (2y_2 + 2y_6 + y_7 + y_9)M \quad (3)$$

$$\text{O: } \epsilon\phi\gamma + 2x = (2y_1 + y_2 + 2y_4 + y_5 + y_8 + y_9 + y_{10})M \quad (4)$$

$$\text{N: } \epsilon\phi\delta + 2(1-x) = (2y_3 + y_{10})M \quad (5)$$

where M is the total number of moles. The sum of mole fractions results in:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{10} y_i - 1 = 0 \quad (6)$$

This equation introduces the six equilibrium constants that will give 11 equations for the 10 unknown mole fractions (y_i) and the number of moles (M). The reactions are:

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{H} \quad K_1 = \frac{y_7 p^{1/2}}{y_6^{1/2}} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{O} \quad K_2 = \frac{y_8 p^{1/2}}{y_4^{1/2}} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2 + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{OH} \quad K_3 = \frac{y_9}{y_4^{1/2} y_6^{1/2}} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 + \frac{1}{2}\text{N}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{NO} \quad K_4 = \frac{y_{10}}{y_4^{1/2} y_3^{1/2}} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{O} \quad K_5 = \frac{y_2}{y_4^{1/2} y_6 p^{1/2}} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 + \text{CO} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO}_2 \quad K_6 = \frac{y_1}{y_5 y_4^{1/2} p^{1/2}} \quad (12)$$

The equilibrium constants $K_i(T)$ are fitted as:

$$\log K_p = \text{A} \ln \left(\frac{T}{1000} \right) + \frac{B}{T} + C + DT + ET^2 \quad (13)$$

where T is the temperature, $600 < T < 4000\text{K}$ [13].

The equilibrium constant expressions can be rearranged to express the mole fractions of the 10 species, all in terms of y_3, y_4, y_5 and y_6 , i.e., molar fractions of $\text{N}_2, \text{O}_2, \text{CO}$ and H_2 , respectively.

$$y_7 = c_1 y_6^{1/2}, c_1 = \frac{K_1}{p^{1/2}} \quad (14)$$

$$y_8 = c_2 y_4^{1/2}, c_2 = \frac{K_2}{p^{1/2}} \quad (15)$$

$$y_9 = c_3 y_4^{1/2} y_6^{1/2}, c_3 = K_3 \quad (16)$$

$$y_{10} = c_4 y_4^{1/2} y_3^{1/2}, c_4 = K_4 \quad (17)$$

$$y_2 = c_5 y_4^{1/2} y_6, c_5 = K_5 p^{1/2} \quad (18)$$

$$y_1 = c_6 y_4^{1/2} y_5, c_6 = K_6 P^{1/2} \quad (19)$$

By establishing connections between the derived equations and eliminating shared terms, 4 equations can be derived, each with 4 unknowns y_3, y_4, y_5 and y_6 , i.e.:

$$f(y_3, y_4, y_5, y_6) = 0 \quad (20)$$

Equation (20) constitutes a nonlinear equation system that necessitates an iterative solution via a numerical approach. In this study, we employed the Newton-Raphson method, and initialized the iterative process with mole fractions derived from a low-temperature combustion model featuring 6 species. We developed a MATLAB code based on the computational routines of [13], as presented in [16], adapted to the specific conditions of oxy-fuel combustion. A more comprehensive account of the methodology can be found in [16, 17].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We compared the equilibrium composition of octane (C_8H_{18})-air mixtures for 21% O_2 and 79% N_2 to the reaction products when using the parameters in Table I.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS USED IN NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Fuel	% Oxygen	Temperature	Fuel-air equivalence ratio	Pressure
Octane (C_8H_{18})	21, 50, 65, 80, 95 and 99	1500K - 3150K	0.8, 1.0, and 1.2	50 bar

Figures 1-3 illustrate the composition shifts with temperature and equivalence ratio for the combustion of C_8H_{18} considering the parameters presented in Table I. In Figure 1, C_8H_{18} -air mixture (21% oxygen and 79% nitrogen by volume) is assumed and the results are very similar to those found in [13, p. 87]. At low temperatures, for the stoichiometric ($\phi = 1$) case, the major products species present are N_2, H_2O , and CO_2 (Table II). For lean ($\phi = 0.8$) and rich ($\phi = 1.2$) cases, although N_2, H_2O and CO_2 are still the main product species, other species arise. For the lean case, a significant amount of O_2 is present, whereas for the rich case there are CO and H_2 . When the temperature of the reaction rises, the predominant species dissociate and react resulting in relevant additional species. Notice that in this case there is an exponential rise in product species such as CO, NO, OH, O_2, O, H_2 , and H . For lean conditions, the O_2 fraction remains relatively unaffected by the changes in temperature. For rich conditions, the H_2 fraction initially decreases, but subsequently rises with increasing temperature. The product species CO and H_2 generally increase with equivalence ratio, while the O_2, NO, OH , and O mole fractions decrease. It is important to notice that, at high temperatures, a considerable amount of NO is produced, which is significant even in relatively low concentration because it is an air pollutant. Figures 2-3 clearly show that N_2 mole fraction decreases for all equivalence ratios and temperatures while H_2O and CO_2 rise as the oxygen percentage increases. In general, the whole of the analysis done for the case with 21% O_2 still stands because the curves have analogous behavior. At lower temperatures, significant amounts of oxygen can still be observed in the lean case, while the rich case shows high levels of CO and H_2 . As the

temperature increases, the levels of other species continue to rise exponentially.

TABLE II. PERCENTAGE OF THE SUM $N_2+H_2O+CO_2$ FOR $\phi = 1.0$

Temperature	% Oxygen					
	21	50	65	80	95	99
2000 K	99.52	99.23	99.12	99.04	98.97	98.96
3150 K	83.54	69.74	64.12	59.23	55.02	54.07

Table II provides insight into the impact of varying the oxygen input on the sum of products N_2, H_2O , and CO_2 at different temperatures for the stoichiometric case ($\phi = 1.0$). It is noteworthy that for a temperature of 2000K, the sum of products is relatively insensitive to changes in oxygen input. However, at a higher temperature of 3150K, although N_2 still tends to zero, there is a significant decrease in the sum of products with increasing oxygen input. Notice that for 99% of oxygen at 2000K the percentage of H_2O and CO_2 are 52.19% and 46.04% (Table III) and at 3150K they are 35.49% and 18.10% (Table IV), respectively. Thus, there is a reduction on CO_2 and H_2O formation with increasing oxygen amount and temperature, which is also observed in air combustion (Figure 1). Overall, the results presented in Tables II-IV underscore the complex interplay of various factors in oxy-combustion, and emphasize the importance of a holistic approach to achieving the desired outcomes in combustion systems.

Fig. 1. Equilibrium composition of C_8H_{18} -air mixtures for different temperatures at $\phi = 0.8, 1.0$ and 1.2 for $0.21O_2 + 0.79N_2$.

Figure 4 shows the ratio between the molar fraction of product species for 80% O_2 (Figure 3) and 21% O_2 (Figure 1) combustion. The Figure provides a visual representation of the changes for all 10 product species when the oxygen percentage is increased. In this representation, all product species with ratios smaller than 1 decrease with an increase in oxygen

concentration. Conversely, those product species with ratios greater than one exhibit an increase with an increase in oxygen concentration.

Fig. 2. Equilibrium composition of C₈H₁₈ combustion for 0.5O₂ for different temperatures at $\phi = 0.8, 1.0, \text{ and } 1.2$.

Fig. 3. Equilibrium composition of C₈H₁₈ combustion for 0.8O₂ for different temperatures at $\phi = 0.8, 1.0, \text{ and } 1.2$.

It should be noticed that the molar fraction of N₂ for 80% O₂ combustion has decreased to around 20% compared to the 21% O₂ combustion. In addition, it is observed that N₂ reduction is almost insensitive to temperature. In the case of

NO, it is observed that it also reduces but for the lean ($\phi = 0.8$) case, 85% of its content remains. Nevertheless, when $\phi = 1.2$, the concentration of NO remains approximately 45% at low temperatures, but it progressively increases at higher temperatures, reaching nearly 60% at 3000K. The amount of CO₂, H₂O, and O₂ at low temperature and $\phi = 0.8$ increased nearly 3.3 times. The amount of CO₂ tends to rise with the temperature for all values of equivalence ratio. CO generally increases with the equivalence ratio and with temperature for $\phi = 0.8$ and $\phi = 1.0$ but tends to decrease for high temperatures and $\phi = 1.2$.

Tables III and IV show the percentages of all products from some variations of the parameters shown in Table I. It is worth noting that for T = 2000K (Table III), the variation of all products is very low between 95-99% oxygen, except for N₂ and NO. Tables V and VI show the reduction rates of N₂ in intervals of input O₂. The reduction of N₂ as a function of O₂ is not constant. From 21%-50% of O₂, for every 1% increase in O₂, there is a reduction of 1.07% of N₂, while between 95%-99% of O₂, for every 1% increase, the reduction of N₂ is 0.74%. Overall, from 21% to 99% of O₂, the rate of reduction of N₂ is 0.93.

Fig. 4. Ratio (0.8O₂ / 0.21O₂) of the product species for different temperatures at $\phi = 0.8, 1.0, \text{ and } 1.2$.

TABLE III. VARIATION OF THE % OF EACH PRODUCT VERSUS % OF OXYGEN INPUT FOR T=2000K AND $\phi = 1$

	% Oxygen					
	21	50	65	80	95	99
N ₂	73.31	42.24	28.26	15.46	3.70	0.73
H ₂ O	13.96	30.30	37.67	44.41	50.62	52.19
CO ₂	12.25	26.68	33.20	39.16	44.65	46.04
CO	2.25E-01	3.66E-01	4.19E-01	4.63E-01	4.99E-01	5.06E-01
O ₂	1.03E-01	1.83E-01	2.16E-01	2.47E-01	2.76E-01	2.85E-01
H ₂	5.66E-02	9.19E-02	1.05E-01	1.16E-01	1.25E-01	1.27E-01
NO	5.48E-02	5.56E-02	4.94E-02	3.90E-02	2.02E-02	9.10E-03

OH	4.26E-02	7.25E-02	8.43E-02	9.45E-02	1.04E-01	1.06E-01
H	1.70E-03	2.20E-03	2.40E-03	2.50E-03	2.60E-03	2.60E-03
O	1.00E-03	1.30E-03	1.40E-03	1.50E-03	1.60E-03	1.60E-03

TABLE IV. VARIATION OF THE % OF EACH PRODUCT VERSUS % OF OXYGEN INPUT FOR T=3150K AND $\phi = 1$

	% Oxygen					
	21	50	65	80	95	99
N ₂	67.39	36.56	23.79	12.61	2.80	0.48
H ₂ O	9.08	20.62	25.70	30.27	34.43	35.49
CO ₂	7.07	12.56	14.63	16.35	17.79	18.10
CO	4.56	11.47	14.70	17.69	20.50	21.26
O ₂	2.73	4.89	5.72	6.44	7.09	7.27
H ₂	2.56	5.12	6.19	7.17	8.14	8.46
NO	1.90	1.98	1.76	1.38	0.69	0.29
OH	1.88	3.02	3.42	3.74	4.00	4.04
H	1.51	1.91	2.03	2.13	2.20	2.21
O	1.32	1.87	2.06	2.21	2.36	2.40

TABLE V. DECAY RATE ANALYSIS, T=2000K, $\phi = 1$

% oxygen (interval)	21-50	50-65	65-80	80-95	95-99	21-99
Decay rate	-1.07	-0.93	-0.85	-0.78	-0.74	-0.93

TABLE VI. DECAY RATE ANALYSIS, T=3150K, $\phi = 1$

% oxygen (interval)	21-50	50-65	65-80	80-95	95-99	21-99
Decay rate	-1.06	-0.85	-0.745	-0.65	-0.58	-0.858

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The study of the oxy-combustion of C₈H₁₈ presented in this paper provides valuable insights into the equilibrium products that can be formed during the combustion of this fuel using a 10-species model. Significantly, we emphasize that the reduction of N₂ is not uniform and varies with the amount of present O₂. The reduction rate of N₂ was observed to be 0.93 overall, covering the range of O₂ percentages between 21% to 99%. The methodology and approach used in this study can also be applied to analyze the products of other types of hydrocarbon fuels (C_aH_bO_cN_d), which is important for predicting the quantities of exhaust pollutants such as NO and CO in a kinetically controlled fashion. Furthermore, the assumption that the burned gases produced by the combustion of fuel and air are in chemical equilibrium is a good approximation for steady-state operating conditions in internal combustion engines. This simplifies the modeling of the combustion process and enables the use of thermodynamic cycle models to estimate engine performance.

Although significant progress has been made in the study of oxy-combustion during the recent years, it remains a rapidly evolving field with several challenges and open questions that require further investigation. These challenges include issues such as flame instability and the cost of operating an oxy-combustion system. In conclusion, while oxy-combustion offers many potential benefits, there are still significant technical and economic challenges that need to be addressed. Further research and development efforts are needed to overcome these challenges and fully realize the potential of oxy-combustion for clean and efficient energy production.

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Robust Nonlinear Predictive Control Applied to Induction Motors

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a nonlinear predictive controller is proposed for a variable-speed induction motor. The research work is directed towards improving the trajectory tracking capability, stability guarantee, robustness to parameter variations, and disturbance rejection. The Generalized Predictive Control (GPC) without constraint and output-constrained controller to induction motor drive is illustrated. The variables to be controlled are rotor speed and flux trajectory. The load torque is considered an unknown disturbance. Finally, the tuning parameter of GPC is automatically determined. The simulation results show a good performance for the nonlinear dynamic system.

Keywords-robust; induction motor; polynomial approach; output constraint; predictive control

I. INTRODUCTION

Generalized Predictive Control (GPC) is among the most popular control techniques, having many ideas in common with Dynamic Matrix Control (DMC) [1] and Model Algorithm Control (MAC) [2]. The control algorithms differ mainly in the plant (and/or noise) models used and the cost function chosen. The GPC exhibits very good performance and robustness provided that the tuning parameters are properly selected. However, the selection of these parameters is not an easy task. First there are no precise guidelines for the selection of these parameters in order to ensure closed loop stability [2, 3], although recent works have proposed modifications of the prototypical structure in order to guarantee stability. GPC algorithms have been proposed under various names by several authors [4-7] and constitute a class of powerful control algorithms that have been widely applied on industrial processes. GPC is a technique with success in industrial applications. Besides its quality, GPC provides unconstrained case linear laws easy to implement in polynomial formulations [3, 4] and can further be reinforced by adding equation constraints for stability. The application to fast processes with constraints has been delayed and the optimal control action is

generally provided by an on-line optimization procedure, generally a time-consuming process.

The classical predictive control approach to drive applications includes several different control strategies. The various control schemes can be divided in a few main groups. The most published schemes so far belong to the families of hysteresis-based or trajectory-based predictive control. On the contrary, GPC belongs to the Model-Based Predictive Control (MBPC) group, which is founded on totally different ideas. The idea of MBPC is to calculate a control function for the future time in order to force the controlled system's response to reach the reference value. Therefore, the future reference values have to be known (which is the case in many industrial applications) and the system behavior must be calculable by an appropriate model. All the GPC algorithms are very similar because they have the same general idea in common. Authors in [7, 8] present an approach to the design of an RST cascade predictive structure to control rotor position, speed, and the rotor flux amplitude of an induction machine. The proposed cascaded version introduces a formulation of the reference signals in the structure of the inner and external loop which enables tracking flux and position. The purpose is to propose a new methodology to current-fed induction motor. This approach

results from a combination of the differential flatness properties and the monovariable GPC with the Multiple Reference Model (GPC/MRM) algorithm. The chosen outputs are the rotor speed and the square of the rotor flux [8]. Different techniques have been proposed from the active-set methods to LMI [11]. Lately, the idea of moving a part of the computational effort offline emerged and alternative techniques [9, 10] emerged based on look-up tables of linear affine controllers for regions of the state-space. The continuous robust GPC of a permanent synchronous motor drive is explored in [14]. This work combines GPC controller with linear predictive control technology for Permanent Magnet Synchronous Model (PMSM). A Continuous Linear Model (CTLM) is used to develop the GPC controller and determine the degree of the relative disturbance in [12-14, 18]. The SVPWM (Space Vector Pulse Width Modulation) GPC of linear induction motor drives was studied in [14, 15]. The authors used space vector pulse with modulation. Authors in [19, 20] used the FOD (Field Oriented Control) for the robustification of explicit predictive control law [20]. The work in [21] is based on parametric programming and concentrates on control robustification. GPC strategy is introduced for the prediction of the Controlled Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (CARIMA) plant model in [10, 21].

In this paper, an algorithm based on RST is presented. Our method uses the synchronous motor as a highly nonlinear multivariable system. It deals with the development of a high performance nonlinear predictive control induction motor drive. The research work is directed towards improving the trajectory tracking capability, stability guarantee, robustness to parameter variations, and disturbance rejection. Simulation results and the concluding remarks on the advantages and perspectives are also presented.

II. GENERALIZED PREDICTIVE CONTROL

A predictive strategy first requires the definition of a numerical prediction model. A commonly used form in GPC is the CARIMA model [6]:

$$A(q^{-1})y(t) = B(q^{-1})u(t - 1) + C(q^{-1})\frac{\xi(t)}{\Delta} \quad (1)$$

where $u(t)$, $y(t)$ are the process input and output, A and B are polynomials in the backward shift operator, $\xi(t)$ is an uncorrelated random sequence and the operator $\Delta(q^{-1}) = 1 - q^{-1}$ ensures an integral control law.

$$A(q^{-1}) = 1 + a_1q^{-1} + \dots + a_{na}q^{-na}$$

$$B(q^{-1}) = 1 + b_1q^{-1} + \dots + b_{nb}q^{-nb}$$

$$C(q^{-1}) = 1$$

n_a and n_b are degrees of polynomials A and B respectively.

A. Definition of the Quadratic Cost Function

The performance index is a weighted sum of predicted output tracking errors and future control errors, so the cost function to be minimized is [10, 19, 20].

$$i = \sum_{j=N_1}^{N_2} \varepsilon_y^2(t + j) + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^{N_u} \varepsilon_u^2(t + j - 1) \quad (2)$$

Assuming $\varepsilon_u(t + j) = 0$ for $j \geq N_u$:

$$\varepsilon(t + j) = y(t + j) - y_{ref}(t + j)$$

with:

$$\varepsilon_u(t + j) = \Delta u(t + j) - \Delta u_{ref}(t + j) \quad (3)$$

where N_1 and N_2 are the minimum and maximum costing horizons, N_u is the control horizon, and λ is the control weighting factor. The GPC version with reference models imposes that the predicted output tracks a reference trajectory y_{ref} coupled to a reference control signal u_{ref} . The originality of our approach is the formulation of the reference models for the y_{ref} for the rotor speed and the planned trajectories which satisfy the motor's constraints. The reference control signal u_{ref} will be expressed in terms of the chosen outputs [9-11, 20]. The linear structure RST law can be used in order to obtain access to a larger class of table controllers, by means of the Youla-Kucera parameterization.

III. DESIGN OF THE RST POLYNOMIAL CONTROLLER

To solve the minimization problem [10], an optimal j -step ahead predictor based on the output error must be computed:

$$\Delta(q^{-1})A(q^{-1})J(q^{-1}) + q^{-1}F_j(q^{-1}) = 1$$

$$G_j(q^{-1}) + q^{-1}H_j(q^{-1}) = B(q^{-1})J_j(q^{-1})$$

where F_j , G_j , H_j , and J_j are solutions of the Diophantine equations.

The optimal control law which minimizes the cost function is first deduced in a matrix form:

$$\varepsilon_{uopt} = -M[if\varepsilon_v(t) + ih\varepsilon_u(t - 1)] \quad (4)$$

with:

$$M = [G^T G + \lambda I_{N_u}]^{-1} G^T = \begin{bmatrix} M_1^T \\ \vdots \\ M_{N_u}^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where:

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} g_{N_1}^{N_1} & g_{N_1-1}^{N_1} & \dots & \dots \\ g_{N_1+1}^{N_1+1} & g_{N_1}^{N_1+1} & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ g_{N_2}^{N_2} & g_{N_2-1}^{N_2} & \dots & g_{N_2-N_u+1}^{N_2} \end{bmatrix}$$

The coefficients of the matrix G correspond to the step response:

$$if = [F_{N_1}(q^{-1}) \dots F_{N_2}(q^{-1})]^T$$

$$ih = [H_{N_1}(q^{-1}) \dots H_{N_2}(q^{-1})]^T$$

$$\varepsilon_{uopt} = [\varepsilon_{uopt}(t) \dots \varepsilon_{uopt}(t + N_u - 1)]^T$$

$$S(q^{-1})\Delta u(t) = -R(q^{-1})(t) + T(q^{-1})w(t) \quad (6)$$

with:

$$[S(q^{-1})] = \text{degree}[B(q^{-1})]$$

$$R(q^{-1}) = M_1^T if; \text{degree}[R(q^{-1})] = \text{degree}[A(q^{-1})];$$

$$T(q^{-1})w(t) = \Delta(q^{-1})S(q^{-1})u_{ref}(t) + R(q^{-1})y_{ref}(t) \quad (7)$$

where $R(q^{-1})$, $S(q^{-1})$, and $T(q^{-1})$ compose the equivalent controller of the GPC algorithm [2, 7]. The minimization of (7) provides the determination of the polynomials' structure of the GPC controller as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Equivalent polynomial controller.

IV. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF INDUCTION MOTOR FRAME ABC

The induction motor is generally used in industrial applications because it is reliable, robust, and has a low cost. A well-founded induction motor gives good results under various operating states. To achieve this, the values of the motor are kept in mind. Dynamic simulation plays a significant part in evaluating a model's design process in order to eliminate design errors. The induction motor is modeled in a synchronously revolving rotor flux-oriented frame, which is used as a reference. For sensorless vector control and induction motor control methods, accurate knowledge of a few induction motor parameters is necessary. The presentation of the drive will degrade if the original data in the motor do not match the values utilized in the controller. Various mechanisms have been developed to calculate the online and offline parameters of the induction machine for its application in high-performance drives. The aim of this paper is to present dynamic modeling and other considerable approaches used for estimating the induction motor parameters. Also, some simulation examples related to dynamic modeling and parameter estimation techniques, which may be useful for specialists in the field of electric drive control systems, are considered. Electrical drives based on induction motors are commonly used in industrial applications due to their simplicity and low maintenance cost. We are interested in the induction motor ABC frame model. Park transformation is not needed to realize the system. However, even if traditional control techniques of induction machines are adopted, e.g. scalar control, FOC, Direct Torque Control (DTC), predictive control, etc., improvements can be achieved in order to extend the operating range, improve behavior during saturations in order to reduce electrical influence and mechanical parameter variations, and improve transient performance. The reader is referred to [12-16] for the general theory of electric machine and induction motors for related control.

$$V = RI + \frac{d\phi}{dt} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{sa} \\ v_{sb} \\ v_{sc} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_s & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R_s \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_{sa} \\ i_{sb} \\ i_{sc} \end{bmatrix} + \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{sa} \\ \phi_{sb} \\ \phi_{sc} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The rotor voltage is described by the matrix form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{ra} \\ v_{rb} \\ v_{rc} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_r & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & R_r & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R_r \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_{ra} \\ i_{rb} \\ i_{rc} \end{bmatrix} + \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{ra} \\ \phi_{rb} \\ \phi_{rc} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

With the previous hypotheses, all the relations of induction motor are presented. The matrix of the real flux is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \phi_{sabc} \\ \phi_{rabc} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} L_s & M_{sr} \\ M_{sr} & L_r \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

with:

$$[L_s] = \begin{bmatrix} L_s & M_s & M_s \\ M_s & L_s & M_s \\ M_s & M_s & L_s \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$[L_r] = \begin{bmatrix} L_r & M_r & M_r \\ M_r & L_r & M_r \\ M_r & M_r & L_r \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$[M_{sr}] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\alpha) & \cos(\alpha + 2\pi/3) & \cos(\alpha - 2\pi/3) \\ \cos(\alpha - 2\pi/3) & \cos(\alpha) & \cos(\alpha + 2\pi/3) \\ \cos(\alpha + 2\pi/3) & \cos(\alpha - 2\pi/3) & \cos(\alpha) \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

The dynamic equation of the system is described by:

$$J \frac{d\Omega}{dt} = T_E - T_L \quad (14)$$

where J is the inertia of the machine, R_s and R_r are the stator and rotor resistances, L_s and L_r are the stator and rotor inductances, Ω is the rotor speed, α is the rotor position, M_{sr} is the mutual inductance, p is the number of pole pairs, f is the friction coefficient, T_L is the load torque, and T_r is the time rotor constant.

Fig. 2. Field oriented control of IC by GPC.

V. FIELD ORIENTATION CONTROL

The considered plan is an experimental setup of a squirrel cage induction motor. Benchmark systems for the positioning control laws of asynchronous machine details regarding the general theory of electric machines and induction motors can be found in [16, 17, 21]. The machine considered is a three

(squirrel) cage asynchronous motor with two pairs of poles in star power connection. The model takes into account the matrix transformations of the one phase system to a two phase representation, and the field oriented control including a torque and flux loop. The aim of the inner torque and flux control is to obtain a particular situation corresponding to the control of a DC motor. The model summarized in Figure 2 will be used to test the polynomial law in speed and position. For robust control of the motor velocity (good stability margins, small overshoot of the step response according to the guaranteed stability recommendation [22]), the auto calibration procedure by a controller is designed. The compliant link where the torque is often saturated during rapid slewing is controlled. The tuning parameters have their optimal values [21, 22].

according to the guaranteed stability recommendations and the auto calibration procedure, the above described controller is designed.

Fig. 3. Closed loop of poles.

Fig. 4. Velocity of the induction motor.

VI. STUDY AND TEST OF STABILITY

The stability of the scheme can be tested by looking in the Bode or Black diagram (Figures 6-7).

$$H(q^{-1}) = \frac{q^{-1}B(q^{-1})R(q^{-1})}{S(q^{-1})\Delta(q^{-1})A(q^{-1})} \tag{15}$$

The results are shown to exhibit the stability of the external loop, considering the open loop is defined as in [10]. This is a test for both the induction machine and the polynomial algorithm. The frequency does not enter 3db, guaranteeing an overshoot less than 5. For a robust control of the motor velocity (good stability margin, small overshoot of the step response)

Fig. 5. Torque with PWM.

Fig. 6. Bode plot.

Fig. 7. Black plot.

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

To test the performance of the nonlinear predictive controller, simulations were performed on an IM with nominal parameter values given in the Appendix and the load torque shown in Figure 8. The digital model of the motor is run with a sample time of 1µs. The space vector PWM inverter feeding the induction motor has a PWM period of 100µs. The full state vector is well known, where the stator voltage, stator current and speed are taken from the IM model and the rotor is estimated by (9). At first, the machine controlled by the cascade control law is run with the nominal values of the machines parameters. The tracking performance for rotor speed

with measure is shown in Figure 9, with disturbance at 0.5s in Figure 10, and without disturbance in Figure 11.

$$\frac{\Omega(t)}{\Gamma(t)} = \frac{1.344q^{-1} + 3.024q^{-2} + 1}{1 - 0.92q^{-1} - 0.02q^{-2}} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 8. Torque with constraints.

Fig. 9. Output reference speed.

Fig. 10. Output speed with disturbance.

The simulations were performed with a sampling period of $T_s=0.05s$. We chose the GPC parameters $N_1, N_2, N_u, \lambda, GM, QM$, and BM . $w(t+j)$ is the future set point and N_1, N_2, N_u ,

and λ , are parameters that must be elaborated. $G = [1.34, 5.68, 0.96, 14.24, 18.53, 22.81, 24.09, 31, 96, 1]^T$ is a column vector and $GG^T=2919.09$ is the scalar sum of the squares of the first eight step responses.

$$R(q^{-1}) = 0.284 - 0.237q^{-1} - 0.0048q^{-2}$$

$$S(q^{-1}) = 1 + 0.734q^{-1}$$

$$T(q^{-1}) = 0.0043q + 0.000182q^1 + 0.00319q^2 + 0.00319q^3 + 0.0045q^4 + 0.00594q^5 + 0.0731q^6 + 0.1006q^6$$

Fig. 11. Output speed without disturbance

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, nonlinear predictive control is developed for speed and flux tracking of an induction motor drive. It was shown that this kind of control is effective for solving the control problem of induction machines. The computation of the predictive control law is easy and does not need online optimization.

The performance of nonlinear predictive control to the induction machine drive is exhibited and the rejection of the unknown load torque is enhanced. This work presented the simulated induction motor with an ABC frame, and generalized predictive control without and with constraints. RST synthesis was used for the rotor speed controller of the induction motor. Simulation results were given in the case of nominal and mismatched parameters of the complete nonlinear model. This is particularly beneficial in the case of motor driven speed, as seen in the example of a computer-controlled compliant link where the torque is often saturated during rapid slewing, forming an interesting limiting case and making the performance and robustness evaluation of the designed controller a challenging engineering problem. The choice of the tuning parameters is not yet optimized, essentially dealing with the choice of the control weighting factor and the output prediction horizons. However, the resulting performances are satisfactory, and the appropriate choice of the GPC tuning knobs may improve the robustness of this controller.

APPENDIX

The control law was implemented on a small 1.5KW induction motor, which corresponds to the Benchmark AC machine of the LAN (Laboratoire d'Automatique de Nantes), with the following features:

$$\begin{aligned} R_r &= 2.61\Omega, & J &= 0.0256\text{Kgm}^2 \\ R_s &= 4.287\Omega, & f &= 0.0029 \\ L_r &= 0.368\text{H}, & p &= 2 \\ L_s &= 0.404\text{H}, & w_{\text{nom}} &= 150\text{rad/s} \\ M &= 0.368\text{H}, & T_{\text{cm}} &= 10\text{Nm}, \Phi_{r\alpha\beta} = 0.725\text{Wb} \end{aligned}$$

The GPC chosen design parameters of the robust controller as shown in Figure 1 (gain margin(dB), Φ_M : phase margin (degree), BW : bandwidth(rad/s)) are:

$N_1 = 1$: is the minimum cost

$N_2 = 8$: is the maximum cost.

$N_u = 1$: is the control horizon.

$\lambda = 200$: is the control weighting.

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The Design Method of Traction Power Supplies in Integrated Metro Systems

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ABSTRACT

Integrated subway systems have emerged as a new trend that provides the highest quality service at the lowest investment cost by combining the advantages of the two largest passenger transport capabilities during peak hours. Under the integrated model, designing the traction power supply is much more complex than for other independent systems. This article presents the results of a study on the method of calculating the design load of the power supply for the transport operation of the system. Matlab R2017b/Railway Systems is a reliable software for simulating and analyzing some necessary data, and the research results show the feasibility of the method when applied to the case of asynchronous load on the system. The results meet the power supply design standards according to IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and IEC 60146-1 overload allowances for class VI, and voltage standards according to EN 50163, UIC 600, and IEC 60850.

Keywords-subway train; integrated subway system; urban integrated railway; traction substation

I. INTRODUCTION

The integrated subway model - MRC is a combination of subway trains (MRT) and suburban trains (CR). This combination model allows the operation with a very large transport capacity during peak hours in order to meet the demand for travel between the suburbs and the city center, which each type alone cannot meet, and to return to the separate normal operating state of each type during off-peak hours with the lowest investment cost and the highest service quality. This method allows for increasing the transport capacity and service frequency of the subway line without the need to increase the number of purchased trains operating on the line. On the other hand, the suburban train, when running on the line, will operate like a subway train. The diagram of the integrated train operation is described in Figure 1 of [1], in which A to E are the terminal stations of the subway line, B to E (or B to A but stops at any station) the terminal stations of the suburban railway, and B to A is the integrated peak-hour suburban railway station.

Over the past few years, many studies have emphasized the advantages of having a subway system that is integrated [2-6]. To guarantee that the system operates in a manner that is flexible, efficient, dependable, and energy-saving, it must have a robust power supply system that can support maximum

transportation capacity during peak hours. Despite this, the majority of research studies have concentrated on planning, predicting, and handling transportation capacity and energy conservation while assessing the advantages it provides to the overall development of smart cities in the current integrated subway context [7-11]. Some recent studies have been conducted on the method of designing the power supply for electric subway trains [12-20] and the study of operating voltage in a pure system [19]. This article presents the results of the research on calculating the design of traction power supply for the integrated system. In the design of the power supply for traction, to ensure continuous, flexible, reliable, safe, and efficient system operation, the traction power station capacity must meet two evaluation criteria: power supply capacity and minimum contact voltage allowed in normal operating conditions and emergencies.

The majority of the research on creating power systems for subway trains uses computer simulations that are comprehensive, effective, and affordable. In this particular study, the software chosen for simulating and calculating a power supply that meets the global standards is Matlab R2017b/Railway Systems.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Calculating the Power of the Traction Substation

There are many methods used to calculate the design load of the electric traction power supply for a subway or suburban railway system [12-20]. However, these methods only allow separate calculations for each system. For integrated systems that combine two systems with different capacities on the same power supply system, this difference, which arises from the characteristics of the train, is an important issue in load calculation. Since the transport capacity of subway and suburban trains is different, the current used is also different. Correspondingly, the acceleration and operating speed are different, so the mechanical resistance (R_r) and acceleration resistance (R_a) are also different. As a result, the maximum instantaneous traction force performed on each cycle of each train trip between the two stations is different. From all these differences, an asynchronous load is created over the range of the power supply of a traction substation. Therefore, calculating this complex asynchronous load needs to meet the demand for the highest power usage during peak hours.

The components of train motion resistance (R_r), acceleration resistance (R_a), curve resistance (R_c), gradient resistance (R_g), and tunnel resistance (R_t) can appear in one cycle of the train motion starting at station j within the power supply range of a traction substation i .

$$R_{r,x,y} = A + Bv + Cv^2 \tag{1}$$

$$R_{g,i,j} = \pm G/1000 \tag{2}$$

$$R_{t,i,j} = \frac{f_t \cdot v^2}{w} \tag{3}$$

$$\begin{cases} R_{c,i,j} = \frac{650}{r-55}, & r < 300 \\ R_{c,i,j} = \frac{500}{r-30}, & r \geq 300 \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

$$R_{a,x,y,i,j} = \frac{a\xi}{g} \tag{5}$$

The maximum resistance is:

$$\begin{cases} \sum R_{i,j} = R_{c,i,j} + R_{g,i,j} + R_{t,i,j} \\ R_{\max,i,j} \leq \sum R_{i,j} < R_a + R_r \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

Let M_x and M_y be the total weight of the subway train x and the suburban train y at full load with maximum carrying capacity. The maximum instantaneous traction force of train x and y in each direction, within the supply range of a traction power station i and traveling from station j in the direction of k and towards h , can be calculated:

$$F_{t,i,j-kx,\max} = M_x \cdot (R_{a,x} + R_{r,x} + \sum R_{\max,j-kx}) \tag{7}$$

$$\sum R_{\max,j-kx} = R_{c,j-kx} + R_{g,j-kx} + R_{t,j-kx} \tag{8}$$

$$F_{t,i,j-hx,\max} = M_x \cdot (R_{a,x} + R_{r,x} + \sum R_{\max,j-hx}) \tag{9}$$

$$\sum R_{\max,j-hx} = R_{c,j-hx} + R_{g,j-hx} + R_{t,j-hx} \tag{10}$$

$$F_{t,i,j-ky,\max} = M_y \cdot (R_{a,y} + R_{r,y} + \sum R_{\max,j-ky}) \tag{11}$$

$$\sum R_{\max,j-ky} = R_{c,j-ky} + R_{g,j-ky} + R_{t,j-ky} \tag{12}$$

$$F_{t,i,j-hy,\max} = M_y \cdot (R_{a,y} + R_{r,y} + \sum R_{\max,j-hy}) \tag{13}$$

$$\sum R_{\max,j-hy} = R_{c,j-hy} + R_{g,j-hy} + R_{t,j-hy} \tag{14}$$

The maximum traction force under normal conditions is:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n F_{t,i,j,(na)\max} = \sum_{na} p_i \in i,j P_{l,\max} \cdot F_{t,i,j,(na)\max} \tag{15}$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{na} p_i \in i,j P_{l,\max} = \frac{60}{c_{l,\max}} \cdot \frac{D_{TPSi}}{v_{sc}} \cdot 2 \\ 1,25 \leq c_{l,\max} < c_{l,MRT}, c_{l,\max} = \frac{C_{p,\max}}{C_{t,\max}} \\ F_{t,i,j,(na)\max} \in kx, hx, ky, hy \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

When an error (er) occurs:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i+1} F_{t,i,j,(er)\max} = \sum_{er} p_i \in i,j P_{l,\max} \cdot F_{t,i,j,(er)\max} \tag{17}$$

where:

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{er} p_i \in i,j P_{l,\max} = \frac{60}{c_{l,\max}} \cdot \frac{2}{v_{sc}} \cdot [D_{TPSi} + \frac{D_{TPSi+1}}{2}] \\ 1,25 \leq c_{l,\max} < c_{l,MRT}, c_{l,\max} = \frac{C_{p,\max}}{C_{t,\max}} \\ F_{t,i,j,(na)\max} \in kx, hx, ky, hy \end{cases} \tag{18}$$

The maximum instantaneous power demand within an hour is described by:

$$P_{t,i,j,(na)\max} = \sum_{i=1}^{P_{l,(na),\max}} F_{t,i,j,(na)\max} \cdot \frac{v}{3,6 \cdot \eta_{mc} \cdot \eta_{mt}} \tag{19}$$

$$P_{t,i,j,(er)\max} = \sum_{i=1}^{P_{l,(er),\max}} F_{t,i,j,(er)\max} \cdot \frac{v}{3,6 \cdot \eta_{mc} \cdot \eta_{mt}} \tag{20}$$

where η_{mc} and η_{mt} are the mechanical and engine efficiency respectively:

$$\begin{cases} \eta_{mc,\min} < \eta_{mc} \leq \eta_{mc,\max} \\ \eta_{mt,\min} < \eta_{mt} \leq \eta_{mt,\max} \\ v_{sc} < v \leq v_{peak} \end{cases} \tag{21}$$

The auxiliary power consumption is:

$$P_{[x,y],i(na)aux} = \sum_{na} p_i \in i P_{l,\max} \left(\begin{matrix} n_{[x,y]} \cdot P_{d,[x,y]} \\ + m_{[x,y]} \cdot P_{c,[x,y]} \end{matrix} \right) \tag{22}$$

$$P_{[x,y],i(er)aux} = \sum_{er} p_i \in i P_{l,\max} \left(\begin{matrix} n_{[x,y]} \cdot P_{d,[x,y]} \\ + m_{[x,y]} \cdot P_{c,[x,y]} \end{matrix} \right) \tag{23}$$

The maximum instantaneous total power requirement within an hour is defined as:

$$P_{TPSi(na)\max} = P_{t,i,j(na)\max} + P_{[x,y],i(na)aux} \tag{23}$$

$$P_{TPSi(er)\max} = P_{t,i,j(er)\max} + P_{[x,y],i(er)aux} \tag{24}$$

If the system has regenerative braking, the percentage of energy recovered η_{re} is:

$$P_{TPSi(re, na)\max} = P_{TPSi(na)\max} (1 - \eta_{re}) \tag{25}$$

$$P_{TPSi(re, er)\max} = P_{TPSi(er)\max} (1 - \eta_{re}) \tag{26}$$

with criterion:

$$\begin{cases} \eta_{re,na,min} < \eta_{re[x,y]} \leq \eta_{re,na,max} \\ \eta_{re,er,min} < \eta_{re[x,y]} \leq \eta_{re,er,max} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

The power selection for the traction substation is:

$$P_{TPSi(er,na)max} \leq P_{TPSi(na),min} \quad (28)$$

$$P_{TPSi(re,er)max} \leq P_{TPSi(re),min} \quad (29)$$

$$P_{TPSi(re),min} < P_{TPSi} \leq P_{TPSi(na),min} \quad (30)$$

Therefore, the selected power for the traction substation according to (28)-(30) must comply with IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and IEC 60146-1 standards.

B. Operating Voltage

Let U_{dc-o} , U_{fdc} , and $U_{tx:xi,yi}$ be the operating voltage of the unloaded rectifier, the supply voltage, and the contact voltage, respectively:

$$I_{i(na)max} = \sum_1^{c_{l,max}} I_{x,y(i) \in \sum_{na, p_1 \in i_j} P_{l,max}} \quad (31)$$

$$I_{i(er)max} = \sum_1^{c_{l,max}} I_{x,y(i) \in \sum_{er, p_1 \in i_j} P_{l,max}} \quad (32)$$

$$U_{fdc,(na,er)} = U_{dc-o} - I_{i(na,er)max} \cdot \sum R_{TPSi,cf} \quad (33)$$

$$\sum \Delta U_{dc:j,j+xmax} = I_{i(na,er),Lx} \cdot r_{cls} \cdot L_x + I_{i(na,er),x} \cdot r_{cls} \cdot X_{max} \quad (34)$$

$$U_{tx(na,er),min} = U_{fdc,(na,er)} - \sum \Delta U_{dc:j,j+xmax} \quad (35)$$

The minimum contact voltage at the end of the power supply section of a traction substation operating in normal or fault conditions must satisfy the operating voltage requirements of the EN 50163, UIC 600, and IEC 60850 standards, as specified in (35).

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. Load Parameters

The route profile from substation 3 to substation 4 can be seen in Table I. TPSi is the i^{th} traction substation, STj is the j^{th} passenger station, G%o is the lope of the railway, C is the curve radius, Rt is the coefficient of tunnel resistance for smooth plane double track, and SP is the end of power supply section. The load parameters are exhibited in Table II and the traction parameters in Table III [1].

TABLE I. PROFILE OF THE ROUTE FROM TRACTION SUBSTATION NO. 3 TO NO. 4 ALONG THE LINE

Km	TPSi	STj	G%o	C	Rt
10.0	SP	11			
11.00		12			
11.50			+35	650	
12.00		13			
12.40	3				
13.20		14			
13.70			+5	500	
14.00	SP				
14.40		15			
15.40		16	-5		17.14
15.80			-20		17.14
16.00	4				17.14
16.40		17			17.14
17.40		18			17.14

TABLE II. TRAIN LOAD PARAMETERS

Symbol	Specifications	Description
$C_{p1,z}$	45.000; 54.000	Person/hour/direction
n_x, n_y	2; 2	Control car
m_x, m_y	6; 5	locomotive unit
$m_{d,x,y}$	40 tons; 42 tons	Control car
$m_{c,x,y}$	38 tons; 41 tons	Locomotive unit
$S_{d,x}$	3.2x22 m ²	Floor area of a passenger car
$S_{c,x}$	3.2x23 m ²	Passenger area
$S_{d,y}$	3.27x25 m ²	Floor area of a passenger car
$S_{c,y}$	3.27x26 m ²	Passenger area
$f_{s,d,x,y}$	0.45%; 0.42%	Occupancy rate
$f_{s,c,x,y}$	0.55%; 0.45%	Occupancy rate
$f_{d,x}$	38 seats	Cabin seat
$f_{c,x}$	44 seats	Passenger seat
$f_{d,y}$	32 seats	Cabin seat
$f_{c,y}$	42 seats	Passenger seat
m_p	55 kg	Weight/passenger

TABLE III. TRAIN TRACTION PARAMETERS

Symbol	Metric	Value
$C_{L,p1}$	[p/h/d]	45,000
$C_{L,p2}$	[p/h/d]	54,000
$a_{x,max}/\beta_{x,max}$	[m/s ²]	0.9/1.0
$a_{y,max}/\beta_{y,max}$	[m/s ²]	0.85/1.0
R_x, R_y	[kg/tán]	
$R_x = 3.25 + 0.039 \cdot V + 0.000659 \cdot V^2$		
$R_y = 2.45 + 0.044 \cdot V + 0.000374 \cdot V^2$		
v_{sc}, v_{max}	[km/h]	45/60
Train load Ix [A]: 400·(4M)+200·(2M)+200·(2Mc)		
Train load [A]: 400·(4M)+200·(1M)+200·(2Mc)		
Support load Iaux [A]: 25.3333·(6M)+24·(2Mc)		
Support load Iauy [A]: 26.6667·(5M)+24·(2Mc)		

B. Design of the Calculation Process

The process of calculating the design of a pullable electrical supply is described as an algorithmic flowchart in Figure 1.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Result of Selecting the Power Capacity for the Traction Substation

1) Case 1

The calculated power capacity for traction substation No. 3 in case 1 is presented in Table IV.

In summary, the maximum calculated power required for the traction of both normal operation and contingency situations meets the actual power consumption demand of the selected train load. Therefore, it satisfies the design calculation requirements. The selected power capacity of the traction substation must also meet the overload conditions in both normal and contingency situations. The chosen power per unit converter is 3,2000MW, and the traction substation power is 6,4000MW, which is less than the actual power consumption demand of 6,5113MW, but greater than the demand in cases of regeneration when braking normally and in contingency situations, which are 3,9068MW and 5,8602MW, respectively.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the load calculation process.

TABLE IV. THE CALCULATED POWER CAPACITY FOR TRACTION SUBSTATION NO. 3 IN CASE 1

Component	Phase 1	Ph 2
n	3.0000	2.5000
Fmax [kN]	244.4978	244.4978
Pmax.na [MW]	7.9319	9.5183
Pmax.er [MW]	11.8989	14.2775
Pre.na [MVA]	4.7592	5.7110
Pre.er [MVA]	7.1387	8.5665
Pload.na [MW]	6.5113	7.8136
Pload.er [MW]	9.7670	11.7203
Pldre.na [MW]	3.9068	4.6881
Pldre.er [MW]	5.8602	7.0322
prec [MW/dv]	3.2000	3.2000
nprec [dv]	2+1	3+1
Ptps [MW]	6.4000	9.6000
Pol.na(2h) [MW]	9.6000	14.4000
Pol.er(2h) [MW]	14.4000	14.4000

The power supply capacity of the traction substation with the ability to withstand overload for two continuous hours according to the IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and IEC 60146-1 standards, is 9,6000MW, which is greater than the actual consumption demand of 6,5113MW and the theoretical calculation of 7,9319MW for normal operation. The ability to withstand overload for contingency situations is 14,4000MW

(all three converters working together), which is greater than the actual consumption demand of 9,7670MW and the theoretical calculation of 11,8979MW.

In phase 2, under normal circumstances, the station operates with three power supply units providing 9,6000MW, which is greater than the maximum calculated power requirement of 9,5183MW, the regeneration requirement under contingency situations of 8,5665MW, and the actual power consumption demand of 7,0322MW. If there is no regeneration, the overload capacity is 14,4000MW, which is greater than the maximum calculated power requirement of 14,2775MW and the actual power consumption demand of 11,7203MW. Therefore, the analysis of the results shows that the selected power capacity is suitable for the required load demand.

2) Case 2

In the case of an incident, traction substation number 3 must also supply power to an additional segment from traction substation number 4. The calculated power capacity for traction substation number 3 in case 2 is shown in Table V.

TABLE V. THE CALCULATED POWER CAPACITY FOR TRACTION SUBSTATION NO. 3 IN CASE 2

Component	Phase 1	Phase 2
nCR	4.5000	3.0000
nInter	3.0000	2.5000
FmaxCR [kN]	205.6862	205.6862
FmaxInter [kN]	244.4978	244.4978
Pmax.na [MW]	4.5590	6.8385
Pmax.er [MW]	9.2539	12.6911
Pre.na [MVA]	3.1913	4.7869
Pre.er [MVA]	6.4777	8.8838
Pload.na [MW]	3.9758	5.9637
Pload.er [MW]	7.5965	10.4181
Pldre.na [MW]	2.7831	4.1746
Pldre.er [MW]	5.3176	7.2927
prec [MW/dv]	3.2000	3.2000
nprec [dv]	2+1	2+1
Ptps [MW]	6.4000	9.6000
Pol.na(2h) [MW]	9.6000	14.4000
Pol.er(2h) [MW]	14.4000	14.4000

In this case, the selected power capacity for the station must meet two different loads. The capacity of each rectifier unit is 3.2000MW, and the station is designed with a (2+1) configuration for each load phase. In phase 1, the station supplies a capacity of 6.4000MW, which is greater than the normal maximum load calculation (4.5590MW) and the contingency load in case of regeneration inhibition (5.3176MW), but smaller than the normal maximum load calculation without any contingency (9.2539MW). However, the station's ability to withstand 150% overload for two consecutive peak hours is 9.6000MW, which is higher than the actual consumption load (7.5965MW) and even the maximum calculated contingency load without regeneration inhibition (9.2539MW), meeting the standards' requirements.

In phase 2, under normal operating conditions, the station provides the rated power of 6.4000MW, which is lower than the maximum calculated load (6.8385MW), but the ability to withstand overload is up to 9.6000MW in the event of

regeneration inhibition (8.8838MW and 7.2927MW), but cannot handle contingencies without regeneration inhibition. Therefore, in this case, the station must operate with three rectifier units simultaneously with a total capacity of 9.6000MW, with the ability to handle overload up to 14.4000MW, which is higher than the actual consumption capacity of 10.4181MW and the maximum calculated capacity of 12.6911MW. Thus, the analysis results show that the selected power capacity is suitable for the load requirements.

The calculated and selected power capacity for the traction substation in both cases 1 and 2 are based on the comprehensive calculation method for the integrated subway train load. This method effectively meets the load requirements and ensures good performance for 150% overload capability for two consecutive hours. Therefore, there is no need to consider overload cases of 200%, 300%, and 450%, as per the criteria for evaluating the design of traction substation power capacity specified by IEEE P1653.2, EN 50328, and IEC 60146-1.

B. Operating Voltage

Checking the operating voltage is the final step in designing the power supply for this integrated subway electrical load.

In phase 1, the unloaded rectified voltage is 1.656V for two parallel rectifiers in normal operation and three rectifiers in the event of a failure, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Operating voltage in phase 1.

On the left segment, the supplied voltage at the supply station is 1.325V and the contact voltage at the furthest end of the left segment is 1.183V. On the right segment, the contact voltage at the end of the segment is 1.252V in normal operation and 1.161V in case of a failure, and the contact voltage at the extended segment is 1.047V. Therefore, in phase 1, the smallest contact voltage at the end of the extended segment in case of a failure is 1.047V, which is higher than the minimum allowable limit of 1.000V.

In phase 2, in normal operation with three parallel rectifiers, the no-load voltage is 1.656V, as shown in Figure 3. In normal operation, the supply voltage at the supply station for both sections is 1.391V, the minimum contact voltage on the left

section is 1.221V, and the minimum contact voltage on the right section is 1.266V, which is greater than the minimum allowed voltage of 1.000V. In the event of a fault, the supply voltage is 1.259V on both left and right sections, the minimum contact voltage on the left section is 1.089V, and the minimum on the extended right section is 957.5V. Thus, although the station using 3 rectifiers, it exceeds the allowable overload power of 150% (14.4MW) according to the standard, violating the voltage standard (957.5V < 1.000V). Therefore, the station's capacity must be increased by using 4 parallel-connected rectifiers, at which time the supply voltage on both sections is 1.358V, the minimum contact voltage on the left section is 1.188V, and the minimum contact voltage on the extended right section is 1.057V, which is greater than the minimum allowable voltage of 1.000V according to EN 50163, UIC 600, and IEC 60850 standards. Thus, increasing the power supply capacity at the traction substation can meet the demand of the load consumption, reduce voltage drop, and increase the contact voltage to satisfy the selection condition 1 (No.op1), without considering the selection condition 2 (No.op2) in the design calculation process.

Fig. 3. Operating voltage in phase 2.

V. CONCLUSION

The current paper proposes a calculative method for the power design of a traction substation based on the maximum instantaneous traction force calculation under the integrated subway railway model. The method was designed and simulated on Matlab R2017b/Railway Systems, and its reliability was demonstrated through various cases of loads for maximum power during peak hours. The method also ensures transparency and logic when calculating data in a sequence with filtering and cross-referencing for backup situations to avoid power waste. The calculated power is higher than the load demand from 14.67% to 21.81%, allowing the selection of a substation power that meets the standards for the redundancy factor and the allowed range of low voltage overload operation.

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GIS-Based Multi Criteria Analysis for Solar Power Plant Site Selection Support in Mecca

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ABSTRACT

One of the major sources of renewable energy, particularly electricity generation and water desalination, is solar energy. The National Initiative to produce Water and Electricity started when the electricity consumption in Saudi Arabia began to increase by about 5% per year. The current investigation aims to use a multicriteria GIS technique to identify the best spatial location for solar energy collection in the Mecca Administrative District. The best locations for solar power plant construction were determined with the use of a set of factors and criteria, including planning and environmental criteria, and terrain calibrator. These criteria were defined through a thorough literature review. This information was then used to create a digital geographic database, which was incorporated into an integrated GIS to produce a spatial fit model. According to the suitability data, most of Mecca region is ideal for solar energy projects, with an applicability percentage ranging between 30% and 80%. These findings are encouraging and promising for Mecca's renewable energy industry and they should be considered. It was discovered by examining these spatial locations and the level of suitability to the specifications that the lands with a sufficient share of more than 80% form an area of around 4000km² and makeup 3% of all suitable lands. The governorates of the Mecca Administrative Area are home to most of these exceptionally suited locations. The Taif governorate takes first place with 35% of the total area and the two governorates of Turbah are placed second and third with 24% and 14%. In the Mecca Administrative Area, the appropriate lands for solar energy projects are distributed spatially according to a digital map. The study proposes incorporating the findings into the Saudi national plan for renewable energy sources.

Keywords-solar power; special analytics; multiple criteria; DSS; GIS

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's actual power generation capacity raised from 15,212MW to 51,302MW, with more than 7% mean annual growth. Simultaneously, the portion of one subscriber increased from 23,928kWh to 33,936kWh. Electricity is one of the most significant factors contributing to the rapid development and growth in all spheres of life on a global scale [8-11]. One renewable energy source that may be used anywhere and is free

and endless, is solar energy. This form of renewable energy is clean and does not emit any pollutants, unlike the conventional energy sources. The strategies, methods, and processes for harnessing solar energy and turning it into electrical energy are becoming more and more popular on a global scale. Over the past 15 years, the development of the electricity generation from solar energy led to a reduction in electricity cost by 4% per year [13-18]. High levels of solar radiation that can be converted into energy are present throughout the Middle East, especially in the Arab world. Recently, countries in this region

have tended to increase research, development, and investment efforts in solar energy. In the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the interest in solar energy exists for forty years [25-27]. It should be mentioned that several studies in the Kingdom have shown that, taking into consideration the economic value of the environmental and the health risks of oil use, the cost of producing power from solar energy is less than that of producing electricity from oil [13-17]. All the Gulf Cooperation Council nations have begun investing in renewable energy sources, particularly solar energy, at a regional level [18-24].

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are the best option for gathering, storing, processing, analysing, and displaying spatial and non-spatial data to come up with technological answers to multi-domain problems. A set of alternatives or solutions are presented to decision-makers after the multi-parameter GIS approach has studied the potential of a variety of natural, economic, and environmental criteria in a particular spatial location. This approach can be utilized in a wide variety of situations and it has been used to choose the optimal location for several projects, including solid waste treatment facilities, sewage treatment plants, agricultural development, and renewable energy projects. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has used this approach in several different fields. This strategy, for instance, was used to determine the optimal locations in the for the construction of rainfall harvesting dams and flood control systems, to choose the optimum site for the construction of tourist facilities, and GIS with multiple calibrations was used to determine the most suitable spatial locations for setting up solar collector projects in Mecca area from Kingdom of Saudi Arabia [1-7]. This study aims to provide solutions to help policymakers choose the most suitable locations to set up solar mining projects.

II. STUDY AREA

The Mecca region spans a sizable area and is situated in the center of the western sector of the Kingdom [29]. This region covers about 150km², or 7% of the whole area of the Kingdom. By 2025, the number of inhabitants is anticipated to reach 9.7 million [28].

III. RESOURCES AND TECHNIQUES

The initial data for the study came from several sources, and the requisite databases were later built. The information which was digitized came from [29]. Development Specialist Mecca provided information on major cities, air terminals, electrical installation broadcasting classes and street organization.

The ground elevation of the Mecca specified area extends from -9m to 2586m, with a mean of 843m [29]. The highest mountains in the region are the Al-Hadab Mountains in Maysan Belharith, which are nearly 2,500m above sea level. The Sarawat-Hijaz Mountains extend from the northwest to the southeast, forming a group of hills that are characteristic of the topography of the Mecca Administrative Region. These hills include the East Al-Sarawat plateau, which stretches from the city of Taif in the north to the border of the Al-Baha region in the south, and the Rakba plain's elevation, which stretches for

around 400km and nearly 200km north to south. A collection of coastal fields arranged in the form of a run parallel to the Ruddy Sea's shore and varying in width from 15 to 25km are also included in the region's topography [27]. The major energy distribution network in Mecca has a total length of about 900km while the main road network has a total length of over 7000km. The majority of the cities are grouped together in the west, near the shore.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

The first procedures in data handling attempt to arrive at a group of criteria that have to be available in selecting the most appropriate geological areas for the use of the geographic data framework (GIS) in order to facilitate the selection of the locations for sun-oriented energy plants [19–21], which results in choosing the best spatial sites for solar power plants. One of the most crucial factors is the amount of solar radiation [28], followed by the criterion of trends and the inclination direction, which has an impact on the setup and installation of the necessary equipment for solar power plants.

Fig. 1. Optimal site selection criteria for solar cell construction.

Regarding the environment, picking the best places for solar energy projects involves the distance from major cities, airports, roads, electrical distribution networks, and beaches. Seven criteria were chosen (see Figure 1) and their relative weights were calculated (see Table I).

TABLE I. CRITERIA TO BE CONSIDERED WHEN SELECTING THE BEST SITES FOR SOLAR POWER PLANTS

Principle type	Principle	Result %
Planning	Towns and airfields	10
	Streets	10
	Shoreline	10
	Power networks	15
Environment	Solar radiation	30
Terrain calibrator	Inclination	10
	Inclination direction	15

For each of the stated criteria, a network layer representing the categorization of the criteria's values was derived [20-24]. These network layers were then reclassified according to scale ranging from 1 to 10 for simplicity of presentation and analysis. The final fit model was then obtained by applying the appropriate weights [28].

V. MODEL BUILDER

The process of creating a model involves feeding it with raw data, such as street networks, towns and airfields, digital elevation model, power system, coastline. The digital elevation model was used to extract solar radiation, inclination, and inclination orientation. The weight for each cell was determined using the Euclidean distance tool, and the street grid chart, power grid chart, town map, airfields, and shoreline map were created by reclassifying (or changing) the values in the raster, using the tool for weighted overlay [8]. The optimal location for solar power plants in Mecca was identified using specific weights for each parameter (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. The model builder will decide which locations are ideal for building solar plants.

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSES

Many initial models were built up matching the layers of the criteria values to the degree of spatial suitability for each criterion [8, 12]. Figures 3-11 were made with the ESRI ARC/GIS software, version 10.3. Figure 3 shows the territorial suitability for the sun powered radiation model, with the center and eastern areas having the most noteworthy esteem. Since most cities are located on the western side of coastline and in connection to basis for separate shoreline, areas of appropriate height are those that are the most remote from the shoreline, as shown in Figure 5 of the spatial appropriateness demonstrate for the cities and air terminals measure.

Fig. 3. Solar radiation classification chart.

Fig. 4. Classification of the distance to cities and airports.

Fig. 5. Classification of the distance to the coastline.

Fig. 6. Degrees of conformity to the power line standard in locations in Mecca.

Fig. 7. Degrees of conformity to the road standard in Mecca.

Fig. 8. Mecca's conformance map to slope standards.

Figure 6 outlines the spatial amplexness from the power dispersion. It should be noted that high altitude areas are those that are not distant from the control conveyance line. This model pertains to the criterion of distance from the electricity distribution network. Additionally, the chart shows that the optimal areas are concentrated on the western portion of the research region for this criterion. Figure 7 portrays the area suitability with regard to the proximity to the road network.

Fig. 9. Map classifying orientation.

Fig. 10. Best sites for solar power plants in Mecca.

Figures 8 and 9 indicate that most of the authoritative locales have great suitability degrees with regard to slope and slope orientation, with the exemption of the centre fragment of the area, which has extraordinary slants. At the highest places the degree of suitability was medium and occasionally weak.

To ensure that the sun's rays fall directly on the solar cells, it is ideal for the gradient to face south, southeast, or southwest. As a result, these restrictions were used in the final fit process, which can be seen in Figure 10.

Mecca as a whole is ideal for the solar energy harvesting, with a reasonable rate between 30% and 80%. The findings of

the current study are important for Mecca's renewable energy sector. A detailed examination of the spatial zones and their level of compliance with the regulations shows that a 3% of the qualified lands that are defined by a satisfactory extent of more than 80% and cover a total area of about 4000km².

two Turbah governorates with 24% and the Rania governorate with 14%. The governorates of Maysan and Al-Khumra follow, each with 14%, and none of the other governorates have any place with a degree of compliance more than 80%.

VII. CONCLUSION

The current research focuses on the Mecca region of Saudi Arabia, mainly due to the promising prospects for international energy interconnection. The distribution of spatial phenomena varies between natural and human phenomena that spread on the lands of Mecca Governorate, such as road networks, electricity network, cities and airports, solar radiation, and tendencies. Combined, these are criteria that the study relied on to design a model that determines the suitability for the application of solar energy projects. Based on the investigation and analysis conducted in this study, it was found that the degree of spatial appropriateness varies, and the land area with a fit coefficient greater than 80% is about 5,000km². Mecca Governorate's center region contains the majority of these areas. To evaluate the best locations for the deployment of photovoltaic power stations in the Mecca region, this study considered various criteria (planning standards, environmental standards, terrain calibrator). The results showed that, with varying degrees ranging between 30% and 80%, the larger part of the Mecca Regulatory Locale is suitable for establishing solar power plants. The conclusions of this investigation are more accurate than those obtained from previous studies, which conclude that the whole area of Mecca is suitable for solar power plant placement. This study's outcome can help decision-makers to specify the most suitable locations to set up solar harvesting projects in the Governorate of Mecca.

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Fig. 11. Sitemap with relevance ≥ 80% in Mecca.

Fig. 12. Areas with at least 80% compliance.

TABLE II. DISTRIBUTION OF LOCATIONS WITH SPATIAL SUITABILITY GREATER THAN 80%

Percentage %	Area in km ²	Governorate
24	1051	Turubah
14	608	Raneh
35	1521	Taif
6	278	Khorma
5	236	Moyaha
1	48	Kamil
5	211	Jamom
9	403	Maysaan
100	4356	Total

Table II and Figures 11 and 12 show how these appropriate locations are distributed throughout the governorates of the Mecca Authoritative Locale. The Taif governorate has the most suitable areas, with 35% of the overall zones, followed by the

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A Non-destructive Radar Device for Detecting Additive Materials in Concrete

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ABSTRACT

The use of electronic devices based on electromagnetic waves is promising for inspecting additives in structural concrete. However, the existing commercial devices are high-cost and do not publicly provide circuit design information. To overcome this issue, this study designed a low-cost nondestructive testing device with a radar sensor, using an HB-100 radar sensor module to generate and receive the radar wave. A suitable bandpass filter was used to suppress electrical noise in the received signal, an Arduino board was used for signal processing, and the measured data were displayed on a computer. The output at the IF pin of the sensor module presents the Doppler frequency and absorbance of the target materials. The device was tested to detect additives inside the concrete. An additive material can be recognized by the fact that the obtained signal magnitudes are different with different additive materials. The findings in this study can contribute to making a low-cost nondestructive testing device based on radar technology for structural concrete inspection.

Keywords-HB 100 radar sensor; active bandpass filter; nondestructive testing; structural inspection

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is one of the most important components used in civil engineering infrastructures. Unwanted additive materials in concrete can cause cracks over time due to dopants, corroding steel rods, or environmental factors [1-8]. Ensuring the structural integrity of concrete is very important for the longevity and safety of infrastructures [9-10]. Currently, infrared thermography, ultrasonic-echo, and radars are conventional technologies for detecting internal additive materials [1-8], with radar being widely used. In this method, when the waves are transmitted through concrete, they are partially attenuated and reflected depending on the dielectric properties of the concrete material. The comparison to the initial wave provides useful information about the materials inside the concrete [1]. On the other hand, existing commercial radar testing devices have high costs and limitations in the information of circuit design, which could be due to industrial secret policies [1-2].

The HB 100 Doppler radar sensor is widely used for motion detection thanks to its low cost and high reliability [11-12]. Recently, the HB 100 sensor was used for additional functions such as underground metal detection [13] or wooden pole inspection in forests [14]. Unfortunately, up to now, there are very few studies on the use of the sensor for detecting additive materials in concrete. This study designed a nondestructive testing device with the HB-100 radar sensor. The output of the Intermediate Frequency (IF) pin of the sensor module presents the Doppler frequency and the absorbance of the target materials. The IF signal was enhanced by a band-pass active filter before going to the microcontroller. The final measured signal on a computer can adequately distinguish the additives in the concrete.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN OF THE NONDESTRUCTIVE TESTING DEVICE

The proposed system was based on the HB100 Miniature Microwave Sensor, an X-Band Doppler transceiver module speed sensor radar commercially available by ST Engineering

Electronics Ltd, Singapore [15]. The module has the features of low current consumption and a long detection range of about 20m. An effective isotropic radiated power of 15dBm was transmitted at the frequency of 10.525GHz. Table I presents the parameters of the sensor.

TABLE I. RADAR SENSOR'S DEVICE PARAMETERS

No	Specification	Parameters
1	Working voltage	5V±0.25V
2	Operating Current	50mA max., 30mA typical
3	Emission parameters	2-16m
4	Helium emission frequency	10.525GHz
5	Frequency setting accuracy	3MHz
6	Output power	13dBm
7	Harmonic emission	<-10dBm
8	Pulse width	5uSec
9	Sensitivity	-86dBm
10	Vertical 3dB beam width	36°

Figure 1 shows the structure of the nondestructive testing device system. The microwave motion detector continuously transmits the signal within its range, and when the signal hits the target object it receives the reflected signal. The reflected signal is mixed with the transmitted and then the IF or Doppler frequency f_D signal can be given by [13]:

$$f_D = \frac{2v \cos \theta F}{c} \tag{1}$$

where v , θ , F , and C are the target speed, the angle between the trajectory of the concrete target and the radial line joining the target and the radar, the transmitted frequency, and the speed of light, respectively. The f_D is typically below 100Hz [15]. The radiation patterns of the antenna and their half-power beam width can be seen in [15]. The antenna patches were mounted on the module facing the desired detection. When measuring, the orientation of the module can be directed to get the best coverage. Fundamentally, the amplitude of the IF signals is very low and it is easy to attach electrical noise. To overcome that issue, an instrument amplifier based on a Texas Instruments LM324 was designed, as shown in Figure 2. The IF signal was amplified in the first stage by a noninverting amplifier and then by an inverting active bandpass filter [16]. The low- (f_L) and high-cutoff (f_H) frequencies were calculated to be 3.38 and 72.38Hz, using the following equations:

$$f_L = \frac{1}{2\pi R_6 C_7} \tag{2}$$

$$f_H = \frac{1}{2\pi C_5 R_7} \tag{3}$$

The amplified signal was connected to an analog pin on an Arduino board. The microcontroller has a built-in ADC that processes the signal, converts it to a digital value, and sends it to a computer via a USB cable with a serial communication protocol. The amplitude of the signal can be observed in computer software. Figure 3 shows a photo of the completed non-destructive testing device with the HB100 radar sensor. For convenient use of the device, the radar sensor was separated from the PCB by a 50cm long cable.

Fig. 1. The design of the nondestructive testing device system.

Fig. 2. Design of the active band-pass filter for the HB100 sensor.

Fig. 3. The hardware implementation of the non-destructive testing device.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the test procedure, where wooden, steel, and plastic bar objects were placed inside a hole in the concrete sample. The distance between the surface and the hole was approximately 5cm. In this experiment, the target was stationary, thus, to make HB 100 detect the Doppler effect, the radar sensor needed to move toward the target. The radar sensor was manually controlled to gradually move at a constant speed of about 0.45m/s and then touched the surface of the concrete sample. That generates a constant frequency of a certain amplitude. The amplitude levels of the reflected beat frequency were recorded at room temperature by a computer. Figure 4 also presents the data measured from the concrete sample with different additives. It can be noted, that while the frequency values were not significantly altered, the magnitude or data volume depended on the additive materials. Sensed data were further analyzed. The maximum values of the data volume in nominal units extracted from the examples in Figure 4 were 466, 468, 478, and 482 for solid concrete, wood inside the concrete, steel inside the concrete, and plastic inside the concrete, respectively. Figure 4 demonstrates that the designed device system could clearly distinguish the different materials.

Fig. 4. Obtained signals measured from solid concrete with different additive materials.

The amplitude of the received signal can be expressed as [17]:

$$A = A_0 e^{-\alpha Z} \tag{4}$$

where A_0 , α , and Z are the initial amplitude, attenuation factor, and travel distance, respectively. The value of α can be given by [17]:

$$\alpha = 2\pi F \left[\frac{\epsilon\mu}{2} \left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\epsilon\omega}\right)^2} - 1 \right) \right]^{1/2} \tag{5}$$

where μ is the magnetic permeability of the material, ϵ is the dielectric permittivity of the material, and σ is the electric conductivity.

TABLE II. MATERIALS' DIELECTRIC PERMITTIVITY

No	Tested material	Dielectric permittivity ϵ
1	Concrete	4.5
2	Wood	4.0
3	Steel	3.5
4	Plastic	3.1

Table II shows the dielectric permittivities of the tested materials [18-19]. The α in (5) strongly depends on the dielectric permittivity of the material. Therefore, (4) implies that the amplitude of the received signal is decreased with increasing dielectric permittivity. Figure 5 shows the relation between the maximum data volume of the received signal and dielectric permittivity. As can be noted, a material with higher dielectric permittivity results in a lower amplitude of the received signal, i.e. it absorbs more of the transmitted signal. That is consistent with the theoretical relationships (4) and (5). The amplitude levels in Figure 5 also confirm that the additive materials in concrete can be clearly identified. In previous studies on non-destructive radar inspection devices [1, 7, 8, 11-13], the measured data were visualized and could be exported in several aspects, such as additive materials, defects, and scanned mapping. However, these devices had a complicated structure with a special radar sensor and an elaborated signal processing system. This study used a simple design with a low-cost commercially available motion radar sensor and a popular microcontroller. Although the device needs to be further improved, integrating data analysis or visual mapping, it can be realized that the advantages of the proposed design are its low cost and simplicity.

Fig. 5. Dielectric permittivity and maximum data volume of the received signal obtained from different additive materials inside the concrete.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated an electronic device based on electromagnetic waves to inspect additive materials in structural concrete, based on the HB-100 sensor module to generate and receive the radar wave. A band-pass active filter was designed to suppress electrical noise from the received signal. The output at the IF pin of the sensor module presents the Doppler frequency and absorbance of the target materials. An Arduino microcontroller was used for signal processing and the measured values were displayed on a computer. The proposed device was used to detect additives inside a concrete sample, and the obtained signal magnitudes were different for different additive materials. This design used a low-cost commercially available motion radar sensor and a popular low-cost microcontroller. The results of this study show the feasibility of designing and implementing a low-cost nondestructive testing device based on radar technology for structural concrete inspection.

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Sustainable Green City Development Project Analysis using the Critical Path Method (CPM) and the Crashing Project Method on Time and Cost Optimization

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ABSTRACT

Due to the increase in population all over the world, the term city development has emerged using the method of sustainable green cities, which are cities designed taking into account the environmental impact to reduce the required input from energy, water, and food production. This study discusses this topic with three main objectives; the first is to analyze the project work network of the Sustainable Green City Development Project, the second is to investigate the impact of speeding up the project on network planning, and the third is to determine the cost differences before and after acceleration. The Critical Path Method (CPM) is valuable for managing complex projects if the activity durations are known. However, in reality, the projected durations may vary in the course of a project due to multiple factors, such as equipment breakdowns, human errors, and material shortages. This study used the CPM and crashing methods to determine the optimal project turnaround time using critical path optimization techniques. Analysis using CPM showed that the initial project duration was 1205 weeks but can be reduced to 1197 weeks. However, with acceleration, there is a slight difference, corresponding to a 0.67% decrease in the duration and approximately 8 weeks. The study showed that the total cost of the project work is US \$55M at the normal duration and became US \$59M after acceleration, which is a slight increase.

Keywords-Critical Path Method (CPM); crashing method; network planning; optimal duration; optimal cost

I. INTRODUCTION

Project scheduling involves determining the timeline, resources, labor, and materials required for each project activity [1]. It is important to ensure that the implementation of a project follows the schedule plan, which is achieved by selecting the most appropriate planning game. The game practice provides certainty in the completion of the project, minimizing delays and negative impacts on quality, cost, and time [2]. The optimal scheduling of a home energy system has a significant effect on its operating cost [3]. In the current competitive business landscape, completing projects quickly and cost-effectively is crucial for successful project management. Effective planning and timely completion of projects provide a significant advantage in terms of cost, time, and customer satisfaction. Consequently, there is an increasing interest in project management methods to ensure timely delivery success. Project planning is a crucial step in project management and employs various methods. Critical Path Method (CPM) is one of the most preferred methods due to its effectiveness. CPM identifies the critical path, which is the path from the beginning to the end of the project, where all

slack times are zero [4]. This method also helps to identify critical activities on the critical path, allowing for resource concentration to reduce project length. Furthermore, CPM can also identify bottlenecks in the project [5].

When it comes to real-life applications, it can be difficult to determine the exact duration of the activities of projects. Expert opinions and estimates are used to determine activity durations, but different experts may provide different estimations for the same project [6]. CPM is a valuable approach for determining the project completion time by considering the priority relationships among activities. In real-life scenarios, CPM is an effective tool for planning and managing intricate projects [7]. The project network diagram always starts with an event marking the project's beginning and concludes with an event indicating its completion [8]. A project can contain multiple paths or routes from the initial event to the final [9]. "Crashing Project" refers to the process of accelerating the period of a project [10-11], reducing its overall duration by shortening the activities while minimizing the associated costs. The goal of crashing is to expedite the project schedule without causing a significant increase in cost. This can be achieved by identifying

critical activities that are hindering the project's progress and allocating additional resources. Crashing ensures that the project is completed on time or ahead of schedule while maintaining quality standards and meeting all requirements.

This study aimed to address the issue of delayed completion time in the Sustainable Green City Development Project by effectively planning and scheduling project activities and sub-activities. To achieve this goal, CPM was used to design network planning that takes into account the priority relations between project activities. The implementation of effective network planning can provide a more organized work schedule, resulting in optimized time and cost management. The crashing method was also used to expedite the project timeline without cost increases, further ensuring that project completion occurs within the stipulated time.

II. METHODS

A. Critical Path Method (CPM)

CPM is a scheduling technique that is used to manage a series of activities that depend on each other in terms of their start and end times. These times converge eventually to arrive at the expected outcome of the project. The goal of this method is to identify the critical path that must be followed to reach the project endpoint within the given time and explore different options that may arise in case the durations of activities change [12]. To understand CPM, it is important to understand some basic concepts. A project network refers to a graphical representation of activities and their prioritized relationships within the project. Activity is any work that contributes to the completion of the project. A predecessor refers to an activity that must be completed before another, known as a successor, can begin. The Earliest Start (ES) of an activity is the earliest time it can begin once all preceding activities have been finished. The Earliest Finish (EF) is the time obtained by adding the duration of the activity to the ES of the activity. The Latest Start (LS) is calculated by subtracting the activity completion time from the Latest Finish (LF). LF is determined by adding the activity duration to LS. Slack (S) is the time available between the ES and LS or LF and EF times for an activity. The critical path refers to the sequence of activities that have no slack time [13-14]. Any delay in these critical activities will delay the overall project. Therefore, it is essential to manage the project efficiently to avoid delays in these activities [15-17].

Critical Chain Project Management (CCPM) is a TOC tool used for planning and project management. It can be used in one- and multi-project structures, where resources are used in several projects simultaneously [18-19]. Table I provides definitions of the activities and sub-activities for the Sustainable Green City Development Project, which will be planned and scheduled using CPM to optimize time and cost and minimize delays. Table I also shows the activities and sub-activities of the project. The sub-activities are given an alphabetical code, and Figure 1 shows a Gantt chart of the sub-activities. Figure 1 shows that the critical path of the project passes by the sub-activities A, D, I, J, K, and L. It can also be noted that the total project duration is 25 years, based on the

approximate timing of each of the critical sub-activities described in Figure 1.

TABLE I. ACTIVITIES AND SUB-ACTIVITIES OF THE SUSTAINABLE GREEN CITY DEVELOPMENT PROJECT

No	Activity	Sub-Activity	Code
1	Reduce carbon emissions	Investing in renewable energy sources	A
2	Supporting the tourism sector	Creating new tourism products and experiences that showcase the local culture and environment	B
3	Increase green areas	Promote local tourist attractions	C
		Planting trees in public parks	D
		Preserving natural areas	E
4	Improving public facilities and services	Developing programs to support small businesses and entrepreneurs	F
		Attracting investors from outside the region	G
5	Improving healthcare and physical fitness	Develop programs to promote healthy eating and lifestyle	H
		Providing mental health support services	I
6	Improve transportation services	Implementation of bicycle and pedestrian paths	J
		Encouraging the use of alternative means of transportation to reduce carbon emissions	K
7	Improving cultural and entertainment services	Hosting international sports events	L

Fig. 1. Gantt chart of the sustainable green city development project.

Table II shows a comparison of the normal schedule cost and duration compared to the crash, mentioning the sub-activity precedence. This Table shows that shortening the duration of an activity will cause its cost to increase. For example, shortening the duration of activity A by 2 weeks will increase the cost by \$1M. This observation applies to all the activities mentioned in Table II.

TABLE II. ANALYSIS RESULTS ACCORDING TO POSSIBLE VALUES

Activity	ES	EF	LS	LF	Slack LS-ES	On critical path
A	0	332	0	332	0	Yes
B	0	128	523	651	523	No
C	0	300	351	651	351	No
D	332	624	332	624	0	Yes
E	332	404	552	624	220	No
F	0	150	591	741	591	No
G	300	390	65	741	351	No
H	390	573	741	924	351	No
I	624	824	624	824	0	Yes
J	824	924	824	924	0	Yes
K	924	1117	924	1117	0	Yes
L	1117	1205	1117	1205	0	Yes

Table III shows the results of optimizing project time and cost. The total cost of the project based on the normal schedule

was \$55M and will last 1205 weeks. Shortening an activity by one week will increase its cost by \$0.5M. This indicates that shortening the overall project duration from 1205 to 1197 weeks will increase the overall cost of the project from \$55M to \$59M. Figure 3 shows the variation of the project cost with its duration. It can be noted that the relationship between duration and cost is a linear relationship with a negative slope. At 1205 weeks duration, the cost is \$55M. As the duration shortens, the cost increases by \$0.5M/week. Table IV shows the same results differently.

TABLE III. RESULTS OF TIME AND COST OPTIMIZATION USING CRASHING METHODS

Cycle	Activity	Time	Cost	Total Cost	Duration
0	-			55,000,000	1205
1	A	2	500,000	56,000,000	1203
2	D	2	500,000	57,000,000	1201
3	K	1	500,000	57,500,000	1200
4	L	3	500,000	59,000,000	1197

Fig. 2. The activity-on-mode network diagram of optimizing time using crashing methods.

Fig. 3. Reduction of the project's duration from 1205 to 1197 weeks with cost increasing to \$59M.

B. Optimization using the Crashing Method

This is a structured and logical approach to reduce the time required for a project [20]. The goal of this method is to optimize the duration of the project activities in a cost-efficient manner. The method involves a trade-off between time and cost, which means that a reduction in the duration of the project activities is achieved at an additional cost. This cost incurs due to the increase in work efficiency to reduce the project's overall duration. The use of the crashing method can significantly impact project delays by decreasing the time allocated to

activities on the critical path. This method applies a cost slope, which refers to the additional cost when the time required for project completion is reduced.

C. Experimental Analysis

CPM involves several steps, such as the identification of individual activities, the determination of their sequence, the organization of the network diagram, the estimation of the completion time for each activity, and the definition of the critical path [6]. Table IV provides a list of activities, their predecessors, and their expected normal and crash durations and costs, which are essential to estimate the overall duration of a project. Additionally, the Table illustrates the project's network diagram, which highlights the relationships between the project activities and their dependencies.

TABLE IV. DATA OF THE SUSTAINABLE GREEN CITY DEVELOPMENT PROJECT

Activity	Precedence	Normal		Crash	
		Time (weeks)	Cost (\$)	Time (weeks)	Cost (\$)
A	-	332	5,000,000	330	6,000,000
B	-	128	1,000,000	127	1,500,000
C	-	300	2,500,000	299	3,000,000
D	A	292	3,000,000	290	4,000,000
E	A	72	500,000	71	1,000,000
F	-	150	9,000,000	148	10,000,000
G	B, C	90	13,000,000	90	13,000,000
H	G, F	183	4,000,000	180	5,500,000
I	D, E	200	3,500,000	200	3,500,000
J	H, I	100	7,000,000	100	7,000,000
K	H, J	193	2,000,000	192	2,500,000
L	K, J	88	4,500,000	85	6,000,000

Figure 4 shows the Activity-On-Mode (AON) network diagram for the normal schedule. The figure also shows the critical path, which is A, D, I, J, K, and L. It can also be observed that the total project duration is 1205 working weeks. Table III also shows the earliest start, latest finish, earliest finish, latest start, slack, and the presence of the activities on the critical path. It can be seen that all critical activities that lie on the critical path have zero slack. Figure 4 also shows the AON network diagram for the crash schedule. The crash schedule can be shortened to 1197 weeks, but this shortening will increase the overall cost of the project.

Fig. 4. The AON network diagram of the project.

III. OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION

The process of determining the time needed to complete a project and identifying the critical path involves using the expected durations of the activities and establishing sequential relationships among them. Based on these observations, the results were presented in Table II, indicating that the duration of this particular project was estimated to be 1205 weeks, while the critical path was A, D, I, J, K, and L. So, any delay in completing any of the activities in the critical path will directly impact the overall project duration. Therefore, the project manager should focus on these critical activities to ensure the project's timely completion.

Accelerating activities in the critical path increases the total cost by US \$4M. A time shortening of 8 weeks can be obtained by adopting CPM to optimize resources and manage the critical path. This means that the project can be completed 8 weeks earlier than the expected time of 1205 weeks. The time efficiency gained by using the CPM methodology was $(1205-1197)/1197 \times 100\% = 0.67\%$. This shows that the CPM method can help project managers significantly reduce the time required to complete a project, optimize project resources, and deliver the project within the expected timeline.

A. Using Crashing Methods to Optimize Time and Cost

The crashing method was used to optimize project completion time while minimizing costs. The method involved adding extra labor, such as US \$500 per person per week, in critical activities to speed up project completion. By deploying additional labor, activities on the critical path can be completed quicker, resulting in the overall project's time and cost optimization.

B. Trade-Off Analysis (Time and Cost)

Reduction stage with maximum crashing duration:

- Cost slope = US \$0.5M/week
- Time Normal = 1205 weeks
- Crashing Time = 1197 weeks
- Total crashing = 8 weeks
- Total project duration = 1197 weeks
- Direct costs = Normal direct costs + cost slope = \$55M + (0.5M * 8) = \$59M.

IV. CONCLUSION

Effective project management is crucial for the success and future of any enterprise in modern days. Due to the high competitiveness in the business environment, the ability to complete projects within stipulated time and cost is becoming increasingly important. This study focused on the Sustainable Green City Development Project, and the results showed that CPM is an effective tool for project management. Using CPM, the critical path for the project was determined as A, D, I, J, K, and L, with a duration of 1205 weeks. The study also demonstrated the use of the crashing method to optimize the project completion time while minimizing costs. By accelerating the duration of critical activities, the project

completion time was reduced to 1197 weeks, with a total cost of US \$59M. The time efficiency gained by using CPM was 0.67%. These findings show the importance of using project management tools, such as CPM and the crashing method, to optimize project completion time, reduce costs, and ensure project success.

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Blockchain-Assisted Homomorphic Encryption Approach for Skin Lesion Diagnosis using Optimal Deep Learning Model

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ABSTRACT

Blockchain (BC) and Machine learning (ML) technologies have been investigated for potential applications in medicine with reasonable success to date. On the other hand, as accurate and early diagnosis of skin lesion classification is essential to gradually increase the survival rate of the patient, Deep-Learning (DL) and ML technologies were introduced for supporting dermatologists to overcome these challenges. This study designed a Blockchain Assisted Homomorphic Encryption Approach for Skin Lesion Diagnosis using an Optimal Deep Learning (BHESKD-ODL) model. The presented BHESKD-ODL model achieves security and proper classification of skin lesion images using BC to store the medical images of the patients to restrict access to third-party users or intruders. In addition, the BHESKD-ODL method secures the medical images using the mayfly optimization (MFO) algorithm with the Homomorphic Encryption (HE) technique. For skin lesion diagnosis, the proposed BHESKD-ODL method uses pre-processing and the Adam optimizer with a Fully Convolutional Network (FCN) based segmentation process. Furthermore, a radiomics feature extraction with a Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Network (BiRNN) model was employed for skin lesion classification. Finally, the Red Deer Optimization (RDO) algorithm was used for the optimal hyperparameter selection of the BiRNN approach. The experimental results of the BHESKD-ODL system on a benchmark skin dataset proved its promising performance in terms of different measures.

Keywords-blockchain; smart healthcare; image encryption; deep learning; skin lesion classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, innovative technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and big data have promoted innovations in healthcare worldwide [1], as they contribute to the development of smart healthcare systems that improve the experience of medical services. Smart healthcare is based on the electronic health and medical records of residents, integrated with information technologies, namely Cloud Computing (CC), IoT, big data, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and mobile communications that are used to develop different systems [2], namely humanized health management systems and convenient medical service systems. Furthermore,

Blockchain (BC) and Machine Learning (ML) technologies have affected a wide range of scientific and industrial applications. The security, traceability, decentralization, and transparency of the ML and BC technologies enable the medical sector to upgrade and optimize different aspects, such as customer file management, customer health management [3], information system management, and medical insurance management, in addition to improving the efficacy across various applications [4]. Skin cancer is the most common form of cancer in the world [5]. Awareness of new or changing skin growths or spots, especially those that look unusual, must be assessed. The physician must assess progressive change or any new lesion in its appearance (color, size, or shape) [6-8].

This study designed a Blockchain Assisted Homomorphic Encryption Approach for Skin Lesion Diagnosis using an Optimal Deep Learning (BHESKD-ODL) model. The proposed BHESKD-ODL model uses BC to store the medical images of patients to restrict access to third-party users or intruders. In addition, the BHESKD-ODL model secures the medical images using the Mayfly Optimization (MFO) algorithm with the Homomorphic Encryption (HE) technique. For skin lesion diagnosis, the presented BHESKD-ODL method uses pre-processing and the Adam optimizer with a Fully Convolutional Network (FCN)-based segmentation process. Moreover, a radiomics feature extraction with a Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Network (BiRNN) was employed for skin lesion classification. Finally, the Red Deer Optimization (RDO) algorithm was used for the optimal hyperparameter selection of the BiRNN algorithm. The BHESKD-ODL model was experimentally tested on a benchmark skin dataset.

II. RELATED WORKS

A reliable method was proposed in [9] for skin cancer diagnosis using dermoscopy images for enriching the diagnostic abilities and visual perception of medical professionals for discriminating between malignant and benign lesions. In [10], an effective version of the recently formulated opposition-based golden jackal optimizer (IGJO) was modeled. In [11], a new automated CAD system for skin lesion classifier was presented, having high accuracy and low computational complexities. In [12], a novel analysis method for unsupervised skin melanoma removal was presented. In [13], the lesion segmenting approach was modeled as a Markov decision process, solving it by training an agent for segmenting regions utilizing a deep RL method, learned in continual action space, and utilizing the deep deterministic policy gradient technique. In [14], a new hybrid ML method for the detection of melanoma was proposed. This method used traditional ML approaches, including XGBoost supervised ML, CNNs, and EfficientNet. In [15], a potential skin cancer detection method was proposed, named Fractional Student Psychology Based Optimization-based Deep Q Network (FSPBO-based DQN), in a wireless network scenario. At first, an image was given to the preprocessing stage, where a Type II fuzzy system and the cuckoo search optimized (T2FCS) method were used to eliminate the noise of images. In [16], fairness problems in Swarm Learning (SL) were inspected. SL is a fresh edge-computing related decentralized ML method that is devised for heterogeneous illnesses recognition in precision medicine. Although several models are available in the literature, most studies did not focus on hyperparameter tuning and optimal key generation process.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

In this study, a secure automated skin lesion diagnosis model was designed, named BHESKD-ODL, that uses BC to securely store medical images of patients to restrict access to third-party users or intruders. In addition, the BHESKD-ODL method applied HE with the MFO-based optimal key generation process to achieve security. For skin lesion diagnosis, the presented BHESKD-ODL method used pre-processing and the Adam optimizer with FCN-based

segmentation, radiomics feature extraction, BiRNN-based classification, and RDO-based hyperparameter tuning. Figure 1 shows the general procedure of the BHESKD-ODL approach.

Fig. 1. General procedure of the BHESKD-ODL system.

A. Blockchain (BC)

This study used Blockchain (BC) to store images of patient skin lesions to make them inaccessible to third parties, due to the higher privacy and security requirements of medical information [17]. Hyperledger Fabric was used for saving these kinds of responses before being sent back to the user. Every reply in peers is gathered by the user and can be sent to the "orderer". During this case, every transaction is well-arranged by the orderer in ascending order and then designed to block.

B. Image Encryption using the Optimal HE Technique

The HE method was used to encrypt the medical images. In the cryptography field, the term HE describes the kind of encryption capable of performing specific computable functions on cipher images. A homomorphic function used to cipher images provides a similar (after decryption) outcome as applying the function to the original unencrypted information.

Considering m_1 and m_2 as messages, c_1 and c_2 indicate the corresponding cipher images. The operation $\dot{+}$ in an additive HE generates the cipher image $c_+ \leftarrow c_1 \dot{+} c_2$ that could be decrypted to m_1+m_2 . Likewise, for \times in multiplicative HE, it provides the $c_\times \leftarrow c_1 \times c_2$ cipher image that is decrypted to $m_1 \cdot m_2$. The HE obtains c_+ and c_\times cipher images, without the knowledge of m_1 and m_2 . Traditional encryption could not calculate m_1+m_2 and $m_1 \cdot m_2$ without decrypting c_1 and c_2 at first, once the user sacrifices privacy. The MFO algorithm was used for the optimal key generation process. Mayflies (MFs) in

swarming would split into individual females and males for the MFO [18]. Male MFs are continuously vigorous, since they are superior in improvement. The parameters in the MFO are similar to those of PSO, as the location is changed based on the existing velocity $v(t)$ and positions $p_i(t)$ at a given number of iterations. Every female and male MF use (1) for updating their location. At the same time, the velocity is upgraded in different forms.

$$p_i(t+1) = p_i(t) + v_i(t+1) \quad (1)$$

In the course of cycles, male creatures in Swarming Intelligence (SI) will continue to the subjugation or exploring processes. The velocity would be adjusted based on the present fitness value $f(x)$ and the better fitness value in the historical movement (xh_i). If $(x_i) > f(xh_i)$, the velocity of male MFs' is upgraded based on the existing velocity, the separation amongst them, and the global optima position. The preceding better movement is formulated as follows:

$$v_i(t+1) = g \cdot v_i(t) + \alpha_1 e^{-\beta \gamma_p^2} [\chi_{n_i} - \chi_{i(t)}] + \alpha_2 e^{-\beta \gamma_g^2} [\chi_g - \chi_i(t)] \quad (2)$$

where g represents the parameter that exponentially reduced from the highest to the lowest amount, and α_1 , α_2 , and β denote the constants for balancing the value. The Cartesian spacing amongst organisms and their prior better option, the global best location in SI, can be represented as γ_p and γ_g . The Cartesian distance is formulated by:

$$\|x_i - x_j\| = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (x_{ik} - x_{jk})^2} \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, if $(x_i) < f(xh_i)$, the male MFs will update the speed from the existing location through an unsystematic dance factor d :

$$v_i(t+1) = g \cdot v_j(t) + d \cdot \gamma_1 \quad (4)$$

where the indiscriminate quantity in even designation and dissemination from the range [1, 1] is denoted by γ_1 . The initial mate in the MFO technique can be the best male and female MFs, the second robust male and female MFs can be the second mate, and so on. Consequently, in the i -th female MFs, if $(y_i) < f(x_i)$, it can be formulated as:

$$v_i(t+1) = g \cdot v_i(t) + \alpha_3 e^{-\beta \gamma_m^2} [x_{i(t)} - y_i(t)] \quad (5)$$

The Cartesian distance can be denoted as γ_m . If $(y_i) < f(x_i)$, the female MFs adjust the velocity until the present one runs through further dance coefficients fl , given by:

$$v_i(t) = g \cdot v_i(t) + fl \cdot \gamma_2 \quad (6)$$

In (6), γ_2 is the indiscriminate quantity in even designated and dissemination from the range [1, 1]. The offspring develops at a randomized rate from the mother, formulated by:

$$offspring1 = L \times male + (1 - L) \times female \quad (7)$$

$$offspring2 = L \times female + (1 - L) \times male \quad (8)$$

The MFO algorithm generates a fitness function for the HE technique. The maximization of the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) is considered the fitness function:

$$Fitness = \max\{PSNR\} \quad (9)$$

C. Skin Lesion Classification

The lesion classification process uses image preprocessing, optimal FCN-based segmentation, BiRNN-based classification, and RDO-based hyperparameter tuning.

1) Image Preprocessing

At the initial stage, the BHESKD-ODL method uses Gaussian Filtering (GF) for noise removal [19]. GF is linear smooth filtering, whereas the weight selected to smooth is based on the summary of the Gaussian functions. GF in the non-stop space is determined by:

$$h(m, n) = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{m^2}{2\sigma^2}} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{n^2}{2\sigma^2}} \right) \quad (10)$$

GF is an impulse response:

$$g(x) = \sqrt{\frac{a}{\pi}} e^{-ax^2} \quad (11)$$

This formula can be also expressed with Standard Deviation (SD) as a parameter:

$$g(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (12)$$

Then, the CLAHE technique was used for the contrast enhancement process. CLAHE is a kind of Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE) that deals with the over-amplification of the contrast. CLAHE works on smaller image regions, named tiles, instead of the whole image. Lastly, inpainting technology is applied for hair removal procedures in the skin region.

2) Image Segmentation

The FCN method is used to segment the skin lesion regions in dermoscopy images [20]. Every layer of the dataset in a ConvNet is a 3D array of size $h \times w \times d$, where h and w indicate the spatial dimension, and d indicates the channel or feature dimensions. The initial layer is the image with an $h \times w$ size and d color channels. ConvNet is based on translation invariance. The fundamental elements (activation, convolution, and pooling functions) operated on local input regions and were only based on relative spatial coordinates. Considering x_{ij} for the data vector at the (i, j) position in a specific layer, the data vector y_{ij} for the subsequent layers can be given by:

$$y_{ij} = f_{ks}(\{x_{si+\delta i, sj+\delta j}\}_{0 \leq \delta i, \delta j \leq k}) \quad (13)$$

where k indicates the kernel size, s represents the subsampling or stride factors, and f_{ks} defines the type of layer: a matrix multiplication for average pooling or convolution, a spatial max for max pooling, component-wise non-linearity for the activation function, etc., for other kinds of layers. This functional procedure can be preserved in composition, with kernel size and stride following the transformation rules:

$$f_{ks} \circ g_{k's'} = (f \circ g)_{k'+(k-1)s', s's'} \quad (14)$$

While a deep net calculates a non-linear function, a net with only layers of these forms computes a non-linear filter that is termed a full convolution or deep filter network. The Adam optimizer was applied for the parameter tuning of the FCN, to improve optimization and convergence behavior [21]. This

method produces smooth variation with lower memory requirements and effectual computational efficiency. Based on Adam, the bias is formulated by:

$$\theta_l = \theta_{l-1} - \frac{\alpha \hat{q}_l}{\sqrt{\hat{m}_l + \epsilon}} \quad (15)$$

where α is the step size, \hat{q}_l indicates corrected bias, \hat{m}_l refers to the bias-corrected second-moment evaluation, ϵ signifies the constant, and θ_{l-1} represents the parameter at the prior time instant ($l-1$). The corrected bias of the first-order moment was formulated by:

$$\hat{q}_l = \frac{q_l}{(1-\eta_1^l)} \quad (16)$$

$$\hat{q}_l = \eta_1 q_{l-1} + (1 - \eta_1) G_l^1 \quad (17)$$

The corrected bias of the second-order moment is:

$$\hat{m}_l = \frac{ml}{(1-\eta_2^l)} \quad (18)$$

$$\hat{m}_l = \eta_2 m_{l-1} + (1 - \eta_2) H_l^2 \quad (19)$$

$$H_l = \nabla_{\theta} loss(\theta_{l-1}) \quad (20)$$

3) Feature Extraction

At this stage, radiomic features are extracted from the dermoscopy images. The radiomic features are derived by an in-house software, using Python's scikit-learn package and PyRadiomics [22]. Shape, texture, and intensity are the 3 evaluated types of characteristics. Nineteen intensity-based features and 26 shape-based features can be extracted for every extraction setting (filter, width, contour, and bin). Nineteen distinctive settings could be permutations of 2 contours (Gold and HGG), two filters (LoG and original), bandwidth (2, 4, 8, 16), and 1450 total amount of derived radiomics imaging features.

4) Image Classification using the Optimal BiRNN Model

At this stage, the BiRNN approach was used for the classifier of skin lesion images. A bi-directional RNN is an integration of two RNNs training the network in opposite directions, one from the start to the end of the sequence, and the other from the end to the start [23]. BiRNN analyzes a future event by not limiting the learning model to historical and current. As the bi-directional state modeling has improved results over the uni-state modeling in relation learning, a bi-directional state modeling method was used where h_0^c are the backward neuron activation models $P(h_t|\delta_t, h_T, \dots, h_1)$ and \vec{h}_T are the forward neuron activation $P(h_t|\delta_t, h_0, \dots, h_{T-1})$. Then, implementing the softmax procedure, the maximum probability of the sample is discovered through the objective function. Finally, the RDO algorithm is used for the optimal hyperparameter tuning of the BiRNN model. Like other meta-heuristics, the RDO begins with a random population that is a counterpart of RD [24]. The primary population for RD is generated as follows:

$$RD = X1, X2, X3, \dots, X_{Nvar} \quad (21)$$

Next, the fitness of every individual in the population can be evaluated by:

$$Value = f(RD) = f(X1, X2, X3, \dots, X_{Nvar}) \quad (22)$$

Male RD is trying to increase the grace by roaring. A *resdlproV_i* process might fail or succeed. Particularly, male RDs are the better option. This process tries to find the neighbors of the solution, concerning the solution space. When the objective function of the neighbors is male RD, it is replaced by the previous one if it is superior to the prior male RD, and it can be formulated as follows:

$$male_{new} = \begin{cases} male_{old} + a_1(UB - LB) * a_2 + LB, & \text{if } a_3 \geq 0.5 \\ male_{old} - a_1((UB - LB) * a_2 + LB), & \text{if } a_3 < 0.5 \end{cases} \text{ is less than 0} \quad (23)$$

where *UB* and *LB* denote the upper and the lower boundaries of the problem to develop a relevant male neighborhood solution. The existing location of male RD is *male_{old}*, and its following location is *male_{new}*. Based on randomization, *a1*, *a2*, and *a3* are the 3 phases of the roaring procedure, which is a uniform distribution of a random number within [0,1]. *N_c* can be evaluated using:

$$N_c = round(\gamma \cdot N_{male}) \quad (24)$$

where *N_c* indicates the number of male commanders in the population, γ is a randomly generated value within [0,1], and *N_{male}* indicates the number of overall males. Note that γ represents the initial value of the model which ranges from 0 to 1. The number of stags can be evaluated using:

$$N_s = N_{male} - N_c \quad (25)$$

The fighting strategy can be formulated using:

$$new1 = \frac{C+S}{2} + b_1((UB - LB) * b_2 + LB) \quad (26)$$

$$new2 = \frac{C+S}{2} - b_1((UB - LB) * b_2 + LB) \quad (27)$$

where *new₁* and *new₂* indicate the new solutions proposed by the fighting strategy, *C* and *S* denote the stags and commanders, respectively, *UB* and *LB* indicate the upper and lower boundaries of the problem, and similarly, *b₁* and *b₂* indicate the upper and lower boundaries of the search space, with uniformly distributed number ranges from 0 to 1. Considering the four options *C*, *S*, *new₁*, and *new₂*, only the finest one regarding the OF is selected.

Hinds were used amongst commanders to form a group of harems as follows:

$$V_n = v_n - \max v_i \quad (28)$$

where *V_n* is the normalized value of *n*-th commander's power (VF), and *v_n* is the power of the *n*-th commander (OF). The normalized power of the commander is calculated by:

$$P_n = \left| \frac{v_n}{\sum_{i=1}^n v_i} \right| \quad (29)$$

and the number of hinds of the harem is given by:

$$N.harem_n = round(P_n \cdot N_{hind}) \quad (30)$$

where *N_{hind}* is the overall amount of hinds. The fitness selection is an essential factor in the RDO algorithm. Solution encoding was used to assess the aptitude (goodness) of the candidate solution. The accuracy value was the core condition used to design a fitness function:

$$Fitness = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (31)$$

where TP and FP are the true and false positive values, respectively.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The skin lesion classification of the BHESKD-ODL system was tested using the ISIC database [25]. The BHESKD-ODL approach was simulated using Python 3.6.5 and an i5-8600K/16GB/GeForce 1050Ti 4GB PC. Figure 2 shows some examples of the visualization of images of skin lesions. The first row shows the original images, the second row demonstrates the encrypted images, the third row illustrates the decrypted images, the fourth row exhibits the pre-processing images, and the fifth row defines the segmented images.

Fig. 2. (a) Original images, (b) encrypted images, (c) decrypted images, (d) preprocessed images, (e) segmented images.

Table I shows the encryption results of the BHESKD-ODL with other methods, in terms of MSE and PSNR. The results show that the BHESKD-ODL model achieved excellent performance with maximal PSNR and minimal MSE. Based on MSE, the BHESKD-ODL model reached 0.0908, while the HOCE-ECC, GO-ECC, PSO-ECC, and CS-ECC models had increased MSEs.

TABLE I. MSE AND PSNR RESULTS OF BHESKD-ODL AND OTHER APPROACHES

Methods	MSE	PSNR
BHESKD-ODL	0.0908	58.6095
HOCE-ECC	0.1190	57.3800
GO-ECC	0.1340	56.8600
PSO-ECC	1.1450	47.5400
CS-ECC	1.2780	47.0700

Table II shows an overall comparison analysis of the BHESKD-ODL method with recent DL approaches [26-27]. The results show that BHESKD-ODL reached increased performance over the other models. These results demonstrate that the BHESKD-ODL model showed secure skin lesion classification performance.

TABLE II. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF BHESKD-ODL WITH RECENT DL METHODS

Methods	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
BHESKD-ODL	99.54	99.61	99.92
Inception-V3	85.70	86.46	86.06
VGGNet	78.60	79.60	79.68
AlexNet-VGGNet	79.90	80.35	80.47
U-Net	80.00	79.43	78.92
Resnet50	83.60	84.89	85.14
Resnet50-Inception	84.10	84.25	84.09

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the design of an automated and secure skin lesion diagnosis model, named BHESKD-ODL. The BHESKD-ODL model uses blockchain technology to securely store patient medical images and restrict access to third-party users or intruders. Additionally, the BHESKD-ODL method applies homomorphic encryption with a Mayfly optimization-based key generation process to achieve security. For skin lesion diagnosis, the presented BHESKD-ODL model uses preprocessing and the Adam optimizer with FCN-based segmentation, radiomics feature extraction, BiRNN-based classification, and RDO-based hyperparameter tuning. The experimental evaluation of the BHESKD-ODL method used a benchmark skin dataset. A detailed comparison study showed the promising performance of the BHESKD-ODL model concerning distinct measures. In the future, hybrid metaheuristic algorithms can be employed to improve the performance of the BHESKD-ODL model.

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Factory Test of a TP-100 Lithium-Ion Vision Battery System for Possible Implementation in Soweto, Johannesburg, South Africa

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ABSTRACT

Until recently, lead-acid batteries were the go-to source for storing energy for UPS/Inverter applications. The most common types of batteries used in wind applications are Valve-Regulated Lead-Acid batteries (VLRAs). But, lead-acid batteries have drawbacks that make them risky and expensive to use in wind turbine applications. They are the element that is most likely to fail at the moment when they are most needed. It is hard enough to deploy and manage lead-acid batteries traditionally. But when VLRAs are used in remote facilities, there are some problems that increase the effort and the cost of using them. Currently, the Soweto Small Wind Turbine is incorporated with the Vertiv (Inverter) and VRLA battery type. TP 100 Vision lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO₄) batteries offer substantial advantages. This battery system is ideal for both UPS/Inverters and energy storage systems, offering excellent compatibility and a secure, durable lifespan. Factory testing was carried out on the installation and testing of a TP 100 Vision battery to a Vertiv-type UPS at a South African company. A variable resistive load bank was added to the UPS output in order to test and evaluate the outcome. This paper presents the factory testing results and proposes the implementation of the TP100 Vision battery to a 500W Small Wind Turbine (SWT) in Soweto, Johannesburg, South Africa.

Keywords-TP 100 Vision battery; factory test; Soweto SWT implementation

I. INTRODUCTION

In South Africa, the main energy source is electricity produced by fossil fuels such as oil and coal. Reliance on these energy sources continues to severely limit the national electricity production. The total wind power potential of South Africa is estimated to be 6,7000GW and is found to be competitive with the solar potential [1]. Moreover, the use of fossil fuels in the generation of electricity contributes significantly to Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions, which contribute to climate change [2, 3]. According to [4], utilizing renewable energy as an alternative energy source will reduce environmental problems, essentially GHG emissions and air pollution. Storage of energy is an important factor in wind turbine use. These batteries store the generated energy from the

turbine, and the stored energy is sent through an electronic regulator to the inverter for output supply. A battery storage system is regarded as an indispensable component in numerous applications. There are two battery types suitable for wind turbine application, Valve-Regulated Lead-Acid (VRLA) and Lithium-Ion batteries (Table I).

The utilization of sustainable batteries for energy storage is highly recommended in order to safeguard the environment from impeding emissions [5]. Additionally, the investigation conducted in [6] presents evidence that lithium batteries utilizing LiFePO₄ technology possess eco-friendly characteristics and are capable of being entirely recycled. The Li-Ion battery technology is relatively recent in its inception [7-11]. Lithium ion batteries have been gaining increasing

recognition as a reliable choice for back-up power systems and UPSs/Inverters, primarily due to their exceptional properties such as heightened safety measures and greater energy densities both in gravimetric and volumetric terms. Therefore, a preliminary review on recent developments of Li-Ion batteries acting as battery storage systems on wind turbine application will be discussed below. Two Li-Ion batteries with 400kW output power and 744kWh energy capacity with an 800kW wind turbine, connected to the grid, near in Regina, Saskatchewan, North America were studied in [12]. The wind-battery system's data were continuously monitored to evaluate the performance and to assess the reliability and durability of the storage system. The aim was to quantify the battery effectiveness and assessing peak energy dispatching times. The data showed that there was 65% ramp rate reduction and 400kW dispatching for 90 minutes 3 times per day.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF VRLA AND LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES

VRLA	Lithium-Ion Vision
Unreliable performance	Reliable performance
Short life	Long life
Requires huge area for installation	Can fit in any space - compact space
They are heavy and difficult to move	They can be easily accessed and are not heavy to move
Temperature sensitive	Accommodates higher temperature
Slow recharge	Fast recharge

According to the U.S. Department of Energy's Global Energy Storage Database, there were 102 Li-Ion battery installations worldwide in operation or in development in March 2014, with an estimated combined storage of more than 175MWh [13]. Authors in [14] proposed the use of Li-Ion batteries as a backup power of the pitch system of wind turbines. The battery management system was designed based on DSP28335. By the use of CAN communication and voltage current Hall sensors, the system realized the collection of cell voltage, total voltage, and charge and discharge currents parameters of the batteries. Ampere-time integration and other methods were used to estimate the battery State of Charge (SOC) when they charged or discharged. During the charging and discharging period, the data of the ICA were recorded. Finally, the function of battery management system was verified by experiments.

Uninterruptible power supply (UPS) systems are of significant importance as contingency and emergency power solutions for vital applications, including but not limited to computers, medical and life support systems, communication systems, office equipment, hospital instrumentation, industrial controls, and integrated data centers. In instances of failure, UPS systems offer dependable, unwavering voltage and frequency power [15].

In this article, the implementation of the TP100 Vision Lithium Battery system integrated to a Vertiv type UPS is studied. The battery system was optimally implemented and tested at one of the companies in Johannesburg, South Africa. The tests results which were performed can greatly benefit the consideration of integrating the TP-100 Vision battery system to a wind turbine installation in Soweto.

II. PRODUCT OVERVIEW AND CHOSEN METHODOLOGY

A. TP100 Vision Lithium Battery

Figure 1 depicts a 50Ah - TP100 Vision Lithium battery module. Table II shows the features of a Vision Lithium battery. The module has BMU units that monitor voltage and temperature to control temperature and balance battery cells, improving efficiency and cycle life. Moreover, the module is filled inside with sheet metal shell for safety and reliability also designed for stable and secure battery cluster integration.

Fig. 1. TP100 51.2 Vdc at 50Ah Vision Li-Ion battery module.

TABLE II. 50Ah – VISION LI-ION BATTERY FEATURES

Feature	Value
Voltage and block capacity	51.2Vdc at 50Ah
Cell type	Lithium ion Phosphate (Life PO ₄)
Cell dimensions	130 × 36.5 × 162mm
Weight	1.42kg
Nominal cell voltage	3.2V/cell
Minimum cell voltage	2.8V/cell
Max cell voltage	3.65V/cell
Operating Temperature	0 – 45°C

B. Cabinet Battery Monitoring System (CBMS)

Figure 2 shows an overview of the CBMS. The CBMS cabinet has three levels of architecture, namely battery current detection, alarms and protection, and data analysis and communication. The BMS cabinet includes the control switch circuit, the main circuit breaker, a detection circuit, power supply, processing circuit, starting circuit, chassis, and wiring. Moreover, it manages the state and protects against overcharging and short circuits.

Fig. 2. CBMS view.

Fig. 3. GBMS view.

Fig. 4. 50Ah – BMS cabinet with GBMS, CBMS, and battery module.

Fig. 5. The followed methodology.

Figure 3 depicts an overview of the GBMS, which contains the lithium battery with an integrated display. It is responsible for collecting and processing data from the CBMS. The Group Battery Manage System (GBMS) displays the CBMS status in real-time at control cabinet level. It works with UPS/Inverter, using multiple connections to maintain system safety and reliability. Figure 4 shows a complete setup of the BMS Cabinet, with CBMS, GBMS and integrated Battery Module. The block diagram of the followed methodology can be seen in Figure 5.

C. Setup, Installation, and Evaluation

A BMS cabinet packed with 10x50Ah Vision battery power modules was connected and configured to a Vertiv type UPS. Figure 5 shows the setup and operation with 45kW dummy load installed, but with only 27kW applied to the output of the UPS. Discharge test was performed to test the Vision batteries with a stop watch timer set on. GBMS was used to monitor every battery module and temperature within the BMS cabinet as shown in Figure 6. Figures 7-11 show the GBMS view during testing in Johannesburg.

Vision Lithium battery Setup
160 kVA Vertiv UPS
Dummy load to Output of the 160KVA UPS

Fig. 6. Setup and operation of UPS and the vision battery system.

Fig. 7. GBMS monitoring system during testing (1).

Fig. 8. GBMS monitoring system during testing (2).

Fig. 9. GBMS monitoring system during testing (3).

Fig. 10. GBMS monitoring system during testing (4).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With 45kW load installed and only 27kW applied to the UPS output, during battery discharge, the results showed that the Vision Lithium battery system was reliable as a storage system. Figures 11-16 depict the readings from the UPS system.

Fig. 11. Battery report from the UPS.

Fig. 12. Bypass report from the UPS.

Fig. 13. Input report from the UPS.

Fig. 14. Input report from the UPS (2).

Fig. 15. Output report from the UPS.

All the mentioned parameter values were validated by physical measurements with calibrated current-meter, voltmeter, and frequency meter on the terminal points of the UPS. The GBMS proved to be reliable as it was accurately monitoring all vision battery modules and temperature within the BMS cabinet. Validation was done by connecting the BMS

monitoring system software using RJ45 cables to the LAN point of the CBMS and the values were compared with what was shown on the GBMS screen.

Fig. 16. Output report from the UPS (2).

III. CONCLUSIONS

The objectives from this research was to propose a Lithium-Ion battery product which was compatible to a Vertiv UPS/Inverter type, then integrate the two and evaluate the performance during charge and discharge, and also to assess the reliability and durability of the system. With the wind turbine currently incorporated with a Vertiv Inverter and a VRLA battery type system, there were certain drawbacks experienced and observed during operation similar to those mentioned in Table I.

The performance from the data observed in this research clearly showed why Lithium-Ion batteries are the optimum storing energy source for wind turbine applications. Over a 10-year period, the Lithium-Ion batteries provide significant TCO savings without the inconvenience and replacement cost of the lead-acid batteries. The longer lifespan and reduced maintenance needs of Lithium-Ion batteries produce a significant return on investment in less than five years. Lithium-Ion battery smaller size and reduced weight provide better flexibility for use in remote facilities and their superior performance can also help to ensure uptime and continuous operations for wind turbine projects. The combined advantages in cost-effectiveness, performance, and safety worth the initial investment, as Lithium-Ion batteries provide dependable long-term service.

The TP-100 Vision Lithium-Ion battery will be integrated to a 500W (7-rotor-blade) prototype with NACA-4412 blade design wind turbine in an original system in Soweto, Johannesburg. Based on the results observed during this research, the TP-100 Vision Lithium-Ion battery system proved to be feasible for a wind turbine system implementation in Soweto.

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Adaptive Particle Grey Wolf Optimizer with Deep Learning-based Sentiment Analysis on Online Product Reviews

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ABSTRACT

The increasing use of e-commerce websites and social networks is continually generating an immense amount of data in various forms, such as text, images or sounds, videos, etc. Sentiment analysis (SA) in online product reviews is a method of identifying the overall sentiment of customers about a specific product or service. This study used Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to identify and extract opinions and emotions expressed in text. Online reviews are often written in informal language, slang, and dialects, making it difficult for ML models to accurately classify sentiments. In addition, the use of misspelled words or incorrect grammar can further complicate the analysis. The recent developments of Deep Learning (DL) models can be used for the accurate classification of sentiments. This paper presents an Adaptive Particle Grey Wolf Optimizer with Deep Learning Based Sentiment Analysis (APGWO-DLSA) method to accurately classify sentiments in product reviews. Initially, data pre-processing was performed to improve the quality of the product reviews using the word2vec embedding process. For sentiment classification, the proposed method used a Deep Belief Network (DBN) model. Finally, the hyperparameter tuning of the DBN was performed using the APGWO algorithm. An extensive experimental analysis demonstrated the improved results of APGWO-DLSA over other methods, showing a maximum accuracy of 94.77% and 85.31% on the Cell Phones And Accessories (CPAA) and Amazon Products (AP) datasets.

Keywords-sentiment analysis; online product reviews; machine learning; deep learning; natural language processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Sentiment Analysis (SA) uses Machine Learning (ML) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods to extract and identify subjective data from text [1]. It is useful to understand the sentiments of product reviews since they allow companies to know the overall satisfaction of users [2]. SA regulates the insolence of a writer or a speaker regarding the contextual polarity, a specific topic, or some particular event, discussion, etc. The indispensable task of SA is to identify the polarity of the text at a document or sentence level [3]. The rise in Internet use has enabled all users to share their views using various platforms [4]. SA assists to examine such opinionated data and deriving certain significant insights which could be helpful for others to make decisions [5]. Social networking sites generate various kinds of data such as sports, products, movies, healthcare, hotel, and news and articles reviews. Many SA algorithms have been proposed, using computational linguistic

methods or ML [6], such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Naive Bayes (NB), and Maximum Entropy [7]. ML methods show much better efficiency than computational linguistic methods. As Deep Learning (DL) presents notable results for a variety of NLP problems, it has attracted the interest of researchers [8], and several DL methods have been used, such as DCNN, CNN, deep Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM), Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), etc. [9]. However, reviews or sentences stating various aspects related to complicated sentiments are not treated very well by these methods. Similarly, complete SA evaluation using ML has not offered efficient training time and better accuracy [10].

Several methods have been proposed to conduct SA using DL, and the best method depends on the specific needs of the application. Although several approaches have been proposed for sentiment classification, there is still a need to improve their performance. Due to the continuous expansion of the DL models, the parameter count increases, leading to overfitting of

the model. As the manual selection of hyperparameters is a laborious task, it is useful to use evolution algorithms. This study developed an Adaptive Particle Grey Wolf Optimizer with DL-driven SA (APGWO-DLSA) model to accurately classify sentiments on online product reviews. For sentiment classification, the proposed APGWO-DLSA model used a Deep Belief Network (DBN). The hyperparameter tuning of the DBN was performed using the APGWO approach. A wide range of simulations was carried out to demonstrate the improved performance of the APGWO-DLSA model.

II. RELATED WORKS

In [11], a novel word representative method was presented, that incorporated the contribution of a sentiment dataset into the standard TF-IDF method and produced weighted word vectors. This weighted word vector can be input to bi-directional LSTM (BLSTM) to efficiently capture contextual datasets. The sentiment tendency of a comment can be gained using FFNN classifiers. In a similar condition, the SA approach was compared to NB, CNN, LSTM, and RNN SA methods. In [12], a Graph Convolution Network was presented with an External Knowledge model (EK-GCN). In [13], a particular order of pre-processing stages was presented to enrich the SA performance of an ANN, since typically, the weights of the ANN are arbitrarily initialized (R-ANN) and may not provide a favorable result. In [14], a new cognitive computing method used big data analysis tools for SA and pre-processing to eliminate unnecessary words. In [15], the performance of companies was investigated using DL and ML, showing how AI can improve business procedures and results using SA. This study examined all aspects of AI in the business domain with its benefits in enhancing business performance. In [16], DL was used to analyze the sentiments of pets.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

This study presents the APGWO-DLSA method for sentiment classification on online product reviews. The APGWO-DLSA method includes data preprocessing, word2vec word embedding, DBN classification, and APGWO-based parameter tuning. Figure 1 illustrates the entire workflow of the APGWO-DLSA method.

A. Data Preprocessing

Initially, data pre-processing was performed to improve the importance of product reviews. Data analysis requires data pre-processing to eliminate redundancies and improve the learning method of the classification model and accuracy [17]. Redundant data represent any information that contributes minimal or none to predicting a targeted class, but it increases the feature vector size and presents redundant computation complexity. Subsequently, the accuracy of a classifier model is degraded if improper or no pre-processing is performed before encoding. This study used Python's NLP toolkit to preprocess the data. At first, the text was transformed into lowercase, and then punctuation, links, and HTML tags were discarded. Then, lemmatization and stemming approaches were implemented to clean the stopwords, and finally, the text was detached.

- Change to lowercase: the text was converted to lowercase. The model considers low- and upper-case words as distinct,

influencing the classification performance and the training process.

- Removal of punctuation, URL links, numbers, and tags: They do not contribute to the classifier accuracy since they provide no further meaning for the learning model and increase feature space. Thus, eliminating them aids in decreasing the feature space.
- Lemmatization and stemming: The objective of this step is to minimize inflectional forms and occasionally derivative relevant forms of the word to the typical baseline.
- Removal of stopwords: Stopwords are often used words that provide no valuable data.

Fig. 1. Working process of the APGWO-DLSA method.

B. Word Embedding

The word2vec model was used for the word embedding process. Word2vec is a popular word embedding algorithm that maps word types that have the same meaning and are closer to each other [18]. This method uses 2 approaches; The former is the skip-gram approach that accepts the center word as input, transfers it to the embedded layer, and later predicts the context word in a small dataset. The other approach is the Continuous BoW (CBOW) approach, which uses contextual words as input, transfers them to the embedding layer, and forecasts the center or the original word. CBOW works very fast and offers a good representation of the most common word.

C. Sentiment Classification

The APGWO-DLSA used the DBN model to classify sentiments. DBN uses the structure blocks of RBM and several RBM approaches [19]. RBM with a single hidden layer may not be effective for extracting features from data. The feature learned and then trained in an RBM network is used as input to distinct RBM networks. Therefore, the last RBM network learns features of the whole trained method and extracts the features from the input data. Back-Propagation (BP) is frequently used to train a typical ANN with a huge number of

model parameters. This can be achieved more efficiently using the pre-training method. The pre-training method in a DBN is a procedure of greedy layer-wise and alternative sampling. After the unsupervised pre-processing from the greedy layer-wise procedure, $h^k(x)$ refers to the representation of abstracts x in the k layer. To achieve optimum distinctive performance, the labeled data were used to correct the parameter space W . This was developed by including a final layer of variables prepared by the chosen label samples in the trained database. This optimizer method is signified by the subsequent equation:

$$f(h^K(X), Y) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^c T(h^K(x_i^j) \times y_i^j) \quad (1)$$

where T is the loss function. The squared error function has been generally exploited in BP, and the loss function was:

$$r = h^K(x_i^j) \times y_i^j \quad (2)$$

D. Hyperparameter Tuning

APGWO is considered a hyperparameter optimizer of the DBN model. Eberhart and Kennedy presented a PSO model on the herd prey hunting approach from the environment, where all the animals in a pack are aware of their position relative to the food and the position adjacent to it [20]. This study proposed a PSO technique to solve optimization problems. The two basic features of PSO are the present element position x and the velocity v . Simultaneously, the Fitness Function (FF) computes the fitness values for all parts. At the same time as the departure, the position of all the elements is stated at random. Every feature is influenced by two position parameters: $pBest$ and $gBest$. The PSO element navigates the problem space with subsequent attributes that are present. Afterward, all steps, the velocity, and the position of all components can be defined by the following equations:

$$v_k^{t+1} = w * v_k^t + c_1 * rand * (pbest_k^t - x_k^t) + c_2 * rand * (gBest - x_k^t) \quad (3)$$

$$x_k^{t+1} = x_k^t + v_k^t \quad (4)$$

The values of c_1 and c_2 are generally stated as constants in PSO for balancing the exploration phase, most probably to $c_1=c_2=1$ or $c_1=c_2=2$. During all the iterations, the equation is used for changing the acceleration coefficients. Equations (5) and (6) define these novel coefficients:

$$c_1^t = 1.2 - \frac{f(x_k^t)}{f(gBest)} \quad (5)$$

$$c_2^t = 0.5 + \frac{f(x_k^t)}{f(gBest)} \quad (6)$$

where t is the iteration, k is the coefficient, and f is the global optimum fitness of swarms. The values 0.5 and 1.2 are chosen by empirical analysis. The instance of the inertia equation is:

$$w_t = (maxIter - t) * \frac{wMax - wMin}{maxIter} + wMin \quad (7)$$

The sigmoid function is:

$$v'_{ij}(r) = sig(v_{ij}(r)) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-v_{ij}(r)}} \quad (8)$$

The development of the particle's positions is determined by:

$$x_{ij}(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } r_{ij} < sig(v_{ij}(t+1)) \\ 0_t & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where the ij parameter is a value from 0 to 1. During the PSO execution, some GWO iteration rounds reproduce the possibility of mutations that resolve the result in hybrid variation. The possibility of mutations was fixed at 0.1. The internal round can be only activated sometimes, as these values were smaller to make sure that the solution quality was unaffected. The primary and final weights can be represented by w_{max} and w_{min} , and this study used fixed values of 0.9 and 0.2, respectively. The purpose for reducing the FF is:

$$\text{Minimize } \alpha \times E_t + (1 - \alpha) \times \frac{S}{L} \quad (10)$$

where E_t signifies the validation set rate of errors, $\alpha=0.9$, and S and L represent the count of the selected features and the entire count of features, respectively. An effort is developed to concurrently optimize this FF and decrease the count of chosen features to improve validation accuracy. The optimization focuses on improving validation accuracy once the α value was higher. The fitness value can be computed by the APGWO algorithm by:

$$\text{Fitness} = \max(P) \quad (11)$$

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (12)$$

where TP and FP signify the true and false positives.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The APGWO-DLSA model was developed and executed using Python 3.6.5 on an i5-8600K/16GB RAM/GeForce 1050Ti 4GB PC. The SA effectiveness of the APGWO-DLSA method was examined on two datasets: Cell Phones And Accessories (CPAA) and Amazon Products (AP), as shown in Table I. Figure 2 shows the confusion matrix created by the APGWO-DLSA model on the two datasets. The results showed that the APGWO-DLSA model accurately determined two kinds of sentiments. For instance, with 70% TRS in the CPAA dataset, the APGWO-DLSA model recognized 61410 positive samples and 7256 negatives. Meanwhile, with 30% TSS in the CPAA dataset, the APGWO-DLSA model recognized 26327 positive samples and 3120 negatives. Eventually, with 70% TRS in the AP dataset, the APGWO-DLSA model recognized 9189 positive samples and 361 negatives. Finally, with 30% TSS in the AP dataset, the APGWO-DLSA method recognized 3936 positive samples and 169 negatives.

TABLE I. DATASET DETAILS

Class	No. of instances	
	CPAA	AP
Positive	88516	13251
Negative	11484	749
Total	100000	14000

Table II shows the SA results of the APGWO-DLSA method on the CPAA dataset, demonstrating that it distinguished positive and negative data instances. With 70% TRS, the APGWO-DLSA model achieved average $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_t$, F_{score} , and MCC of 94.77%, 95.75%, 94.77%,

95.25%, and 90.52%, respectively. Additionally, with 30% TRS, the APGWO-DLSA method achieved average $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_l$, F_{score} , and MCC of 94.65%, 96.20%, 94.65%, 95.41%, and 90.84%, respectively.

achieved average $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_l$, F_{score} , and MCC of 85.31%, 92.26%, 85.31%, 88.43%, and 77.26%, respectively. Figure 3 displays the accuracy and loss curves examination of the APGWO-DLSA method on the CCAA and AP datasets.

Fig. 2. Confusion matrices: (a-b) CCAA dataset on TRS/TSS of 70:30; (c-d) AP dataset on TRS/TSS of 70:30.

TABLE II. SA RESULTS OF THE APGWO-DLSA MODEL ON THE CCAA DATASET

Class	$Accuracy_{bal}$	$Prec_n$	$Reca_l$	F_{score}	MCC
Training Phase (70%)					
Positive	99.08	98.77	99.08	98.93	90.52
Negative	90.46	92.73	90.46	91.58	90.52
Average	94.77	95.75	94.77	95.25	90.52
Testing Phase (30%)					
Positive	99.21	98.71	99.21	98.96	90.84
Negative	90.10	93.69	90.10	91.86	90.84
Average	94.65	96.20	94.65	95.41	90.84

TABLE III. SA RESULTS OF THE APGWO-DLSA MODEL ON THE AP DATASET

Class	$Accuracy_{bal}$	$Prec_n$	$Reca_l$	F_{score}	MCC
Training Phase (70%)					
Positive	98.93	98.38	98.93	98.66	73.06
Negative	70.51	78.48	70.51	74.28	73.06
Average	84.72	88.43	84.72	86.47	73.06
Testing Phase (30%)					
Positive	99.32	98.30	99.32	98.81	77.26
Negative	71.31	86.22	71.31	78.06	77.26
Average	85.31	92.26	85.31	88.43	77.26

Table III shows the overall SA results of the APGWO-DLSA method on the AP dataset, demonstrating that the model distinguished positive and negative samples proficiently. For example, with 70% TRS, the APGWO-DLSA method achieved average $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_l$, F_{score} , and MCC of 84.72%, 88.43%, 84.72%, 86.47%, and 73.06%, respectively. Furthermore, with 30% of TSS, the APGWO-DLSA model

Fig. 3. Accuracy and loss (a-b) on the CCAA dataset, (c-d) on the AP dataset.

Table IV shows the comparative SA results of the APGWO-DLSA with existing models in the CCAA dataset [21], demonstrating its superior performance. The APGWO-DLSA model reached the highest $accu_y$ of 94.77%, while the XGBoost, RF, SVM, gradient boosting, NB, and DL models reached 91.60%, 91.38%, 90.16%, 89.74%, 91.01%, and 90.85%, respectively. Simultaneously, the APGWO-DLSA model had a higher F_{score} of 95.25%, while the XGBoost, RF, SVM, gradient boosting, NB, and DL achieved 91.89%, 91.79%, 89.81%, 90.49%, 91.64%, and 89.88%, respectively.

TABLE IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF APGWO-DLSA WITH OTHER MODELS ON THE CCAA DATASET

Methods	$Accuracy$	$F-Score$
APGWO-DLSA	94.77	95.25
XG Boost	91.60	91.89
Random Forest	91.38	91.79
SVM	90.16	89.81
Gradient Boosting	89.74	90.49
Naïve Bayes	91.01	91.64
DL Model	90.85	89.88

Table V compares the SA results of the APGWO-DLSA with existing models on the AP dataset. The results show that the APGWO-DLSA model achieved the best performance. The APGWO-DLSA model achieved the highest $accu_y$ of 85.31%, while the XGBoost, RF, SVM, gradient boosting, NB, and DL models achieved 80.63%, 83.23%, 83.02%, 81.49%, 81.38%, and 80.93%, respectively. Similarly, it can be noticed that the APGWO-DLSA model reached the highest F_{score} of 88.43%, while the XGBoost, RF, SVM, gradient boosting, NB, and DL

methods achieved 82.24%, 83.42%, 84.25%, 83.94%, 84.80%, and 84.36%, respectively. These results highlight the enhanced SA results of the proposed APGWO-DLSA method

TABLE V. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF APGWO-DLSA WITH OTHER MODELS ON THE AP DATASET

Methods	Accuracy	F-Score
APGWO-DLSA	85.31	88.43
XG Boost	80.63	82.24
Random Forest	83.23	83.42
SVM	83.02	84.25
Gradient Boosting	81.49	83.94
Naïve Bayes	81.38	84.80
DL Model	80.93	84.36

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the APGWO-DLSA method for accurate sentiment classification in online product reviews. This model invokes data preprocessing with word2vec word embedding process, uses the DBN model for sentiment classification, and selects the hyperparameters of the DBN model. The proposed model was tested in two product review datasets and its were compared with the results of other methods. The comparative analysis results showed that APGWO-DLSA achieved optimum accuracy of 94.77% and 85.31% on the CPAA and AP datasets, respectively. In the future, an advanced DL classification model can be developed to further improve the APGWO-DLSA model.

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Design and Testing of a Radiofrequency Ellipsoidal Helmholtz Coil in Contrast with a Circular Pair for Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

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ABSTRACT

The design and testing of a Helmholtz prototype probe with a relatively homogeneous radiofrequency field that can be used for MRI are presented in this paper. It consists of two coaxial separately tuned ellipsoidal rings of wire in a symmetric arrangement. The developed ellipsoidal structure is tested experimentally in free space and is compared with the results obtained with an equivalent circular standard Helmholtz coil. Complete electrical modeling of the coils taking into account all couplings (inductive and capacitive) is studied. The proposed ellipsoidal Helmholtz coil provides better performance in terms of field homogeneity, efficiency, and quality factor. The width of the lobe at 10% for the ellipsoidal coil is 20% bigger. Moreover, a significant improvement in the quality factor is observed in free space. Also, the efficiency is increased by 37%. Finally, the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) of the ellipsoidal coil is higher than that of the circular coil.

Keywords-MRI; NMR; radio frequency; RF coil; ellipsoidal configuration; B₁ homogeneity

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is a non-invasive imaging technique that does not use harmful radiation, unlike other imaging modalities. MRI is based on the phenomenon of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), a phenomenon independently discovered by two research teams [1, 2]. NMR exploits the resonant behavior exhibited by certain materials when placed in a strong magnetic field. These materials selectively absorb electromagnetic energy at a frequency specific to their constituent cores and which varies with the strength of the externally applied static magnetic field. The absorption of electromagnetic energy positions moves the nuclei of the materials in a state of resonance, after which they return to their original state of thermodynamic equilibrium through a process known as relaxation with release of energy. In addition, there are a host of tissue-specific properties that interact with applied magnetic fields, the two most important of which are relaxation longitudinal (spin-lattice) and transverse relaxation mechanisms (spin-lattice). The use of signal coding techniques based on a spatial arrangement of magnetic field gradients allows obtaining information on the internal structure of biological samples. This information carried by the energy emitted by biological tissues, constitutes the basis of the MRI imaging modality [3-5].

In MRI, the need to make coils with the most uniform radiofrequency (RF) field B_1 is necessary, hence the use of volume RF coils. Among these volume coils, there are the "birdcage" type coils, with several types of operation and structures. They give good results, but they still have some drawbacks and constraints related to their construction. Indeed, the realization of this type of coils becomes complex because the most homogeneous RF field is obtained with a high number of bars, moreover, the excessive metal mass constituting the base rings of the coils loops out to be a seat of Foucault induced currents and causes disturbances during the switching of the gradients and visible trailing phenomena on the images. Moreover, the homogeneity of the B_1 field and the quality factor depend on the symmetry of the coil, hence the need for more precision at the manufacturing level [6-8].

In the case of simpler coils, such as Helmholtz coils which generate a field B_1 along the axis of the coil, the improvement in the homogeneity of the field is clearly greater. Thus, unlike "birdcage" type coils, the optimization of the structure in the absence of periodicity is very significant [7-9].

The main objective of this paper is the design and testing of circular and ellipsoidal Helmholtz coils that can produce a relatively, high electromagnetic field homogeneity to be used for NMR applications.

II. CALCULATION OF THE B₁ MAGNETIC FIELD

This section is devoted to the calculation of the field produced by the circular and ellipsoidal structures. The objective is to obtain an RF induction B₁ of better homogeneity so as to produce a homogeneous field of order 2 in the optimum case. The structure has a reduced dimension compared to the wavelength, so it is possible to apply the law of Biot-Savart and the principle of superposition to obtain the total field [9] on their axis [10]. The magnetic field of a circular loop of N turns whose plane of the coil is centered at z=+R/2 (field B₁(z)), is written [11-12] as:

$$B_1(z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I R^2}{2 \left(R^2 + \left(z - \frac{R}{2} \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (1)$$

while the magnetic field of a loop of N turns whose plane of the coil is centered at y = -R/2 (field B₂(z)), is:

$$B_2(z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I R^2}{2 \left(R^2 + \left(z + \frac{R}{2} \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (2)$$

The field on the axis of a circular Helmholtz coil is the combination of the two previous magnetic fields, the superposition theorem which is validated by the linearity of Maxwell's equations gives the total field:

$$B_{\text{Helmholtz}}(z) = B_1(z) + B_2(z) \quad (3)$$

We proceed by similarity with a structure consisting of two ellipsoidal loops, as shown in Figure 1. Each single loop has a semi-axial dimension x₁ and y₁.

Fig. 1. Helmholtz structure with elliptic loops.

To analyze this situation, a formula for the field produced around the origin (x = y = z = 0) by any loop traversed by a current I and of declination α with respect to O_z is proposed [13-14]:

$$B_{1z} = \left(\frac{i\mu_0}{2} f \right) \sin\alpha \times \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} P_{n+1,1}(\cos\alpha) \left(\frac{r}{f} \right)^n P_n(\cos\theta) \right\} \quad (4)$$

where P_{nm}(cosα) are the associated Legendre polynomials and P_n(cosα) are the Legendre polynomials.

For the field on the O_z axis, P_n(cosθ) = 1, and r = z, and the previous equation becomes:

$$B_{1z} = \left(\frac{i\mu_0}{2} f \right) \sin\alpha \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^{n=\infty} P_{n+1,1}(\cos\alpha) \left(\frac{z}{f} \right)^n \right\} \quad (5)$$

The total field is the sum of the elementary inductions. It is possible to use the first terms of development. Thus an appropriate spacing of the two loops allows a better homogeneity of the magnetic field with a cancellation of derivatives of order two of the field B₁ along the axis O_z and fortuitously the derivative of order four is relatively weak. For this, the two loops must be positioned at an azimuthal angle α of 0.734 rad (about 42°). There is a unique solution for which the second order derivative of the field B₁ is zero. For this optimal structure (E_{opt}), the secondary geometric data are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE ELLIPSOIDAL COIL

Primary axis a (cm)	Secondary axis b (cm)	α (rad/deg)
3.042	2.459	0.734/42.09

The eccentricity of the ellipsoid is:

$$e = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{b^2}{a^2} \right)} = 0.587 \quad (6)$$

The value of the magnetic field at any point in the space is the sum of the fields created at this point by each of the single ellipsoidal loops and the approximated expression is [15-16]:

$$B_z = \frac{\mu_0 I a b}{\pi} \left\{ \frac{E\left(\frac{a^2-b^2}{a^2+(M-z)^2}\right)}{(b^2+(M-z)^2)\sqrt{a^2+(M-z)^2}} + \frac{E\left(\frac{a^2-b^2}{a^2+(M+z)^2}\right)}{(b^2+(M+z)^2)\sqrt{a^2+(M+z)^2}} \right\} \quad (7)$$

with:

$$E(k) = \int_0^{\pi} \sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (8)$$

III. COMPARISON OF THE B₁ FIELD HOMOGENEITY

The performance in terms of homogeneity of the B₁ field of the ellipsoidal Helmholtz Coil (H_E) are compared with a circular Helmholtz Coil (H_C) of the same radial size (diameter d equal to 5cm). Figure 2 shows the simulation of the theoretical curves of the normalized magnetic induction B_{1z} produced along the axis O_z by both coils.

Fig. 2. Profiles along the O_z axis (in m) of the normalized induction (coils: H_C, H_E).

Thus, the theoretical width (absolute or relative) of the profiles can be calculated at 1% and 10% of the maximum. The values are presented in Table II.

TABLE II. PROFILE WIDTH FOR BOTH COILS

Configuration	Profile width at 1%	Profile width at 10%
Circular H _C	2.31	3.83
Ellipsoidal H _E	2.92	4.44

Compared to the reference H_C, the lobe width at 10% of the ellipsoidal coil is increased by 12%. This increase is also greater (20%) for lobe width at 1%. The performance stated above is very general and does not in fact depend on the size of the coil. Indeed, it suffices to apply a simple scale factor compared to the circular and ellipsoidal prototypes to obtain coils of greater or lesser size.

IV. ELECTRICAL MODELING

In this section, the complete electrical modeling of the structures, considering all couplings, is investigated. The complete electrical modeling of the coils is necessary to explain their operation and thereby demonstrate their feasibility. The general electrical model for the developed structures is represented schematically in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. General electrical model for the developed structures.

Because of the symmetry, the input impedance Z can be expressed as [17-19]:

$$\begin{cases} z_1 = jL_1\omega + \frac{1}{jC_1\omega} + jM_{12}\omega \\ z_2 = jL_2\omega + \frac{1}{jC_2\omega} + jM_{12}\omega \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The two electrically isolated loops are characterized by a set of two equations with two unknowns (I_1 and I_2):

$$\begin{pmatrix} z & J(M_{12})\omega \\ J(M_{12})\omega & z \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

In fact, two resonance modes are distinguished: a co-current mode with a symmetric behaviour $I_1 = I_2$, which is the mode of interest, and a counter-current mode with non-symmetric behaviour $I_1 = -I_2$ (gradient mode). In co-current mode, the system of (10) comes down to a single equation [20]:

$$ZI_1 + J(M_{12})\omega I_2 = 0 \quad (11)$$

Equation (10) corresponds to the resonance equation:

$$(L_1 + M_{12})\omega^2 - \frac{1}{C} = 0 \quad (12)$$

If the coupling coefficient k is introduced ($M_{12} = k L_j$), the resonance equation (12) becomes:

$$C(L_1 + k_{12}\sqrt{L_1L_2})\omega^2 = 1 \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) has a positive real solution [21]:

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{C(L_1+k_{12}\sqrt{L_1L_2})}} \quad (14)$$

For the counter-current mode ($I_1 = -I_2$), the value of frequency is:

$$f_2 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{C(L_1-k_{12}\sqrt{L_1L_2})}} \quad (15)$$

The two resonance modes are located on either side of the resonance frequency f_0 ($f_0 = 1/(LC)$) and they are all the more distant as the coupling is strong. A representation of the input impedance amplitude Z_e is given in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Theoretical curve of the input impedance of two identical tuned circuits.

The current ratio is given by the secondary circuit equation, which is [22]:

$$\frac{I_1}{I_2} = \frac{-jM\omega}{z} \quad (16)$$

When there are no losses at the resonance frequency f_1 of the first mode $Z=jX=-jM\omega$ and consequently $I_2/I_1=+1$, the mode is co-current.

For the mode at frequency f_2 , a change of sign takes place, so $Z=jX=+jM\omega$ and the mode is counter current ($I_2/I_1=-1$).

In the case of low losses or high quality factor, i.e. $Q_0 = RL\omega_0 \gg 1$ [23], these two modes retain their characteristics in terms of frequencies and currents, while the impedances at resonance remain low [24]. The simulation allowed observing the variations of the currents and their relationship (Figure 5). The two loops are tuned to the same frequency $f_0 = 105\text{MHz}$, with $k=0.05$, $L = 117.6\text{nH}$, $C = 19.47\text{pF}$, $R = 0.41\Omega$, and quality factor $Q_0 = 189$.

It can be seen that at f_0 , the transfer of power from the primary to the secondary coil is optimal. This is a particularity of the inductive coupling which is widely used in RF [25-26]. For the other frequencies f_1 and f_2 , the currents I_1 and I_2 have a maximum value and the difference between the two modes remains at the phase level.

Fig. 5. I_1 and I_2 variation curves and their ratio.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Prototype Dimensions

The results of the experimental tests obtained with the developed coils are presented in this section. An ellipsoidal Helmholtz coil and a circular Helmholtz coil were built for MRI (H1) at 100.241MHz. To facilitate comparisons, they have the same radial size $d=5\text{cm}$. The precise dimensions of the coils are given in Table III. Figure 6 shows a photography of both developed coils. The diameter of the wire constituting the loops is 1mm.

TABLE III. COIL DIMENSIONS

Coils	Loop diameter	Distance between loops
Circular Helmholtz	5cm	2.5cm
Ellipsoidal Helmholtz	$a=3\text{cm}, b=2.4\text{cm}$	3.1cm

Fig. 6. Circular and ellipsoidal Helmholtz coils.

B. Tuning and Matching of the Coils

Each loop of the coil was tuned at the same self-resonance frequency f_0 , higher than the resonance frequency of the coil. By predetermination of f_0 , an empty preset of the coil can be

accomplished. Fine tuning of the coil at the working frequency f_l is then performed if necessary [27]. Using the HP 4195A network analyzer, we were able to obtain the variation of the magnitude and the phase in air without load of the input impedance seen by a test loop in terms of frequency as shown for the ellipsoidal coil in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Curve of the input impedance of the ellipsoidal coil seen by a test loop.

At resonance frequency f_l , there is almost the same value for the first mode and a small error for the second mode. At f_2 , the difference is around 3% for the circular coil H_C and around 1% for the ellipsoidal coil H_E . The matching of the coils was carried out without load using a coupling loop (inductive coupling). The position of the coupling loop relatively to the coil determines the optimal distance to get an impedance of 50Ω for the matching [28]. This is approximately 1.9cm for the H_C (1.99cm in theory, this corresponds to an error of 5%) and 2.7cm for the H_E (2.56cm in theory, corresponding to an error of 6%). This matching technique allows optimal energy transfer between the coils and the transmission and reception system. It should be noted that the matching and tuning of the coils depend on the nature of the sample and therefore adjustments should be considered for any new load.

C. Testing the Coils without Load

Off-field (in-air) tests were performed for both H_C and H_E coils. Thus, in the absence of a sample, relative field measurements along the axis of the coils were carried out using a small measurement loop connected to the HP 4195A network analyzer, and comparative readings of the intensity profile of the magnetic field B_1 were established as shown in Figure 8. The experimental curves of the normalized magnetic induction produced along the Oz axis by both coils are given in Figure 9.

Fig. 8. Axial profiles in terms of distance (cm) for coils H_E and H_C .

Fig. 9. Axial profiles in terms of distance (cm) for coils H_C and H_E .

The obtained B_1 field profiles along the axis for the two coils (Figure 8) are in good agreement with the theoretical predictions of Figure 2. Compared to the H_C (reference coil), the width at 10% of the lobe is 1.32 times greater for the ellipsoidal coil, which is comparable to the theoretical predictions. Another positive point for the ellipsoidal coil, its efficiency is better. Indeed, at identical absorbed power, the field emitted in the center is on average about 20% higher than that produced by the H_E coil. Moreover, the quality factor of the ellipsoidal coil has also an interesting increment of 32%.

VI. CONCLUSION

The design and testing of two prototype probes for MRI comprising two circular and ellipsoidal free elements was presented. The two loops are correctly spaced and connected directly in series to a tuning capacitor. A complete electrical modeling of the coils taking into account all couplings (inductive and capacitive) was investigated. For a given resonant frequency, a predetermination of the tuning frequency of the tuned circuits is carried out, as well as the calculation of the associated tuning capacitors.

At the practical level, the prototypes built are in fact of the same radial dimensions to facilitate comparisons. Thus, compared to the reference circular Helmholtz coil, field measurements in free space with the ellipsoidal coil are in good agreement with the theoretical predictions. The width of the lobe at 10% is increased by 20% for the ellipsoidal coil. Moreover, a significant improvement in the quality factor is observed in free space for the ellipsoidal coil. Also, the efficiency is increased by 37% for the ellipsoidal coil. Finally, the signal to noise ratio is higher for the ellipsoidal coil compared to the circular coil.

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A Student Learning Style Auto-Detection Model in a Learning Management System

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ABSTRACT

Learning style plays an important role in enabling students to have an efficient learning process. This paper proposes an auto-detection model of student learning styles in learning management systems based on student learning activities. A literature review was conducted to investigate the components of online learning activities. The search terms used were "online learning activities", "learning management systems", and "Felder-Silverman Learning Style Model (FSLSM)." A combination of the search terms above was also executed to enhance the search process. Based on the results of the review, eleven classes of online learning activities were identified, namely forum, chat, mail, reading materials, exam delivery time, exercises, access to examples, answer changes, learning materials, exam results, and information access. The online learning activities identified were then mapped to the Felder-Silverman model based on four model dimensions: processing, perception, input, and understanding. The proposed model shows the attributes of the online learning activities based on the dimensions in the FSLSM. The proposed model can assist educators to improve learning content according to the suitability of students and recommend appropriate learning materials to students based on their characteristics and preferences. Future studies include the use of machine learning algorithms such as decision trees to auto-detect student learning styles in learning management systems.

Keywords-auto detection; student learning style; Felder-Silverman learning management system

I. INTRODUCTION

The ways that we teach and learn have changed as technology has advanced. The quick advancement of information and communication technologies has transformed conventional classrooms into cutting-edge learning spaces [1]. For instance, the ability to study whenever and wherever you want has been made possible through the internet sharing of educational information [2]. Online attendance marking systems have also significantly decreased the amount of time spent by teachers verifying students' attendance, increasing the amount of time spent teaching and learning. Additionally, tests or assignments can be given online along with the necessary guidance and criticism to encourage learning outside the scheduled classes [3]. There are numerous more typical amalgamations of teaching methods that are enabled or made easier by contemporary technologies. Due to the growing number of smart learning elements accessible, managing these characteristics is essential for efficient and well-organized instructional processes. Educational institutions now frequently run their own Learning Management Systems (LMSs) and offer a variety of online smart learning capabilities for a wide range of students [4]. An LMS is a web-based system with a wide selection of instructional and course management capabilities. LMS can facilitate group conversations, debates, document sharing, assignment submission, quizzes, grading, and course evaluations through these educational technologies. An LMS also has the potential to serve students from a variety of backgrounds, including those related to culture, age, or gender.

Identification of student learning style categorizes students according to the way they view and respond to information during the teaching process [5]. There are various types of learning styles that can be adopted by students depending on the suitability of the learning environment. A study conducted between the medical students of Isfahan University showed that learning style may be influenced by student gender [6]. Male students are more inclined to kinesthetic learning style while female students are more inclined to aural learning style. On the other hand, there are contradicting research results stating that gender is not a key aspect in determining student learning style [7]. BizzApps software was used to study whether learning styles affect student achievement [8]. The results of the study show that learning style can contribute to the students' success if the learning process is tailored towards it. In addition, 25% of students prefer various learning styles applied during the teaching process as this encourages them to actively contribute to the classroom. Identification of learning styles can assist educators to improve the learning content according to the suitability of students and recommend appropriate learning materials based on their characteristics and preferences [9].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several models that have been used to classify student learning styles. One popular model is the VARK model, which categorizes students into four learning styles: Visual, Auditory, Reading/writing, and Kinesthetic/tactile [10]. The VARK model has been used in various educational

settings and has been found to be effective in helping students identify their preferred learning style and improving their study skills [10]. Another model that has been widely used is the Honey and Mumford model, which classifies learners into four categories: activist, reflector, theorist, and pragmatist [11]. This model emphasizes the importance of experiential learning and encourages students to engage in various learning activities that match their preferred learning style. Other notable models include the Kolb learning style inventory, which categorizes students into four learning styles: converging, diverging, assimilating, and accommodating [13], and the Dunn and Dunn model, which emphasizes the importance of environmental factors and categorizes students into five categories: environmental, emotional, sociological, physiological, and psychological [13]. While these models have been effective in helping students identify their preferred learning styles and improving their study skills, they have some limitations. For instance, they are often criticized for oversimplifying the complex process of learning and for not accounting for the multifaceted nature of learning styles. Additionally, some of these models may not be suitable for all students, as individual differences and cultural factors can play a significant role in determining learning style preferences [11].

The Felder-Silverman Learning Style Model (FSLSM) was defined by Felder and Silverman and is commonly used in engineering and computer science education studies [10–13]. FSLSM learning styles have four dimensions, with each dimension consisting of two types of learning styles. The four dimensions are preprocessing, perception, input and understanding [14]. Figure 1 shows the Felder-Silverman learning style model.

Fig. 1. The Felder-Silvermann Learning Style Model (FSLSM).

The processing dimension pertains to the way students process information, with active and reflective learners as subcategories. Active learners engage in discussions and group learning, while reflective learners prefer solitary learning but think deeply about the information. The perception dimension describes how students perceive information, with sensing learners focusing on facts and practical assignments and intuitive learners preferring to apply concepts in real-life

scenarios. The input dimension relates to the way students receive information, with visual learners understanding concepts through images and diagrams, and verbal learners preferring detailed explanations. Lastly, the understanding dimension pertains to the way students organize information, with sequential learners using linear step methods to understand and solve problems, while global learners understand information in a random, non-linear fashion.

The research gap in this area lies in the lack of automation in identifying student learning styles in an LMS. The existing models require manual input from the student or the teacher, which can be time-consuming and may not always be accurate. Therefore, there is a need for an automated system that can accurately identify student learning styles based on their behavior in the LMS, e.g. navigation patterns, content access, and interaction with the learning materials. The proposed model in this paper aims to fill this gap by using machine learning algorithms to automatically detect student learning styles in the LMS, which can improve the personalized learning experience and enhance student engagement and academic performance. The proposed model is based on the FSLSM.

III. METHODOLOGY

Literature review was conducted to identify the components of online learning activities used in LMSs. The literature was sourced from four databases: Ebsco Host, IEEE Explore, Proquest, and Google scholar. The search terms used were "online learning activities", "learning management systems", and "Felder-Silverman Learning Style Model (FSLSM)." A combination of the search terms above was also executed to enhance the searching process. A search was also conducted in Google to identify miscellaneous books, publications, and organization websites using the same terms. The purpose of the literature review was to identify online learning activities in LMSs and their integration with the FSLSM. The online learning components identified were then mapped to the FSLSM based on the four model dimensions. The purpose of this mapping was to match the suitable online learning components in LMSs with the appropriate learning dimensions. A model was then proposed from the integration of the online learning activities and the FSLSM. The attributes of the proposed model are defined to support the identification of learning style using LMSs.

IV. RESULTS

A. Online Learning Activities

Based on the review, eleven components were identified as activities in online learning that can be identified in LMSs. Basic component requirements are important when building online activity course learning. The first basic components are forums, chat, and mail [15]. These components are used to evaluate the students' active involvement in the on-line communication. The next components are related to a student's perception. They are reading materials, whether abstract or concrete, the time taken to submit quiz questions, tests, and

exams, the time taken to perform reinforcement exercises, the access to examples, the frequency of changing answers during the exams, the number of attempted exercises [16, 17]. The learning materials component categorizes a student as a visual or verbal learner. In this component, learning materials are implemented into two categories, namely through diagrams and listening. After that, a quiz can be implemented based on the given input. The obtained score can assess student tendencies. The activities involved are reading materials in the form of videos, text, diagrams, and pictures [13]. The final component is accessing information and exam results [16]. This component describes how students receive the information provided and then sort it according to their understanding. Their level of understanding can be seen through the results of the examination based on the scales that have been set. Table I shows the mentioned components.

TABLE I. ONLINE LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN LMSs

Activities	Explanation	References
Forum	Involves forum posts, replies, and readings	[16]
Chat	Participates, listens, no participation	[16]
Mail	Use, does not use	[16]
Reading materials	Concrete, abstract	[16, 17]
Exam delivery time	Time taken to submit the exam questions	[16, 17]
Exercises	The amount of exercises that had been done	[16, 17]
Access to examples	The number of access to examples attempted	[16, 17]
Answer changes	The numbers in the answer changes during exams	[16, 17]
Learning materials	Diagrams, pictures, videos, text, presentations	[17]
Exam results	High, moderate, low	[16]
Information access	Global, sequential	[16]

A. Integration of Felder-Silverman Learning Style Model and Online Learning Activities

Based on the results, the components of online learning activities are mapped to the dimensions of the FSLSM. Table II shows a summary of online LMSs activities based on the FSLSM according to the literature review. The main online activities in processing are related to forum, mail, and chat activities [16]. The main online activities for perception are related to exam revision, questions, exercises review, reading materials, and learning resource types [16, 17]. The main online activities related to input are video and visual materials, forum visits, questions, and right answers [17]. The main online activities related to understanding are information access, content visit, and exam results [16, 18].

V. THE PROPOSED MODEL

Figure 2 shows the proposed model to identify student learning styles in LMSs based on the Felder-Silverman approach. The identified attributes were mapped to the four main dimensions of the FSLSM and are included in the proposed model. A definition of the attributes and its related values are displayed in Table III.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF ONLINE LEARNING ACTIVITIES BASED ON FLSLM

FSLSM	[17]	[18]	[16]	[19]	[20]
Processing	forum_post	content_visit	forum	format_activity	question_answer
	self_assessment	forum_post	mail	learning_resource_type	visit_learning_content
	forum_view	forum_stay	chat	interactivity_type	forum_visit
	text_materials	forum_visit		interactivity_level	
Perception	concrete_materials	question_graphic	exam_revision	format_activity	right_answer
	examples	question_text	exercises	learning_resource_type	revised_answer
	abstract_materials		exam_delivery_time		
	exercises_review		answer_changes		
			access_to_examples		
Input	visual_materials	forum_visit		format_activity	right_answer
	video_materials	question_graphic		learning_resource_type	forum_visit
	text_materials	question_text			
	forum_post				
Understanding	navigational_pattern	content_visit	information_access	structure_activity	option_solve_problem
	course_overview		exam_results		visit_learning_content

Fig. 2. The proposed model.

TABLE III. PROPOSED ATTRIBUTES AND VALUES FOR THE LEARNING STYLE DIMENSIONS IN THE PROPOSED MODEL

Dimension in FLSLM	Learning style	Attribute_Name	Attribute_Value	Percentage of attribute_value	Ref.
Processing	Active	- Forum_Post	- No of posting in forum	- More than 75%	[16, 21]
		- Mail	- Use or do not use	- More than 75%	
	- Chat	- Participate or not participate	- More than 75%		
	- Course_outline	- No of visited courses outline	- Between 25% - 75%, none		
Reflective	- Forum_View	- No of view post in forum	- More than 75%	[12, 20]	
	- Mail	- Use or do not use	- Between 25% - 75%, none		
Perception	Sensing	- Chat	- Participate or not participate	- Between 25% - 75%, none	[16, 21]
		- Course_outline	- No of visited courses outline	- More than 75%	
		- Concrete_Materials	- No of visits	- More than 75%	
	- Exercises	- No of visits	- More than 75%		
	- Exam_Delivery_Time	- Submission time in exam	- More than 75%		
Intuitive	- Access_To_Examples	- No of visits	- More than 75%	[16, 21]	
	- Answer_Changes	- No of attempted answer change	- Between 20% - 50%, none		
Input	Visual	- Abstract_Materials	- No of visits	- More than 75%	[19]
		- Exercises	- No of visits	- Between 25% - 75%, none	
	- Exam_Delivery_Time	- Submission time in exam	- Between 50% - 75%, none		
	- Access_To_Example	- No of visits	- Between 25% - 75%, none		
Verbal	- Answer_Changes	- No of attempted answer changes	- More than 50%	[17, 20]	
	- Visual_materials	- No of visits	- More than 75%		
Understanding	Sequential	- Video_materials	- No of visit	- More than 75%	[16, 20]
		- Graphic_Question_Type	- No of correct answers	- More than 75%	
		- Text_materials	- No of visits	- More than 75%	[17, 20]
		- Audio_materials	- No of visits	- More than 75%	
		- Text_Question_Type	- No of correct answers	- More than 75%	[17, 20]
		- Forum_Post	- No of forum posts	- More than 75%	
		- Sequential_Information_Access	- No of visits	- More than 75%	[16, 20]
		- Exam_Results	- Right answers on process questions	- Way more than 70%	

Table III shows the proposed attribute and values of online learning activities mapped to the FLSM dimensions. Table III describes in detail the mapping of each learning activity and the involvement of students in each activity. The learning style of students can be identified more accurately based on the involvement of students in each online learning activity. The attribute value for each learning style is based on previous study studies. Active and reflective learning style is dependent on the number of forum posts, usage of mail, chat, and course outline visits. Sensing and intuitive learning styles depend on the number of visits to course materials, exercises, exam delivery time, and number of answer changes. Visual and verbal learning styles depend on the number of visits towards video, visual, text, and audio material. Sequential and global learning styles depend on exam results and the number of visits. The proposed attributes and values of online learning activities mapped to the dimensions in the FLSM, as presented in Table III, provide a comprehensive guide for educators to identify students' learning styles based on their engagement with online learning activities. This approach has the potential to improve the effectiveness of online learning by enabling educators to tailor their teaching methods to the specific learning styles of their students. The proposed approach of mapping online learning activities to the dimensions of the FLSM is a novel way of identifying students' learning styles in online learning environment. This approach allows educators to use data from the LMS to gain insight into the way their students engage with online activities and customize their teaching methods accordingly. For example, by analyzing a student's forum participation and email usage, educators can identify whether the student has an active or reflective learning style. Similarly, by analyzing a student's usage of video and visual materials, educators can identify whether the student has a visual or verbal learning style.

Overall, the mapping of online learning activities to the dimensions of the FLSM is a valuable contribution to the field of online education. This approach provides a practical and data-driven method for identifying students' learning style in online learning environments and has the potential to improve the quality and effectiveness of online education.

VI. CONCLUSION

Knowledge of the learning style is an important element in ensuring that the teaching and learning process is well implemented. The proposed model defines the learning style attributes which can help identify the respective learning style. Understanding student learning styles can help teachers to improve the learning content according to the suitability of students, recommend appropriate learning material, and improve the communication and interaction skills between humans and computers through features in the learning management system [21]. Since most interactions between students and instructors occur in learning management systems, the system should be developed to cater the student specific requirements during the teaching process for a successful learning experience. Furthermore, incorporating these learning style attributes into the design of learning management systems can enhance the overall learning experience. Such features can

include adaptive learning technologies, personalized learning pathways, and customized feedback mechanisms. By leveraging the power of technology to support and complement traditional teaching methods, educators can create a more dynamic and interactive learning environment that meets the needs of diverse learners.

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Optimization of Technological Parameters when Plasma Nitriding the Gear Working Surface

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of optimizing the technological parameters when plasma nitriding the gear working surface. 27 experiments were carried out on an H4580 Eltrolab instrument to obtain a working surface hardness database table, and the Minitab statistical software was used to process the experimental results. A regression equation was identified to analyze the influence of temperature, time, and gas permeation concentration on the hardness of the working surface. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that all these nitriding parameters influence the regression equation. The results showed that the permeation temperature TL has the greatest influence on the hardness, while the permeation time h and the first gas permeation concentration $G1$ had less influence. An optimal set of technological parameters was established, where the permeation temperature was $TL=550^{\circ}\text{C}$, permeation time was $h=8\text{h}$, and the first gas permeation concentration was $G1=4\text{h}$. Experiments were carried out using this set of optimal parameters to evaluate the microstructure and the depth of the hardening layer of the part surface. Finally, this study presented the whole process for the permeation and plasma nitriding of 18XIT steel.

Keywords-permeation temperature; permeation time; gas permeation concentration; working surface hardness; plasma nitriding; regression

I. INTRODUCTION

Plasma nitriding is widely used in steel machine parts [1-2], as it can control the white layer making it very suitable for creating products with high-quality requirements [3-5]. The permeation process is carried out at low pressure in a vacuum furnace with a mixture of H_2 , N_2 , CH_4 , and Ar gases [1, 3-4, 6-7]. These gases are ionized under high voltage, creating a plasma. Nitrogen ions are accelerated during the collision of the plasma with the sample. This ion bombardment heats, cleans, and forms a hard layer with good wear resistance, increasing fatigue strength [7]. In recent years, many studies have been conducted on the nitriding process model, but it is generally not enough to predict the influence of the parameters on the quality of the permeable layer [3-5, 9-13].

In [9], Wagner's generalized common model was used to analyze the permeable layer formation and use it in plasma nitriding experiments. The parabolic curve in the proposed predictive models shows the increase in nitrogen content in the permeable layer and the diffusion area in plasma nitriding [5, 9]. In [14], a numerical simulation model was presented for the nitride layer growth and nitrogen distribution in the ϵ , γ' , and α

phases during plasma nitriding of low-carbon steel. The results showed that the nitride layers consist of ϵ , γ' , and α phases and that the thickness of these phases follows a parabolic pattern. In [9], a numerical model of nitrogen diffusion in low-carbon steel was presented, showing that diffusion depended on nitrogen concentration and that the thickness of the permeable layers was the square root of the nitriding time at 843°K (570°C). In [15], a nitriding process model for low-carbon steel was investigated, performing gas nitriding using $\text{NH}_3\text{-H}_2$ gas permeation. A simple model was designed to predict the thickness of the nitride layers in pure iron, built using a kinetic model derived from Fick's second law. Several studies attempted to predict and evaluate the distribution of nitrogen concentrations and nitride compounds formed during pure iron nitriding and the depth of the nitrogen diffusion area after plasma nitriding [3, 8, 16]. As the plasma power increases, the maximum adhesion values change, reaching 80MPa when the plasma power approaches 80kW [11]. In [12], the influence of plasma nitriding technology parameters on the deformation of hypoid gears was investigated, using blue light technology with a non-contact measuring device to determine the deformation after plasma nitriding.

There is a lack of studies on plasma nitriding for parts made of 18XIT alloy steel (equivalent to SAE 5120) [2, 6, 12, 17]. This study used an ELTROPUL permeation furnace with a pre-made plasma pulse source with stable plasma flow in all cases and easily penetrating details with complex geometries. Along with mathematical statistics tools and Minitab software, methods such as EDAS, MARCOS, TOPSIS, MOORA, and PIV [11-13, 18-25] were used to design and process the experimental data of this study.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS

The plasma nitriding sample consists of passive hypoid gear teeth, machined from alloy steel 18XIT according to the Russian standards (equivalent to SAE 5120) [2, 6, 17], having a chemical composition of (%): C: 0.17 – 0.23; Si: 0.17 – 0.37; Mn: 0.8 – 1.1; P: < 0.035; S: < 0.035; Cr: 1 – 1.3; Ni: < 0.3; Ti: 0.03 – 0.09; Cu: < 0.3; N: < 0.008 [2]. The gear was hardened to achieve a hardness ranging from 34-36HRC, equivalent to 336-354HV of the Vickers hardness measurement, and then each tooth was cut apart by the wire cutting method, in order from 1 to 27, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Sample preparation: (a) Hypoid gear pairs after machining, (b) plasma nitriding samples cut from hypoid gears.

According to the JIS Z 2244-2009 standard, a control sample of the same material was included in addition to the experimental sample when conducting each experiment. An H4580 Eltrolab was used to perform programmable plasma nitriding, and the following parameters could be set when programming [5]: number of hours executed in each step of the program h , number of minutes executed in each step of the program m , pressure P (in pascals), permeation temperature TL ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), temperature rise rate of the furnace over time TG ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$), furnace wall temperature TW ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), temperature rise rate of the furnace wall over time WG ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$), voltage V (V), pulse duration PD (μs), number of pulse repetitions PR (μs), gas flow 1 $G1$ (l/h), gas flow 2 $G2$ (l/h), gas flow 3 $G3$ (ml/h), and gas flow 4 $G4$ (l/h).

The permeation process with samples of the same material and size changes little the permeation temperature TL , so the voltage V and pressure P were fixed [1, 11, 26]. The temperature rise rate of the part over time TG , furnace wall temperature TW , and temperature rise rate of the furnace wall

over time WG depend on permeation temperature TL and permeation time h . Gas permeation flows $G1$, $G2$, $G3$, and $G4$ are proportional to each other [26]. According to the requirements for selecting input factors, the experimental variables of temperature TL , permeation time h , and first gas permeation concentration $G1$ were selected. The remaining factors remained unchanged. A total of 27 experiments were planned and the program to control the permeation process was set on the H4580 Eltrolab software. As the depth of the plasma nitriding layer on the surface of the experimental sample was very thin (μm), the microscopic hardness was tested using the Vickers hardness measurement method (HV) according to the JIS Z 2244-2009 standard with an FM-700e. Table I shows the experimental results.

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Trial	Permeation time h (h)	Permeation temperature TL ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Gas flow 1 $G1$ (l/h)	Hardness, H (HV)
1	4	510	4	632.0
2	4	510	6	644.2
3	4	510	8	654.1
4	4	530	4	670.7
5	4	530	6	676.2
6	4	530	8	678.8
7	4	550	4	699.9
8	4	550	6	700.4
9	4	550	8	694.2
10	6	510	4	638.1
11	6	510	6	641.3
12	6	510	8	653.5
13	6	530	4	670.6
14	6	530	6	677.9
15	6	530	8	676.4
16	6	550	4	703.1
17	6	550	6	701.5
18	6	550	8	693.9
19	8	510	4	652.7
20	8	510	6	652.7
21	8	510	8	659.7
22	8	530	4	684.8
23	8	530	6	681.4
24	8	530	8	684.3
25	8	550	4	717.0
26	8	550	6	706.1
27	8	550	8	701.9

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out on the regression equation results, to remove the parameters that do not affect them [11, 14, 16-24]. The regression equation for hardness H can be written as follows:

$$H = -2726 - 6.44 h + 10.52 TL + 87.17 G + 1.090 h^2 - 0.00776 TL^2 - 0.690 h \times G1 - 0.1552 TL \times G1 \quad (1)$$

Figure 2 and regression show that TL has the greatest influence on hardness, while h and $G1$ have less. In Figure 2, the effect of h is parabolic, starting from a level (0), reaches a minimum, and finally approaches the maximum value of 685HV in the level area (+1) of the planning. The effect of TF is almost linear, starting at 645HV and reaching a maximum value of about 700HV. The effect of $G1$ is linear, starting from

the minimum value at level (-1) and reaching the maximum value at level (+1).

Fig. 2. The influence of parameters on hardness.

Figure 3 shows a plot of the standardized effects of parameters on the hardness of the working surface. TL has the greatest influence on hardness, followed by h, while G1 has the lowest influence. The interaction between TL, G1, and h greatly affects the hardness of the surface. These results are consistent with the theoretical basis of the first and second Fick laws since the temperature is the main factor that strongly influences the coefficients and diffusion. Maximal optimization was carried out with the following boundary conditions:

$$\max \text{Hardness} : \begin{cases} 4 \leq h \leq 8 \\ 510 \leq TL \leq 550 \\ 4 \leq G1 \leq 8 \end{cases}$$

providing the results shown in Table II.

Fig. 3. Standardized effects of variables for hardness.

TABLE II. OPTIMIZATION RESULTS USING BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Solution	h	TL	G1	Hardness fit
1	8	550	4	715.876

The maximum optimization value of stiffness in the planning area was 715.876 at $h=8h$, $TL=550^\circ\text{C}$, and $G1=4l/h$. Experiments were carried out using the optimal set of parameters to evaluate the microstructure and hardening layer depth of the detailed surface. Figure 4 shows the optimization analysis chart.

Fig. 4. Optimization analysis chart.

Figure 5 shows the microstructure image, indicating that the surface of the test sample corresponds to the materials of the part with a clear, permeable layer. The ϵ and γ' phases are the white layers that can be seen when etching and taking photos through a microscope. The microscopic organization includes carbides and nitrites distributed in ferrite.

Fig. 5. Microstructure of the plasma nitriding layer.

Phase ϵ has a needle shape, as shown by the chemical composition analysis of the permeable layer, using the SEM/EDX (line-scan) method in Figure 6. The microscopic examination showed carbide and nitrite distributed in Ferrite and Perclite. The microscopic hardness to the penetration depth was measured on a cross-section through the permeable layer and at intervals. Surface hardness was high and decreased when depth increased up to $350\mu\text{m}$, where it remained constant, corresponding to the hardness of the base metal (340HV). The %N content can be determined by the thickness of the phases ϵ , λ , and α and the depth of the permeable layer. Figure 8 shows the EDX analysis results, illustrating that the %N content on the surface was high (10.68%N), but the deeper into the interior, the lower it was.

Fig. 6. SEM image (x8000).

Fig. 7. Hardness distribution with the depth of penetration.

Figure 9 shows the EDX analysis at one location of the sample, while Figure 10 shows the nitriding process of hypoid gear pairs using the optimal parameters. Except for the optimal set of the examined parameters, the remaining parameters were fixed when conducting experiments.

Fig. 8. Nitrogen composition according to penetration depth.

The process of plasma nitriding can be summarized as follows:

- Clean the details to be absorbed
- Check the permeation equipment system (electrical, air conduction, cooling)
- Fix the details and put into the furnace box (make sure the details are installed tightly, do not move during the infiltration process)
- The power is closed under high voltage and low pressure to heat for the first time until it reaches approximately 250-300°C. This temperature is then maintained to activate the surface. After about 2.5h, the temperature should raise at a rate of 100°C/min (second heating phase) until the permeation temperature reaches 550°C. The end of the 8-hour permeation period is the auto-cooling period, as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 9. EDX analysis at one location on the sample.

Fig. 10. Plasma nitriding technology process of hypoid gear pairs.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study identified a regression equation as the basis for analyzing the influence of temperature, time, and gas concentration on the hardness of the working surface of a gear. The results of the analysis showed that the permeability temperature TL had the greatest influence on hardness, followed by the permeation time h and the gas concentration $G1$. The interaction between infiltration temperature TL , gas permeation concentration $G1$, and permeation time h also affects surface hardness, but to a different extent.

The results of this study were completely consistent with the theoretical basis of the first and second Fick laws. The maximum optimization value of stiffness in the planning area was 715,876, using $h=8h$, $TL=550^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $G1=4l/h$. Experiments were carried out using these parameters to evaluate the microorganism and the depth of the hardening layer of the surface. The control program for the permeation process and the plasma nitriding technology process of hypoid gear pairs made of 18XIT steel were proposed. The proposed optimized set of technological parameters can be used when plasma nitriding various machine parts made of 18XIT or equivalent materials to get an optimal result.

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Energy Consumption Analysis for the Prediction of Battery Residual Energy in Electric Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

The emergence of Electric Vehicles (EVs) is a turning point in decarbonizing the road transport sector. In spite of the various apprehensions of the customers, such as range anxiety, long charging times, higher costs, and the lack of charging infrastructures, EVs have managed to considerably penetrate into the market. Appreciable subsidies in EV purchase and possibilities of renewable energy-based local charging equipment have encouraged more and more people to own EVs. Electrifying road transport also calls for scaling up of all stages of the supply chain as it involves a lot of raw materials and critical metals used for battery technology. One of the most important factors determining the range of an EV is the energy density of the battery, which has reached over 300 Wh/kg, from 100-150 Wh/kg a decade ago. This clearly means that the same vehicle can travel double the distance with the same mass. Understanding and modeling the energy consumption in an EV is quintessential in alleviating the fear of range anxiety. This paper presents a detailed mathematical equation-based energy consumption analysis of a particular EV model for Indian roads. Very few researchers have worked on drive cycles suitable for India. The novelty of the current work is that the energy consumption calculation can be worked out for any EV model or vehicle type through simple mathematical equations.

Keywords-electric vehicle; Electric Vehicle Charging Stations (EVCSs); residual energy; aerodynamic drag; kinematics; tractive forces; rolling force; power electronics

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric Vehicles (EVs) are in the centre of attraction for researchers for quite some time. Reduced dependency from fossil fuels and lower emissions and sustainability are the key advantages of EVs. Yet, there are still few barriers to be crossed for EVs to heavily penetrate the market. These include range anxiety and the lack of charging infrastructure. Undoubtedly, EVs are going to be the future of transportation and mobility sector. Research on new materials and battery chemistries along with other innovations form the thrust for EVs to become the gamechanger in automotive sector. There are four main types of EVs, namely the Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs), Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs), Plugin Battery Electric Vehicles (PHEVs), and Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle (FCEVs).

BEVs, also known as All-Electric Vehicles (AEVs) are driven using battery-powered electric drivetrain. The large

battery pack which powers the vehicle can be charged by plugging into the electricity grid. The charged battery pack in turn powers one or more electric motors to run the electric car. Figure 1 shows the various components and systems in a BEV. The main components of a BEV include the electric motor, inverter, battery pack, a control module that includes the power electronic circuitry, and the transmission gear. The power for the electric motor is derived by converting the DC voltage of the battery to AC by an inverter. For acceleration, the controller adjusts the vehicle speed by changing the frequency of the AC power from the inverter to the motor. The motor then makes the wheels move with the help of the transmission system. On deceleration, the motor works as an alternator and produces regenerative power, which charges the battery.

Accurate range prediction can help alleviating the range anxiety problem in EVs. The range of an EV depends on the residual energy in the battery and the rate of energy consumption of the vehicle. There are various components of

energy consumption that are related to travel (velocity, topography, inclination, etc.), weather (ambient temperature, windspeed, visibility, etc.), vehicle (auxiliary usage), traffic (congested roads), and battery (State of Charge-SoC, capacity, etc.). The battery health and degradation form an important factor determining the energy efficiency of an EV [1-9].

Fig. 1. Parts of an EV.

II. ENERGY ESTIMATION

Energy estimation in EVs is done with two basic approaches, namely the Forward approach (dynamic approach) and the Backward approach (quasi-static approach) [6]. The forward approach is performed using equations of the powertrain components and the dynamic interaction between them. The backward approach assumes a reference drive cycle as input and calculates the forces acting at the wheels and proceeds the analysis backward through the powertrain. Later, the model computes the motor torque and the battery energy required to power the electric motor [6].

Various energy estimation models have been implemented, including longitudinal, statistical and computer-based ones. Longitudinal vehicle dynamics-based model borrows its concepts from vehicle dynamics theory and calculates the required power at the wheels to overcome the tractive forces. Some researchers have modelled regenerative braking as a linear function of vehicle speed to estimate the energy recovered while braking or driving downhill [7]. The instantaneous EV speed and acceleration is used to provide an accurate second-by-second energy consumption estimation [7]. The impact of auxiliary devices is also considered for an improved estimation. The relationship between EV power, speed, acceleration, and road grade is explored in [8] to determine the required power at the wheels. The model can be either used for instantaneous energy consumption estimation or energy consumption prediction over a trip [8]. Statistical models use real world driving data and derive empirical relationships between various factors and thus energy consumption [6]. Real-world data of EV energy consumption can be useful in building energy consumption calculation models. Considering vehicle dynamics equation as the foundation, multiple linear regression is used to construct three models. Each model uses a different level of aggregation of the input parameters, allowing predictions using different types of available input parameters. One model uses aggregated values of the kinematic parameters of trips and allows prediction with

basic input parameters such as travel distance, travel time, and temperature. The second model includes detailed acceleration data. The third model uses data of the kinematic parameters as input parameters to predict energy consumption [7].

Authors in [4] used the vehicle dynamics equation to calculate the required mechanical energy and have also included added a temperature and time-dependent term to study auxiliaries and temperature-dependent efficiencies. The physical relations in the vehicle dynamics equation are used to construct three models for EV energy consumption prediction in [5]. In [6], multiple linear regression method is applied to a real-world trip and energy consumption data. The data set considers one vehicle and hence the constructed models are specific to that particular drivetrain. The influence of ambient temperature and auxiliary loads over electricity consumption is explored in [7]. An energy consumption model is proposed based on the GPS observations of 68 EVs in Aichi Prefecture, Japan. The model is calibrated through ordinary least square regression and multilevel mixed effects linear regression. The results depict that the ambient temperature directly influences the output energy losses and the interactive effects associated with vehicle auxiliary loads. Neglecting the interactive effects between ambient temperature and vehicle auxiliary loads will cause inaccurate readings of the energy consumption of the heater air conditioner [7]. Authors in [8, 9] propose a method for SoC and range estimation by considering location-dependent environmental conditions and time varying drive system losses. To validate the method, an EV was driven along a selected route and battery SoC at the destination was compared with the value predicted by the algorithm. The results show excellent accuracy in the SoC and range estimation.

Computational and statistical methods are more apt for energy estimation as they require fewer calculations than the analytical methods based on physical models. However, they are less accurate than the analytical methods. A novel methodology to estimate the driving behavior in terms of future vehicle speeds is implemented in [10]. A driving behavior model is built using a variation of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) called Nonlinear Auto Regressive model with exogenous inputs (NARX). The context-aware NARX model is trained based on previous driving behavior recordings, the recent driving reactions, and route average speed retrieved from Google Maps in order to perform driver-specific and self-adaptive driving behavior modeling and long-term estimation. Authors in [1] used a vehicle kinetic model to evaluate the energy consumption in mini taxis in sub-Saharan Africa. Per-second GPS data gathered on minibus taxis include 62 trips across 3 routes with different driving conditions near Stellenbosch, South Africa. The paratransit vehicle energy consumption was estimated to range from 0.29 to 0.51 kWh/km depending on the driving condition [1]. Authors in [11] proposed a method to evaluate the actual driving energy consumptions of EVs using real driving speed and charging energy information. Using energy flow analysis in the EVs, an analytic expression for estimating the energy consumption of EVs is derived. The energy consumption calculation is conducted using regression analysis. Equations for various energy split ups are also given.

The energy consumption models proposed in most of the literature are designed for specific vehicle types and specific road terrains. Most of the researchers have worked on locations outside India and the models and drive cycles selected do not match the Indian roads and climate. Automobile Research Association of India (ARAI) recommends a drive cycle that suits urban transport in India. This research work follows the Indian Drive Cycle (IDC) as its input speed profile.

Our research work focusses on building a vehicle kinematic model wherein the residual energy in the EV battery for different vehicle types and/or for varying ambient conditions can be calculated. The modified urban IDC is taken as the input speed profile in our work because its average speed and acceleration values match those on Indian roads. The energy consumption in the vehicle was calculated at regular intervals for various ambient conditions and internal parameter variations. The difference between the previous energy value and the current energy consumption gives the value of the remaining energy within the battery. The residual energy in the battery gives a clear indication about the residual range of the vehicle. Real time validation part with the help of actual data collected in the vehicle is not done. The distance travelled for a single drive cycle of IDC (10.654kms as specified by ARAI) multiplied with the number of cycles before battery charge falls below the safe margin is approximately matching the manufacturer's claim.

III. ANALYSIS OF VEHICLE DYNAMICS

An energy consumption model can be built by using forward or backward approaches. The backward approach consists of creating a vehicle model that simulates electrical parameters based on kinematic and dynamic requirements. The forward approach utilizes statistical models based on measurements of the EV consumption from real-world data or test cycles. Using real-world measurements gives more realistic values for energy consumption and relies on available data and statistical modeling [8-12]. It is mostly not associated to vehicle dynamics and drivetrain behavior. Figure 2 shows the various components in an EV and their losses.

Fig. 2. Energy consuming components in an EV.

Using a vehicle model provides a direct link with the vehicle dynamics and drivetrain behavior [7-9]. Here, the influences of the drivetrain parameters on energy consumption are clearer. Though every EV has a range value specified by

the manufacturer, none of the vehicles proved them. Changes that occur en-route such as wind speed, slope variations, and traffic cause mismatch in the range values due to the dynamics involved in energy consumption in real time. Authors in [9, 11] used real-world measurements for energy consumption calculation, with a limited number of external parameters are included in their models. A new approach of EV modeling that incorporates battery dynamics into motor-vehicle model and accounts for the drag force is proposed in [12]. The model is called the Integrated Battery-Electric Vehicle (IBEV) model. Two types of batteries namely lithium-ion batteries and lead-acid batteries were studied and modelled separately. The paper includes novel contributions such as EV modeling that includes the battery dynamics into the motor-vehicle model, vehicle speed and torque controller designs using LQI control, and a Kalman filter based on the proposed IBEV model, formulation of energy consumption performance indices for EV applications, and demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed approach through a speed-control comparison study for different test cases.

From the existing literature, it is clear that there is a need for an energy model which incorporates all the important factors governing the vehicle range with an option of varying them during the trip. Including such variations can help in performing studies on real life situations that may cause the EV battery to exhaust. The current study aims to understand the energy consumption of an electric vehicle calculated from battery to wheel, thereby making it possible to predict the All Electric Range (AER). The energy consumed on real-time basis is evaluated by calculating the tractive requirements of the vehicle as well as additional power requirements included in the trip [10-18]. This primarily involves the auxiliary systems coming into play. Table I shows the details and specifications of the EV under study. The maximum battery capacity is 40.5kWh and the motor torque is 250m. The various assumptions and ambient conditions are described below.

TABLE I. SPECIFICATIONS OF THE CHOSEN EV

Parts/ parameters	Specifications
Motor	250Nm Torque
Battery	40.5kWh
Coefficients	$C_{RR} = 0.02$, $C_d = 0.29$, air density = 1.225 kg/m^3
Dimensions	Length 3993mm, width 1811mm, height 1606mm
Wheel base	2498mm
Mass	1400 kg

A. Indian Drive Cycle

The drive cycle selected was corresponding to the urban drive cycle or the urban IDC as suggested by ARAI. The complete drive cycle is subdivided into 2 parts. Part 1 of the IDC consists of 4 repeating cycle patterns of 195s each. Part 2 is a 400s long driving pattern with higher acceleration levels. The total distance travelled is 10.647kms [19].

B. Analyzed Parameters

1) Route Slope

The gradient of the route is one of the key factors that determine the total tractive power taken up by a vehicle. As the

road grade is increased, the gradient force requirement is also increased.

2) Auxiliary Power Requirements

The AC and heating systems form an important part of the auxiliary power requirement from the battery apart from navigation, power steering and brakes.

3) Wind Speed

The effect of wind aiding /opposing the vehicle is an important energy-consuming component.

4) Mass of the Vehicle

Mass of the vehicle affects the rolling force, the gradient force, and the inertial force of the vehicle. The tractive force of a vehicle is defined as the force required to keep the vehicle in motion. The four main components of the tractive forces include aerodynamic force, rolling force, inertial force, and the gradient force.

$$F_{\text{Tractive}} = F_{\text{aero}} + F_{\text{Roll}} + F_{\text{inertia}} + F_{\text{gradient}} \quad (1)$$

where:

$$F_{\text{gradient}} = M_{\text{Veh}} g \sin \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$F_{\text{Roll}} = C_{\text{RR}} \cdot M_{\text{Veh}} g \cos \alpha \quad (3)$$

$$F_{\text{aero}} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot A_{\text{F}} \cdot C_{\text{d}} \cdot [(V_{\text{Veh}} - V_{\text{Wind}})]^2 \quad (4)$$

$$F_{\text{inertia}} = F_{\text{Ia}} + F_{\text{Ie}} = \delta \cdot M_{\text{Veh}} \cdot a \quad (5)$$

$$F_{\text{Tractive}} = (F_{\theta} + F_{\text{R}} + F_{\text{A}} + F_{\text{I}}) \cdot \frac{(1 - \eta_{\text{G}})}{\eta_{\text{G}}} \quad (6)$$

In the above equations V_{Veh} is the velocity of the vehicle, V_{Wind} is the wind-speed in km/h (positive for tailwind and negative for headwind), C_{RR} , C_{d} represent the coefficient of rolling resistance and the drag coefficient, respectively, g is the acceleration due to gravity (m/s^2), α is the road inclination in degrees, A_{F} is the vehicle frontal area (m^2), M_{Veh} is the mass of the vehicle (kg), ρ is the air density (kg/m^3), a is the vehicle acceleration in (m/s^2), and δ is the coefficient of rotary inertia.

The internal resistance of the battery is considered to be equal to 0.03725Ω . An analytical study on the various factors of energy consumption is presented in the subsequent sections.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

An energy model suitable for a tropical country like India will require appropriate constants to be selected that can match with the weather and terrain of the place. A kinematic vehicle model should be developed in order to calculate the power consumed by the EV. In order to propose an energy consumption model, the tractive forces were calculated with the parameters of the chosen vehicle. The constants chosen are mentioned in Table I. The velocity profile was selected to be the urban IDC as recommended by ARAI [19]. Each drive cycle consists of 2 sections. The first section has 3 similar speed vs time envelopes with an average speed of 19kmph and a duration of 195s while the second section has an average speed of 59.3kmph and a duration of 400s. The second section exhibits higher velocity and acceleration values than the first one. The total distance covered per cycle is 10.647km. The

calculated velocity vs time values are plotted in Figure 3. Three drive cycles are shown in the Figure.

Fig. 3. Indian driving cycle.

An analytical study on various factors affecting the energy consumption in an EV was performed in Microsoft Excel and the results are given below. The internal resistance of the battery is one of the key indicators that determine the runtime of the battery. The internal resistance varies with the SoC of the battery. The internal resistance of Lithium-ion batteries goes flat from battery empty stage to almost full charge [2, 6]. The main assumption in this paper is that the internal resistance of the battery is assumed to be a constant.

A. Slope of the Road

Road gradient is defined as the rise or fall of the road level while moving along its length. In other words, it is the rate of rise or fall with respect to the horizontal distance travelled. Another way of expressing grade is that it is the percentage of rise or fall. Different types of gradients are defined, namely maximum gradient, ruling gradient, limiting gradient, and exceptional gradient [16]. The general method of representing grade is 1 in 'n' where '1' is the vertical unit and 'n' is the horizontal distance. Another common method of expressing grade is:

$$\text{Gradient} = \frac{\text{Vertical distance}}{\text{Horizontal distance}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Indian Road Congress (IRC) defines specific road grades for different types of road terrains (Table II [20]). The percentage value of grade is converted into degrees:

$$\text{Grade}^\circ = \tan^{-1} \frac{\text{Gradient (in \%)}}{100} \quad (8)$$

TABLE II. ROAD GRADES IN INDIA AS PER IRC [20]

Terrain nature	Ruling gradient	Limiting gradient	Exceptional gradient
Plain	1 in 30 (3.3%)	1 in 20 (5%)	1 in 15 (6.7%)
Mountainous	1 in 20 (5%)	1 in 16.7 (6%)	1 in 14 (7%)
Steep	1 in 16 (6%)	1 in 14.3 (7%)	1 in 12.5 (8%)

Figure 4 shows the graph of the remaining energy in an EV travelling through different road gradients of 0, 3, and 7°, respectively.

Fig. 4. Variation of the residual energy vs time for various gradients.

It is observed that the energy consumption rate increases with increase in the road gradient. The energy plot droops down linearly with increase in road gradient. Statistical analysis was conducted to determine the exact relation between road gradient and energy consumption which in turn reflects at the residual energy. Table III shows the average residual energy in the EV after running through 25 drive cycles for different road grades. Supervised statistical learning is helpful for building statistical models for prediction/estimation of an output based on one or more inputs. The residual energy values were calculated and averaged for 25 drive cycles for different road gradients and plotted.

TABLE III. RESIDUAL ENERGY VS SLOPE

Slope (°)	Average residual energy after 25 drive cycles (Wh)	Residual energy value after 25 drive cycles (Wh)
0	29062.74	18441.45
4	28464.03	16361.98
5.71	24876.73	2246.85
7	18025.33	4599.49

Figure 5 shows the variation of the residual energy values for the EV under various road slopes with all the other parameters, i.e. vehicle dimensions, air density (1.225kg/m³), C_d = 0.29, C_r = 0.02, wind speed = 90mps, auxiliary load = 100W, and battery internal resistance = 0.03725Ω, remaining constant.

Fig. 5. Prediction plot of residual energy with respect to slope.

The correlation study helps establishing the relationship between two or more variables. The correlation between the two variables was analyzed using the Data Analysis tool of

Microsoft Excel [21]. The predicted residual energy curve is shown in the red dotted lines of Figure 5 and satisfies:

$$y = -1561.7x^2 + 4136.9x + 26479 \quad (9)$$

The correlation matrix is shown in Table III. The value of the correlation coefficient is close to -1 (i.e. -0.8343) which means that the factors slope and residual energy have strong negative correlation.

TABLE IV. CORRELATION MATRIX BETWEEN RESIDUAL ENERGY AND SLOPE

	Slope	Energy
Slope	1	
Energy	-0.8343	1

B. Auxiliary Load on the EV

Multiple factors affect energy consumption in EVs including travel-related, environment-related, and vehicle-related factors, vehicle auxiliary loads, and roadway-related and traffic-related factors [10-16]. Vehicle auxiliary loads basically serve heating, ventilation, and air conditioning purposes. The auxiliary systems in EVs are powered from an auxiliary battery which in turn draws power from the main battery. Power steering and power brakes do not have a significant impact on the vehicle range while, the air-conditioning and heating systems have a strong impact on the energy consumption, and hence range. As EVs do not have an engine producing heat to warm the car, they use battery-powered heating systems. EV batteries lose range as additional power requirements come from operating the car in cold weather. Depending on the outside temperature and the desired temperature in the vehicle, the range reduction can be significant.

Fig. 6. Residual energy plot for increasing auxiliary loads.

Figure 6 shows the plot of remaining energy versus time for an EV connected to various amounts of auxiliary loads. The auxiliary load is increased and its influence on the energy consumption is studied. The energy calculations were done for 25 drive cycles for auxiliary loads of 100W, 300W, 600W, and 900W. It is found that the energy consumption is more for higher values of connected auxiliary loads and hence the residual energy reduces drastically as compared to lighter

loads. The correlation between the two variables was analyzed with the Data Analysis tool of Microsoft Excel and is shown in Figure 7. The predicted residual energy curve is shown in red dotted lines and satisfies the fourth order polynomial equation:

$$y = -91.46x^4 + 1260.7x^3 - 5391.8x^2 + 6742.3x + 27011 \tag{10}$$

Fig. 7. Prediction plot for residual energy with respect to auxiliary loads.

The correlation matrix is shown in Table IV. The value of the correlation coefficient is -0.57 which means that the factors auxiliary load and residual energy have a weak negative correlation. The R² value of 0.698 was observed in the statistical study of auxiliary load versus remaining energy of the EV.

TABLE V. CORRELATION MATRIX BETWEEN RESIDUAL ENERGY AND AUXILIARY LOAD

	Aux. load	Energy
Aux. load	1	
Energy	-0.57	1

C. Influence of Wind Speed

Wind has a major impact on the range of an EV as it determines the aerodynamic drag force that needs to be overcome by the vehicle. Wind can be thought of as a vector quantity as it has a particular velocity value and its direction matters. The complexity of accounting wind speed in the energy consumption calculation is that it is very dynamic in nature, since its magnitude or direction could change rapidly. Wind increases the air resistance on the vehicle. The aerodynamic drag varies with the square of the vehicle velocity. About 70% of this drag is found to be accumulated from overall vehicle resistance at high speeds [22]. Wind direction also holds an important place in deciding the energy consumed by an EV. Winds can appear as headwinds which oppose the motion of the vehicle thus reducing its speed, or tailwinds which aid the vehicle motion. An analytical study was done on the effect of headwind and tailwind on the energy consumption of the vehicle. Figure 8 shows the variation of residual energy for different wind speeds (headwind). Vehicle dimensions, mass, drag, and rolling resistance coefficients were kept constant and the auxiliary load was fixed at 200W. The correlation between wind speed and residual energy was analyzed and the trendline generated in Microsoft Excel is shown in Figure 9. Polynomial trend-line of second degree was

found to be the perfect fit for the generated curve. The R² value was found to be 0.9961 which shows a perfect fit. The polynomial equation is given by:

$$y = -9.8227x^2 + 66.931x + 39445 \tag{11}$$

The linear regression plot generated in Excel is shown in Figure 10. The green dots represent the actual values calculated while the blue dots represent the predicted values. The blue line connecting the blue dots shows the regression. The correlation coefficient value was found to be -0.74 indicating a negative correlation and the P value in the regression analysis was found to be 0.037 which proves that the parameter wind speed is statistically significant to the residual energy.

Fig. 8. Residual energy plot for various wind speeds.

Fig. 9. Prediction plot for residual energy with respect to wind speed.

Fig. 10. Linear regression plot for residual energy vs wind speed.

D. Influence of Tire Pressure

Rolling resistance force is defined as an energy loss due to tire deformation. When the tires rotate on the road surface for a loaded vehicle, the contact area is compressed and causes tire deformation. Under unloaded condition, the tire is uncompressed and returns to original position. The deformation force on the tire under loading condition is greater than the deformation force for unloading condition. This is called hysteresis. Low tire pressure produces more hysteresis loss than high tire pressure because the tire has larger deformation. This loss is gradually reduced when the tire pressure increases [23]. Low tire pressure means low tire stiffness because the rubber molecules vibrate more than in the case of high tire pressure. The stiffness increases linearly with tire pressure [23]. Figure 11 shows the variation in the residual energy with respect to change in the rolling resistance coefficient. Differences in the road surface, especially uneven and rough roads, can result in change of rolling resistance coefficient. It is observed that a small change in Crr can cause higher energy depletion rates.

Fig. 11. Influence of road surface on residual energy.

Fig. 12. Prediction plot for residual energy with respect to Crr.

Figure 12 shows the results of correlation analysis on remaining energy and rolling resistance coefficient C_{rr} . The trendline is linear with the equation given by:

$$y = -1371.9x + 40419 \quad (12)$$

The R^2 value was found to be 0.7819 which shows a strong association between the parameters. The blue line in Figure 12 shows the actual values of residual energy whereas the red dotted lines indicate the linear prediction trendline which approximately falls on the points. Table IV shows the correlation matrix between the residual energy and the rolling resistance coefficient.

TABLE VI. CORRELATION MATRIX BETWEEN RESIDUAL ENERGY AND C_{RR}

	C_{RR}	Energy
C_{RR}	1	
Energy	-0.903	1

E. Impact of Vehicle Mass

The mass of the vehicle impacts directly the rolling resistance force and the gradient force. Although one specific vehicle is selected for the study, the variation in mass can be interpreted as the extra cargo that is added to it during the travel. The orange line in Figure 13 shows the actual values of residual energy whereas the red dotted lines indicate a quadratic polynomial prediction trendline which approximately falls on the points. The correlation coefficient of mass and residual energy is -0.88 which shows a strong negative correlation.

Fig. 13. Prediction plot for residual energy with respect to vehicle mass.

Modern computational tools, such as neural networks and machine learning, have been useful in studies on range detection [24-31]. The factors influencing an EV range have complex relationships and dependence over one another and hence manual calculations will not suffice. Machine learning models can be very useful in analyzing them.

V. CONCLUSION

Range anxiety is one of the biggest hurdles in the electrification of the transport sector. Accurate prediction of vehicle range and energy management methods can significantly build confidence in the minds of customers to buy EVs. The existing literature contains works on the influence of various factors governing the range of an EV. A comparison of the conducted studies shows that most researchers studied the influence of these factors considering one at a time, while the others are assumed to be constants. It is very important to know that most of the publicly available datasets are made for vehicle models outside India or for higher end vehicles. Data collected from EV fleets are mostly GPS data taken in per minute or per second form. Most studies have been conducted in countries

other than India and for specific vehicle types. The transport sector in India is significantly large and diverse. The number of vehicles on the Indian roads is very large, hence demands much faster adoption of EVs compared to any other country. This work considers the Indian urban drive cycle as an input along with the parameters appropriate for Indian weather and traffic conditions. There is a need for experimental research for energy estimation and prediction in the Indian context. This research intends to build an energy consumption model for EVs that run on Indian roads. This paper presents an analytical study on the various factors affecting the energy consumption of EVs with the help of statistical methods. The factors studied include slope, auxiliary loads, wind speed, coefficient of rolling resistance, and mass of the vehicle. The Indian urban drive cycle selected for the research matches the speed profile that is possible on Indian roads. First, the tractive force required to propel the EV is calculated with appropriate constants and speed values as per the IDC and the energy consumed is calculated periodically. Five important factors were found to be statistically significant to the energy consumption of the vehicle. The level of dependence of each of these factors to the energy consumed was studied through calculations and correlation analysis. The mathematical equations for further modelling were derived from Microsoft Excel. As an extension to this work, the dependency equations can be used to build an energy consumption model that can help in the prediction of the vehicle range. This research work can result in an energy estimation model that is generic in nature and be helpful to researchers in understanding the various factors that affect the residual energy of an EV which ultimately relates to the range of the vehicle.

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Assessment of the Flexural Strength of Binary Blended Concrete with Recycled Coarse Aggregates and Fly Ash

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of blending fly ash and recycled aggregates as replacements for cement and conventional coarse aggregates, respectively. Recycled concrete helps to reduce waste management issues and protect the environment. Fly ash was used in percentages from 0% to 10% with an increment of 2.5%, whereas demolition debris was used in a proportion of 50% with conventional aggregates. The 1:2:4 mix with a 0.5 w/c ratio was used to make six concrete mixtures, one of them made entirely of congenial aggregates. Slump tests were performed for all mixtures. A total of 30 prisms of size 500×100×100mm were made and cured for 7 and 28 days. The flexural strength of the specimens was assessed under a two-point bending test till failure. The 5% fly ash and 50% Recycled Coarse Aggregates (RCA) mixture produced better results than the other mixes, showing a decrease in flexural strength of 10.74% and 15.75% after 7 and 28 days of curing, respectively. The small reduction in flexural strength compared to preserving conventional deposits and reducing the hazardous environmental impact of cement production and debris waste makes this mix suitable for use in structural members.

Keywords-green concrete; recycled aggregates; demolishing waste; fly ash, workability; flexural strength; two-point loading

I. INTRODUCTION

Many researchers are actively investigating partial or alternative replacements for concrete materials to increase the strength of the final concrete and protect the environment from the emissions caused by the primary manufacturing processes of concrete ingredients. Many different materials have been investigated for this reason, among them demolition rubbles from concrete constructions as coarse aggregates in fresh concrete. As garbage management is an important concern, using filler material as coarse aggregates in fresh concrete on the work site has many advantages. Yet, the quality of aggregates and the concrete created in this way are impacted by the age of the concrete and the old mortar adhering to it. In particular, green concrete's strength is lower than that of conventional since it uses recycled aggregates from demolition waste. For a few decades, research has actively sought strategies to address this shortcoming. The effects of green concrete on the environment and its contributions to a sustainable environment were studied in [1-2]. The inconsistent nature of the waste's reported results demonstrates the need for additional research in the field to increase confidence in its application [3-4]. In [5-6], the basic properties of materials, the workability of wet concrete, and the mechanical behavior of concrete incorporating different replacement levels were determined, suggesting the use of Recycled Coarse Aggregates (RCA) at suitable replacement levels. In [7-10] the effects of curing methods, water-cement ratio, and temperature on hardened concrete with recycled aggregates were investigated.

Fly ash is a very fine powder created during the primary combustion process. Every year, large amounts of this waste are produced all over the world, seriously harming the ecosystem. Fly ash has been used in concrete as a pozzolanic cement replacement (siliceous and aluminous) to reduce waste and its associated issues. When water is added, calcium hydroxide interacts with it and creates cementitious compounds. In [11], fly ash was reviewed as a supplementary material for concrete and mortar, focusing on its chemical properties and concluding on its use as a sustainable material for green concrete production. To create M15, M20, and M25 concrete, fly ash substituted cement in amounts of 20%, 40%, and 60% in [12], presenting a numerical model for the strength vs water-cement ratio based on the obtained fundamental and strength characteristics of the concrete. The curves developed from the model can be used to calculate the amount of fly ash needed to provide the required strength on concrete.

In [13], fly ash was used to produce high-strength concrete, showing an increase in strength and a decrease in sorptivity after 28 days of curing. Fly ash was also used to create concrete without increasing carbon dioxide emissions [14], suggesting the use of stainless steel as a reinforcement and cladding for greater longevity. In [15], fly ash was used in large volumes as a cementitious compound to study micromechanics characteristics, showing that its use increased the tensile strain capacity of the concrete, but the compressive strength determines its dosage. In [16], fly ash and alkaline solutions were used to determine the mix design criteria and produce cement-free concrete. The comparison to standard concrete revealed strong connections. In [17], laboratory research was

conducted on the use of fly ash from 10% to 30% by volume of cement, showing that although fly ash had a detrimental effect on compressive strength, a dosage of up to 20% resulted in increased density and tensile strength. In [18], fly ash was used in dosages of 0-20% to produce M20-grade concrete, exhibiting increased strength and durability after 7 and 28 days of curing. In [19], quarry dust and fly ash were used in dosages of 0-30%, concluding that using both materials together improved strength and contributed to environmental preservation.

Fly ash has a significant impact on the strength of concrete, but this impact varies greatly depending on the water-to-cement ratio. Early strength is often lower when fly ash is used as a substitute compared to ordinary Portland cement [20]. When using large amounts of fly ash, the final strength may not exceed 70% of the control mixture. Hydration products (CSH jell) are formed when fly ash combines with calcium ions in the pore solution of concrete and water [21-23]. Authors in [24-26] concluded that the replacement of cement with suitable doses of fly ash in conventional or recycled concrete has positive effects that can lead to indigenous material and environmental preservation to some extent.

Many studies have been conducted on fly ash as a cement replacement, but very few investigated the use of both fly ash and demolished concrete as partial or total replacements for cement and coarse aggregates, respectively. It is evident that more studies are required to fully understand the collective effects of materials on the strength properties of concrete. As a consequence, this study examined the impact of using fly ash as a partial replacement for cement on the flexural strength of concrete made with a partial replacement of conventional coarse aggregates with recycled concrete. Furthermore, this study evaluated strength under two-point loading, which is believed to be better than the one-point loading generally used.

II. MATERIALS AND TESTING

This study used ordinary Portland cement from Pakistan and hill sand from a nearby market which was sieved to eliminate lumps and larger particles. The aggregates came from debris from the demolition of a two-story reinforced concrete building in Nawabshah, Pakistan, and the huge blocks were pounded to generate coarse aggregates with a maximum size of 25mm. The aggregates were cleaned, washed, and then left to dry after removing unwanted materials. The same-sized traditional coarse aggregates acquired from the local market were washed and dried. Fly ash class C from a coal power plant was used as cement replacement in weight-for-weight doses of 0, 2.5, 5, 7.5, and 10%. Figure 1 shows the aggregate produced from demolished waste and Figure 2 shows the cement, sand, and fly ash.

A. Sieve Analysis

Hill sand from approved sources from the local market was used as fine aggregates. Figure 3 shows the aggregate sieve analysis. The fineness modulus of the fine aggregates was 2.4. The percentage passing through various sieves and the fineness modulus of the aggregates was within the allowable range of ASTM C136/C136M-14 [28]. Figure 4 shows the sieve analysis results of both the conventional and the recycled

aggregates, following the normal practice to verify properly graded aggregates in the concrete mix. The fineness modulus of the aggregates was 5.33 for Normal Concrete Aggregates (NCA) and 5.35 for RCA. The results of the sieve analysis were within the allowable ranges of ASTM C136/C136M-14 [28].

Fig. 1. Coarse aggregates.

Fig. 2. Fine materials.

Fig. 3. Sieve analysis of fine aggregates.

Fig. 4. Sieve analysis of NCA and RCA.

B. Mechanical Properties of Aggregates

The mechanical properties of aggregates play an important role in the preparation of the desired concrete, particularly water absorption and specific gravity. Table I shows the determined water absorption, specific gravity, abrasion, soundness, and impact and crushing values of both NCA and RCA, following the relevant ASTM standards [30].

TABLE I. WATER ABSORPTION AND SPECIFIC GRAVITY

Test	NCA	RCA
Water absorption	1.64	3.42
Specific gravity	2.57	2.31
Abrasion	18.5	43.1
Soundness	3.9	5.62
Impact value	19.8	28.4
Crushing value	26.2	34.1

Equal halves of traditional coarse aggregates and debris from demolition building waste were used. The dosage of recycled aggregates was chosen according to [27]. Concrete ingredients were combined in a 1:2:4 ratio with a 0.5 water:cement ratio. Six different concrete mixes were prepared, namely CM, B1, B2, B3, B4, and B5. Fly ash doses of 0%, 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10%, each with 50% recycled aggregates were used for 5 concrete mixes, while only traditional elements were used to produce the control concrete mix (CM). The water used had a pH level of 6.7 (see Table II).

TABLE II. MATERIAL DETAILS

Batch #	Cement (kg)	Fly Ash (%)	FA (kg)	NCA (kg)	RCA (kg)	Water (kg)
CM	10	0	20	40	0	5
B1	10	0	20	20	20	5
B2	9.75	0.25	20	20	20	5
B3	9.5	0.5	20	20	20	5
B4	9.25	0.75	20	20	20	5
B5	9	1	20	20	20	5

C. Workability of Concrete

Each concrete mix was tested separately using the slump cone method to check its workability, according to ASTM C143 [29], and Table III shows the results.

TABLE III. SLUMP CONE RESULTS OF ALL MIXES

Batch No.	Fly Ash (%)	Slump (mm)
1	0.0	50.0
2	0.0	42.0
3	2.5	41.5
4	5.0	41.0
5	7.5	39.5
6	10.0	38.0

D. Preparing and Curing of Specimens

Five prisms of 500"×100"×100" were prepared for each of the 6 batches. The concrete was prepared for the molds, poured, and compacted according to the ASTM C31/31M-19 [30]. The specimens were demolded on the next day and allowed to dry in the air for 24 hours in the laboratory. All specimens were then totally immersed in potable water for 7 and 28 days. Thus, a total of 60 specimens were used in this study. Figure 5 shows the specimens and the curing process.

E. Flexural Strength

After the respective curing time, the specimens were moved out of the water and their surface was wiped off with a dry clean cloth. The specimens were then dried in the air for 24 hours. A universal testing machine was used to determine

flexural strength under two-point loading, following ASTM C78 [31]. The load application rate on the testing device was set to 0.5kN/sec, and it increased until failure. Figure 6 shows some specimens and Table IV shows the specimens' flexural strength, as calculated from their failure load and dimensions using the standard formula.

was 108% more than that of conventional, while the specific gravity was 11.25% less. Similarly, the abrasion values, the soundness, and the impact and crushing values were 132%, 44%, 43.4%, and 30% higher. The deviation of the properties of the recycled aggregates confirms the findings of previous studies and shows that the strength of the concrete using the aggregates may also be affected. Indeed, the deviation was due to the age and exposure of concrete during previous use and mortar attached to the recycled aggregates. Thus, the higher demand of the recycled aggregates for water was adjusted in the water-cement ratio, and 0.5 was adopted.

The slump test results indicate that the slump of traditional concrete was within the acceptable range. However, the results of other mixtures were lower than those of ordinary concrete. Figure 7 compares the slump values of the mixes with the control mix. It can be noted that adding more fly ash caused the slump value to decrease more. The maximum slump decrease, which was approximately 30%, was seen for 10% fly ash cement replacement. This shows that there is more water needed for mixes with fly ash. Furthermore, while choosing the w/c ratio for the mix, more admixture or mechanical effort will be needed to maintain the requisite workability.

Fig. 5. Casting and curing of specimens.

TABLE IV. AVERAGE FLEXURAL STRENGTH

#	Batch	Fly ash (%)	7-day curing		28-day curing	
			Mean load (KN)	Mean strength (N/mm ²)	Mean load (KN)	Mean strength (N/mm ²)
1	CM	0.0	7.02	5.29	8.77	6.61
2	B1	0.0	5.82	4.37	7.28	5.46
3	B2	2.5	5.91	4.42	7.39	5.53
4	B3	5.0	6.34	4.72	7.646	5.572
5	B4	7.5	5.76	4.32	6.80	5.10
6	B5	10.0	5.42	4.01	6.41	4.80

Fig. 7. Comparison of slump values.

Fig. 6. Beam testing.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the fine aggregate sieve analysis were used to evaluate the fineness modulus, which was found to be in the range of fine sand. The percentage of the aggregates passing on various sieves met the required ranges. Both used coarse aggregates confirmed the standard requirements of well-graded aggregates. With only a small variation in range values over a sieve, both curves' trends were quite comparable and the percentage passing on various sieves met the requirement of coarse aggregates. The water absorption of recycled aggregates

Fig. 8. Flexural strength (7-day curing).

Fig. 9. Flexural strength (28-day curing).

Fig. 10. Average flexural strength comparison of 7- and 28-day cured specimens.

Figures 8 and 9 compare the average flexural strength of all specimens. It was observed that the included RCA affected flexural strength by 17.40% and 17.51% for 7- and 28-day curing, respectively. On the other hand, the addition of fly ash up to 5% countered the problem and gave a better result. The increase of fly ash beyond 5% decreased flexural strength. Increasing fly ash percentage reduced both workability and flexural strength. The results show the comparison of average flexural strength between the control mix and the one using just 50% recycled aggregates. Among all the mixtures, the mix with 5% fly ash and 50% recycled aggregates provided the highest flexural strength. The average flexural strength decreased by 10.74% and 15.75% for 7- and 28-day cured specimens, respectively, when compared to the control mix.

Figure 10 compares the flexural strength results for the 7- and 28-day cured specimens, showing the same trend of increase in strength. For the standard curing period of 28 days, it may be observed that the loss of strength due to the use of recycled aggregates was counteracted by the addition of 2.5% of fly ash. A similar trend in strength was observed with 5% fly ash in addition to the small increase in strength, but further addition of fly ash resulted in a decrease in strength. This was attributed to the lesser bonding capability of fly ash than

cement. Based on these results, the recommended dosage of fly ash was 5% along with 50% RCA from demolished waste.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study used fly ash and recycled aggregates from demolition debris in concrete to investigate their impact on the workability and flexural strength of concrete. The mechanical properties of aggregates were found to maintain the workability of the desired concrete, particularly water absorption and specific gravity. The findings showed that the specific gravity of RCA was lower and that their water absorption was higher than that of natural coarse aggregates. The greater water absorption of the recyclable aggregates increases the water requirement of the concrete mix, demanding an adjustment to the design. It was also observed that as the dosage of fly ash increased, the slump value of concrete mixed with all conventional constituents decreased. To maintain workability, an adjustment of the water-to-cement ratio in line with the water absorption of recycled aggregates is necessary, otherwise, greater mechanical effort or admixture will be needed during preparation and compaction. Flexural strength results showed that a dosage of 5% fly ash is ideal since it resulted in the least loss of flexural strength for both cases of 7 and 28 days of curing. Therefore, 50% recycled concrete aggregates from demolished concrete waste with fly ash up to 5% are recommended for concrete with good residual flexural strength compared to conventional concrete.

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A Deterministic Finite-State Morphological Analyzer for Urdu Nominal System

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ABSTRACT

The morphological analyzer is a computational process that combines lemmas with other linguistic features to produce new lexical word forms. This paper investigates the processing of a nominal system in the Urdu language. It focuses on the inflections of noun forms and studies number, gender, person, and case representations, using a Finite State Machine (FSM) to analyze and create all the possible forms of the standardized registers. The application of the analysis using this tool provides and displays all the possible structures and their declensions. This study adds all the necessary features and values to the lexical concatenating nouns according to their patterns. The accuracy score of the output is 92.7, where the actual output depends on the detailed design of the FSM and the specific morphological processes provided to the finite state tools.

Keywords-computational morphology; Urdu language; morphological analyzer; finite-state automata; inflection; derivation

I. INTRODUCTION

Hindustani is the lingua franca of India and Pakistan, which was developed into two standardized registers: Hindi and Urdu. The main difference between these two registers is the use of different scripts [1]. For example, Hindi uses the Devanagari script, while Urdu uses an extended form of the Perso-Arabic script. Urdu, Kaithi and Devanagari scripts are indigenous to India. The Urdu script is primarily used to write the Urdu language, while the Kaithi script is used for various languages, including Bhojpuri, Maithili, and Magahi. On the other hand, the Devanagari script is used for several languages, including Hindi, Marathi, Nepali, and Sanskrit. It is important to note that these scripts have evolved and have been influenced by various other scripts, such as Arabic, Persian, and Sanskrit. These scripts' continued use and preservation are crucial in maintaining India's diverse linguistic and cultural identity. In Urdu grammar, nouns are classified into two genders:

masculine and feminine. This classification is based on the natural gender of the object being referred to. The number of nouns in Urdu can be singular or plural. The plural form of a noun in Urdu is formed by adding a suffix to the singular form. This system of gender and number classification is an essential aspect of the Urdu language and is used extensively in its literature and everyday communication [2].

A. Urdu Morphology

It is suggested that Hindi and Urdu share 82% of their daily vocabulary [1, 3], but this number drops if we move to a more specific domain to 69% for tourist phrases. "Hindi" is a very loose term covering widely varying dialects. It has been used to develop multilingual grammars that can be used for translation. Authors in [3] demonstrated that Hindi and Urdu share a grammar, but the lexicons diverge hugely beyond basic and general registers. Telugu/Kannada uses a Sanskrit-based lexicon essentially identical to that of Hindi. Morphology

studies how words are formed out of smaller units called morphemes [4]. The various morphological processes employed in Urdu are: (i). Affixation, (ii) zero-modification, (iii) reduplication, (iv) internal-change, and (v) suppletion. Morphology is about the structure of words and is mainly concerned with the formation of words in human languages [5]. Urdu has many examples in which certain words are formed by repetitions of the same form. Bloomfield referred to inflection as the outer layer of the morphology of word forms and derivation as the inner layer. This inflectional affixation is not used to produce new words in Urdu, they are used only to indicate aspects of the grammatical function of a word. The Urdu post-positions: /par/, /se/, and /ne/ may be grouped in locative case markers. In three cases, Urdu nouns are inflected for two numbers, i.e. singular and plural, direct, oblique, and vocative. Urdu verbs have persons, numbers, gender, tense, mood, and aspect categories. The Urdu verb form agrees in gender and number with the subject.

B. Inflection

The affixations that precede or follow a language's root depend on the language typology [6]. The inflections of the language itself decide the concatenative and non-concatenative morphology. Many languages combine between regularity and irregularity of their word formation. The decision to address the morphology of a language as concatenative or non-concatenative depends on the grammarians. It is not valid for a language to be called non-concatenative language if some irregular word-formation processes are detected. What criteria have been followed to cluster language inflections or derivational? Like other languages, Urdu has regular and irregular word formations [7]. The distinction of gender and case in nouns in Urdu is inflected for two classes: the first is the number, singular or plural, and the second is based on declension, marked and unmarked types. Table I shows inflection paradigms in nouns. Table II shows noun inflections with examples [8]. The distinction is overtly noticed in number, gender, and case.

TABLE I. INFLECTION PARADIGMS IN NOUNS

		Singular		Plural		
		Direct	Oblique	Direct	Oblique	Vocative
Masculine	1 st	-ā		-e	-ō	-o
	2 nd				+ō	+o
Feminine	1 st	-ī, -i, -I, -yā		-iyā	-iyō	-iyō
	2 nd			+ē	+ō	+o

TABLE II. NOUN INFLECTION EXAMPLES

		Singular		Plural		
		Direct	Oblique	Direct	Oblique	Vocative
Masculine	1 st	larkā kuā	larke kuē	larkō kuō		larko
	2 nd		seb vālid cākū ādmī	sebō vālidō cākuō ādmīyō ⁴		pitāo ādmīyo

II. URDU COMPUTATIONAL MORPHOLOGY

Urdu computational morphology studies the way Urdu forms and structures words [9]. This field is concerned with

analyzing and understanding the rules and patterns that govern the formation of words in Urdu and using this knowledge to develop computational tools to process and analyze Urdu text. One of the main challenges in Urdu computational morphology is dealing with the complex inflectional and derivational morphological processes present in the language [10-12]. For example, Urdu verbs have a rich system of inflectional forms, which can change depending on factors such as tense, aspect, and person. Urdu nouns can also be inflected to indicate case and number and can be formed through various derivational processes. To address these challenges, researchers in the field of Urdu computational morphology have developed several different tools and techniques. One popular approach is to use rule-based methods, where a set of rules are defined for each morphological process, and these rules are then applied to words to analyze and generate new forms. Another approach is the utilization of statistical methods, where patterns in large text corpora are used to train computational models that can automatically identify and analyze morphological forms.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in using deep learning approaches for performing different Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks, e.g. Text Classification (TC), Question Answering (QA), Name Entity Recognition (NER), Sentiment Analysis (SA), etc. [13-15]. In the same way, deep learning techniques have been used for Urdu computational morphology. These techniques are effective in learning complex patterns in the language and have been used to develop many state-of-the-art tools for morphological analysis and generation in Urdu [16].

Urdu is a morphologically rich language with a complex system of inflections and derivations [17-19]. The main inflectional categories in Urdu include gender, number, case, and tense, while the main derivational processes include affixation, compounding, and conversion. In computational morphology, the task of analyzing and generating the inflected and derived forms of words is known as morphological analysis and generation [20]. Some computational approaches have been proposed for Urdu morphological analysis and generation, including rule-based, finite-state, and machine learning-based methods. Rule-based methods rely on manually crafted rules to analyze and generate inflected and derived forms, while finite-state methods use finite-state transducers to model the morphological processes of a language [21, 22]. On the other hand, machine learning-based methods use data-driven techniques such as neural networks to learn the morphological patterns of a language. One of the significant challenges in the computational morphology for Urdu is the large number of inflected and derived forms that a word can have. The rich inflectional system of Urdu, combined with relatively free word order, makes it challenging to analyze and generate inflected and derived forms fully automatically. However, recent advances in machine learning techniques have shown promise in addressing this challenge. The research on Urdu computational morphology is ongoing, focusing on developing more accurate and efficient morphological analysis and generation methods. This includes the use of neural networks, LSTM, and attention-based architectures for morphological analysis and generation, which perform well in Urdu.

III. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research questions for this study focus on the lexical processing of Urdu nouns inflection.

- Question one: Does the Urdu language have a concatenative inflective morphology system?
- Question two: Can finite-state machines process Urdu nouns systematically?

IV. RELATED WORK

Urdu and Hindi are quite similar on a spoken level, but Hindi is written in Devanagari script, which is entirely different from the Urdu script. Regarding linguistics, morphology refers to the formation of words by focusing on their internal structure. Morphology is divided into two classes: inflectional morphology and derivational morphology. NLP is the primary interface between humans and computers. It is considered a branch of Artificial Intelligence (AI). Authors in [23] studied rule-based stemmer in Urdu and presented a rule-based stemmer for Urdu. They stated that stemming is a process in which affixes are separated from their root word. Their work was restricted to the Urdu language, which meant that the root word was not extracted from other languages like English, Persian, and Arabic. This stemming algorithm separated prefixes, suffixes, and infixes. It matched the word with the affixes and pulled out the word. The system and evaluation exhibited 86.5% accuracy. Authors in [24] developed an approach for building a finite-state morphological analyzer for Urdu and Hindi that is compatible with the XFST tools already used in both scripts. That was a part of the ParGram project, and they developed a grammar for South Asian Urdu. Very few resources exist for this language, and no broad-coverage finite-state morphological analyzer existed before this study. The approach allowed for an underlyingly similar treatment of Urdu and Hindi via a cascade of finite-state transducers that transliterate the very different scripts into a standard ASCII transcription system. The paper has addressed several issues in building a finite-state morphological analyzer for Urdu. The authors further explored the reduplication in Urdu, again based on solutions proposed concerning XFST. The discussion in their study mainly revolves around where and how information should be encoded concerning the morphology-syntax interface that has been defined between finite-state morphological analyzers and lexical-functional grammar. An improved statistical morph analyzer for Hindi, Urdu, Telugu and Tamil, was conducted in [25]. The authors proposed a statistical morph analyzer for Indian languages. The gender, number, person, and case accuracy was 86.81% for Telugu and 78.97% for Tamil. They studied two families of Indian languages, Indic and Dravidian, because most Indian languages fall into these two groups. Morphological analysis for Indian languages was conducted using the rule-based approach. Experiments were conducted for the four Indian Languages [ILs] mentioned above. The results were compared to Morfette (M) [26] and SMA [27]. The authors reported that for all four ILs, SMA++ outperforms the other SMAs. For Hindi and Urdu the L+G+N+P+C accuracy was 85.87%. For Telugu, the accuracy was 86.81%, and for Tamil, it was 78.97%. Authors in [28] reported a rule-based implementation of a morphological

analyzer for Hindi. The study focused on designing a morphological analyzer for Hindi, a language rich in morphemes, which can be used for machine translation, which works on a rule-based approach and maintains a database for exceptions. The authors propose that the system's accuracy is very high as all the possible exceptions are covered. The word sense disambiguation can be integrated with this analyzer so that the words having multiple senses can be analyzed accurately. Authors in [29] studied the influence of morphology on word recognition in Hindi and Urdu. Hindi showed priming for morphologically and form-related primes, but the morphology study was not advantageous. Urdu showed faster latencies for targets preceded by morphologically related primes relative to those preceded by form-related primes. The evidence shows that the phonological, orthographic, and semantic/syntactic characteristics influence the visual recognition of the words presented in isolation. Targets were Urdu words of one syllable paired with two-syllable primes of three types.

V. FINITE STATE MACHINE (FSM)

An FSM is a mathematical model representing a language's morphological processes [30]. In the case of Urdu, an FSM could be used to model the language's inflectional and derivational processes and generate inflected and derived forms of words. FSMs are used to identify the regularity forms in a language by using a regular expression to perform the process of inflection morphology. The computational and linguistic components are represented together to produce the correct grammar forms using FSMs. The machines are used in NLP to construct lexical analyzers and to compile derivational and inflectional rules of language morphology using finite state tools, and a lexical analyzer was developed for the Urdu nominal system. A regular expression and the inflectional rules of the natural language can represent the set of strings S . The processing and the output can be represented and recognized by the FSA as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Finite-state automaton.

Formally, a finite-state is represented by $M = (S, \Sigma, s_0, \delta, F)$ where: S a finite set of states, $S = \{S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3\}$, Σ is a finite set of input symbols called the alphabet (root. reg, Infl. reg, Num., Gen), δ is a transition function ($\delta: S \times \Sigma \rightarrow S$), S_0 is the start state ($s_0 \in S$), and F is a set of finite states called accepting or final states. In Figure, it is $F \subseteq S_3$.

VI. LEXICON

Lexicon generates entries for computational morphological analysis in the framework of finite-state morphology and uses

instance, this sample has 10 roots and 12 inflection forms. The transition performs using 70 states, 85 arcs, and 20 paths. All the possible forms are generated with other linguistic information related to nouns in Urdu. Figure 5 shows a sample of one possible output wordlist of an FSM for the Urdu language and the readable output with all the needed features of the Urdu nominal systems. The first generated form is the singular and the plural nouns. Then the number, gender, and person singular and plural nouns are generated.

The output data extracted from the developed lexicon are evaluated with the correct forms of the different types of nouns in Urdu: the proposed computational algorithm and linguistic analysis were assessed with the high accuracy of 92.7%. Table IV displays the obtained results.

	1	2	
1	l a r k + N +MS +SG +D		
2	l a r k a 0 0 0 0		
3			
4	l a r k + N + R		
5	l a r k 0 0 0 0		
6			
7	b a c c h i + N +PL		
8	b a c c h i y a n		
9			
10	b a c c h i + N +SG		
11	b a c c h i 0 0 0		
12			
13	d a w a y i + N +PL		
14	d a w a y i y a n		
15			
16	d a w a y i + N +SG		
17	d a w a y i 0 0 0		
18			
19	k a l a m + N +PL		
20	k a l a m e i n		
21			
22	k a l a m + N +SG		
23	k a l a m 0 0 0		
24			
25	k a m r a + N +PL		
26	k a m r a e 0 0		
27			
28	k a m r a + N +SG		
29	k a m r a 0 0 0		
30			
31	r a s t a + N +PL		
32	r a s t a e 0 0		
33			
34	r a s t a + N +SG		
35	r a s t a 0 0 0		
36			
37	p a n k h a + N +PL		
38	p a n k h a e 0 0		
39			
40	p a n k h a + N +SG		
41	p a n k h a 0 0 0		

Fig. 5. Singular and plural output wordlist sample.

TABLE IV. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS DATA AND RESULTS

Data (roots)	Correct output	Generated forms	Accuracy
2000	95.4%	30.000	92.7%
1000	96.6%	15.000	90.4%

The above statistical analysis shows that Urdu has a concatenative morphological system. The Deterministic Finite-State Morphological Analyzer tool is designed to analyze the morphology of Urdu nouns. It operates based on a FSM, which allows it to accurately identify and classify the various

morphemes that make up a given word. This tool is highly effective in identifying the root of a word, as well as its various inflections and derivations. Its deterministic nature ensures consistent and reliable results, making it an essential tool for researchers working with language data.

IX. DISCUSSION

In this work, an attempt was made to develop a morphological analyzer for the low-source language Urdu. The first research question focused on the concatenative nature of Urdu noun forms. The study utilized an FSM to generate a morphological analysis of Urdu nouns. Figure 3 displays the regularity in most of the nominal forms of Urdu, which is consistent with previous research on the topic [9, 18, 24]. The study's findings reveal that Urdu has a concatenative system in the context of the noun forms, consistent with [18] in which it was reported that Urdu has a concatenative inflective morphology system. However, there are some exceptions when it comes to causative verbs, which can exhibit stem-internal changes in some instances. The data highlight the significance of comprehending the linguistic characteristics of all potential inputs that can be utilized by the tool. This understanding can ultimately result in improved output quality.

The finite-state tool was utilized to process noun inflection in Urdu. Figure 2 shows the lexicon development and rule generation to enable the FSM to produce all possible noun forms, each with its corresponding linguistic description. This approach effectively addressed the research question two. This study analyzed the rules and patterns that govern the formation of words in Urdu. The goal was to develop computational tools to process and analyze Urdu inflections. By understanding the intricacies of Urdu word formation, the accuracy and efficiency of language processing tools can be improved. The output displays various inflected forms of Urdu nouns, such as singular and plural forms, cases, and different grammatical genders. The specific morphological processes provided by the finite state tools and the detailed design of the FSM determine the actual output. The accuracy score of the analysis is above 90%. The FSM ensures accuracy and completeness in analyzing and creating these forms. This approach achieves a comprehensive understanding of noun forms, allowing for precise communication in written language.

X. CONCLUSION

This paper focused on the Urdu computational morphology using finite states to generate a morphological analysis for Urdu nouns. This study is concerned with analyzing and understanding the rules and patterns governing the formation of Urdu words. The objective is to use this knowledge to develop computational tools to process and analyze Urdu nouns. The output showcases Urdu nouns' inflected and derived forms, including singular and plural forms, various cases, and grammatical genders. The specific morphological processes used by the finite state tools, along with the detailed design of the finite state machine, determine the precise output. Overall, this paper contributes to computational morphology by comprehensively understanding finite-state technology's use in analyzing Urdu nouns' morphology. This study is limited to

Urdu noun forms analysis, and future studies will focus on other lexical categories of Urdu.

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A Contemporary House Proposal: Structural Analysis of Wood and Steel Bungalows

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ABSTRACT

The housing typologies that meet shelter and other basic needs are diverse, and bungalows are one of them. These buildings are generally single-story and mostly use wooden building materials. This paper introduces a new construction technique using steel, which is more durable than typical wooden bungalow houses. This design aimed to create a new building stock based on the logic of mass production, where modular steel bars can be prefabricated and transported to the construction site. An architectural design with a steel construction instead of a wooden one and a hexagonal plan instead of a rectangular one was developed. Structures designed with wooden and steel materials were compared using the structural analysis method. Structural analysis of the construction designs using wood and S235 steel grade was performed with the SAP2000 software. The structures were evaluated according to displacement, modal analysis periods, and self-weight, and their static suitability was tested. This new architectural design was developed because steel can maintain its strength for a long time compared to wood and has a higher modulus of elasticity. The results showed that wood and steel materials exhibit similar behavior under the same cross-sections, but the steel structure has come to the forefront as it is lighter than wood in terms of self-weight.

Keywords-building design; bungalow; house; steel construction; structural analysis; wood construction

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of home has a different meaning for each person, as some people define it as a living space while others define it as a place of entertainment, rest, and sleep. Considering the house as a sheltering need is an indicator of its main function [1]. The origin of single-family houses dates back 2,000 years [2]. As the world population increases, housing production increases to meet current demands in the housing sector [3]. Parameters such as awareness, sense of responsibility, and waste management should be considered along with the increase in housing production [4]. High productivity, efficiency, quality, and sustainable steps are nowadays widely considered in the construction sector [5-6]. Sustainable architectural approaches to environmental problems are being developed for new houses to be built [3, 7]. Bungalows account for one such house type. In general, single-story bungalows without stairs form a living space [8]. Since this living space consists of a single space, it can have a simple

basic geometry, or it can be produced from parametric plans using various shapes [9].

Colony-shaped portable bungalow prototypes have been used in the construction of modern houses [10]. Several studies have been conducted on bungalows. In 1999, a bungalow was designed in Malaysia with a photovoltaic panel system installed on its roof, and energy tests were carried out [11]. A study conducted in Great Britain showed that heating costs in detached houses and bungalows were higher than those in apartments [12]. Performance and economic analyses were performed with photovoltaic panels for a bungalow house in Damansara, Malaysia in [13]. Noise analysis was carried out in bungalow houses in the context of acoustics in England, evaluating environmental and socio-economic factors [14]. Thermal comfort tests and experiments were carried out in a detached bungalow-type house in Ireland using smart algorithms [15]. In building design, the use of materials is also important. In [16], wood and steel-reinforced concrete were

evaluated in housing construction in terms of energy use and emissions. In [17], the mechanical properties and manufacturing technologies of engineered wood and bamboo composite materials were investigated and compared. In [18], cross-laminated timber and concrete slab flooring were analyzed in terms of structural performance, cost, and greenhouse gas emissions. The use of different approaches in building designs requires considering different parameters. Integration of different parameters improves the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry. In addition to material differentiation, design phases [19-20], cost analyses [21-23], and entrepreneurial views [24] also contribute to the AEC industry.

As most of the bungalow studies are focused on energy, it can be observed that the structural analysis studies on bungalows and material comparison are limited. This study presents a contemporary bungalow proposal, performing a design and structural analysis comparison of a bungalow made of wooden and steel materials and hexagonal form, by bringing a new perspective to bungalows in traditional materials and forms. The structural analyses of the constructions designed with wood, which is a traditional building material, and S235 steel class were compared using the SAP2000 software and the finite element method. This software offers 2D and 3D modeling possibilities, from simple to complex geometries, that accelerate the engineering processes [25].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bungalow houses are usually built with wooden materials. This study used S235 steel, which is a frequently used and long-lasting building material [26-27]. The reason for choosing steel is its robustness, its ability to be used in frame systems, and its potential for improved aesthetics and functionality. Although wooden construction materials are also used in frame systems, when compared to steel in the same span, the material cross-section is larger and does not provide an effective solution. While there are common structural steel types such as S235 (St37), S275 (St44), and S355 (St52), S235 unalloyed structural steel has higher strength, is used by steel manufacturers and designers in Turkey, and is wider than other steel types [28]. Figure 1 shows the flowchart of this study.

Fig. 1. Flow chart of the study.

The displacements in the X and Y directions were calculated under self-loads, considering weights for the structural analysis of the wooden and steel structures. The required strength for the system and elements was determined according to different critical load combinations, specifically: $G+Q$, $1.4G$, and $1.2G+1.6Q$. The mode values were also used to determine the dynamic state of the designs. Fixed support was used for the elements of the structures that rest on the ground. Steel construction profiles can be produced in square, rectangular, and pipe forms. For the steel cross-section, a hollow circular steel structural element was chosen to avoid sharp ends in frame systems and provide ease of application. Similarly, the wooden structure used circular structural elements. The wood and steel construction elements had a pipe section of 500mm in diameter, and the steel construction elements had a wall thickness of 15mm. Table I shows the properties of the structural wood and steel used in the designs.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF STRUCTURAL MATERIALS

WOOD	Density	0.800kg/m ³	Shear modulus	3800N/mm ²
	Modulus of elasticity	9.8GPa (9800MPa)	Poisson's ratio	0.3
STEEL	Density	7,850kg/m ³	Minimum yield strength of steel	235N/mm ²
	Modulus of elasticity	200GPa (200000MPa)	Poisson's ratio	0.286-0.315 (0.3 taken.)
	Shear modulus	8100kN/cm ²	Tensile strength	360–510MPa

III. CASE STUDY – BUNGALOW HOUSE

Bungalow houses can be used in the countryside and provide the opportunity to live a life in touch with nature. Today, the importance of nature is more evident in the city centers due to the dense construction and population. This study considered a steel-built design, which is an innovative and sustainable building material that does not take up much space. The design focused to keep the construction area small on the land by increasing the vertical elevation of the structure. To this result, the upward-rising structure was expanded, and the architectural spaces were increased. Structural elements must be modular manufactured for easier transport. In the design, the steel elements that form the frame of the building should be manufactured as modular and transported to the construction site. The geometry of the structure was formed from a regular hexagon, which allows steel members of equal length to be produced modularly. The durability and the cost of the two types of structures were investigated. Figure 2 shows the appearance of the designed bungalows.

Fig. 2. The exterior and the location of the bungalow.

Figure 3 shows the structural design. The structure rises 12m on a regular hexagonal plan, covers a 12×12m area, and has an expanded frame with a 1.5-meter-long cantilever. After raising 6m, the frame of the structure narrows, and a square horizontal frame of 6×6m was obtained at the top level of 12m. The building structure was completely formed from wooden and S235 steel structural materials. A beam was added between the two longest corners of the regular hexagon geometry at the 6-meter level. Wooden and steel construction elements were connected with rigid connections.

Fig. 3. The structure of the bungalow and the connections of the steel elements.

The total mass and rigidity of the structure with the incoming loads affect the amount of displacement. In addition, the calculation of vibration periods plays an important role. In steel frames, the material and its diameter along with the thickness of the wall cause these values to vary [29]. The elastic properties of the structure should also be considered during the design phase [30]. Using displacement data, the static and dynamic properties of buildings are analyzed for safety [31], while displacement also changes the performance-based designs [32]. Table II shows the values of the building structures according to the displacement analyses.

TABLE II. DISPLACEMENTS UNDER SELF-LOADING

WOOD		Δx	Δy	Δz
	Displacement under self-loads	-	-	-0.42mm
Displacement in the X-direction	1.35mm	-	0.7mm	
Displacement in the Y-direction	-	2.04mm	0.98mm	
STEEL	Displacement under self-loads	-	-	-0.33mm
	Displacement in the X-direction	1.53mm	-	0.76mm
	Displacement in the Y-direction	-	2.13mm	1.05mm

The performance analysis identified the period values of the system. Mode values are defined as the values of the natural vibration period on the principal axes of the structure [33]. The mode concept plays a role in showing the deformation patterns of periods. Modal analysis is also essential for determining structural damage [34]. In the mode values, the first three values of the natural vibration period with the highest mass participation are considered. The connection points of the bar elements also play an active role in the mode values [35]. This study examined the first three mode values that provide the most mass participation in terms of mode value. Horizontal and vertical vibration periods may occur in three-dimensional structures. A high period value means low rigidity, as there is an inverse proportional situation. At this point, a comparison between the period value and stiffness can be made. Table III shows the mode values of the structural system. The total

weights of the structures having the same geometry and cross-sections of the structural elements were obtained. By looking at the total weight values, inferences can be made about the costs. Table IV shows the weights of the wood and steel structure designs.

TABLE III. DEFORMATIONS AND FIRST NATURAL VIBRATION PERIODS

WOOD		
Mode-1	Mode-2	Mode-3
0.09s	0.09s	0.06s
STEEL		
Mode-1	Mode-2	Mode-3
0.31s	0.28s	0.21s

TABLE IV. TOTAL WEIGHTS OF STRUCTURES (Kg)

Self weight of the systems	
Wood	Steel
6805kg	3467kg

IV. CONCLUSION

Building construction techniques vary according to the characteristics of the buildings. There are also different construction techniques in houses. Structure materials used in houses have changed from the past to the present. The use of local materials, which are found predominantly in the construction area, is dominant in the construction of buildings. The use of local materials is at the forefront in bungalows, which form one of the housing types. These structures have been used in different combinations throughout history. It is possible to encounter this situation in the need for luxury housing or accommodation for refugees. This study presented a new architectural design for such buildings. The design used high-strength steel for the construction due to its innovative and durable characteristics. The proposed steel design was evaluated by comparing it with a similar wooden one.

Structural analyses were performed on the two bungalow designs. At first, the displacement of the structures under self-loads was examined. Due to the tests carried out toward gravity and along the X and Y-axis, it was observed that the maximum displacement values were in the Y-axis direction. Considering the displacement values obtained, it can be inferred that the proposed steel system provides positive feedback. The modal analysis results showed that an ideal system was designed. A comparison of the self-weights of the structures shows that the wooden material is approximately 50.1% heavier than steel, providing an advantage for the steel load-bearing design. As a result, the designed steel bungalow house met the structural criteria, showing its advantages and usability.

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Sustainable Hybrid Design to Ensure Efficiency and Air Quality of Solar Air Conditioning

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ABSTRACT

This research work aims to investigate and subsequently optimize the operating parameters that affect thermal comfort and indoor air quality in the school environment. The proposed design uses a coupling between solar ventilation and the absorption chiller-air conditioning. The heating tower of an adsorption chiller connected to an air conditioning system can be driven by the waste heat from a solar ventilation (exhausted hot air) system thanks to this linkage. In order to simulate variables like the velocity magnitude distribution in the air-conditioned room, mathematical modeling is numerically executed. Air temperature evolution along the height of the conditioned room in the mid-length and the air velocity evolution along the length of the conditioned room in the mid-height are studied. According to the numerical simulation results, the inlet air temperature soars as the inlet air velocity rises. Inlet air velocities of 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s are correlated with inlet air temperatures of 20.7°C, 21.2°C, and 21.3°C, respectively. We conclude that an inlet air velocity in the order of 1m/s (in relation to a maximized air change rate) is in agreement with the general ASHRAE standards for indoor air quality in the case of the school environment, coupled with the essential need to limit as much as possible the spread of viruses.

Keywords-solar air conditioning absorption; ventilation; human comfort

I. INTRODUCTION

The indoor air quality and the thermal comfort in school environment are highly important factors that affect learning and teaching performance. The optimization of such factors within the appropriate standards, will ensure healthy indoor air quality and enhance the human thermal comfort. In this framework, the recent literature reveals some interesting works. Authors in [1] carried out an integrated experimental and simulation approach in order to evaluate the Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), principally in terms of acceptable thermal level as well as indoor air quality, under the climate conditions of Florina, Western Macedonia, Greece. Authors in [2] monitored the Indoor Air quality, in terms of air temperature, air relative humidity, CO₂ concentration, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, in 10 school classrooms, over a period of one year and under the climate conditions of Victoria, Australia. Results show that the ventilation rates should be increased. Authors in [3] modeled and simulated the effect of wind tower ventilation on classroom thermal comfort during August under the climate conditions of Trabzon, Turkey. The results show that the wind tower ventilation often induces thermal discomfort under the considered climate conditions. Authors in [4] compared different standards to assess the indoor air quality and the thermal comfort in school buildings, under the northern Italy

climate conditions. The results show principally that the operative temperature is the most appropriate way to establish and check thermal comfort in classrooms.

The COVID-19 pandemic renewed the interest in indoor air quality and ventilation, in order to limit viruses spreading especially in school environment. Authors in [5] investigated the effects of measures, associated to the COVID-19 pandemic control and prevention, on the ventilation and thermal conditions in 31 Dutch secondary school classrooms. The results show principally that the ventilation rate is enhanced mainly thanks to the occupancy reduction after the COVID-19 lockdown. Also, it was shown that the doors and windows openings were not enough to reach the required ventilation rate. Authors in [6] evaluated the SARS-CoV-2 airborne risk of infection based on natural ventilation rate calculation in an elementary school classroom, under the climate conditions of Uruguay. The results show that periodic ventilation permits to significantly reduce the airborne transmission, even if it is carried out during short time spans.

In the same context, sustainable and hybrid natural ventilation-air conditioning systems are more and more developed to create indoor air quality as well as thermal comfort. Authors in [7] designed a new sustainable hybrid solar ventilation-air conditioning system and investigated its

ventilation and thermal performances under the climate conditions of Gafsa, Tunisia. Technologically speaking, the ventilation is ensured by a solar chimney system while the air conditioning is based on desiccation and adsorption chilling. The coupling between the solar ventilation and the solar air conditioning is based on the use of the wasted heat of the hot air, coming from the outlet of the chimney, to power the heating tower and regenerate the desiccation compartment of the air conditioning system. Authors in [8] proposed a novel natural ventilation design called wind chimney. This design permits to create natural ventilation in buildings located in zones with dominant wind flow, based on aerodynamics law and air pressure difference caused by wind flow. Authors in [9] investigated the impact of the meteorological conditions on the daily incident solar flux on the facades of a house at Adrar region, Algeria. Authors in [10] demonstrated by numerical simulation that the temperature of the internal air varies with climate conditions, location, number of covers, and the solar greenhouse shape. Roofs may be used to generate electricity by connecting PV systems. Authors in [11] studied the solar energy potential and presented an economic study of a 5kW grid-connected rooftop photovoltaic (PV) system in Botswana. Many researchers have proposed hybrid systems for air conditioning, electricity production, and desalination. Authors in [12] presented a solar hybrid system designed for water desalination, air-conditioning, and electricity production.

In Saudi Arabia, individuals are investing more time inside buildings where the utilization of air conditioning is essential. In schools, the chance of disease spreading through bead and vaporized transmission is exceptionally high. Fitting ventilation/air recharging might be a proficient arrangement to decrease infection transmission or other chemical of physical operators delivered by actions (e.g. cooking or smoking) or environment (e.g. sandstorms). It is critical to create advances and consider techniques to handle hyperthermia.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The proposed design, shown in Figure 1, uses a coupling between the solar ventilation and the absorption chiller-air conditioning. This coupling permits to recover the waste heat of a solar ventilation (exhausted hot air) system and reuse it to drive the heating tower of an adsorption chiller associated to an air conditioning system. A solar chimney system oriented south is used to ventilate a conditioned space naturally, and an absorption chiller-air conditioning system is used to cool it. In particular, in terms of clothes insulation and air renewal, the suggested design should ensure a person's thermal comfort and a healthy indoor air quality. The air gap is heated by the solar chimney system using the greenhouse effect. This will create a pressure difference that will allow the expelled air from the conditioned room outlet (the solar chimney's inlet (3)) to be driven in the direction of the absorption chiller's heating tower (7-8). The heating tower should be heated and driven by an auxiliary heater AH (6-7) associated with an auxiliary blower AV (5-6) if the heat from the considered ejected air is inadequate to run the heating tower correctly (insufficient solar energy). The absorption chiller can be powered by the cooling and heating towers. The result is the production of the storage of cold water in a cold-water tank, and its use in a water-air

radiator (heat exchanger (9)). The blower V1 (1) draws in fresh air (I-Air) from the outside, which is then cooled by the water-air radiator (2). The final step is to inject the obtained process air into the conditioned chamber after being dusted off through the filter F1 (3).

Fig. 1. The proposed solar ventilation-absorption air conditioning system design.

III. MATHEMATICAL MODELING

Special interest is given to the examination of the ventilation and thermal performance of the conditioned area. In this way, the suitable numerical modeling is based on the Navier-Stokes conditions in terms of progression condition, x and y-momentums conditions, vitality preservation condition as well as turbulent dynamic vitality and turbulent scattering [4]. The heat exchange model is considered in bi-dimensional steady state with the k-ε turbulence model. The Boussinesq estimation is expected since the air temperature contrast between solar chimney inlet and outlet is considered low.

A. Continuity Equation

The continuity equation reflects the principle of mass conservation in terms of relation between the air velocity and the cross-sectional area through which the fluid flows. The decrease of this cross-sectional area induces an increase of air velocity. The continuity equation is written as:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

B. Momentum Equations

The momentum equations reflect the principle of linear momentum conservation along a specific direction in space. The momentum of an object is the product of its mass and its linear velocity. It represents the quantity of motion of the considered object. The momentum equations along the x- and y-directions of the space are written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial uu}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial vu}{\partial y} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) \\ &+ \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left((\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial uv}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v^2}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \\ + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left((\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x} + g\beta(T - T_0) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

C. Energy Conservation Equation

As its name suggests, this equation reflects the principle of energy conservation. It expresses the first law of thermodynamics as a balance equation for the rate of change of kinetic energy and internal energy. The energy conservation equation is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial uT}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial vT}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left(\frac{\mu}{Pr} + \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) \\ + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\left(\frac{\mu}{Pr} + \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

D. Turbulent Kinetic Energy

The turbulent kinetic energy k reflects the intensity of turbulence in a flow. The equation governing the transport of the turbulent kinetic energy k is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial uk}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial vk}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_k}{Pr_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x} \right) \\ + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_k}{Pr_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho} (G_k + G_b) - \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

E. Turbulence Dissipation

The turbulent dissipation reflects the viscous conversion of mechanical energy to heat. The equation governing the turbulence dissipation ε is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u\varepsilon}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v\varepsilon}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_\varepsilon}{Pr_\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x} \right) \\ + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_\varepsilon}{Pr_\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial y} \right) + C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{\rho k} (G_k + C_{3\varepsilon} G_b) \\ - C_{2\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where the empirical constants $C_{1\varepsilon}$, $C_{2\varepsilon}$ and $C_{3\varepsilon}$ have the values of 1.44, 1.92, and 0.09, respectively, Pr_k and Pr_ε , are the turbulent Prandtl numbers for the variables k and ε having values of 1.0 and 1.3, respectively, and G_k indicates the gradients in mean velocity:

$$G_k = \mu_t \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} - \frac{2}{3} \rho k \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \quad (7)$$

G_b represents the production of the turbulent kinetic energy due to the buoyancy:

$$G_b = \beta g_i \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \quad (8)$$

It can be concluded that the mathematical modeling governing the ventilation and the thermal performance of the conditioned area was elaborated under the assumptions of Boussinesq approximation as well as the bi-dimensional steady state heat transfer with the k- ε turbulence model. In the next section, this mathematical modeling is numerically implemented. The simulation results are presented and discussed.

IV. RESULTS

A. Air Flow within the Conditioned Room

Figure 2 shows the air velocity magnitude distribution within a conditioned room with length $X=4\text{m}$ and height $H=3\text{m}$. The inlet of the air is located to the lower right wall, while the outlet air is connected to the inlet of the solar chimney and it is located in the top of left wall. The inlet air velocity is varied as 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s. It is clear that the air breeze (forced air flow) carried out between the air inlet and the outlet keeps almost the same shape with a global air velocity enhancement as the inlet air velocity increases. The global air velocity distribution above the air breeze is slightly more pronounced than that below. This is expected since the space occupied by the air above the air breeze is significantly larger than that below. It should be also noted that the air velocity magnitude in the neighborhood of the air outlet is enhanced. This is expected since the air outlet is connected to the solar chimney inlet where a strong air suction effect is applied.

Fig. 2. Air velocity magnitude distribution in the conditioned room.

Figure 3 depicts the vertical evolution of the air velocity along the height of the conditioned room in the mid-length level defined by $x=2m$. The inlet air velocity is 1m/s, 0.5m/s, and 0.05m/s. The room air velocity rapidly increases from 0.26m/s, 0.14m/s, and 0.02m/s to reach a maxima in the neighborhood of $h=0.7m$ of 0.91m/s, 0.45m/s, and 0.05m/s for an inlet air velocity in the order of 1m/s, 0.5m/s, and 0.05m/s, respectively. This is expected since the air velocity in this room region (room bottom) is highly influenced by the air breeze carried out between the air inlet and outlet of the conditioned room. Between $h=0.7m$ and $h=1.45m$, the room air velocity rapidly decreases to 0.3m/s, 0.15m/s, and 0.05m/s for an inlet air velocity of 1m/s, 0.5m/s and 0.05m/s respectively. Between $h=1.45m$ and $h=2.6m$, the room air velocity moderately decreases to 0.04m/s, 0.02m/s, and 0.005m/s for an inlet air velocity in the order of 1m/s, 0.5m/s, and 0.05m/s, respectively. This is expected since this room region is relatively far from the influence of the air. Between $h=2.6m$ and $h=3m$, the room air velocity moderately increases to reach 0.12m/s, 0.06m/s, and 0.01m/s for an inlet air velocity of 1m/s, 0.5m/s, and 0.05m/s respectively. This is expected since this room region is close to the inlet of the solar chimney (located in the top region of the room) where the air velocity is more pronounced due to the strong suction effect induced by the solar chimney. It should be noted that the air velocity increase and decrease rates are more pronounced for higher inlet air velocity.

Fig. 3. Air velocity evolution along the height of the conditioned room in the mid-length.

B. Air Temperature in the Conditioned Room

Figure 4 depicts the horizontal evolution of the air temperature along the length of the conditioned room in the mid-height level defined by $h=1.5m$. The inlet air velocity is varied as 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s. The room air temperature rapidly decreases from 21.8°C, 22.4°C, and 22.45°C to a minimum in the neighborhood of $x=0.5m$ (left side of the room) of 17.2°C, 17.1°C, and 17.1°C, for an inlet air velocity of 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s, respectively. Between $x=0.5m$ and $x=1.1m$, the room air temperature evolutions rapidly increase to 18.4°C, 18°C and 17.9°C for inlet air velocity of 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s respectively. This important increase and decrease rates are expected since the convection in

this room region (close to the inlet of the solar chimney) is enhanced by the pronounced air velocity caused by the strong suction effect induced by the solar chimney. Between $x=1.1m$ and $x=3.5m$, the room air temperature evolutions stagnate around 18.3°C, 17.9°C, and 17.8°C for an inlet air velocity in the order of 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s, respectively. Between $x=3.5m$ and $x=4m$, the room air temperature drastically increases to 20.7°C, 21.2°C, and 21.3°C for inlet air velocity of 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s, respectively. It should be noted that the air velocity increase and decrease rates are more pronounced for higher inlet air velocity.

Fig. 4. Air temperature evolution along the length of the conditioned room at the mid-height.

Fig. 5. Air temperature evolution along the height of the conditioned room in the mid-length.

Figure 5 depicts the vertical evolution of the air temperature along the height of the conditioned room in the mid-length level defined by $x=2m$. The inlet air velocity is varied as 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s. The room air temperature rapidly decreases from 19.47°C, 19.89°C, and 19.93°C to reach a minimum in the neighborhood of $h=0.6m$ (left side of the room) in the order of 17.0°C for all inlet air velocity values. Between $x=0.6m$ and $x=1.35m$, the room air temperature rapidly increases to 18.5°C, 18.1°C, and 17.95°C for inlet air

velocity of 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s, respectively. It is to note that the air velocity increase and decrease rates are slightly more pronounced for higher inlet air velocity values. These increase and decrease rates are expected since the convection in this room region (located in the bottom side of the room) is highly influenced by the air breeze carried out between the air inlet and outlet of the conditioned room. Between $h=1.35\text{m}$ and $h=3\text{m}$, the room air temperature stagnates around 18.35°C , 17.95°C , and 17.85°C for inlet air velocity of 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s, respectively.

C. Thermal Comfort and Indoor Air Quality

The proposed design ensures two tasks:

- Acceptable thermal comfort in a school environment.
- Acceptable indoor air quality in a school environment.

The comfort zone is within the air temperature range from 18°C to 27°C while the air relative humidity range is from 20% to 80% with a slight air temperature limitation from 28°C to 25°C when the relative humidity passes from 50% to 80%. Taking into account the morning air relative humidity in the region of Bisha, Saudi Arabia in May and June (globally around 47% and 29%, respectively), it is easy to locate the (inlet air temperature, inlet air relative humidity) points on the psychrometric chart. Figure 6 shows that the inlet air is within the thermal comfort zone for both May and June.

Fig. 6. Inlet air within the comfort zone in May and June.

V. DISCUSSION AND OPTIMIZATION OF AIR CONDITIONING PARAMETERS

In this paper, the two major air-conditioning parameters, inlet air temperature and inlet air velocity, are optimized with the goal of improving thermal comfort and indoor air quality in the school environment. The air-conditioning optimization should ensure a compromise between appropriate inlet air temperature and inlet air velocity, inducing the highest possible air change rate and the lowest possible air temperature, while remaining within the limits of human thermal comfort.

According to the results of numerical simulations, the inlet air temperature rises as the inlet air velocity rises (this is directly related to the air change rate). Inlet air temperatures in

the order of 20.7°C , 21.2°C , and 21.3°C are associated to inlet air velocities in the order of 0.05m/s, 0.5m/s, and 1m/s, respectively. The inlet air velocity in the range of 0.05m/s is disallowed within the parameters of the optimization under consideration because it causes stagnation, which significantly worsens thermal comfort and raises the risk of virus transmission. Thus, an inlet air velocity in the order of 0.5m/s that is associated to the lowest inlet air temperature (21.2°C), shall be selected as a primary choice. However, the inlet air temperature associated to an inlet air velocity of 1m/s is in the order of 21.3°C . So, it is clear that there is no perceptible air temperature difference when the inlet air velocity passes from 0.5m/s to 1m/s. It is appropriate to choose, as the final optimization step, an inlet air velocity in the order of 1m/s associated with an inlet air temperature in the order of 21.3°C because the air change rate should be maximized as much as possible. The general ASHRAE standards [13] for indoor air quality in the case of a school environment, along with the crucial need to limit the spread of viruses as much as possible, are in agreement with an inlet air velocity in the order of 1m/s (in relation with a maximized air change rate).

VI. CONCLUSION

The ability to create thermal comfort in the conditioned area and its thermal performance are numerically investigated, presented, and discussed in this paper. It is appropriate to select an inlet air velocity of 1m/s and an inlet air temperature of 21.3°C because the air change rate should be increased as much as possible in the school environment to prevent virus spreading. Future research on the hybrid solar ventilation-air conditioning design is conceivable, with the goal of enhancing its ventilation, hygrometric, and thermal performance along with its sustainability in relation to the use of solar energy. Also, a desiccant compartment can be integrated and investigated in order to improve the hygrometric and thermal capacities of the considered air-conditioning system. It should be noted that an appropriate coupling between the solar ventilation system and the desiccant compartment can be studied in the future.

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Reliability-Constrained Optimal Scheduling of Interconnected Microgrids

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) optimization model for the scheduling problem of the interconnected microgrid system. The proposed model is capable of efficiently minimizing the microgrids' total operating costs and improving the entire system's reliability, as it is constrained based on enhancing the interconnected microgrids' reliability. The Expected Energy Not Supplied (EENS) is considered in order to ensure minimizing the interconnected microgrids' power deficiency. Furthermore, the proposed model has the capability to solve the optimization problem considering the islanded operation of the interconnected microgrids, i.e. when disturbances occur on the upstream grid. Numerical simulations on a test system containing three interconnected microgrids are performed to evaluate the effectiveness of the model and the results demonstrate the merits and features of the reliability-constrained optimal scheduling model in minimizing the interconnected microgrids' total operating costs and enhancing the interconnected system reliability.

Keywords-distributed energy resources; Expected Energy Not Supplied (EENS); interconnected microgrids; islanded operation; optimization; optimal scheduling

I. INTRODUCTION

The reliability of power systems is one of the most important factors of human quality of life, as power outages for a few minutes may cause serious problems [1-4]. Therefore, it is significant to constantly develop and improve the reliability of power systems in order to maintain their quality and sustainability [5-8]. Enhancing and evaluating the power systems' reliability has been extensively researched and analyzed. Authors in [9] investigated the reliability analysis of the IEEE40-bus system coupled with enormous PV and wind systems. By dividing the power system layout into various parts, the zone branch approach was used to evaluate the reliability parameters of the distribution systems. In [10], a cost-reliability bi-objective optimization model was developed for microgrids to acquire the optimal sizing and siting of energy storage systems. The developed model included minimizing the microgrid's total cost and Loss Of Load Expectation (LOLE) and the ϵ -constraint method and fuzzy satisfying technique were utilized to solve the proposed problem. The uncertainty related to the availability of capacity and the load level was taken into consideration in [11] using a generic and coherent approach. In addition, applications were illustrated and a new method for the determination of the probabilistic assessment of reliability indices and performance quality metrics was described. In [12], a comprehensive methodological framework was proposed, based on quantitative and Latin hypercube sampling methods, to study the prospective impact of vehicle-to-grid with utility-connected battery swapping station for enhancing the supply dependability in future distribution networks. The study in [13]

utilizes the fmincon optimization tool to inspect the impact of integrating renewable energy resources into microgrids in terms of measuring and evaluating the enhancement of the system's reliability. The obtained results indicated the improvement of measuring the system's reliability. Authors in [14] proposed an optimization model based on enhancing the reliability to solve the optimal scheduling problem of the integrated microgrids and evaluated some of the reliability indices of the system including CAIDI, SAIDI, and SAIFI. Microgrids as an intelligent technique are partially intended to support power systems' reliability [15-18].

Microgrids are typically designed to facilitate integrating Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) into power systems to support the local load demand and expand the predicted economic benefits [19-21]. DERs may involve non-dispatchable renewable units, Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs), and dispatchable Distributed Generators (DGs) [22-24]. Once the microgrids are developed, achieving optimal scheduling is a crucial factor in realizing the desired objectives. Several research studies have been extensively conducted in this field [25-31]. In [25], an optimization resiliency-oriented scheduling model was proposed to enhance the resiliency of the microgrid by reducing local load curtailment. Authors in [26], proposed an optimization model to solve the scheduling problem of several integrated microgrids using the Lagrangian relaxation method to preserve the microgrids' privacy. In [27], a discretized step transformation scheme based on chance-constrained programming was proposed considering the spinning reserve uncertainty to solve the scheduling problem for isolated microgrids. Authors in [28] proposed an optimal

scheduling strategy to regulate the microgrid operation and support its resiliency based on developed constraints that enable the islanding operation. Authors in [29] proposed a multi-objective optimization approach to determine the optimal scheduling of unbalanced microgrids considering energy saving, improvement of power quality, and cost minimization. In [30], an automated reinforcement learning-based optimization scheme was proposed considering multi-period forecasting associated with load and renewable generation to solve the optimal scheduling problem of isolated microgrids. Authors in [31] proposed a scheduling model considering radiation changes of photovoltaic systems and uncertainties associated with grid bid changes and load demand forecasting to solve the optimization problem. In addition, they utilized a modified bat algorithm to solve the proposed problem considering a variety of uncertainties. Nonetheless, the microgrids can be interconnected to each other to maximize the anticipated goals. The optimal interconnected operation of the microgrids can maximize the reliability and resiliency of local power systems, boost the economic advantages of individual microgrids, and foster the use of renewable energy resources.

The current paper proposes a generic optimization model to solve the optimal scheduling problem of interconnected microgrids considering enhancing the interconnected system's reliability. Based on the developed operational constraints, the proposed model minimizes each microgrid's Expected Energy Not Supplied (*EENS*), hence, maximizing the reliability of each microgrid involved in the system. In addition, it minimizes the entire interconnected system's total operation cost. Furthermore, it is featured with the capability to solve the scheduling optimization problem during the islanded operation. The proposed optimization problem is developed based on a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) and solved over a completed 24-hour scheduling horizon.

II. MODEL OUTLINE

The proposed reliability-constrained optimal scheduling model of interconnected microgrids aims to minimize each microgrid's "involved in the integrated system" total operation cost and minimize the microgrid's *EENS*. In addition, it considers the optimal scheduling of the interconnected microgrids during both grid-connected and islanded operations, i.e. during outages and disturbances.

The microgrids will exchange the power (export and import) with the utility grid during the grid-connected mode to maximize their economic benefits, while they exchange power locally, i.e. among the interconnected microgrids, during the islanded mode to boost and maximize their reliability and own economic benefits. To clarify this significant point, there will be no local power exchange among the interconnected microgrids during the grid-connected mode since it will be more economical for the seller microgrid to sell its excess generation to the utility rather than the other interconnected microgrids. On the other side, the microgrid that experiences a power deficiency would prefer to buy the power from the utility, as they have the option to buy their further needs of power at cheaper prices at the hourly market prices. Accordingly, there is no power exchange among the interconnected microgrids during the grid-connected mode,

while they will observably exchange power during the islanded operation for mutual benefits, i.e. to increase the seller microgrids' economic benefits and minimize the buyer microgrids' energy deficiency.

The proposed interconnected microgrid system is demonstrated in Figure 1. It is worth mentioning that the developed model would significantly improve the individual microgrid's reliability in addition to the overall reliability of the interconnected system as it pointedly encourages the microgrids to exploit all available DERs of the interconnected system as much as possible. In other words, the proposed model inspires the microgrids to exploit all installed DERs to supply the other microgrids that experience power deficiencies for mutual benefit.

Fig. 1. Interconnected microgrid system.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The objective function of the proposed reliability-constrained optimal scheduling problem of the interconnected microgrid system aims to minimize each microgrid's total operating costs and to minimize the probability of power deficiency occurrences within the microgrids, as follows:

$$\min \sum_t^T \sum_m^M \sum_s^K \left(\sum_t^G F_{mi} (P_{tmsi}) I_{tmi} + \rho_{tm} P_{tms}^M + \sum_{n, n \neq m}^M \lambda_{tmn} P_{tms}^C - \kappa PD_{tms} \right) \quad (1)$$

The developed objective function involves four main expressions. The first expression represents the generated power from the installed dispatchable DERs, which is further multiplied by a commitment binary indicator to specify the commitment state. The second expression represents exchanging the power with the utility grid. Nonetheless, this expression could mean either cost or revenue depending on the power flow direction. The third expression represents the power exchange between the interconnected microgrids. However, this expression will bring cost for buyer microgrids and revenue for seller microgrids. The last expression is added to add value to the percentage of the power deficiency within the microgrids. The minus sign is added as the percentage of the power deficiency will be displayed in the negative. Nonetheless, it is multiplied by an auxiliary cost value, which is supposed to be higher than the other costs to prioritize the reliability of the interconnected system. It should be indicated

that the proposed optimization model is developed to be compatible with both, islanded and grid-connected, modes using the islanded operating indicator s .

$$\sum_t P_{ims}^G + P_{ims}^R + \sum_t P_{ims}^S + P_{ims}^M \quad (2)$$

$$+ \sum_{n, n \neq m} P_{imms}^C = D_{ims} - EENS_{ims} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s$$

$$-P_{ims}^{M, \max} U_{is} \leq P_{ims}^M \leq P_{ims}^{M, \max} U_{is} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s \quad (3)$$

$$-P_{ims}^{C, \max} (1 - U_{is}) \leq P_{ims}^C \leq P_{ims}^{C, \max} (1 - U_{is}) \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s \quad (4)$$

The total generated and imported power must be balanced with the total power demand, which is satisfied by (2). However, it is worth mentioning that the $EENS$ is included in the power balance equation to achieve a feasible solution during outages or disturbances, i.e. during the islanded operation. The power exchange between the microgrids and the utility grid must be within the maximum line capacity limits, which is satisfied by (3). Nonetheless, the line capacity limits are multiplied by the islanding binary variable to regulate the microgrids' operating modes among the islanded and grid-connected operation. On the other side, the power exchange among the interconnected microgrids is also subjected to line capacity limits, which is satisfied by (4). However, it should be mentioned that this operational constraint is also multiplied by the islanding binary variable to force the power exchange between the interconnected microgrids to zero during the grid-connected operation.

$$P_{mi}^{\min} I_{imi} \leq P_{imsi} \leq P_{mi}^{\max} I_{imi} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s, \forall i \in G \quad (5)$$

$$P_{imsi} - P_{(t-1)msi} \leq UR_i \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s, \forall i \in G \quad (6)$$

$$P_{(t-1)msi} - P_{imsi} \leq DR_{mi} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s, \forall i \in G \quad (7)$$

$$T_{mi}^{\text{on}} \geq UT_{mi} (I_{imi} - I_{(t-1)mi}) \quad \forall t, \forall m, s=0, \forall i \in G \quad (8)$$

$$T_{mi}^{\text{off}} \geq DT_{mi} (I_{(t-1)mi} - I_{imi}) \quad \forall t, \forall m, s=0, \forall i \in G \quad (9)$$

The installed dispatchable units are subject to respective operational constraints to regulate their operation. Each dispatchable unit can generate power only between the maximum and minimum capacity limits, which are satisfied by (5). In addition, they are multiplied by a commitment binary variable I to state whether the dispatchable unit is committed or not during the specified optimal scheduling hour. Moreover, each dispatchable unit is restricted by the ramping up and down rate limits, as in (6) and (7), respectively. Furthermore, once the dispatchable unit is switched ON or OFF, it is restricted by the minimum up and down time limits, of (8) and (9), respectively.

$$D_{md}^{\min} z_{imsd} \leq D_{imsd} \leq D_{md}^{\max} z_{imsd} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s, \forall d \in D_A \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{[\alpha_d, \beta_d]} D_{imsd} = E_{md} \quad \forall m, \forall s, \forall d \in D_A \quad (11)$$

$$T_{md}^{\text{on}} \geq MU_{md} (z_{imsd} - z_{(t-1)msd}) \quad \forall t, \forall m, s=0, \forall d \in D_A \quad (12)$$

The adjustable loads are regulated by constraints (10)-(12). Each adjustable load in the microgrids is restricted by the

minimum and maximum rated power, as in (10). However, some of the adjustable loads that are switched ON might be subject to a minimum required energy to accomplish the operating cycle, which is regulated by (11). On the other hand, some adjustable loads must operate continuously for a certain amount of time after being turned ON, which is satisfied by (12).

$$P_{imsi} \leq P_{imi}^{ch, \max} u_{imi} - P_{imi}^{ch, \min} v_{imi} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s, \forall i \in S \quad (13)$$

$$P_{imsi} \geq P_{imi}^{ch, \min} u_{imi} - P_{imi}^{ch, \max} v_{imi} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s, \forall i \in S \quad (14)$$

$$C_{msi} = C_{(t-1)msi} - P_{imsi} u_{imsi} \tau / \eta_i - P_{imsi} v_{imsi} \tau \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s, \forall i \in S \quad (15)$$

$$C_{mi}^{\min} \leq C_{msi} \leq C_{mi}^{\max} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s, \forall i \in S \quad (16)$$

$$T_{mi}^{ch} \geq MC_{mi} (u_{imsi} - u_{(t-1)msi}) \quad \forall t, \forall m, s=0, \forall i \in S \quad (17)$$

$$T_{mi}^{dch} \leq MD_{mi} (v_{imsi} - v_{(t-1)msi}) \quad \forall t, \forall m, s=0, \forall i \in S \quad (18)$$

$$u_{imsi} + v_{imsi} \leq 1 \quad \forall t, \forall m, s=0, \forall i \in S \quad (19)$$

The connected BESSs are subject to several operational constraints to acquire their optimal scheduling. Maximum and minimum charging and discharging restrictions apply to BESSs, as in (13) and (14). In accordance with the charging and discharging operations over the defined scheduling horizon, and taking into account the BESS efficiency, the stored energy in the BESS is calculated by (15). The minimum and maximum capacity restrictions impose additional limits on the BESSs, as in (16). Each BESS is restricted by time limits once it starts charging or discharging, as in (17) and (18), respectively. Furthermore, the binary variables u and v are added to the BESS operational constraints (19) to regulate their operation mode to either charge or discharge during the specified optimal scheduling time.

$$\psi_{ims} = \frac{D_{ims} - EENS_{ims}}{D_{ims}} \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s \quad (20)$$

$$PD_{ims} = (\psi_{ims} - 1) \times 100\% \quad \forall t, \forall m, \forall s \quad (21)$$

The microgrids' power deficiency is a significant factor in indicating the interconnected microgrids' reliability; thus, it is restricted by the developed constraints (20) and (21). The probability of $EENS$ is calculated by (20). The percentage of the microgrids' power deficiency is regulated and measured by (21).

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Three independent microgrids were utilized to study and investigate the proposed reliability-constrained optimal scheduling model of the interconnected microgrids, which are named MG A, MG B, and MG C. The microgrids' local installed dispatchable generators are specified in Table I. The microgrids' BESS characteristics are demonstrated in Table II. The efficiency of all BESS is supposed to be 90% [26]. Each of the microgrids is accompanied with its own renewable, i.e. nondispatchable, generators, and their forecasted power generation is shown in Figures 2 and 3, for solar PVs and wind

turbines power, respectively. Table III shows the characteristics of the adjustable loads that are installed in the microgrids.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF INSTALLED DISPATCHABLE GENERATORS

DG	MG A	MG B	MG C
	Price (\$/MWh)		
G 1	28.1	30.9	38.7
G 2	38.9	45.7	46.9
G 3	62.2	73.5	75.4
G 4	66.3	78.4	-
-	Minimum up and down time (h)		
G 1	3	4	5
G 2	3	4	4
G 3	1	2	2
G 4	1	3	-
-	Minimum and maximum capacity (MW)		
G 1	1-5	1-2	0.5-2
G 2	1-5	0.5-2	0.8-2.5
G 3	0.8-3	0.5-1	0.5-3.5
G 4	0.8-3	1-3	-
-	Ramp up and down rate (MW/h)		
G 1	2.5	1	1.5
G 2	2.5	2	1.5
G 3	3	1	2.5
G 4	3	1.5	-

TABLE II. MICROGRIDS' BESS CHARACTERISTICS

Microgrid	BESS characteristics		
	Charging and discharging minimum and maximum power (MW)	Charging and discharging minimum operating time (h)	Capacity (MWh)
MG A BESS	0.4-2	5	10
MG B BESS	0.2-1	4	5
MG C BESS	0.8-2	4	6

Fig. 2. Solar PVs power in MG A, MG B, and MG C.

The microgrids' hourly fixed load data are shown in Figure 4. All the microgrids are electrically connected to the utility grid as an infinite bus. The market price of the power exchange between the utility grid and the microgrids is demonstrated in Figure 5. Figure 5 also shows the price of the local power exchange among the interconnected microgrids, which is set to be 10% higher than the market hourly prices arbitrary to create incentive to local power exchanges. In addition, a marginal value of the power deficiency, i.e. κ , of \$10/kWh is assumed [32]. The lines between each microgrid and the utility grid and the lines among the interconnected microgrids are subject to line capacity limits, which are restricted to 10MW and 2MW, respectively. A 24-hour scheduling horizon is considered to solve the proposed problem. In addition, 25-islanded-scenarios

are considered to solve the optimization problem, where one scenario indicates the grid-connected operation and the rest indicate islanded operation in each specific hour. The optimization problem is programmed and solved using CPLEX 11.0 in GAMS [33]. Five case studies were carried out to demonstrate the features and effectiveness of the proposed model. The summary of the microgrids' total operation costs is shown in Table IX for all cases.

Fig. 3. Wind turbines power in MG A, MG B, and MG C.

Fig. 4. Hourly fixed load in MG A, MG B, and MG C.

Fig. 5. Hourly forecasted market prices and local power exchange prices.

A. Case 0-Base Case: Individual Microgrid Optimal Scheduling

In this case, each microgrid in the system is optimized individually, i.e. there is no interconnection among the microgrids, to ensure the lowest potential operational cost and maximum reliability. The total operational costs of MG A, MG B, and MG C, considering the islanded operation scenarios, are computed as \$14,699.19, \$9,387.56, and \$10,001.18, respectively.

TABLE III. ADJUSTABLE LOAD

Microgrid	Adjustable load characteristics				
	Load type	Required energy (MWh)	Minimum and maximum capacity (MW)	Start and end time (h)	Minimum up time (h)
MG A	Shiftable 1	1.6	0 – 0.4	11 – 15	1
	Shiftable 2	1.6	0 – 0.4	15 – 19	1
	Shiftable 3	2.4	0.02 – 0.8	16 – 18	1
	Shiftable 4	2.4	0.02 – 0.8	14 – 22	1
	Curtailable 5	47	1.8 – 2	1 – 24	24
MG B	Shiftable 1	1.6	0 – 0.4	12 – 16	1
	Shiftable 2	2.4	0.02 – 0.8	15 – 23	1
	Curtailable 3	47	1.8 – 2	1 – 24	24
MG C	Shiftable 1	2	0 – 0.5	9 – 13	1
	Shiftable 2	2.4	0.2 – 0.8	11 – 17	1
	Curtailable 3	36	0.8 – 1.6	1 – 24	24

Fig. 6. Microgrids’ power deficiency in Case 0.

In this case, each of the microgrids in the system experiences some power deficiency during the optimal islanded operation, which is illustrated in Figure 6. The percentage of the power deficiency in the microgrids is calculated as 1.61%, 2.33%, and 7.67% for MG A, MG B, and MG C, respectively (see Table VIII). The hourly optimal scheduling of the installed BESSs in the microgrids is demonstrated in Figure 7. This case study demonstrates that although optimal solutions for microgrids are identified, the lack of complementary power supplies may result in failure to reach maximum reliability.

B. Case 1: Optimal Scheduling when the Interconnection is only between MG A and MG B

In this case, the impact of integrating MG A and MG B on the optimization outcomes is investigated. MG A’s total operation cost is slightly reduced by 0.34% to \$14,648.59,

while the total operation cost of MG B is slightly increased by 0.43% as it is computed to \$9,428.60. It should be mentioned that the optimization outcomes of MG C are not impacted in this case study as its optimal scheduling results remained exactly the same as in the base case.

Fig. 7. Optimal scheduling of the BESS in Case 0.

TABLE IV. LOCAL POWER EXCHANGE BETWEEN MG A AND MG B IN CASE 1

Scenario no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$P^{C(A-B)}$ (MW)	-0.26	-0.47	-0.36	-0.28	0.56	0	0.57	0.69
Scenario no.	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
$P^{C(A-B)}$ (MW)	0.70	0.78	0.54	0.46	0.46	0	-0.32	-0.47
Scenario no.	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
$P^{C(A-B)}$ (MW)	-0.45	-0.12	-0.80	0	0	0	0	0

Fig. 8. Power deficiency differences in Case 1 for MG A and MG B.

The hourly power deficiency is reduced by 81.98% and 56.65% for MG A and MG B, respectively, as shown in Figure 8. In this case, MG A and MG B experience power deficiency of 0.29% and 1.01%, respectively. The percentage of power deficiency is summarized in Table VIII for all cases. Obviously, enabling the integration among these two microgrids would result in permitting local power exchange among them. The results of the optimal hourly power exchange among the interconnected microgrids are shown in Table IV. It should be noted that the minus sign signifies that the power is transferred from MG A to MG B, and vice versa. Observably, allowing the integration among certain microgrids

demonstrates slight improvements in terms of interconnected microgrids' economic benefits and improves their reliability as it authorizes further paths to optimize the microgrid scheduling.

C. Case 2: Optimal Scheduling when the Interconnection is only between MG A and MG C

In this case study, the interconnection among the interconnected microgrids is only enabled between MG A and MG C. The microgrids' total operation cost is computed as \$14,201.05 and \$10,569.53 for MG A and MG C, respectively, while the total operating cost of MG B remained unchanged as in case 0. Even though the total operation cost of MG C is increased by 5.68%, the power deficiency of MG C is obviously reduced by 87.39%. The percentage of the power deficiency is computed as 0.22% and 0.97% for MG A and MG C, respectively, while it remained unchanged for MG B, as shown in Table VIII.

TABLE V. LOCAL POWER EXCHANGE BETWEEN MG A AND MG C IN CASE 2

Scenario no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$P^{C(A-C)}$ (MW)	-2	-2	-2	-1.52	0.56	0	0.57	0.69
Scenario no.	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
$P^{C(A-C)}$ (MW)	0.70	0.60	0.54	0.42	0.68	0.29	0	0
Scenario no.	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
$P^{C(A-C)}$ (MW)	0	0	-1.06	-0.25	-1.66	-2	-1.94	-1.89

Fig. 9. Power deficiency differences in Case 2 for MG A and MG C.

The hourly power exchange between MG A and MG C is illustrated in Table V. The minus sign indicates that the power is transferred from MG A to MG C, and vice versa. The improvements in the microgrids' power deficiency are graphically illustrated in Figure 9, which also shows the hourly load curtailment in MG A and MG C.

D. Case 3: Optimal Scheduling when the Interconnection is only between MG B and MG C

In this case, the interconnection among MG B and MG C is activated, hence, the power can be locally exchanged among these interconnected microgrids. The optimization results of the

hourly local power exchange are illustrated in Table VI, where the minus sign indicates that the power is exported from MG B to MG C and vice versa. The total operating costs of these two interconnected microgrids are slightly changed, as it is indicated in Table IX. MG B's total operating cost is reduced by 0.61% (computed as \$9,329.68), while MG C's total operating cost is slightly increased by 1.19% (computed as \$10,120.02). However, the power deficiency of these two microgrids is noticeably decreased, by 65.23% and 58.15% for MG B and MG C, respectively. The changes in the power deficiency are graphically demonstrated in Figure 10. The reduction percentage of total power deficiency is calculated as 0.81% and 3.21% for MG B and MG C, respectively, as it is shown in Table VIII. On the other side, the optimization results of MG A have not been changed compared with the base case, as it is excluded in this case study from the interconnection.

TABLE VI. LOCAL POWER EXCHANGE BETWEEN MG B AND MG C IN CASE 3

Scenario no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$P^{C(B-C)}$ (MW)	-0.74	-0.73	-0.84	-0.92	-0.90	-1.19	-0.84	-0.28
Scenario no.	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
$P^{C(B-C)}$ (MW)	-1.19	0	0	0	0	0	0.66	0.38
Scenario no.	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
$P^{C(B-C)}$ (MW)	0.18	0.51	0.82	-0.21	-1.58	-1.22	-0.59	-0.73

Fig. 10. Power deficiency differences in Case 3 for MG B and MG C.

E. Case 4: Optimal Interconnected Microgrids Scheduling

In this case, all microgrids are electrically interconnected in the studied system. This case study inspects and explores the potential impacts of interconnecting the microgrids on their total operating costs and reliability. The optimal local power exchange scheduling among the interconnected microgrids, over the scheduling horizon, is demonstrated in Table VII. The optimization results of the optimal scheduling of the BESS are slightly changed in this case study, which is demonstrated in Figure 11. These slight changes are caused by the local power exchange among the microgrids. The total operating costs of the interconnected microgrids are computed as \$14,379.87, \$9,328.19, and \$10,308.36 for MG A, MG B, and MG C,

respectively. Even though the total operating costs are slightly increased in some of the microgrids (by 3.07% in MG C), the encountered power deficiency in all the microgrids is dramatically minimized to zero, which emphasizes a significant improvement in the interconnected system reliability.

TABLE VII. LOCAL POWER EXCHANGE BETWEEN ALL THE MICROGRIDS IN CASE 4

Scenario no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
$P^{C(A-B)}$ (MW)	-1.18	-1.42	-0.38	0	0.56	0	0.57	0.37
$P^{C(A-C)}$ (MW)	-2	-2	-2	-1.13	0	0	0	0.32
$P^{C(B-C)}$ (MW)	-0.72	-0.95	-0.02	-0.72	-0.90	-1.19	-0.84	0
Scenario no.	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
$P^{C(A-B)}$ (MW)	0.70	0	0	0.17	0.46	0	-0.22	-0.47
$P^{C(A-C)}$ (MW)	0	0.78	0.54	0.42	0.68	0.27	0	0
$P^{C(B-C)}$ (MW)	-0.39	0	0	0	0	0.48	0.44	0.38
Scenario no.	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
$P^{C(A-B)}$ (MW)	-0.45	-0.01	-0.80	0	0	0	0	0
$P^{C(A-C)}$ (MW)	0	0	-0.26	-0.04	-0.10	-0.91	-1.85	-1.66
$P^{C(B-C)}$ (MW)	0.10	0.48	0	-0.21	-1.56	-1.20	-0.90	-0.23

TABLE VIII. PERCENTAGE OF MICROGRIDS' POWER DEFICIENCY IN ALL CASE STUDIES

Case no.	MG A	MG B	MG C
Case 0	1.61%	2.33%	7.67%
Case 1	0.29%	1.01%	7.67%
Case 2	0.22%	2.33%	0.97%
Case 3	1.61%	0.81%	3.21%
Case 4	0%	0%	0%

TABLE IX. SUMMARY OF MICROGRIDS' TOTAL OPERATION COST

Case no.	MG A	MG B	MG C
Case 0	\$14,699.19	\$9,387.56	\$10,001.18
Case 1	\$14,648.59	\$9,428.60	\$10,001.18
Case 2	\$14,201.05	\$9,387.56	\$10,569.53
Case 3	\$14,699.19	\$9,329.68	\$10,120.02
Case 4	\$14,379.87	\$9,328.19	\$10,308.36

Fig. 11. Optimal scheduling of the BESS in Case 4.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper highlighted the potential benefits and features of enabling the interconnection among adjacent microgrids and proposed a reliability-constrained optimal scheduling model for interconnected microgrids. The proposed model was capable of economically minimizing the interconnected microgrids' total operating costs and was capable of efficiently maximizing the interconnected system's reliability. The key features of the proposed optimization model can be summarized as follows: (i) it ensures the minimization of the microgrids' total operating costs and supports the optimization of the battery energy storage systems scheduling, (ii) it is capable of efficiently

maximizing the interconnected system reliability by minimizing the expected energy not supplied in the microgrids, (iii) it takes the potentiality of islanded operation scenarios into account (i.e. in the event of disturbances and outages), and (iv) it is developed based on mixed-integer linear programming to facilitate reaching fast and efficient optimal solutions.

The proposed model exploited all the distributed energy resources installed in the microgrids, including the battery energy storage systems, to support the reliability and economic benefits of the microgrids by enabling local power exchange among the interconnected system. The proposed optimization scheme was investigated in several case studies, including the optimal individual scheduling of the microgrids as a base case, to explore and validate its performance and feasibility. The obtained optimization results indicated its superior performance in minimizing the microgrids' total operating costs and the expected energy not supplied in the microgrids. Nevertheless, the proposed optimization model is generic, and various test systems could be applied to investigate its feasibility and performance without loss of generality.

NOMENCLATURE

Indices:

- ch Superscript for BESS charging operation mode.
- d Index for loads.
- dch Superscript for BESS discharging operation mode.
- i Index for DERs.
- s Index for scenarios.
- m,n Index for microgrids.
- t Index for time.

Sets:

- D_A Set of adjustable loads.
- G Set of dispatchable generators.
- M Set of microgrids.
- K Set of islanded scenarios.
- S Set of BESSs.
- T Set of time periods.

Parameters:

- DR Ramping down rate.
- D Aggregated load demand.
- DT Minimum down time.
- D^{max} Adjustable load maximum rated power.
- D^{min} Adjustable load minimum rated power.
- E Total required energy of adjustable load.
- $F(.)$ Generation cost of DERs.
- MC Minimum charging time of BESS.
- MD Minimum discharging time of BESS.
- MU Minimum operation time of adjustable load.
- P^R Aggregated forecasted renewable generation.
- UR Ramping up rate.
- UT Minimum up time.
- ρ Forecasted hourly market prices.
- κ Value of power deficiency.
- λ Local power exchange prices.
- α,β Adjustable loads' defined start and end times.
- η BESS efficiency.

Variables:

- C Total stored energy in BESS.
- $EENS$ Expected energy not supplied.
- I Binary variable for commitment status of dispatchable units.
- P DERs generated power.
- P^C Local power exchange.
- PD Power deficiency.
- P^M Power exchange with the utility.
- T^{ch} BESS's number of successive charging hours.

T^{dch}	BESS's number of successive discharging hours.
T^{on}	Total number of successive ON hours.
T^{off}	Total number of successive OFF hours.
U	Binary variable for islanding operation status.
τ	Time period.
u	Discharging state of BESS.
v	Charging state of BESS.
ψ	Probability of expected energy not supplied.
z	Adjustable load status.

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Workability and Flexural Strength of Recycled Aggregate Concrete with Steel Fibers

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ABSTRACT

This study examined how concrete workability and flexural strength are affected by steel fibers and recycled aggregates. Steel fibers were used in doses between 1-5%, with an increment of 0.5%, and 50% of the natural coarse aggregates were replaced by recycled. Two mixes of conventional and recycled aggregate concrete without steel fibers were used as control mixes. Concrete mixes were prepared using 1:2:4 and 0.45 water-to-cement ratios. Workability was determined using the slump cone. Three prism specimens sized 500×100×100mm were prepared for each batch and cured for 28 days in potable water. After curing, the specimens were air-dried in the laboratory and tested to evaluate their flexural strength under two-point loading. The load and deflection were monitored at regular intervals until failure. A comparison of results with control mixes showed that as the percentage of steel fiber increased, flexural strength increased by 69% and deflection decreased by 66%. The use of steel fibers improved the flexural strength of the recycled aggregate concrete by 59%.

Keywords-demolished waste; recycled aggregates; green concrete; steel fibers; flexural strength; sustainable development; waste management

I. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry has undergone drastic changes over time and has faced great challenges, particularly for high-rise infrastructures from a strength, safety, and durability points of view. The present global boom of construction is due to the

modern development and the increasing accommodation needs in city centers. This increased demand forced the construction industry to opt for vertical instead of horizontal expansion. This requires the demolition of old deteriorated short buildings to construct tall ones. This procedure not only demands excessive

use of natural aggregates but also generates a huge quantum of demolition waste. Approximately 450 million tons of demolition waste are generated per year in the European Union [15], of which 50-55% is concrete. Some of this waste is used under floors and in plinth protections but generally goes to landfills for dumping. On the other hand, the shortage of space, particularly in city centers, increases the serious problem of dumping. On-site use of demolition waste still leaves a large amount of waste. Another possible use of it is in new concrete, and several studies investigated its use as a substitute for fine and coarse aggregates. Concrete waste is large in volume compared to the other demolition waste ingredients. As the major space-taking component of concrete is coarse aggregates, the use of concrete waste as coarse aggregates would consume more waste, facilitating waste management and reducing the use of Natural Coarse Aggregates (NCA). Furthermore, the use of demolition waste as coarse aggregate provides an alternative indigenous material as a component for concrete.

Various studies attempted to investigate this problem. One way to increase the strength characteristics of concrete is by using various types of fibers. The use of fibers also aids in the disposal of that material's waste. Fibers in concrete have many advantages. The studies in [1-2] made field investigations to highlight the issue, its impact, and its remedies, pointing out that proper implementation of rules and regulations by governments will help to streamline its use. In [3-5], the tensile strength of concrete with Recycled Coarse Aggregates (RCA) was investigated, showing that it was similar to conventional concrete regardless of its source, quality, or quantity. In [6], waste from laboratory-tested cylinders was used in the preparation of new concrete beams to check their flexural strength, reporting a minimum difference in peak load from their counterparts, regardless of the dosage of RCA. In [7], it was reported that demolition waste can be used as coarse aggregates with minimum loss of flexural capacity if proper design and application limits are considered. In [8], demolition waste was used as coarse aggregates in dosages of 30%, 50%, and 100% to check the flexural capacity of the produced concrete, observing similar crack patterns but a lower flexural strength when varying the tensile reinforcement ratio to 0.5%, 0.79%, and 1.14%. In addition, this study noticed that the ductility of the beams was not influenced by the dosage of the RCA. Adding recycled materials to concrete reduces its flexural strength [9]. In [10], flexural strength was reduced by 8.8% and 5.5% for 7- and 28-day cured normal mix RC beams, respectively, and an 11.68% loss of strength was reported for 28-day cured rich mix concrete beams [11]. Fire not only affects the appearance of reinforced concrete beams but also deteriorates their resisting capacity. In [12-14], a 1000°C fire on reinforced RCA beams reduced bearing capacity by 8%, 22%, and 32.41% for fire exposures of 6, 18, and 24 hours, respectively.

In [16], RCA concrete samples were prepared and cured for 1, 2, 7, 28, and 56 days with a compressive strength target between 20-50MPa, and the test results revealed a residual concrete strength of 90% with only a 3% reduction in the modulus of elasticity. In [17-18], fly ash was used in RCA concrete to improve strength, showing that a dosage of 25-35% fly ash allows a larger proportion of NCA to be replaced with

RCA made from demolition waste. The studies in [19-22] investigated the mechanical and durability properties of RCA concrete with fly ash and customizable water-binder ratios, demonstrating that the use of large amounts of fly ash in recycled aggregate concrete enhanced its properties in terms of compressive strength, tensile strength, and resistance to chloride action. In [23-24], it was shown that RCA concrete containing biomass bottom ash behaved worse, concluding that it should only be used in non-structural concrete. In [25], the strength characteristics of RCA concrete were positively affected by the quality of the parent concrete, as when the strength of parent concrete was 80-100MPa, RCA concrete exhibited properties almost similar to the NCA.

Several studies have investigated the use of fibers to improve concrete properties. The use of steel fibers from waste steel has been also examined in both concrete types. In [26], the effect of the aspect ratio of steel fibers on the flexural strength of RCA concrete was studied, using steel fibers between 0.5-2.5% and four aspect ratios. The results indicated that the optimum dosage of steel fibers was 1.5% and that an increased aspect ratio resulted in an increase in strength. In [27], the collective effect of fly ash and steel fibers on the tensile and flexural strength of concrete was investigated, using different doses of fly ash and steel fibers. The results showed that using 2% steel fibers and 30% fly ash increased flexural strength to a maximum of 8%. In [28], the effect of steel fibers was studied in reinforced RCA concrete exposed to temperatures of 200, 400, and 600°C, showing that the presence of steel fibers reduced the strength of the concrete but helped in preventing its spalling. In [29], 1-5% steel fibers were used in concrete, showing that the optimal dose was 3% as it provided an 18% and 52% increase in compressive and flexural strength, respectively. In [30], the use of 2.5% steel fibers provided a 61% increase in flexural strength. In [31], it was concluded that using 1% steel fibers in concrete containing 100% RCA increased its strength up to 37%. In [32-34], the effect of normal and equivalent mortar volume methods on RCA concrete containing steel fibers was studied, showing up to 50% and 35% increase in flexural strength for beams failing in shear and flexure, respectively. In [35] the use of polypropylene and steel fibers in RCA was reviewed, concluding that mineral fibers have a better synergistic effect and produce concrete with better properties. In [36], the use of steel fibers in RCA concrete improved the strength characteristics of both reinforced and unreinforced concrete beams. Not only steel fibers, but also GGBF slag and fly ash [37], biomedical waste [38], curing methods [39], and curing types [40] have been investigated to check their effect on the strength properties of RCA concrete. Steel fibers and RCA were also studied in [41]. Although several studies investigated the use of steel fibers in RCA concrete, there is a scattering in the optimum dosage, aspect ratio, and type of steel. A similar scatter appears in the results of studies on the flexural strength of fibrous RCA concrete. This study attempted to laboratory investigate the flexural- strength of fibrous RCA concrete under two-point loading.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Concrete Ingredients

This study used ordinary Portland cement under the brand name Pak Land. The fineness of the cement was checked with a #100 sieve and was found to be 94%. The initial and final setting times of cement were 68 and 231 minutes, respectively. The values obtained for cement followed ASTM C150/C150M-18 [42]. Hill sand obtained from approved sources was used as fine aggregate. Figure 1 shows the sieve analysis results of the fine aggregates, while its fineness modulus was 2.375. The percentage passing through various sieves and the fineness modulus of the fine aggregates were within the allowable ranges of ASTM C136/C136M-14 [43].

Fig. 1. Sieve analysis of fine aggregates.

Fig. 2. Sieve analysis of NCA and RCA.

Coarse aggregates were also obtained from approved sources and their maximum size was 25mm. The aggregates were sorted for unwanted substances, washed, and dried, and sieve analysis was performed. Figure 2 shows the results of the sieve analysis, which were within the allowable ranges of ASTM C136/C136M-14 [43]. The fineness modulus of the aggregates was 3.18. Demolished waste was collected from a demolished ground-story reinforced concrete building. Mixed debris, as shown in Figure 3, was brought to the laboratory and hammered to a maximum of 25mm, equal to the maximum size of NCA, as shown in Figure 4. The obtained aggregates were sorted, washed, and dried, and a sieve analysis was performed, as shown in Figure 2. The fineness modulus of the recycled aggregates was recorded at 3.18. Like conventional aggregates, the parameters of the recycled aggregates were within the allowable ranges of ASTM C136/C136M-14 [43]. This study used water, obtained from a water supply, with 7.1 pH.

Fig. 3. Demolished waste.

Fig. 4. NCA and RCA.

Figure 5 shows the steel fibers used, which were cut from steel wire of 1mm diameter. The length of each fiber was 25mm. The tensile strength of the fibers was 1140N/mm².

Fig. 5. Steel fibers.

The concrete was prepared in a 1:2:4 ratio. The water-to-cement ratio was 0.5. The steel fiber content used in the concrete was 1-5%, with an increment of 0.5%, resulting in 10 batches (B1 to B10). Additionally, two control mixes were prepared without steel fibers, one with NCA (CC) and another with RCA. Table I provides the details of the mixes.

B. Water Absorption and Specific Gravity

The water absorption and specific gravity of the aggregates were evaluated following the procedures specified in ASTM C-127 [44], and Table II shows the results.

TABLE I. DETAILS OF CONCRETE MIXES

B#	NCA (%)	RCA (%)	Steel fibers (%)	Cement (kg)	FA (kg)	NCA (kg)	RCA (kg)	Steel fibers (kg)
CC	100	0	0.0	10	20	20	0	0
RCA	50	50	0.0	10	20	10	10	0
B1	50	50	0.5	10	20	10	10	0.3
B2	50	50	1.0	10	20	10	10	0.6
B3	50	50	1.5	10	20	10	10	0.9
B4	50	50	2.0	10	20	10	10	1.2
B5	50	50	2.5	10	20	10	10	1.5
B6	50	50	3.0	10	20	10	10	1.8
B7	50	50	3.5	10	20	10	10	2.1
B8	50	50	4.0	10	20	10	10	2.4
B9	50	50	4.5	10	20	10	10	2.7
B10	50	50	5.0	10	20	10	10	3

TABLE II. WATER ABSORPTION AND SPECIFIC GRAVITY

Aggregate type	Specific gravity	Water absorption (%)
Natural Coarse Aggregates	2.57	1.64
Recycled Coarse Aggregates	2.31	3.42

C. Workability

The workability of the designed mixes was evaluated using the slump cone test following ASTM C143 [44]. Cone filling, rodding, lifting, and measurement of the slump were carried out in a standard fashion, as shown in Figure 6. Table III shows the slump values recorded for all mixes.

Fig. 6. Slump cone test.

TABLE III. SLUMP CONE TEST

Batch no.	Steel fibers (%)	Slump (mm)	Batch no.	Steel fibers (%)	Slump (mm)
1	0.00	70.0	7	2.50	60.0
2	0.00	62.0	8	3.00	59.5
3	0.50	61.5	9	3.50	57.0
4	1.00	61.0	10	4.00	55.0
5	1.50	62.0	11	4.50	54.5
6	2.00	61.0	12	5.00	54.0

D. Sample Preparation and Curing

Three prism specimens with dimensions of 500×100×100mm were prepared in all 12 batches to check the flexural strength of the concrete. In total, 36 prism specimens were prepared. The concrete ingredients in the required proportion were batched by weight, followed by thorough mixing. Water was then added, and the mixer was run until a uniform paste was formed. The inner side of the molds was oiled, and each mold was filled in 3 layers and compacted with

a needle vibrator. The specimens were demolded after 24 hours and left at room temperature to dry for a day. Then all the specimens were cured for 28 days in potable water. Figure 7 shows a few specimens.

Fig. 7. Specimens and curing.

E. Specimen Testing

After curing, the specimens were taken out of the water and left to dry for 24 hours. All specimens were tested on a universal testing machine under a two-point load, at one-third of either support, following ASTM C150. During testing, load and deflection were monitored at regular intervals. The failure of the specimens was checked at the maximum sustained load. Figure 8 shows a few specimens during the test, and Table IV shows the average results of five samples in each mix for both flexural strength and deflection.

Fig. 8. Specimen testing.

TABLE IV. AVERAGE FLEXURAL STRENGTH

Batch no	Steel fiber %	Load (KN)	Mean flexural strength (N/mm ²)	Mean deflection (mm)
1	0.00	8.57	6.43	3.40
2	0.00	7.50	5.62	5.34
3	0.50	8.74	6.56	4.40
4	1.00	9.23	6.92	4.18
5	1.50	10.02	7.52	3.82
6	2.00	10.17	7.63	3.64
7	2.50	10.40	7.80	3.18
8	3.00	10.69	8.02	2.34
9	3.50	10.84	8.13	2.12
10	4.00	11.07	8.30	1.88
11	4.50	11.32	8.49	1.56
12	5.00	11.94	8.95	1.14

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Both aggregate types satisfied the standard requirements of well-graded aggregates, as shown in the sieve analysis results. RCA absorbed water at a rate of 3.42%, while NCA absorbed 1.64%. A comparison of the specific gravity findings of the two aggregates showed that RCA had 10% lower specific gravity than NCA. This can be attributed to the age of the old concrete and the old mortar connected within the RCA. Both variables contribute to the higher water absorption of RCA.

The slump of the traditional concrete was within the acceptable range for the specific mix. However, the slump of the other mixes remained lower than that of conventional concrete. Figure 9 compares the traditional and the fiber concrete, whereas Figure 10 shows the percentile decrease in the slump of the RCA mixes. Adding more steel fibers to the mixture caused a drop in the slump value. The maximum drop in the slump (22.9%) was noticed when using 5% of fibers. This demonstrates that the water requirement of the blend is higher when using steel fiber, and it should be taken into account when choosing the w/c ratio for the mix, or else more admixture or mechanical effort will be needed to keep the necessary workability.

reduced the flexural strength (-12.5%), but the problem was counteracted with the addition of steel fibers. In all mixes, an increase in flexural strength was observed with the increase in steel fiber content. It is also anticipated that a further increase in steel fiber content will further increase flexural strength and reduce workability, and this should be carefully considered when deciding the dosage of steel fibers. The increase in flexural strength is attributed to the strength of the steel fibers plus their function to provide good interlocking between the ingredients of the concrete matrix, leading to a higher load-carrying capacity of the hardened concrete. Therefore, it can be used in new concrete, along with 50% RCA from demolition debris. This will not only lessen the waste management burden but also help in conserving conventional aggregates and protecting the environment. This study used steel fibers made from the new steel wire, but fibers can also be produced from waste steel, further reducing waste issues. Figure 12 shows the percentile deviation of the flexural strength of concrete mixes with steel fibers with the control mix. It can be seen that at the highest dose of steel fibers, the increase in flexural strength was 39% compared to the control mix while the same against the recycled aggregate concrete was 59%.

Fig. 9. Comparison of slump values.

Fig. 10. Change in slump vs control concrete

Fig. 11. Mean flexural strength.

Fig. 12. Deviation of flexural strength.

Figure 11 compares the flexural strength results of the concrete mixes with the control mix. It can be seen that RCA

Figure 13 compares the average deflection for all specimens with the control mix. The pattern of deflection is

reversed to flexural strength when increasing steel fiber content. This happens because the addition of steel fibers improves strength and thus reduces deflection. It is also anticipated that further addition of fibers will further decrease deflection, showing that steel fiber content can be used to control strength and deflection. However, it might contribute to the brittleness of the concrete and may result in sudden failure of the member. Therefore, this aspect should be studied and considered before deciding on the required displacement control using steel fibers. It may further be observed that RCA increased deflection by 57%, but when using 3% steel fibers, it was controlled and reduced by 66.5%.

Fig. 13. Mean deflection test.

It was also observed that the specimens failed in flexure which confirms the theoretical failure mode of plain concrete. The analysis of the specimens showed that at failure they did not split into two pieces but the fibers provided an interlocking medium. The same event may have helped improve strength, reduce cracks, and provide the interlocking mechanism to reduce the crack width.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study examined the workability and flexural strength of binary blended concrete with RCA and steel fibers. Based on the observations of laboratory investigations, the following can be concluded:

- RCA had a lower specific gravity and greater water absorption than NCA. This greater water absorption increased the water requirement of the concrete mix, necessitating an adjustment to the design.
- The mechanical properties of the resulting concrete were significantly affected by RCA. Compared to the control mix, the use of 50% RCA resulted in decreased workability and flexural strength and increased deflection. This is because of old, dry, and porous aggregates that are weaker in strength and need more water.
- Using a higher proportion of steel fibers and a consistent dosage of 50% RCA, flexural strength and deflection increased significantly. The maximum strength increase was recorded at the highest dosage of steel fibers. It is also anticipated that a further increase in fiber content will

further increase flexural strength, but the brittleness and durability of concrete may be a problem and need to be carefully considered before deciding the optimal dosage.

- In failure, the beams were not split into parts due to the interlocking mechanism of the steel fibers, as they provide a medium to bridge cracks and improve strength.
- The combined mix of steel fiber and RCA can be used to improve concrete strength.

Therefore, this study recommends the use of 50% RCA from demolished waste with steel fibers for producing concrete with good flexural strength and controlled deflection.

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